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PDSTRIP Fin and Sails Treatment – Physics and Expert Knowledge

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Abstract

This paper presents the underlying theory for fins and sails in the public-domain strip method PDSTRIP. Fortran90 source code is given with direct reference to the outlined theory. Expert knowledge is compiled to aid estimation of user-specified input. Knowledge incorporated in diagrams has been converted to formulae with the help of artificial neural nets.

1 Introduction

The standard design tools for seakeeping are

- Green Function Method for offshore structures of zero (or very low) speed
- Strip method for slender ships of low to moderate speed

Strip methods date back to *Korvin-Kroukowski and Jacobs (1957)*. The strip method presented here follows the slightly different method of *Söding (1969)*. The basic idea of the strip method is to convert a 3-d problem into several (independent) 2-d problems. This reduces the effort for grid generation and computation significantly. While strip methods are well established in industry to evaluate the seakeeping of 'normal' displacement ships, the seakeeping analysis of sailing yachts introduces several complications not addressed by regular strip methods:

- Non-symmetric cross sections: Due to yaw and heel, sailing yachts have typically non-symmetric cross sections. However, an extension of modern close-fit methods for the 2-d hydrodynamics module to non-symmetric cross sections is straight-forward.
- Speed influence: The classical strip method approach considers the geometry of the ship up to the waterline at zero speed. The submerged waterline of sailing yachts changes significantly with forward speed, changing the stiffness matrix (waterline area and metacentric heights) as well as added mass, damping and exciting forces. The speed-dependent submerged waterline (due to dynamic trim and sinkage, steady wave profile) could be computed by a non-linear wave resistance code as described in *Bertram (2000)*. An interface to PDSTRIP has not yet been created.
- Lifting surfaces: Sailing yachts have often relatively large lifting surfaces (keel fin and rudder). These require special treatment in a strip method, either by introducing lifting elements (dipoles, vortices) or by empirical models. The lifting surfaces affect added mass, damping and exciting forces.
- Sails: The large sails add considerable 'external' roll damping and sometimes significant damping.

In late 2005, a research project between FH Kiel and ENSIETA started to develop a seakeeping module to be added to a Velocity Prediction Program (VPP) for competitive sailing yachts. The long-term aim is to have a versatile, public-domain strip method for teaching, research and industry, *Bertram et al. (2006a,b)*, *Palladino et al. (2006)*. As a major component for sailing yachts, we focus here on the treatment of sails and fins, extending the fin theory outlined in *Graf et al. (2007)* to movable fins.

2 Description of the strip method

2.1 Global aspects

We consider the rigid-body motion \vec{u} of the ship in 6 degrees of freedom with $\vec{u} = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6\}^T$ (surge u_1 , sway u_2 , heave u_3 , roll u_4 , pitch u_5 , yaw u_6). The fundamental equation of motions for harmonic motions $\vec{u} = \hat{\vec{u}}e^{i\omega t}$ is, see *Bertram (2000)*:

$$(-\omega_e^2 M - B + S) \cdot \hat{\vec{u}} = \hat{\vec{F}}_e \quad (1)$$

$\omega_e = \omega - kv \cos \mu$ is the encounter frequency. $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number, ω the wave frequency, v the ship speed and μ the wave direction. The symbol $\hat{}$ indicates generally a complex amplitude. M is the real mass matrix of the ship, S is the real matrix due to hydrostatics, B is the complex matrix due to ship motions (added mass and damping) and $\hat{\vec{F}}_e$ are the excitation forces due to the incident wave and its diffraction. In general B is calculated from 2-d hydrodynamic forces exerted from the water on a sectional strip moving periodically, *Bertram et al. (2006a)*. The 3-component motion amplitude vector of the strip $\hat{\vec{u}}_x = \{\hat{u}_2, \hat{u}_3, \hat{u}_4\}^T$ is related to the respective force vector $\hat{\vec{f}}_x = \{\hat{f}_2, \hat{f}_3, \hat{f}_4\}^T$ by:

$$\hat{\vec{f}}_x = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{m}_{22} & \bar{m}_{23} & \bar{m}_{24} \\ \bar{m}_{32} & \bar{m}_{33} & \bar{m}_{34} \\ \bar{m}_{42} & \bar{m}_{43} & \bar{m}_{44} \end{bmatrix} \omega_e^2 \hat{\vec{u}}_x \quad (2)$$

The elements of the complex added mass matrix in Eq.(2) can be interpreted as real value added masses m_{ij} and damping n_{ij} :

$$\bar{m}_{ij} = m_{ij} + \frac{n_{ij}}{i\omega_e} \quad (3)$$

Rewriting Eq.(2) as time derivative of momentum allows to take into account forward ship speed by introducing substantial derivatives for partial time derivatives. Transformation of the 3-component strip velocity and forces into the global ship motion coordinate system and integration over ship length allows to calculate B . A similar approach is used for the excitation forces, the forces acting on the fixed hull generated by an incident wave. These forces consist of the Froude-Krilov part (due to the pressure in the undisturbed wave) and the diffraction part (due to the pressure from the diffraction of the wave due to the ship hull). For surge motion a different approach has to be used, since strip theory cannot predict added mass for surge. Here an empirical formula for the added mass of a ship is used and introduced into the matrix B .

2.2 Fins

Ships frequently have fins (rudders, stabilizing fins, keels). Sailing yachts have unusually large fins in comparison to 'normal' ships. The shape of a fin is characterized by a mean chord length c (in x direction) and a span s measured in the y, z -plane, Fig.1. Fins having an aspect ratio $\Lambda = s/c \ll 1$, and fins which continue the hull to the rear (like skegs or rudders) may be treated as parts of the hull.

Fins having a span s which is in the same size range or larger than the distance between fin center and the 'roll axis' (approximately parallel to the x -axis through the center of gravity of ship's mass) will be treated more accurately if they are subdivided into two or more fin strips. In this case, the lift gradient $dC_L/d\alpha$ of the strip fin has to be determined using the aspect ratio Λ of the total fin, not that of the part fins. α is the angle of attack, C_L the lift coefficient of a foil.

The program considers only the oscillating forces normal to the (average) center plane of the fin; in linear approximation, this force is the lift. Resistance forces and lift forces depending nonlinearly on the angle of attack are neglected. Especially, the stall angle is not taken into account. The influence of waves and vortices generated by one fin on other fins (e.g. a rudder behind the keel fin of a sailing yacht) is neglected.

Fig.1: Fin axis vector \vec{a}_F , pressure center \vec{x}_f , velocity reference point \vec{x}_{F1} , unit normal \vec{n}_F

The position of a fin is characterized by its pressure center $\vec{x}_F = \{x_F, y_F, z_F\}$. The local flow velocity (needed e.g. to determine the average angle of attack) is calculated at x_{F1} . We assume $x_F = \{x_F - c/2, y_F, z_F\}$. The direction of the axis of a fin is characterized by the unit vector $\vec{a}_F = \{a_x, a_y, a_z\}$. All three vectors, Fig.1, are required as user input. Example: For a rudder $\vec{a}_F = \{0, 0, 1\}$ as shown in Fig.1 (input as $(0,0,-1)$, because the PDSTRIP input coordinate system has z pointing upwards; correspondingly, a stabilizing fin on port, pointing down at an angle of 45° would be input as $(0., 0.707, -0.707)$). Then the rudder angle is taken positive to port.

The angle α_{s3} of movable fins specifies the right-hand rotation of a fin around its axis \vec{a}_F . We assume a linear relationship between ship motions and control mechanism:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{s3} = \vec{\alpha}_F \hat{u} \quad (4)$$

The user-specified complex vector $\vec{\alpha}_F = \{\alpha_{F1}, \dots, \alpha_{F6}\}$ describes the active control of the fin.

To determine the angle of attack, ship and wave orbital motions are taken into account, but radiation and diffraction waves are neglected. Let \vec{n}_F be a unit vector, in the y, z -plane, and normal to the fin center plane:

$$\vec{n}_F = \frac{(1, 0, 0) \times \vec{a}_F}{|(1, 0, 0) \times \vec{a}_F|} = \{0, n_{F2}, n_{F3}\} \quad (5)$$

The amplitude of flow speed in the direction of \vec{n}_F induced by the incident wave of complex amplitude $\hat{\zeta}$ and water depth D is:

$$\hat{v}_{FW} \hat{\zeta} = \frac{\omega \hat{\zeta}}{\sinh(kD)} e^{ik(-x_{F1} \cos \mu + y_F \sin \mu)} \cdot \vec{n}_F \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \sin \mu \cosh(k(z_F - z_B)) \\ -i \sinh(k(z_F - z_B)) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

z_B is the vertical coordinate of the water bottom, z_{wl} is the vertical coordinate of the calm-water surface, $D = z_B - z_{wl}$. $z_B = D$ if the origin is in the calm water plane. The above formula is for z pointing downwards. For z pointing up, the z -values change sign and μ changes sign. For sufficiently deep water, Eq.(6) can be substituted by:

$$\hat{v}_{FW} \hat{\zeta} = \omega \hat{\zeta} e^{-k(z_F - z_{wl}) - ik(-x_{F1} \cos \mu + y_F \sin \mu)} \cdot \vec{n}_F \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ \sin \mu \\ -i \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The complex amplitude \hat{v}_{FS} of the fin velocity in direction \vec{n}_F relative to the inertial coordinate system follows from the ship motions:

$$\hat{v}_{FS} = i\omega_e \cdot W_F \cdot \hat{u} \quad (8)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} W_F &= \{0, n_{F2}, n_{F3}, -n_{F2}z_F + n_{F3}y_F, -n_{F3}x_{F1}, n_{F2}x_{F1}\} \\ &= \{0, n_{F2}, n_{F3}, -n_{F2}z_F + n_{F3}y_F, -n_{F3}(x_F - c/2), n_{F2}(x_F - c/2)\} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The added mass of a fin for accelerations in direction \vec{n}_F is determined as

$$m_F = c_M \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \rho c^2 s \quad (10)$$

c_M is a user-specified input, ρ the density of water.

The complex amplitude of the acceleration due to orbital motion is $i\omega \cdot r \cdot \hat{v}_{FW} \cdot \hat{\zeta}$, that due ship motion is $i\omega_e \cdot r \cdot \hat{v}_{FS}$. r is a user-specified factor taking into account the presence of the hull in the vicinity of the fin. Thus the added-mass force at the fin due to the wave is

$$\hat{F}_{FW} = \hat{v}_{FW} \cdot r \cdot m_F \cdot i\omega \cdot \hat{\zeta} \quad (11)$$

and due to the ship motion

$$\hat{F}_{FS} = \omega_e^2 \cdot r \cdot m_F \cdot W_F \cdot \hat{u} \quad (12)$$

An acceleration due to ship motion results in a force on the fin opposite to the fin acceleration, hence the sign in \hat{F}_{FS} .

Beside the added mass forces, additional periodic forces are generated due to the time varying angle of attack of the fin $\hat{\alpha}$. The complex amplitude of this force \hat{L} acting in direction \vec{n}_F is calculated from the lift of the fin:

$$\hat{L} = \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot v^2 \cdot s \cdot c \cdot \frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} \hat{\alpha} = v^2 \cdot b_F \cdot \hat{\alpha} \quad (13)$$

with

$$b_F = \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot s \cdot c \cdot \frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} \quad (14)$$

The formula was derived for stationary conditions; it is applicable for $\omega c/v \ll 1$, which is typical for our applications. The lift coefficient gradient $dC_L/d\alpha$ is a user-specified input.

The complex amplitude of the angle of attack $\hat{\alpha}$ is the sum of four contributions $\hat{\alpha} = \hat{\alpha}_W + \hat{\alpha}_{s1} + \hat{\alpha}_{s2} + \hat{\alpha}_{s3}$:

- Due to the wave (for ship speed $v \neq 0$):

$$\hat{\alpha}_W = r \cdot \frac{\hat{v}_{FW}}{v} \cdot \hat{\zeta} \quad (15)$$

For $v = 0$ the expression is not evaluated because then $\hat{L} = 0$.

- Due to the fin moving with the ship in direction \vec{n}_F :

$$\hat{\alpha}_{s1} = -r \cdot \frac{\hat{v}_{FS}}{v} = -i\omega_e \cdot r \cdot \frac{W_F}{v} \cdot \hat{u} \quad (16)$$

- Due to the rotation of the fin with the ship:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{s2} = r \cdot c_F \cdot \hat{u} \quad (17)$$

with

$$c_F = \{0, 0, 0, 0, a_{F2}, a_{F3}\} \quad (18)$$

- Due to the fin control:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{s3} = s \cdot \alpha_F \cdot \hat{u} \cdot \sqrt{a_{F2}^2 + a_{F3}^2} \quad (19)$$

s is a user-specified factor accounting for the type of rudder. The factor $\sqrt{a_{F2}^2 + a_{F3}^2} \leq 1$ takes a possible inclination of the fin axis against the y-z-plane into account.

We introduce the velocity at the fin v_F :

$$v_F = b_f \cdot v \quad (20)$$

Eqs.(11) to (13) can be combined into a single expression, using the different components of the angle of attack following Eqs.(15) to (19):

$$\hat{F}_F = \left[(\omega_e^2 \cdot r \cdot m_F - i\omega_e \cdot r \cdot v_F) \cdot W_F + v_F \cdot v \cdot r \cdot c_F + v_F \cdot v \cdot s \cdot \sqrt{a_{F2}^2 + a_{F3}^2} \cdot \vec{\alpha}_F \right] \cdot \hat{u} + [\hat{v}_{FW} \cdot r \cdot (i\omega \cdot m_F + v_F)] \cdot \hat{\zeta} \quad (21)$$

The arising total complex amplitude of the fin force consists of terms depending linearly on ship motion (first line), which contribute to the complex matrix B in Eq.(1), and of terms depending linearly on wave amplitude (second line), which contribute to the excitation forces \vec{F}_e . F_F acts at point \vec{x}_F in direction \vec{n}_F . It is transformed to a 6-component generalised force vector acting at the coordinate origin by left multiplication with V_F :

$$V_F = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \vec{n}_F \\ \vec{x}_F \times \vec{n}_F \end{array} \right\} = W_F^T \quad (22)$$

2.3 Sails

Periodical forces on sails influence ship motions. In fact, the damping effect on roll motion is often dominant. We approximate the sail as a plane. Only forces normal to the sail plane are considered. The treatment of sails is then analogous to that of fins.

For accurate results, a sail should be subdivided horizontally into several strips, Fig.2. The chord vector \vec{c} points from the leading to the trailing edge of the sail strip and its length is the chord length c of the sail strip. The mast vector \vec{m}_S points upward and its length is the height of the sail strip. The reference point \vec{x}_S is assumed to lie at half the height of the strip and about $0.25c$ behind the leading edge of the sail strip. \vec{x}_{S1} is located $0.5c$ behind \vec{x}_S :

$$\vec{x}_{S1} = \vec{x}_S + 0.5\vec{c} \quad (23)$$

Chord vector and mast vector determine the sail area vector \vec{s} :

$$\vec{s} = \vec{c} \times \vec{m}_S \quad (24)$$

\vec{s} is a vector normal to the sail plane, having the sail strip area as length. It can also be written as sail strip area times its unit normal.

Fig.2: Sail subdivision (left) and zoom on one sail element (right)

At first damping forces are considered. The steady force on a sail, acting normal to the sail plane, is approximated as

$$F_S = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{\text{air}} |\vec{s}| |\vec{u}_W - \vec{u}_S|^2 C_N \quad (25)$$

ρ_{air} is the density of air, assumed to be $\rho_{\text{air}} = \rho/800$. \vec{u}_W is the ‘‘apparent’’ wind velocity, i.e. the wind velocity relative to the ship sailing with its average speed ahead as given. \vec{u}_S is the oscillating velocity of the sail speed reference point x_{S1} due to ship motions. Its complex amplitude is

$$\hat{\vec{u}}_S = i\omega_e \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\hat{u}_6 & \hat{u}_5 \\ \hat{u}_6 & 0 & -\hat{u}_4 \\ -\hat{u}_5 & \hat{u}_4 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{S1} \\ y_{S1} \\ z_{S1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{u}_1 \\ \hat{u}_2 \\ \hat{u}_3 \end{bmatrix} \right) = i\omega_e \cdot W_S \cdot \hat{u} \quad (26)$$

$$W_S = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & z_{S1} & -y_{S1} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -z_{S1} & 0 & x_{S1} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & y_{S1} & -x_{S1} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

C_N is the normal force coefficient of the wind force on the sail, assumed to be a linear function of the angle of attack α of the wind relative to the sail until stall sets in. This is assumed to happen at $C_N = \pm 1.5$, Fig.3. We thus approximate:

$$C_N = \begin{cases} \frac{\partial C_N}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \alpha & \text{until stall} \\ 1.5 \operatorname{sgn}(\alpha) & \text{after stall} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Fig.3: Assumed lift coefficient function; stall after $C_N = \pm 1.5$

In Eq.(25), the quantities \vec{u}_S and α vary due to the ship motions. Linearizing this change, the complex amplitude of $|\vec{u}_W - \vec{u}_S|^2$ is $-2\vec{u}_W \hat{\vec{u}}_S$ and the complex amplitude of α is approximately $\hat{\alpha} = -(\hat{\vec{u}}_S / |\vec{u}_W|) \cdot (\vec{s} / |\vec{s}|)$. For large absolute value of $\hat{\alpha}$ the expression for $\hat{\alpha}$ is inaccurate, but that case appears only for small wind speeds and then the term containing $\hat{\alpha}$ is small anyway. This gives the complex amplitude of the sail force as

$$\hat{F}_S = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{\text{air}} |\vec{s}| \left(-2\vec{u}_W \hat{\vec{u}}_S C_N(\bar{\alpha}) + |\vec{u}_W|^2 \frac{\partial C_N}{\partial \alpha} \hat{\alpha} \right) \quad (29)$$

The second term is zero for stall, i.e. if $C_N = \pm 1.5$. $\bar{\alpha}$ is the average angle of attack (positive, if u_W has a positive component in direction \vec{s}):

$$\bar{\alpha} = \arcsin \frac{\vec{u}_W \cdot \vec{s}}{|\vec{u}_W| |\vec{s}|} \quad (30)$$

To apply \hat{F}_S in the computation of the motion transfer functions, the ship motion \hat{u} has to be separated:

$$\hat{F}_S = -\frac{1}{2} \rho_{\text{air}} |\vec{s}| \left(2 \vec{u}_W C_N(\bar{\alpha}) + |\vec{u}_W| \frac{\partial C_N}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\vec{s}}{|\vec{s}|} \right) i\omega_e \cdot W_S \cdot \hat{u} \quad (31)$$

The force and moment acting on the ship due to the sail force is $V_S \hat{F}_S$ with

$$V_S = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \vec{s}/|\vec{s}| \\ \vec{x}_F \times \vec{s}/|\vec{s}| \end{array} \right\} \quad (32)$$

For light ships with large sails, the added air mass of the sails may contribute considerably to the moment of inertia around the longitudinal axis. The added mass of the sail is

$$m_F = c_M \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \rho_{\text{air}} |\vec{s}| |\vec{c}| \quad (33)$$

Because \vec{s} contains already a factor c , the added mass is proportional to the square of the chord length as for the fin added mass.

The complex amplitude of the added-mass forces due to the sails are then:

$$\hat{F}_{S_a} = -c_M \frac{\pi}{4} \rho_{\text{air}} \vec{s} |\vec{c}| (i\omega_e)^2 \cdot W_S \cdot \hat{u} \quad (34)$$

c_M can be estimated as described for fins. The effect of the sail added-mass force on the ship force and moment is again determined by left-multiplication of \hat{F}_{S_a} with V_S .

The contribution of sails to the matrix B is the sum of the damping and mass force without the right-hand factor \hat{u} :

$$B_S = - \sum_{\text{all strips}} \rho_{\text{air}} V_S \left(\vec{u}_W C_N(\bar{\alpha}) |\vec{s}| + \frac{1}{2} |\vec{u}_W| \frac{\partial C_N}{\partial \alpha} \vec{s} + \frac{\pi}{4} c_M i\omega_e |\vec{c}| \vec{s} \right) i\omega_e W_S \quad (35)$$

For aftward wind, the point of attack of the wind force \vec{x}_S and the velocity reference point \vec{x}_{S1} exchange their positions. This is of minor importance and is neglected in the program.

2.4 Expert knowledge

2.4.1 User-specified input

The user has to specify several coefficients to compute the influence of fins in PDSTRIP. Some guidelines for users can be found in various places in *Graf et al. (2007)*, *Bertram et al. (2007)*. These rules are compiled and extended here for convenience:

- For fins attached to the hull (like the keel), the aspect ratio Λ should be doubled.
- \vec{x}_F is located normally at half span, $0.25c$ behind the leading edge.
- $r \approx 1$ for fins at a sufficient distance from the hull.
- $r > 1$ for fins attached to the hull and pointing to the sides or downward.
- $r \approx 0$ for rudders (or all fins attached at the aft end of the hull, if they do not reach out of the hull's wake).
- $r = 0$ always when the fin is already included in the geometrical hull description.
- Rules for c_M are discussed separately in the next subsection.

For fins in free flow, the lift coefficient gradient can be approximated as, *Bertram (2000)*:

$$\frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} = 2\pi \frac{\Lambda(\Lambda + 0.7)}{(\Lambda + 1.7)^2} \quad (36)$$

However, the lift coefficient gradient may be influenced substantially by various effects. Propeller slip-stream, wake and boundary layer change the flow speed at the fin. Because in the formula for the lift force L the ship speed v is used instead of the flow speed at the fin, the lift coefficient gradient according to Eq.(36) should be multiplied by the square of the ratio actual inflow speed over ship speed.

- Propeller slipstream. We estimate the effect of propeller-rudder interaction by adding a semi-empirical correction to the lift gradient. *Söding (1998)* proposes “a simple global correction of the lift force of a rudder behind a propeller (to be added the lift computed by the usual empirical formulae for rudders in free stream)”, *Bertram (2000)*:

$$\Delta L = T \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + C_{Th}}}\right) \sin \delta \quad (37)$$

Here, T denotes the propeller thrust, C_{Th} the thrust loading coefficient (defined as usual) and δ the rudder angle. For small δ , we can approximate $\sin \delta \approx \delta$. Assuming that the rudder angle δ coincides with the angle of attack α , we then have an additive correction for the lift gradient coefficient:

$$\Delta \frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} = \frac{T}{\frac{\rho}{2} v^2 A_R} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + C_{Th}}}\right) \quad (38)$$

A_R is the rudder area.

- Ship’s wake. The integral effect of the wake behind a ship is expressed by the wake fraction $w = 1 - (v_A/v)$. v_A is advance velocity, i.e. the average flow velocity in the wake in the propeller plane. *Schneekluth and Bertram (1998)* give simple estimates, e.g. following *Krüger (1976)*:

$$w = \begin{cases} 0.75 \cdot C_B - 0.24 & \text{for single-screw ships} \\ 0.81 \cdot C_B - 0.34 & \text{for twin-screw ships} \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

C_B is the block coefficient of the ship.

- Boundary layer along the hull reduces the velocity and thus stagnation pressure.
- Non-viscous interaction between hull and fin increases the lift gradient.
- Exceeding the stall angle would decrease the lift. Foils attached to the hull stall earlier than in free uniform flow. This can be explained by the disturbed flow on the suction side of the foil, *Schlichting and Truckenbrodt (1979)*.
- Gaps between different parts of the fin decrease the lift.
- The boundary layer at the fin decreases the lift; the effect is negligible except for very small fins in model experiments)

More elaborate models to consider the above effects modifying $dC_L/d\alpha$ may be subject to future research.

Analogously, the normal force coefficient gradient of a sail strip is approximated

$$\frac{\partial C_N}{\partial \alpha} = 2\pi \frac{\Lambda(\Lambda + 0.7)}{(\Lambda + 1.7)^2} \quad (40)$$

Λ is the aspect ratio. If wind flow under the lower edge of the sail is severely restricted, Λ should be increased, for full suppression of the flow below the lower edge of the sail by a factor of 2.

For movable fins (rudders, stabilizing fins), the control vector $\vec{\alpha}_F$ needs to be specified. A fin can increase or decrease motions, depending on the position of the fin, the direction of $\vec{\alpha}_F$ and the sign of the real parts (corresponding to restoring forces) and the imaginary parts (corresponding to damping forces) of the components of $\vec{\alpha}_F$. A rudder with $\vec{\alpha}_F = \{0, 0, 1\}$ would typically have a control system (helmsman, autopilot) that corrects for course changes (yaw motion) only. In this case the first five components of $\vec{\alpha}_F$ are complex zeros. For yaw, we could e.g. prescribe 2° rudder angle for 1° yaw angle (course deviation). In addition, we may want to introduce a damping moment, e.g. by setting the imaginary part to e.g. 10. This would yield $\vec{\alpha}_F = \{(0., 0.), (0., 0.), (0., 0.), (0., 0.), (0., 0.), (2., 10.)\}$. It is recommended to test

whether the correct signs have been selected by comparing the motions with and without fin control. Also, after a computation, it should be checked whether the fin exceeds an angle where stall has to be expected. For the example of the rudder, we would then check whether $|\alpha_{F6}| \cdot |\hat{u}_6| \hat{\zeta}$ exceeds a stall angle, which may be assumed at 35° . If the stall angle is exceeded, a smaller α_{F6} should be chosen and the simulation should be repeated.

The user-specified rudder factor s is:

- $s = 1$ for fins turning as a single body (like spade or simplex rudders)
- $s < 1$ if the front part is fixed and only the aft part rotated (semi-balanced rudder); $s = 0.7$ is a typical value for a semi-balanced rudder, where the rudder area A_R then relates to the area including the horn.
- $s > 1$ for flapped rudders (like Becker rudders), typically $s = 1.7$.

2.4.2 Added mass coefficient for fins

If the fin is already included in the geometrical hull description, $c_M = 0$.

The added mass coefficient c_M was estimated in *Bertram et al. (2007)* to $c_M \approx 1$ for $s/c \gg 1$, $c_M \approx \Lambda$ for $\Lambda \ll 1$, where Λ is defined as:

$$\Lambda = \begin{cases} 2s/c & \text{if the fin is attached to the hull without gap for water to flow through} \\ s/c & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

For intermediate ratios Λ , *Meyerhoff (1968)* give a diagram, Fig.4, to estimate c_M , where the abscissa should use $1/\Lambda$.

Fig.4: Added mass coefficient c_M vs. $1/\Lambda$; planform rectangular (full line), elliptical (dotted line)

For a variety of reasons, a formula is preferable to a diagram. We have used artificial neural nets, *Mesbahi (2003)*, in the past to turn knowledge given in curves into programmable formulae, e.g. in *Bertram and Mesbahi (2004)* for power prediction of semi-planing and planing hulls. We use the same approach here. The neural nets had two hidden layers with 4 nodes each. We derived thus:

For rectangular planform:

$$c_M = 0.046500 + 0.99000 \cdot \text{sig}[2.56576 + 2.91378 \cdot \text{sig}(2.97899 - 5.87816x^*) - 5.72552 \cdot \text{sig}(-1.13235 + 18.3059x^*)] \quad (42)$$

with $x^* = \frac{0.090909}{\Lambda} + 0.040909$

For elliptical planform:

$$c_M = 0.047944 + 0.96111 \cdot \text{sig}[-0.30975 - 2.29389 \cdot \text{sig}(-1.84793 + 5.35277x^*) + 5.17223 \cdot \text{sig}(0.882984 - 15.4695x^*)] \quad (43)$$

with $x^* = \frac{0.090909}{\Lambda} + 0.040909$

In both cases, the sigmoid function was used:

$$\text{sig}(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (44)$$

3 Conclusion

The information compiled from various publications and interviews with experts allows to estimate important user input for a simulation of a ship in seaways employing the code PDSTRIP (or a related simulation method). The knowledge incorporated in diagrams has been converted to formulae which can be easily programmed.

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Appendix 1: Program code for fins

Table I relates nomenclature used here to the variables in the program.

Table I: Fortran variables and corresponding symbols in documentation

fortran name	data type	significance	variable
addedmassfin	real	added mass of fin	m_F
afin	real(3)	axis vector	\vec{a}_F
alfin	complex	specific instance of calfin for one fin	$\vec{\alpha}_F$
bfin	real	intermediate quantity for fin force determination	b_F
bfinnew	complex	complex added mass matrix of fins, contribution to	B
calfin	complex(6)	fin control angle amplitude/motion amplitude	$\vec{\alpha}_F$
cfin	real	chord length of fin	c
cfinmatr	complex	vector for fin forces due to ship motion	c_F
cvfs	complex	velocity amplitude of a fin due to ship motion	\hat{v}_{FS}
cvfw	complex	velocity amplitude of a fin due to incident wave	\hat{v}_{FW}
ci	complex	imaginary unit	$i = \sqrt{-1}$
ciome	complex	abbreviation for	$i \cdot \omega_e$
cmfin	real	added mass coefficient of fin	c_m
clgrfin	real	lift coefficient gradient	$dC_L/d\alpha$
cosm	real	cosine of encounter angle	$\cos \mu$
efinnew	complex	excitation force due to fin, contribution to	F_e
lfin	real	span length of fin	s
om	real	wave circular frequency	ω
ome	real	encounter circular frequency	ω_e
pi	real	$\pi = 3.14159\dots$	π
rho	real	water density	ρ
rfin	real	hull influence factor for fin lift	r
rnf2	real	y-component of fin normal vector \vec{n}_F	n_{F2}
rnf3	real	z-component of fin normal vector \vec{n}_F	n_{F3}
sfin	real	fin angle factor (rudder type)	s
vfin	real	velocity at fin	v_F
vs	real	ship speed	v
wfinmatr	complex(1,6)	transformation matrix	W_F
waven	real	wave number	k
xfin	real(3)	center of fin	\vec{x}_F
zbot	real	z-coordinate of the water bottom	z_B
zw	real	temporary storage of auxiliary term	
zwl	real	z-coordinate of the still waterline	z_{wl}

The lines in the Fortran program corresponding to the documentation of the theory are given below.

After reading the data from the input file, the program

- ensures that axis vector \vec{a}_F has unit length
- computes the added mass following Eq.(10)
- computes the unit normal \vec{n}_F according to Eq.(5)
- computes the transformation matrix W_F according to Eq.(9)
- computes the intermediate quantity b_F according to Eq.(14)
- computes the vector c_F according to Eq.(18)
- computes $s \cdot \sqrt{a_{F2}^2 + a_{F3}^2}$

for all fins:

```

Fins: do ifin=1,nfin                                     !prepare fin data
  zw=sqrt(sum(afin(1:3,ifin)**2))
  afin(1:3,ifin)=afin(1:3,ifin)/zw
  addedmassfin(ifin)=cmfin(ifin)*pi/4.*rho*cfin(ifin)**2*lfin(ifin)
  zw=sqrt(afin(2,ifin)**2+afin(3,ifin)**2)
  rnf2=-afin(3,ifin)/zw
  rnf3= afin(2,ifin)/zw
  wfinmatr(:, :, ifin)=fillrealmatr(1,6,(/ 0., rnf2, rnf3, rnf2*xfin(3,ifin)-rnf3*xfin(2,ifin), &
    -rnf3*(xfin(1,ifin)-0.5*cfin(ifin)), rnf2*(xfin(1,ifin)-0.5*cfin(ifin))/))
  bfin(ifin)=0.5*rho*lfin(ifin)*cfin(ifin)*clgrfin(ifin)
  cfinmatr(:, :, ifin)=fillrealmatr(1,6,(/0.,0.,0.,0.,-rnf3,rnf2/))
  skorfin(ifin) = sfin(ifin)*zw
enddo Fins

```

Then the program

- computes the velocity amplitude at the fin due to the incident wave (for unit wave amplitude $\hat{\zeta} = 1$), using a simplified expression for sufficiently deep water, according to Eqs.(6) and (7)
- computes the velocity at the fin following Eq.(20)
- computes the contribution to added mass and damping (the complex added-mass matrix B) according to Eq.(21), transforming to the global ship system according to Eq.(22)
- computes the contribution to the exciting force vector F_e according to Eq.(21), transforming to the global ship system according to Eq.(22)

```

ForFins: do ifin=1,nfin                                !influence of fins[...]
  [...]
  if (waven*(zbot-zwl)>3.0) then                        !deep water. xfin input system, zwl interior system
    cvfw=om*exp(cmplx(-waven*(-xfin(3,ifin)-zwl), waven*(-(xfin(1,ifin)-0.5*cfin(ifin))*cosm- &
      xfin(2,ifin)*sinm)))*(wfinmatr(1,2,ifin)*sinm+wfinmatr(1,3,ifin)*ci)
  else
    cvfw=om/sinh(waven*(zbot-zwl)) &                !xfin in input system!
      *exp(ci*waven*(-(xfin(1,ifin)-0.5*cfin(ifin))*cosm-xfin(2,ifin)*sinm)) &
      *(wfinmatr(1,2,ifin)*sinm*cosh(waven*(-xfin(3,ifin)-zbot)) &
        -wfinmatr(1,3,ifin)*ci*sinh(waven*(-xfin(3,ifin)-zbot)))
  endif
  vfin=bfin(ifin)*vs
  [...]

  bfinnew=transpose(wfinmatr(:, :, ifin)).mprod.( &
    (ome**2*rfin(ifin)*addedmassfin(ifin)-ciome*vfin*rfin(ifin))*wfinmatr(:, :, ifin) &
    +vfin*vs*rfin(ifin)*cfinmatr(:, :, ifin)+vfin*vs*skorfin(ifin)*alfin)
  [...]
  efinnew=cvfw*rfin(ifin)*(ci*om*addedmassfin(ifin)+vfin)*transpose(wfinmatr(:, :, ifin))
  [...]
enddo ForFins

```

Appendix 2: Program code for sails

Table II relates nomenclature used here to the variables in the program.

Table II: Additional Fortran variables and corresponding symbols in documentation

fortran name	data type	significance	variable
addedmass	complex	added mass and damping matrix	B_S
baralpha	real	average angle of attack of sail strip	$\bar{\alpha}$
csail	real	sail chord vector	\vec{c}
cmsail	real	added mass coefficient of sail	c_M
cn	real	normal force coefficient of sail	C_N
dcndasail	real	lift gradient coefficient for sail strip	$\partial C_N / \partial \alpha$
msail	real	mast vector	\vec{m}_S
mu	real	wave angle	μ
muw	real	direction of true wind relative to wave propagation	μ
rhovsail	complex	intermediate matrix	$\rho_{\text{air}} V_S$
sailfactor	complex	intermediate result for sail force; in in Eq.(35):	$-(\dots)i\omega_e$
ssail	real	sail vector	\vec{s}
ssailabs	real	absolute value of sail vector	$ \vec{s} $
uw	real	true wind speed	$-$
uwind	real(3)	apparent wind vector	\vec{u}_W
uwindabs	real	apparent wind speed	$ \vec{u}_W $
vs	real	ship speed	v
wsailmatr	complex	W matrix for sail	W_S
xsail	real(3)	sail force point of attack	\vec{x}_S
xsail1	real(3)	point where sail angle of attack is determined	\vec{x}_{S1}

The lines in the Fortran program corresponding to the documentation of the theory are given below. After reading the data from the input file, the program

- converts the input data from the input coordinate system (with z pointing upwards) to the internal coordinate system (with z pointing downwards)
- computes the speed reference point \vec{x}_{S1} according to Eq.(23)
- creates the matrix W_S according to Eq.(27)
- computes the sail area vector \vec{s} according to Eq.(24) and $|\vec{s}|$
- computes $\rho_{\text{air}} V_S$ with V_s following Eq.(32)

for all sail strips:

```

muw=muw*pi/180          !Preparations for sails. First change from input system to interior system
Sails: do isail=1,nsail
  xsail(:,isail)=(/xsail(1,isail),-xsail(2,isail),-xsail(3,isail)/)
  csail(:,isail)=(/csail(1,isail),-csail(2,isail),-csail(3,isail)/)
  msail(:,isail)=(/msail(1,isail),-msail(2,isail),-msail(3,isail)/)
  xsail1(1:3,isail)=xsail(1:3,isail)+0.5*csail(1:3,isail)          !speed reference point
  wsailmatr(:,isail)=fillrealmatr(3,6,(/
    1., 0., 0., 0., xsail1(3,isail), -xsail1(2,isail), &
    0., 1., 0., -xsail1(3,isail), 0., xsail1(1,isail), &
    0., 0., 1., xsail1(2,isail),-xsail1(1,isail), 0. /))
  ssail(1:3,isail)=csail(:,isail).vprod.msail(:,isail)
  ssailabs(isail)=sqrt(sum(ssail(1:3,isail)**2))
  rhovsail(1:3,1,isail)=ssail(:,isail)*rho/800./ssailabs(isail)
  rhovsail(4:6,1,isail)=xsail(:,isail).vprod.ssail(:,isail)*rho/800./ssailabs(isail)
enddo Sails

```

Then the program

- computes $\bar{\alpha}$ according to Eq.(30)
- computes C_N according to Eq.(28)
- computes the contribution to the added mass and damping (the complex added-mass matrix B) according to Eq.(35)

```
IfSails: if (nsail>0.and.itz==1) then          !change of addedmass due to sails only once
  uwind=uw*(/cos(mu(imu)+muw),-sin(mu(imu)+muw),0./)
  uwind(1)=uwind(1)-vs                        !uwind = apparent wind
  if (abs(uwind(1))<0.001) uwind(1)=1e-3
  uwindabs=sqrt(sum(uwind**2))
  AllSails: do isail=1,nsail
    baralpha=asin(sum(uwind*ssail(1:3,isail))/uwindabs/ssailabs(isail))
    cn=max(-1.5,min(dcndasail(isail)*baralpha,1.5))
    sailfactor(1:3)=-uwind(1:3)*cn*ssailabs(isail) &
      -pi/4.*cmsail(isail)*ciome*sqrt(sum(csail(1:3,isail)**2))*ssail(1:3,isail)
    if (abs(cn)<1.5) sailfactor=sailfactor-0.5*uwindabs*ssail(1:3,isail)*dcndasail(isail)
    sailfactor(1:3)=sailfactor(1:3)*ciome
    addedmass(:,:,1)=addedmass(:,:,1)+(rhovsail(:,:,isail).mprod. &
      reshape(sailfactor,(/1,3/)).mprod.wsailmatr(:,:,isail))
  enddo AllSails
endif IfSails
```

Interaction and Ergonomics Issues in Immersive Design Review Environments

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Abstract

This paper discusses the interaction paradigms and ergonomics issues for immersive engineering design review environments based on the AutoEval system. It presents how previous findings of individual, isolated aspects in human-computer-interaction can be transferred or adapted successfully to an application oriented environment that combines a variety of tools to interact with 3D data. A special focus is put onto scale issues arising from the physical size and configuration of the immersive workspace: As opposed to indirect editing tools, the direct “hands-on” manipulation paradigm that is used in the AutoEval system requires rescaling of 3D objects that exceed the size of the physical interaction space, such as large architectural models or maritime platform designs. Such scaling operations, however, interfere with certain goals of the design review process, such as examining regulation conformance of exit routes in ship designs. The paper analyses the latest revision of the AutoEval system that combines different interaction paradigms within a Workbench display environment and discusses alternative visualisation strategies for review tasks where 1:1 scale rendering is required.

1. Introduction

Augmenting traditional design review methods using immersive real-time 3D visualisation systems promises great advantages in engineering. The potential to render and inspect a CAD model in full 3D improves the understanding of the form and function of a design because it reduces the cognitive load required to interpret an abstract 2D plan or drawing. Visualising an object within its full environment also supports understanding of its role within a larger system or context. Dynamic selection of the desired viewpoint and scale for the visualisation easily reveals information about the object that would otherwise require expert knowledge to interpret based on technical plans and, hence, enables the participation of non-expert stakeholders within the design review or sign-off process.

The enormous cost of early virtual reality systems limited the widespread use of immersive visualisation systems to a select few, highly complex and expensive projects where the potential savings in engineering time or reduction of risk factors would justify the expense. However, the ever increasing market of computer games over the last few years has turned high-performance graphics hardware into an inexpensive commodity product, and the widespread use of digital projectors in any type of presentation has further driven down the cost to visualise and present complex 3D data significantly. Even though immersive virtual reality still requires certain components that have not yet profited from mass production (e.g. 3D input devices and physical space requirements), the total system cost has decreased to a level where the major questions have shifted from bare affordability to practical issues of how to use such systems to the best effect, particularly how to interact with data.

This paper elaborates on user interface issues for manipulating 3D models in an immersive virtual reality environment in the context of design review applications for engineering. It is based on the study of the initial design, use and revision of AutoEval, an immersive design review application prototype originally designed for and in collaboration with a major car manufacturer, *Anderson et al. (2002)*. The system was designed to enable non-expert users in senior management to quickly review car designs and apply basic changes through an intuitive, “hands-on” interface. The system has been ported from the Silicon Graphics platform, for which it was originally implemented starting in 2001, to a modern and more cost-effective PC environment in 2005. This redevelopment effort provided the occasion to review earlier design decisions and refine and extend the interface, leading to AutoEval mkII.

Since its original development, the system has been demonstrated to and used by hundreds of visitors to the laboratory. Although no formal usability tests have been conducted, observing how the users approached the system and listening to their informal comments has provided valuable insight into the strength and weaknesses of the system. This paper puts these observations into context with previous research in the field of human-computer-interaction and 3D user interface technology. Although the majority of previous research focuses on individual isolated aspects of the interface, the analysis of AutoEval shows that these findings are mostly transferable to a system combining several interface elements within the same workspace.

2. Related Work

This work builds upon a wide range of findings in the field of human-computer interaction and 3D user interfaces in particular. There is also a large body of research specifically addressing design review system requirements and virtual prototyping, such as *Biermann et al. (2002)* or *Bullinger et al. (1999)*. This paper, however, focuses on the interaction design and ergonomic issues.

Research into workspace technology has been ongoing since Ivan Sutherlands SketchPad Interface, *Sutherland (2003)* for drafting back in 1963. Recent work in the field of workspaces includes investigations into multi-modal and bimanual implementations to aid in the visualization of increasingly complex data sets and design of 3D geometry. DesignSpace, *Chapin et al. (1994)*, attempted to provide a collaborative 3D workspace for users to achieve real-time interaction with 3D geometry. This early system was limited by the technology available and mainly addressed high level theories in human factors. The Immersive Modeling Environment, *Yoshimori (2000)*, attempts to merge the 2D and 3D workspace together by allowing designers to pull points off of the screen into the 3D space above to define shapes. This approach was intended to improve the user's engagement during the design process; however details of the manipulation techniques for design review for this system were not evident. Similarly, *Nakashima et al. (2005)* combine 2D and 3D interaction in a collaborative setting using the illusion hole display and additional 2D projectors.

Many research institutions have approached the design of interactive workspaces. The responsive workbench, *Krüger et al. (1995)*, has been commercialized as the Fakespace Workbench and provides the hardware interface used in AutoEval. ERGODesk, *Forsberg et al. (1998)*, introduces a workbench-like environment supporting both 2D and 3D interaction and a multimodal interface. The Visual Interaction Platform (VIP), *Aliakseyeu et al. (2001)*, is an augmented reality system that enables interaction techniques such as writing, sketching, manipulating and navigating in 2D and 3D data. IBM researches into intelligent spaces with a modular concept but less focus on 3D, *Lai et al. (2002)*. These research projects typically focus on ergonomic and hardware aspects, whereas the work presented here focuses on interaction paradigms and user interface concepts.

More recent projects put an emphasis on how the user will function within the workspace, which has become a priority issue for system design. There are numerous technologies available for research implementation, and investigating the behavioural concepts of user interaction in 3D is a continuing research project, *Payne (2003)*.

Research into individual aspects of 3D user interfaces has a long tradition in the human-computer-interaction community; *Bowman and Hodges (2005)* and *Hinkley et al. (1994)* provide excellent in-depth reviews of the field. This review paper draws upon these findings and refers to them throughout the remainder of this paper, putting them into the context of an integrated application.

3. System Overview

The AutoEval interface provides a multi-modal approach to human-computer interaction in 3D. It combines stereoscopic rendering with tactile and audio cues to ease spatial interaction with a virtual model. The AutoEval system was originally developed on the Silicon Graphics platform. Graphics

rendering was implemented using the OpenGL Performer scene graph library, *Rohlf and Helman (1994)*. Most of the other components were implemented for this particular application.

AutoEval mkII completely replaced the existing code base. Device control, configuration and visual and auditory rendering are now provided by a VR application programming interface, the blue-c API, *Naef et al. (2004)*. The switch to a recent VR toolkit enabled us to implement the new system within a fraction of the original project duration and increase its flexibility and portability at the same time. Rendering is still provided by Performer, which made the reuse of the existing models significantly easier.

3.1. Hardware Environment

Although the underlying VR toolkit supports a wide range of display and interaction devices in a transparent manner, the AutoEval mkII system is optimized for the Fakespace Workbench environment, Fig.1. The stereo CRT projection system is driven by a standard dual CPU PC with nVidia Quadro FX4400 graphics card. Audio cues are provided using an eight channel 3D audio rendering system, *Naef et al. (2002)* that is driven by the main PC.

A Polhemus Fastrak system tracks position and orientation of the right hand for interaction and the head for perspective correction. An Immersion CyberTouch glove is used to measure finger bending angles and to provide tactile feedback through its integrated vibrator motors. A 3Dconnexion SpacePilot device was used for additional indirect manipulator tests using the left hand.

The hardware environment and interface for the original AutoEval system was nearly identical from an end-user's point of view, but was driven by a Silicon Graphics Onyx 2 computer and a separate audio rendering workstation (Lake Huron). Improvements in the user's experience when using the new system are therefore down to a refinement of the user interface paradigms and not due to hardware improvements. The new hardware, however, allows visualising significantly more complex models thanks to the improved system performance.

Fig.1: Hardware setup

3.2. Loader and Scene Management

The loader module reads the 3D model data from files, assembles the parts into the scene graph, and prepares the structures for editing. As AutoEval is a concept prototype, there is no provision for automatic assembly of complex interactive objects. Instead, there are hard-coded loading routines for interactive models such as the multi-colour car with doors and bonnets that can be opened, or a Tri-

maran ship model where the hull sizes can be changed individually, Fig.2. Various parts of the model have special selection masks set to indicate if an editing operation is applicable to its children.

The current workflow to bring design data from a CAD system into the real-time visualization environment requires a significant amount of manual labour. Geometry data needs to be simplified and cleaned up, and material properties must be defined. The real-time rendering system only handles basic geometric primitives (e.g. triangles, quads). Smooth surfaces generated from NURBS modelling tools must therefore be converted into polygonal surfaces, which often results in an excessive number of primitives if parameters are not chosen carefully. Excessive detail that is not relevant for visualization (e.g. holes in surfaces that are covered by bolts and therefore not visible) further increases model complexity. In practice, we found it often more effective to rebuild the model completely in a visualization-optimized software package (e.g. Maya). Consequently, automatic conversion tools that guarantee data consistency are a top development priority for a production system.

Fig.2: Models used for testing and demonstrating the system: Car, M1 tank, off-shore platform

3.3. Menu and Visual Style

The visual design of the review environment was optimized to keep it as uncluttered as possible, while maintaining all options in direct access and keeping the menu level depth at a minimum.

The main menu is a single row of quadratic icons at the bottom end of the screen, hovering roughly 5cm above the screen surface. A second row above at the right hand corner of the screen is used as a sub-menu. Sub-menu items essentially include axis selection for editing operations. Menu items are selected by pointing through the icon with the index finger; a short sound and tactile cue signal successful selection. Having the menu icons close to the screen eases 3D picking and also provides a natural feedback cue as the user touches the screen.

Fig.3: Menu icons

The menu icons are part of the 3D scene, and are rendered with perspective correction based on the head-tracking information. Their position is fixed relative to the physical projection environment. Positioning the menu items directly on the screen surface (e.g. rendered as 2D overlays) resulted in the

best image quality and made menu selection very easy. This perfectly static rendering, however, broke the immersion because the icons did not gel well with the rest of the scene: The majority of objects are rendered with non-zero disparity and exhibit artefacts such as cross-talk between the eyes or a minor time lag during perspective correction based on head-tracking. The 2D plane perfectly aligned with the screen surface, on the other hand, was too crisp and static. It was perceived as part of the physical working environment instead of the virtual scene. Moving the same virtual menu plane just a few cm away from the physical screen surface subjected it to minor artefacts and immediately restored the sense of immersion while still keeping menu selection fairly easy.

The colour scheme of the menu icons was carefully chosen to combine aesthetics with perception issues. The icons have to be easy to distinguish given limited screen resolution and sharpness, but they should not attract too much attention. A colour scheme based around shades of green with a few red items added was chosen. Green provides a high contrast with the given CRT projection system and the sensitivity of the human eyes, *Glassner (1995)*. Limiting the scheme to one primary colour also avoids artefacts introduced by colour convergence errors most prominent around the screen borders where the menu is placed. Although modern DLP projectors provide a wider range of usable colours, the perception issues remain the same.

User feedback on the visual style has been very positive. People usually required some minor introduction into the functionality of the interface and the menu system, but felt comfortable using it almost immediately. The menu selection system, however, required precise calibration of the tracking system: People were generally aware and tolerant of the difficulties of trying to pick objects in 3D as they were unsure whether problems arise from stereoscopic perception limitations or actual tracking technology deficiencies. However, they were generally surprised when they “missed” a menu button even though they could easily physically point to and touch a menu icon close to the projection surface. The main sources for calibration errors are differing hand sizes and shapes, because the tracking sensor is attached to the back of the hand, whereas people use the index finger to actually point. Future refinements should therefore include an adaptable hand model that takes hand sizes and data from bend sensors into account. The majority of users, though, had no significant problems with calibration.

3.4. Feedback

The feedback modules provide interface cues to the user. Feedback modules include 3D audio rendering, haptic feedback and visual cues for the input devices. These modules monitor the status of the active editing tools to derive the status. Various levels of feedback can be configured for evaluation purposes.

In line with the findings of *Wang and McKenzie (2000)* and *Lindeman (1999)*, users consistently find it difficult to pick and manipulate objects in 3D without some sort of physical feedback, even if the system is properly calibrated and provides high quality stereoscopic rendering. It becomes more difficult for objects that are rendered with a large disparity (far away from the physical projection plane). The difficulty is increased further as the user covers part of the scene with the hand, sometimes breaking the depth perception. It is therefore critical to support and guide the user with various additional cues.

Visual cues include a small pointing arrow and optional pointing line to visualize and guide the interactions. Touched or grabbed objects are highlighted through overlaying a wire-frame rendering of the active object. Visual cues are only partly sufficient because the users often cover the active object completely with their hands while editing. They also fail when grabbing objects that are hidden or outside the rendering frustum. Additional non-visual cues are therefore necessary.

The AutoEval system exploits the senses of touch and hearing to provide additional cues. The main interaction device, the CyberTouch glove, has small variable vibration actuators on every finger and the palm. These are activated to provide tactile feedback for events such as touching an object (soft

vibration on all fingers as long as the object is touched), picking an object (strong vibration on all fingers), selecting a menu item (short buzz on the index finger) or enabling an indirect manipulator (vibration in the palm).

3D sound cues further support feedback. Individual sounds are associated with events (e.g. a click for menu selection) and triggered in parallel to the tactile feedback. Sounds always originate from the position where the action was triggered (e.g. they follow the hand) and are rendered using an eight speaker spatial audio system. Using 3D audio as opposed to general stereo sounds increases immersion and intuitiveness since all cues originate from the same physical location, but we expect no measurable impact on the task performance.

We found that novice users reacted very positively to the tactile feedback, but often failed to notice both visual and audio cues at first. People who used the system more regularly were satisfied with visual and audio cues alone, but still appreciated the tactile sensation. People also seemed to pay more attention to intense but short cues (e.g. a sound click or a short activation of the vibration motors) signalling a state transition, as opposed to long “buzzing” cues signalling a constant state (e.g. constant vibration while the user touches an object).

4. 3D Interaction on the Workbench

The effective interaction within the 3D volume presented by the work environment is an ongoing topic of research. Unlike desktop interaction based on keyboard and mouse, there are a large number of interaction paradigms available for designing the interface for an application, *Bowman et al. (2005)*. The following sections discuss the choices taken for the AutoEval system for navigation to inspect, and interaction to edit the model.

4.1. Navigation

Ware and Osborne (1990) define various control metaphors for navigation, including the eyeball-in-hand, scene-in-hand and flying vehicle control metaphors. As the user can easily pick and move the object with the glove interface, the scene-in-hand metaphor is inherent in the AutoEval system. This method works nicely for objects that are close and relatively small, but less so for moving through the interior of the object. The scene-in-hand metaphor perfectly suits the original task of reviewing automotive designs with a hands-on approach, as the object needs to be scaled to fit the working volume in any case. The interior of objects is revealed using a dynamic clipping plane tool instead.

The SpacePilot device was used during the development of the mkII version to control an additional flying vehicle navigation control that allowed the user to hover around the object. This additional navigation mode was dropped as it proved to be fully redundant given the natural scene-in-hand navigation functionality. It was considered slightly confusing as there was no visual space reference available other than the model, causing users to get lost quickly if they did not navigate carefully. Dedicating the SpacePilot device exclusively to an indirect manipulator task proved significantly more useful.

4.2. Direct and Indirect Manipulation

The AutoEval system provides two basic modes of interaction: direct and indirect manipulation of the objects. Both modes have their distinctive advantages and limitations, as discussed in *Naef and Payne (2007)*. Direct manipulation requires the user to grab an object for editing, and move or rotate it with the hand. All edit operations are applied at 1:1 scale. Indirect manipulation, on the other hand, is a multi-step process, first requiring the user to select the object to be edited, and then apply an editing operation through a proxy interface. Through the proxy, any type of hand movement can be mapped and scaled arbitrarily.

4.2.1. Direct Manipulation

The main advantage of the direct manipulation mode is intuitiveness. Grabbing the object in the virtual environment is the exact same gesture as picking up a small object in the real world: The hand touches the object, and grabs it by pinching it with the thumb and index finger. The object follows any hand movement while it remains pinched. Once the pinch gesture is opened, the object stays put. The major differences to a real-world situation are the fact that objects float in space without gravitational effects and the inherent limitations of the projection and interaction hardware that only provides limited force feedback cues. To increase precision, direct manipulation modes can be constrained. Movement and rotation can be restricted to certain axes while the scale of the mapping remains constant.

Our experience confirms the findings of *Zhai et al. (1996)* that the dexterity of the wrists imposes limitations, particularly when rotating the object around the x and z axes (pitch and heading), whereas the y axis (parallel to the underarm – roll) enables about 180° rotation effortlessly. Large rotation edits therefore often require several consecutive editing steps.

Scaling an object has no naturally corresponding one handed gesture in the real world; our choice of gesture is therefore arbitrary. We chose a model where the user pushes or pulls along the axis to be scaled. The mapping mode and scale was chosen experimentally, the majority of users seem to get along with the mode rather quickly.

Direct manipulation as described above requires the virtual object to reside within the physical working volume; otherwise it can not be picked. To relax that constraint, a “laser-pointer” approach is often used in virtual environments, *Bowman et al. (1997)*, *Vogel and Balakrishnan (2005)*, where selection is no longer limited to the position of the hand; instead, any object that is intersected by a ray extending from the hand can be selected. Once selected, the object stays fixed to the ray. While this mode relaxes the workspace size constraints, precise manipulation can be difficult as even slight hand rotations might translate into large translations, and other mapping modes and scaling paradigms must be defined for any editing operations where the “object-on-a-stick” paradigm does not work at all. For the AutoEval system, we opted for an indirect manipulation option instead.

4.2.2. Indirect Manipulation

To overcome some limitations of the direct manipulation paradigm, the AutoEval system augments the editing system with two types of indirect manipulation: the first based on an interaction proxy, the other based on a rate-control mechanism using the SpacePilot interface. The indirect manipulation system is designed to enable smaller scale or high-precision editing, not to replace the direct manipulation paradigm altogether.

Fig.4: Indirect editing: a) User pinches the proxy object, b) Proxy objects for rotation, c) Scaling

Indirect manipulation through a proxy object is implemented as part of the sub-menu system, Fig.4, where the menu item acts as the proxy object that can either be touched (pointing gesture) to enable the associated edit mode for direct manipulation, or pinched to indirectly edit the object that was selected/pinched last.

The indirect manipulation edit module supports three basic modes to define the transformation amount and direction. All modes apply a transformation (move, rotate, scale) along a single axis to the last selected object. The edit magnitude and direction is defined by the vector between the current hand position and where the associated UI widget was pinched initially. The three available edit modes differ in how the hand movement is mapped and scaled onto the edit operation.

The **wrist rotation** mode provides a “virtual knob” paradigm to change a value; a gesture similar to somebody changing the volume on a stereo set. Rotation is always incremental, relative to the position where the widget was pinched. This mode enables precise edits since users have a fine and precise motor control for the wrists, but it is not always considered intuitive by users.

Hand movement mode transforms the movement of the hand along the physical x axis into an edit amount. Unlike wrist rotation which is limited to roughly 180°, hand movement allows a larger motion range, but provides slightly worse motor control as it requires movement of the whole arm or body if the natural limits of the lower arm range are exceeded, *Zhai et al. (1996)*.

Finger bend mode measures the average joint angle of the middle, ring and pinkie finger using the glove sensors and transforms this difference into an edit value. This mode was introduced with the original AutoEval system for scaling objects. Finger bend mode is precise, but has a very limited range. We observed that repeated grab-bend-release gesture sequences to extend the edit range are awkward and tiresome for several reasons: the middle, ring and pinkie fingers have to be moved to the start position before the pinch gesture is conducted, and there is simply no equivalent real-world gesture or action with such a strong separation between the index finger and the middle/ring/pinkie group. In practice, it is also possible to change the direction of the edit after the pinch gesture, unless the fingers are held in a middle position, requiring a very conscious initiation of the hand gesture.

All of the moves above support an **optional scaling modifier** to enable a variable control-display ratio *Poupyrev et al. (2000)*, enabling both very small scale surgical edits as well as broad and fast transformations. The edit amount is amplified as the user moves the hand away along the physical Y axis from the edit widget after picking the widget. This mode is very useful for experienced users by allowing them to easily work around dexterity limits, but it requires explanation as it is not intuitive to first time users.

Indirect manipulation has several advantages over direct manipulation: the object no longer needs to reside within the physical working volume, the hand remains in a relatively relaxed position if the widgets are positioned sensibly, and the editing range can be scaled without breaking intuitiveness to enable precise edits. Direct manipulation, on the other hand, is significantly more intuitive and engaging than any of the indirect edit modes thanks to the direct link between the hand and the object. Both edit modes are available concurrently in the system under normal operation mode; it is the user’s choice which mode is more appropriate for the task at hand.

4.2.3. Rate Controlled Indirect Manipulation

All interaction tools mentioned above rely on the magnetic tracking system that returns the position and orientation of the hand in space, with the glove finger bend sensors used to trigger actions. In addition to the inherent precision limitations of the tracking hardware, they rely on the hand position held freely in space with no tangible reference point. The most precise handling, however, should be done with the fingertips controlling the tool and the hand rested on a surface (like writing on paper or using a mouse). This type of precision editing operation is provided by the SpacePilot interface, Fig.5.

Fig.5: The SpacePilot rate control input device

The 3Dconnexion SpacePilot is an elastic rate control interface. A small “joystick” handle with an elastic suspension that is held with the fingertips can be pushed and rotated in three directions, providing a full 6 degree of freedom input. Its movement is restricted to a very short distance and angle; hence it is not suitable as an absolute input device, but it provides a very precise direction and magnitude. This direction and magnitude is mapped onto the indirect edit operation. Instead of the direct link between the hand movement and the edit operation as in the previous manipulation modes, the operation is applied gradually over time until the handle is moved back into the neutral position; the SpacePilot defines a translation and rotation velocity for the object.

The SpacePilot causes very little fatigue as the hand can comfortably rest on the device. On the downside, rate control is an acquired skill and there is little feedback from the device due to the very small movement range, *Zhai (1998)*. Novice users therefore tend to prefer the glove interface for most tasks. Adding the SpaceMouse extends the original AutoEval system towards a two-handed interaction paradigm where the right hand is used for menu and object selection and broad manipulation, whereas the left hand is used for precise edits. This setup deviates from *Guiard’s* framework of bimanual asymmetric tasks *Guiard (1987)* that uses the dominant hand for precision manipulation, whereas the non-dominant hand defines the rough reference frame (e.g. writing on a piece of paper with the right hand, the left hand moves the paper). In our case, the non-dominant left hand controls the precise editing operations using the SpacePilot, whereas the right hand is used for large-scale edits and viewpoint manipulation using the scene-in-hand paradigm (see section 4.1). Although previous tests *Balakrishnan and Kurtenbach (1999)* suggest that using the dominant hand for precision edits would be more appropriate, the need to change the glove between the hands as the main interaction device renders this approach impractical for our system. Precision for the non-dominant hand, however, is ensured at the cost of manipulation speed by keeping the transformation velocity low (the object is moved very slowly), making it unsuitable for large edits.

5. Handling Scale and Choosing Display Systems

Stereoscopic displays theoretically offer the potential to render objects at a perceived real-world size. The physical display environment is essentially a window through which the user looks at the 3D model. In practice, there are several factors that limit the size and distance at which objects can be rendered and manipulated. These factors became evident while trying to extend the AutoEval system towards different applications such as ship design, *Sherwood Jones et al. (2006)* as well as trying to adapt it to a different projection system, *Naef and Collicott (2006)*.

5.1. Limitations of Stereoscopic Rendering

Human depth perception is essentially based upon three basic components: Stereoscopic vision, motion parallax, and depth-of-field of the eye focusing system. Further distance cues include atmospheric effects (e.g. haze) and experience (e.g. the size of known objects as relative cues). Current rendering technology can simulate most of these effects. Images can be generated and displayed separately for both eyes using a variety of stereoscopic projection systems (time-sequential, polarization, head-up displays with separate displays, etc.), simulating the different perspective due to the distance between the eyes. 3D tracking of the user's head provides the position information relative to the display required to render the correct perspective, providing accurate motion parallax cues. Basic atmospheric effects (fog, haze) are provided by the graphics hardware; more complex effects can be simulated in software, but are usually prohibitively expensive in terms of compute power and, hence, practical for pre-rendered animations only.

There are, however, several limitations imposed by current rendering technology. None of the current stereoscopic projection systems can simulate depth of field or focal distance. Instead, the eyes stay focused on the physical display surface, sending a conflicting depth cue to the brain. This discrepancy confuses depth perception and causes fatigue and, in extreme cases, nausea (simulator sickness).

Stereoscopic projection systems include additional limitations. Unless they use totally isolated display systems per eye (e.g. head-mounted displays), there is always a certain amount of cross-talk caused by imperfect image splitter systems (e.g. LCD shutter glasses, polarization filters) that manifests itself as "shadows" particularly in high-contrast regions without fine detail. Previous experiments have shown that even among people with regular stereoscopic depth perception, there is a significant difference in scale perception between individuals. There is also a sizeable proportion of the population that has limited or no stereoscopic depth perception at all, typically caused by eyesight limitations (e.g. squint).

The combined impact of these limitations means that the least fatiguing and highest quality projection is achieved when the virtual object is rendered roughly at the size and distance corresponding to the physical projection surface. Rendering closer to the user increases fatigue, whereas depth perception is diminished with increasing distance.

5.2. Workspace Design and Display System Selection

Previous research, *Pheasant (1996)*, concludes that minimal fatigue is achieved if the actual physical working volume is significantly smaller than the maximal reach of the users' arms. Fine motor control is best achieved at a hand position slightly above elbow height and within an area that corresponds to approximately one forearm's span from the body. A cube of 0.4m size centred in front of the abdomen is therefore an ideal workspace, and most actions should be restricted to this region, otherwise precision is diminished and fatigue increased. Fig.6 illustrates the working volume.

Fig.6: The preferred working volume and its relative coverage on two types of screens

A direct manipulation interface as used in the AutoEval system is therefore only efficient if the model resides within the physical working volume. The Fakespace Workbench projection environment is well suited as the projection surface is just below the volume and is able to display everything that resides within the working volume without losing resolution by covering large areas outside.

A typical wall mounted display surface, on the other hand, does not cover the full workspace unless the user stands very close to the screen. To be effective, the working volume has to be raised significantly, increasing fatigue, as the arms then need to be held at chest height for extended periods of time.

The original AutoEval prototype included the option to position a menu tool outside the visible area. To let the user find and grasp the tool, the 3D audio system was used to provide auditory cues: a sound was emanated from the position of the tool and changed pitch according to the distance between the hand and the tool. While such concepts enable positioning objects temporarily outside the visible range to keep the environment uncluttered, they cannot significantly extend the usable interaction volume for editing since the interpretation of auditory position cues tends to be significantly slower and less precise than visual cues.

Display coverage of the working volume is only one aspect when choosing the most appropriate display system. The mode of visualisation is equally important: The Workbench is only appropriate for tasks where looking down onto the object is preferred. It fails, however, at providing a sense of being inside an object, or standing in front of something large. A wall mounted display is more suited if the task requires this type of view.

Maximum flexibility is obviously provided by projection systems that completely surround the user, such as the CAVE. Apart from cost and space issues, such systems typically offer limited display resolution within the active work volume due to the need to cover a large field of view combined with limitations of current projector technology.

5.3. Preferred Model Size

The limitations of both the interaction workspace and volume and the stereoscopic rendering system suggest using model sizes that correspond roughly to the physical projection environment. In the case of the AutoEval system, this meant rendering cars approximately at a 1:5 scale. Professional car designers are used to physical models of the same scale and, hence, had no difficulty adapting to the system.

For other applications, however, such scaling might not be appropriate. Depending on the visualisation task, an accurate sense of scale must be maintained. Rescaling of the model to fit the projection environment is not acceptable in these cases, requiring the application designer to work around projection system limitations and design suitable interaction methods. Typical examples include visualisation of architectural models where an understanding of the spaces is essential. Similarly, reviewing health and safety rules compliance, such as the analysis of exit routes on ships or the work environment design for heavy machinery, requires a proper estimate of the object sizes and distances. In these cases, the basic rule of “bigger is better” holds true for the selection of the most appropriate projection technology, although cost issues will limit the feasibility of large displays.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper summarises the experience drawn from designing, implementing and revising AutoEval, a concept prototype of a design review system using immersive virtual reality technology to visualise digital prototypes. Contextualising within and comparing the experience drawn from presenting the system to hundreds of visitors to the lab against previous research mostly confirmed previous findings derived from testing isolated aspects of 3D interaction. Nonetheless, there are cases where established principles, such as *Guiard's (1987)* framework of interaction, cannot be applied due to hardware limi-

tations or conflicting requirements. Nonetheless, understanding such principles supports the engineering process to find the optimal compromise between requirements.

The AutoEval system is still a work in progress. Besides ongoing refinement of the interface and further, more formalised user tests, we are targeting new fields where immersive visualisation promises increased productivity: visualising the human body, particularly for anatomy teaching, is a natural match for the interface and workspace. We are also trying to extend the interaction system to other types of projection environments to enable interaction with models that do not naturally fit into the constrained workspace of the Fakespace workbench.

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Data Management for Better Ship-Care and Recycling

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Abstract

This paper gives an overview on the background of data management and development of an appropriate tool respecting the needs and requirements related to the new legally binding instrument on ship recycling, currently under development at International Maritime Organization (IMO). Due to a large variety of requirements on such a tool and considering the amount of data to be handled, a complex system allowing different approaches by creation of technical and logical data relations has to be created and made available, not only for assuring the life-time maintenance of data contained.

1. Introduction

The future IMO Instrument on Ship Recycling will require detailed information about chemical substances contained in the structures and equipment of ships to ensure workers' safety and environmental protection during ship recycling operations. The Inventory of Hazardous Materials will be the most challenging part of the future convention for shipbuilding industry, manufacturers and suppliers, as well as for ship owners. Annex 1 (formerly known as "Single List") lists the concerned substances in the equipment and components. The "Guideline for the Development of Inventory of Hazardous Materials" describes how they have to be recorded. This guideline also gives details for describing materials containing the substances within this Inventory of Hazardous Materials (IHM). The IHM forms the basis for further recycling planning. It consists of:

- Part 1 – Ship's Structure and Equipment
- Part 2 – Operationally Generated Wastes
- Part 3 – Stores

A tool for easy data management respecting the different user needs can be seen as an prerequisite for assuring compliance with this instrument.

2. IMO-draft "International Convention for the Safe and Environmentally Sound Recycling of Ships"

The intention of the IMO Convention is to provide regulations for

- the design, construction, operation and preparation of ships as to facilitate safe and environmentally sound recycling of ships, without compromising the safety and operational efficiency,
- the operation of ship recycling facilities in a safe and environmentally sound manner, and
- the establishment of an appropriate enforcement mechanism for ship recycling, which includes certification and reporting requirements.

The different stakeholders in the current scrapping process have several interests for the development of a new Convention, in order to make the ship scrapping more transparent and find a common regulation of the responsibilities of the parties in the shipping and recycling industry. Furthermore, it has to be kept in mind that the implementation of a too tough convention might cause that current ship scrapping countries might not ratify the Convention, which could reduce the effectiveness of the new convention significantly.

It is essential that a “level playing field” will be established internationally for all stakeholders in the ship scrapping industry in order to assure a fair and functioning ship recycling industry. The standards generally applied should generate a change in the safety, health and environmental relevant scrapping practises. The IMO, the specialised agency of the United Nations dealing with maritime affairs, is considered to have the best possibility to implement such a regulation with currently 167 Member States and three associated Members.

The IMO is currently developing a new Convention with the draft title “International Convention for the Safe and Environmentally Sound Recycling of Ships”. This Convention is expected to have a massive impact on the ship recycling industry and all stakeholders involved.

The Convention will be applicable to all ships of 500 Gross Tonnes [GT] or above, excluding warships, naval auxiliary ships or ships used for governmental non-commercial services. These ship types are always excluded from IMO legislations.

One of the aims of the IMO Convention is to have an effect on the complete life-span of the ship. In the end only certified ships will be allowed to enter appropriately certified recycling facilities.

One of the requirements is that besides the establishment of the Part I of the Inventory, the Parts II & III of the Inventory, the Gas-free-for-hot-work Certificate, the Ship Recycling Plan and the International Ready for Recycling Certificate (IRRC) have to be prepared prior to any recycling activity. All of these documents are linked with each other. Compliance with all those requirements will be controlled by a survey, certification and reporting system.

3. The requirements of the IMO Convention

Detailed information about built-in components will be required in future for all ships. The basis of this information will be the so-called “Single List”. The Single List is a catalogue of materials which are considered potentially hazardous, and which could be contained in a component or in the ships’ structure itself.

The Inventory is a “blueprint” of hazardous materials on board a ship. Its objective is to identify, locate and estimate the presence of the hazardous material on board. The Inventory, also known as “Green Passport” by the industry, is subdivided into three parts as seen in Table 1, all parts are focusing on different aspects and are to be applied at different stages of the ships’ life cycle..

Table 1: The Inventory – Data Demand (acc. to (MEPC.55/3/1))

Category Tables (Single List)	Part I	Part II	Part III
	Structure & Equipment	Garbage	Stores
A. Prohibited / Restricted Hazardous Substances	X		
B. Chemical Substances	(X)		
C: Potentially Hazardous Goods		X	X
D: Regular Consumable Goods			X

Differences in the focus of the Part I of the Inventory are to be made for new-buildings and existing ships. The development of the Part I of the Inventory for new-buildings is in the responsibility of the shipyard and substances listed category tables A and B are to be applied. This is achieved by a standard procedure relying on the data of the “Material Declaration Form” and the “Supplier’s

Declaration of Conformity”¹. For existing ships preparation is under the responsibility of the ship owner/operator and only substances listed category-table A are to be investigated by experts onboard. The correctness of the Part I of the Inventory is reflected by the Flag State or the Recognised Organisation with the issuance of a Certificate. Obviously, the Part I of the Inventory needs to be updated and maintained during the operational life of the ship.

Operational relevant goods like lubricating oil, anti-seize compounds or grease, which are applied to keep normal performance of gear and equipment and machinery, are out of scope of the provision.² The sources and kind of information may vary between new and existing ships, as described in the following two chapters.

3.1. Part I for New Ships

The source of information for materials and equipment onboard new ships are the suppliers and manufacturers, delivering data on request of the building yards which will be responsible for the preparation of the Inventories for new-buildings. Substances of concern are listed in table A and table B of Annex 1 to the guideline. However, obtaining the required information should be done prior to or during construction phase. The ship yards have to “reference” the information received from the suppliers to the location and/or system of the related item onboard. For reduction of manpower and keeping the data manageable a linking-tool between data of materials and the shipyards software assembly-system has to be created. Such an inventory software tool on top of the yards assembly-system should generate a ship specific Inventory automatically.

Data Collection for New Vessels requires from manufacturer and suppliers to provide Material Declaration Forms / Declaration of Conformity.

3.2. Part I for Existing Ships

Existing ships have to comply “as far as practicable”, but repairs and conversions have to follow instructions as set out for new vessels. Procedures for collection of data are proposed in the submission to MEPC 55 prepared by Germany, and Japan. Gaining data of materials contained in existing ships can include Analyses Results, General Assumptions, Manuals, technical Documentation, Manufacturer / Supplier Material Declaration Forms or Declaration of Conformity and be extended up to taking and analyzing samples for the preparation of the inventory.

3.3. Parts II & III of the Inventory

After the decision of the ship owner to recycle his ship is taken, he has to choose an appropriate certified recycling facility which is capable of handling the listed hazardous materials. Therefore, additionally to the Part I of the Inventory, the Part II (Operationally Generated Wastes) and Part III (Stores) have to be prepared. The scope of the Inventory of Part II and III shall include the hazardous materials and items as listed in category tables C and D. These parts are to be prepared under the responsibility of the ship owner prior to the last voyage to the Ship Recycling Facility.

3.4. The Ship Recycling Plan

Ships destined to be recycled shall provide to the recycling facility all available information relating to the ship for the development of the Ship Recycling Plan required. Guidelines on the development of a Ship Recycling Plan regarding the recommendations of the IMO Resolution A.923 (23) have been established by the IMO and shall be taken into account.³

1 cf. MEPC 55/3/1, submitted by Japan & Germany, 07.07.2006

2 cf. MEPC 55/3/5, submitted by Germany, 10.08.2006

3 cf. MEPC Circ 419, 12.11.2004

A Ship Recycling Plan must be developed by the recycling facility prior to any recycling of a ship can take place, taking into account the guidelines developed by the Organization. The Ship Recycling Plan shall be developed in consultation with the ship owner in the language accepted by the Party authorizing the ship recycling facility. The Ship Recycling Plan includes, inter alia, prior material removal in accordance with the capability of the recycling facility to manage the type or amount of materials. The Ship Recycling Plan shall be available for inspection by officers of the Administration responsible for surveying the ship, or the entrusted surveyors, or to organizations recognized by the Administration.

3.5. The gas-free-for-hot-work Certificate

Ship recycling facilities authorized by a Party shall establish and utilize procedures to prevent explosions by establishing procedures for ensuring “gas-free-for-hot-work” conditions as appropriate⁴ throughout the ship recycling process in order to elevate the workers health and safety standards.

4. The Control System

The control of the Implementation of the new IMO Convention is done in accordance with a surveying and certification system. An overview of this system is shown in . All the surveys and certification processes are at least partly relying on the information being required under the IMO convention.

Fig.1: The surveying and certification system

For all ships, there will be an initial survey by the Flag State / RO in order to verify the correct

4 cf. MEPC 55/3/12, submitted by India, 17.08.2006, the Gas-Free-for-Hot-Work Certificate needs to be performed for all tanks and cofferdams potentially containing flammable vapours. Excepted are the fuel oil tanks and sludge tanks in machinery spaces which are needed for the final voyage.

implementation of the Part I of the Inventory. For new-buildings, the part I of the Inventory has to be prepared and certified during the design and construction phase of the vessel whereas for existing ships it has to be prepared and certified during operation of the ship..

During the operational life cycle of the ship, periodical surveys are conducted to control and confirm the continuous updating of the IHM. Additional surveys are required in order to confirm updating of the Inventory during major conversions or repairs. Additionally, the Port State Control Regime can control the possession, correctness and the conformity of the Part I of the Inventory.

During the preparation for recycling, a Final Survey prior to the ship being taken out of service and before the recycling of the ship can be started has to be completed. Besides the IHM it has to be verified that the Ship Recycling Plan is developed by the authorized ship recycling facility. The Administration issues the International Ready for Recycling Certificate (IRRC) thereafter which allows the recycling facility to start its work after the completion of the reporting system.

5. Data Management

For any vessel a huge amount of information has to be collected and maintained, up to a couple of decades, which makes a software tool designed for these purposes indispensable. The Inventory itself has to be in a format appropriate for shipboard maintenance. Here data adoption to shipboard replacements including deactivation of non actual data due to maintenance and change of materials will be focal points. After the operational life of the vessel the computer systems will have changed and later availability and accessibility of data has to be assured. At the last stage the ship recycler has to be able to use the data collected and maintained for a long period of time.

Data will have to be handled at different stages and the tool has to be adaptable to the specific needs and processes.

Correctness of information is of utmost importance, especially for data gained by onboard inspections for existing ships. Therefore it is GL's strategy to involve experts with sufficient knowledge to avoid possible liability problems.

Due to the different backgrounds and intentions of users, various approaches to the data sets need to be possible. Therefore the data is stored in a highly flexible data model with the information being inserted only once, but various relations are added. The software tool is web-based to provide access to users anytime and anywhere.

The developed data model considers STEP⁵ to provide a uniform standard. Due to the fact that, according to IMO, hazardous material information has to be attached to locations. Therefore, it is crucial that the user is able to find every desired location as easy as possible. Thus the data model is layered and structured to build a hierarchic navigation tree for convenient usage. The navigation tree consists of two layers. The first layer contains zones. It is considered to subdivide the modelled vessels into zones in longitudinal directing to guide the user. This subdividing should be logical, for example dividing the ship from its bulkheads into zones comparable to sections as used in building stage, or in functional areas e.g. machinery zone, cargo space, superstructure, fore peak, etc. The second layer consists of compartments, which can be attached to zones as a sub-location by a reference. Compartments are considered as rooms and labelled by their functional names as given by the general arrangement plan, e.g. "Main engine room". This provides the basis for a location related inventory, furthermore clear room identification throughout the ship's lifetime is promoted. They are the last leaf of the navigation tree and thus a compartment cannot have another zone or compartment

⁵ STEP, the **S**tandard for the **E**xchange of **P**roduct **M**odel **D**ata, is a comprehensive ISO standard (ISO 10303) that describes how to represent and exchange digital product information.

Source: <http://www.steptools.com/library/standard/>

attached, only installed parts and systems. Zones may have installed parts and systems attached as well. Installed Parts are equipment and machinery, such as main engine, auxiliary engine, cranes and winches, which could be combined to installed systems. Hazardous material information can be attached to zones, compartments, installed parts or systems by a reference. All references between zones and compartments as well as between compartments and installed parts may be labelled to give the referenced object additional information which will detail e.g. the position of the object, like deck 1, floor, ceiling, etc. or hazardous material information. Fig.3 illustrates the navigation tree at an example showing zones (blue boxes) with sub-located compartments (green boxes) and attached installed parts (orange boxes).

Fig.3: Navigation tree of data model

Compartments are independent objects which can be referenced in various ways. As shown above in Fig.3, the zone “Machinery Zone” references the compartments “Main engine room” and “Auxiliary engine room”. The references are labelled with the decks where those rooms are located. Both rooms have attached hazardous material information, as shown in the red boxes in the figure. The references from the compartments to the hazardous material information specify the location of the material. “Unspecified” means that the whole room is contaminated or the exact source of contamination is unknown, “Ceiling” means the ceiling of the compartment is contaminated, for instance as a part of a fire protection zone. The user can also add additional information about the materials’ application, e.g. paint, coating, insulation.

The user has also the opportunity to add any file to the software tool as an attachment, such as drawings, manuals, photos, and reports of sampling analyses or Material Safety Data Sheets (MSDS). Especially the drawings, such as the general arrangement plan, provide overviews and this can be used for showing e.g. the clustering of the ship into zones, as illustrated by Fig.4. Furthermore, a hyperlink function could be used to connect plan and the data model, as it shown in the centre of Fig.4. Reversely, hazardous materials could be marked in such a plan, therefore these plans could be later used as a basis for the development of the recycling plan, as requested by the future IMO convention on ship recycling.

The user interface in Fig.5 shows an example for compartments, which have hazardous materials attached to as well as installed parts, which also contain hazardous material information.

Fig.4: General arrangement plan subdivided into different zones and with hyperlink

The screenshot shows a software interface with a tree view on the left and a detailed view on the right. The tree view shows a hierarchy of parts and materials, including 'Machinery Zone', 'Auxiliary engine room', 'Main engine room', and 'Exhaust Pipes'. The detailed view shows the 'Diesel Engine 8V 396 TC 62' part, with fields for ID, Description, Last changed, File number, Manufacturer, and Approval reference number. Below this is a table of parameter sets and a table of historic parameter sets.

Parameter sets	Assembly	Material	Hazardous materials	Functional Units	Where used list	Data sets	Manufacturer	Attachment
<input type="checkbox"/>	Default		Planning			09.11.2006 10:58:23 [pk]		

Parameter Set	Status	Valid from	Valid to	Changed on
No Items found				

Fig.5: Screen shoot

An Inventory of Hazardous Materials according to IMO could be generated by the software tool automatically. The list shows all hazardous material information with the location, installed parts and the appearance of the material herein, and approximated quantity.

Table 2 shows an example.

Table 2: Inventory of Hazardous Materials

No.	Name of Equipment and Machinery	Specified Chemical Substances (Classification in the Single List)	Parts of Use	Appx. Quantity	Location	Remarks
1	Exhaust Pipes	Asbestos	Rock wool	0	Main engine room	Assumed:
		Asbestos	Cover of isolation	0	Main engine room, Main engine room	Assumed:
		Asbestos	Yarn	0	Main engine room	Assumed:
2	Main engine 1: 8V 396 TC 62	Asbestos	Head gasket	0	Main engine room	Assumed:
3	Main engine 2: 8V 396 TC 62	Asbestos	Head gasket	0	Main engine room	Assumed:
4	Main engine 3: 8V 396 TC 62	Asbestos	Head gasket	0	Main engine room	Assumed:
5	Auxiliary engine: Happy virtual people auxiliary engine	4,4'-methylene dianiline	Insulation	0	Auxiliary engine room	Based on supplier data
		LD39	Lubricant	15 l	Auxiliary engine room	Based on supplier data
		Asbestos	Insulation	0	Auxiliary engine room	Based on supplier data

6. Conclusion

A well structured software tool for collection and handling of data at planning / construction phase at the ship yard as well as during ship operation has been developed to allow handling of detailed information in various ways. An adoptable software tool is a key element and prerequisite for:

- fulfilment of the future requirements on Ship Recycling,
- exchange between different stakeholders, and parties concerned
- manageability of data
- compatibility of data
- keeping costs at a moderate level
- successful shipboard application.

In respect to the above criteria, this complex system has to assure ease of use and processing of data to reach a high level of data traceability and flexibility. It is essential to allow user specific views on stored data according to the intended use, e.g. sorted by:

- shipboard system
- component
- shipboard location
- material
- protective information

To achieve these goals, the following requirements must be fulfilled throughout the whole “data management chain”:

- Standardised Data format
 - o Exchange between manufacturers, suppliers, yards, and owners / operators
 - o linked with Assembly Group System of yard
 (semi-) automatic Preparation of Inventory
- Shipboard System
 - o continuously update-able
 linked to Maintenance-Programme (option)
- Value for Recyclers
 - o Exact information on Hazardous Material
 - o Utilisation for Occupational Safety & Environmental Protection measures
- Data Security (min. 30 years)

A Semi-Autonomous Towed System for Underwater Pipeline Survey

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Abstract

This paper reports the developing efforts and initial experimental tests of a towed semi-autonomous system for automatic tracking of underwater pipelines. The paper is in particular focused on the modeling of the coupled cable-vehicle system, and on the testing of a new guidance system based on the differential magnetometer which is the output measurement in the feedback loop.

1. Introduction

Underwater pipeline and cable survey is a time-consuming, expensive and demanding task. Nowadays commercial companies perform the task with a Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV), linked to a surface ship through an umbilical cable, and carrying some payload sensors as the inspection task may require (e.g., camera, imaging sonar, magnetometer, etc.). The ROVs are generally driven by a two people team, one to keep the vehicle along the pipeline track, the other to monitor the payload sensor data. The task is very demanding for the team members and so a team shift is needed after no more than four hours, because the usual lack of variability in the inspection data (sonar/video images etc.) makes it difficult to maintain the proper concentration and level of attention, exposing the task itself to human errors. Given the reasons above, there is a considerable effort in oceanic engineering toward the investigation of devices and techniques that may lead to a partial or possibly complete automation of the survey task.

Several approaches have been explored, from the ambitious goal of employing Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) for detecting and following the pipeline, in a totally autonomous mode, *Acosta et al. (2005)* and *Evans et al. (2003)*, to the use of visual feedback to enhance the ROV steering and mitigate the potential damage due to decrease of attention of the pilots *Conte et al. (2004)* and *Zanoli et al (2001)*.

This paper reports the progress of a project directed toward the realization of a towed vehicle able to maintain itself centred over the pipeline at a specified altitude, while the towing ship follows the nominal pipeline route. The towed vehicle is equipped with navigation sensors (inclinometer, compass), pipeline following sensors (two magnetometers installed in differential configuration) and both depth (pressure) and altitude (echo sounder) sensors. Autonomous vehicle steering is accomplished through control surfaces and rudder orientation. The availability of such a system will eliminate the need of steering, allowing the operator team to concentrate on the inspection data only. Moreover, a towed system allows to increase the velocity of the surface ship with respect to ROV inspection, contributing to the reduction of the overall survey time. Additional requirements for such a system are ease of transportation and operation, to allow it to be installed also on small work boat, and low cost.

The project is a joint effort between the Dept. of Mechanical Engineering of the University of Genova – DIMEC – and ISME, the Italian Interuniversity Ctr. of Integrated Systems for the Marine Environment. In particular, DIMEC has the responsibility of the mechanical and hydrodynamic design, while ISME is in charge of the tracking and control system.

Towed underwater systems with autonomous or semi-autonomous navigation capabilities are not common, either as commercial products or research prototypes. One notable exception is the Triaxus

system, www.triaxus.com, which however has been designed as a general-purpose payload carrier for oceanographic measurements in the water column. The different application field has led to a very different system with respect to the one investigated in this paper, with consequent differences in the dynamic and control issues addressed. The dynamic behaviour of towed underwater bodies has quite peculiar characteristics and it has been studied in detail for passive systems, see *Vannahme and Clauss. (2002)* and references therein, or with the goal of positioning the towed system with respect to the towing ship *Campa et al. (1998)*.

In this paper a general description of the system and its main characteristics are reported. The non linear dynamic model of the vehicle has been developed following the standard treatment described - for instance - in *Fossen (1994)*, while the towing cable has been modelled by the spatial discretization of the cable into finite linear segments, using the lumped mass approach *Buckham et al. (2003)*. A preliminary test on land of the pipeline sensing apparatus has been carried out. On the basis of both, the previous numerical models and the results of the tests, an automatic guidance system has been developed using, in the feedback loop, the measurements coming from the differential magnetometers. Data of the preliminary test are reported together with simulation results of the whole system.

2. The system

The final design of the towed system consists in a torpedo-shaped body with six fins, Fig.1. The three bow fins are independently actuated; the two lateral stern fins are jointly actuated. As a result, the towed system has five degrees of freedom. Propulsion is accomplished through the towing cable. Transversal to the system bow (dark in Fig.1) there is a cylinder cap on which two magnetometers are installed, to provide data on the pipeline position with respect to the surge axis of the vehicle. A similar cylinder is placed at the stern of system, to provide additional information on the pipe line position. The vehicle has an approximate length of 1.4 m, and an internal diameter of 0.25 m, it has the space for a payload, plus a suite of internal sensors for navigation: inclinometer, compass, echosounder and depth sensors. The towing cable is the carrier of the power to the vehicle, and also of the communication to and from the vehicle.

The guidance system, based on PID controllers, has the goal of keeping the vehicle centered over the inspected pipeline, at a fixed altitude, maintaining the vehicle surge axis parallel to the pipeline.

Both the depth and the steering controllers have been synthesized separately considering the motion on the vertical plane and on the horizontal plane respectively, and tuned in order to allow the vehicle to translate, in line with the pipeline axis, by small pitch and yaw angles. The magnetic sensors provide the feedback signal for the steering controller and allows tracking even if the pipeline is partially buried.

The differential magnetometers measurement is proportional to the point wise asymmetry due to the misalignment between the pipeline and the sensor. Having two such systems at the bow and stern of the vehicle, assuming a flat seabed, with stable pitch and roll, it is possible to derive the error in vehicle orientation with respect to the pipeline and the error in the surge-sway plane between the vehicle center of mass and the pipeline position. Maintaining to zero both errors allows the payload to be always positioned vertically above the pipelines. Of course, being it a towed system, the control objective can be met only if the towing ship has approximately the same route of the pipeline, above the pipeline. So the control system is intended to compensate for small deviations (up to some meters), from the equilibrium position. In order to allow the towing ship to maintain the desired route, the data from the vehicle (orientation, etc.), transmitted through the towing cable, are also displayed on board of the towing ship, to allow the ship master to correct to gross deviations from the desired route.

The set points (in particular altitude set point), as well as additional high-level commands, can be programmed and downloaded through the surface interface of the system, to allow for operator

intervention in case of malfunctioning or other needs.

Fig.1: CAD drawing of the designed vehicle (courtesy of DIMEC). The dark cylinders, one in front and one at the rear of the vehicle, are the differential magnetometers employed for pipeline tracking.

3. Dynamic system modelling

The dynamic model of the system has been developed by separately modeling the towed vehicle, the towing cable and the towing ship and then joining the three models. As for the cable, a lumped parameters dynamic model has been developed following the approach proposed by *Buckham et al. (2003)*, *Perrault et al. (1997)*, *Vaz and Patel (1995)*; the standard treatment for autonomous underwater vehicle, *Fossen (1994)*, *Prestero (2001)*, has been considered to model the towed vehicle; as far as the towing ship is concerned, a simple kinematic model has been considered.

3.1. Cable model

A body reference system (X_b, Y_b, Z_b) , is fixed on the surface vessel, being X_b the ship surge direction; it is assumed that the ship is moving at constant velocity v_b , directed along X_b . Through this assumption, the ship reference system is an inertial reference system, and the velocity v_b becomes a parameter of the model. The cable is divided into n equal length elastic elements, and the mass of each element is lumped at the nodes at both ends of the element. Internal and external forces are applied to every node except the top one, whose motion is prescribed by the towing ship. The motion of each node can be evaluated separately, on the basis of the lumped mass approximation; while the elastic internal force allows to satisfy the geometric compatibility equations by constraining this motion. Applying Newton's Second Law for the i -th node of the cable we obtain:

$$\ddot{r}_i = M_i^{-1} \left[(T_{i+1} + P_{i+1}) - (T_i + P_i) + \frac{1}{2}(D_i + D_{i+1} + W_i + W_{i+1}) - \frac{1}{2}(B_i + B_{i+1}) \right] \quad (1)$$

T_i is the internal force generated by the cable's elastic behaviour of the i -th element, P_i is the internal damping in the element i , D_i is the drag force acting on the element i while B_i and W_i are the buoyancy and the weight of the element respectively. M_i is the inertial matrix and r_i the position of the i -th node. All the previous quantities are referred to the inertial reference frame. This method allows to easily join the models of the towing ship, the cable and the towed vehicle simply defining the motion at the ends of the cable by the dynamics of the two vehicles. For further details about the cable model see *Buckham et al. (2003)*.

3.2. Vehicle model

The towed vehicle is described by modeling it as an autonomous vehicle. *Prestero (2001)* described the three-dimensional equations of motion for an hydrodynamic torpedo-shaped underwater vehicle using a suitable body-fixed coordinate frame, located at the center of buoyancy of the vehicle itself.

The motion of the body-fixed frame of reference is described relative to an inertial reference frame. The body-fixed frame has six velocity components, $v = [u, v, w, p, q, r]$, while the six components of position, in the global reference frame, are $\eta = [\eta_1, \eta_2] = [x, y, z, \phi, \theta, \psi]$. Control inputs are related to the orientation of the control surfaces, no thrusters are present, being the propulsion accomplished through the towing cable, so the inputs vector is $u = [\delta_r \ \delta_s \ \delta_b \ \delta_{bs} \ \delta_{bp}]$ in which the first two components correspond to the rudder and stern plane deflection, and the last three correspond to the rudder, port and starboard bow plane.

The generalized torque acting on the vehicle, in the body fixed reference frame is $\tau = \tau_v + \tau_c$, where τ_c is the towing force provided through the cable, while $\tau_v = [X \ Y \ Z \ K \ M \ N]$ includes coriolis, gravitational and centrifugal terms, hydrostatic and hydrodynamics forces and moment.

The motion of the towed vehicle is described by a system of nonlinear equations as a function of the vehicle generalized coordinates η :

$$M_v(\eta)\dot{\eta} + B_v(\eta, \dot{\eta}) + D_v(\eta, \dot{\eta}) + G_v(\eta) = \tau_v + \tau_c \quad (2)$$

The inertia matrix $M_v(\eta)$ includes both mechanical and hydrodynamic added masses. Starting from the previous equation, two simplified linear models are derived in order to synthesize the control system, as described in section 5.

Fig.2: On the left: the three systems of reference and the model of the finite elements model of the cable. On the right: towfish-fixed and inertial coordinate systems.

4. Pipeline detection and differential magnetometer data

A critical point in the system, in order to properly track the pipeline, is the method employed to detect and follow the pipeline itself. In subsection 4.1 a detection method, based on the measuring of the geomagnetic gradient around an iron pipeline is reported, and the theoretical results compared to the magnetic field measured over a buried sewage pipeline. In subsection 4.2 the performance of the pipeline sensing system is investigated considering the interference of the towfish motors.

4.1. Pipeline detection method

Let us consider the presence of a magnetic induction field B in a region of empty space. If a permeable magnetic body is placed in the region, the intensity of the magnetic induction is modified and the field lines tend to become normal to the surface of the body. Let us consider an infinitely long cylindrical pipeline with internal radius a and external radius b and magnetic permeability μ . Let us consider a NED reference frame, being x -axis along the axis of the pipeline, and let us suppose the

external field $\vec{B}_0 = B_0 \hat{y}$. We aim to find the magnetic field H and the induction field B everywhere in space, most particularly outside of the pipeline. Considering the absence of currents, the magnetic field H is derivable from a scalar potential Φ : $\vec{H} = -\nabla\Phi(r, \theta)$. Moreover $\vec{B} = \mu\vec{H}$, so the divergence equation $\nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0$ becomes $\nabla \cdot \vec{H} = 0$ in the various regions. This way the potential Φ satisfies the Laplace equation $\nabla^2\Phi = 0$ everywhere: outside and inside the pipeline and at the pipeline itself.

We are interested in finding the expression of the magnetic field H , outside the pipeline. By solving the Laplace equation, in cylindrical coordinate, we obtain the expression of the potential Φ :

$$\Phi_{ext}(r, \theta) = \frac{B_0}{\mu_0} \left[\frac{K}{r} - r \right] \cos \theta \quad (3)$$

$$K = \frac{b^2 (\mu^2 - \mu_0^2) (a^2 - b^2)}{a^2 (\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2 (\mu + \mu_0)^2}$$

K is a function of the pipeline's geometrical properties and of the material of which the pipeline is made, μ_0 is the magnetic permeability of the vacuum. Further details about the solution of Laplace equation are reported in appendix A.

To confirm the theoretical results and verify the functioning of the sensors, a field test has been performed on land over a known buried sewage pipeline of dimensions similar to those expected by pipelines at sea, but with thinner walls. In particular, the land test pipeline has a diameter of 0.8 m and a thickness of 0.003 m, buried at a depth of 0.7 m in clayey soil. The pipeline material has a relative magnetic permeability estimated above 4000. The intensity of the magnetic field has been measured sampling the magnetic field on a vertical section normal to the pipeline axis, with extension of 6 m in the horizontal direction and 1.6 m in the vertical direction respectively. Sampling distance has been of 0.2 m in the horizontal, and 0.4 m in the vertical. Fig.3 shows the resulting magnetic field intensity (reconstructed from the samples with multiquadrics interpolation), compared to the theoretical one obtained from Eq.(2) by using the parameters of the testing pipeline. From the available data, it can be seen that the local maximum intensity of the magnetic induction field is not in correspondence of the vertical over the pipeline, but it depends on the mutual orientation of the local geomagnetic field with respect to the pipeline. This is accounted for using the International Geomagnetic Reference Field *IAGA (2006)* together with the Eq.(2): in particular, the vertical component of the geomagnetic field can have an inclination between 45° and 60° with respect to the Earth surface, in the Mediterranean sea, so that, the maximum deviation from the normal to the pipeline axis is about 30° - 45°. This kind of behavior has been taken in to account to synthesize the system of guidance.

4.2 Analysis of the gradiometer performance

A second indoor test has been performed in order to assess the influence of the motors on the differential magnetometers. The differential system has been placed at an horizontal distance varying from 0.2 to 1.4 m from a brushless motor of nominal power of 12 W (12 V, 1 A). The two magnetometers are symmetrically placed with respect to the motor, as in the vehicle design.

The power to the motor has been varied during the test, in order to simulate transients behavior. Irrespectively from the distance, the perturbation of the motor to the single magnetic field measurement can be quantized in an offset of approximately 1400 nT. As far as the differential measurement is concerned, however, the measured gradient average is not affected – what is affected is the standard deviation of the measurement. In particular, in the case of 0.2 m distance (the worst case, and also the effective case for the stern unit), the gradient standard deviation with the motor off is 20 nT/m, while with motor on is 130 nT/m - one order of magnitude more.

Such a high standard deviation in the measurements cannot be tolerated, since it would completely mask the measurement in operational conditions. For this reason, filtering of the measurement signal has been investigated, and it turns out that a simple moving average algorithm can greatly reduce the measurement standard deviation and improve the signal to noise ratio (SNR). In the implementation of the moving average filter, the magnetometers have been sampled at 15 Hz sampling frequency, and a window of 10 samples has been considered for the average.

Fig.3: On the left: experimentally measured magnetic field intensity over a sewage pipeline (bottom of the figure). The drawing is in scale with the pipeline photograph. On the right: theoretical magnetic field induction considering the parameters of the testing pipeline and external vertical field of 44 μT .

The standard deviation measured with motor on after application of the moving average filter is 34 nT/m, with a SNR improvement estimated in 23 dB. Longer windows can further increase the SNR and reduce the measurement standard deviation. However, the moving average filter on the output measurement implies a low pass filter in the overall control loop: this means that it slows down the transient response of the controlled system, the more so the longer the averaging window. A compromise between SNR in the measurement and requirements on the transient behavior of the controlled system will be determined at the stage of synthesizing and implementing the control law. On the basis of the previous tests, the applicability region of the sensor has been computed considering a detection threshold of 67nT (ten times less than the actual sensitivity of the sensor); in Fig.4 the magnetometer sensitivity region is reported. The useful region is a rectangle of 8m height and 10m width, centered over the pipeline.

Fig.4: Sensor Sensitivity Region: in black the practical region; in light grey the boundary of the region in which the horizontal gradient is higher than the detection threshold (67nT).

5. Control System

The control system is based on two PID controllers, one for the vertical plain is meant to maintain the vehicle at a specified depth (or altitude with respect to the sea-bottom) and the other to track the pipeline on the basis of the measurements coming from the differential magnetometers.

The vehicle altitude and pitch are controlled through the horizontal surfaces placed at stern and bow. Even though the two bow surfaces are independent, they are jointly controlled, and the control action is the opposite of the one applied at the stern surface. A simple inner-and-outer (pitch-and-depth) loop PID depth controller is tuned on the basis of a decoupled linearized model, obtained from equation NL, considering the steady state condition (nominal surge velocity of 2 knots and values of the attitude angles equal to zero). As shown in Fig.5, the pitch angle, in the inner loop, is controlled through a PID, while in the outer loop, the depth controller has the proportional term only.

The control law for the inner loop can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\delta_s(s)}{e_\theta(s)} = -P_\theta \left(1 + \tau_d s + \frac{1}{\tau_i s} \right), \quad \delta_{bp/bp} = -\delta_s \quad (4)$$

$e_\theta = \theta_d - \theta$ is the difference between the desired pitch angle and the actual pitch of the vehicle, P_θ is the proportional gain and τ_d, τ_i the derivative and the integral time constant respectively.

The control law for the outer loop can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\theta(s)}{e_z(s)} = P_z \quad (5)$$

$e_z = z_d - z$ is the difference between the desired depth and the actual depth of the towfish, and P_z is the proportional gain.

Fig.5: Depth and Pitch control system block diagram

A second-order response was assumed for the system and the controller parameters tuned in order to have a settling time of 10s and maximum overshoot of 5%. Table I gives the values of the parameters.

Table I: Parameters of the pitch-depth controller

P_θ	τ_d	τ_i	P_z
2.3	0.3	1.75	2

As for the steering controller, an analogue procedure has been followed. The vehicle yaw and horizontal position with respect to the pipeline are controlled through the joined action of the two vertical rudders, placed underneath the vehicle at bow and stern. A PD controller is used in the inner loop to control the yaw angle, while, in the outer loop, a term proportional to the gradient of the magnet induction field provides the yaw reference to the inner loop.

The control law for the steering control can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\delta_r(s)}{e_\psi(s)} = -P_\psi(1 + T_d s), \quad \delta_b = -\delta_r \quad (6)$$

$e_\psi = \psi_d - \psi$ is the difference between the desired yaw angle and the actual yaw angle of the towfish, P_ψ is the proportional gain and T_d the derivative time constant.

The control law for the outer loop can be expressed as:

$$\psi = P_m(\Delta B - \Gamma) \quad (7)$$

P_m is the proportional gain, Γ is a correction term which takes in to account the relative orientation between the pipeline axis and the vertical direction of the geomagnetic field, as discussed in subsection 4.1, while

$$\Delta B = |B_{left}| - |B_{right}| \quad (8)$$

is the difference between the magnitude of the magnetic induction field measured by the left magnetometer and the right one respectively.

The steering controller has been tuned in order to have a settling time of 10s and a damping factor of 0.95; the values of the parameters are reported in Table II.

Table II: Parameters of the steering controller

P_ψ	T_d	P_m
20	0.5	12.000

The minus sign applied to the proportional gain of the pitch and yaw control laws is due to the difference in sign conventions between the stern plane angle and vehicle pitch angle, and between the rudder angle and vehicle yaw angle. A positive stern angle will force the vehicle to pitch down, generating a negative moment around the y-axis.

The wide range of maneuver around the steady state position allows to compute the length of the cable deployed as a function of both the speed of the towing ship and the pipeline depth, without considering it as a control variable.

6. System simulation

This section reports an example of the pipeline docking maneuver. In the simulation an underwater pipeline, placed at 148 m depth, having the same properties of the one described in the above section, has been considered. The towing ship, perfectly aligned to the pipeline axis, has a constant surge velocity of 1.8 m/s. The towfish, initially aligned to the pipeline, starts from the steady state condition (142 m depth): previously reached with a 300 m long towing cable. During the first part of the simulation the vehicle is manually driven by the operator in order to acquire a raw measurement of the

magnetic field around the pipeline, while the depth controller has to keep the vehicle at constant depth. The path followed by the vehicle is shown on the left in figure 6: while, on the right, the noisy measurements of the gradient are reported in grey, and the filtered values in black. A noise power of 130 nT/m has been considered. The gradient sign indicates whether the towfish is on the left side (negative gradient) or the right side (positive gradient) with respect to the pipeline. Once a preliminary measure of the magnetic field is available, the vehicle is brought into the applicability region of the sensor and the steering control system is activated (at the time $t=60$) allowing the towfish to autonomously follow the pipeline. During the automatic approaching maneuver the vehicle has been requested to reach a new depth reference of 145 m. The vertical position of the towfish with respect to the pipeline is shown in Fig.7, together with the orientation of the control surfaces. As reported in Figs.6 and 7, during the docking maneuver, the vehicle attitude angles are, in general, less than 10° and the towfish correctly reaches the pipeline moving in line with its axis.

Fig.6: On the left: lateral position of the towfish during the docking maneuver, in the first part of the simulation (light grey) the vehicle is manually driven while the depth controller maintains constant depth. On the right: measurements of the gradient (raw measurements in grey, filtered data in black).

Fig.7: Left: vertical position of the towfish with respect to the pipeline. Center: deflection angles of the control surfaces (δ_x and δ_y). Right: attitude angles of the towfish during the docking maneuver.

7. Conclusions and future plans

Current advances and developments toward the realization of a prototypal system for semi-autonomous inspection of underwater pipelines have been reported. In particular, the paper has focused on the dynamic model of the towed system, and to the preliminary tests of the magnetometer system that is to provide the crucial data to the pipeline tracking feed-back loop. A PID based control system has been developed, and the performance during the approaching maneuver reported considering noisy data coming from the magnetic sensors. In February 2007, the vehicle construction was completed and experimental tests expected to start by the end of the month.

Appendix A - Magnetic field computation

Consider the problem of finding the fields H and B in a region of space where a constant magnetic induction field is applied to an infinitely long cylinder with internal radius a , external radius b and magnetic permeability μ . The external field is directed along the y , normal to the cylinder axis, Fig 8.

Fig.8: Magnetostatic problem: Constant magnetic field applied to an infinitely long cylinder

In static condition, and in absence of currents, the magnetic field H is derivable from a scalar potential $\vec{H} = -\nabla\Phi(r, \theta)$ and, from the equation of the divergence, the potential Φ has to satisfy the Laplace equation $\nabla^2\Phi = 0$ everywhere: outside and inside the pipeline and at the pipeline itself.

Considering the Laplace's equation in cylindrical coordinates, with no x -dependence:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \Phi(r, \theta) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \Phi(r, \theta) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \Phi(r, \theta) = 0 \quad (9)$$

by applying the separation of variables method the solution is written as a product of functions:

$$\Phi(r, \theta) = R(r) \cdot \Theta(\theta) \quad (10)$$

$\Theta(\theta)$ is a function of the θ only and satisfies the following ordinary differential equation (ODE):

$$\Theta''(\theta) + \lambda\Theta(\theta) = 0 \quad (11)$$

whose eigenfunctions are $\Theta(\theta) = A \sin(\theta\sqrt{\lambda}) + B \cos(\theta\sqrt{\lambda})$, where, considering θ as periodic of period 2π , we obtain $\lambda = n^2$ and n an integer number.

While in Eq.(10) $R(r)$ is a function of the r only and satisfies the following ODE:

$$r^2 R(r)'' + rR(r)' - n^2 R(r) = 0 \quad (12)$$

whose solutions are

$$\begin{cases} R(r) = C + D \ln(r) & n = 0 \\ R(r) = E_n r^n + F_n r^{-n} & n \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

Therefore, the general solution for the magnetic potential Φ is:

$$\Phi(r, \theta) = D \ln(r) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (E_n r^n + F_n r^{-n}) (A_n \sin(n\theta) + B_n \cos(n\theta)) \quad (13)$$

Since that solution must be finite as $r \rightarrow 0$, and outside the pipeline the solution must give the applied field as $r \rightarrow \infty$, and considering the external field directed along y and the symmetry of the problem, we obtain the follow expression for the magnetic potential in the different region: inside the pipeline, outside the pipeline and at the pipeline itself.

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_{int}(r, \theta) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^n \overline{B}_n \cos(n\theta) \\ \Phi_{ext}(r, \theta) &= -\frac{B_0}{\mu_0} \cos \theta + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{-n} \overline{D}_n \cos(n\theta) \\ \Phi_{pipe}(r, \theta) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (r^{-n} + \beta_n r^n) \overline{F}_n \cos(n\theta).\end{aligned}\tag{14}$$

Where $\overline{B}_n = B_n E_n$, $\overline{D}_n = B_n F_n$, $\overline{F}_n = B_n F_n$, $\beta_n = E_n / F_n$ and B_0 is the value of the external field.

At each boundary the normal component of the magnetic induction B , and the tangential component of the magnetic field H are continuous. Applying the boundary condition, Eqs.(14) yields:

- Boundary condition at the interface $r = b$:

$$-B_0 \cos \theta - \mu_0 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n b^{-n-1} \overline{D}_n \cos(n\theta) = \mu \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-n b^{-n-1} + n \beta_n b^{n-1}) \overline{F}_n \cos(n\theta)$$

$$\frac{B_0}{\mu_0} b \sin \theta - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n b^{-n} \overline{D}_n \sin(n\theta) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n (b^{-n} + \beta_n b^n) \overline{F}_n \sin(n\theta)$$

- Boundary condition at the interface $r = a$:

$$\mu_0 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n a^{n-1} \overline{B}_n \cos(n\theta) = \mu \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-n a^{-n-1} + n \beta_n a^{n-1}) \overline{F}_n \cos(n\theta)$$

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n a^n \overline{B}_n \sin(n\theta) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n (a^{-n} + \beta_n a^n) \overline{F}_n \sin(n\theta).$$

The external field imposes that $n=1$, so posing $n=1$ we obtain a four equations linear system which provides the values of the four unknowns \overline{B}_n , \overline{D}_n , \overline{F}_n , β_n :

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{B}_1 &= \frac{4\mu B_0 b^2}{a^2 (\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2 (\mu + \mu_0)^2}, & \overline{D}_1 &= (a^2 - b^2) \frac{B_0}{\mu_0} \frac{b^2 (\mu^2 - \mu_0^2)}{a^2 (\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2 (\mu + \mu_0)^2}, \\ \beta_1 &= a^{-2} \frac{\mu + \mu_0}{\mu - \mu_0}, & \overline{F}_1 &= \frac{2B_0 a^2 b^2 (\mu - \mu_0)}{a^2 (\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2 (\mu + \mu_0)^2},\end{aligned}$$

and so the expression of the scalar potential Φ in all the regions:

$$\Phi_{int}(r, \theta) = \frac{4\mu B_0 b^2}{a^2 (\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2 (\mu + \mu_0)^2} r \cos \theta,$$

$$\Phi_{ext}(r, \theta) = \frac{B_0}{\mu_0} \left[\frac{(a^2 - b^2)}{r} \frac{b^2(\mu^2 - \mu_0^2)}{a^2(\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2(\mu + \mu_0)^2} - r \right] \cos \theta,$$

$$\Phi_{pipe}(r, \theta) = B_0 \left(\frac{(\mu - \mu_0)}{r} + (\mu + \mu_0) \frac{r}{a^2} \right) \frac{2a^2b^2}{a^2(\mu - \mu_0)^2 - b^2(\mu + \mu_0)^2} \cos \theta$$

Applying the relation $\vec{H} = -\nabla\Phi(r, \theta)$ we obtain the components of the magnetic field H in cylindrical coordinates.

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CADET - IT Support for Joint Naval Shipbuilding Projects

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Abstract

The basic idea is to develop methods and tools dedicated to European cooperative naval (military) projects. The project proposal CADET, and its software tools in particular, shall support all decision steps recognized as contributing to the success of any naval cooperative project. They provide a common methodology, a common language, as well as the same structure of information for all partners (navies and shipbuilders).

1. Purpose

The basic idea behind the “CADET” project proposal is to develop methods and tools dedicated to European cooperative naval (military) projects. Partners would be provided with a complete road map of the project, from initial navies requirements to final building in the shipyards.

CADET tools are intended to support all decision steps which have been recognized as contributing to the success of an EC naval cooperative project. They provide a common methodology, a common language, as well as the same structure of information for all partners of a cooperative naval project (navies and shipbuilders).

2. History of EC naval cooperative projects

A short history of EC cooperative naval projects shows that there is some room for improvement, in particular it can be noted that:

- after the initial enthusiasm, bitter discussions follows;
- the duration of the definition phase of the common vessel is usually quite long (several years);
- large differences between navies requirements may limit the common design work to not much more than a common platform;
- having searched without success to build a common ship type, each navy may finally build a quite different ship;
- partners sometimes go away before the end of the project.

Fig.1: Horizon frigate

Fig.2: CVF aircraft carrier

Although insiders may judge the summary of Table I as caricatured or partly inaccurate, it provides useful cues on the difficulties encountered in those joint programs.

Table I: Recent history of joint naval projects involving European shipbuilders (from public sources)

Starting year	Ship type	Partners	Outcome
1979	NATO frigate	All NATO countries	Collapses for no agreement on common vessel.
1994	HORIZON frigate	UK, Italy, France	UK withdraws for no agreement on common vessel. Definition of the vessel lasts 9 years. One frigate costs approx. 1.3 Billion Euros. 20 frigates planned, but 4 frigates finally built (2 for France and 2 for Italy).
1994	TRILATERAL frigate (TFC)	Germany, Netherlands, Spain	Common platform, but no common systems.

First delivery Sept 2005	Scorpène (AIP conventional submarine)	French DCN /Spanish NAVANTIA	Rather successful, but the situation is close to NAVANTIA building under licence from DCN.
First delivery 2004	U212A (AIP conventional submarine)	German HDW / Italian FINCANTIERI	Rather successful, but the situation is close to FINCANTIERI building under licence from HDW.
1994	Viking project (conventional submarine)	Sweden, Denmark, Norway	Rather successful, but Norway left on budgetary grounds.
2002	Multi-missions European frigate (FREMM) 27 frigates expected	Italy, France	Agreement on hull and propulsion. Some discussion still on-going on systems.
2006	CVF aircraft carrier (approx. 60 000 tons)	UK, France	UK sold their design to France. No “common” design.

3. EC research policy

The huge EC shipping industry initiative, “Waterborne”, mentions that EC naval ships of the future should be “off the shelf” ships. The idea is clearly to build long series of naval ships, thus cheaper to build and to maintain.

4. EC industrial policy

USA and EC have a very different industrial organisation regarding naval shipbuilding:

- USA has two industrial groups only: Northrop Grumman and General Dynamics, each one operating three yards;
- EC has multiple countries, industrial groups and shipyards. There is, by now, little consolidation of the industry.

This disadvantage could be compensated by an enhanced EC cooperative organisation and systems.

Well managed naval cooperation is therefore of high value for the EC naval industry, and it is the only way, in the foreseeable future, to economically produce and maintain naval ships in the EC. There is an on-going trend towards the shaping of a few naval shipbuilders consortiums in Europe. The creation of long term cooperation between naval shipyards should logically encourage the implementation of CADET-like methodology and tools for building ships in cooperation.

In the aeronautics industry, the Airbus consortium has provided one full scale example of organization for EC joint projects: following the common design phase, the plane is assembled at a single construction site. Components are build in different countries then shipped and assembled in this single construction site. Anyway, there is one single plane model eventually proposed to the market.

Naval shipbuilding is a different story, as it must take into account the different requirements from the national navies. Therefore, it is reasonable to expect the final result of any cooperation to consist of one ship version per nation. The improvement in productivity can therefore only come from upstream, concentrating, during the cooperative work, on common high level design and common procurement list.

5. Tools functions

The partners are guided step by step in the common design, going through appropriate CADET software modules.

These modules focus on the information really common to all partners, therefore staying at the suitable level of abstraction. They do not address any information which might be specific to any partner (e.g. relating to the level of pre-assembly of blocks, the size of drydocks or assembly halls).

The “Common design database” is filled-out with high level information, in the first place. The partners will progressively move to lower levels of information, translating this high level information into lower level information. The lowest level of information will eventually be made of components which can be physically manipulated by the yard.

Example :

- if the high level information is: ship speed = 20 kts,
- we can derive, at a lower level of information: engine power = 8000 KW,
- eventually we end, at the lowest level of information, with the engine main body description.

Each time a consensus is reached between the partners, the corresponding information is entered into the relevant software tools and transferred into the “Common design database”, in which the complete cooperative information is finally stored.

Typical software modules are as follows:

- general requirements of the ship: operational objectives as defined by the navies, main characteristics (speed requirements, dimensions, etc).
- initial design: it provides a simplified structural model of the ship, visualisation of the ship included.
The block cutting options will be studied at this stage, leading to the rational choice of the most appropriate building shipyards.
All usual initial design studies are carried out at this stage, such as weight, hydrostatics, damage stability, longitudinal strength, speed and power prediction.

Fig.3: Common design - Requirements and initial design

- systems definition: it generates the “wiring diagrams” of the major systems on-board, typically propulsion, navigation and weaponry.

It concentrates on the functional relationship between equipments and not on any geographical positioning on board or specific maker/model of equipment.

Standard values for the characteristics of equipment are proposed in menus (dimensions, pressure, power, etc), in view to fostering the choice of standard equipment.

A modular design of systems is proposed, in the sense that each major operational requirement corresponds to a certain module of systems. Therefore the whole ship systems are made of the assembly of the “common platform” module and the optional modules, which could be, for instance, “anti-aircraft”, “anti-ship” or “anti-submarine” modules.

Fig.4: Common design - Modular systems

- fight simulation: the set of whole ship systems modules defines a “virtual ship”, which can be systematically tested by an adequate simulation software, for its reaction against various threats, both for fighting capability and survival skills.
- procurement: for each piece of equipment referenced in the “wiring diagrams” of the systems, the partners take decisions regarding the choice of maker and model. Each partner is informed of the choices made by the other partners, so that, in case of discrepancy, he has to make sure that there are strong grounds no to choose the same equipment. The tool calculates the achieved global level of procurement commonality between the partners. For instance, if partners have, let us say, 50% of the equipment list in common, this could be considered as a success.

Fig.5: Common design - Simulation and Equipments orders

Each partner will inject the contents of the “Common design database”, resulting from the common design decisions taken by all partners, into his own CAD system. Starting from there, he will finalize his own version of the ship. He will then be free to adjust to any local constraints regarding the specific navy requirements, optimisation of the design, specific choice of supplier, building habits or building facilities

Fig.6: Individualized designs

6. Implementation

This research project is expected to be financed either by the concerned Ministries of defence, with taxpayers' money or as a Joint Industry Project, where partners invest their own money. It should be carried out by a consortium, associating several European naval shipbuilders, naval procurement agencies and societies specialised in naval CAD, with official support from the European Defence Agency. Once the tools developed and operationally used for real cooperative programs, we can imagine that they would be run by either:

- a common subsidiary of European naval shipbuilders,
- an independent service company,
- an EC administration technical service.

7. Benefits

The research project in itself will familiarize the naval shipbuilding actors with the idea of cooperative work, so that they will consider this option when starting their next real shipbuilding program. The software tools will ensure that:

- for each cooperative program, the general design will be discussed and shared between partners, gathering the best of partners' expertise and ideas;
- a shipbuilding efficient strategy will be decided at an early stage, by selecting the building yards on the basis of rational factors, such as blocks size and weight. For instance, an aircraft carrier being a wide vessel, the choice of a shipyard with wide drydocks looks like a natural initial choice;
- the extent of common design of systems will be maximized: only when there is a difference in the navy requirement will the system design be different;
- the extent of common procurement will be maximized: this feature will materialize in huge savings during the whole service life of the ships, as spare parts and repair contracts will be cheaper, due to a higher numbers of orders;
- once this common design phase is finished, each partner is free to deal with his national version of the ship, as he wishes, having in view the optimisation of his design: this could cover specific navy requirements, detailed arrangement, choice of minor equipment and adaptation to shipbuilding facilities constrains.

Fig.7: "CADET" cooperation schema

As a consequence, cross repair of naval ships between EC nations will be made theoretically possible, as repair shipyards, having become familiar with the common systems and equipment of ships of the same family, will be able to service all of them.

Hierarchical Approach to Reliability-Based Inspection Planning of Hull Structures

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Abstract

This paper addresses two important computational aspects of inspection and maintenance optimization of deteriorating ship structures or floating production/storage facilities: (1) the hierarchical modeling of a ship hull to allow for the efficient use of Bayesian probability nets (BPN) in the analysis required to develop optimal risk acceptance criteria; and (2) the use of hierarchical Bayes methods to update the condition states of spatially distributed hull components such as plates, girders, and connections. Using the hierarchical modeling of a hull described in this paper, a quantitative risk assessment model can be developed to quantify the risks associated with the degradation of the ship hull, using event and consequence scenario. Hierarchical Bayes models are discussed in this paper both for the case of spatial conditional independence and for the more general case where spatial correlation is considered. The latter is especially useful for decision making involving one- and two-dimensional components such as girders, pipes, vessels and plates subject to corrosion. The influence of correlation length between condition states is examined.

1. Introduction

The use of hierarchical methods in reliability-based inspection and maintenance planning finds its original applications in offshore structures, *Straub and Faber (2004)*, and process plants, *Sunkpho and Garrett (2003)*. This paper shows that ships and hull structures are also excellent candidates for such a treatment. The concept is fundamental to the framework of inspection and maintenance planning and considerably simplifies the computational aspects of inspection updating and optimization in the case of a complex engineering system. A multi-level discretization scheme works very well for hull structures as illustrated in the paper. One key benefit is that BPN can be used to analyse the relation between component degradation states (corrosion, fatigue and leaks) and the overall performance of the ship hull expressed in terms of event scenarios described by logical relationships between lower-level failure events. This results in a hierarchical approach which is amenable to optimization and the formulation of practical risk acceptance targets for individual components.

The use of hierarchical Bayes models has also revealed itself very beneficial in a variety of engineering decision making contexts, particularly when data originating from different sources or from spatially distributed systems need to be processed. Its use is popular in systems engineering and in a large variety of non-engineering fields ranging from biostatistics to environmental and geographical models. References can be found in *Banerjee et al. (2004)*, *Singpurwalla (2006)*, and *Maes and Breitung (2007)*. In engineering they are typically used in decision making involving deteriorating infrastructure since they allow data from different spatial contexts to be aggregated in such a way that information about the individual states of deterioration is spread and used properly throughout the system (in this case the ship structure). Hierarchical Bayes models are explained both for the case of spatial conditional independence and for the more general case where spatial correlation is considered. The latter is especially useful for one- and two-dimensional components such as girders and plates subject to corrosion. The influence of correlation length between discretized condition states is analyzed in two ways: first, by investigating the sensitivity of the posterior distributions of the condition states on the assumed correlation length; and second, by treating the correlation characteristics themselves as Bayesian hyper-parameters. An example illustrating the updating of degradation condition states following inspection in a linear component is provided.

2. Hierarchical modeling of the ship hull

In the process of assessing risk for ship and floating facilities it is convenient to consider the ship hull from a holistic perspective where the individual components of the hull are selected according to their functional significance. The hull structure can be considered as an assembly of engineered components, as shown in the three-level hierarchy depicted in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Three-level hierarchical modeling of the ship hull

The objective of the hull as a whole is to keep the ship or floater in operation in accordance with its design requirements. A breach of the integrity of the failure at an overall level can therefore be considered as an event leading to any one or more of the following consequences:

- Loss of or damage to the vessel as a result of a loss of buoyancy or explosions/fires
- Loss of production as a result of reduced operability
- Loss of lives as a result of foundering or explosion/fires
- Spills and other damages to the environment

When as shown in Fig.1, the hull is treated as an assembly of components and/or sub-functions the hull may be considered to consist of an assembly of tanks tied together at the deck plate, the tank partitions and the bottom and side plates. These individual components are furthermore stiffened by girders and web frames to ensure sufficient structural integrity of the hull.

The hull components as described in the foregoing have basically two functions namely, to ensure that the overall ship has a sufficient structural integrity, and to provide the means for containing cargo and ballast. Failure of the components of the hull at this hierarchical level of discretization can be assumed to result in the following events:

- Loss of or reduced structural integrity (stiffness/load carrying capacity)
- Loss of containment/leaks of the individual tanks

Moving down to the next level of discretization, we may now consider the aforementioned hull components to form an assembly of plates connected by welded joints. Failure of these individual components may lead to:

- Crack or pit through plate thickness
- Reduced overall plate thickness
- Joint stiffness reduction or failure

Based on the hierarchical discretization of the ship hull outlined above, it is now possible to relate degradation due to fatigue and corrosion to the overall performance of the ship hull in terms of event scenarios described by causal or logical relationships between individual failure events. The probability as well as the expected consequences of each of the event scenarios may then be quantified. In a risk-based optimization, they may eventually be compared with optimized acceptance criteria. If necessary, risk mitigation measures through inspection and maintenance strategies focused on the control of degradation may subsequently be developed such that certain acceptance criteria in regard to life saving, economical/material losses and damages to the qualities of the environment are fulfilled.

The principles of risk assessment of engineering systems are outlined in a recent JCSS publication “Principles for Risk Assessment in Engineering”, *JCSS (2006)*. Using the hierarchical modeling of the hull described in the preceding section, a quantitative risk assessment model can now be developed to quantify the risks associated with degradation of the ship hull (*Nishijima et al., 2007*). Event scenarios evolve from fatigue and corrosion at the (lowest) local level and propagate in terms of consequences over the different components and hierarchical levels of the hull structure. In this way a directed graph of logical and causal dependencies or a so-called network can be developed.

To analyze this network, Bayesian Probabilistic Networks (BPN), see *Jensen (2001)*, seem appropriate but other similar tools may also be utilized. With reference to the hull structure illustrated in Fig.1a BPN for the quantitative risk analysis of the ship structure can have the appearance shown in Fig.2, with the hull being built up as an assembly of individual tanks. In Fig.2 only two identical cargo tanks are shown but in principle all tanks (cargo and ballast) can be included.

Fig.2: Network structure for a BPN analysis as part of the risk assessment of a ship hull structure (top level of discretization)

The condition state of each tank may be represented by the nodes “CapRed” (reduced load carrying capacity), “Explosion” (explosion due to leak and subsequent ignition) and “EnvDam” (environmental damage due to leak). The combination of these condition states for all the tanks allows us to assess the overall performance of the ship hull as expressed by the nodes “HullFail” (hull failure), “EconLoss” (overall consequence category: material and economical losses), “LossLives” (overall consequence category: loss of lives) and “EnvirDam” (overall consequence category: damages to the environment).

Using BPN, the conditional probability tables of the different states of these nodes can be assessed largely by engineering expertise (subjectively) and/or by consultation of appropriate databases.

Consider now a lower hierarchical level. The individual tanks in Fig.2 may also be represented by their own BPN as illustrated in Fig.3 where a ballast tank is considered. It is seen that the BPN for the ballast tank is defined in terms of objects comprising the possible components of the ballast tank, here for illustrative purposes through the objects: “DeckPlate”, “BottomPlate”, “CargoCargoPlate”, and “CargoBallastPlate”. The three ovalized result nodes in Fig.3 match the nodes defined in the higher-level BPN shown in Fig.2.

Fig.3: Illustration of BPN for the risk assessment of a ballast tank (middle level of discretization)

The bottom hierarchical level is illustrated in Fig.4 in the case of the bottom plate of a ballast tank. It can be seen that the risk assessment is now based on the structural degradation performance of the individual components of the hull structure at the lowest hierarchical level. In the case of this particular tank plate it is the fatigue performance of welded plate connections as well as the corrosion performance of the tank plates that govern the condition of the tank plate. The probabilities for the corresponding states may be controlled and updated by inspection and maintenance planning.

In principle if a rigorous BPN is conducted including all the dependencies (at a reasonable level of engineering detail) the performance of the hull structure as a whole can be formulated and quantified in terms of the performance of the individual details of the hull components including the effects of fatigue, corrosion pitting and corrosion wastage (general corrosion).

Fig.4: Illustration of BPN for the plate component of a ballast tank including conditional probability tables

3. Framework for compliance with risk acceptance criteria

Suppose now that the BPN representing the entire hull is subject to a risk-based optimization in order to determine the maximum acceptable probability of failure for individual structural details. The objective is to first set acceptable overall risk targets and then to determine, by optimization, how these targets correspond to acceptance criteria for the individual (lower-level) components. For instance, when considering only fatigue, the node “Fatigue” in Fig.4 would represent the acceptable probability of fatigue (per annum) for one specific detail in the considered plate component. Note that this probability can simply be described on the basis of the corresponding FDF’s, assumptions concerning dependency between fatigue failures, and a small algorithm for evaluating series systems reliability. The maximum acceptable probability of failure for this individual welded connection may be identified by minimization of the total expected lifecycle cost in accordance with *Straub and Faber (2005)*.

In such an optimization the minimization is performed subject to fulfillment of the overall acceptance criteria (these are input using the BPN nodes describing life safety, economical losses and environmental damages). This in turn raises the question what kind of overall risk acceptance criteria are appropriate for vessels in regard to:

1. life safety
2. damages to the qualities of the environment
3. economical losses/asset damages

In regard to life safety absolute criteria are given in terms of Average Individual Risk (AIR) with a tolerability limit equal to 10^{-3} per year and a target limit for design equal to 10^{-4} per year. Effectively this is interpreted in a way that the maximum acceptable AIR for the purpose of inspection and maintenance planning should be selected as equal to 10^{-3} per year. Also, when the risks associated with degradation (fatigue and corrosion) induced failures are above 10^{-4} per year, inspection and

maintenance plans must be implemented as a Risk Reduction Measure (RRM). The optimization of the inspection and maintenance plans must then follow the principle of service life cost minimization as suggested in this paper.

As far as environmental acceptance criteria as well as economic losses/asset damages are concerned, risk acceptance criteria are provided in terms of severity categories and frequency domains as shown in Fig.1. The actual numerical values in this figure, while reasonable, are given for the purpose of illustration only. Tables I and II further describe how severity can be interpreted in the context of Fig.1.

I : Improvement deemed necessary
 II : Target for improvement
 III : Remote risk

- $10^0/y - 10^1/y$: Frequent. The event will occur several times on a given installation.
- $10^{-1}/y - 10^{-2}/y$: Probable. The event may occur 1 time on a given installation.
- $10^{-2}/y - 10^{-3}/y$: Possible. The event may occur 1 time for 10-20 installations.
- $10^{-3}/y - 10^{-4}/y$: Low probability. The event may occur 1 time for 100-200 installations.
- $10^{-4}/y - 10^{-5}/y$: Remote.
- $10^{-5}/y - 10^{-6}/y$: Very remote.

Fig.5: Acceptance criteria for environmental damage as well as economic and asset losses (the numerical values are given for illustration only)

Table I: Interpretation of severity in the context of Fig.1 for economic, material, and asset losses

Minor	Consequences limited onto a local area where the event occurs
Significant	Consequences are limited to a zone (or module) of the FPSO. Possible off-site effects; 3 rd party interest not endangered
Major	Consequences extend to several zones (or modules) of the FPSO; 3 rd party interest endangered but not threatened
Catastrophic	Consequences extend to all the FPSO; 3 rd party interest threatened, and impacts on the environment

Table II: Interpretation of severity in the context of Fig.1 for environmental damage (values given for illustration only)

Class 1	Less than 20 m ³ of oil spill
Class 2	Between 20 to 200 m ³ of oil spill
Class 3	Between 200 to 2000 m ³ of oil spill
Class 4	More than 2000 m ³ of oil spill

Returning now to the optimization procedure required to determine acceptable risk levels for the individual component hot spots, we use the following approach. Consider first consequences related to environmental damage and to material/economical losses: here we identify “event scenarios” caused by degradation (fatigue and corrosion) and then group them into different categories of consequences. Thus we can determine which event scenarios belong to the different severity categories shown in Fig.5 and Table I. Having identified the severity class for each scenario, the requirement in regard to acceptable probability for each degradation event which initiates the individual scenarios may now be determined. It is clear that many different degradation events may initiate event scenarios leading to consequences belonging to one particular severity of consequences. This implies that an optimization must be performed in order to determine in what way the risk acceptance requirements can be fulfilled most optimally for the given severity category.

As far as life safety risk acceptance criteria are concerned, we simply determine the expected loss of lives as a result of all possible degradation events. Following the same approach as outlined above an optimization is performed to determine how to optimally satisfy the overall AIR requirements.

The optimum is achieved when the risk reduction achieved through inspection and maintenance of each individual structural element (hot spot) relative to the corresponding costs is identical for all hot spots. The costs for optimal inspection and maintenance for each individual hot spot is easily obtained from data base tables where the minimum costs as function of the FDF’s may be identified as a function of the hot spot acceptable annual probability of failure. It is clear that the outlined approach requires considerable analysis and for this reason it is a good practice to include only those hot spots which contribute significantly to the risks. These may be identified prior to the optimization by means of sensitivity analysis of the hull BPN.

4. Hierarchical Bayes methods

The use of hierarchical or two-stage Bayesian models has revealed itself very beneficial in a variety of engineering decision making contexts, particularly when data originating from different sources or from spatially distributed systems need to be processed. They are typically used in decision making involving deteriorating infrastructure. In this paper the emphasis lies on how hierarchical Bayes methods can be used in the context of reliability-based inspection and maintenance planning for simple spatially distributed ship components such as girders and plates. Here we describe a useful two-stage hierarchical model, *Maes (2006)*.

A hierarchical Bayes model relates observable variables X to exchangeable (non-observable) condition states θ which can be modeled as conditionally independent given hyper-parameters α . Full specification of such a model rests upon:

4. The prior pdf $f(\alpha)$ for the hyper-parameters α .
5. The conditional pdf $f(\theta|\alpha)$ for the condition states θ given the value of the hyper-parameter(s) α .
6. The conditional pdf $f(X|\theta)$ of the observable X , given the values of the parameters θ .

The objective is to assist decision making by updating the condition states after observation of certain data X , e.g. following inspection. This allows the prior for the hyper-parameters to be updated and from this we also obtain a posterior distribution for the condition states. With respect to the latter we

can consider updating the condition states of the n components or zones where data X ($i=1, \dots, n$) were originally observed, or we can also find a predictive posterior for other (arbitrary) condition states θ . In the first case, the expression for the posterior pdf of an observed condition state 0 (denoting one of the n specific states) is based on a mixture of the zone-specific data x_0 and the posterior of the hyper-parameters given x^* (excluding the data for state 0):

$$f(\theta_0|x) \propto f(x_0|\theta_0) \int_{\alpha} f(\theta_0|\alpha) f(\alpha|x^*) d\alpha \quad (1)$$

Similar expressions can be derived for the joint posterior pdf of two or more condition states (Maes, 2006). In the other case, for an arbitrary, or new, or not previously observed, or an additional condition state θ , the posterior pdf is simply

$$f(\theta|x) \propto \int_{\alpha} f(\theta|\alpha) f(\alpha|x) d\alpha \quad (2)$$

where the posterior pdf of the hyper-parameters can be found simply from:

$$f(\alpha|x) \propto \prod_{i=0}^n \int_{\theta_i} f(x_i|\theta_i) f(\theta_i|\alpha) d\theta_i f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

Similar expressions can be derived for the joint posterior pdf of two or more additional condition states as in *Maes (2006)*. One original criticism of the above approach is that spatial dependence between condition states cannot be included in the model. Also, the model as described above would become hard to implement if condition states are ranged or restricted variables, as in the case of a condition state representing the actual % deterioration of a component or zone. To alleviate this situation we extend the model in the next section.

5. Computational aspects of hierarchical Bayes

Since the introduction of Gibbs sampling in statistics in the early nineties, the computational approach to Bayesian probability modeling has essentially experienced a revolution. Modern computational methods are based on the use of Gibbs sampling and more specifically the Metropolis-within-Gibbs algorithm in what is now generally referred to as Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods. Used widely in many fields, MCMC has recently been applied in engineering, *Borsuk et al. (2001)*, *Qian et al. (2003)*. It is freely available in a number of software packages such as Bugs (Bayesian updating using Gibbs sampling) and WinBugs, *Spiegelhalter et al. (2003)*, which is used for the example application described subsequently.

Essentially, the entire hierarchical Bayes model including the auxiliary variables must be specified so as to define its full joint distribution. This is similar to BPN for discrete random variables which have important computational applications in engineering. A graphic representation of a fully specified hierarchical Bayes model is an essential start in developing the model. Fig.7 is an illustration of such graphs and is discussed in more detail in the subsequent section. In these directed graphical models (parent-descendants) rectangles represent constants while ellipses denote stochastic nodes. Solid arrows indicate a stochastic relation while hollow arrows represent deterministic relationships.

Once the model is fully specified, values of the unknown parameters are sampled from their conditional posterior distribution given any observed nodes. Repeated (Gibbs) sampling from successive nodes following the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm together with a variety of MCMC-specific adaptive and tuning options leads under very broad conditions to stable samples for the posterior distributions of the various variables. The application of MCMC methods to engineering modeling and decision making is potentially very extensive, as it essentially eliminates most of the hurdles associated with the complexities of multivariate Bayesian analysis.

6. Hierarchical Bayes with spatial correlation and nonlinear link functions

In order to allow spatial dependency in an hierarchical Bayes model, we introduce auxiliary random variables β . The relationship between the condition state θ which in many cases (but not necessarily) represents the mean $E(X)$ of the observed variables, and these auxiliary variables β , is specified using a non-linear link function g , which is only required to be monotonic and differentiable. The variables β can now be modeled as conditionally dependent variables given the hyper-parameters.

$$\theta = g^{-1}(\beta) \quad (4)$$

One of the first applications of such models for reliability analysis was the Challenger space shuttle disaster as described in the interesting account in *Dalal et al. (1989)*.

Hence an extended hierarchical Bayes model consists of:

1. The prior pdf $f(\alpha)$ for the hyper-parameters α .
2. The joint conditional distribution $p(\beta|\alpha)$ of the auxiliary variables parameters β given the hyper-parameters α .
3. The link function g relating the auxiliary variables to the condition state variables θ using (4).
4. The distributions $f(X|\theta)$ of the observable variables X given the condition states θ .

As an example, consider spatially distributed condition states measuring deterioration in terms of a percentage loss of structural section due to corrosion. Specifically, we consider a one-dimensional or two-dimensional structural system such as a girder, a line pipe, a vessel or a plate subject to deterioration. We can reasonably assume that the condition state θ can be viewed as a spatially varying homogeneous random field with mean μ , variance σ^2 , and correlation length δ . The latter three variables can be treated as hyper-parameters in hierarchical Bayes. Measurements X_i of the deterioration process can be performed at specific locations i with spatial coordinate s_i . Hence, the required covariance matrix conditional on the hyper-parameters consists of main diagonal elements σ^2 and off-diagonal elements T_{ij} equal to:

$$T_{ij}(\sigma^2, \delta) = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{|s_i - s_j|}{\delta}\right) \quad (5)$$

As an example consider a line pipe element shown in Fig.6. Inspection has been performed at the five sections with the coordinates specified and a relative loss of wall thickness due to corrosion has been observed in each section as indicated in Fig.6. The use of a percentage section loss between 0 and 100% as the measure of the condition state requires a nonlinear link function with the auxiliary unbounded variables β . These link function must transform values of the auxiliary variable β between $-\infty$ and $+\infty$ into values between zero and unity. Hence the following link function is used:

$$\beta = g(\theta) = \log\left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right) \quad (6)$$

The fully specified hierarchical model is shown in Fig.7. It shows the variables β to be multivariate normal with mean vector μ and covariance matrix T . The data X themselves are assumed to be conditionally gamma distributed with mean θ and standard deviation $\sigma_X=0.1$ representing an inspection tool imprecision of 10% of the wall thickness.

Fig.6: Spatial layout and inspection data for five cross-sections of a line pipe segment

Fig.7: Hierarchical Bayes Model used in the analysis of spatial dependency in a line pipe segment

The base case scenario is to treat the correlation length as a hyper-parameter. For the data included in Fig.6, Fig.8(a)(b)(c) shows the posterior densities of the three hyper-parameters. It can be seen that the third one, namely the correlation length is left-skewed and has a mean and a standard deviation equal to 1.085 units of length and 0.747 units of length, respectively.

Fig.9 illustrates the posterior % deterioration (the condition state) for each of the 5 line pipe sections as updated by (1) as well as, on the right-hand side, for an additional un-inspected section that is located at sufficiently great distance from the inspected zones (else the correlation with the inspected zones needs to be included in assessing the conditional marginal posterior density of this condition state). It shows the mean together with the 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles. It can be seen that the variability of the “predictive” pdf for a randomly selected far-field section has a slightly larger spread than any of the five inspected condition states and that it is marked by a longer upper tail.

Fig.8(a)(b)(c): Posterior pdf of the hyper-parameters mean, variance and correlation length given the inspection data in Fig.6

Further departures from the above base case scenario including the case where the correlation length δ is taken as a constant instead of as a hyper-parameter, are considered by *Maes and Breitung (2007)*.

One important observation is that the tail behavior varies greatly between regions adjacent to inspected zones and far-field un-inspected zones which has important implications on system reliability and inspection planning. This is a direct consequence of the way hierarchical Bayes models are updated, as can be seen e.g. by contrasting equations (1) and (2).

Fig.9: Posterior mean, 2.5 percentile, and 97.5-percentile of the condition states

7. Conclusions

Based on a hierarchical discretization of the ship hull it is possible to relate degradation due to fatigue and corrosion to the overall performance of the ship hull in terms of event scenarios described by causal or logical relationships between individual failure events. The probability as well as the expected consequences of each of the event scenarios can then be quantified. In a risk-based optimization, they may eventually be compared with optimized acceptance criteria. Risk mitigation measures through inspection and maintenance strategies focused on the control of degradation can effectively be developed such that specific acceptance criteria in regard to life saving, economical/material losses and damages to the qualities of the environment are satisfied. A quantitative risk assessment model can be developed to quantify the risks associated with degradation of the ship hull. Event scenarios evolve from fatigue and corrosion at the (lowest) local level and propagate in terms of consequences over the different components and hierarchical levels of the hull structure.

By applying Bayesian Probabilistic Networks to the resulting directed graph of logical and casual dependencies, the overall risk assessment accounts for the structural degradation performance of the individual components of the hull structure at the lowest hierarchical level. In the example it is the fatigue performance of welded plate connections as well as the corrosion performance of the tank plates that govern the condition of the tank plate. The probabilities for the corresponding states can be controlled and updated by inspection and maintenance planning. In principle if a rigorous BPN is conducted including all the dependencies (at a reasonable level of engineering detail) the performance of the hull structure as a whole can be formulated and quantified in terms of the performance of the individual details of the hull components including the effects of fatigue, corrosion pitting and corrosion wastage (general corrosion).

For spatially distributed systems, hierarchical Bayes methods provide an excellent alternative to strictly using location-specific data by exploiting observation or inspection data for similar systems. The emphasis in this paper lies on how hierarchical Bayes methods can be used in the context of reliability-based inspection and maintenance planning for simple spatially distributed ship components such as girders and plates. The paper includes MCMC-based techniques to model and update range-restricted condition states such as % deterioration. It also describes the role of spatial correlation and its effective treatment as hyper-parameter in empirical Bayes methods.

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A GIS Based Simulation Tool for Civilian Harbour Protection

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Abstract

This paper introduces a software simulator, based on a geographical information system, to provide area coverage maps for underwater security in civilian harbours and to improve port security evaluating the impact of both new sensors and modifications in the sensor placement.

1. Introduction

In the last few years there has been a remarkable interest in civilian harbour protection because of increasing threats against civilian targets. Up to now the harbour security problem was investigated only in military scenarios where there are different possibilities to act and react against a menace and where the harbour traffic is tightly controlled. Moreover in a military scenario it is possible to think that each ship is a potential sensor to protect the port, *Schneider and Cortsen (2005)*. In civilian ports the problems are completely different: the traffic is not completely controlled, there are less possibilities to test the harbour security in an effective way, each ship is not a security asset but a possible menace. However in the last years an understanding of the great importance of the problems connected with the civilian harbour security has been growing, *Ramberg (2005)*, considering both the civilian and the commercial aspects crucial for the protection of non-military harbours. In particular there are over 46,000 ships engaged in carrying 80% of the world's trade among 4,000 ports; a small number of these ports manages the majority of the trade, making these places a very important and up to now vulnerable targets for terrorist attacks. A recent US study concluded that a small but clever attack on two US ports would have an economic impact up to 58B USD on the US alone, *Ramberg (2005)*. In this context the use of software instruments to test an harbour protection system could be very effective in both military and civilian scenarios but in this latter case it could be the unique way to obtain a good assessment of the protection effectiveness of a given system. In particular the possibility to simulate the scenario permits to test different kind of detection system deployments and environmental conditions, and finally to choose the best anti-intrusion sensors configuration with a very limited influence in the normal harbour activity.

Building an underwater anti-intrusion system is a complex operation, starting from the selection of the right detection sensors to be placed in the specific port. Several systems, as acoustic systems, *Tesei et al. (2005)* or fluxgate magnetometers, as well as AUVs, *Caiti et al. (2005)*, *Bovio (2005)*, can be used to control an underwater harbour area, but the selection of the most appropriate one in a specific harbour could require a long time and big investments; the use of simulative packages can be a fast and cost-effective tool at the very least to restrict the choice to a small subset of potential assets. Moreover a simulation tool permits to verify the anti-intrusion performance against a wide set of intruders that cover several and complex trajectories in the port.

In this paper we focus on the description of a simulation tool that permits to evaluate the area coverage of underwater anti-intrusion configurations in civilian/commercial harbours. The tool, based on Geographical Information Systems (GIS) technology, has been designed in order to compare, in simulation, the performance of different sensor configurations against several kinds of intruders (divers, AUVs, ships, etc). The figures of merit are the mean Probability of Detection (PD), that allows to determine the overall area coverage of the detection system configuration, the expected time from initial detection by sensors to interception by surface response crafts and the expected halt distance of underwater intruders of various speeds. In the present paper only the area coverage based on the PD has been considered. PD is computed each time according to a set of rules involving the

sensors technical characteristics, the environment characteristics and finally the type of intruders. The tool has an additional optimization facility, based on a Genetic Algorithm (GA), that allows to compute automatically the sensor configuration with the highest area coverage at the minimum sensor cost. The paper is organized as follows: in the next section the proposed simulation tool is described in detail, explaining the software modules and architecture; in section 3 the GA-based optimization procedure is outlined, and examples of the effectiveness of the proposed simulation tool are shown; finally, conclusion are given and on going work is shortly reported.

2. Simulation tool description

A GIS-based simulation software for underwater anti-intrusion detection is now described. The software runs under the Microsoft Windows Operating System and it is based on the ESRI MapObjects 2.3 library. It permits to load a geographical area with a required level of details, as for instance a coastal area with bathymetric and temperature information, to add several kinds of underwater sensors in the area, as. acoustic or magnetic sensors, to consider several type of intruders (e.g., AUVs, divers, ships) and to verify what security level is guaranteed by the sensors configuration chosen against the particular intruder selected. Moreover the simulation software is strictly connected with the Matlab environment to improve the tool flexibility when a new sensor or a new kind of intruder is added: Matlab allows to easily insert new sensors or intruder models. Finally, a GA, built in the Matlab environment, permits to find the optimal sensors configuration to obtain a desired security level in the area at the lowest cost. The simulation software is divided in four different sub-systems plus a separated Matlab module that implements the GA: an environment sub-system, a sensor sub-system, an intruder subsystem. In this way the software architecture separates in a modular way elements that are conceptually very different.

2.1 Environment sub-system

This part of the software simulates the harbour environment. It is based on a GIS architecture in order to add any kind of information about the harbour in a easy and straightforward way and with the level of details required for the simulation: it is possible to insert bathymetric or acoustic information as well as any other information that might be useful for the simulation. The GIS platform is a well known platform in the field of geographical information software and this allows to use historical environmental information or information used with other GIS tools. In a GIS software environment each map of a given area is built from geographically overlapping layers and in each layer only one kind of information is represented: different data types are stored in different layers. Finally each map layer is related to a database table that records all the attributes of all the objects in that specific layer. The maps in a GIS software can be represented in two ways, as *raster map* and as *vectorial map*. Without enter in a too detailed description, it can be said that the first one is usually used both to represent continuous variables and for the digital acquisition of unformatted images (as satellites images). The raster format, in fact, connects each element to only one attribute. On the other side vectorial maps represent cartographic information through points, lines and polygons (lines and polygons are internally coded as sequence of points) and each element can be connected with several attributes; for example for a polygon that represents a lake various attributes can be recorded as the area, the perimeter, the maximum depth, etc. The vectorial maps are usually employed to represent complex geographical elements with high resolution (these maps do not use a lot of memory thanks to the multi-attributes structures), or to display objects in motion (there is a special layer, called tracking layer, to represent elements that change their position with time). The developed simulation software uses the ESRI MapObject library, a standard interface for cartographic software, with a related file type called "ESRI shape" to represent all maps information. For these reasons each map is codified in the Vector Product Format (VPF) and recorded as ESRI shape file. On the basis of these powerful architecture, the simulation software divides the map layers in two different types: bathymetric layers and costal/obstacles layers. A specific interface is realized to specify what are the bathymetric layers and what the costal/obstacles ones. The latter layers are then united to form a unique layer, invisible to the user, that allows for a quick evaluation of the correctness of the position of moving objects (as intruders, or moving sensors): the software has to test only one large layer instead of many small

different layers. It is possible to display more than one harbour environment at a time. The tool is based on a multi-document architecture (MDI) that allows to load or to create different scenarios. In this way it is possible to evaluate the performance of the sensors configuration chosen in different harbours or compare different sensors configuration in the same port. This is an important feature to select the best anti-intrusion sensors configuration.

2.2 Sensors sub-system

The sensors sub-system is responsible for the overall detection sensors performance prediction. The main issue in this module is the sensor model: in particular, in the developed software each sensor is characterized by the so called "Probability of Detection" (PD) function. This function expresses the probability of detecting an intruder belonging to a given class (see section 2.3 on intruder characterization) as a function of the spatial position of the intruder with respect to the sensor. Through the definition of PD for any given sensor class, the sensor implementation details are hidden from the simulation. In addition, the PD can be (as it is for the most of existing detection systems) a function of several environmental factors, as bathymetry, water temperature, tidal currents, flows, etc., that can be read from the environmental subsystem. An example of the PD representation for two sensors placed in a particular position within an harbour is given in Fig.1.

Fig.1: PD (Probability of Detection) contour levels for two arbitrary sensors within the harbour area. The harbour is represented in the GIS system, together with bathymetric and other environmental information (if any). The PD contours range from hot colours (high) to cold colours (low PD). The PD is 100% at the sensor location. The map gives information on the area covered by the system composed by the two sensors

The user can introduce sensors in the system by defining sensor classes, and subsequently calling several instances of sensors from any given class (e.g.: "magnetometer xyz" is a class of sensors; the specific anti-intrusion system to be evaluated has n sensors of this class). There are two ways of introducing sensor classes in the simulation tool: predefined classes and user defined classes; in both cases, classes definition can be added using a graphical interface (GI) or through the system database (DB). Predefined sensor classes are sensors already defined in the tool with a very simple model: the PD is not influenced by the environmental condition in the area, obstacles do not interfere with these sensors functioning, spatial distribution in the neighbourhood of the sensor assumes simple geometrical shapes (cylindrical, ellipsoidal). These kind of PDs are obviously very simplistic, but they

can be indeed useful for a “quick and dirty” model of performance for a preliminary sensor configuration to be refined in successive steps with a more realistic sensor modelling.

User-defined sensor classes can be introduced either in matrix form, directly loadable in the simulator DB, expressing the spatial variability of the PD at the user-chosen definition, or, with a link to the Matlab environment, through a call to a Matlab function, that can read all the needed environmental information from the DB and produce the PD map for any given instance of the user-defined sensor class.

Once sensor classes have been defined, sensor instances from the various classes can be called and placed within the harbour environment either by drag and drop directly on the harbour geographical map, or by specifying their geographical location in lat/long coordinates. In this way it is possible to configure the anti-intrusion system. Once the configuration phase is terminated, the simulator is ready to compute the area coverage for the chosen system configuration (and for a chosen intruder class, see section 2.3) in terms of combined PD starting from the PD of the various sensors. In particular, it is assumed that the PDs of each sensor instance are independent from each other. Hence, for a given spatial position, the probability of detecting the intruder at that position is given by the probability that at least one of the sensors is detecting the intruder. This can be formulated, from elementary probability theory, in the following recursive form:

$$PD = PD_1 + \sum_{i=2}^n \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} \overline{PD_j} PD_i \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of sensors. Using the fact that $\overline{PD_i} = 1 - PD_i$, from Eq.(1) it is possible to compute the overall PD at any point in the harbour. An example of computation of the overall PD and production of a global area coverage map is given in Fig.2, where the PDs of different sensors are combined accordingly to Eq.(1).

Fig.2: an example of area coverage map in terms of global PD for a given sensor configuration computed from the PD of the individual sensors accordingly to Eq.(1). Hot colours represent higher PD, cold colours represent lower PD

2.3 Intruder sub-system

This module simulates the intruder behaviour during an anti-intrusion simulation. The intruder is characterized through a kinematical model, and of course by its belonging to specific intruder classes. In particular the intruder class (e.g. submersible, ship, diver, etc) affects the sensors performance: magnetic sensors more easily detect ships than divers while an acoustic sensor has different detection performance if the threat is a submersible or a diver. To test the anti-intrusion system the intruder module can generate automatically several kind of intruder trajectories. However it is important to note that when the intruder path is established it does not change up to the end of the intrusion simulation, when other intruder trajectories can be selected. This, on one hand, allows to test the harbour protection system along a specific path, while, on the other hand, it does not consider situations in which the intruder strategy dynamically changes during the incursion. The intruder trajectories are defined as sequence of points and can be imported in a simulation from both the ASCII format (.txt) and the ESRI shape file format or can be automatically generated by the tool itself. Moreover the user can define new paths to test the harbour protection configuration using a drag and drop graphical interface directly on the map and finally save them in either the ASCII or Shape format. As shown in Fig.3, on the basis of the speed and the sampling time, the entire path is divided in segments and at each segment is associated a PD from the global area coverage map computed as in section 2.1. Defining $p(a)$, $p(b)$, as the PD along two adjacent segments a , b , of the path, the PD along the two segments is given by:

$$p(a, b) = p(a) + p(b) - p(a)p(b) \quad (2)$$

which is a particular instance of the more general Eq.(1). The overall probability that the target will be detected along the selected track is computed from Eq.(2) generalized to N segments recursively.

Fig.3: computation of the PD along a path for a given intruder

3. Optimal sensor configuration

Sensor configuration for an underwater anti-intrusion system is generally defined by an expert user on the basis of the working constraints in the experimental area and on the cost constraints. Within the above constraints, the user select a configuration that, based on her/his expertise is the “best” one, in the sense that guarantees the widest achievable area coverage. Area coverage here has to be intended in terms of extension of the harbour area with an overall PD above a pre-defined threshold (for instance, 90%). The simulation software described in the previous section can certainly be used to help the expert user in the a-posteriori evaluation of a given configuration without the need to test it on the field. However, since the software has the availability of all the information needed, it would be desirable if the tool could find, automatically, the best sensor configuration, avoiding the trial and error placement and giving the best solution in a straightforward manner. To this aim, the simulation tool is connected with a genetic algorithm (GA) to implement automatically the search for the optimal sensor placement. GA has been chosen as the search engine because it can deal with highly nonlinear

multiobjective optimization problems. From the point of view of the software implementation, the GA is an external module running in the Matlab environment; the simulator - GA connection is realized using the Matlab workspace as shared memory, in particular the simulator saves in specific variables the harbour area, the sensor performance and the settings for the GA, while the GA returns the optimization results in other variables in the Matlab workspace. In order to avoid blocking the simulator when the GA is running, Matlab is executed using a separate thread loaded when the simulator starts. It is assumed here that the reader is familiar with the basic mechanism of GA, so only the specific choices and implementation details relevant to our application are reported. For basic information on GAs the interested reader is referred to the numerous literature on soft computing, as for instance *Goldberg (1989)*. In order to determine the optimal sensor configuration, the GA has to return a set of sensors, specifying, for each sensor, its type (acoustic, magnetic, etc) and its position and orientation in the three dimensional harbour area: the GA codifies all these information in the chromosomes which assume the structure shown in Eq.(3). Information from the GIS database that the GA has to retrieve include the maximum number of sensors allowed in the area - this number could be due, for example, to economical reason -, the sensors classes available, the cost associated to each sensor and finally the PD related to each sensor. The chromosome i -th, that represents a possible configuration of the i -th sensor, codifies in binary the following information:

$$chromosome(i) = [type \ x \ y \ z \ \theta_x \ \theta_y \ \theta_z] \quad (3)$$

To be more precise a chromosome codifies, for each sensor, the class (*type*), the position (x, y, z) in a 3D environment and the orientation ($\theta_x, \theta_y, \theta_z$). Each individual in the GA population is composed by a string of chromosomes. It is important to note that the GA allocates the maximum number of sensors (chromosomes) in composing an individual, but when a sensor is not necessary in the configuration the GA gives it the NULL type or put it outside the admissible area. In this case the sensor does not contribute to the area coverage. Since the GA has to return the sensors configuration that maximizes the area coverage and that minimize the cost, the solution proposed assumes the following structure: first the overall area coverage is determined by computing the overall PD (as described in the previous section). Thus a measure of the area coverage is given by the integral of the total PD $p(\bar{x})$ over the chosen area:

$$HP = \int_A p(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} \quad (4)$$

where A is the working area and $\bar{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ is a point of the 3-dimensional domain. The second target for the GA is the minimization of the sensor configuration cost: this is obtained for each individual as $C = \sum_{i=1}^M c_i$, where c_i is the cost of the i -th sensor and M is the number of sensors placed. Finally, since the GA has to return the sensors configuration that maximize the sensors coverage and that minimize the cost associated to the chosen configuration, a multiobjective function is composed from the two goals introducing two (user -specified) weights and obtaining a single target function with two objectives:

$$fitnessValue = W_1 \int_A p(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} + W_2 \sum_{i=1}^M c_i = W_1 HP + W_2 C \quad (5)$$

On the basis of the values of the two weights the most important target is either the area protection or the cost related to the sensors configuration. Eq.(5) is modified in order to normalize the two objectives of the optimization function, to avoid problems connected with the use of different units of measurement, and it is then reported to a maximization problem as follows:

$$fitnessValue = W_1 \int_A p(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} / N_1 + W_2 (1 - C / N_2) \quad (5)$$

where N_1 is the area coverage normalization factor and it corresponds to the best area coverage achievable, regardless the sensor costs; N_2 is the cost normalization factor and it corresponds to the maximum cost; finally C is the total cost of the sensors configuration.

Since $0 \leq C \leq N_2$ (the cost related to any sensors configuration is lower or equal to the maximum cost) then $0 \leq C/N_2 \leq 1$ and then also $0 \leq (1 - C/N_2) \leq 1$ and then when the cost C increases the value $(1 - C/N_2)$ decreases and we have modified the cost minimization problem to a maximization problem with the fitness value always between 0 and 1. At this point the GA assumes the standard algorithmic structure of Fig.4.

Fig.4: algorithmic structure of the implemented GA

As usual, the GA is initialized with a random initial population. It then follows the cycle where the best individuals are selected using the proportional selection approach and are put in the mating pool. The individuals in the mating pool take part to the crossover. To be more precise, the individuals are extracted from the mating pool with a uniform probability and then the crossover is executed applying the standard one-point crossover operator to two individuals and generating two other individuals. If N is the number of individual in the initial population, then N individuals are selected as the best ones, N individuals enter in the mating pool and N new individuals are created with the crossover. Finally the new generation is created applying the mutation operator to the new individuals generated from the crossover operation. This new generation is evaluated and the process begin again. The implemented GA has successfully passed sanity-check cases, in which the optimal solution could be predicted a priori. In order to illustrate the GA behaviour in a realistic case, a 2-dimensional harbour has been selected, as shown in Fig.5. The GA was asked to place a maximum of 20 sensors in the area, choosing from 5 different classes (as shown in table 1), all with different costs and performance; as it may be expected, the best performance was associated to the most expensive sensors. The algorithm was run for a total of 3000 generations, each consisting in a population of 100 individuals, a mutation rate of 0.01 and a crossover probability of 0.7. Finally the weights were set as $W1 = 0.8$ and $W2 = 0.2$. The GA was implemented using Matlab 7 sp3 on a computer with a Pentium 4 processor running at 3 GHz, and the computation required a total time of approximately 3 days. The best configuration found had a fitness value is 0.9998 (the fitness function is always between 0 and 1) and it consists of a total of 9 sensors, over the 20 sensors allowed, belonging only to two of the possible five classes. As shown in Fig.6 the area coverage is almost the maximum allowed.

4. Conclusions and future developments

A GIS-based simulation tool for underwater harbour protection has been described. It has been shown that it can be used in several situation and it could be instrumental in finding an anti-intrusion sensors configuration in a civilian port, where the influence in the normal activities must be reduced to the minimum level. In this case the use of a simulation tool permits to place directly in the water the final anti-intrusion configuration chosen. Moreover a GA has been described to find the optimal sensors placement in the harbour. The GA was chosen as an optimization search method because of its ability in dealing with highly nonlinear problems. Future developments are foreseen in terms of developing intruder dynamic models, and additional figure of merits of the overall system.

Fig.5: Harbour area selected for the GA optimal sensor placement test

Fig.6: Area coverage obtained with the best solution as determined by the GA

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Human-Centered Development of Support Systems for Naval Tactical Decision Making

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Abstract

To ensure the successful fulfillment of nowadays naval missions, it is essential to provide decision makers with adequate support for the quick and accurate identification of contacts of interest as well as the thorough compilation of the tactical situation. Especially in littoral waters, there is a very high density of objects, entailing the possibility of various different asymmetric threats. Modern sensors provide loads of data and information, based on which decisions have to be made in extremely limited time. When 21st century command and control (C2) systems are being developed, these aspects must be particularly considered. An exemplary C2 system component for surface warfare will be designed and implemented, in order to create a demonstration facility and guidelines for future procurement specifications. The demonstration facility will consist of two workplaces. One of them is being newly designed within an ongoing study and is to provide support for information compilation and decision making. The other workplace is the result of previous studies and deals with a particular aspect of reconnaissance, namely the classification of surface targets based on electro-optical data. The former one is meant to be merely a prototype for the demonstration of human-system-integration issues, whereas the latter one is actually ready for operational use and currently deployed onboard those German vessels involved in the UNIFIL operation to secure the Lebanese coast and prevent arms smuggling. In order to disencumber human decision makers, it is of paramount importance to have graphical user interfaces that are as easy to use and as easy to learn as possible. To reach this objective, a highly human-centered development approach is chosen. Subject matter experts are frequently inquired throughout all phases and experimental tests with experienced officers take place under realistic service conditions, yielding feedback that is used for continuous optimization. The paper explains the methodology and presents results and lessons learned from experimental campaigns, including the latest within the scope of UNIFIL.

1. Introduction

The participation in so-called “out of area” missions, e.g., to back a peace keeping mission or to enforce an embargo, is characteristic for nowadays naval vessels’ duties, *BMVg (2006)*. In such missions, the tasks of situation recognition and assessment are characterized by eminently high complexity and uncertainty due to the simultaneous presence of neutral, friendly, and hostile objects. As opposed to the blue water scenarios of the cold war, the avoidance of collateral damage is mandatory now. Against this background the identification of unknown objects, the detection of the abilities and intentions of possibly threatening objects, the interpretation of rules of engagement, and the ultimate decision on whether or not to engage a particular object lead to exceedingly difficult decision making situations.

Besides the shift in mission objectives there has also been a lot of technological advancement in recent years. Range, speed, and accuracy of weapons have increased, and so did sensors and communication facilities. The growing amount of available data about the operational area and the increasing importance of communication, computers, intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance in C2 have given rise to the term C4ISR. Consequently human decision makers have less time remaining to ponder. This means high workload and stress for them and will possibly result in wrong decisions with serious consequences. Thus the importance of supporting decision makers to reduce workload and therewith improve planning, decision making, and operation safety increases significantly.

Reconnaissance is one of the most crucial tasks navies are facing. The quick classification and identification of unknown seagoing vessels is of the greatest importance, especially in the context of

deployments like Operation Active Endeavor, where the mission is to conduct operations against suspected terrorist activities in the Mediterranean. Since the start of the operation in October 2001 nearly 79,000 merchant vessels have been monitored (as of 12 April 2006) by the forces of Active Endeavor (AFSOUTH, 2007). Modern combat direction systems (CDS) make use of several different stationary and mobile image generating sensors that constantly deliver raw image material to be evaluated in a ship's combat information center (CIC). As environment, sight and weather conditions vary, so does this material concerning its quality. Infrared (IR) sensors, for instance, deliver a significantly inferior signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio and are responsive to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity. Hence the analysis of contained details and information can become exceedingly difficult and time consuming, if accomplished solely by human operators on their own. But given the busyness of merchant waterways nowadays, time is a very limited asset. Consequently, an advanced support system is needed to guarantee a quick and reliable classification and identification of observed contacts of interest (COI).

A demonstration facility with two different workplaces is being created. One of the workplaces contains the support system KEOD 2.0, which has been developed within earlier projects to support the classification of surface vessels based on electro-optical imagery, which is one particular aspect of situation recognition. This system has been tested extensively and will be officially deployed soon. At present, it is already deployed provisory to those vessels of the German navy that are currently involved in the UNIFIL (United Nations Interim Force In Lebanon) operation to secure the Lebanese coast and prevent arms smuggling. The other workplace shall provide support for the overall tasks of C2, including situation recognition, the assessment of own and enemy abilities and possible courses of action, collaboration potential within the task group, engagement planning, and damage assessment. Unlike the first workplace, this one will be merely a demonstration facility. The intention is to use it as reference for future procurement specifications.

2. Some fundamentals for C2 support

The assistance to be included shall be deemed a cognitive amplifier, on no account shall human decision making be replaced by complete automation. Tactical decision making, due to its immanent complexity and high stakes, must be considered a naturalistic decision making process. Thus, all eight characteristic factors, as mentioned by *Orasanu and Connolly* (1993), are at quite difficult levels:

- Ill-structured problems: Significant preparatory work is necessary to obtain an understanding of what is happening and what responses might be appropriate. There is no single best way to proceed.
- Uncertain dynamic environments: Because of environmental and weather conditions as well as restrictions with the use of sensors, data about nearby tracks may be scarce or ambiguous. Furthermore, in the missile age settings are likely to change quickly.
- Shifting, ill-defined, or competing goals: Decision makers are driven by multiple competing aims, such as self-protection and the avoidance of collateral damage ("engagement blue-on-green"). It is unclear how things should be traded off against each other.
- Action/feedback loops: Own actions can lead to reactions of other involved parties. By this means additional information can be generated, but new problems might occur, too. An object might feel provoked, for instance, when being targeted by illumination radar.
- Time stress: The existence of time pressure is obvious, because anti-ship missiles can be fast and difficult to detect early. Hence decision makers do not have much time to ponder and are likely to experience stress.
- High stakes: Outcomes of real significance to the participants are involved, such as being hit by enemy fire, mistakenly killing civilians, loss of one's career or even of one's life.
- Multiple players: Although by definition the final decision is to the commanding officer (CO), there are several CIC team members involved in the decision making process, and the report of a single person can make the decisive difference.
- Organizational goals and norms: There are miscellaneous organizational settings relevant to the decision-making process. Therefore applied goals and values cannot simply be the personal

preferences. Furthermore, the organization may respond to the decision makers' difficulties.

Sheridan (1992) differentiates ten degrees of automation, as shown in Fig.1. Level 1 would mean not to provide any decision support at all. Levels 8-10 are not eligible for tactical decision making because in these approaches operators are completely dismissed from the loop. Level 7 can be regarded acceptable only for the initiation of so-called "last-chance" defenses against very critical threats, such as an inbound anti-ship missile. The support provided to operators should normally reside among levels 2 to 6 and adapt according to the complexity of the task at hand, the overall situation, and the operator state, as far as it is possible to assess it.

Degree of automation	System features
1	The computer offers no assistance, human must do it all.
2	The computer offers a complete set of action alternatives, and
3	narrows the selection down to a few, or
4	suggests one, and
5	executes that suggestion if the human approves, or
6	allows the human a restricted time to veto before automatic execution, or
7	executes automatically, then necessarily informs the human, or
8	informs him after execution only if he asks, or
9	informs him after execution if it, the computer, decides to.
10	The computer decides everything and acts autonomously, ignoring the human.

Fig.1: Scale of degrees of automation, *Sheridan* (1992)

As pointed out in the introduction, operators onboard naval vessels have to make decisions based on a multitude of data and information. In current C2 systems these are predominantly presented in alphanumeric form. According to *Card et al. (1999)* a user-centered presentation of complex data should feature the use of computer-supported, interactive, visual representations to amplify cognition by

- Increasing the memory and processing resources available to operators,
- Reducing the search for information,
- Using visual representations to enhance the detection of patterns,
- Enabling perceptual inference operations,
- Using perceptual attention mechanisms for monitoring, and
- Encoding information in a manipulable medium.

Fig.2: Polar display for nuclear power, *Wickens et al. (1997)*, right one indicates parameter deviations

Fig.2 shows two states of a safety parameter monitoring display, *Wickens et al. (1997)*, designed to support nuclear power plant operators. A polygon connects the values, indicated by the distance from

the center, of eight parameters. As long as everything is all right a harmonic uniform polygon, as the one on the left, originates from the data. The right one indicates that there are parameters that deviate from normal. This visualization technique can be used to transform multiple different alphanumeric values into one graphical element.

3. Human-centered approach

The major goals of the work are to design ergonomic operating concepts and to realize prototypical user support systems. With the design of systems, in order to keep operators in the loop, the main focus is on an efficient handling of the tasks to do, optimized graphical user interfaces, and clearly guided operating sequences, *Schweingruber and Brütting (2004)*. Therefore, several discussions with experts as well as surveys of the procedures aboard take place.

It was decided to deploy on standard desktop PCs with flat screen display, mini keyboard and mouse. Experimentation with a test-bed for naval C2 components has shown that standard mice are highly accepted and well suited for support systems in naval environments (Grandt et al., 2003). An argument often put forward in favor of roll balls is that they are relatively robust against ship movements, as compared to mice only loosely connected by a cable. However, by taking adequate measures undesirable mouse displacements can be prevented. Furthermore, most people are already trained with mice.

Both workplaces are implemented in the modern and reliable programming language Java. A graphical development environment is used that allows quick testing of semi-manufactured products. GUIs that lack an understanding of the presumable operating procedures tend to be functionality-oriented and hence difficult to use and difficult to learn. According to the philosophy of rapid prototyping, subject matter experts, namely those operators in the ship's CIC assigned to perform the tasks to be supported, are frequently asked to examine the systems and give feedback, based on which systems can be optimized and enhanced. In the beginning, expert talks mostly take place ashore. Main partners are from Naval C2 Systems Command (KdoMFüSys) and the Federal Office of Defense Technology and Procurement (BWB).

Testing under realistic circumstances, as performed mainly in the next phase, is of course a part and parcel of human-centered development. Besides performance, reliability and stability of a system, acceptance and utilization by the navy personnel is of paramount importance. Experiments under realistic conditions are particularly valuable to find out about the two last mentioned.

The applied test procedure was designed based on navy specific requirements in consideration of tactical conditions. Limiting the group of test persons to seagoing personnel guarantees a homogenous collective with appropriate education and training as well as the most up to date experience. In experiments, navy personnel get a standardized personal introduction to systems and their functionality. Then operators observe an exemplary performance by the investigator before they have to work on realistic scenarios on their own.

To evaluate the effectiveness of a system, an extensive questionnaire was designed that subjects have to fill in directly subsequent to an experiment. The questionnaire consists of rating scales and questions. Test persons are asked to rate certain qualities of a system by means of the 2-level rating scale (see Fig.3) called ZEIS, *Pitrella (1989)*. On the first level, a relatively raw decision has to be made among poor, medium and good. On the second level, a finer differentiation takes place on an 11 point scale with adequate descriptions.

The main advantages of subjective rating scales are that they are well accepted by test persons, highly valid and provide hints for system development, *Pfendler (2000)*. The rating scale is used to review a system in regard to the five criteria suitability for the task, self-descriptiveness, controllability, conformity with user expectations, and error tolerance.

Fig.3: ZEIS rating scale for suitability for the task

These ergonomic criteria are defined in international standard *DIN EN ISO 9241-10 (1996)*, as follows:

- Suitability for the task: A dialogue is suitable for a task when it supports the user in the effective and efficient completion of the task.
- Self-descriptiveness: A dialogue is self-descriptive when each dialogue step is immediately comprehensible through feedback from the system or is explained to the user on request.
- Controllability: A dialogue is controllable when the user is able to initiate and control the direction and pace of the interaction until the point at which the goal has been met.
- Conformity with user expectations: A dialogue conforms with user expectations when it is consistent and corresponds to the user characteristics, such as task knowledge, education and experience, and to commonly accepted conventions.
- Error tolerance: A dialogue is error-tolerant if, despite evident errors in input, the intended result may be achieved with either no or minimal corrective action by the user.

Although these criteria are analysis oriented and do not contain any advice on how to deal with design conflicts, they provide an accredited assessment framework. Augmenting this norm that specifically applies to dialogue design, comments on the standards, *DATEch (2006)* give advice for whole systems. In addition to filling the rating scales, subjects have to answer questions on what in particular displeases them and what appeals to them, so that system designers not only know where deficits are but also get hints on how to address them.

4. Support system for classification based on electro-optical data

One of the workplaces in the demonstration facility will be filled with a support system for surface vessel classification based on electro-optical imagery. This system is based on two algorithms, *Günther et al. (1996)*, that were developed at the Helmut Schmidt University of the Federal Armed Forces in Hamburg (HSU-HH). One performs investigations of object contours (contour classifier), whereas the other investigates relative locations of visible marks (marks classifier). Both deliver result lists containing those ship classes that have most in common with the analyzed data. The algorithms have been tested extensively at the Bundeswehr Technical Centre for Ships and Naval Weapons (WTD 71) in Eckernförde and both proved to be reliable and accurate, *Römer (2001)*.

The original GUI was created for testing purposes by HSU-HH and extended by WTD 71. The focus was on proving the validity of the algorithms, usability aspects were not taken into account. The support system with this GUI carries the name KEOD 1.0 (classification using electro-optical data) according to the navy project within which the deployment is organized. The goal of the successfully completed UNbiS (user support concept for the application of optical sensor imagery for the classification and identification during surface reconnaissance) study was to create and realize an ergonomically optimized GUI. The resulting support system is called KEOD 2.0. The follow-up study UKIDuO (support for classification, identification and data acquisition of civilian and unconventional objects) aims to enhance the system, so that it can deal with non-conventional objects and will finally result in a KEOD 3.0.

4.1. Classifiers

The contour classifier needs the outer contour of the object to be classified (OTBC) and the information whether it has its bow left or right on the image as input. It compares the OTBC with reference silhouettes of all known ship classes in the database. These silhouettes are supplied binary and were derived from 3D models picturing representative role, pitch, and position angles. Bow and stern positions in the contour of the OTBC are fitted into the binary reference matrix so that the silhouette's length is standardized. To assign the data at hand to the most probable reference objects, an average-free normalized cross-correlation function is used, whereupon movements in x and y directions are performed until a maximum correlation coefficient is found. Sections where lines are close-by but not exactly one upon the other are accounted for devalued. In the final step, the result list is sorted according to the correlation coefficients so that the ship with the most similar contour heads the result list.

The marks classifier needs horizontal and vertical positions of visible marks on the image at hand as well as the rotation angle around the vertical axis. The support system's database contains the same data for all known ship classes. The classifier compares the data of the OTBC with that in the database. This is achieved by accumulating scaled Euclidean distances between OTBC and presumably corresponding database mark positions. The visibility of the individual ship parts with different position angles is considered, so that erroneous assignments of hidden ship parts are impossible. The operator's statement that a particular mark can be seen at a certain position is dealt with in a fault-tolerant way. Each pair of ship parts is allocated a confusion probability, from which a coefficient for the respective Euclidean distance is derived. The database ship classes are listed according to their total distance to the OTBC, so that the ship class with the most similar marks heads the result list.

4.2. GUI design

Beginning with sensor imagery at the one side and the two reliable algorithms described above on the other side, an ergonomically optimized GUI had to be designed.

To guide users through the steps necessary to feed the algorithms with data and to interpret the results, a sequence of clear cut process states (see Fig.4 on the left) has been developed in cooperation with subject matter experts. In every process state, only information that is needed to fulfill the particular subtask is displayed, *Mooshage and Schweingruber (2005)*.

To make it easy for operators to find required information and functionality, throughout all process states the overall layout is constant. The GUI is subdivided into four quadrants (see Fig.4 on the right) that stand for different subject areas, *Schweingruber and Mooshage (2005)*.

Fig.4: Process states (left) and GUI segmentation (right) of the support system

The 1st quadrant always contains imagery originating from the attached sensor. Depending on the process state currently performed, different manipulations can be made within this image. The 2nd quadrant is reserved for controls belonging to certain tasks. Contents of this area change according to the process state that is selected. In the 3rd quadrant, the overall controls can be found. This area consists of buttons to go to another process state, to load, save and store classification results, as well as to change the language used by the system, to change the colors between day-light and darkness mode, and to shut down the system. In the 4th quadrant, there is a database viewer in which all known ship classes can be browsed through. It is possible here to look at reference pictures, outline drawings, VRML models, as well as facts and data of all ship classes in the database. The sub-database choice function, which allows reducing the search space to a dedicated selection of ships, is also located in this quadrant.

In process state Surveillance, the operator's task is to choose appropriate imagery from the available material. A time-bar allows reviewing what has been recorded within the past few minutes. Through buttons that are similar to fast backward, fast forward, single image back, single image ahead etc. on typical remote controls or simply by clicking at any position in the time-bar it is possible to navigate the available imagery easily. Images can be further optimized by zooming and manipulating brightness and contrast. Once the operator has decided which image to take, the next process state can be selected.

Process state Orientation provides graphical support for the ascertainment of the rotation angles on all three axes, because both classifiers need information about the object's spatial orientation on the chosen image. In the 2nd quadrant, a model ship can be rotated to the appropriate position. It is possible to choose among three different ship types, so that the model is somewhat similar to the OTBC seen above. However, it is not intended to have more ship types for choice, lest operators waste too much time for choosing.

In process state Contour, the object's shape is supplied. The operator is asked to do that within the sensor image area in the 1st quadrant. It can be performed by inputting points that are connected by a polygon, by completely painting, or any combination of both. A preview line between the last clicked point and the current mouse position always indicates how it would look if clicked now. By clicking the right button of the input device, points can be removed. Painting can be removed by holding that button and moving the device, whereat the motion speed determines how fast painted sections are taken away. The 2nd quadrant provides undo and reset buttons as well as a button to close the polygon, so that it is not necessary to exactly hit the starting point again. In experiments, many subjects are of the opinion that it is possible to automate this task, but according to experts from the Research

Institute for Optronics and Pattern Recognition (FOM) in Ettlingen, there is no accurate algorithm for this job as of today. Especially the multitude of different image qualities prevents the successful application of a single algorithm to deal with all of them reliably.

Within process state Marks, the operator is asked to input identifiable marks. If process state Contour has not been completed before, it is necessary to highlight the frame of the OTBC first, otherwise it is derived from the silhouette. In the 2nd quadrant, a list of all position dependant marks such as bridge, turrets, masts etc. can be found. After a mark has been chosen, its position must be clicked at on the image at the 1st quadrant. An erroneously entered mark can be removed by placing the cursor nearby and clicking the right button. Therefore the temporarily nearest mark is always highlighted by a circle. Furthermore, an undo button allows removing the mark entered last, a remove button to remove all of a kind and a reset button to forget about all of them. It is not necessary to always move the cursor to the menu below the image to change to another kind of mark. By clicking the left or right button outside the frame, the next or previous line of the marks list is selected. The marks are sorted as they typically appear from bow to stern.

Process state Supplements can be used to incorporate any almost definite information into the classification process. If, for instance, the length of the OTBC can be estimated quite exactly, ships that are significantly shorter or longer can be neglected. Other criteria are any kinds of marks, nation, form of bow and stern, part of hull number, and ship grouping. Supplements can be used in addition to the algorithms or as stand-alone means for classification.

Finally, process state Result presents a list containing the most probable ship classes as figured out by algorithms and supplements function, and offers several opportunities to compare the material at hand with reference imagery, outline drawings, 3D models, and data records. The database viewer at the 4th quadrant changes its appearance, so that 3D model, outline drawing and the reference image with the most similar rotation angle of an entry selected in the result list can be seen in maximum size directly alongside the chosen original sensor image. It is important that the operator performs a visual comparison, because the scope covered by the algorithms is limited and humans have different skills as to pattern recognition. Once the operator has found the entry within the result list that seems to equate the OTBC, the decision can be saved. It is possible to add comments in written and spoken form, so that another operator investigating the material can be told the circumstances of the classification, e.g. why there was a particular interest in that special object.

Process state Store is not directly connected to the classification sequence. The amount of stored classifications is likely to increase quickly when vessels are, for instance, deployed to sea area monitoring operations. To ease the handling of such material, this process state provides a concise table that is sortable according to many different criteria. The content of the store can be burned on DVD to enable the crew to send it to naval command for further analyses.

5. Evaluation and enhancement of KEOD

This support system has been tested extensively during development. Many subjects mentioned potential details to augment and enhance the system in their questionnaires as well as in personal discussions with the investigator. Ideas were discussed with experts from KdoMFüSys, and the reasonable ones were realized. The co-author of this paper and his personnel belong to these experts and contributed many suggestions for improvement.

5.1. First experimentation campaign

Initial tests took place onboard German fast patrol boat *S71 Gepard* (P 6121) in the Baltic Sea in November 2004 as well as onboard the German frigate *Lübeck* (F 214) on the passage from Reykjavik/Iceland to Wilhelmshaven/Germany in December 2004. Some examples of ideas and suggestions brought forward by test persons can be found in the criticism below.

5.1.1. Fast patrol boat S71 Gepard

The questionnaire was filled out by 4 subjects. The results of the rating scales are as follows:

Suitability for the task: poor 0, medium 3, good 1. On the finer second level of the rating scale, suitability for the task was rated an average value of 6.4. It was criticized that there was (by then) no filter function to generate sub-databases. The concise and clear menu structure was praised.

Self-descriptiveness: poor 0, medium 1, good 3. On the finer second level of the rating scale, self-descriptiveness was rated an average value of 8.0. There was no concrete criticism.

Controllability: poor 0, medium 1, good 3. On the finer second level of the rating scale, controllability was rated an average value of 7.2. There was no concrete criticism.

Conformity with user expectations: poor 1, medium 2, good 1. On the finer second level of the rating scale, conformity with user expectations was rated an average value of 5.4. It was criticized that there was (by then) no information about work progress when saving or loading sequences.

Error tolerance: poor 1, medium 3, good 0. On the finer second level of the rating scale, error tolerance was rated an average value of 5.4. There was no concrete criticism.

In addition to the written comments, the investigator made notes of oral remarks. One operator proposed that it should be possible in the database area to type a letter on the keyboard and in this way make the visible part of the ship class list jump to the position where names start with this letter. This functionality was realized shortly after. Other comments praised that it is easy to learn how to operate the system, and that the direct comparison of pictures facilitates quick and save classification.

5.1.2. Frigate Lübeck

The questionnaire was filled out by 18 subjects. The results of the rating scales are as follows:

Suitability for the task: poor 0, medium 8, good 10. On the finer second level of the rating scale, suitability for the task was rated an average value of 7.0. It was criticized that (by then) it was not possible to have an object identified by entering its hull number and that the reminder to draw the waterline as first part of the contour was not pregnant enough.

Self-descriptiveness: poor 0, medium 9, good 9. On the finer second level of the rating scale, self-descriptiveness was rated an average value of 6.8. It was criticized that there is no information about work progress when saving the contour and that no tool tip functionality is implemented.

Controllability: poor 0, medium 7, good 11. On the finer second level of the rating scale, controllability was rated an average value of 7.3. It was criticized that it is not possible to print the screen content.

Conformity with user expectations: poor 0, medium 5, good 13. On the finer second level of the rating scale, conformity with user expectations was rated an average value of 7.5. It was criticized that there is no information about work progress when saving the contour.

Error tolerance: poor 2, medium 9, good 7. On the finer second level of the rating scale, error tolerance was rated an average value of 6.3. There was no concrete criticism.

In addition to the written comments, the investigator made notes of oral remarks. One operator complained that it was not possible to reach the detailed information about a certain ship class when in process state Result. The investigator then asked for a proposal on how to make it reachable. The operator proposed that double clicking the left mouse button on a result list entry should do it. The

functionality was realized in exactly the proposed way shortly after. Other comments again praised that it is easy to learn how to operate the system and that it facilitates quick and reliable classification.

5.2. Second experimentation campaign

The support system, meanwhile optimized and enhanced based on the findings of the first campaign, was evaluated again during SEF (standard mission training task group fleet), which is the most important annual exercise of the German navy. It took place in the Baltic Sea in September 2005. Besides the German participants, Scandinavian and East European navies as well as NATO task group SNMG1 (Standing NATO response force Maritime Group 1) were involved. The exercise was based on a complex geo-political scenario and consisted of a phase with guided exercises and a free-play phase.

Tests took place onboard several German vessels, namely tender *Donau* (A 511), fast patrol boats *S71 Gepard* (P 6121), *S76 Frettchen* (P 6126), *S73 Hermelin* (P 6123), as well as frigates *Hamburg* (F 220) and *Köln* (F 211). Crew onboard *S71 Gepard* had changed considerably since November 2004, so that no operators participated a second time; thus these experiments could be assumed independent from the earlier ones. Again many subjects mentioned potential details to augment and enhance the user support system in their questionnaires as well as in personal discussions with the investigator whereof examples can be found in the criticism below.

5.2.1. Tender Donau

The questionnaire was filled out by 9 subjects. The results of the rating scales are as follows:

Suitability for the task: poor 0, medium 1, good 8. On the finer second level of the rating scale, suitability for the task was rated an average value of 7.6. One subject suggested adding a functionality to reverse image colors, because it might be easier to spot the contour then.

Self-descriptiveness: poor 0, medium 4, good 5. On the finer second level of the rating scale, self-descriptiveness was rated an average value of 6.9. It was criticized that there is no online help. An online help is currently being implemented and will be part of the next version of the system.

Controllability: poor 0, medium 1, good 7. One operator felt unable to express an opinion. On the finer second level of the rating scale, controllability was rated an average value of 7.8. There was no concrete criticism.

Conformity with user expectations: poor 0, medium 1, good 7. One operator felt unable to express an opinion. On the finer second level of the rating scale, conformity with user expectations was rated an average value of 7.5. It was proposed to add more feedback when the operator has to wait while the system is loading or saving data.

Error tolerance: poor 1, medium 2, good 6. On the finer second level of the rating scale, error tolerance was rated an average value of 6.6. There was no concrete criticism.

5.2.2. Fast patrol boats S71 Gepard, S76 Frettchen and S73 Hermelin

The questionnaire was filled out altogether by 13 subjects. The results of the rating scales are as follows:

Suitability for the task: poor 5, medium 2, good 5. One operator felt unable to express an opinion. On the finer second level of the rating scale, suitability for the task was rated an average value of 5.6. Some subjects found the time needed to make necessary inputs too long; many asked for the contour to be deduced automatically. It was also said that the GUI is not comparable to any system aboard, because it is much more versatile, substantial and user friendly.

Self-descriptiveness: poor 1, medium 7, good 5. On the finer second level of the rating scale, self-descriptiveness was rated an average value of 6.3. It was praised that having listened to the instructions there were hardly any difficulties in using the system.

Controllability: poor 0, medium 2, good 11. On the finer second level of the rating scale, controllability was rated an average value of 7.7. One subject gave the opinion that drawing the contour might be easier with a touch screen monitor.

Conformity with user expectations: poor 0, medium 5, good 8. On the finer second level of the rating scale, conformity with user expectations was rated an average value of 7.0. It was criticized that the control step to close the filter is different from the one used otherwise.

Error tolerance: poor 4, medium 4, good 5. On the finer second level of the rating scale, error tolerance was rated an average value of 5.4. There was no concrete criticism.

5.2.3. Frigate Hamburg

The questionnaire was filled out by 19 subjects. The results of the rating scales are as follows:

Suitability for the task: poor 0, medium 1, good 18. On the finer second level of the rating scale, suitability for the task was rated an average value of 8.0. It was criticized that the operator had to push a button to close the contour polygon before being able to save it. The functionality has been changed in the meantime so that the polygon is automatically closed when saving. Furthermore it was proposed to add a so-called operator library for ships that are sighted but not yet in the database. Two subjects suggested augmenting nation lists with little images of nations' flags.

Self-descriptiveness: poor 0, medium 8, good 11. On the finer second level of the rating scale, self-descriptiveness was rated an average value of 7.3. Two subjects mentioned that there are no warnings before irreversible actions are executed. Both proposed retaining that unchanged, because they find the typical dialogue windows annoying. One subject proposed some minor changes to make the filter more concise, all of which were implemented in the meantime.

Controllability: poor 0, medium 7, good 12. On the finer second level of the rating scale, controllability was rated an average value of 7.2. It was suggested that it should be possible to rotate VRML models at any time.

Conformity with user expectations: poor 0, medium 3, good 16. On the finer second level of the rating scale, conformity with user expectations was rated an average value of 7.8. Some subjects asked for scores with the result list, but this piece of information is intentionally not given because it would reduce the weightiness of human visual comparison.

Error tolerance: poor 1, medium 3, good 14. One operator felt unable to express an opinion. On the finer second level of the rating scale, error tolerance was rated an average value of 7.4. There was no concrete criticism.

5.2.4. Frigate Köln

The questionnaire was filled out by 22 subjects. The results of the rating scales are as follows:

Suitability for the task: poor 0, medium 8, good 14. On the finer second level of the rating scale, suitability for the task was rated an average value of 7.5. It was praised that the complete functionality of the system can be reached by mouse. Many subjects asked for the contour to be deduced automatically or for means to reduce the time needed for manual input. Furthermore it was proposed to add an operator library.

Self-descriptiveness: poor 0, medium 7, good 15. On the finer second level of the rating scale, self-descriptiveness was rated an average value of 7.4. It was praised that images can be deleted without a query dialogue.

Controllability: poor 0, medium 2, good 20. On the finer second level of the rating scale, controllability was rated an average value of 8.0. It was proposed to add functionality to increase speed of fast forward and backward as well as to make single image back and ahead repeat buttons.

Conformity with user expectations: poor 0, medium 7, good 15. On the finer second level of the rating scale, conformity with user expectations was rated an average value of 7.7. It was criticized that there is not enough feedback when the operator has to wait while the system is loading or saving data.

Error tolerance: poor 1, medium 7, good 11. Three operators felt unable to express an opinion. On the finer second level of the rating scale, error tolerance was rated an average value of 6.9. There was no concrete criticism.

Changes and augmentations to the support system were realized until March 2006, the deadline for version KEOD 2.0. Afterwards a number of documents had to be written in order to prepare the necessary official testing by the responsible entities. More detailed reports about the two above mentioned experimentation campaigns can be found in earlier publications, *Schweingruber and Mooshage (2005)*, *Mooshage and Schweingruber (2006)*.

6. UNIFIL NAVOPS

The United Nations Interim Force in Lebanon, or UNIFIL, was created by the United Nations in 1978. Following the cease-fire ending the 2006 hostilities, the mission was enlarged in accordance with *UNSCR 1701 (2006)*, including a naval component to assist the Lebanese navy in securing the Lebanese coast and prevent arms smuggling.

The German navy provides a total of eight vessels to this naval operation, seven of them dispose of electro-optical sensors. In order to ease the recognition of unknown surface objects and to collect imagery to be used for database updates, it was decided to equip these vessels provisionally with KEOD 2.0 support systems. The deployment was declared a test, so that it was possible to distribute questionnaires with the system to get more feedback about how it is used. So far, returned questionnaires arrived from task group tender *Frankfurt am Main (A 1412)*, fast patrol boats *S74 Nerz (P 6124)*, *S77 Dachs (P 6127)*, *S78 Ozelot (P 6128)*, and *S80 Hyäne (P 6130)*, as well as frigate *Mecklenburg-Vorpommern (F 218)*, which already returned to its home port at Wilhelmshaven. *Mecklenburg-Vorpommern's* support system was transferred to succeeding frigate *Brandenburg (F 215)*. *Brandenburg* and frigate *Karlsruhe (F 212)* did not send any feedback yet. Altogether, 23 questionnaires have been returned so far.

According to the written and verbal reports received so far, it was easy for operators to learn how to use the system and get results of good quality with it. The responsible officers reported that the system, despite partially used without any briefing, was very helpful and that they look forward to getting it permanently. Unfortunately, some of the subjects found the two-level rating scale in the questionnaires not as easy. For security reasons, it was impossible to have an experimenter aboard. That is why merely from the text questions in the second part of the questionnaire results could be analyzed. Some of the most important outcomes are as follows:

- 65% of the subjects were of the opinion that the system includes all necessary functionality. The most mentioned point of criticism was that contours are not deduced automatically. This value is usually a lot better, when an experimenter has the chance to explain that contour deduction is too complex for automation given the abundance of different image qualities.
- 57% of the subjects were of the opinion that they did not have to perform any unnecessary steps.

Many subjects stated that they find manually drawing the contour unnecessary.

- 62% of the subjects were of the opinion that the amount of work invested is appropriate for the results gained. Again it was criticized that contours have to be drawn manually.
- 87% of the subjects were of the opinion that they did not have to perform tasks that the system should do instead.
- 77% of the subjects stated that they did not have to input anything that the system should already know.
- 67% of the subjects were of the opinion that no workarounds and tricks were necessary to achieve desired results. Interpreting this value one should bear in mind that due to incomplete briefings not all functions of the system were familiar to all subjects.
- 87% of the subjects were of the opinion that all necessary information is available well arranged on the GUI.
- 87% of the subjects stated that they could always easily spot what to do next.
- 90% of the subjects were of the opinion that messages from the system were always comprehensible.
- 82% of the subjects stated that they never needed the help of colleagues or the manual to find out how to go on.
- 86% of the subjects were of the opinion that all steps are arranged in a suggestive sequence.
- All subjects stated that they could continue interrupted actions without any problems at any later time.
- All subjects stated that they could undo steps whenever necessary.
- 61% of the subjects stated that they did not notice any longer waiting times.
- All subjects were of the opinion that functions and menu items are always at the appropriate / expected position.
- 80% of the subjects were always sure that the system is still running when they had to wait for a moment.
- 70% of the subjects stated that they were never surprised by a reaction of the system. It is to keep in mind that not all subjects got an adequate briefing.
- 86% of the subjects were of the opinion that they could always repair the consequences of incorrect inputs with slight effort.
- 86% of the subjects stated that all necessary functions are available whenever needed.
- All subjects had the impression that they could explore the system by trial and error without any risk.

As indicated before, briefings were scarce due to tough time constraints when the system was installed. Also there is no online help included in the deployed version. The predominantly positive feedback, despite these circumstances, confirms once again, that the human-centered approach in fact leads to systems with adequate functionality and intuitive handling that are highly accepted and appreciated by operators.

7. Conclusion and outlook

Because of new types of missions accompanied by more sophisticated actors and sensors the work human decision makers have to perform onboard naval vessels is becoming significantly more demanding. Hence providing operators with adequate support is an essential requirement for 21st century naval C2 systems. Full automation is impossible because many of the tasks to be done feature eminently high complexity. Critical steps and final decisions must always be performed by human operators. But disencumbering them and appropriately helping them to create a correct understanding of the situation can make the difference between a catastrophe and doing exactly the right thing. Relief can be achieved by improving the visualization of complex dynamic information and easing human system interaction.

While the workplace meant to support the overall tasks of naval C2 is still in the design phase, the support system for classification of surface targets based on electro-optical imagery has reached a

deployable status. It will be officially deployed as soon as all bureaucratic hurdles are overcome. Provisionally deployed systems have proved that the system is of great benefit within the scope of UNIFIL naval operations. Version KEOD 3.0, that is currently being realized, will include new features, such as an online help, capability to classify non-military and unconventional vessels, as well as an operator library.

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Collaborative Design - A Practical Approach based on the Use of Replicated Databases for Concurrent Design

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the two traditional approaches, concurrent and distributed work in ship design, but focuses on the concurrent solution as the evolution of the basic technologies such as databases and communications points to a more efficient solution. A shipbuilding oriented 3D CAD/CAM system, integrating the whole ship product model in a single database, can facilitate the necessary coordination between the different agents, but it also introduces challenges to be resolved before an efficient solution can be reached. In this respect, the experience of SENER is described. SENER is a company that plays the double role of software developer and ship design agent, and develops tools to adapt a relational database, as well as the associated database management software, to a remote concurrent design environment using database replication techniques and more precisely the multimaster replication working in synchronous mode. From a shipyard perspective, as the owner of the information, there are additionally other issues to be solved, such as the control of access to restricted areas of the project due to both confidentiality reasons and the maturity of the information already stored. The scalability of the solution is also analyzed in order to test the performance of the described solution in an environment involving a large number of users.

1. Introduction

Under the concept of global economy, enterprises are distributing design and production environments around the world in different business areas. Shipbuilding industry is a good example for complex distributed processes as more than 75% of the creation of value is performed by numerous suppliers.

The pressure to reduce lead-times and to cut design costs combined with more complex vessels is demanding a similar reduction in the design cycles. On the other side, there has been an important reduction in the direct workforce capacity of the shipyards, pushing them towards an outsourcing strategy by subcontracting more and more significant parts of the design work. As a consequence, today's ship design is an activity that involves collaborative participation of multiple design centres worldwide.

Collaborative design can be analyzed by means of two approaches that are not considered mutually exclusive:

- Concurrent design, that allows separate teams to work simultaneously on the same design and accessing the same ship product model from geographically dispersed sites
- Distributed design, by splitting the ship design and engineering activities into distinct areas allowing thus, several design teams to work at different locations

Although the distributed design, either based on distribution by disciplines (functional), by zones (geographical) or by design stages (sequential) can be the only solution in environments where the communications are expensive or hard to establish due to inadequate technological infrastructure, distribution implies data duplication which may cause coordination problems. Therefore, this paper focuses on the concurrent design approach and describes the experience of SENER, a company that plays the double role of software developer (FORAN System) and ship design agent, in the development of tools to adapt a relational database as well as the associated database management software, to remote concurrent design environments using database replication techniques.

2. Background

Concurrent design has always been an important issue for Integrated Shipbuilding CAD Systems. This chapter describes the evolution of CAD Systems in relation to its architecture, data storage methods and available IT infrastructure.

2.1. Shipbuilding CAD Systems. Architecture

From an architectural point of view, CAD Systems were originally developed as standalone applications, conceived to work in a local environment. The evolution towards distributed environments has not been parallel to other type of software due mainly to two reasons:

- The high volume and the complexity of data managed by the application, which was considered as an inconvenience to store it in a database
- The demanding requirements in terms of interactivity, solid modelling and advanced graphic capabilities

These characteristics prevented, in a first stage, the possible evolution towards client-server architectures and, later on, the evolution to more advanced architectures like n-tier and distributed models. The presumed difficulty to efficiently store geometric information in relational databases was the main reason for which CAD Systems have not evolved towards client-server architectures, and the impossibility to use thin client architectures (due to the high demand of local resources) prevented the evolution towards multi-tier application models.

2.2 Data storage

Originally developed to store the information in files, CAD Systems evolved to the use of databases. In the first instances, relational databases were used to store attributes while in some of the second instances, proprietary databases were developed to store 3D Ship Model geometrical and topological information as well as attributes.

More recently, there has been a trend to replace proprietary databases with commercial databases that provide standard access languages and database server capabilities. Although in a first view, relational databases may appear to be inefficient to store geometry, modern CAD systems usually store topology and parametric information rather than geometry, which leads to a drastic reduction in the size of the information and it facilitates the management of the topological relations by means of tables stored in a relational database.

The main reasons behind the migration to relational databases can be shown in the Table I:

Table I: Comparative analysis of the different data storage methods

FEATURE	SINGLE FILES	PROPRIETARY DATABASES	STANDARD SQL DATABASES
MULTI-USER	Low	High	High
DATA INTEGRITY	Low	Medium	High
PRODUCT MODEL CONSISTENCY	Low	Medium	High
SCALABILITY (DATA/USERS)	Medium/Medium	Medium/Medium	High/High
DATA AVAILABILITY	Low	Low	High
PERFORMANCE	High	Medium	Medium-High

In the case of FORAN System, the process of evolution started at the end of the 1970's when the

concept of single database was implemented by means of a proprietary database and later on, at the end of the 1990's, that solution was replaced by the use of a commercial relational database (ORACLE) based in the following advantages:

- Platform independence
- High scalability (of users / of data)
- High reliability regarding data integrity
- High performance
- Data extraction available to third party systems
- Comprehensive administration tools
- Easier user privileges (roles) configuration
- Open to remote access

The last listed advantage has proven to be one of the most important with respect to the concurrent design, particularly once introduced the use of replication techniques as described in Chapter 3.

2.3 IT Infrastructure

The development and use of Integrated CAD Systems able to create 3D Ship Model, has been closely linked with the development of Local Area Networks (LAN) and, later on, Wide Area Networks (WAN) with sufficient bandwidth to manage the flow of information.

This flow of information in a LAN depends on a number of factors including:

- The complexity of the 3D Model and the number of concurrent users, which vary throughout the project life cycle. While at the beginning the number of users is small and the model has few elements, near the end the number of users is still near the maximum when the model is almost complete
- The volume and frequency of transactions between the users and the 3D Model, which in turn depends on the structure of the database (topological models need smaller size databases) and on the frequency of 3D Model updates. This, again, depends on software design and workstation characteristics
- The location of the application software when most of the process is done at the workstations. If the software resides in the server, the network traffic is increased
- The switching capabilities of the network. The traffic decreases as the switching capabilities increase

From the above considerations it follows that the bandwidth necessary in a LAN and, even more, in a WAN, is an important consideration when selecting the hardware configuration. In addition, when working in WAN environments, mean latency times are even more critical than bandwidth requirements. Use of Virtual Private Networks based on MPLS Technology is recommended, with high-speed connections. Latency times in the range of 8 to 12 Ms are required in WAN environments to get a reasonable performance.

To perform concurrent design, that means all users accessing to the same database, and in addition to LAN and WAN scenarios, there is a third one based in the use of Terminal Servers (TS) technology as shown in Fig.1.

Main advantages of this solution are as follows:

- CAD System is not installed in the Remote Sites
- Bandwidth requirements for Terminal Server clients are rather low, around 150 Kbps per user
- Terminal Servers can be connected to the Database Server at a high speed (1 Gbps), improving thus considerably the access of the remote users to the Database

Fig.1: Approach based in the use of Terminal Server technology

The main drawback of TS scenario is that intensive graphic operations, including dynamic zoom and rotation, may resent in performance (OpenGL). To solve this drawback, FORAN provides some shortcuts for intensive graphic operations to facilitate the use of Terminal Servers. New advances in TS technology could also improve considerably the performance of 3D applications in the near future by using new cluster rendering methods. As a summary, the use of TS could be an efficient solution where the available bandwidth is not very high.

3. Replication

FORAN System has already undergone a fundamental re-engineering process in order to be used effectively for concurrent design as it allows working in a WAN exactly in the same way as in a LAN. The bandwidth requirements are considerably lower than for other systems, mainly due to its largely topological character (rather than geometrical). The volume of the database is lower by an order of magnitude and the amount of information to be transferred decreases accordingly reducing thus the required bandwidth by an additional order of magnitude. In this way, a large number of users can be working concurrently from remote locations on the same ship model.

After the migration of FORAN System from a proprietary database to a commercial relational database (Oracle) the following collaborative working scenarios are available:

- LAN scenario. All users work in a Local Area Network
- WAN scenario + Terminal servers. Database only accessible within master LAN. Remote FORAN execution via terminal server (Citrix).
- WAN scenario + Remote database access (small/medium number of users. Only one database instance in master LAN but accessible from other LANs
- Distributed scenario using standalone databases. One database instance in each site. FORAN data exchange tools can be used to keep the databases updated.

A new scenario has been added by integrating Oracle database replication capabilities to synchronise distributed shipbuilding FORAN projects through a WAN environment. Note that a FORAN project corresponds to one ship design and is the smallest replicated item within the FORAN System. There are several ways of exploiting Oracle replication, but the first FORAN release working under replication has been developed by using Synchronous Multi-Master Replication.

3.1. Multi-Master Replication

Multi-master replication is the ability to allow data in multiple databases to be automatically kept in synchronization. In a multi-master replication system, if a row gets inserted into one of the databases in the system, that row will be automatically propagated to all of the other databases in that system. Updates and deletes to the data in any of the databases will be propagated in the same way.

A multi-master replication environment within FORAN is set up by configuring a Project (ship) created in several databases to be part of a “replication group”. One of the projects (in a specific database) in the group is defined as the “master project,” and all of the other projects in the group are classified as “slave projects.” The main difference between the two types of projects is that sequences and locks are not replicated by Oracle and they exist only in the master project whereas slave projects include synonyms of them or access directly to the master objects. These missing features in Oracle replication have been solved in FORAN since they are key features for the right functionality of unique objects identifiers (sequences) and work-session clashes (locks).

Multi-master replication is the most complex, in terms of configurability, of all the methods provided by Oracle (read-only and/or updateable materialised views) but it is the only one that covers most of the functionality required by FORAN (e.g. trigger replication). To relieve the complexity of configuring a multi-master replication environment the FORAN database administration tool (FDDBA) has been re-designed from scratch in order to hide the Oracle internals from the FORAN administrator standpoint.

Fig.2: New FORAN Database Administration tool (FDDBA)

In the Fig.3, project PR01 is replicated both in Server A and in Server B. PR01 in Server A is the master project of the replication group and includes the actual sequences and lock-mechanism. In any other aspect, designers work locally in PR01 and all the changes are automatically updated in the other servers.

Fig.3: A FORAN replicated project

3.2. Synchronous vs. Asynchronous Replication

There are two basic ways for the transactions to get propagated to remote databases: “synchronously” and “asynchronously”. Synchronous replication occurs by causing each transaction to be applied to all the projects in a replication group immediately. The way this is achieved is by using Oracle’s two-phase commit functionality, to ensure that all of the database servers in question can apply a given transaction. If any of the sites in the group cannot accept the transaction (such as because the site’s database has crashed, or the network connection to a database is down), then none of the projects in the replication group will be able to accept the transaction and therefore the transaction will not be able to take place.

The way asynchronous replication works is that all the transactions that occur on a project are temporarily placed in a buffer, called the deferred transaction queue. Periodically, such as once per minute, all of the transactions in a database deferred transaction queue are sent to all of the other databases. Finally, the transactions in a deferred transaction queue that have already been sent to other databases must be periodically purged to prevent the queue from growing too large.

Although asynchronous replication offers some advantages compared to synchronous replication:

- It has been available for a much longer time
- It uses less network bandwidth. It stores multiple transactions and propagates them all as a group so that it requires fewer connections to be established
- It provides higher performance when parallel propagation is used (not available in synchronous replication)
- It provides for high availability of the replication group. With asynchronous replication, if one of the sites in the replication group crashes, all of the other sites will still be able to accept updates

FORAN replication functionality is based on synchronous replication since asynchronous replication has one major drawback: it opens up the possibility for data conflicts. There are three basic types of conflict:

- An “update” conflict occurs when the same row is updated on two (or more) different databases before either one of those updates can be propagated to the other databases
- A “uniqueness” conflict occurs when propagation of data would cause two different rows to have the same value for a column, when that column has a unique constraint on it
- A “delete” conflict occurs when one or more rows get deleted from one database, but when Oracle tries to propagate the deletes it cannot find all of the rows in the remote databases

Because there is a possibility of data conflicts, Oracle has provided “conflict resolution handlers” to try to resolve data conflicts. In general, these conflict resolution handlers work well for resolving update conflicts, but they do not work well with uniqueness conflicts (and there are no handlers provided for delete conflicts). Furthermore, even after using one of the methods for uniqueness conflicts, there will still be differences in the data in one database as compared to the data in another database.

4. Security of the information

Parallel to the increasing of the needs to outsource the design, new demands for access and change control arise. From a shipyard perspective, as the owner of the information, the control of access to parts of the project becomes a key issue, due to several reasons:

- Critical areas for which access must be restricted
- Distribution of the work among the users
- Restrict undesired modifications according to maturity
- Subcontracting policies for certain parts of the ship

4.1. The concept of Control Unit

The FORAN approach to the access and change control tasks has been developed in a new module, FCM, that introduces the concept of “Control Unit”, a new entity that represents the area to be controlled. Each unit is defined by a discipline and an activation level, it is managed by one or several unit managers, and it contains the configuration to be applied for access and change control as shown in Table II.

Table II : Control Unit, Disciplines and Activation levels

DISCIPLINE Element types to be controlled, i.e. HVAC	Unit managers	General data
ACTIVATION LEVEL Specific work area inside the discipline where controls will be activated, i.e. Zone Z034, System S001		Change control Configuration
ACTIVATION STATUS Activated, deactivated, unlinked		Access control Configuration

The activation level defines what level of the FORAN hierarchy is to be controlled and often coincides with a working area (e.g. Zone & System). An activation level can belong to more than one discipline and it may be used to define different control units such as:

- Hull Structure – Materials – Table of standard gross plates
- Hull Structure 3D Model – Deck and Zone
- Outfitting standards – Components – Model library tree
- Outfitting 3D Model – Equipment - Zone & System
- Electrical – Cables – ‘From’ or ‘to’ device – Zone & System
- Accommodation – Accommodation deck

4.2. User roles

For the purpose to allow access control and change control, three different types of user roles can be defined:

- The Administrator defines the areas to be controlled, creates units and assigns unit managers to the already defined units
- Unit Manager responsibility includes the configuration of their units' access as well as the definition of the settings related to change control
- Designers will be allowed to read/modify only the units for which has permissions enough

In the case of large organisations working in complex projects, the configuration and setup of the different concepts could be a tedious and heavy task as a huge number of units, users and lots of variations and combinations units-users-settings must be defined. To facilitate this task, the module FCM provides advanced tools including unit multiselection, possibility to share settings between units and management of user roles by groups.

Fig.4: Access control and change control acting together

4.3. Access and Change control

The Unit Managers can at any time decide to activate the access control to an unit. Then, a designer running any FORAN module will be allowed to read or modify the corresponding unit only if the Unit Manager has previously authorized him.

In addition to the access control, FCM introduces several simple but efficient change control tasks, including the registry of changes made on units, freezing and unfreezing of units and generation of reports. One of the main tasks of the change control system is to avoid the modification of project elements that have reached a certain level of maturity and, consequently, the unit manager has marked as ‘frozen’.

The concept of external freezing (or locking) has been developed in order to allow the link with external applications like PLM or ERP systems. This link has been solved by means of a flag (or a set of flags) stored in an intermediate database table. These flags will be externally updated in order to indicate if a modification of an element would be acceptable to the corresponding external applications. Other flags might also be used in order to, for example, allow changes over a unit, but only after a warning message has been shown to the user. Fig.4 shows how access and change control work.

5. Scalability

The first release of FORAN System providing Project Replication, covers replication of one project in two-server (one master project – one slave project). Replicating a FORAN project in more than one database server is limited by the complexity hit on Oracle configuration and database administration. Future FORAN releases will include 1-n project replication.

Fig.5: A FORAN project replicated in three servers

In Fig.5, master project PR01 at Server A is replicated at servers B and C. Changes at any of the servers are immediately transferred to the other servers. In addition, Project Replication within the FORAN System allows replicating different projects between different database servers.

In Fig.6, Server B includes simultaneously a master project (PR04) replicated at Server C and a slave project (PR01). The master project PR04 is in this case replicated at Servers A and C. The master project PR01 located at Server A is in this example replicated at Servers B and C.

Performance is one of the key factors affecting the success of a shipbuilding CAD application running on a collaborative environment and detailed tests must be carried out to demonstrate it. However, it is not feasible and cost effective to reproduce real working conditions with a large number of users working in a project. To test the performance and to optimize the application behaviour, SENER decided to develop a specific project (FORAN Scalability, Distributed Work and Remote Access Project) to improve dramatically all FORAN aspects related to the collaborative work of many users in the same project.

Fig.6: Different FORAN replicated project layouts

One of the key initiatives in this project, aiming to collect metrics on the access of many users to a ship project, was the development of a Load Simulation Tool with the following three objectives:

- To perform Scalability tests with large number of users in LAN environments
- To perform Scalability tests with short/medium number of users in WAN environments
- To perform Scalability tests with large number of users in Replicated environments

Fig.7: Oracle Load Analyser

In the case of replication, tests were done by simulating the access of 200 users to a Database located on a server and at the same time simulating the access of other 100 users to a replicated Database located in another server. Connection between both servers had a bandwidth of 4 Mbps with latency times of 8 ms (round trip). The main conclusions of these tests are:

- Mean access times for read operations were similar to the ones obtained for the same number of users in LAN environments. They can be considered as excellent.
- Mean access times for write operations were slightly higher than the ones obtained in LAN environments, but still acceptable.

6. Conclusions

Based on SENER experience with FORAN, the best method to carry out collaborative engineering in complex projects is based in the use of database replication techniques in a WAN environment connecting several sites, that is, accessing to a master database, replicated in the other sites, that stores the ship product model generated by the contribution of the different design groups, working from their own premises.

By means of communication networks with the appropriate bandwidth and mean latency times, subcontractors can access in a controlled way to the ship's 3D model, which notably facilitates the coordination and the data integrity. The contribution of the replication is significant, as it use reduces the level of communications requirements, because more than 90% of the traffic between the database server and the client is due to reading operations that, under the replication scenario, are performed locally reducing thus the amount of information transferred by a significant factor. The scalability tests demonstrate that no performance degradations have been observed when working with large number of users.

An important aspect of all this process refers to the considerations with respect to the security and access and change control, for zones or for any other functional criteria, as there may be restrictions to access to critical areas of the project as well as to avoid undesired modifications once the information is considered mature enough.

With no doubt, the possibility to perform remote concurrent engineering work on common product models is leading shipyards and engineering contractors to a different manner of co-operation, enabling them to undertake larger and more complex projects, demanding more resources and different and complementary design groups. This strategy allows the bringing together of a series of design groups, including very small engineering companies or even individuals working at home, assigning to each of them only that portion of the work which is routine for them and well within their experience, facilities and capabilities.

New FORAN release incorporates database replication capabilities allowing an efficient collaborative design.

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Integrated Technical Information Management to Support Class Approval Processes in Shipbuilding

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Abstract

Class approval processes in shipbuilding introduce new requirements for technical information management systems. Currently, these requirements are not sufficiently addressed by traditional PDM/PLM solutions. Classification societies have to manage classic, product-oriented structures (as designed, as built), associated simulation data (FEM, substituted systems), and relationships to part catalogues and material databases. Additionally, the underlying information model has to be extensible and adaptable during production use in order to satisfy short-term requirements from different certification projects. In the context of the TIS project at Germanischer Lloyd we implemented a "Technical Information System" that is based on PDTEC's ice.NET Platform. TIS integrates data models from various legacy systems and provides configurable XML and Webservice interfaces to associated simulation programs. TIS also addresses the general and shipbuilding-specific requirements mentioned above. In addition to the information model and system architecture we have developed we present how to provide functional prototypes within a short time frame and limited budget that enables process-specific organization of information in a networked, project-oriented folder structures with access control mechanisms, tracking and audit support. On the basis of a project example we demonstrate the requirements-driven extension of the data model with the UML-based development tool ice.NET Studio.

1. Introduction

As a classification society in the maritime field, GL creates authoritative standards for ship technology, safety and quality and defines own rules and guidelines in line with the latest technical developments. In the classification process, marine and inland waterway vessels are monitored according to the GL rules. This is mandatory for newbuildings and for the fleet in service. All of these ships are entered into GL's Register. After establishing conformity to GL rules, a class certificate is awarded. The following stakeholders are affected by ship classification:

- ship owners and charterers
- shipyards and sub-suppliers
- banks
- maritime insurance companies
- national maritime safety authorities which issue so-called 'trading certificates' as a prerequisite for the operation of a ship

In the certification process – from an IT standpoint – classification societies have to manage classic, product-oriented structures (as designed, as built), associated simulation data (FEM, substituted systems), and relationships to part catalogues and material databases. Additionally, the underlying information model has to be adaptable during production use in order to satisfy short-term requirements from different certification projects.

2. Objectives

Classification societies that serve customers around the globe have to deal with a very heterogeneous data structure. Their partners can vary from first tier suppliers - at the head of innovation up to a small company far away from modern technologies. All these partners use different software products with a huge variety of product descriptions.

The GL needs a software system that is able to store the entire description of an approval. This includes technical parameters, calculation values, schedules and many others. For such a process the system needs a flexible data model that is able to deal with manifold and permanently changing information.

Classification societies have offices all over the world. Therefore the system must have a web based system architecture for user interfaces and server connections. At the same time the approval process includes manifold tasks. The presentation of data has to be in accordance with the user's task which results in the necessity to produce variations of different views into the data quickly.

The software system has to manage different types of technical information. This includes:

1. Parts and components (Gear unit, pump, propeller, ...)
2. Ship systems (Propulsion system, steering gear system, hydraulic system, ...)
3. Measurement data (Plate thickness, corrosion, ...)
4. Material data (Physical properties, chemical properties, ...)
5. Hull structure data (Deck, panel, plate, stiffener, ...)
6. Data for hydrostatic calculation (Hull, rooms, loading, ...)
7. Simulation model (FE model, CFD model, ...)

Parts, components, ship systems and materials dominate the focus of the current implementation. But the system is also restricted by some general requirements such as a structured and controlled data access for each staff member, an advanced change management which considers the approval status, the version management and others. The system has to support multiple references to a single object instance and also to functions that check and compare data between different approval processes. Another important feature is its preparation for long-term archival storage.

Fig.1: Design information of a steering gear, <http://www.hatlapa.de>

However the basic function is to deal with the different kinds of approvals. All of these based on the GL rules and on a variety of numerical analysis and calculations. The approval could be valid for a part design and who's function is described in terms of technical drawings, data sheets or CAD models. But approvals may also be applied to less physical objects such as hydraulic or electrical

schema or even model abstractions such as shaft alignment calculations. Further more the installation of a part on board of a ship or its use as a component in a system, abstract or actually installed on the ship can be objective to an approval. For a better understanding of this process, we will present the example of a steering gear. Fig.1 shows the design of a steering gear described in a technical drawing and in CAD models. Fig.2 shows some parameters which are important for the function description.

Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.

Hydraulic Steering Gear	
Manufacturer HATLAPA	Type electro hydraulic
Working Torque 3.540.000 Nm	Working Pressure 20.000.000 Pa
Hydraulic Cylinder	
Material GGG40	
Inner Diameter 0,2 m	Outer Diameter 0,25 m
Electric Motor	
Type A.C. squirrel cage induction moto	Construction Class B3
Rotational Speed 29,16 rps	Power 170.000 kW
Ambient Temperatur 45 °C	Duty Code S6-25% Protection Code IP54
Pump	
Volume Flow 1,22	Type axial piston
Plunger	
Length 2,01 m	Free Length 1,025 m
Diameter 0,151 m	Thickness Of Pin Lug 0,155 m
Plunger Pin	
Material 42CrMo4V	Diameter 0,145 m
Pivot	
Material GS45	
Pivot Arm	
Distance 0,325 m	Number 4
Thickness 0,14 m	Width 0,2 m

Fig.2: Parameters of steering gear

A physical instance of a steering gear is installed on board of a ship, Fig.3. Such an installation of a steering gear is subject to be approved by GL. The GL surveyor finally adds serial number, photos, notes and comments to the product data of this approval. At the same time the steering gear may be a component in different systems. It may be a component in the manoeuvring system. Simultaneously it can be a component in the hydraulic system and many other systems such as the electrical system or the safety system. In each system the steering gear contributes differently to the approval.

Fig.3: Installation of a steering gear, <http://www.hatlapa.de>

Fig.4: A steering gear as a system component, , <http://www.hatlapa.de>

The objective in the TIS project is to provide the information that meets the requirements from above and at the same time to be flexible enough to be extended to meet new demands that may arise in a future application context. For the project's success it is critical that application domain experts (e.g. shipbuilding engineers) cooperatively work together with IT specialists in order to create suitable requirements and validate intermediate results during all project phases. The usual requirements regarding time, quality and resources apply for here as it does for any other industrial software project.

3. IT challenges

The biggest challenge for the IT solution is the requirement for multi-dimensional information management caused by the planned scope of the TIS system. Multi-dimensional information management (MDIM) means that a variety of different information aspects that can be grouped into independent dimensions have to be integrated into a single software system.

Fig.5: IT challenge: multi-dimensional information management

Examples for dimensions that were relevant for the TIS project are:

- Managing information and providing functionality for different application domains,
- Information structuring principles caused by the different nature of specific data chunks,

- Temporal aspects (influenced by how information is handled over time),
- Integration approaches and technology ,
- The software system landscape that has to be integrated with the TIS system.

Table I shows specific aspects of these dimensions.

Table I: Examples for dimensions of information management

Application domains: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanical Engineering • Ship Structure Engineering • Hazardous Materials Management • Approval / Certification Process Management • Organizational Management (Yards, Owners, Manufacturers) • Production Structures • Simulation / Calculation 	Structuring principles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object-oriented • Document content • Serialized / Table-style • Relational Bulk Data • Hierarchical Data (e.g. XML) • Messages • Process / Transactional Data 	Temporal aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initially loaded data • Master data • Reference data (Material/Substances) • Continuous Information (Measurement Campaigns) • Model (!) extended over time • Effectivity
Integration approaches: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realtime • Service-oriented • Data exchange • Offline / Replication • Office integration 		System landscape: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ship Information System • Calculation Programs • Cross-Org./Reference Systems (e.g. Material/Substance DB) • ERP (Parts, Customers) • Legacy applications

The complexity inferred by the MDIM requirement arises due to the fact that aspects from different dimensions can appear in virtually any combination. For example product structure data that is represented by an object-oriented model which was initially loaded from a legacy system usually has to be transferred through data exchange to a simulation program. Or hazardous material substance data that is hierarchically structured in a reference classification system may be accessed and updated in real time through Webservice interaction. The ideal solution to the MDIM problem is an approach that enables the software system to separate the implementation of the different aspects into suitable and manageable modules. The complete (complex) system solution is then a combination of these modules. Therefore a platform is needed as a design and development basis for these modules. Interoperability based on common abstractions is the main objective of this approach.

4. Software Platform

One of the first – and one of the most important – steps of designing such an information system is the choice of the underlying software platform. This choice fundamentally affects all of the further characteristics of the software project: the quality of the resulting system, the necessary resources and the duration of the design and implementation phase. All depend on the architecture of the platform.

4.1. Platform Selection, Make or Buy Decision

There is a variety of options in choosing a platform and the implementation strategy. The most extreme positions are:

- Completely implement the resulting software system on top of generic base technology.
- Buy a full-featured software application that fulfils the requirements as much as possible and customize or extend it to close the gap between actual and required functionality.

Another option that combines the positions mentioned above is to utilize a PLM platform that provides an application basis and reusable building blocks ("components"). In order to fulfil the specific system requirements a suitable set of components has to be assembled and complemented by custom development. Fig.6 shows the implications of the platform selection on one of the most important project characteristics: the effort in time and resources in order to implement the required system functionality.

Fig.6: Implications of platform selection on implementation effort

If the resulting software system is completely implemented on base technology ("100% Make"), the total effort is dominated by design and implementation activities. The software components that were used by following this approach do not have to be customized because of their generic nature. Examples of possible components are:

- Relational database engine (Oracle, Microsoft SQL Server)
- Programming languages and environments (C++, C#, J2EE, Microsoft Visual Studio, Eclipse)
- Web server technology (Microsoft IIS/ASP.NET, IBM WebSphere, BEA WebLogic)

The possibilities to lower the implementation effort by architecture and design decisions are limited because the total effort is mostly determined by the required system functionality. Theoretically, this development effort can be completely avoided by buying an out-of-the-box solution that covers all requirements. However, after analysing the specific requirements of the TIS project it was evident that there was no single application available on the market that comes close to what the resulting software system should be capable of. Therefore the additional effort that was necessary to adapt an off-the-shelf PDM/PLM solution to the specific project requirements was estimated not to be substantially lower than the development effort to implement the solution on top of generic base technology. The necessary resources would just be shifted to the "Customizing" effort.

A suitable PLM platform is supposed to provide a powerful and versatile design and implementation base as well as a rich set of reusable building blocks. On the other hand the platform should not constrain the functionality in the direction of a specific solution domain or into specific application semantics. Therefore, a suitable platform provides richer design and implementation support than generic base technology and a more flexible approach than customizing a PDM/PLM solution. The most promising option was to choose the PLM platform approach. This approach offers the possibility to reduce the effort that is necessary to cover the specific requirements: The customizing effort can be reduced by providing an innovative platform architecture that removes the need for tedious implementation and integration activities. The development effort can be reduced by providing reusable software components that already offer substantial portions of the resulting solution's functionality, Fig.7.

Fig.7: Improving the efficiency of a software platform

4.2 The ice.NET Platform

ice.NET is a software platform for information systems that have to meet requirements beyond the scope of traditional PDM/PLM. While classic PDM/PLM systems usually focus on established data structures and information patterns, the ice.NET platform provides abstractions, components and tools that enable the development of software solutions that exactly reflect the required information structures of the specific application domain. Especially the multi-dimensional integration of different informational aspects (section 2) is a fundamental design criterion for the development of the ice.NET platform.

Fig.8: The ice.NET Platform Structure

4.3 Platform Architecture

An important aspect for a successful development of the TIS system is the ability to customize and extend the information model according to

- new knowledge about the application domain, gathered during the system development,
- user requirements and comments that occur during test/review phases,
- new project-specific requirements, detected during the productive use of the TIS.

The most fundamental problem of traditional software architectures that prevents systems from meeting the requirements for easy and inexpensive model extension is caused by the 1:1 mapping between the system architecture and the software architecture.

Fig.9: Classic system / software architecture – information silos

While the system architecture is determined by state-of-the-art deployment patterns (web application servers, server farms, etc.) flexibility is available in the area of software architecture. However, in traditional PDM/PLM architectures the layers of software architecture reflect the layers of system architecture:

- Data access components (data layer) that contains the a relational database schema
- Business logic on an application layer
- Presentation functionality on the GUI layer.

The semantic/functional aspects of the software system is structured orthogonally to these layers and end up with software parts on each layer for each software function (product structure, classification, change management, etc.). Extending the data model infers schema changes and therefore requires modifications on all of the three layers. If the extension affects adjacent functions and their schema part the required modifications become expensive and time-consuming. In contrast to the traditional approach the software architecture suggested by the ice.NET platform differs fundamentally from the system architecture. The software architecture is driven by the following definition of the term platform:

A platform is a design and implementation basis as well as an integration environment for components that implement common abstractions.

A software platform typically consists of

- an architecture that specifies the base abstractions and the component interfaces
- a base implementation that provides generic parts for the software systems based on the platform
- a methodology that documents how to use the platform as a basis for software systems and how to successfully develop platform-compliant, reusable components

The basic layer ("platform") of ice.NET defines the base abstractions. These abstractions consist of the most fundamental parts of the Unified Modelling Language (UML), such as

- Objects, object types and attributes
- Relationships and relationship types
- Packages as a grouping mechanism for model entities (e.g. object types, relationship types) and package dependencies

Fig.10: ice.NET software architecture – components based on common abstractions

Additional abstractions that go beyond the scope of UML are defined as well:

- Folders, files and vaults
- Users, teams, roles and access control lists (ACLs)

The middle layer is the location for the platform components. The components can be grouped into four families:

- Model packages, that contain information schema parts according to the UML model (the static aspects of an information system),
- Business objects that provide software functionality associated with specific model types (dynamic aspects),
- Generic services that provide software functionality not associated with specific model types and therefore applicable to all or at least a wide range of platform objects,
- Technology bindings that integrate core technology (relational databases, programming languages) or standard protocols (XML, SOAP) into the platform and make them available for the usage with data instances that conform to the platform's base abstractions.

On top of the platform and the component layer is the solution layer. Software solutions consist of a suitable collection of components integrated by application-specific code conceptually located at the solution layer. Ideally, the amount of functionality provided by reusable components is significantly higher than the amount of functionality that has to be implemented for the individual solution. This infers three positive characteristics of ice.NET-based software solutions:

- Less effort (cost, time, resources) necessary to implement the solution due to the reuse of already existing components,
- Higher quality due to the higher test coverage and improved robustness of the components that were applied to and tested under various conditions and application areas,
- Higher flexibility due to the fact that the reusable components were designed for interoperability with any other components based on the platform abstractions. Therefore suitable components can be easily selected and exchanged according to new functional requirements.

4.4. Components, Services and Tools

For the development of the TIS system we used several components to cover basic functionality independent from the specific semantic requirements:

- Unit of Measurement (UoM) to configure the presentation of UoMs independent from technical storage (e.g. displaying a ship's speed in knots while storing the value in m/s)

- Audit Trail to track user's changes on important objects
 - Document Management with Fulltext Search to provide basic documentation functionality
- In order to design the information model the ice.NET Studio SmartClient has been used.

Fig.11: ice.NET Studio

The SmartClient provides a graphical UML modeling environment and is directly connected to a ice.NET development/test system through a SOAP-based Webservice interface. Therefore, any model updates performed by the UML editor is directly propagated to the server and immediately available for the running application. With this technology model changes can be validated very efficiently and modeling errors were detected very early, without requiring much effort to correct them.

5. Practical application

In the context of the TIS project at Germanischer Lloyd we implemented a "Technical Information System" that is based on the ice.NET platform. TIS integrates data models from various legacy systems, provides configurable XML and Webservice interfaces to associated simulation programs and addresses the general and shipbuilding-specific requirements mentioned above. Fig.12 shows an overview of the data structure of TIS and Fig.13 shows an example of the UML description of data model.

The technical information system shows all the information that is relevant for ship approval processes, set out in a unique way, Fig.14. There is an easy to navigation folder tree on the left and a detail view on the right. The folders include Part descriptions, Approvals, Installed Systems etc. The action menu with the function calls is also on the right.

Fig.12: Data structure

Fig.13: An UML representation of the steering gear data model

The folder marked 'Part description' for example, holds data objects of type 'Part' containing the design description of a part or an assembly in terms of its general product description. The data in Part description has been extracted from building plans and data sheets. Normally the Part name should be the manufacturer's type designation. Typical parameters are 'Cylinder diameter', 'Length of ...', 'Power' or 'Moment'. Parameters are organized in sets ('Parameter set'). In addition, they are grouped in approval data (e.g. 'Connection type' or 'Working torque') and calculation data (e.g. 'Bolt length A' or 'Cylinder material tensile stress'). Fig.15 shows the form that handles the parameter set of a 'Part'.

Fig.14: The web based user interface

Fig.15: A parameter set of a part

The folder 'Installed part' collects data object of type 'Part instance'. These objects describe the installation of a real instance of part or assembly on board of the ship. Such an object contains parameters like 'Serial number, Approved usage' or 'Position' and optionally a link to one 'Part description'. Also several 'Installed parts' can be linked the same 'Part description' in case of similar parts being installed on board. Fig.16 shows the user interface for 'Installed parts'. An approval in terms of a data object is a special view on a linked pair of a 'Part' and a 'Part instance'. In addition the 'Part instance' parameter 'Number of Referenced Approval' has to be the same as the 'Part description' parameter 'Approval reference number'. In the folder 'Approvals' you can find all data pairs meeting this condition, Fig.17 (left). Fig.17 (right) shows the compressed view on such an approval pair.

Fig.16: An Installed part

Fig.17: Two frames to handle approval information

A System is a set of data objects such as subsystems and components, Fig.18, which work together as a general functional unit. There are two kinds of systems. The first one is the 'Installed System'. It depicts a real system on board such as the propulsion train or the LO system. The second one is the 'Calculation system', which may render a calculation model as an abstraction of reality. A component is a part of a system. It contains specific properties which are defined in dependency of system context and optionally it is linked to a 'Part'

6. Conclusions

Based on the ice.NET software platform and an advanced information model a powerful data management system for technical data in the ship classification process has been implemented. TIS is an example of how to provide functional prototypes within a short time frame and limited budget. The system is characterized by a process-specific organization of information in a networked, project-oriented folder structures with access control mechanisms. Tracking and auditing functionality is also part of the software system.

Fig.18: A system view

The TIS project demonstrates the capabilities of a requirements-driven, dynamic approach of adapting the data model by using the UML-based development tool ice.NET Studio. This flexibility of modelling has empowered the GL to start practical implementation of TIS based on fragmentary knowledge about the software-specific representation of the necessary domain information. During the introduction phase the data model has been extended in order to meet further requirements that arose from an improved understanding of the domain data models and their implications on the usability of the software system. We were also able to introduce new application aspects in later project phases without invalidating major project results that were achieved so far. The management of hazardous materials in the context of ship systems, components and parts was such an extension of the system's functionality, *Gramann et al. (2007)*.

Therefore, the ice.NET development approach enables and improves the cooperative work of application domain experts (e.g. shipbuilding engineers) together with IT specialists based on well-known, common abstractions, rapid delivery of prototypes and software updates and early and frequent user feedback.

Based on the object-oriented abstractions of the ice.NET platform it was possible to use a variety of already existing software components as building blocks for TIS. This significantly reduced the overall development and testing time. Especially a rich set of powerful user interface components enabled the development team to provide multiple variants of critical user interfaces in order to collect feedback from the end users.

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Stochastic Optimisation of IACC Yachts

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Abstract

Previous efforts to automate the optimisation of International America's Cup Class (IACC) yachts have typically used an objective function that evaluates the performance of an individual boat using direct Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) analysis of the hull design. This approach suffers from the use of an inappropriate measure of merit as well as having extremely long execution times. A superior method is the use of an objective function incorporating a match racing tournament amongst a population of candidate designs. The resulting need to maintain a population of designs makes the problem well suited to population based optimisation methods such as Genetic Algorithms (GA). Performance issues are addressed through the use of a neural network based metamodel, trained using parameters sampled from the design space and calculated using the SPLASH potential flow code. This has resulted in an optimisation system that gives good results while retaining reasonable execution times.

Nomenclature

<i>AG</i>	Aft girth
<i>BWL</i>	Maximum beam of waterline
C_M	Midship area coefficient
C_P	Prismatic coefficient
<i>FG</i>	Forward girth
<i>LCB</i>	Longitudinal centre of buoyancy
<i>LCF</i>	Longitudinal centre of flotation
<i>LBG</i>	Length between girths
V_{MG}	Velocity made good relative to the direction of the wind

1. Introduction

Prior to the 1980s, the design development of America's Cup yachts primarily relied on tank testing, with only limited computing power available for numerical analysis. With computer costs plummeting and computing power increasing dramatically in the early eighties, it became possible to consider simulating the work previously done in a towing tank on a computer.

Until the introduction of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software, yacht design optimisation had been based on the creation of a matrix of proposed designs which were built as scale models and tank tested. This allowed some parameter variation to take place and conclusions to be drawn from the results; however the time and cost of tank testing prohibited the systematic optimisation of a hull design. The quality of the finished hull design was very much dependent on the skill and experience of the designer, and the conclusions he could draw from a small amount of data and a large amount of intuition. The insight of the yacht designer was paramount and it is no surprise that the post war years of the America's Cup were dominated by the designs of one very talented man, Olin Stephens, who was involved in the design of all but one America's Cup winner from 1937 to 1980.

One of the first America's Cup yachts to gain significant advantage from numerical simulations was Australia II, winner of the 1983 America's Cup, with the intuition of her designer Ben Lexcen being grounded in the computational work of two Dutch engineers, Peter van Oossanen and Joop Slooff, *Van Oossanen and Joubert (1986)*. Since then, America's Cup syndicates have devoted ever increasing amounts of time and money to both hydrodynamic and aerodynamic simulations of the hull and rig designs.

Although much work has been done with CFD analysis of yacht designs during the past 25 years, surprisingly little has been done to automate the process to allow the computer to search for an optimum design for a given set of weather conditions. To some extent this has been due to the amount of computing power required; however it is also due to the enormous complexity of the yacht design and analysis process. To solve the problem effectively there is both a requirement to perform the optimisation in a reasonable amount of time using available computer hardware, as well as simplifying the problem by removing unnecessary complexities.

2. Overview

This paper describes a global optimisation system for the design of International America's Cup Class (IACC) yachts. The system, named VESPA (short for Virtual Evolution based Sailing Performance Analysis), was developed in conjunction with the Alinghi syndicate and has been used to make design recommendations for the 2007 America's Cup.

The development of such a system is a daunting challenge and its feasibility depends heavily on the components chosen and how they interact, as poor choices could easily result in a system that was impractically slow. As pointed out by *Harries et al. (2001)* –

“For an IACC yacht the design evaluation becomes a challenging task in itself since a (probabilistic) measure of merit ought to be considered ... however, an extraordinary amount of computation will be required to determine this ultimate measure of merit and to optimise for it.”

Harries highlights the two key issues in creating a system such as VESPA – the correct choice of measure of merit and the problem of system performance. Using modern Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) CFD codes directly in an optimisation loop could conceivably result in execution times that stretch into weeks or months for the fastest optimisation methods. Unfortunately, the most useful measures of merit for this particular problem require some of the slowest optimisation methods, since they need an entire population of designs to be maintained. This combination of slow analysis with slow optimisation techniques makes the option of direct CFD analysis unattractive, even when using solvers running in parallel on a cluster of computers.

VESPA has been designed to avoid these pitfalls and integrates the following key components in order to create an efficient optimisation system:

- A powerful parametric transformation function to allow VESPA to vary hull shapes based on a small number of key parameters, while still producing hull shapes that are both acceptable to the design team and legal under the IACC Rule, *IACC (2003)*.
- Generation of a systematic series by sampling of the design space using a modern Design of Experiments (DOE) method. The parametric transformation function is then used to create hulls, derived from a specified parent model, matching these sampled parameter values.
- Analysis of lift and drag for the hulls in the systematic series using the SPLASH potential flow code.
- The use of neural networks to fit the SPLASH data for all hulls in the systematic series to produce a global regression model, or metamodel, for lift, drag and other parameters.
- Customisation of a proven Velocity Performance Prediction (VPP) program to read the neural network based metamodel and to allow it to be called as a Dynamically Linked Library (DLL) from another application.
- A stochastic Race Modelling Program (RMP) that creates a tournament of races for the population of boats. This RMP uses performance data derived from the VPP to race each boat against every other multiple times, in wind conditions sampled from a specified distribution of wind strength.
- A Genetic Algorithm (GA) based optimiser that takes the parent IACC hull design which is used to generate the lift and drag models, and evolves a population of variations using the parametric transformation function.

2.1. Integration of components

The components of VESPA are integrated in the manner illustrated in Fig.1. There are two main parts to the system, the creation of the metamodel, which occurs in advance of the optimisation process being performed, and the optimisation loop itself.

Fig.1: VESPA logic flow

Later sections of this paper describe each component, together with the reasons governing their selection for inclusion within VESPA.

3. Why use automated optimisation?

It is firstly important to distinguish between the use of the term optimisation within this paper and the common usage of the term by yacht designers. In this work, optimisation is taken to mean an automated, computer based process that searches for the most efficient design.

When yacht designers speak of design optimisation, they are generally describing a manual search through different design alternatives. This may be done using a systematic series that has been designed and built as tank models, allowing some interpolation of results, or by the stepwise evaluation of design variations using a CFD or VPP program.

This form of optimisation typically progresses by searching a single parameter direction until no further improvement is seen, followed by a switch to a different parameter, which is again searched until once again no further benefit is seen. At this point additional parameters may be searched or the process may repeat from the first parameter until no improvement can be made.

This method is illustrated in Fig.2, where parameter P1 is searched until a maximum is found, followed by a search using parameter P2, resulting in a solution reasonably close to the optimum. This approach, more correctly termed the alternating variable method, is simple and effective on well behaved functions that have a reasonable number of independent parameters.

Fig.2: Alternating variable method

Fig.3: Alternating variables with correlation

The problem with this method is that it ignores the possibility of correlation between the variables. This correlation effectively causes a ridge or valley to form diagonally through the solution space. When this occurs, it causes the search in the current search direction to completely destroy the property that the current point is the minimiser in previously used directions, *Fletcher (1987)*.

This leads to oscillatory behaviour of the alternating variable algorithm, as illustrated in Fig.3. In this case an initial search along P1 locates a ridge in the solution surface that runs diagonally relative to the variables being searched. A switch to a search of P2 does not go far before it also reaches a maximum. Another switch back to the P1 search direction makes another small gain, followed by a further small gain on each successive alternation of search direction.

The result is an optimisation method that either progresses slowly or fails to locate an optimum at all. Although this search method is seldom used as a computer based optimisation algorithm, it is a widely used as a manual search method for yacht design.

One possible example of the problems inherent in this approach is the design of the midship section of International America's Cup Class (IACC) yachts. When the class was first introduced for the 1992 America's Cup, the IACC rule contained a maximum beam limit of 5.5 metres, and the competing yachts were all close to this limit. Boats of this vintage also had a great deal of topside flare and low Midship Area Coefficient (C_M) values (Fig.4).

Fig.4: Comparison of 1992 (left) and 2007 (right) IACC mid-sections

During the years that followed, the beam of IACC yachts has progressively reduced until today they are less than 3.5 metres wide. Topside flare is now close to zero and C_M values have increased to the point that the boats are boxy and slab sided. Yet it has taken fifteen years, thousands of man-hours and millions of dollars of research and development funding for this progression to occur.

One possible explanation for the long period of time it has taken to move from one design extreme to the other is that BWL , C_M and flare are correlated variables; that is, the optimum value of one is dependent on the value of the others.

To explain why this may be so, it is necessary to understand the constraints of the America's Cup rule. Under the rule, the effective length of the boat is governed by the LBG measurement, which measures the length of the hull in a plane 200mm above the datum waterline. If a yacht is made narrower while the displacement and C_M are kept constant, the draft of the canoe body must increase to compensate.

This draft increase has several undesirable effects; the exposed span of keel reduces as the hull gets deeper, and to meet the required LBG , the aft buttock lines must steepen and the counter stern must rise, reducing the sailing length of the boat when heeled. To avoid these effects the canoe body draft needs to be prevented from increasing significantly, requiring more volume to be forced into the available hull depth by increasing C_M . When C_M increases the topsides naturally become more vertical, so a reduction in topside flare is inevitable.

This interdependence of design variables complicates any search for an optimum design, as a change to one variable needs to be matched by simultaneous changes to the correlated variables. A search by alternating variables is likely to result in only slow improvement.

Automated optimisation methods have been designed to avoid this pitfall. Algorithms such as the conjugate gradient method attempt to determine the best search direction for convergence, however manual searches do not have this sophistication. This ability of automated optimisation procedures to find solutions where manual methods fail suggests that there may be scope for an automated optimisation system to improve the design of racing yachts.

4. Measures of merit

Before describing the implementation of VESPA, the factors that have determined the key decisions in the design of the system should be explored. The most important of these is the final stage of an optimisation loop, the evaluation of the measure of merit by the objective function. The form that this measure of merit takes influences the choices made at every other stage of the optimisation process, so it is important to look closely at the benefits and drawbacks of each possible alternative.

4.1. Upright resistance

Many researchers have attempted to minimise the resistance of an upright hull, with or without appendages, at one or more speeds. This approach has primarily been used for the optimisation of

ships operating in an upright state at relatively fixed speeds, although there have also been examples, *Harries et al. (2001)*, of this approach being applied to IACC yachts.

This body of work, focussed on the refinement of ship forms, has advanced the field of yacht design through the development of innovative hull shape deformation procedures and CFD analysis methods. However, for yachts that operate over a wide range of velocities, heel and yaw angles, the upright case is not indicative of the overall performance of the yacht and this approach is of little value.

4.2. Heeled lift and drag

The next level of complexity encompasses the optimisation of both lift and drag at multiple velocities, heel and yaw angles. This approach has mainly been used by authors working specifically on CFD solvers such as *Peri and Mandolesi (2005)*. Although this approach is an improvement over the upright case, it suffers from not incorporating a measure of stability, and therefore sail carrying ability, as a factor. For example, a narrower hull may have less resistance, but may also have less stability, giving it less sail carrying ability. There is no way of knowing without more detailed analysis whether the yacht would be faster or slower overall.

4.3. Velocity Performance Prediction

To properly incorporate factors such as stability it is necessary to combine hull lift and drag data with information about the weight, centre of gravity and sail plan of the yacht to produce a set of polar performance curves for the yacht (Fig.5). This is done using a Velocity Performance Prediction Program, or VPP. Much work has gone into the development of VPPs during the past 30 years, *Kerwin (1978)*, *Oliver and Cloughton (1995)*, with the result that they are now capable of producing reasonably accurate sets of polar performance data over a range of true wind directions and wind strengths for most yacht types.

Although using yacht polar performance data is superior to looking directly at hull lift and drag, it raises the difficulty of how one selects the exact conditions for which the yacht is to be optimised. In some cases, *Fassardi and Hochkirch (2006)*, the best V_{MG} for a single wind strength is used as a measure of merit. In another case, *Jacquin et al. (2002)*, multiple upwind and downwind V_{MG} values have been used as objectives in a multi-objective optimisation.

The primary output from a VPP is a set of polar curves which tell the designer how the boat performs for each wind strength and point of sail. Although this information is valuable, VPP output is not sufficient to differentiate between the performance of two boats unless the weather in which the boat is to be sailed is taken into account. As stated in *Letcher et al. (1987)*;

Fig.5: A yacht polar performance plot

“Yacht racing has an essentially random component in that the relative performance of two yachts depends on the wind speed and sea conditions, which vary randomly from day to day. VPP results by themselves are therefore inconclusive and possibly misleading for determining the order of merit of two candidate yachts over a series of races”

4.4. Comparison plots

In order to compare how well two boats perform it is necessary to convert the VPP derived polar performance data into comparison plots as shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6: Performance comparison plot

Wind speed is plotted on the x axis and deltas between the V_{MG} of the two boats on the y axis, typically expressed in metres per minute or seconds per mile. The performance of the reference boat is plotted as a horizontal line and the test boat deltas plotted against it, with points below the abscissa being faster and points above, slower.

Although comparison plots or time deltas are not particularly appropriate as a measure of merit for an automated optimisation process, they have been widely used as the basis for manual design optimisation for some time, *Chance (1987)*, *Rosen et al. (2000)*, *DeBord et al. (2002)*. Most importantly, they provide a rapid visual check of overall performance, and therefore play an important role in the validation of any designs created by an optimisation system.

4.5. Race Modelling Programs

To more accurately model an entire yacht race many factors need to be taken into account. On an actual race course the wind varies in both speed and direction, boats influence one another with backwind and wind shadow, there are multiple legs and boats are forced to concede right of way on the course and at rounding marks. The result is a bias in favour of the boat that is faster upwind and can lead around the first windward mark. Statistics for the America's Cup Acts between 2004 and 2006 show that for the top four boats, 80% of races were won by the boat that rounded the first weather mark in front.

To handle these conditions and more accurately account for this bias it is necessary to create a more accurate simulation. This can be achieved by breaking the race up into discrete periods of time and stochastically sampling wind conditions for each step from distributions derived from historical data.

Many RMP have been developed to date with varying levels of complexity, from simple probabilistic methods through to fully detailed simulations. Possibly the most sophisticated to date is the ACROBAT program, *Philpott et al. (2001)*, *Philpott (2003)*.

ACROBAT is a fixed interval time stepped simulation and was intended to be a highly accurate simulation of the racing performance of an IACC yacht. ACROBAT incorporated detailed calculations for many aspects of yacht racing including:

- A stochastic wind model generated using a Markov chain.
- Independent wind fields for each of the two yachts in the race, correlated according to their spatial separation.
- Modelling of the dynamics of tacking and mark rounding.
- Interactions between yachts, including backwind effect and wind shadows.
- Route optimisation, covering and collision avoidance penalties.

Choosing the required level of detail to accurately rank two boats for the purposes of optimisation is not straightforward, however. More detailed simulations have longer execution times but may not necessarily have a better ability to rank the performances of two boats in a match race. A detailed simulation that is not totally accurate may give inferior results to a less detailed statistical approach.

4.6. Monte Carlo race model simulations

Regardless of how sophisticated it is a simulation of a single race does not provide sufficient information to fully optimise a yacht design, as it cannot sufficiently capture all of the random variation in conditions for which racing yachts need to be designed.

A more effective measure is based on a Monte Carlo simulation, where the RMP is run repeatedly for hundreds or thousands of races. Although to the author's knowledge this has not previously been used as the measure of merit for an automated design optimisation procedure, there has been some excellent work done in this area for the comparison of specific yacht designs, including work done by the Partnership for America's Cup technology, *Gretzky and Marshall (1993)*, the ACROBAT program, *Philpott et al. (2001)*, *Philpott (2003)* and the Sail America team, *Letcher et al. (1987)*.

4.6.1. Stars & Stripes '87

The seminal work in the use of Monte Carlo simulations for the design of IACC yachts was performed by the Sail America team for the 1987 America's Cup. Racing for the challenger selections started in late October when the winds were moderate and continued through to the end of January when the sea-breezes were very strong. The different rounds of the Louis Vuitton Cup were also awarded progressively more points for successive competition rounds, making early losses less important in terms of total points. Boats that performed poorly were also eliminated after certain rounds in the competition.

The Sail America team had access to both VPP and RMP software. Using these programs they were able to perform Monte Carlo simulations of a racing across the entire summer. These simulations found that although the yachts that Sail America had already built would be capable of winning the America's Cup, they would be unlikely to survive the early elimination rounds in the selection trials. Sail America chose to build a third boat, named *Stars & Stripes '87*, that was slightly shorter than their previous designs, which would both be fast enough to survive the earlier selection rounds while still having dominant heavy weather performance in the actual America's Cup final.

4.7. Tournament modelling

The research performed by the Sail America design team illustrates several key points:

- Variations in wind strength, both intra-day and across the duration of the competition need to be accounted for.
- The structure of the tournament (i.e. number of competitors, points allocated per race and timing of competitor eliminations) can affect the outcome of the simulation.
- The ideal boat for a competition may not necessarily be a static optimum; rather, it may be dependent on the design of the opposing boats.

These points are as valid today as they were in 1987. The America's Cup is now a best of 9 race series, while the Louis Vuitton Cup, the selection series for the America's Cup challenger, has significantly more races over a period of 8 weeks.

The successful challenger for the America's Cup has to firstly win the challenge series and then compete against the defending yacht. The total time period for this is close to 3 months, over which the standard deviation of wind strength will be significantly higher than the typical standard deviation for a typical sailing day. Due to seasonal variations, the mean wind strength may also vary over the 3 month period.

In addition, the America's Cup is a tournament of individual matches, and success is based on points accumulated for race wins, not accrued race times. Races won by one second carry as many points as races won by five minutes. This has a significant effect on the measure of merit. For example, compare a yacht that wins five races by five seconds each and loses one race by one minute, against a yacht that loses five races by five seconds and wins one by one minute. The second yacht may have a shorter accrued time for all the races taken together, so arguably could be termed the faster yacht, however the first yacht will get the majority of the points, and in the case of the America's Cup final, would win the event.

To account for these effects it is important to evaluate the ability of a yacht to win races against a range of opponents, over a range of weather conditions, by simulating an entire tournament of races.

4.8. Measure of merit - summary

These factors make a strong case for the use of a full tournament model as the objective function for an America's Cup yacht design optimisation. This tournament should provide a probability of winning based on races against multiple boats with temporal variations in wind strength included. This choice, however, has a significant impact on the design of the RMP and VPP, as well as affecting the selection of an appropriate optimisation method.

5. Objective function

Many attempts at yacht design optimisation have viewed the task as a multi-objective problem, or at least a single objective problem with a large number of constraints. Although this may be true for cruising yacht design where there are conflicting requirements for speed, comfort, stability seaworthiness and cost, IACC optimisation is based solely around the wish to be the winner of a specific set of races. As a result, IACC optimisation can be viewed as being a problem with a single objective, although it is clear that the calculation of the objective function is a formidable task.

Based on the observations outlined in Section 4 regarding measures of merit, it was decided that the objective function for VESPA should have the following properties:

- It should use a tournament of multiple boats, with the measure of merit being the win/loss ratio against all competitors.
- It should include multiple races, each sampling the wind distribution covering the period of the event to provide a mean wind strength for each race. This distribution needs to be adjusted for any drift in the mean wind strength over the period of interest. The objective function should also have the ability to use normal or lognormal distributions for wind strength, including upper and lower cut-off values to handle the wind strength limits above and below which races are not sailed.
- Each race should have its own standard deviation for wind strength. For example, the standard deviation for a 3 month period may be 8 knots, whilst the standard deviation for a single race, taking only 90 minutes, may be 3 knots.
- It should allow wind direction variation with a specified standard deviation.

The VESPA objective function consists of a RMP where each member of the population (typically 25 boats) is raced against each other boat for 100 different races, with each race having its own wind speed and standard deviation. This RMP consists of a fixed time interval simulation with each time step stochastically sampling its wind speed and direction from the specified wind distributions. The VESPA RMP has been designed to have exceptionally low execution times, as the approach taken requires that the optimisation process will run millions, rather than hundreds, of race simulations.

For the VESPA RMP the focus is on the simulation of the simplest possible race that correctly ranks two boats, rather than attempting to create a perfect simulation of all of the physics of a typical race. The decision was also made to focus on factors affecting straight-line speed and to ignore the effects of hull shape changes on manoeuvring.

As short execution times were considered essential, the VESPA RMP dispenses with direct physical modelling of many of the complexities of racing where it is considered that no net benefit for either boat exists, or when the effect can be approximated in a probabilistic manner. For example, each boat in a race has to round the same number of marks in the same way. Unless the two boats are overlapped, the roundings can be considered to be identical with no net benefit accruing to either boat. If the boats are overlapped, the result can be approximated with a trailing boat penalty, effectively a statistical model of the likely effect of a particular type and degree of overlap. On average, boats in a set of races will also execute a very similar number of tacks. As a result the VESPA RMP does not directly model tacking or mark rounding manoeuvres.

Some of this simplification is possible because of recent changes to the IACC rule. In previous versions of the IACC rule a range of waterline lengths, displacements and sail areas were legal. However the Version 5 modifications to the IACC rule have reduced these ranges to the point that all boats can be considered to have the same length, displacement and sail area, and as a result the difference between their performance when tacking or rounding marks is significantly reduced.

6. Optimisation method

The fact that the objective function chosen for VESPA is based on a comparison of a yacht's performance against the performance of a group of other yachts presents some interesting difficulties. Firstly it implies that an entire population of boats needs to be modelled and optimised rather than simply optimising a single yacht. If only a single yacht is optimised while its opponents stay static it will rapidly improve to the point that it wins all or nearly all the matches and the optimisation process will be unable to progress further. In addition, rather than the fitness of a particular design being an absolute measure, it is relative to the quality of its competitors, making the fitness landscape a dynamic one which changes with each step in the optimisation.

Although these realisations bring with them some challenges, they do simplify the choice of optimisation method. The dynamic nature of the fitness landscape makes it unlikely that a gradient based method (e.g. Newton-Raphson or Quasi-Newton) or search pattern based method (e.g. Nelder-Mead simplex or Hooke-Jeeves direct search) would behave in a stable fashion. The fact that a population of boats need to be modelled and evaluated does make stochastic, population-based methods such as Genetic Algorithms and Particle Swarm methods a natural choice.

As a result, the optimisation method chosen for VESPA is a floating-point based Genetic Algorithm (GA). The implementation of the GA was carried out in C++ and the following genetic operators were adopted, based on recommendations derived from *Mason et al. (2005)*:

- Two point crossover
- Gaussian distributed mutation
- Elitism
- Tournament selection

The GA used by VESPA can be run with any population size desired, however this was typically set to between 25 and 30 boats. In general, populations need to be large enough to capture sufficient genetic diversity, but once this condition is satisfied, larger populations simply result in longer execution times per generation.

In practice, running VESPA with populations greater than 30 resulted in longer run times but no increase in the speed of convergence on a solution, whereas populations less than 15 had insufficient genetic diversity to converge on a global optimum and tended to get stuck in false optima.

In addition to the question of single or multiple objectives, optimisation problems typically have constraints, as well as bounds on input values. In the case of VESPA the input variables are bounded to lie within the ranges specified for the systematic series used for the fitting of the lift and drag metamodels (see Section 8), as values outside these ranges are unlikely to be predicted accurately.

In terms of constraints, all designs are constrained to be legal IACC designs by ensuring that the key measurements (length, sail area and displacement) comply with the IACC formula;

$$\frac{L + 1.25 \times \sqrt{S} - 9.8 \times \sqrt[3]{DSP}}{0.686} \leq 24.000$$

This is achieved by scaling sail area so that the above equation equals 24.0 at all times. The IACC rule is framed in such a way that small variations away from the desired L, S and DSP values effectively apply an exponential penalty, so it is not necessary to apply penalty constraints within the optimisation itself.

The result of the application of bounds to the input variables and the scaling of hull shapes to comply with the IACC rule was that no issues regarding infeasible designs were encountered. This was also partially due to the complementary nature of the input variables chosen, however future work will need to consider and deal with the possibility that infeasible designs may be generated.

7. CFD

CFD is the process of simulating the fluid flow around a body such as a yacht hull by solving a set of equations, typically the Navier-Stokes equations or Laplace's equation for inviscid, incompressible, potential flow.

The CFD code chosen for use with VESPA is SPLASH, a potential flow code widely used for America's Cup work since 1987, *Rosen et al. (1993)*, *Rosen et al. (2000)*. Although in theory potential flow codes such as SPLASH may not be as accurate as more recently developed RANS codes, in practice SPLASH gives good results commensurate with its relatively short run times.

8. Metamodels

Although the genetic algorithm is a natural fit with the population based objective function adopted, the large number of evaluations required for convergence raises significant performance problems when using direct CFD analysis to determine the performance of an individual yacht.

Using SPLASH as a CFD solver requires approximately four hours per design to calculate sufficient data to adequately determine overall performance of the yacht. Although running on a cluster of computers might reduce execution times, the direct calculation of CFD data for each boat in the population could result in an application having runs times extending to days or weeks.

For computer based analysis functions that run slowly, such as CFD codes, an alternative to direct analysis of the function is the strategy of sampling the solution space and deriving some sort of statistical model, termed a metamodel. For a metamodel to be an effective representation of the function being fitted several conditions need to be fulfilled:

- There should be an adequate number of samples taken of the solution space. The number of samples required is dependent on the number of dimensions and the complexity of the function. This is most easily determined by a sensitivity analysis.
- The sampling should be as uniform as possible, however should avoid the rigid spacing of a full-factorial array.
- The method used to fit the sampled data should be capable of creating a smooth, least squares fit to the data with a low RMS error.

Many possible candidates for metamodels exist, including multivariate non-linear regression, response surfaces, Kriging, radial basis functions, Gaussian processes and neural networks. Many of these methods are surveyed in *Simpson et al. (2001)*. For the lift and drag data from SPLASH that VESPA is concerned with i.e. non-linear but relatively smooth, each of the above methods has advantages and disadvantages, however most would give adequate results.

Other significant differentiating factors in the choice of a metamodel are data management issues to do with ease of fitting, validation and visualisation. These are primarily related to the user interface of the software involved and favour methods that are sufficiently mature and widely used that there is a variety of well designed commercial software available. It cannot be over-emphasised that the ability to optimise the quality of fit and validate the results easily is paramount, as a small error can drive the optimisation process to unrealistic results. Software with good data manipulation and visualisation capabilities is of great importance.

After careful evaluation of alternatives, neural networks were selected for use in VESPA for the creation of metamodels for lift and drag data created by SPLASH. Neural networks have been shown to perform well in this type of application, *Mason et al. (2005)*, and have powerful commercial software available at reasonable cost.

Although the primary use of a metamodel is the reduction of the evaluation time of an expensive function, there are additional benefits. For noisy functions a metamodel can smooth the data making the optimisation process simpler. For those functions that can suffer from some numerical instability, such as some CFD programs, the process of fitting the metamodel can also be used to filter out non-converged points for a net increase in data quality.

8.1. Design of experiments

To provide the design parameters for the small set of hull forms to be used as input to SPLASH it is necessary to sample the design space. Sampling based on a regular grid of points is unsuitable for this purpose as the gaps between the rows and columns can result in poor metamodel fitting. Random sampling also results in a poor distribution, with clusters of points and large areas without samples being apparent.

For the sampling of hull design parameters a quasi-random, low-discrepancy DOE method was chosen, the Uniform Design, *Fang (2006)*, based on recommendations contained in *Notz (2003)*. Although low-discrepancy sequences such as those by *Sobol (1967)* were considered, the regular spacing of the Uniform Design was preferred as the intervals could be chosen to correspond with portions of the test matrix previously used both for SPLASH analysis and for tank testing. This made comparison of neural network predictions with existing data easier, as results from multiple sources could be compared on the same graph.

An example of a 25 point, two-dimensional Uniform Design is compared in Fig.7 to a Sobol sequence for the same number of points. It can be seen that although both sequences span the space effectively, the Uniform Design exhibits a more regular spacing than does the Sobol sequence.

Fig.7: A comparison of Sobol (left) and Uniform Design (right) sequences

8.2. Neural networks

A total of 25 designs were generated for SPLASH analysis from each parent model. The SPLASH output was then used as a source of data for neural network training. The number of designs was determined by sensitivity analysis; the prediction accuracy reduced unacceptably if less than 20 designs were used, whereas there was little difference in the prediction accuracy if greater than 30 hulls were used.

In addition to the 25 hulls used for neural network training, 6 test hulls were generated and analysed in SPLASH. The data for these hulls were not utilised in the training of the neural networks, rather they were used purely to test the ability of the neural networks to predict output values for arbitrary combinations of design parameters.

These numbers correspond well to those achieved by *Fassardi and Hochkirch (2006)*, who demonstrated that as few as 30 designs, uniformly sampled using a Sobol sequence and approximated by a response surface methodology, gave equivalent results to a solution derived from 946 designs.

For the SPLASH data required for VESPA, neural networks were trained using feed-forward multi-layer perceptrons with a single hidden layer. These were able to achieve both very high correlation coefficients as well as low RMS error values for designs in the validation set.

9. VPP

VESPA has been designed to work with any VPP that can be compiled as a DLL and operated through a simple function call interface.

During its initial prototyping phase VESPA was developed using the code for the SPAN VPP, originally written by the author as part of the Maxsurf suite of design software. SPAN, however, had not been specifically adapted to suit IACC yachts, so for actual IACC optimisation work VESPA was interfaced to PAP, a VPP developed by one of the Alinghi design team, Manuel Ruiz de Elvira.

PAP was originally developed in 1996 and was used for the design and analysis of SUI-64, the winner of the 2003 America's Cup. PAP is a reliable, well validated code used by the design team of the current holder of the America's Cup, so it is seen as an ideal VPP on which to base an optimisation system.

To enable the PAP VPP to accurately assess the performance of boats with parameters specified by VESPA, it has been modified to read XML files containing neural network definition files for lift and drag. These XML files are read by PAP and used to reconstruct the neural networks to determine lift and drag values for any hull required by VESPA.

10. Hull variation

For optimisation to proceed it is necessary for the GA to be able to vary hull shapes, based on parameters specified in the genomes of the population members. There are several ways that this can be achieved.

10.1. Interactive modelling

The most common method used for computer based hull shape definition, interactive modelling, typically presents the user with a network of control points, shown in Fig.8, which are moved in x, y and z axes to create a hull shape. This method typically uses Bezier, NURBS or subdivision surfaces for its underlying geometry.

Fig.8: A NURBS surface and its corresponding net of control points

Although this method is suitable for *ab initio* design and is widely used by interactive CAD systems for hull design, it is not ideal as a strategy for shape control in an automated optimisation procedure due to the large number of variables required. A typical IACC hull might be modelled with a control point mesh of 10 columns and 8 rows, giving 80 control points, each free to move in x, y and z directions. This gives 240 degrees of freedom to be encoded into the genome of the GA, resulting in very slow convergence. Fairness and convexity constraints also mean that there is strong correlation between the variables, making successful optimisation problematic.

10.2. Parametric modelling

Parametric modelling defines hull shapes using a set of key parameters which are satisfied simultaneously by their own optimisation loop. This approach, as elaborated in *Harries and Abt (1999)* and *Harries et al. (2001)*, potentially reduces the number of number of degrees of freedom to less than 50. These variables are also much closer to the types of parameters used by naval architects for the analysis of hull forms.

Parametric modelling is the ideal approach to use on simple geometric shapes. In the case of the optimisation of semi-submersible oil rigs, *Birk (2005)* was able to define the geometry of the semi-submersible pontoons and struts with a very small number of parameters. For commercial ships that have flat-of-bottom and flat-of-side joined by a bilge radius, the number of parameters increases, however the ship can still be defined with a fairly compact set of variables.

IACC hull shapes, on the other hand, have specific features that are consequences of the way in which the hull is measured. The result is a shape that has bumps and flats in unusual places to gain best effect under the IACC rule. The shape of these features is very much subject to the preferences of the individual designer.

The need to model such features potentially raises the number of parameters that are needed to produce a hull shape that takes best advantage of the IACC rule as well as satisfying the requirements of the designers. For example, *Harries et al. (2001)* and *Baik and Gonella (2005)* describe the optimisation of IACC hulls using the FRIENDSHIP parametric modeller using between 44 and 51 parameters; however the hulls illustrated in these works did not contain the now ubiquitous Davidson knuckle bow, nor the various flat areas that are now common on IACC hulls. In addition, Baik and Gonella failed to properly constrain fore and aft girth measurements, resulting in unrealistic hull forms. It is likely that the accurate modelling of a modern IACC hull would require substantially more parameters for the shape to be acceptable to the current designers in the class.

10.3. Parametric transformation

Parametric transformations have been used by naval architects for some time to modify the form parameters of existing designs. One of the first descriptions of a technique to modify the LCB and C_P of an existing lines plan was provided by *Lackenby (1947)*. Lackenby's method consisted of a technique for moving sections of the hull forward and aft in a smooth fashion to match prescribed LCB and C_P values, however other parameters such as displacement, water plane area and LCF could also vary in an uncontrolled manner.

The introduction of NURBS surface modelling systems for the definition of hull shapes introduced another difficulty. Lackenby's method operates directly on hull sections and modified sections needed to be interpolated and faired. This was straightforward when the hull definition was stored as a lines plan. However, a NURBS surface is defined by the locations of its control points, and its hull sections are calculated when required from this surface definition. For NURBS surfaces it is not possible to directly move hull sections, rather, it is the surface control points that needed to be moved.

A solution to this problem was developed by the author and implemented in the Maxsurf design program, *Formation Design Systems (2006)*. This solution uses a modification of the Free Form Deformation (FFD) approach, *Sederberg and Parry (1986)*, that had been developed for the computer graphics and animation industry to permit objects to be deformed in a fluid manner.

The method surrounds a geometry, in this case a NURBS surfaces, with a trivariate NURBS lattice which then has its control points modified. The effect is that the original surface is embedded in a flexible space and any deformation of that space is applied to the surface geometry (Fig.9).

Fig.9: Deformation of a sphere using an FFD lattice, *Menzel et al. (2005)*

In the case of the Maxsurf parametric transformation, the major change to the FFD method is the use, not only of the control point locations, but also their NURBS weighting values to modify the original hull geometry. A simplified example of this technique is shown in Fig.10; where a circular arc midship section is shown mapped onto a two dimensional NURBS surface which is defined solely by four corner control points. When the control point weight values along the bottom and right edge of the surface are increased, the parametric spacing of the surface compresses in the direction of the increased weights and the mapped curve distorts in a fair manner to effectively increase the C_M of the section. By moving the upper right control point further to the right a measure of topside flare is introduced.

Fig.10: Midship section deformation using weight modification and lattice distortion

The actual transformations used in the VESPA parametric transformation are more complex than this example, encompassing distortions longitudinally, transversely and vertically, however the principles used are the same as illustrated in Fig.10.

The FFD method has previously been applied successfully to design optimisation problems using evolutionary algorithms. *Peri and Campana (2005)* used FFD transformations of a cruise-ship hull form in order to optimise its sea-keeping qualities. *Menzel et al. (2005)* investigated the use of FFDs in the evolutionary optimisation of turbine blade aerofoils and found that they resulted in a genome of lower complexity as well as improving optimisation performance.

The use of evolutionary algorithms in conjunction with the FFD method has interesting parallels with biological evolution. D’arcy Thompson’s “On Growth and Form”, *Thompson (1917)*, detailed the variations found in the evolution of different species. Thompson showed that many of the high-level changes that occurred in evolution consist of both linear and non-linear transformations of previous forms (Fig.11).

Fig.11: Non-linear deformation of primate skulls

Thompson’s transformations are directly analogous to the non-linear mappings used by VESPA to deform a parent hull shape to match a set of desired hull parameters. Both natural evolution and evolutionary optimisation systems such as VESPA benefit from methods that can achieve significant and effective variation yet can be encoded by the genome in a concise manner.

10.3.1. VESPA parametric transformation

The parametric transformation as implemented in VESPA performs a Newton-Raphson based search for specified LCB , C_p , C_m , flare, FG and AG values using non-linear transformations, together with linear scaling to achieve the required BWL , LBG and Displacement. The additional specification of draft would lead to an over-prescribed problem, so draft is left as a free variable.

The IACC rule has strict limits on the values for displacement, LBG , FG and AG . The parametric transformation method adopted allows these to be strictly controlled and all hull variations are constrained to meet specific values for these measurements.

Of particular value is the ability to vary hull shapes based on a very small number of meaningful parameters. In the current implementation the variables chosen were BWL , C_p , C_m , flare and LCB . Having a small number of variables also makes the encoding of a genome for the GA a simpler task, allowing the optimisation to proceed efficiently due to the concise representation.

There are several advantages to this method. First and foremost is that a known parent hull encapsulating the designer’s knowledge and design preferences is being used as the basis for the transformed design. An existing NURBS surface representation of an IACC design contains an enormous amount of information, sometimes the result of years of research and millions of dollars in development costs, so it is important that design features be preserved wherever possible. If the parametric modelling approach were to be adopted it would not necessarily be easy to reproduce the parent hull design’s features to the precision required.

It is also important that transformed hulls do not sacrifice fairness, convexity or flatness where required. Because the applied transformations are curvature continuous, they are fairness preserving. In addition constraints can be applied to the transformations to ensure that the result also preserves convexity or planarity requirements.

11. Validation

The accuracy of the results of an optimisation system such as VESPA is absolutely dependent on the quality of the data that is used. The nature of optimisation is that it will ruthlessly exploit weak data. Rather than minimising the function of interest, the optimisation procedure may simply locate the point of maximum disparity between simulation and reality.

Validation of all stages of the objective function evaluation is essential. In the case of VESPA this consisted of five distinct areas that required validation.

11.1. SPLASH validation

SPLASH is a program that has been widely used by America's Cup syndicates for twenty years. It has been widely compared and validated against tank test data during this time and as a result its capabilities are well understood, *Rosen et al. (1993)*.

Specific validation in the case of predictions made by VESPA consisted of the comparison of SPLASH data and tank data for the parent and optimised hull. In the cases where tank testing was performed, the deltas between the two hulls as predicted by SPLASH and the tank corresponded well, however difficulties were also noted with the ability of SPLASH to accurately predict the impact of extreme values of some design parameters.

11.2. Neural network validation

When SPLASH data was fitted using neural networks, the dataset was partitioned into 3 separate groups of data. Of the data for the 24 hulls in the systematic series, 80% was set aside for training and 20% for validation testing. An additional 6 hulls, whose parameters were selected using a quasi-random method, were analysed for use solely as an independent test set. This allowed the prediction capability of the neural networks to be tested to a high degree of confidence.

Analysis of training, validation and test sets showed that mean predictive error was less than 1% for both lift and drag values. Extensive outlier analysis was also performed to ensure that particular portions of the solution space were not poorly fitted, as flaws in a small part of the dataset could be exploited by the optimiser.

In order to improve on this accuracy, once optimisation runs had been performed and a likely area of the parameter space had been isolated as a location for an optimum design, a further 6 to 8 designs were created in the vicinity of this optimum design and combined with the original dataset. Neural networks were then retrained, effectively increasing the local prediction accuracy in the area of the optimum design.

11.3. VPP validation

Specific validation of the VPP was not performed as PAP has had extensive testing over the past 10 years. Due to its use by IACC syndicates during this period, it has been compared to performance data from full scale testing and has been found to reliably predict IACC performance.

The only change made to the VPP was to incorporate the neural network XML file definitions as the source of the lift and drag data, with the aerodynamic model and the algorithms used for balancing forces and moments within the VPP being left unchanged.

11.4. RMP validation

The VESPA RMP was tested using the same synthetic VPP data used to validate the GA optimiser. Statistical analysis of actual race data was used to quantify some of the values used for the RMP, such as trailing boat penalties applied at rounding marks.

11.5. GA validation

The GA was validated using a variety of synthetic problems to ensure correct functioning. When combined into the VESPA program it was also tested using synthetic VPP performance data to test the ability of VESPA to correctly find a known optimum design. In these tests the correct optimum was reliably found from a variety of initial populations.

In addition to this testing, all optimum hulls found by VESPA were re-analysed directly in SPLASH and compared to their parent models. In early testing, flaws were found in the fitting of the neural network models that resulted in poor optimisation outcomes, however once this fitting problem was corrected VESPA immediately began to show good results.

12. Results

The results of the VESPA project were extremely promising. VESPA was able to locate optimum designs in a reliable and repeatable fashion and these designs were shown to be superior to their parent models when directly analysed using the SPLASH potential flow code.

An early optimisation result was a design known as X3, which had SPLASH results demonstrating superior speed over its parent model in all wind strengths, both upwind and downwind. Considering that its parent was one of Alinghi's best design candidates at the time, this was an excellent result.

13. Conclusions

The VESPA project was intended to produce an automated optimisation system that could locate the optimum design parameters for an IACC yacht for a given set of weather conditions, while executing on available hardware in a reasonable period of time. The system has achieved these aims, with optimised designs being shown to be superior to their parent designs when directly re-analysed using SPLASH. The execution time for an optimisation run is also reasonable, taking approximately 12 hours on a 2.4 GHz Pentium4 based system.

Currently the weak link in this method is the accuracy of the results produced by the CFD analysis, as small errors here can result in misleading outcomes from the optimisation process. However, it is likely that CFD accuracy will improve in the future.

The use of metamodels by VESPA is an approach that increases in value as the execution time of the CFD analysis grows. As a result it is anticipated that this method will be even more appropriate when used with RANS codes whose execution times are substantially higher than potential flow codes such as SPLASH.

Although so far VESPA has been specifically targeted to IACC design, it is equally appropriate to other forms of yacht design, including long distance ocean racing and fleet racing. In these cases the objective function may need to be changed from being tournament based to being based on aggregate course times. A different optimisation method may also be more appropriate, however the basic principles of using a non-linear metamodel to approximate the results of an expensive CFD analysis and using a stochastic RMP that models the tournament structure of the actual racing would remain.

Considering that VESPA has shown that it is potentially able to improve on the best design produced by a talented yacht designer, does this mean that systems such as VESPA will make the yacht designer redundant in the near future? Although VESPA shows a great deal of promise, it still requires a high quality parent model to use as a starting point, and this project had the advantage of being able to use the knowledge and designs of arguably the best IACC design team in the world. Starting with a lesser parent model would not necessarily have resulted in optimised designs of equivalent quality. VESPA works well in conjunction with an expert designer to rapidly test and optimise new design concepts, but it is clear that there is still a need for both inspiration and insight in yacht design, and that skilled yacht designers are not going to be made obsolete any time soon.

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Possible Fields of Application of Virtual Reality in Shipbuilding

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Abstract

Results of an in-house workshop on finding possible application fields of virtual reality in shipbuilding are presented through this paper. The workshop consisted on several sessions attended by an interdisciplinary group of ship engineers. Existing 3D data has been visualized in a power wall and appreciated by using polarized glasses. Main topics were fly-through, reviews, ergonomics and assembling simulations.

1 Introduction

The research on new technologies and their applications is a crucial task to remain industrial technology leader. Since several years the Virtual Reality (VR) technology belongs integrally to the product development and production in the automobile industry. Good stereo projected VR solutions with their strongest property as the immersive visualization in scale 1:1 belong to the engineering process.

There are some reasons to investigate the appropriate use of this plastic visualization tool in shipbuilding: (a) replacement or complement of mock-ups, (b) high assembling-density of engine installations as shown in Fig. 1 and system coordination as well as the resulting complex system production, (c) high requirements for efficient training due to more frequent changes of crew and (d) remarkably lower investment cost of current VR systems by improved quality of software and hardware.

In this paper, possible fields of application are discussed based on results coming from an extensive in-house workshop. Experts from different fields, sales and proposal, ship and structural design, engine installation and system coordination, outfitting, production, training etc. took part in a kind of hands-on-training in front of a power wall. The participants gave their feedback by filling a questionnaire. Different ship subsystems, e.g. main engine rooms, sections with highly dense system coordination, a workshop, a bridge, a corvette mast module, a combat information center, as well as a complete yacht and a complete frigate have been visualized. The VR software was used for fly through, reviews, ergonomics, package and documentation.

Fig.1: Engine room

Virtual reality systems use tessellated (mostly in triangles) files for visualization, rather than the mathematically correct but complex CAD files. Herewith an improvement of the navigation speed even of a major amount of data can be then achieved. This VR property helps to get a faster overview of complete ship sections or even the whole ship layout. Hereby, review activities can be conducted as for example creating cut planes, requesting part information, measuring distances, etc. Documentation skills as putting markers, annotations and writing session protocol files in PDF or HTML format are also available.

2 Virtual reality in shipbuilding

Virtual reality can be defined as a computer-generated simulation of a real or imagined environment. For an immersive visualization, stereoscopic projection units and stereoscopic goggles are needed. A fly-stick can be used as io-device for fly-through activities. A tracking system scans movements of the goggles + fly-stick and forwards the positions to the visualization system.

As for the hardware of a VR system, most used environments seems to be the cave and the powerwall. A cave (computer aided virtual environment) can be understood as room with projected sides. Staying inside the cave, the immersive feeling is very strong. A single side environment, so-called powerwall, seems to be however suitable enough for shipbuilders regarding economic, handling and maintenance aspects.

The expectation of a smooth integration of a VR system into IT landscape is huge. Therefore some requirements have to be filled. A stand-alone working VR system does not play any roll in shipbuilding. It must be fully integrated into the ship design process. A smooth connection to the existing product data management (PDM) system is indispensable. Further, it should be possible to access the 3D Data in such way, that assembly groups can be functional (e.g. fresh water piping system) or spatial(e.g. a certain ship section).

Following features of a VR systems are (expected to be) supported:

1. For fly through: A fluent fly through navigation is the most standard feature of a VR system. It is possible to visualized a greater amount of data remembering that VR data is triangularized for performance purposes. With the help of a tracked fly stick it is possible to navigate freely in the space with 6 degrees of freedom. Some degrees of freedom can be constrained for simulating a walk navigation on a picked ground, e.g. on a deck.

2. For reviews: The execution of engineering reviews is a crucial task for shipbuilders. Several engineers, sometimes including the ship owner, review from time to time the progress of the building system. The tasks to be covered in such kind of sessions are for example the creation of cut planes, the setting of markers and annotations, the displaying part data, e.g. part name, the measure of distances, the creation of screen shots etc. More other standard CAD functionalities are also supported.

Important here is the treatment of generated review protocols. This information should promptly reach the data management system of the shipyard and the person to whom it may concern. By the next review, it is possible to fly directly to the markers for checking the geometry changes. This is possible since the markers are set in the space and not attached to any geometry.

3. For ergonomics: Ergonomic plays an important roll in workspaces. The design of workspaces should guarantee a comfortable working environment. For naval vessel, ergonomics studies help remarkable the design of consoles of for example combat information centers. A human model can be set onto a chair for analyzing instrument reachability and visibility of displays. One can get the view of the human model and walk through. The positioning of the human model by the fly stick or direct input, the visualization of reach-ability regions, the visualization of visibility regions are also possible features.

4. For assembling: Assembling simulations as well as physical collision tests are package functionalities. Herewith, engine modules can be picked up and moved through for studying possible disassembling routes for maintenance purposes. Assembling simulation are highly welcomed by production and maintenance teams. Such a simulation can save time by assembling ship components instead of viewing at drawings, specially for complex assemblies.

5. For customizing: Most VR tools available on the market are generally design for the automobile industry. A couple of extensions should be realized for covering functionalities expected by shipbuilders. An application programming interface (API) facilitates the customizing of such extensions as for example to show/hide a frame system, to show/hide all part names, to show/hide additional information (even in 2D), etc.

3 Some of possible application fields

Fig.2: Review: Piping below floor plate

Fig.3: Review: Half-transparent floor

Fig.4: Review: Bridge with textures

Fig.5: Assembling: Collision arrows

Fig.6: Ergonomic: Reach-ability range

Fig.7: Ergonomics: Human-Engine Model

4 Workshop results

An intensive in-house workshop were conducted by using a VR system from IC:IDO consisting of a powerwall with a display of 2.0×1.5 m (2 projectors SXVA+ 1400×1050), optical tracking, 3D input device and head tracked goggles. Daily session contended a brief introduction by a VR expert for about

30 minute. Later, the participants had a hands-on-training. At the end of each session, questionnaires have been distributed.

A block of questions were related to the VR system and the other block to possible application fields in shipbuilding. Results presented here, most relevant only, reflect the feedback of engineers working on detailed design of engine installation and system coordination.

An important aspect by analyzing the feedback is the consideration of emotional comments of participants. During the workshop, many participants got immediately impressed from the immersivity. In some cases it influenced the way of filling the questionnaire regardless of thinking about the real benefit. This aspect is to be filtered.

Fig.8: Some criteria of a VR system

Figure 8 reflects the opinion of participants regarding some criteria of the VR system. An overall good acceptance of presented VR system could be appreciated, specially the navigation speed and the immersivity by a 1:1 scale. Under hardware handling is meant, the friendly handling of the fly-stick tested here. The fly-through navigation implies a certain training. The statement that any PC-mouse user could navigate after 15 minutes failed.

As for the main goal of the workshop, Fig. 9 shows the opinion regarding to the possible fields of application. An unclear feedback can be extracted for application possibility in the initial design . Approximately 30% of participants disagree with the reasonable applicability. Current visualization tools support well the expectation of ship initial designers. A little more clear diagram can be shown for the detail design. About 20% of participants still disagree mainly because of unfilled requirements as like 3D data is not constantly available. The rest belongs to the 3D modeled engine installation and system

coordination. Presented 1:1 scaled immersive visualization seems to be really a solution for better and faster understanding of complex ship systems.

As per diagram, ergonomics shows a greater acceptance. This result has been however influenced by the emotional appreciation of presented human model. Most shipbuilders may agree that ergonomics does not own currently a high priority in shipbuilding. As for manufacturing, sometimes at shipyards the interface engineering / production suffers a downstream of data. While the engineering struggles to construct in 3D, the production gets later two dimensional drawings only. For new production teams, it could take some time for understanding complex systems. The workshop feedback shows not only great

Fig.9: Fields of application: suitability feedback

acceptance for the ship production, but also the production seems really to be benefited by a VR system. Three dimensional data would then come directly from the engineering and be visualized at production workshops. A real-case session showed the clear benefit. In this case, 3 production and 2 engineering employees tried to find an access into the bow of a yacht. After approximately 90 minutes the search failed. The same search started minutes later on the powerwall. A solution was found in 20 minutes.

Simulation based training seems to be also an appropriate application field as shown in a developed concept by Blohm + Voss. A two dimensional machinery software is combined with the immersive visualization for training purpose. Finally, the sales department would immediately like to have a powerwall at their room. They see it as an acquisition tool. A detailed analysis showed however that it does not help for proposals, since at that time less 3D data is available. It could be use only for showing previous vessels.

Figure 10 reflects the opinion regarding the saving of engineering hours by using a VR system. Even if the real-case mentioned before saved approximately three quarters of the time and a top manager prognosticated a saving of 10%, it is difficult to get an accurate answer to details about where exactly and how many hours could be saved. This complicates an investment analysis requested by the company's controlling.

Figure 11 shows the feedback about the improvement of the meetings quality by using virtual reality. An overall acceptance can be extracted. This tool was widely accepted as an appropriate tool for quality management. Managers have outed the use of this tool also for controlling purposes.

Figure 12 gives a picture of the possible utilization of a VR system. Here again, those participants who have weekly coordination meetings have voted for frequently use. As next it seems to be necessary the analysis of the capacity utilization of affected departments.

Additionally, some conservative comments have been captured related to the serious use of the VR system. Some participants saw it as a toy and not really as a working tool. Further, in presented case, the real use of 3D parametric CAD software has a life of about 40 months only and it does not cover the complete engineering process. Some departments are still working with drawing tools.

Fig.10: Saving engineering hours

Fig.11: Enhancing VR meetings quality

Fig.12: Using a VR system

5 Conclusion

Results of an in-house workshop on virtual reality in shipbuilding have been presented here. The goal was to find possible application fields with positive return on investment.

Expensive and technological demanding machinery spaces (engine installation and system coordination) resulted to be the most benefited application field by the VR systems with 1:1 scaled immersive visualization. The reason: assembly density of complex engine and machinery rooms keeps continuously increasing. A VR system can be helpful for a better and faster understanding of such complex ship systems and used as tool for quality management.

The workshop showed also certain requirements for well-working VR systems. An easy and robust integrity into the (hopefully CAD homogeneous) IT infrastructure for a fast and direct 3D-data access for visualization is indispensable. Further, review screen shots and annotations should be able to be sent to the PDM system or to be forwarded to whom it may concern. Delayed or inaccessible information is counterproductive. Shipyards have entered into the 3D ship design world couple of years ago. Additionally, the VR hardware cost has reduced remarkable. These reasons move shipyards more and more to analyze the acquisition of a VR system. This is doubtless a step for trying to remain technology leader.

Two important aspects are worth to be remembered. A VR system does not generate extra engineering work, it does only visualized existing data. Further, many of the CAE problems are not due to less visual quality but linked to the complex shipbuilding work-flow constrained by the e.g. short construction period, the strong parallelized work, the constantly construction update due to late information, etc.

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Efficient Exploitation of Existing Corporate Knowledge in Conceptual Ship Design

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Abstract

This paper presents some fundamental processes related to design inference and knowledge acquisition in the context of shipbuilding. Key categories of existing knowledge relevant for conceptual design are identified and classified. Alternative strategies for making this knowledge operable in a conceptual design context are discussed.

1. Introduction

In the conceptual design phase some of the most important decisions regarding the vessel are made. Various sources estimate that between 60% and 80% of the total life cycle cost is determined during this part of the design process, *Dierolf and Richter (1989)*. All later design decisions have to be taken within the boundaries set by the decisions made in this phase, with only limited influence on cost and overall performance.

Conceptual design is also characterized by a high degree of design freedom, Fig.1. The design problem is open – no decisions have yet been made that limit the options beyond the bounds given in the top-level mission requirements. All subsequent decisions will put constraints on this freedom. Since not making decisions is hardly a viable alternative, the effort must be put on making these early decisions correct. One of the main obstacles to improving decision-making in conceptual design is that the knowledge to support these early decisions is limited. By knowledge is meant all types of facts, methods, heuristics, and experiences that are both relevant and can be identified, transferred and made operable in the decision-making context of the design problem.

Fig.1: As the design process proceeds, the knowledge about the design increases, while the freedom to make changes decreases

The limited availability of relevant and operable knowledge can be attributed to several sources. One is the inherent uncertainty related to the mapping between the design space and the performance space, that is, the uncertainty in the transformation between the form and the function of the vessel. This uncertainty can be related to the ship system itself, e.g. available volumes, final weights, position of the centre of gravity, material quality, or to the environment in which the ship system operates, e.g. freight rates, cargo inflow, costs, transport demand, weather conditions. Because of this, it is difficult to establish analytical relationships between the design variables and the set of design goals and

mission requirements. To a large extent these relationships have to be modelled on the basis of empirical data and heuristic rules.

Another aspect of the limited availability of knowledge is the relatively high ratio of qualitative to quantitative information. This makes it more difficult to transfer, share and store design knowledge, and also makes the knowledge less available for computer-based design tools which require a high degree of formalism.

Despite the importance of the decisions made in the early stages of the design process, only a minor share of the resources is spend here. *Levander (1991)* estimated the time and money allocated to the pre-contract phase to only 1% - 2% of that of the post-contract phase at a typical shipyard. Taking into consideration the complexity of the structure to be built and the financial commitment made in the contract, this effort may seem too limited. However, it needs to be traded off against the risk of not receiving the contract, thus making the allocation of resources for conceptual ship design a difficult decision problem in itself.

To summarise, the decisions made in the conceptual design phase are important, yet the provision of support for these decision is made difficult by problem characteristics such as uncertainty, lack of knowledge, and time and resource constraints. In the remainder of this paper, I will present and discuss some strategies that can contribute to alleviating this situation based on exploiting knowledge embedded in various existing, and originally not design-related, sources of data and information within the company. The first part of the paper is based on work at NTNU some time ago, *Erikstad (1997)*, while the latter is based on a project in progress with DNV.

2. Knowledge acquisition in conceptual design

Conceptual design is generally characterised by a lack of knowledge. In light of this, the acquisition and maintenance of the knowledge itself becomes an important task. Let D_i represents design descriptions, I_i represents design interpretations (derived performance), and K_s and K_i represents syntactic and interpretive knowledge, respectively. The acquisition of interpretive knowledge can be modelled as

$$K_i = \tau_1(\{D_1, D_2, \dots\}, I) \quad (1)$$

or alternatively as

$$K_i = \tau_2(\{D_1, I_1\}, \{D_2, I_2\}, \dots) \quad (2)$$

Accordingly, we can model the acquisition of syntactic knowledge as:

$$K_s = \tau_3(\{D_1, D_2, \dots\}, [V]) \quad (3)$$

The inference process in the transformations above is equivalent to *induction*, where a general knowledge statement is concluded from a set of observations or test cases, for instance based on a set of existing vessels from a database or product model. For example, we may have:

$D_1, I_1:$	$DW(ShipA) = 200.000 \wedge V(ShipA) = 15, Resistance(ShipA) = 1200$
$D_2, I_2:$	$DW(ShipB) = 212.000 \wedge V(ShipB) = 14.8, Resistance(ShipB) = 1240$
$D_3, I_3:$	\dots
$K_i:$	$\forall x DW(x) \wedge V(x) \Rightarrow Resistance(x) = f(DW(x), V(x))$

or, in the case of syntactic knowledge generation:

$D_1:$	$V(ShipA) = 15.0 \wedge IsType(ShipA, TypeX)$
$D_2:$	$V(ShipB) = 14.8 \wedge IsType(ShipB, TypeX)$
$D_3:$	\dots
$K_s:$	$\forall x IsType(x, TypeX) \Rightarrow V(x) \text{ isTypically around } 15 \text{ knots}$

One typical example of the transformations τ_1 and τ_2 is the use of statistical inference techniques, with regression analyses as the dominant method. These methods can be used to derive generic empirical relations between the ship main characteristics and derived performances, such as resistance and propulsion, *Holtrop and Mennen (1982)*, or steel weight, *Watson and Gilfillan (1976)*, *Harvald and Jensen (1992)*. They are also used to generate syntactic knowledge, for instance determine design lanes for parameters and/or parameter combinations. Syntactic knowledge generation is closely related to the use of ‘prototypes’ and design ‘classes’.

Syntactic and interpretive knowledge is usually made available as an embedded part of preliminary ship design tools, and not obtained as part of the design process itself. The main drawbacks of this approach is that

- the available design knowledge may have limited validity for the current design context, in particular for original design
- the embedded design knowledge is likely to become outdated as new knowledge and experience is developed
- the embedded knowledge may appear imperceivable – as “black boxes” – for the human designer, with little or no control of underlying assumptions and quality

As a consequence, there is an increased focus on both the integration of learning and knowledge acquisition into the design process itself, *Aamodt (1991)*, *Duffy (1993)*, and on the ability to support dynamic knowledge generation adapted to the current design context. This will be discussed further towards the end of the paper.

3. Data vs. Information vs. Knowledge

Since this paper focuses on exploiting “corporate knowledge”, it is appropriate to define the term “knowledge” more precisely, and relate it to concepts such as information and data. According to *Aamodt (1993)*, knowledge is always subjective, and its existence within a particular system assumes the existence of a corresponding reasoning agent. Thus, for a computer system to possess knowledge it needs to contain reasoning processes to make inferences within that particular domain. Correspondingly, information is viewed as interpreted data, where the interpretation process uses knowledge to transform data into information. This is illustrated in Fig.2.

Fig.2: The distinction between knowledge, information, and data, *Aamodt (1993)*

In this scheme design becomes a process of using knowledge for interpreting data structures and elaborating on design information about the design task, in order to produce information about the design product.

The distinction here between knowledge and information is, however, somewhat unclear. Knowledge is derived by human beings from information by reasoning, discussion, and other mind-involving processes, and “we use knowledge generated by other scientists as information to obtain new knowledge”, *Bras (1992)*. This must be understood such that knowledge by definition only can exist within the human mind. Also, the moment this knowledge is transferred into another medium, whether this is another human being or a computer, it must be regarded as information according to the above view.

However, the distinction between data, information, and knowledge loses some of its importance when taking a holistic view of design where the design system consists of both a human being and a computer, which is always the case in a conceptual design process. From the outside of this system it would be impossible to distinguish between the three categories, since simple data structures and the corresponding reasoning mechanisms would be tightly integrated.

Thus, from a practical point-of-view it would not be possible, nor desirable, to objectively and uniquely make a distinction between the elements to be operated upon in a conceptual design process into a rigid schema of data, information, and knowledge. Rather, this classification has meaning only with respect to how these elements are used in the process. For instance, consider the facts related to a previously built ship as an element to be operated upon in the design process. It can be regarded as data when streamed to a file, as information when used as input to a regression analysis, or as knowledge when used to derive conclusions about a similar ship. The representation of this knowledge element can be similar in all three cases. Thus, it is neither possible, nor necessary, to classify such elements as data, information, or knowledge a priori. Thus, in this paper I will make no systematic distinction between these terms – and generally use the term “knowledge” as a common term.

4. A General Taxonomy of Ship Design Knowledge

What characterises the knowledge relevant for preliminary ship design, taking into consideration both the knowledge possessed by the human designer, and knowledge embedded in computer-based design tools? In the following list some typical examples of such knowledge are listed:

- “The required average increase in propulsion power to maintain the specified service speed on a North Atlantic crossing is 20% - 25%”
- “Most VLCCs have a $L/B > 5.5$ ”
- “Froude’s number is defined as $F_n = \frac{V}{\sqrt{gL}}$ ”
- “Ship A has dimensions $L_{pp}=138$ m, $B=22$ m, ..., installed KW= 8000, ...”
- “The main characteristics of the hull can be described by the parameters L, B, T, C_b, \dots ”
- “The required service speed for the ship-to-be-designed is 13.5 kn”
- “The steel weight of containership might be estimated using the function $w_{st}(\dots)$ ”

The first statement contains a general heuristic, a “rule-of-thumb”, derived through experience. The second contains heuristics for a particular class of ships, possibly obtained through a comparative study of ship of a similar type. The third statement is simply a definition, relating one element of the domain vocabulary to other elements. The fourth statement refers to a particular case, for instance a previously built ship. The fifth expresses syntactic knowledge on what constitutes a valid description of the design object, and the sixth contains knowledge about a design goal. The last statement contains interpretive knowledge as an analysis procedure for a particular ship type. We see that the type and characteristics of the knowledge elements in ship design show a considerable variation. This variation is for instance related to what part of the design process the knowledge is valid, to what part of design object it is relevant, and to the semantic content, or “quality”, of the knowledge.

Fig.3: Classifying dimensions in a taxonomy of knowledge, *Aamodt (1991)*

Fig.3 shows a possible knowledge taxonomy. Such a taxonomy will have two main purposes:

- To serve as a scheme to identify the specific nature of ship design knowledge. This is relevant for determining what representation of the knowledge is appropriate, which again will be decisive for what kind of operations upon the knowledge that is possible. For instance, if we by using the proposed taxonomy were able to classify the dominant knowledge within a particular design domain as numeric, deep, and procedural, we might choose a representation based on numerical variables, constraints and goals, leading to operations research as a possible problem-solving paradigm. If, on the other hand, the knowledge within the domain was predominantly classified as symbolic, shallow, and declarative, a rule-based representation and a predicate calculus inference engine may be appropriate. It is this use of the taxonomy that is most relevant for this paper.
- To serve as a scheme for organising knowledge at the application level in a computer-based design tool. Given that we want the ability to access a large body of declarative knowledge in the design process, this knowledge need to be stored in a way that is both efficient from a modelling point-of-view, and intuitively correct from the perspective of the designer. These two aspects of knowledge organisation might impose conflicting requirements. From a system development perspective we generally want to keep as few dimensions on the knowledge as possible, while from the designers perspective the most efficient way of organising the knowledge will depend on the particular situation, and hence, as many perspectives as possible should be supported to account for this diversity.

5. A Map of Preliminary Ship Design Knowledge

The taxonomy of knowledge presented in the previous section is useful for answering questions such as: “Given a knowledge element e , how can this element be classified using the dimensions $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$?”. This conceptualisation of the domain is a prerequisite for developing a model to be implemented into a computer application.

However, before this classification scheme can be used, we need to identify the elements to be classified, that is, the knowledge elements within the domain. In other words, what is the scope of the actual knowledge taking part in a typical, real-world ship design situation?

As a starting point, the knowledge content may be categorised into five main groups. This categorisation is orthogonal to the knowledge dimensions presented earlier in this paper. These

groups are:

- Previous design cases and existing vessel data
- Generalised design cases, templates
- Syntactic knowledge
- Rules and facts
- Problem solving methods, strategy, and tactics

In the following, each of these groups will be discussed in more detail, and at the end of this section I will draw some general conclusions about the character of the knowledge pertaining preliminary ship design.

5.1 Single design cases

From the practising designer's point-of-view, case-based knowledge in the form of previously designed or built ships represent an important asset in the preliminary ship design situation. A typical application of this knowledge is the use of a past design case or existing vessel as a starting point for a new design. This case can then be modified to account for the specific requirements given for the ship-to-be-designed.

An equally important utilisation of past cases lies in the human designer's capability to draw analogies between the present design situation and past problem-solving experiences. This ability makes the human knowledge base a highly dynamic structure, continually improving its problem-solving capabilities through learning. Much of the knowledge content of such processes belongs to what we classify as tacit knowledge, for which a logical path of explanations is difficult to make.

Currently there exist no computer-implementable inference methods matching the human ability in this area. However, in recent years a substantial research effort has been put into the development of efficient methods for exploiting the knowledge content of case based data efficiently. This has led to a group of different methods which can be classified under the terms machine learning and case-based reasoning (CBR). These methods makes historical data more accessible by using advanced knowledge representations and inductive machine learning to structure the information and discover useful knowledge.

It may be argued that case descriptions themselves can not be classified as knowledge – their semantic content is dependent on a reasoning agent to relate the cases to the current design problem. This is parallel to the discussion in the beginning of this chapter about making a distinction between data, information, and knowledge. Without the ability to make such relations the knowledge content of each case is close to zero.

So far in the ship design domain, reasoning capabilities have been limited to the human designer, developed as a skill basically through experience. This makes it difficult to exploit the knowledge content of previous design cases in computer-based design systems, and emphasises the importance of an efficient man-machine interface and a rational division of tasks between the human designer and the computer.

The "knowledge content" of single design cases is not only a function of the amount and accuracy of the information content. Some specific designs (instances) are said to capture the typicality of a *class* of designs. Such design cases are often denoted archetypes, *Coyne (1990)*, p.30. The concept of archetypes enables us to reason about specific design instances as a substitute for more abstract class descriptions. For instance, we may consider the Fjellstrand 38.8m to be the archetypal medium-size passenger catamaran, or the Aker H-3 as the archetypal twin-pontoon semi-submersible drilling platform. Archetypes should be distinguished from prototypes, that may be defined as a generic design not bound to a particular design instance, though archetypes and prototypes tend to play much the same role in the design process.

There are three main applications of existing cases in conceptual design:

- by copying a single previous design in part or in whole, and eventually modifying it to comply with new functional requirements
- as an information source from which context-relevant knowledge can be derived and made operable for the design problem at hand. A common example of this is by the statistical analysis of a set of existing vessels using regression analysis.
- as a benchmark for the assessment and verification of a given design, by comparing both key performance parameters and main characteristics

For all these three applications of existing designs, a fundamental problem is how the relevant information can be identified, transferred and made operable in the context of the current design problem. This will be discussed in more depth towards the end of this paper.

The main sources of information related to existing designs that can be made operable in a conceptual design context are the following:

- Vessel information databases. These can be external, such as the Lloyds Register Fairplay database, or internal, based on previously designed and/or delivered vessels. These databases are typically easily available, and they follow a standardised scheme for vessel data across different ship types.
- Vessel product models. Here, the different parts and aspects of the vessel are broken down into a heterarchical model of entities and relations. Such product models typically have a much higher degree of detail than do vessel information databases, thus providing opportunities to derive design-relevant knowledge that are both more specific and with a higher quality. However, these opportunities come at the cost of a significantly increased complexity.
- Existing design specifications. These may be high-level (brief/outline) specifications, or more detailed (build/contract). Traditionally, the knowledge embedded in existing specifications is reused simply by copying and using an existing specification as a starting point for a new one. The quality costs related to this approach is discussed in previous papers, *Hagen and Erikstad (2002)*, *Erikstad and Hagen (2003)*. For instance, specification errors are typically and repeatedly copied into new specifications, as are customer-specific requirements that were valid in the previous projects. In addition, this approach will tend to inhibit development as new projects frequently are based on old solutions. The results may be higher cost, higher uncertainty, outdated designs and reduced competitiveness with respect to winning the bid. With the TenderSuite system, the reuse of existing design specifications has been moved to a system level rather than a vessel/project level.
- Operational experience. In the maritime industry, product development in general has been based on the close collaboration and continuous feedback from the shipowners to the yards and ship consultants. This feedback has typically been ad hoc based on the accumulated experience of the crew and superintendent. With the advent of lifecycle oriented product models, the opportunities for deriving the relations between a given design solutions and the corresponding operational performances, such as damages, repairs, etc. One example is the DNV Nauticus product model, using a relatively detailed vessel model as a backbone for all class-related operational recordings by the surveyors boarding the vessel around the globe. Lifecycle product models like this creates an opportunity to dynamically derive answers to questions like “What are the dominating damage types and hot spots for deck machinery for ice-classed containerships?”. Recording, structuring and giving access to this information is a necessary, but not a sufficient, condition for enabling dynamic, adaptive, design-for-operation capabilities. In addition, a methodology and mechanism for identifying and processing the relevant information, and making it operable in a conceptual design context.

5.2 Generalised design cases

As human designers we are also able to reason about design objects without recalling specific

instances or cases. In the human learning process previous experiences with particular ship designs are stored as generalised concepts, or schema, in long term memory. These schema are highly dynamic constructs that are continuously changed and refined over time as more knowledge and experience is gathered. Such schema, when used in product development, are often called templates. Since generalised design cases, or templates, extracts knowledge across a larger set of single cases, it represents an efficient mechanism for storing knowledge. The drawback is that we risk some of the knowledge content being lost, since we cannot anticipate all possible uses of this knowledge in the future.

In the ship design domain, generalised design cases can take several forms. One typical example is the use of dimensionless hull forms from standard series, such as the Taylor-Gertler Series, Series 60, BSRA Series, etc. From these a hull form that is likely to have a favourable resistance performance can be chosen, and subsequently scaled to fit the present design requirements, such as minimum deadweight and volume.

Another way of generalising design knowledge is by the use of templates. Such templates can be described as a collection of design models entities, such as variables, bounds, constraints, and procedures that are relevant for a particular ship type. A typical example of the use of templates is given in *Smith (1992)* for the design of a frigate. The frigate template defines a set of variables to be used, a set of bounds and constraints expressing typical “design lanes” for this ship type, and a set of procedures mapping the design variables to the relevant measures of performance, such as propulsion, seakeeping, and cost. Though some of the information within the template is likely to be augmented when used for a particular design problem, the bulk of the information is typically reused, thus representing a generalised case.

Fig.4: Capturing design knowledge in templates, as part of a specification product platform, *Erikstad and Hagen (2006)*

An important problem related to the use of templates and other forms of generalised design cases is how to handle differences in the generality of the embedded knowledge. This generality may vary from being globally valid, to being valid only for one particular ship. One way to handle this is by integrating all templates into a single one, and taking care of the differences in knowledge content between the sub-types by branching. The main disadvantage with this approach is that the template tends to be complex when a large number of different sub-types are integrated. The opposite alternative is to provide one template for every sub-type down to a certain level of abstraction. While this will reduce the complexity of each template, it implies an extensive duplication of knowledge. It

also tends to make the maintenance of the knowledge base difficult, because a change in a globally valid knowledge item needs to be tracked into each single template. The advent of object-oriented technology has to some degree solved this problem, by using classes as a way to generalise knowledge, and by providing mechanisms such as inheritance and polymorphism to handle a seamless integration of differences in knowledge scope.

The use of generalised templates for specification development is discussed in *Erikstad and Hagen (2006)*. Here, a template is a selection of nodes in the system breakdown structure that are relevant for a particular type of vessel. For each of these nodes either a boilerplate text for the system specification, or an enumeration of variant descriptions to be selected from, is given. These templates may again be a part of a larger product platform structure, where templates are grouped into product families as well as being part of an inheritance hierarchy that combines specialisation with efficient reuse. This is illustrated in Fig.4.

5.3 Syntactic knowledge

A prerequisite for representing knowledge about a particular domain is a vocabulary V . The vocabulary is a set of basic elements, or concepts, used to describe the design object. In the ship design domain the vocabulary is typically dominated by the physical parts of the ship, such as hull, propeller, machinery, and properties such as length, beam, depth, etc. Knowledge about the vocabulary is part of syntactic knowledge K_s .

In the design process the vocabulary elements are related into a valid structure to form design descriptions, D . This is done intuitively by the experienced designer, by the formation of concepts in the human mind. In the computer this can be captured by basic design processes such as the transformation function operating on the vocabulary and syntactic knowledge: $D = \tau_d(K_s, V)$.

The syntactic knowledge being part of this process can take different forms. One is the provision of a unique naming and identification convention. An example of this is the use of a so-called grouping system, where the different concepts used in the description of the ship is given a unique reference. Thus, a consistent model can be maintained across different applications and users.

Fig.5: A mapping from a component-oriented to a system-oriented view is required for direct, context-dependent lookup into supplier and product catalogues

In the Norwegian maritime industry there exists a well-established system breakdown structure, the SFI system, which is used across most types of shipbuilding projects. These projects range from small offshore supply and fishing vessels, to larger passenger ships. Thus, for the end product of a design process that also comprises the design and specification of the ship main systems, the SFI system is a de facto functional breakdown structure. However, much of the available information that supports the design process has other breakdown structures, and in order to exploit this information, some sort of mapping is required. For instance, product, type and supplier catalogues are typically structured according to a component breakdown structure. This is mainly an orthogonal view relative to the system- or function-oriented breakdown structure of the specification, and will require a mapping table that describes what components are part of which ship systems, Fig.5, thus enabling the direct lookup into supplier and product catalogues, Fig.6.

Fig.6: System-wise lookup into supplier and product catalogues using syntactic knowledge encoded in component-to-system mapping tables

5.4 Design codes, rules, and catalogues

The knowledge content of preliminary design also comprises design codes, rules, and catalogues. This knowledge may originate from for instance governmental authorities, class societies, equipment manufacturers, or as national or international standards. Much of this knowledge serves as constraints on the design, stating minimum requirements for the ship-to-be-designed. Representative examples are minimum thickness requirements for structural members, minimum distances between bulkheads, and specification of required equipment. Thus, this knowledge may be classified as descriptive and rule-oriented. However, in recent years we have seen a tendency towards the inclusion of procedure-oriented classification rules, prescribing a set of algorithms or methods to use for making a particular design decision. This knowledge is usually embedded in analysis tools developed by the main classification societies.

5.5 Design strategy and tactics, and general problem solving knowledge

Design strategy and tactics comprises the meta-knowledge in the design process, i.e. how to best design the design process itself. This may include knowledge about what should be the primary decision variables, the sequence of operations upon these variables, the size and granularity of the search space at different stages of the design process, and the subdivision of the design problem into

suitable units. The primary source of this knowledge in the design process is the human designer, based on his/hers experience and expertise. Thus, for this knowledge to be come operable in a computer-based design system, an efficient human-computer interface is required, supporting a true meta-design process. This knowledge may also be captured as design procedures. Such design procedures may be implicitly represented in computer-based design systems, either hidden from the system user in the background computational processes, or visible for the user through the interaction process enforced by the system.

6. Making existing information applicable in the current design context

So far in this paper I have discussed various sources and forms of existing corporate knowledge. From the practicing designer's perspective, however, these knowledge sources are of little value if it is not possible to make them operable in the current design context. The process of reusing existing information will typically follow a three step process:

- Identify existing information (single cases or collections) that are relevant and valid for the current design case. Typically, this implies selection and filtering, which will require some measure of information quality as a basis for ranking.
- Process this information to extract the knowledge that is significant for the current design case. Examples are the extraction of averages and ranges in a collection, regression analyses for estimation functions, visual diagrams of key relations, scaling, etc.
- Transfer the information/knowledge back into the current design process.

In the following, I will discuss each of these three steps in some more detail. The discussion is primarily related to the exploitation of knowledge embedded in existing vessel data stored in a product model.

6.1 Identifying information relevant to the present design context

Consider a reasonably detailed lifecycle product model, containing vessel data for 5000+ vessels, each containing an average of 4000 components (tanks, spaces, systems, equipment, etc.) and 16.000 properties. Each component is classified according to a library of 1000+ different types. In addition, assume that each vessel is described by an average of 6000 functions according to a function library of 5000+. In addition comes data related to operational recordings, administrative data, attached documentation and, for some, 3D geometry data.

Modern ICT technologies, like data mining and OLAP, provide the necessary means for diving into this vast pool of data. But defining the required OLAP cubes and cube properties on a case-by-case basis is like searching for a needle in a haystack. In addition, there is likely to be performance and response-time issues related to this approach, considering the large size of the database. At the other end of the scale, we may provide a limited set of predefined searches, making it relatively simple and efficient to use for the designer, but also limiting the possibilities of adapting the search to the specific characteristics of the design problem at hand.

An information retrieval strategy that aims at balancing the conflicting requirements of simplicity and efficiency vs. flexibility and adaptability may comprise the following elements:

- Defining a limited set of core filtering dimensions, such as vessel type and subtype, vessel size category and, in most cases, age. Whether this will return the most relevant subset of data will of course be dependent on what response parameter is to be estimated. Still, it represents a simple, broadly accepted first stage criteria.
- Filtering the functions and components, and corresponding properties, retrieved by using the current context of the system breakdown structure applied in the design project. This will typically require the provision of a mapping mechanism as was discussed in Section 5.3.

To the extent possible, some measure of information quality should be generated in parallel, and

presented so that it is conceivable for the user. Such measures may then support rational decisions about dataset size, dimensionality and bounds. The R-squared index in linear regression is one such measure that may be used under certain conditions to select among competing retrieval schemes.

6.2 Processing information to extract context-relevant knowledge

The processing of information to generate context-relevant knowledge may follow two separate paths:

- Processing strategies aimed at presenting compiled, structured information to the human designer, that, combined with human expertise, will derive new knowledge. One common example is to provide a set of diagrams and plots of vessel or systems performances, with drill-down capabilities that may provide explanations for deviations from the main design lanes, Fig.7. Using a comprehensive product model as a basis, some degree of pre-definition is likely to be required from a performance point-of-view, for instance by extracting data to an intermediate storage.

Fig.7: Providing compiled structured information to the designer

- Processing strategies performed by the computer with little or no human interaction. An example of this is the prediction of vessel or system performances based on statistical analysis techniques, such as regression analysis. This may be an efficient approach in many cases but has two main drawbacks: It creates “black boxes” for the designer, thus providing limited insight into and understanding of the design space. And it may remove the quality assurance element of an experienced human designer.

In some cases the identified information that is brought into the design context is unstructured, leaving a human interpretation as the only possible option. One example, Fig.8, is providing access to libraries of system-specific specification elements having a textual representation, requiring a human designer both to interpret and extract possible knowledge elements.

Fig.8: Providing unstructured information that requires a human designer for interpretation, such as system specification from as-built vessels

7. Conclusion

The purpose of this paper has been to identify relevant types of knowledge being available to support the conceptual ship design process, and how these elements can be made operable within the context of a specific design task. What we have seen is that the nature of the relevant domain knowledge covers a large span – from deep, generic, procedure-oriented, to shallow, specific, fact-oriented knowledge. This poses a considerable challenge to the way design-relevant knowledge is to be identified, processed and made operable in the current design context. Different strategies are needed, though a common denominator seems to be a tight symbiosis between a computer that provides excellent capabilities for the identification, filtering, processing and presentation of information, and a human designer that are able to combine the provided information with experience and expertise in order to derive design knowledge that can be applied in the current design context.

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Postponement of Product Configuration Decisions in ETO Industries

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Abstract

This paper addresses the postponement of product configuration decisions made by customers and suppliers in ETO Industries. Related work is reviewed to identify benefits, and two cases are presented. One case describes a marine boiler manufacturer and the other describes the commercial airplane industry. Both cases describe how decision postponement is currently being or could be utilized to reduce the risks due to uncertainty. These risks include performing significant engineering work if an order is not taken or requirements change over time. The drivers of decision postponement are different between the two cases, as one is primarily driven by market dynamics and the other by internal and customer processes. Regardless decision postponement can be utilized to reduce risk and increase flexibility.

1. Introduction

Engineer to Order operation has several characteristics differentiating it from mass production or mass customization. One main characteristic is that after a sale, a significant amount of engineering is necessary preceding manufacturing of the product, *Caron and Fiore (1995)*. This is due to a very high variety in the product portfolio, large complex products and as opposed to mass customization, typically a relatively low production volume, *Rahim and Baksh (2003)*. Engineer to Order operation typically implies that only a limited amount of information is known about the product at the time it is sold. However, prior to committing to a legally binding sales contract, enough information must be known to ensure that the price quoted to the customer will result in a satisfying contribution margin. Fig.1 illustrates the typical process from initial customer contact to delivery and commissioning of a product. Since the production phase is preceded by an engineering phase, not all production processes or components have been determined for the product. This logically implies that this information is not known in the sales phase either, and thus some uncertainty about the product exists in the sales phase.

Fig.1: Typical ETO sales-delivery process

1.1 Product Configuration

Product configuration is frequently used to address the needs for defining product variants in mass customization environments. However, as this technology has emerged, it has been applied in conjunction with other types of operation, among other ETO. Traditionally product configuration has been applied to aid a customer or sales person to select a specific product from a solution space of product variety. The purpose of this process has been to present the user with the variety to select from, perform the selection process and retain this information. When product configuration is applied in ETO, the purpose of the process is often to limit the variety to a certain scope due to standardization issues and furthermore render the sales-delivery process more efficient. For advanced ETO products, product configuration can furthermore assist in making choices about the product to ensure consistent design of products. Although most experiences have been gained about product configuration in mass customization companies, a number of successful cases have been described about product configuration implementations in ETO companies, *Hvam et al. (2006)*, *Petersen and Jørgensen (2005)*.

1.2 Related Work

Postponement first introduced by *Alderson (1950)* is often used as a means to improve agility where product variety is high and customer demand is not easy to forecast, *Feitzinger and Lee (1997)*. In its original form, a postponement strategy typically implies that the point where the product is differentiated to meet customer's demand is postponed to the latest possible point in the supply chain, *Feitzinger and Lee (1997)*. This has in particular been recognized as a means to achieve mass customization, since postponement in these cases will imply lower inventories and better responsiveness to customer orders, *Lampel and Mintzberg (1996)*, *Feitzinger and Lee (1997)*. One point in the supply chain is usually decided to be the point where the differentiation for a specific customer order happens, which is usually referred to as the customer order decoupling point (CODP), *Rudberg and Wikner (2004)*. In some cases however, it may be beneficial to introduce several differentiation points in the supply chain, *Garg and Tang (1997)*.

Hvam et al. (2006) describe how decision postponement, which in this case is postponement of issuing a detailed quotation, has benefited a specific ETO company in relation to product configuration. Less iteration was needed in the detailed design phase, since basic decisions had been in focus in the early phases rather than low level details. Also the postponement of detailed design activities meant that more budget quotations could be issued since fewer resources were needed. This ultimately led to a higher number of orders since orders which at first hand could seem uninteresting were less risky to bid for, and thus a higher total number of quotations were issued leading to a higher number of orders.

2 Case Descriptions

This section introduces two cases to illustrate decision postponement in ETO and different advantages from this. The first case is Aalborg Industries, a marine boiler manufacturer, while the second case is the commercial airplane industry.

2.1 Aalborg Industries

2.1.1 Case Introduction

The first case company is Aalborg Industries (AI), a Danish manufacturer of steam boilers and heat generating systems for marine and industrial applications. The primary industry in which AI operates is shipbuilding which implies that the degree of customization is very high while the quantity produced for a certain configuration typically does not exceed half a dozen. Often only a single product is manufactured. The high degree of customization is due to customers' varying preferences and requirements for integration of the product into the surrounding system which in most cases is a ship. The sales-delivery process in AI is characterized by an intensive customer interaction since the customer is directly involved in many of the business processes from quotation to delivery which will be described in detail below. The main product types include oil fired boilers, waste heat recovery systems, thermal fluid heaters and various other system components included to create a functioning system.

2.1.1 Sales-Delivery Process

The process from an initial customer inquiry through sales to the final delivery of a product spans a long time compared to many other industries. The shortest possible delivery time for a product, depending on product type, is a few months and the longest time for the sales-delivery process can span several years. The sales-delivery process, here extended to encompass commissioning and after sales service is illustrated in Fig.2 where the interaction between AI and its customers is also shown. In the following, this process will be elaborated to identify how the product configuration is being defined in each phase of the process.

Fig.2: the sales-delivery process of Aalborg Industries A/S

Postponement of product configuration decisions will be constrained by a number of factors. The question of how much it is possible to postpone product configuration decisions will be constrained by internal business processes as well as customer and supplier business processes. For example a number of key characteristics must be decided upon before a quotation can be issued. In the following, a typical sales-delivery process is described to identify in which phases certain information must be determined and as an implication of this, which configuration decisions must be made. This description addresses the case where the customer is a shipyard since this is the typical case, although other customer types exist including sale directly to ship owners and non marine applications.

In the budget quotation phase, the sales people at AI interact with the early design departments and purchasing at the shipyard. The focus in this phase is, to a great extent, high level requirements, such as capacity, performance, product types, scope of delivery, price and purchasing cost of the boiler system. The shipyards will typically request this type of quotation when they are quoting ship owners for new ships, and thus not very detailed requirements exist. In other cases shipyards do not request budget quotations in their sales phase, and this phase is skipped for AI and the entry point is the detailed quotation phase.

In the detailed quotation phase, the shipyard will issue a more detailed requirement specification for the product and subsequently more detailed information needs to be provided for the shipyard. This may include technical specifications or data sheets, arrangement drawings for main components, list of parts and spare parts. The detailed quotation is the basis of a legally binding sales contract, and it is essential for the customer that the known requirements are met and equally important to AI is that the cost is known so that the desired contribution can be achieved. Thus the decisions regarding configuration that influence these factors must be made in the end of this phase.

In the engineering and procurement phase, AI interacts with the detailed design process at the customer. The focus in this phase is on technical details such as geometric options and detailed configuration choices about components that do not have a significant cost impact. The information provided to the shipyard in this phase includes drawings and datasheets for most components. This implies that specific components must be chosen in this phase. Also all product configuration decisions which have impact on procurement, manufacturing processes and subcontractor tasks must be taken during this phase. The customer will usually have an interest in postponing many detailed decisions to this phase, since the customer does not finish the detailed design of the ship before this phase and for this reason a number of requirements for the boiler system are unknown prior to the detail design phase.

During the manufacturing phase little interaction occurs with the shipyard and the main decisions taken in this process are related to the manufacturing processes. In the following phase, which is the commissioning phase, the boiler is commissioned usually by personnel from AI. This implies calibration, adjustment and startup of the system which is usually done in parallel with the commissioning of the ship. A number of product configuration decisions can be made in this phase, but these mainly include minor adjustments. The last phase is after sales service, which is the rest of the system's life cycle. In this phase the products may be reconfigured to adapt to future needs, but often the system does not change significantly over time.

2.1.2 Decision Postponement using Product Configuration System

AI has implemented a product configuration system to increase the degree of automation in the sales and order execution phases, improve responsiveness to customer inquiries and completeness of documentation. The system consists of a standard configuration tool, customized with a model of the product families to allow these to be configured, a customer relationship management system, a number of documentation generators and interfaces to the ERP system. The system will only allow valid product combinations of products and parameters to be configured, and thus a minimum of engineering effort is needed during the sales phase to design a solution. In the system the sales people can configure a product and generate most sales documentation automatically in the budget and detailed quotation phases. In the engineering phase, the BOM for the configured product can be transferred to the ERP system for procurement purposes and much documentation needed in this phase such as data sheets, lists of parts, arrangement drawings and 3D CAD models can be generated automatically on basis of the configuration.

The implementation of this system has implied that a number of product configuration decisions can be postponed to after the sales phase, including a number of decisions that require engineering. Some of this engineering will be necessary in the following phases, but only if a sales contract is agreed upon. For this reason it is desirable to postpone these activities at least to the time where it is certain that the product is sold, so that the activities are not performed unless it is necessary, which ultimately saves resources. Before a configuration system was implemented at AI, it was necessary in relation to each sale to create a BOM which contained all system components to calculate a price. This also required a number of decisions with regard to component choices which again required engineering effort. In the product configuration system setup this is unnecessary, since it is not necessary to explicitly choose components. This further saves resources since this effort is not needed unless the quotation turns into an order and even then the task is to some extent automated.

Fig.3: Direction of supply and requirements in the supply chain

Seen in a supply chain perspective, decision postponement is also relevant for AI. Most often AI’s customer is a shipyard, which delivers the ship to the final customer, the ship owner, Fig.3. When the shipyard requests a budget quotation, the ship owner may not have decided to purchase the ship from this specific shipyard, but is merely requesting a quotation. In this case it is the shipyard’s interest to minimize the effort to generate a quotation to the ship owner since the quotation may not lead to a sale and the effort in that case will be wasted. Hence the shipyard will be interested in using as few resources as possible to retrieve bids for a boiler. Postponing less significant decisions beyond the order point will allow this since the shipyard can focus on overall requirements and abstract from detailed requirements is not of significance for the price quotation. The configuration system allows this, since the sales person at AI will only need a few characteristics for the product in order to generate a configuration from which a price can be determined.

The fact that few decisions in principle are made about specific component choices in the early configuration phases implies that specific component configuration may be postponed. This means that components are initially specified functionally so that a number of different physical components can fulfill these specifications. Major components such as the boilers and burners are configured component specific, but utilities in the system such as valves and pumps are not explicitly configured component specific. This yields some flexibility in the procurement phase of the sales-delivery process, since specific brands or item numbers are not communicated to the customer for most components in the sales phase. Since the time of procurement can be years after the order has been

taken, there is a great potential in sourcing flexibility since component availability, prices and performance are likely to change over this period. Hence the postponement of specific component choices is essential in optimization and is enabled through the functional specification in the configuration system. This also relates to the supply chain considerations above since functional specification will allow the choice between different suppliers for components. This increases the possibilities to react to price changes over time as well as purchasing higher volumes from a single supplier possibly with greater discounts.

2.1.2 Experiences

AI has faced a number of challenges during the implementation of the product configuration system mainly due to AI being an ETO company. Compared to most other companies implementing product configuration, the product variety is much higher implying a more complex product family model in the configuration tool. It has proven to be unfeasible to implement all variety and a prioritizing has been necessary to decide which products to support in the system. Although a large part of the product portfolio can be configured, it is difficult to predict which product options the customers will demand and thus most configurations need to include components which cannot be configured as a standard option and manual handling is necessary.

One other major challenge is the length of the order life cycle. The time from when a sales contract is signed to the final delivery can span several years. In relation to the product configuration system this implies that standard product design changes may occur over this period. Also, collaboration with suppliers and sub contractors may change. These product changes imply that the products delivered are not identical on a component level even though the functionality is. Some of the challenges in relation to this can be met by postponing product configuration decisions so that the product to a large extent is configured functionally rather than component specific, since components can then be substituted in later deliveries without changing the configuration communicated to the customer.

Despite the challenges described above, the implementation of product configuration at AI is considered to be successful. It has reduced the manual work needed for generating a sales quotation significantly reducing the lead time for quotations, and improving the quotation quality as well. Furthermore the information delivered to engineering, procurement and manufacturing is higher quality using the product configuration system since it is also to some extent generated automatically on basis of the configuration. Finally the configuration system gives the possibility to postpone certain configuration decisions with the advantages described above.

2.2 Commercial Airplane Manufacturer

2.2.1 Case Introduction

In the aerospace industry, especially in the commercial airplane business, the sales-delivery process is very similar to the ship building industry which is described in the previous section. Most passenger and cargo airplane operators order airplanes two years or longer in advance. Recent examples show that UPS ordered Boeing 767s will take two to four years between the order announcement and delivery. Singapore Airlines' order of the A380 from Airbus Industries is taking approximately seven years from sale to delivery, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Airbus_A380. There are several significant events throughout the process, such as the sales announcement, definite agreement, implementation, and delivery. The sales-to-delivery process, Fig.4, presents a generic process in the commercial airplane industry.

2.2.2 The Sales-Delivery Process

Commercial airplanes sales may sometimes be linked to high level political events as part of trade balances and / or leverage tokens. However, one of the most important factors in the process is the timing and efficiencies between the time of the sale and delivery. Since detailed configuration and

customization varies among airlines, the production time hence varies among airlines customers. The “Sale” event in the Fig.4 indicates that there is an agreement between the airline and the manufacturer. The agreement normally does not contain detailed configuration of the aircraft. The “Definite Agreement” event in the Fig.4 indicates that both parties have reached an agreement to have all options defined. The airplane manufacturer will then start ETO processes that tailor to the customer’s needs. Customized component procurement will also gradually start. The “Implementation” event in the Fig.4 indicates that almost all of the customization work has been completed and the ETO results are getting released to the production shops, which normally are distributed globally. The implementation event for long lead time components will drive the final delivery date. The “Delivery” event in the Fig.4 indicates the product is delivered to the customer. There are occasions where the product may not be totally finished due to unique requirements in the definite agreement that cause the duration between implementation and delivery to not be long enough. Thus, the airplane can still be delivered and certified to fly followed by aftermarket customization.

Fig.4: the sales-delivery process of an airplane manufacturer

2.2.3 Decision Postponement

Many airlines desire to have their aircraft configured and produced with minimum time between Definite Agreement and Delivery. The airplane manufacturer’s ability to encompass decision postponement in the production system is an important marketing strength. *Zeng et al. (2006)* pointed out that about 60% of the configuration is defined at the time of sales order placement, and 25% of the configuration is defined four to eighteen months before delivery, while 15% of the configuration takes place one to four months before delivery. One of the key measures that benefit airlines is to shorten that eighteen months Definite Agreement to Delivery time to as close to four months as possible.

Magnitudes of decision postponement depend not only on the airplane manufacturer’s ability in ETO, but are also influenced by internal processes for those airlines that have unique interiors and processes to address them. The time between definite agreement and implementation is where the airlines work closely with the manufacturer and suppliers.

2.2.4 Experiences

Generally, the larger the aircraft, the more configuration options that are available. In that case, there are more possible ETO activities. A noticeable example is the difference between a Boeing 737 and a Boeing 777. The 737 is mostly used as a commuter airplane without too much customization. The 777, except the cargo freighter airplane, is mostly used as a long haul airplane where multiple categories of passenger cabins are available almost in every 777 airplane.

The postponement of product configuration can be regarded as so-called “Customer Introduction” in The Boeing Company. A Customer Introduction airplane means it is the first airplane of its model family for a particular airline. For example, the first 787 airplane for Japan Airlines (JAL) is a Customer Introduction airplane, and the second JAL 787 will not be a Customer Introduction airplane. The duration of the Customer Introduction airplane is normally regarded as between the time of definite agreement and delivery. The airplane manufacturer’s performance in producing Customer Introduction airplanes is very critical to the success of the business.

Traditionally, it takes up to two years to deliver a Customer Introduction airplane. Airplane manufacturers are striving to shorten that time to between one and half years and a half year or shorter for existing airplane models. The benefit is that airline customers can postpone their customization and ETO related decisions until it is very close to the final product delivery date. Furthermore, the airlines not only save on their cash flow by delaying their decisions, they can also have much better forecast on market trends as they make final configuration decisions closer to the delivery dates.

3 Discussion of Case Studies

The two case companies share a number of characteristics but are also in some ways different. Both companies are ETO and have a long time span from quotation through sales to delivery. Also in both cases the customization process happens gradually over the sales-delivery process and some decisions are postponed. However there are different drivers to postponing these decisions.

The advantage of postponing decisions which require engineering effort, due to uncertainty, is to some degree generic to ETO companies, which is supported by the theory of postponing value adding decisions, *Womack and Jones (1996)*. By doing this, the waste caused by performing engineering on quotations that do not turn into orders can be reduced to the extent the engineering can be postponed to after the order point. Furthermore the changes in engineering work which are necessary during the sales-delivery process can be reduced if decisions about the requirements for this work are postponed, since this will lead to higher certainty in the basis for the decisions, and thus the decisions are less likely to be changed at a later point.

The two supply chains which the two companies are part of are quite similar. The final customer in each supply chain is an operator of airliners or ships respectively, and the supplier of these will be a shipyard or the commercial airplane manufacturer. AI will then be the supplier of the shipyard. This implies that although the two supply chains are similar, the two case companies are in different situations since AI is one step earlier in the supply chain, as it does not directly supply the final customer. This has implications for the drivers for customization. The primary driver for postponing configuration decisions for the commercial airline manufacturers is the ability to allow customers to take into account recent market forecasts when deciding configuration details. Hence this decision postponement is primarily market driven as it gives the customer benefits and can thus be utilized to achieve competitive advantage compared to other commercial airliner manufacturers in the market.

Changes in market trends are however not likely to influence the configuration of marine boilers, since they do not have a direct linkage to the market application of the ship they way seating configuration of an airliner does. The characteristics of a marine boiler which are related to the market application of the ship will largely be derived from the ship type and capacity. The decisions about these characteristics are typically taken early in the design process and are thus not subject to change after a sales contract is agreed upon. Instead the postponement of configuration decisions is driven by the customer business processes, in particular the design process, and AI's internal business processes.

If certain configuration decisions are postponed, it is essential that they do not influence decisions that must be taken earlier in the business process. This will require the processes to be decoupled as well as the interfaces in the product must support decisions to be postponed. For commercial airplanes this could imply that changing seating configuration in an aircraft does not require structural changes in the aircraft. This can be achieved by implementing a modular product architecture, as this can support that the ability for modules to be replaced or modified without impact on the modules interfacing with the affected module. Process design is furthermore essential for decision postponement, and it must be determined in what sequence decisions must be taken and in which phases they must or can be allowed to be taken.

Specific IT systems are not required to utilize decision postponement, but some can be beneficial.

Product configurators can be used to control the configuration process, by explicitly requiring certain product specifications in certain phases of the sales-delivery process, thereby enabling postponement of product configuration decisions. Simulation tools may also be useful for investigating the impact of postponing decisions, as this may have influence on engineering, logistics and manufacturing.

4 Conclusions

Postponement of product configuration in ETO industries decisions can be utilized to achieve a higher degree of flexibility and reduce risk in relation to sales and order execution of products. Two cases were presented in which decision postponement is used and the benefits from this were described. Though the two supply chains are comparable, the drivers for postponing decisions are different. For the commercial airplane manufacturer, the primary driver is changing market trends in the customers' market which calls for late configuration to meet the current requirements. For the marine boiler manufacturer however, the drivers are primarily flexibility to adapt to the customer business processes and flexibility to optimize the configuration with respect to different criteria. This difference is credited partly to the two companies having different positions in the supply chain relative to the end customer as well as different product characteristics. Finally, product configuration software may be used as a means to enable decision postponement, as this can support the configuration process by specifying which decisions must be taken during various phases of the sales-delivery process.

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Development and Implementation of an Optimisation-Based Space Allocation Routine for the Generation of Feasible Concept Designs

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Abstract

This paper presents a proof of concept for an optimisation-based space allocation approach for the conceptual design of ships. By having a combined heuristic - deterministic search algorithm search for large numbers of feasible concept designs, the human designer can focus on resolving difficult compromise decisions without creating designs that cannot exist, e.g. by being insufficiently stable. Through the use of a packing approach, modified to allow local wrapping, system functionality is ensured and the interaction between envelope and object positions improved. A test case dealing with the design of an offshore patrol vessel shows the possibilities of the new approach.

1 Introduction

Conceptual naval ship design tries to balance available budget with required capability. To assess the capability of a design, designers rely on an extensive collection of prediction tools. Unfortunately, proper evaluation of most military performances, e.g. vulnerability, signatures and operability in a seaway, requires a highly detailed geometrical model of the ship. Such an amount of detail makes large design changes prohibitively expensive and as a result, the opportunity for the designer to balance capability with budget diminishes.

Following the overall approach discussing the application of prediction tools presented in *Van Oers and Stapersma (2006)*, this paper presents a space-allocation routine capable of finding collections of feasible ship designs, which all meet a set of non-negotiable user-defined criteria. The routine maintains flexibility at higher levels of detail, allowing the future use of advanced prediction tools normally employed at the later design stages. The application of the routine is used to find feasible designs (side view arrangement) of an offshore patrol vessel.

2 Approach

2.1 Detail vs. flexibility

Ship design revolves around the application of prediction tools. Such tools are used to evaluate designs prior to their physical creation, reducing the need for expensive prototypes and model testing. As result of a massive research effort, the range of designs for which accurate predictions can be made has increased dramatically in recent years. Unfortunately, the state-of-the-art tools capable of these improved predictions simultaneously came to rely on input with higher levels of detail to obtain those more valid and accurate predictions. As a result, many state-of-the-art prediction tools are currently limited to research purposes and the fine-tuning of existing designs.

Given their broad range of validity, major benefits could be realised by employing state-of-the-art prediction tools from the earliest moment on, i.e. during conceptual design, *Van Oers and Stapersma (2006)*. This in turn demands that a design with the required amount of detail is available. Furthermore, the flexibility at the higher levels of detail should be improved, otherwise design changes cannot be implemented.

Improving flexibility, i.e. reducing the effort to implement changes, is not straightforward for two main reasons. First, the level of detail is directly proportional to the number of decisions taken to achieve the level of detail, i.e. someone has decided at some point that a certain design detail is actually there. Second, ship design is riddled with compromise and trade-offs; the number of human compromise decisions is

therefore equal to the level of detail. The most straightforward approach to increasing flexibility: reduce the number of decisions, will not offer improvement.

Two improvements are proposed to resolve the stale-mate. The first improvement uses the concept of feasible or balanced designs, *Andrews (1998)* and *Van Der Nat(1999)*. If human compromise decisions can be restricted to feasible designs, a significant reduction of user effort can be achieved, as most design effort is spend on achieving balanced ship designs. The second improvement deals with sequentiality. If all calculations are made prior to decision-making, the user can be provided with instant feedback of the consequences of compromise decisions on the overall design.

The first of these two improvements is the main focal point of the space allocation routine presented in this paper. Before presenting the remainder of the paper, a definition of an infeasible design is in order. In this paper, infeasible designs are designs that do not meet a set of user-defined, non-negotiable requirements. In addition, these requirements can be formulated mathematically in a meaningful way, so that mathematical search algorithms can distinguish between feasible and infeasible designs. More specifically, the space allocation routine should be capable of finding designs meeting the following set of requirements.

- Fully functional systems
 - Safeguard mechanical connections between objects
 - Safeguard the operationally required free space of objects, e.g. a firing arc of a gun
- Center of gravity that meets hydrostatic and stability constraints
- Reasonable amount of void space inside the envelope
- No overlap between objects and between objects and operationally required free spaces
- Safeguard user-defined positioning constraints

2.2 Space supply

Following *Van Der Nat (1999)*, the space and weight balance of a design has both a supply and demand side. The envelope, consisting of hull and superstructure, provides both available space, i.e. available length, area and volume, and buoyancy, i.e. available weight. Decks provide additional available length and area. To be feasible, designs need both a positive space and weight balance, i.e. have equal or more supply than demand. Depending on the type of vessel, a ship's design may either be weight or space driven. Fig.1 shows the empty envelope of a ship, with decks positioned inside to increase the available length and area. No restrictive upper limit is placed on the number of decks; the underlying reasoning will be discussed in Section 2.4. In this paper, the envelope dimensions are kept fixed, i.e. only local alterations to the envelope are made.

Fig.1: Envelope with decks

For both weight driven and space driven ships, the ratio of occupied space to available space rarely equals one. An example is the “enlarged ship concept”, presented by *Keuning and Pinkster (1997)*, which

uses additional space onboard to improve sea keeping (more specifically reduce vertical accelerations). Another example is found when looking at a more detailed level. For example, several objects inside an engine room, i.e. the gearbox, uptakes and downtakes and the prime movers fail to occupy all the available space inside an engine room. Nevertheless, their position has a major impact on the resistance of the ship, as they determine the maximum submerged width of most surface combatants.

The variable ratio between available space and occupied space has important consequences for the parametrization of object positions, which is discussed in Section 2.5.

2.3 Space demand

Objects positioned on the decks and the envelope consume available space and weight. For the space allocation routine presented in this paper, objects are represented by rectangular shapes. This does not rule out a different representation for purposes other than space allocation, e.g. radar signature prediction. The designer is responsible for defining objects with a level of detail matching the purpose of the space allocation. In addition to spatial properties, objects also have a weight and center of gravity. To ensure the correct functioning of objects, two additional object characteristics are proposed.

The first characteristic concerns connectivity among objects. To be able to provide thrust, a propulsion system may require several mechanical connections to function correctly. Therefore, relations are used to position chains of objects, safeguarding mechanical connections. As these relations derive from the layout of the propulsion system and the selection of components, they themselves do not resemble compromise decisions. In this paper, such compromise decisions are defined as human decisions that give one design characteristic priority over others. As priorities change frequently during conceptual design, the validity of compromise decisions is rather limited. In contrast, the relations defining mechanical connections are valid as long as both system layout and components stay the same. Fig.2 shows a diesel engine together with a mechanical connection -the propeller shaft- to the propeller.

Fig.2: Diesel engine with a mechanical connection to the propeller

Fig.3: Bridge with operationally required free space

The second characteristic concerns operationally required free space; free space defined around an object to safeguard maintainability and overall functioning. Examples include the maintenance envelope around a diesel engine and the firing arc of a gun. Fig.3 shows a bridge with its operationally required free space. The operationally required free space plays an important role in improving the interaction between object positions and envelope shape, as is discussed in Section 2.4.

2.4 Interaction between object positions and envelope shape

Different ways exist to balance space supply with space demand; the two basic approaches are well known from actual ship building practice. The first approach, packing, assumes the exterior demands to be more important than the interior demands. The second approach, wrapping, assumes the interior demands to be more important than the exterior demands. Fig.4 and Fig.5 show both approaches.

Unfortunately, solely relying on either of the two approaches has severe consequences. A pure packing approach might have an unsuitable envelope shape preventing objects from maintaining their functionality. For example, an envelope may not be wide enough to accommodate a flight deck for helicopter operations. A pure wrapping approach might yield designs which function properly from an object point

Fig.4: Packing approach

Fig.5: Wrapping approach

of view but whose performances following from all object positions taken together may not prove preferable. An example would be to have an extremely wide mono hull that accommodates several helicopter landings spots in beam-wise direction. Any reasonable naval speed requirement, i.e. anything over 5 knots, will not likely be met by the design.

In reality, designers mix the packing and wrapping approach throughout a ship's design, an approach stylised in Fig.6. When investigating this mixed interaction in more detail, one finds that some objects are always allowed to change the envelope. Other objects are solely allowed to change the envelope under very specific conditions, mainly when the envelope provides insufficient free space to position them.

Fig.6: Mixed wrapping and packing approach

Fig.7: Local shape modifications to the envelope

To deal with this mixed approach we propose a modification to the packing approach. While packing all objects, we will allow some objects to locally wrap the envelope to accommodate the object and safeguard object functionality. Two different types of wrapping are made. First, objects with a fixed shape and size will be wrapped locally to provide the minimum required available space, but only if insufficient space is available inside the envelope. An example of such an object is the flight deck which has fixed minimum dimensions to ensure safe operation. Fig.7 shown a possible wrapping; the envelope is extended underneath the flight deck to provide space and ensure structural support. Second, objects with operationally required free space, discussed in Section 2.3, use the free space used to wrap the envelope locally. More specifically, the operationally required free space will be subtracted from the envelope. Again, the flight deck forms a good example; the free space required for flight operations is safeguarded by altering the shape of the envelope, illustrated in Fig.7. Such a modification ensures that, regardless of its position, the flight deck is always adjacent to open air. Proper definition of the local wrapping functions is not straightforward. For example, the user can wrap the envelope around objects by increasing main dimensions or by applying a local wrapping function, e.g. the weapon sponsons on aircraft carriers. In this paper, all wrapping functions are rectangular.

Packing objects globally while locally wrapping the envelope to accommodate specific objects ensures that systems remain functional and that the envelope does not restrict feasible designs. Still, completely unrealistic designs are avoided by predefining the envelope shape for the packing approach. This approach also explains the lack of an upper limit on the number of decks shown in Section 2.3; the envelope is wrapped locally to provide the operationally required free spaces, while any configuration with an extremely high center of gravity will not meet user-imposed constraints on stability.

2.5 Parametrization of object positions

One major decision remains, the parametrization of object positions. Literature shows that two different parametrizations are in use: combinatorial and scalar coordinate parametrizations.

Fig.8: Combinatorial positioning

Fig.9: Positioning with scalar coordinates

From the field of facility layout problems, e.g. *Islir (2006)*, and from related applications in ship design, e.g. *Lee et al. (2003)*, *Nick et al. (2006)*, and *Daniels and Parsons (2006)*, comes the combinatorial parametrization. Positions are defined by sequence, i.e. object two is placed after object one and prior to object three. A positioning routine is used to map the sequence of objects into positions, while preventing any overlap during positioning. The variation of object positions results from changing the positioning sequence. The dimensions of the smallest object fixes the positioning step size. Fig.8 shows an example of space allocation using combinatorial parametrization.

A different parametrization is presented in *Grignon (1998)*, *Grignon and Fadel (2004)* and *Blouin et al. (2006)*. Instead of a combinatorial parametrization, object positions are defined using scalar coordinates. To prevent any unwanted overlap, the objects positions are only used as an initial position; an overlap removal routine moves objects to their final position. Positioning and overlap removal takes place sequentially. Depending on the geometry definition, overlap removal can be computationally expensive, which makes selecting a proper geometry definition essential for any practical application. Section 3.1 discusses the geometry definition used in this paper. Variable filling ratios are easily dealt with, but extremely high filling ratios are computationally expensive to achieve, as the number of overlap removals increases exponentially. Changes in the configuration result from variations in object coordinates, while keeping a fixed positioning sequence. *Grignon and Fadel (2004)* and *Blouin et al. (2006)* show examples dealing with the configuration design of satellites, car engines and trucks. Fig.9 shows an example of space allocation using scalar coordinate parametrization with overlap removal.

Section 2.2 argued that several reasons prevent even space-driven designs from being fully occupied with objects, i.e. ships are never completely full. In addition, arguments were put forward to apply a combined packing & wrapping approach to achieve space-balanced designs with functional systems. A combinatorial parametrization requires a fixed envelope shape to map the object sequence to positions, making local wrapping difficult. Furthermore, the limited control provided by combinatorial parametrization over the positioning step size may provide insufficient accuracy when positioning large or heavy objects.

For the reasons stated above, a scalar coordinate parametrization is selected in our space allocation routine. More specifically, objects are placed in a two-dimensional side view using x for the horizontal coordinates and z for the vertical coordinates. The two main drawbacks: the computational effort of overlap removal and problems attaining higher filling ratios, will be resolved to the extent possible.

3 Space allocation

3.1 Geometry definition & local overlap removal

Different solutions exist to detect and remove overlap among objects. Prior to discussing them, a distinction should be made between overlap detection and overlap removal. Overlap detection aims to solely

detect any overlap, whereas overlap removal tries to remove it. Even though overlap removal requires the use of overlap detection, the information of the overlap detection should be such that the overall computational effort of overlap removal is minimised. Therefore, it might be beneficial to use a more computationally expensive overlap detection, if this yields a reduction in overall computational effort of overlap removal. With the scalar coordinate parametrization, overlap removal takes place sequentially; after a new object is placed at its initial position, overlap between the new object and all prior objects is detected and removed.

Depending on the geometry definition and the overlap removal procedure, overlap detections might need several runs, further increasing the computational effort. Selecting a suitable geometry definition therefore has a major impact on the computational requirements of overlap removal. *Blouin et al. (2006)* provides an overview of the suitability of various geometry definitions. An example of the consequences of geometry definition is presented by *Grignon and Fadel (2004)*. It uses a triangular mesh surface definition to define free-form objects. When overlap occurs, the amount of overlap, e.g. defined by area or volume, is taken as penalty function for a gradient-based search algorithm. By minimising the amount of overlap, overlap is removed, which requires multiple -computationally expensive- overlap detections.

A solid geometry offers a more efficient approach. Such a definition stores not only information on the boundaries of objects as does a surface definition, but also contains information on whether points lie in or outside objects. This opens up the possibility to use routines to detect available space instead of overlap, making overlap removal far more efficient compared to penalty-based overlap removal.

For the routine presented in this paper, a solid based geometry definition is selected. More specifically, the geometry is defined in a two-dimensional cartesian matrix with variable but finite resolution. The matrix consists of cells between decks that are either empty or full. Full cells are indicated with non-zeros, while empty cells contain zeros, shown in Fig.10.

Fig.10: Positioning space with filled and empty cells

Overlap is removed with a deterministic approach, by searching a vector for spots with the required number of zeros. Should an object cover multiple cells in a vertical direction, a vertical summation over rows covering the height of the object yields the required vector with the cells. A similar approach can be used to position multiple objects with fixed relative positions, e.g. the propulsion system. By constructing a vector with available cells for each object separately and adding up the resulting vectors, the search routine can easily search for positions that offer available space for all objects taking the relative object positions into account. The positioning matrix is updated when a suitable object position is found. Fig.11 illustrates this process.

Even though searching a part of the positioning space for available space is more computationally expensive than simple overlap detection, it requires only a single search to detect any available space. With the matrix-based geometry definition, fast existing search routines can be employed, making the resulting overlap removal routine quite efficient. A more detailed estimate of the computational efficiency of the space allocation routine will be the subject of a future paper.

Fig.11: Procedure to remove local overlap

3.2 Global positioning strategy

Section 3.1 discussed the approach to prevent local overlap while positioning objects. Still a decision has to be taken what objects are allowed to overlap. Table I presents the allowed and prohibited overlaps used for the routine presented in this paper. The numbers in Table I refer to the various overlaps shown in Fig.12.

Table I: Different types of allowed and prohibited overlap (numbers refer to Fig.12)

Overlap between →	Other objects	Operationally required free spaces
Object	Not allowed (1)	Not allowed (3)
Operationally required free space	Not allowed (2)	Allowed (4)

In order to deal with these variations in allowed overlap, the positioning routine uses two positioning matrices. The first matrix keeps track of space occupied by objects and is used to construct the vectors required to position objects with operationally required free space. The second matrix keeps track of space occupied by either objects or operationally required free spaces and is used when constructing the vectors for positioning objects without operationally required free space. A local correction to the second matrix is made to remove any artificial overlap following from overlap of objects with their own operationally required free space.

Fig.12: Different types of allowed and prohibited overlap (numbers refer to Table (??))

Fig.13 shows the pseudo code used by the space allocation routine. The routine is implemented in Matlab 2006b. It uses the following strategy to place all objects in the positioning space. Objects are positioned

sequentially, between each consecutive object, overlap is detected and removed. When chains of objects are positioned, the vectors containing the available cells are merged to provide those positions that allow the entire chain to be positioned. Positioning constraints modify the vector containing the available cells. Should an object fail to find space available at its initial position, the position is shifted horizontally to find cells with available space at a minimal horizontal distance to the initial horizontal position. When this proves impossible, the object moves up vertically to the next row of cells. This approach is repeated until the object is positioned or until any positioning constraints are violated. In case an object fails to find cells that allow positioning, it will be placed at its initial position, regardless of any overlap. Different reasons were found that caused such overlap, e.g. positioning objects with operationally required free space occupies large portions of the positioning space, which may prevent objects positioned later on from finding any available space. This means that depending on the positions of prior objects, designs can be generated that still have some total overlap, despite the local overlap removal. After positioning an object (with or without overlap) the positioning matrices are updated with the new objects and the next object starts its positioning process.

```

for i = 1: number of objects
  retrieve initial x position and z position of object(i)
  trigger = not positioned
  while trigger = not positioned
    construct vector from relevant parts of positioning matrices
    modify vector to accommodate x constraints
    modify vector to accommodate operationally required free space
    search vector for cells that can hold object(i)
    if cells are available
      trigger = positioned
      x position = cell with least horizontal distance to initial position
    else
      z position = z position + 1
      if z constraint = violated
        trigger = positioned
        x position = initial x position
        z position = initial z position
      end
    end
  end
end
end
update positioning matrices with object(i) at (x position , z position)
end

```

Fig.13: Pseudo-code of positioning routine

The configuration is complete after all objects are placed. With the object positions and the positioning matrices known, objective functions can be calculated. All that remains is an efficient variation of initial positions to search for feasible designs, the topic for Section 4.

4 Genetic algorithm

4.1 The need for search algorithms

The combination of sequential positioning with operationally required free spaces might lead to configurations which, despite the local overlap removal, still have overlap. In addition, several other characteristics, such as onboard logistics, workability in a seaway or simply the center of gravity depend on the position of all objects. Finding designs which meet the feasibility requirements, discussed in Section 2.1, therefore requires a variation of the initial positions of all objects concurrently. This is achieved by integrating the space allocation routine in a search algorithm, shown in Fig.14.

This brings us to the application of mathematical search algorithms. Such algorithms, commonly known as optimisation algorithms allow users to efficiently search the objective space for the “best” designs. An important distinction must be made between the verb “to optimise” and the mathematical capability,

Fig.14: Integration of space allocation routine (grey box) with a genetic algorithm (white boxes)

i.e. searching for specific solutions. What constitutes “best” from a ship design point of view depends entirely on the objective functions used by the search algorithm. Section 4.3 discusses the objective functions used by the routine presented in this paper.

Several of the feasibility objectives, e.g. onboard logistics, may have multiple non-trivial solutions. Therefore, the search algorithm must be able to deal with multiple local optima. Furthermore, to support compromise decisions, the search algorithm must not find a single compromise design but instead find ranges of good designs. Section 4.2 discusses the heuristic search algorithm while the decision making procedure will be presented in Section 6.

4.2 NSGA-II

The NSGA-II genetic algorithm, presented by *Deb et al. (2002)*, is a well-established genetic algorithm that offers multi-objective search capability. To reduce the effort involved in the proof of concept, an existing NSGA-II Matlab routine was adapted for use in combination with the space allocation routine presented in Section 3. As the focus of this paper lies on the development of the space allocation routine only a summarised overview of the NSGA-II implementation will be provided.

The implementation uses a real-coded chromosome with the object coordinates. For positioning purposes the coordinates are rounded to match the resolution of the positioning space. Selection is carried out by tournament selection. Simulated binary crossover is used to produce the child offspring from the parent population, while preserving the best designs through elitism. No constraint handling was implemented, therefore all objectives functions were treated as such.

4.3 Objective functions

Four objective functions are minimised with the NSGA-II algorithm. These are:

- Total overlap. As was discussed in Section 3.2, some objects may fail to find any available space for positioning. By placing these objects on their initial positions, overlap occurs. By minimising the total overlap of a design, i.e. the number of cells that contain overlap among objects themselves and among objects and operationally required free spaces, designs are found that do not have any total overlap.
- Center of gravity. The difference between the required center of gravity and the actual center of gravity is minimised to achieve an internal arrangement which matches the hydrostatic properties of the envelope. Only the center of gravity of objects is currently taken into account; the center of gravity of the envelope is not included.

- Total void space. After all objects are positioned, the upper contour of the resulting envelope is wrapped, shown in Fig.15. The total number of free cells inside the envelope added together forms total amount of void space, which is minimised to search for designs with high filling ratios.

Fig.15: Generation of envelope contour

- Onboard logistics. A distance-based transport cost model for horizontal and vertical movement is used to minimise the total transport costs. Eq.(1) to Eq.(6) show the model. Parameters c_{hij} and c_{vij} contain the efforts to transport something between object i and object j , based on the efforts t_{hij} and t_{vij} and the cartesian distances d_{hij} and d_{vij} .

$$\text{Adjacency horizontal} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=2}^n c_{hij} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{With } c_{hij} = t_{hij} \cdot d_{hij} \quad (2)$$

$$d_{hij} = \|(x_i - x_j)\| \quad (3)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n-1$ and $j = 2 \dots n$

$$\text{Adjacency vertical} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=2}^n c_{vij} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{With } c_{vij} = t_{vij} \cdot d_{vij} \quad (5)$$

$$d_{vij} = \|(z_i - z_j)\| \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n-1$ and $j = 2 \dots n$

5 Results

5.1 Configuration design of an offshore patrol vessel

A test case was run to configure the side view arrangement of an offshore patrol vessel, *Van der Knaap* (2006). Rectangular shapes of fixed dimensions were used to represent objects, with the additional assumption that objects extend over entire width of the vessel. The objects are placed inside a two dimensional positioning space (xz -plane) of fixed size, i.e. no variation of overall dimensions was implemented. No information on envelope width was included. The positioning matrix has a resolution of 1 m horizontally and 3 m vertically (deck height).

Thirty objects are positioned, resulting in 60 independent variables. Of these objects, eight were fully constrained, located mainly near the stern and bottom of the vessel. Among the constrained objects were a slipway for a rigid inflatable boat and the propulsion system. Several objects had partly constrained positions, e.g. the up and down takes have a horizontal position close to that of the engine rooms. Several objects have operationally required free space to ensure their functionality, among these are the flight deck, the gun, the up and down takes and the bridge. The relative positions of two pairs of objects were fixed: the flight deck with the hangar and the computing room with the radar mast.

Fig.16 shows the most important tradeoff: total void space versus total overlap. Only designs with a total overlap equal to zero are of interest, those indicated with a circle in Fig.16. As the amount of total

overlap was included as an objective the genetic algorithm maintained diversity along the entire Pareto front, with different ratios between total overlap and total void space as a result. Treating total overlap and the center of gravity as mathematical constraints instead of objectives should increase the yield in future applications. Designs that do not meet the feasibility constraints, such as the center of gravity, are removed during post processing.

Fig.16: Scatter plot with all designs: total overlap vs. total void space

Total onboard transport costs (Eq.(1) to Eq.(6)) were also minimised. Figs.17 to 19 show the scatter plots with feasible designs, visualising the relation between total void space, horizontal and vertical transport costs.

Fig.17: Scatter plot with feasible designs: horizontal transport cost vs. vertical transport cost

Fig.18: Scatter plot with feasible designs: horizontal transport cost vs. total void space

Fig.19: Scatter plot with feasible designs: vertical transport cost vs. total void space

Figs.20 to 23 show several concept designs (the bow points to the right). The colours indicate the four main warship functions: fight (red), move (yellow), float (blue) and hotel function (green). Grey areas show operationally required free space. White areas are areas not covered by either objects or operationally required free space. The black dot shows the position of the center of gravity of the objects; void space inside the envelope is not shown.

5.2 Performance

The space allocation routine and the NSGA-II algorithm are implemented in Matlab. The evaluation of a single design outside NSGA-II takes, on average, 0.01 s. This relatively fast implementation allows the evaluation of $6.25 \cdot 10^4$ designs in around 10 minutes, well suited for the daily use in a commercial environment. Test runs that evolve a population of 150 designs over 150 generations usually yield multiple

Fig.20: A feasible concept design

Fig.21: A feasible concept design

Fig.22: A feasible concept design

Fig.23: A feasible concept design

feasible designs, although the amount of total void space will be rather high. To decrease this, longer runs of 500 designs over 500 generations are necessary. Several improvements are presented in Section 7.2 that aim to further increase the yield of the application.

6 Post-processing

As was argued in Section 2.1, finding feasible designs only solves the first part of the problem. The second part deals with narrowing down the set of feasible designs, which can consist of up to $2.5 \cdot 10^4$ designs, to a set of designs promising enough to be evaluated in more detail with extensive human support. Reducing the number of compromise decisions is rather difficult, as was argued in Section 2.1.

During the decision-making, care should be taken to account not only for global performances but also to investigate local compromises. Otherwise, a compromise decision based on a global performance, e.g. the total internal transport cost, will not likely reflect a preferred local compromise. Furthermore, real-life designs will never lie on a Pareto front, as not all relevant performances are accounted for in the optimisation.

Together, these issues warrant a mixed human-computer approach. More informed compromise decisions will be achieved by including the positioning parameters themselves in the decision-making process while still accounting for the global and local performances. To support this process, extensive visualisation is essential, which can be provided by the approach presented in *Van Oers and Van Hees (2006)* and *Van Oers et al. (2007)*. The detailed argumentation and implementation of the decision support approach will be the subject for a future publication.

7 Conclusions & future research

7.1 Conclusions

A combined heuristic-deterministic space allocation routine is presented capable of finding feasible concept designs. This feasible set of designs is intended to be reduced to a smaller set by applying consecutive human compromise decisions while taking both the positions and calculated properties into account. This approach was necessitated by the following observations:

- Many state-of-the-art prediction tools require highly detailed geometrical input.
- The number of design decisions is directly proportional to the level of detail.
- The number of human compromise decisions is also equal to the level of detail.

These problems were resolved by:

- Developing a purposed-built space allocation algorithm and allow it search for feasible designs.
- Allowing humans to take all compromise decisions, but prevent such decisions from creating infeasible designs. To provide sufficient diversity, large numbers of feasible designs are generated.

The space allocation routine presented in this paper has the following characteristics.

- Employs a packing approach with overlap removal to position objects onboard.
- Allows objects to locally wrap the envelope, which greatly improves the interaction between envelope and object positions.
- Allows variable filling ratios and can therefore deal with both weight and space-driven designs at variable levels of detail.
- Safeguards system functionality by ensuring that all required connections among objects and of objects with the outside world remain intact during positioning.

The configuration design of the offshore patrol vessel shows that the routine is capable of finding multiple feasible designs. The improved interaction between object positions and envelope shape is shown by the variety of designs found. Figs.20 to 23 show some examples.

7.2 Future research

The routine presented in this paper served as a prove of concept. Several improvements are planned, the most important ones are listed below:

- Upgrade the space allocation routine to handle three-dimensional space allocation.
- Implement constraint handling in the genetic algorithm.
- Investigate the mathematical performance of the space allocation routine. This includes establishing the effect of varying the fixed positioning sequence and investigating the dependencies between the initial population and the resulting quality of the feasible designs.
- Integrate the space allocation routine with shape optimisation of the envelope.

- Improve support for compromise decisions by including extensive visualisation in the decision process.
- Include connection objects, which lack in the current application. According to *Brown (1987)* gangways and staircases can take up to 15% of the internal available surface area. Fortunately, the sequential positioning presented in Section 3 enables progressive growth of connection objects such as gangways. The aim is to maximise re-use of occupied space, instead of providing a separate physical connection between each object pair. Obviously, transport directions should be taken into account to prevent disruptions. Fig.24 shows the progressive development of gangways between four compartments.

Fig.24: Progressive generation of gangways between four accommodation spaces

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A Data Mining Analysis Applied to a Straightening Process Database

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of a data mining analysis aiming to improve the cost knowledge of the labour intensive straightening process. The data mining approach yields a formula linking the straightening cost to the sections scantlings (plate thickness, dimension and inter-distance of longitudinal stiffeners, dimension and inter-distance of transversal frames) and to other section characteristics.

1 Introduction

The complexity of modern manufacturing processes in a highly competitive environment forces the manufacturers to invest massively in automation and monitoring systems. The large data flows from these new installations are sources of valuable and hidden knowledge that is so far hardly used. Data mining methods through integrated data analysis tools such as the software product PEPITo® give a solution to this situation, allowing easy retrieval of knowledge starting from a data base. This is also a unique opportunity to learn more quickly about the process and to detect hidden and complex relationships between parameters involved. Within this framework we have decided to apply this data analysis method to the straightening process in shipbuilding.

In shipbuilding, the assembly of elements by welding involves necessarily temperature gradients within the material. This phenomenon causes deformations which have to be reduced to obtain an acceptable surface flatness. The straightening is the process that consists to eliminate these distortions for esthetical or functional reasons. The straightening process is labour intensive. Estimating the straightening impact on the production workload is interesting in the context of production simulation, cost assessment of ship hull, structure optimization, design for production, etc.

To reach these objectives, the idea was to elaborate, through a data mining approach, a formula linking the straightening cost to the sections scantlings (plate thickness, dimension and inter-distance of longitudinal stiffeners, dimension and inter-distance of transversal frames) and to other section characteristics. This paper describes each stage of the methodology: the data description, the analysis of data quality, the data exploration and finally the choice of discriminatory attributes and the generation of the data-driven models. Some interesting techniques coming from PEPITo® software were used in order to perform this analysis like: a linear correlation analysis by dendrograms, conditioned histograms, conditioned dots clouds, decision trees tool (based on minimisation entropy) and a Neuronal Network Analysis.

2 Data Mining

2.1 General Definition

Data Mining (DM) is aims to extract synthesized and previously unknown information from large databases. By definition, DM extracts valid, previously unknown, comprehensible, and useful information from large databases for further processing. The data analysis process tries to discover useful patterns in data that are not obvious to the user and to create useful information and knowledge from data to help in decision-making.

2.2 PEPITo[®] – A Unique Solution for Manufacturing and Process Intelligence

Data mining is increasingly used in enterprises decision-making processes. Data mining uses a broad range of tools from statistics, automatic learning, pattern recognition, database technologies, visualization and artificial intelligence. This mix of technologies has been combined in the PEPITo software, <http://www.pepito.be>, used in the work presented here. PEPITo combines visualization, advanced statistics and predictive analytics tools. Furthermore PEPITo has a scalable, high-performance object database enabling it to handle problems with very large data sets (millions of objects with thousands of parameters each). The simple and intuitive user interface hides the complexity of data mining from average users, enabling them to quickly perform data mining tasks on simple problems. In addition, PEPITo has a powerful scripting language (KDLisp). KDLisp is fully programmable with direct access to all the data mining functions, in essence making PEPITo a flexible data mining toolbox. This is significant since most data mining applications involve an iterative process of exploring data models with different data mining techniques. The toolbox concept enables users to easily prototype different data models and to combine, modify and adapt the tools according to characteristics of the problem. It also allows users to integrate the solution seamlessly with other software.

3 The data mining process

We followed the freely available CRISP-DM data mining methodology, <http://www.crisp-dm.org>, Fig.1. This methodology was developed in the 1990s by a consortium of data mining experts, consultants and end users. The proposed reference model covers all aspects of a data mining study, from problem definition, to data analysis and final live deployment. We briefly summarize the different stages of the process below.

Fig.1: CRISP-DM methodology

1. Business Understanding - This initial phase focuses on understanding the project objectives and requirements from a business perspective, then converting this knowledge into a data mining problem definition and a preliminary plan designed to achieve the objectives.
2. Data understanding - The data understanding phase starts with an initial data collection and proceeds with activities in order to get familiar with the data, to identify quality problems, to discover first insights into the data or to detect interesting subsets to form hypotheses for hidden information.
3. Data preparation - The data preparation phase covers all activities to construct the final dataset (data that will be fed into the modelling tool(s)) from the initial raw data. Data preparation tasks are likely to be performed multiple times and not in any prescribed order. Tasks include tables, objects and attributes selection as well as transformation and cleaning of

data for modelling tools.

4. Modelling - In this phase, various modelling techniques are applied and their parameters are calibrated to optimal values. Typically, there are several techniques for the same data mining problem type. Some techniques have specific requirements on the form of data. Therefore, stepping back to data preparation phase is often necessary.
5. Evaluation - At this stage in the project, you have built a model (or models) that appears to have high quality from a data analysis perspective. Before proceeding to final deployment of the model, it is important to thoroughly evaluate the model and review the steps executed to construct the model to be certain it properly achieves the business objectives.
6. Deployment - Depending on requirements, the deployment phase can be as simple as generating a report, or as complex as implementing a repeatable data mining process across the whole enterprise.

4 Straightening process database study

Some interesting tools for data analysis are used in this study in order to find a relevant relation between the straightening cost and the sections scantlings. These tools and the different steps of the study are presented in this section.

4.1 Methodology

First of all, a database was established in order to specify the characteristics of each section and the straightening time associated.

The data mining analysis within the CRISP-DM methodology is divided in four main parts:

- Data description stage: This step consists in a presentation of the attributes (fields of the data base), with their distribution and other statistical parameters (minimum, maximum, mean and variance).
- Data quality stage: This step lists the problematic recordings (strange distribution, missed values, data in conflict with their physical meaning) in order to take care of them in the next stages.
- Data exploration stage: This step consists in pointing out interesting characteristics of the database with the help of visualization tools and descriptive statistical methods. In order to select the determinant attributes in the straightening estimation, different tools of linear correlation analysis (dendrogram), conditioned histograms, conditioned dots clouds, etc were used.
- Data modelling stage: This step consists in building the relation between the straightening cost and the sections characteristics by the use of learning methods like decision tree analysis, artificial neuronal network analysis, etc.

4.2 Data base architecture

Several sources have been used to constitute the database, Table I:

- a workload table of giving the estimated and the real value of the work duration (in hours) ; and giving the responsible of the straightening work (the shipyard workers or sub-contractors).
- ships plans to extract the scantling and dimensions of the main frames.
- tables describing all characteristics of sections constituents

This data base consists of approximately 1000 different entities coming from almost 15 passenger ships.

Table I: Description of the database relating to the straightening

Field	Example	Unit	Description
Ship	32	-	Ship identification
Section	v102	-	
R_time_on_surf	100	h/m ²	Time of strengthening work spent by m ²
Section_surf	396,2	m ²	Surface of the section calculated by the multiplication of width and length, it is thus the ground obstruction surface
Section_weight	210,4	T	Total weight of the section (decks constituents + girders + transversal frames + bulkheads + plating..)
Deck_weight	64.2	T	Weight of the deck (plates + stiffeners + girders)
Plate_weight	59.89	T	Weight of deck plates
Delta_stiff	700	mm	Distance between longitudinal stiffeners
Delta_frame	2760	mm	Distance between transversal stiffeners
Thickness	25	mm	Relevant thickness of the deck plates
H_stiff	280	mm	High of longitudinal stiffeners
T_stiff	11	mm	Thickness of longitudinal stiffeners
H_web_frame	1600	mm	High of transversal stiffeners webs
T_web_frame	15	mm	Thickness of transversal stiffeners webs
H_flange_frame	120	mm	Width of transversal stiffeners flanges
T_flange_frame	15	mm	Thickness of transversal stiffeners flanges
Delta_deck	3600	mm	Distance between two deck
Double_bottom	Y	-	Y if double bottom else N
Section_length	17	m	Length of ground obstruction surface
Section_width	31	m	Width of ground obstruction surface
Deck_nbr	4	-	Number of the deck
Slice	4	-	Slice of the ship where the section is (position in the ship axis)
Grade	A	-	Steel grade
Special	N	-	Id special (formed parts of the ships = not precise data about deck surface) thus Y else N
Family	1	-	Clusters of section defined by ship areas
Deck_surf	525	m ²	Surface of the horizontal plates constituting the deck
S_weight_on_surf	0,628	T/m ²	Section weight on deck surface
S_weight_on_length	5,725	T/m	Section weight on section length
D_weight_on_surf	0,192	T/m ²	Deck weight on deck surface
D_weight_on_length	0,1793	T/m ²	Deck weight on section length

4.3 Data description

This step consisted in a presentation of the attributes (fields of the data base), with their distribution and other statistical parameters (minimum, maximum, mean and variance). One of difficulties which arose during the data base analysis is that the most structural attributes show a discrete distribution with one or few dominant modes, see Fig.2 (2) and (3). For instance, the distance between stiffeners has very often the same value. Those attributes are almost “constant” parameters and thus do not constitute a conclusive information source. In order to minimize this effect, we have replaced some attributes. However, by dividing the weight of plate attribute by the section surface, we obtained information similar to the thickness, but having the advantage to present a distribution much less discrete.

Fig.2: Distribution histograms of attributes (from PEPITo®)

4.4 Data quality

This step listed the problematic recordings (strange distribution, missed values, data in conflict with their physical meaning) in order to take care of them in the next stages. The histograms of all attributes have been realized in order to observe the data and to point out the missed or absurd values. We have decided to eject the recordings corresponding to a straightening time upper a certain value (expressed in h/m²). Moreover, the data were restricted to the passenger ships.

4.5 Data exploration

This work stage consisted in using different approaches to visualize the correlations existing between the attributes and the straightening workload in order to finally select the parameters having the most relevant influence on the straightening assessment. In order to fulfil this stage, four different approaches were used:

- a linear correlation analysis trough a dendrograms elaboration
- conventional conditioned distribution histograms
- conventional dots clouds diagrams
- a decision trees analysis

4.5.1 Dendrogram analysis

4.5.1.1 Methodology

The dendrogram is the graphical representation, Fig.3, of a statistical tool called hierarchical agglomerative clustering. Hierarchical clustering aims to define a sequence of N clusterings of k clusters, for $k \in [1, \dots, N]$, so that clusters form a nested sequence. The agglomerative algorithm starts with the initial set of N attributes, considered as N singleton clusters. At each step it proceeds by identifying the two most similar clusters and merging them to form a new cluster. This step is repeated until all attributes have been merged together into a single cluster. The similarity among the attributes is measured with the linear correlation coefficient:

$$\rho(x, y) = \text{cov}(x, y) / \sigma_x \cdot \sigma_y \quad (1)$$

where, $cov(x,y)$ represents the covariance between X and Y; and σ_x is the standard deviation of x. This tool is particularly interesting for the analysis of attribute similarities, detecting and eliminating the attributes that are too much linear correlated, or detecting important linear correlations between a goal attribute and input attributes. On a dendrogram, the coefficients displayed represent the minimum linear correlation coefficients between one attribute and a group of attributes or between two groups of attributes. The range of the coefficient is in [0,1].

4.5.2 Application

Fig.3 shows a dendrogram analysis of the straightening database. The study showed that the interest attribute (straightening in h/m^2) does not seem to be strongly correlated to the other numerical parameters of the database (in particular the scantling variables). This indicates that there are not linear relations between the scantling variables and the straightening cost. On the other hand, this does not prohibit the existence of a nonlinear relation.

Fig.3: Dendrogram of attributes from straightening database (from PEPITo®)

4.5.3 Conditioned distribution histograms

Fig.4 shows a histogram of straightening workload (h/m^2) conditioned by the thickness plate. Before the use of this method, it is necessary to classify the recordings in clusters following their membership in a particular values range of an attribute; for example, we separate the sections in three groups A, B and C for low, medium or high value of the thickness attribute. We can also visualize the Gaussian curve extrapolated for each cluster and compare the means and standard deviation. The result of this analyze is that the straightening workload grows when the plate thickness decreases. But we note that the dispersion of results is very high.

Fig.4: Histogram of straightening workload (h/m^2) conditioned by plate thickness (from PEPITo®)

4.5.4 Dots clouds diagrams

The following dots clouds diagrams, Fig.5, show straightening cost in function the section weight respectively conditioned by section family and steel grade. The most interesting result is that we can see a correlation (1/X) between straightening cost and section weight whereas we rather await something of similar with the thickness of deck plates. Each cluster (family and steel grade) points at different places from the curve. We can thus see their influence on the straightening cost.

Fig.5 : Dots clouds of the straightening database (from PEPITo®)

4.5.5 Decision Tree

The technique of decision trees (DT) is a tool used in classification problems. It aims to elaborate automatic 'if-then' rules. It has a symbolic output and symbolic and/or numerical inputs. The basic procedure is a search algorithm minimizing a score measure (entropy measure). The implicit goal of this iterative search is to produce a tree, as simple as possible, providing a maximum amount of information about the classification variable of the learning problem. The tree building asks is decomposed generally into two subtasks: Tree growing which aims at deriving the tree structure and tests and tree pruning which aims at determining the appropriate complexity of the tree. The main strength of DT is its interpretability indeed it ease identification of the relevant attributes for a problem. DT is a computationally efficient tool, but less accurate than a neural network.

Fig.6: Decision tree relating to straightening work (from PEPITo®)

This automatic technique performs a series of tests that permit to separate the data in sub-groups. Typically, if we define a cluster LOW (few straightening work – good quality – light grey) and a cluster HIGH (lot of straightening work – poor quality – dark grey), the tree generates itself in order to dispatch the recordings following their quality, Fig.6. If the separation is well established, the extremity cells tend to have one colour and the path that conducts to the green cells traduces us the value that the different attributes have to take to obtain few straightening work.

This method provides two interesting outputs:

- the list of discriminatory attributes and theirs relative percentage (weight of section [56.3%], section family [7.7%], thickness [4.7%], etc.)
- the finding of thresholds in order to make the most efficient separation between attributes. For instance, the main branch of the tree are divided with the following rule : “If the section weight < K1 or 163 tons then straightening is HIGH”

We can deduce that section weight is decisive, but other parameters such as family or thickness are also interesting. This method has the major advantage to select the most relevant variables before an analysis by an artificial neuronal network in order to avoid unnecessary high computing times.

4.6 Data modelling

4.6.1 Selection of relevant attributes

The visualisation methods presented so far revealed that ‘section weight’ is the most decisive parameter, followed by ‘section family’ and ‘plate thickness’. None of the scantling attributes (‘delta_stiffeners’, ‘H_stiffeners’, ‘delta_frame’, etc) seem to be correlated to the straightening workload. Because the attribute ‘section weight’ can fluctuate as function of the section dimensions, we decided to use ‘section weight’ divided by the section surface. Finally, we selected ‘section weight divided by (surface or length)’, ‘section family’ and ‘section surface’ and ‘distance between stiffeners’ as input parameters used to establish the straightening estimation formula.

4.6.2 Artificial Neuronal Network

We used the Artificial Neuronal Network (ANN) technique to find the relation between the five previous attributes and the straightening cost. Artificial Neural Networks, e.g. *Mesbahi (2003)*, have gained popularity for their effective manner to manage complex, multiple input situations and provide a single output. In shipbuilding research, ANNs have been used e.g. for hull resistance prediction, *Couser et al. (2004)*, safety prediction, *Gerigk (2005)*, manoeuvrability prediction, *Ebada and Abdel-Maksoug (2006)*, that for freight rate prediction, *Bruce and Morgan (2006)*, or propulsion prediction, *Roddy et al. (2006)*. One of their key advantages is their ability to easily model complex, non-linear systems, a feature which is not true of statistical regression methods where an appropriate non-linear function must first be found. An advantage of artificial neural networks over statistical methods is their ability to adapt to new data. Once an ANN architecture has been designed, it can quickly be retrained as new data becomes available. Essentially, a complex set of data can be modelled using ANNs to establish patterns in such systems.

The basic architecture, Fig.7, consists of an input layer (with all input variables), and output layer (with one or more output variables) and one or more hidden layers that process the input variables to the output variables, using weights and (usually nonlinear) transfer functions. The main strength of ANN is its universal approximation capability. It is probably the most accurate data mining method among the available data-driven prediction techniques. Unfortunately, from the point of view of interpretability it is perceived as a black box. ANNs require considerable CPU time during the training stage and may become cumbersome for highly dimensioned input spaces. It is thus advisable to use first methods to that reduce the input space, like decision (or regression) trees or dendrograms.

Fig.1 : Artificial Neuronal Network (ANN) Architecture

4.6.3 Application

After having chosen the input parameters, we filtered the input records to obtain the most reliable relation between straightening cost and scantling variables:

- we omitted sections where the straightening work was done by sub-contractors because time measurements (cost table) of straightening are less reliable.
- We considered only the sections having a width near 30 m, because we used the ‘*weight section divided by the section length*’.

This filtering drastically reduced our database.

Fig.8: Error diagrams relating to ANN analysis (from PEPITo®)

We used two ANNs, Fig.8:

1. One with 5 input parameters (‘family’, ‘section surface’, ‘thickness’, ‘section weight divided by length’, ‘distance between stiffeners’), a hidden layer of 5 nodes and 1 output parameter (‘straightening cost’);

- One with 9 input parameters ('family', 'section surface', 'thickness', 'section weight divided by length', 'distance between stiffeners', 'steel grade', 'special flag and double bottom flag'), a hidden layer of 5 nodes and 1 output parameter ('straightening cost');

The left side of Fig.8 shows histogram errors of the ANN analysis. It compares the value to be predicted ('straightening cost') and the value predicted ('straightening cost coming from the output of ANN') during the validation test of the results. The error dispersion is less large in the model at 9 inputs than in the model at 5 inputs. Indeed, the correlation obtained is 0.744 for the model at 5 inputs and 0.888 for the model at 9 inputs. However, the method has its limits. Since the recordings were restricted to the works realised by the shipyard workers, the quantity of data exploited was small and thus the robustness of the formula was not very good. When we constructed the error diagrams, we voluntarily tested the equation on the same data set than the one used to establish the relation. As a consequence, the precision given will be optimistic. We await new data to test the results with a test set different than the learning set.

The analysis of the sensitivities consists in modifying the value of an input attribute (the others being maintained constant) and to observe this impact on the output variable. This methodology has several advantages: visualise a projection of the multi-parameters relation in a two dimensions graphic, understand the validity domains, and outline the influence of different variables. Fig.9 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** presents the relation sensitivity towards the family attribute; the other parameters being maintained fixed to their average value. We observe a normal comportment; e.g. the section coming from superstructures have small thickness and are thus characterised by an important straightening contrary to the sections of hull bottom.

Fig.9: Sensitivity towards the family attribute

5 Conclusions

This data mining study, respecting a rigorous protocol for analyzing the data (since the CRISP-DM methodology was used), has shown how various prediction models of the straightening workload (in h/m²) for deck plate in passenger ships can be designed. We consider that the data mining analysis process and the related tools available on the market will provide an important added value in modelling the ship industry.

Among the various modelling techniques offered in PEPITO®, we privileged the regression techniques (prediction of a numerical continuous variable) of non-linear type and in particular the hybrid techniques using jointly the decision tree analysis and the artificial neuronal networks. This choice was led by the observation of the very weak linear correlation existing between straightening cost and the scantling variables within this data base.

The advantages of data mining utilisation are:

- Selection of the most relevant variables before artificial neuronal network analysis thanks to the decision tree. Moreover, the preliminary identification of the key factors improves the effectiveness of the ANN and reduces the computing times.
- Prediction accuracy brought by the method of the ANN.

We believe that data mining will become an important approach for ship design and production.

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Development of a Hybrid Agent-Genetic Algorithm Approach to General Arrangements

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Abstract

The continuing development of an agent-genetic algorithm hybrid optimization kernel for the allocation of spaces to Zone-decks in a preliminary ship general arrangements design system is presented. In this system, design agents representing the interests of the spaces and the Zone-decks are utilized to propose possible improvements to a population of candidate solutions. Their design change requests are accepted or denied by a domain agent if they will improve the overall ship space allocation design. In parallel, a design judge agent monitors the population and reseeds dominated or infeasible solutions and a genetic algorithm agent provides periodic stochastic manipulation of the population to improve the algorithm's global search capabilities. The algorithm is used to optimize the Zone-deck allocation of spaces for a Notional Corvette-sized vessel.

1. Introduction

The general arrangement of a naval ship design has a significant impact on the effectiveness of that platform in numerous subject areas ranging from cost of replenishment to mission effectiveness and survivability. With such broad sweeping impact, the optimization of the general arrangements is a key concern of naval ship designers. Despite this need for a comprehensive and systematic approach to the optimization of the general arrangements of a ship, the methods typically relied upon are a combination of ad-hoc methods, design rules, and the personal experience of the designer. In addition, detailed arrangements are typically considered only in the later stages of the design. The objective of a project being undertaken by the University of Michigan, *Nick et al. (2006)*, is to develop a methodology and software that provides general arrangements optimization for naval surface ships early in the design process. The system is intended to enter the design process at the end of the conceptual design phase (analysis of alternatives) and at the beginning of preliminary ship design phase. The program takes the outputs of an Advanced Surface Ship Evaluation Tool (ASSET) level of detail synthesis model (ASSET 2005) and then, with the designer in the loop, systematically develops the general arrangements through a three level optimization. At the first level, the system determines the optimal allocation of the spaces to Zone-decks (where a Zone-deck is one deck and one subdivision). Subsequently, the system determines the optimal topological and geometric arrangement of the allocated spaces within the Zone-decks.

The goal of this paper is to discuss the formulation and development of a hybrid agent-genetic algorithm kernel for optimizing the allocation of the spaces to Zone-decks, Fig.1. The Zone-deck allocation problem falls into the category of combinatorial optimization. More specifically the Zone-deck allocation problem shares features with two specific classes of problems: Bin Packing Problems (BPPs), *Khuri et al. (1995)*, *Houchbaum (1997)*, *Papadimitriou and Steiglitz (1998)*, and Quadratic Assignment Problems (QAPs), *Schnecke and Vornberger (1998)*, *Merz (2000)*. Both of these problems fall under the categorization of NP-Hard problems, problems for which there exists no known optimization algorithm that can obtain a solution in polynomial time, *Gen and Cheng (2000)*. The basic idea is to hybridize the intelligent search capabilities of agents with the global search robustness of a genetic algorithm (GA). In this system, design agents are utilized to propose possible improvements to a population of candidate solutions. Their design change requests are accepted or denied by a domain agent review panel that consists of domain agents representing the various disciplines of the ship design. In parallel, a design judge agent monitors the population and reseeds dominated or infeasible solutions, and a genetic algorithm agent provides periodic stochastic global search manipulation of the population.

Fig.1: Zone-deck Allocation Kernel

In this paper, the formulation of the Zone-deck allocation problem is discussed from both a physical and mathematical standpoint. Then, the design and development plan for the agent-genetic algorithm hybrid kernel is addressed. This is followed by a brief discussion of the first three tiers of the application development and their performance results. The development of the more complete Tier Four and Tier Five solutions are then presented. The Tier Five kernel is applied to a Corvette-sized design example. Lastly, the future development of the optimization kernel is briefly described.

2. Overview of the Zone-deck Allocation Problem

2.1. Physical Problem Description

The analysis of alternatives stage, within synthesis programs such as ASSET, generates a number of outputs, including: hullform, major structural subdivisions and decks, and a notional aggregate Area/Volume Report (AVR). This information is merged with the ship template information to establish a detailed list of spaces and their required areas, as well as a list of Zone-decks and their available areas. The Zone-decks are regions of the ship bounded by major structural boundaries, in this case decks and subdivisions, Fig.2. At the level of development presented here, the Zone-decks are defined from beam to beam. However, the system will handle transverse partitioning of Zone-decks of the ship to incorporate major longitudinal passages and features found in more complicated ships such as amphibious assault ships (LHDs) or carriers (CVNs). Not all Zone-decks have arrangeable area. As part of the import process, the user has the option of either excluding entire Zone-decks or partially excluding them through the use of large object space reservations. For example, in this system the following types of spaces are predetermined upstream in the design process:

- Main Machinery Rooms (MMR),
- Auxiliary Machinery Rooms (AMR),
- Major combat system locations and spaces (VLS magazines, guns, etc.), and
- Primary machinery intake and exhaust ducts.

With the input parameters established, the task is to optimally allocate each space within the ship constrained by both the arrangeable area limitations of the Zone-decks and the goals and requirements for each space. Constraints attached to a space can be classified as either topological or geometric in

nature. Topological constraints are primarily used to establish relationships between a space and the outside world, and can be one of four basic types: global location, adjacency, separation, and connectivity. Geometric constraints address the specific requirements of a space’s physical boundary, and can be one of four basic types: area, shape, interference, and accessibility. Of the varying types within the topological and geometric classifications, the constraints that are attached to a space are either directed at the space itself or they are relational in nature. The constraint types that are relational in nature can target: other spaces, specific Zone-decks, complexes (groups of spaces that collectively perform a function, e.g. medical complex), specific objects within the model (e.g. a propeller), a fixed location in the model (X, Y, Z coordinates), and paths. Paths are special types of objects that represent the actual travel through the ship from an object at point A to the object at point B. The space constraints have a discrete implementation in the Zone-deck allocation optimization and a continuous implementation in the subsequent Zone-deck topological and geometric arrangement optimization.

Fig.2: Example of a Zone-deck in the Notional Corvette (zone deck marked in bold)

The following list gives example uses for each of the various types of constraints:

- Topological constraints
 - Global location: Space A prefers to be amidships and above the damage control deck.
 - Adjacency: Space A prefers to be adjacent to the helicopter deck.
 - Separation: Space A prefers separation from the propeller for ambient noise reasons.
 - Connectivity: Space A and Space B prefer to share a bulkhead for access or production reasons.
- Geometric constraints
 - Area: Space A has a required area of $C1 \text{ m}^2$.
 - Shape: Space A must be rectangular with an aspect ratio between $C2$ and $C3$ and possess certain minimum dimensions.
 - Interference: The path connecting Space A and Space B cannot cross the path from Space M to Space N (not yet implemented).
 - Accessibility: The common bulkhead between Space A and Space B must be at least $C4$ centimeters wide.

The Zone-deck allocation optimization considers the efficient utilization of the arrangeable Zone-deck area and the area, global location, adjacency, and separation requirements for each space. The connectivity, shape, and accessibility constraints are added in the subsequent Zone-deck topology and geometry optimization.

2.2. Mathematical Problem Description

As mentioned in the introduction, the Zone-deck allocation problem is similar to the BPP and QAP forms. Bin Packing Problems can be 1D, 2D, or 3D in form and deal with optimally packing N items into M bins. In the Zone-deck allocation problem, the bins are Zone-decks (of various arrangeable areas) and the items to be placed are the spaces (of various required areas). The quadratic assignment problem involves optimally arranging N facilities while minimizing the cost. Cost is established by the application of a distance and connectivity for the flow of materials. For example, two of the more

common QAP applications are manufacturing facilities arrangement and the traveling salesman problem. Similarly, the Zone-deck allocation problem is a constraint programming problem with dynamic relationships; however, in this case the dynamic constraints are the topological and geometric requirements of the spaces.

The initial Zone-deck optimization kernel was a real-coded genetic algorithm, *Nick et al. (2006)*. For compatibility and comparison, it was decided to use the same chromosome structure in the hybrid agent-GA kernel. Each chromosome in the population represents a candidate space allocation design. Each gene in the chromosome represents the Zone-deck assignment for a space. For example, if there are 100 spaces instantiated in the ship template, the chromosome contains 100 genes with each gene corresponding to a space on the instantiated space list. The integer number that resides in that gene (the allele) corresponds to the index number of the Zone-deck to which the space is currently allocated. For example, space number 6 in the example chromosome \mathbf{x} of Fig.3 is currently allocated to Zone-deck number 4.

Gene (Space Index Number)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Allele (Resident Zone-deck Number)	2	4	6	6	5	4	5	2	2	5	5	4

Fig.3: Example Real-Coded Chromosome

In order to adequately model the many different types of constraints in the Zone-deck allocation problem, fuzzy logic utility functions are utilized, *Nehrling (1985)*, *Kosko (1992)*. This decision stemmed from two primary considerations. First, a significant portion of the design rules applied to general arrangements use non-quantified statements such as “close to” or “separated from.” Second, because of the existence of infeasible regions in the combinatorial search space (e.g. you cannot have all spaces in one Zone-deck), the use of fuzzy logic utility functions allows for these regions to be feasible, just less preferred. This allows the optimization to always have some feasible solutions upon which to improve.

The fitness of any one chromosome (candidate space allocation design) is determined by the product fuzzy inference among three components: the minimum Zone-deck utility (which is based on an area utilization fuzzy preference function); the average of the Zone-deck utilities, and the average of the minimum space goal and constraint utilities.

$$\max U(\mathbf{x}) = \max \left[\min(U_{Z-dk}) * \sum_{k=1}^K U_{Z-dk}/K * \sum_{i=1}^I \min(U_{i1}, U_{i2}, \dots U_{ij})/I \right] \leq 1.0 \quad [1]$$

where U_{Z-dk} is the area utilization fuzzy utility for Zone-deck k , U_{ij} is the fuzzy utility for the j th constraint for the i th space, K is the total number of Zone-decks, and I is the total number of spaces. This provides a valuable metric for arrangement comparison based upon the specific needs of the ship.

The Zone-deck area utilization U_{Z-dk} is based on the ratio of the required areas of the spaces currently allocated to that Zone-deck to the available area of the Zone-deck. From this ratio, a continuous fuzzy utilization utility value $[0,1]$ is determined using a two-sided “normal distribution” with an optional central plateau. The minimum space utility reflects the least satisfied (lowest utility) of that space’s collection of fuzzy logic goals and constraints based on minimum correlation fuzzy inference. The average is used so that one particularly unsatisfied space does not drive the whole design. Spaces can have an unlimited number of fuzzy logic goals and constraints of varying types attached to them.

3. Overview of the Agent-Genetic Algorithm Hybrid Structure

3.1. Agent-Genetic Algorithm Hybrid Structure Description

The intent of the agent-genetic algorithm optimization is to take advantage of the intelligent search capabilities of agents and the robustness of genetic algorithms for handling highly multimodal problems. The asynchronous multi-agent system, *Sachdev (1998)*, optimization kernel works on a population of candidate ship space allocations as shown conceptually in Fig.4. Design Agents, representing particular aspects of the design, check out members of the population and analyze them for possible improvements with respect to their specific goals and preferences. If they identify changes that would improve the design from their perspective, they submit a change request to the domain agent review panel. The domain agent review panel in turn takes the incoming requests and passes them out to a collection of domain agents that represent the interests of specific aspects of the design (e.g. habitability, survivability, food services complex, etc.). Each domain agent then determines whether or not it accepts or rejects the change proposed. The domain agent review panel collects the votes on each change request and determines if the change request passes. If the request passes, the change is allowed to be made to that member of the population.

Fig.4: Agent-Genetic Algorithm Hybrid System Schematic

Two other types of agents manipulate the population simultaneously and asynchronously to the design agents' efforts. A design judge agent analyzes the population from a total ship perspective and destroys infeasible or dominated designs and reseeds them with new random designs. Similarly, a genetic algorithm agent performs periodic genetic manipulations on the population (crossover, mutation, inversion) to provide a stochastic global search capability. Both the design judge agent and the genetic algorithm agent operate on the population independent of the domain agent review panel. The system tracks the elite chromosome(s) and does not permit its destruction or manipulation by either the design judge agent or genetic algorithm agent. One important feature of the system is that the decision engines within the agents are completely encapsulated; that is they can approach their analyses using different methods. One design agent might use a fuzzy logic decision engine and another might use heuristics. The important thing that has to be both static and completely defined is how the ship design is described. This provides a common protocol such that when agents access a ship design they understand what they are looking at and can obtain the information they need.

A tiered development approach was chosen as the most effective means of developing the agent-genetic algorithm hybrid system outlined in Fig.4. Each "tier" of the development focused programming effort on a similar problem that was both complete and stood alone, yet provided the necessary building blocks for future tiers. Each tier increased the level of complexity of the program structure and agent decision making kernels. In addition, each early tier provided example problems for which there was either a known closed-form solution or the ability to compare the solution to other existing methods.

Since the first generation Zone-deck space allocation algorithm deals with Zone-decks that are beam to beam (i.e. no transverse asymmetry of Zone-decks), it deals with a 2D grid of Zone-decks that have an available area into which spaces are to be allocated. It was decided that the Tier One application would be developed around a similar type of problem, the spatial arrangement of colored pieces on a game board. Tier One involved colored "spaces" that arrange themselves on a board of "tiles"

according to their own beliefs. This application included the development of the space agent, a single domain agent, fuzzy logic constraints, and a tile class. Tier Two involved a more complicated board and more space types as well as the addition of multiple domain agents and the domain agent review panel. Both the Tier One and Tier Two problems had known solutions. Tier Three involved a significant increase in complexity and was the beginnings of the full-scale application. Unlike the Tier One and Tier Two problems that only allowed one space per “tile,” Tier Three allowed multiple spaces per “tile”. Also the tiles themselves were replaced by Zone-decks and the board becomes a depiction of the inboard profile of the ship. Further, Zone-deck Agents are added to the system to represent the proper area utilization interests of the various Zone-decks of the ship. The Design Judge Agent and the Genetic Algorithm Agent are also added. Due to the addition of the genetic algorithm capabilities, the system was also expanded to work on a population of solutions. For more information on Tiers One, Two, and Three refer to *Daniels and Parsons (2006)*. Tier Four was a complete rewrite of the code from the ground up and reformulation of the optimization core. Its goal was to provide a compiled application to handle the Tier Three problems and add improvements to the code based on lessons learned from the previous three tiers. Tier Five was the first tier to approach the allocation of U.S. Navy Ship Space Classification System (SSCS) based spaces in an actual ship. As a result, numerous changes were made to both the database and the fuzzy logic constraint class due to the increased complexity. The following sections discuss the application descriptions and performance of Tier’s Four and Five.

4. Tier Four Application

4.1. Description

The purpose of the Tier Four application was to combine the lessons learned from the first three development tiers and apply them to a new compiled optimization core (as opposed to interpreted VBA as in the earlier tiers). It was designed to work on the same Tier Three test problems as well as have expandability for testing larger problems. Tier Four was developed in VB.NET as a stand alone application that used an MS Access database file as its native file format. The following sections outline the new structure of the code, shown schematically in Fig.5.

Fig.5: Tier Four Schematic

4.1.1. Genetic Algorithm Agent Changes

As part of the Tier Three performance studies, a Design of Experiments (DOE) 2^k analysis of the applications GA Agent was conducted. As a result of the analysis, it was concluded that the roulette wheel survival mechanism could be removed from the code. This was as expected since the Zone-deck and space agents provide the convergent properties of the algorithm, while the GA agent's role is to provide a stochastic global search capability to possibly improve the population upon which the other agents work. In addition, a Zone-deck inversion operator was added to the code. The intent of this operator was to provide a means of stochastically swapping all the spaces in one Zone-deck with all the spaces in another. This parallels the individual inversion operator which swaps two individual spaces.

4.1.2. Zone-deck Agent Changes

The Zone-deck agent code was made more efficient in internal decision making and the number of lines of code was significantly reduced. Also, both of the design agents (space and Zone-deck agents) were modified to communicate back and forth with the population via chromosome strands. All change requests are made in this way; such that the common language between all of the agents is the chromosome of the problem, which eliminates the need for the much more complicated methods of communication used in Tier Three. As long as an agent knows the chromosome definition and which part(s) of the sequence it is interested in improving, it can participate in the improvement of the individuals of the population. This change also removed limitations on the complexity of change requests that were previously present in Tier Three.

4.1.3. Space Agent Changes

The Space Agents decision engine was upgraded to handle decisions involving swapping with appropriately-sized spaces in Zone-decks to which it might want to move. This was not previously available in Tier Three. As a result, the space agents would often be blocked out of the improvement process. Spaces would only be able to perform non-swap based moves, and as a result, when Zone-decks began to be filled, the space agent's effectiveness diminished substantially. In addition to the upgraded reasoning capabilities, the space agents were also adapted to make all analysis and change requests via communicating chromosome strands.

4.1.4. Domain Agent Changes

The functionality of the Domain Agent was absorbed into a new Chromosome class that is a member of the population object. The purpose of this change was to encapsulate the change request decision making capabilities into a single object. This was a step to facilitate future parallelization, if desired. By encapsulation into individual chromosome objects, parallelization will be possible by breaking up the population to run as subsets and conform to a more cellular population spread across processors. Another important change to the decision making engines of the chromosomes was that the efficiency was improved substantially by the introduction of bi-directional constraint information. In other words, each member of the chromosome sequence has attached to it information on which constraints are affected by its change. If that allele changes value, then the proper constraints are signaled to recalculate their values. This is more efficient than the entire chromosome being checked and updated every time a fitness value is needed for comparison calculations. For example, if there were 1800 constraints attached to various segments of the chromosome and a change request comes affecting chromosome segments that have only 50 attached constraints, the chromosome now only updates calculations for the 50 affected constraints as opposed to the full 1800, which was the case in Tier Three.

4.2. Tier Four Application Performance

For the Tier Four application evaluation, the test problems and algorithm settings as shown in *Daniels*

and Parsons (2006) were used for the number of trials, population and agent controls. This was done to directly compare the performance of the Tier Four application to the original Tier Three performance. Both a simple four Zone-deck ship and a 17 Zone-deck ship were analyzed.

For the four Zone-deck ship problem as shown in Fig.6, the average time to a solution for Tier Four was approximately 0.027 seconds whereas the Tier Three average time was 3.37 seconds. This is a substantial improvement in performance that was primarily due to two factors: the restructuring of the code to be more efficient and the fact that the Tier Four application was in a compiled form as opposed to interpreted VBA.

Fig.6: Inboard Profile for 4 Zone-deck Test Ship

For the 17 Zone-deck ship problem as shown in Fig.7, the average time to solution for Tier Four was approximately 40 seconds whereas the Tier Three time was 38.25 minutes. The overall performance of the Tier Four application indicates a two order of magnitude increase in speed of the new compiled kernel over the old interpreted code.

Fig.7: Inboard Profile for 17 Zone-deck Test Ship

5. Tier Five Application

5.1. Description

The Tier Five application was developed from the Tier Four revised object structure; however, the objects themselves were re-written to incorporate real U.S. Navy Ship Space Classification System (SSCS) based spaces as opposed to colored spaces as was used in the developmental Tier's One through Four. A number of changes were also made to the space, Zone-deck, and constraint objects to reflect the new data structure for the optimization.

The Space Objects now contain information including their SSCS number and name, a gender designator, personnel capacity, required area, complex membership list (i.e. medical, food services, etc.), the estimated mass of the space, and the importance of that space (1 lowest – 10 highest). In addition, spaces can now be fixed to a specific Zone-deck a priori, if desired by the designer. For example, the location of the hanger can be fixed since it is likely to be located in a predetermined Zone-deck at the ASSET level of design. The Zone-deck Objects now keep track of their arrangeable and un-arrangeable areas. They can also exist as three different primary types: Superstructure (SUPER), Above Damage Control Deck Hull (ADCDH), and Below Damage Control Deck Hull (BDCDH), Fig.8. This designation is important because some of the constraints have conditional

behavior depending upon whether the space is located in the superstructure, above the damage control deck, or below the damage control deck.

nil	SUPER	nil	nil	nil	nil						
nil	nil	nil	SUPER	nil	nil	SUPER	SUPER	nil	nil	nil	nil
nil	nil	nil	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	nil	nil	nil	nil
nil	nil	nil	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	SUPER	nil	nil	nil
ADCDH											
BDCDH											
nil	BDCDH										

Fig.8: Zone-deck Types for the Notional Corvette

The Zone-deck Objects also include additional capabilities to associate them with various regions of the ship including Fire Zones, Electrical Zones, Chemical Protection System (CPS) Zones and IT Data Zones, Fig.9. Fire Zones indicate the regions of the ship with enclaved fire fighting capabilities with separating fire boundaries. There are similar displays for the Electrical, CPS, and Data Zones of the ship. Each of these types of Zones behaves as a Complex object. Complexes are aggregations of spaces, Zone-decks or both that can be targeted by a constraint. For example, the designer can establish constraints that will place Space A within a specific CPS zone or within any CPS Zone. Similarly, the designer can specify that a specific type of spaces must be distributed such that at least one or more of that type of space appears in each Fire Zone. It should be noted that the Zone-deck type (Above Damage Control Deck Hull, Fire, Electrical, CPS and Data Zone) assignments are on an individual Zone-deck basis making the representation of nonstandard regions possible. For example with this system, it is possible to represent a stepped damage control deck or CPS zones that do not span the inboard profile uniformly.

nil	FZ_02	nil	nil	nil	nil						
nil	nil	nil	FZ_03	nil	nil	FZ_02	FZ_02	nil	nil	nil	nil
nil	nil	nil	FZ_03	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	nil	nil	nil	nil
nil	nil	nil	FZ_03	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_01	nil	nil	nil
FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_01	FZ_01	FZ_01	FZ_01
FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_01	FZ_01	FZ_01	FZ_01
nil	FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_03	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_02	FZ_01	FZ_01	FZ_01	FZ_01

Fig.9: Fire Zones for the Notional Corvette

The constraints database for Tier Five was rewritten and structured to handle conditional behavior for above damage control deck, below damage control deck, and superstructure locations. The database application interface was also re-written to accommodate the new data structure as well as streamline and simplify the data entry process, Fig.10. While not all functionality will be initially provided, the basic form of the constraint formulation reflects real information from the Navy Standards and guidelines, the test Notional Corvette specific design information, and subject matter experts' inputs. An example of the preliminary limitations of functionality is the object targeting. Tier Five constraints are only be able to target self, other spaces, Zone-decks, and Complexes. Additional targeting for objects, paths, etc. will be added in later development.

Fig.10: Tier Five Constraint Library Editor

5.2 Tier Five Application Performance

A Corvette-size problem was constructed using the Notional Corvette template for the inboard profile with approximately the same number of spaces and constraints as would appear in smaller surface ships. The theoretical combinatorial solution space for this problem is approximately 10^{168} as compared to the 17 Zone-deck tests that had a search space of approximately 10^{86} . This number is based on the number of arrangeable Zone-decks (33) and non-fixed spaces (111) which yields $33^{111} = 3.59 \times 10^{168}$. The inboard profile of the Notional Corvette is shown in Fig.11. Black Zone-decks indicate exclusion zones that are outside the definition of the hull form, gray Zone-decks indicate exclusion zones within the hull form (in this case Main Machinery Rooms (MMR), Auxiliary Machinery Rooms (AMR), tankage, etc.), and white Zone-decks indicate zones that have arrangeable area. In the case of the Notional Corvette, there are 158 spaces of 96 unique types of spaces. A total of 47 spaces, such as the bridge, chain locker, etc. were fixed in location in advance. Additional spaces such as the MMRs, AMRs, Hanger, and Magazines, etc. were also treated as fixed objects due to their predetermined locations upstream in the design process at the ASSET level. Some of the spaces (e.g. MMRs) were represented by identical spaces broken up over multiple decks. In this case, the MMRs occupy all the Hold, 1st Platform and part of the 2nd deck in their respective subdivision zones. Even if spaces are within ship exclusion zones, their space utility constraints are still included in the optimization as their relational requirements with other spaces are still pertinent.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60
61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72
73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84

Fig.11: Notional Corvette Inboard Profile

With a preliminary constraint database of 521 constraints in the constraint library, the Tier Five application yielded the results summarized in Table I. The resulting inboard profile space allocation from the optimum chromosome is shown in the Appendix. The highest fitness value solution was obtained in about 15.6 minutes on a 2GHz laptop with 1 GB RAM as shown in Fig.12.

Table I: Tier Five Settings and Results

Population Settings		Genetic Algorithm Agent Settings	
Population Size	20	Percent Crossover	0.4
Number of Generations	100	Percent Mutation	0.2
Zone-deck Design Agent Settings		Percent Inversion	0.8
Target Area Utilization	0.90	Percent Zone-deck Inversion	0.2
Left Sigma	0.9	Design Judge Agent Settings	
Right Sigma	0.2	Reseed Survival Threshold	0.00001

Elite Chromosome	
Chromosome Fitness	0.72458
Minimum Zone-deck Utility	0.88250
Average of Zone-deck Utilities	0.98765
Average of Min Space Utilities	0.83133

Preliminary results indicate that the Tier Five Application is generating valid, high quality inboard profile space allocations relative to the satisfaction of Zone-deck area utilization and space constraints as well as naval architectural review. To account for the area needed for passages and stair towers on each deck, the target area utilization for each Zone-deck was set at 0.90. The lowest Zone-deck area utilization utility was 0.883 for the Zone-deck on the Hold level in the 10th Subdivision. The average Zone-deck utilization was an excellent 0.988. The average of the minimum space constraint utilities was 0.831. The product of these three results produces a final elite (solution) chromosome overall utility of $0.883 \times 0.988 \times 0.831 = 0.725$. Overall, the inboard profile allocation produced is a reasonable design. Berthing, commissary, command and control, medical spaces, etc. satisfy their constraints well and are in acceptable locations. There a few spaces that do not have satisfactory locations and, therefore, had low constraint utilities as permitted by the averaging of the space minimum utilities. One such space was the Air Conditioning Space located in the extreme aft of the ship where it is far from most of the spaces and equipment that it is servicing.

6. Conclusions

Tier Five is the first level of the Hybrid Agent-Genetic Algorithm Zone-deck allocation kernel to allocate real SSCS spaces to a full-scale notional ship. The program has shown that it is capable of generating high quality inboard profile allocations efficiently. The system provides the designer with an intuitive way to express his/her design wishes to the optimization process. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first use of a hybrid algorithm that combines an agent-based approach with GA global search operators. The initial testing of this approach has shown that it is both faster and more effective than either a pure (more advanced) GA algorithm or a pure agent-based solution to this type of problem, *Daniels and Parsons (2006)*. The next phase of the development will involve increasing the both the flexibility and capabilities of the constraint objects, improving the efficiency of the decision making engines within the design agents, and continuing the parallelization of the code to take advantage of the trends in multicore processor development. This optimization kernel will be incorporated into the overall naval surface ship arrangements optimization system under development.

Fig.12: Time History of Fitness of Elite Chromosome

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Appendix A: Inboard Profile Notional Corvette

	Subdivision 12	Subdivision 11	Subdivision 10	Subdivision 09	Subdivision 08	Subdivision 07
Level 03	ZD_1:	ZD_2:	ZD_3:	ZD_4:	ZD_5:	ZD_6:
Level 02	ZD_13:	ZD_14:	ZD_15:	ZD_16: SP_3 {Aft Mast}; SP_47 {Electrical Equipment Room};	ZD_17:	ZD_18:
Level 01	ZD_25:	ZD_26:	ZD_27:	ZD_28: SP_12 {Aviation Storeroom}; SP_37 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_73 {Helicopter Control Station}; SP_81 {Mechanical Workshop (Aviation)}; SP_145 {Weapons & Electrical Workshop};	ZD_29:	ZD_30: SP_30 {CPS Fan Room}; SP_31 {CPS Fan Room}; SP_130 {SSM Enclosure Magazine};
Main Deck	ZD_37:	ZD_38:	ZD_39:	ZD_40: SP_13 {Battery Locker and Charging}; SP_15 {Boat Gear Locker}; SP_50 {Enclosed RIB Stowage}; SP_69 {Helicopter Hanger Aft}; SP_72 {Helicopter Crash & Rescue Locker}; SP_74 {HIFR Equipment Room (Hanger)};	ZD_41: SP_65 {Foul Weather Gear Locker}; SP_68 {General Stowage}; SP_70 {Helicopter Hanger Fwd}; SP_71 {Helicopter Weapons Stowage}; SP_109 {POL & Paint Locker (Service)}; SP_115 {SD Storeroom};	ZD_42: SP_11 {Aviation Detachment Room}; SP_14 {BC Medical Facility}; SP_36 {Decontamination Station}; SP_82 {Medical Consultation Room}; SP_83 {Medical Storeroom}; SP_118 {Sick Bay}; SP_146 {XO Cabin & Bath};
2 nd Deck Damage Control Deck	ZD_49: SP_1 {AFFF Station}; SP_16 {Bosun Storeroom (Aft Mooring)}; SP_32 {Damage Control Station}; SP_39 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_52 {Equipment Room}; SP_58 {Fan Room}; SP_85 {Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Aft)}; SP_86 {Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Aft)}; SP_157 {HIFR Equipment Room (Flight Deck)};	ZD_50: SP_62 {Fan Room}; SP_105 {PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpB}; SP_106 {PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpB}; SP_107 {PO Cabin (Female)(4) & Bath}; SP_127 {Specialist Cabin (Female)(6)}; SP_128 {Specialist Cabin (Female)(6)};	ZD_51: SP_40 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_54 {Fan Room}; SP_104 {PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA}; SP_124 {Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB}; SP_125 {Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB}; SP_126 {Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB}; SP_139 {Library};	ZD_52: SP_23 {Cleaning Gear Storeroom (Below Decks)}; SP_57 {Fan Room}; SP_99 {PO & Specialist Dining Room}; SP_100 {PO & Specialist Dining Room}; SP_101 {PO & Specialist Dining Room}; SP_117 {Ships Office};	ZD_53: SP_27 {Cool Cold Dry Provisions}; SP_35 {Damage Control Station}; SP_41 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_59 {Fan Room}; SP_67 {Galley & Scullery}; SP_110 {Daily Provision Room}; SP_119 {Small Arms Locker};	ZD_54: SP_61 {Fan Room}; SP_114 {Refrigerator Machinery Room}; SP_137 {Electrical Switchboard Room}; SP_144 {Wardroom}; SP_152 {MMR Diesel (2nd Deck)};
1 st Platform	ZD_61: SP_6 {Air Conditioning Room}; SP_131 {Steering Gear Room}; SP_132 {Steering Gear Room}; SP_140 {Trash Room};	ZD_62: SP_76 {Laundry (Female)}; SP_77 {Linen Locker}; SP_98 {Laundry (Officer & PO)}; SP_129 {Laundry (Specialist)};	ZD_63: SP_102 {PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA}; SP_103 {PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA}; SP_121 {Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA}; SP_122 {Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA}; SP_123 {Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA};	ZD_64: SP_5 {Air Conditioning Room}; SP_75 {JP-5 Pump Room}; SP_113 {Recreation Room}; SP_135 {Electrical Switchboard Room}; SP_138 {Training Room};	ZD_65: SP_156 {AMR (1stPlatform)};	ZD_66: SP_151 {MMR Diesel (1stPlatform)};
Hold	ZD_73:	ZD_74:	ZD_75: SP_4 {Aft Pump Room};	ZD_76: SP_116 {Sewage Treatment Machinery Room}; SP_158 {Mechanical Workshop (General)};	ZD_77: SP_155 {AMR (Hold)};	ZD_78: SP_150 {MMR Diesel (Hold)};

Stern

Amidships

	Subdivision 06	Subdivision 05	Subdivision 04	Subdivision 03	Subdivision 02	Subdivision 01
Level 03	ZD_7:	ZD_8: SP_49 {Electrical Equipment Room};	ZD_9:	ZD_10:	ZD_11:	ZD_12:
Level 02	ZD_19: SP_63 {Fan Room}; SP_64 {Fan Room};	ZD_20: SP_20 {Bridge}; SP_48 {Electrical Equipment Room};	ZD_21:	ZD_22:	ZD_23:	ZD_24:
Level 01	ZD_31: SP_28 {CPS Fan Room}; SP_29 {CPS Fan Room};	ZD_32: SP_24 {CO Cabin & Bath}; SP_25 {CO Storeroom}; SP_44 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_91 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB}; SP_92 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB}; SP_93 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB}; SP_94 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB};	ZD_33:	ZD_34:	ZD_35:	ZD_36:
Main Deck	ZD_43: SP_38 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_51 {Engineer Officer Cabin}; SP_95 {Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath}; SP_96 {Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath}; SP_97 {Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath};	ZD_44: SP_42 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_87 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA}; SP_88 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA}; SP_89 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA}; SP_90 {Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA}; SP_112 {Radar Electronics Room};	ZD_45: SP_2 {AFFF Station}; SP_18 {Bosun Storeroom (MainDeck)}; SP_19 {Bosun Storeroom (MainDeck)}; SP_141 {VLS Equipment Room}; SP_142 {VLS Fan Room}; SP_143 {VLS Magazine};	ZD_46:	ZD_47:	ZD_48:
2 nd Deck Damage Control Deck	ZD_55: SP_33 {Damage Control Station}; SP_46 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_53 {Fan Room}; SP_80 {DC Central & FFDC Station}; SP_134 {Electrical Switchboard Room}; SP_149 {MMR Gas Turbine (2nd Deck)};	ZD_56: SP_26 {Combat Information Center}; SP_45 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_55 {Fan Room}; SP_111 {Quiet Room (Comm)}; SP_136 {Radio Room};	ZD_57: SP_34 {Damage Control Station}; SP_60 {Fan Room};	ZD_58: SP_43 {Electrical Equipment Room}; SP_56 {Fan Room}; SP_78 {Magazine 5" Gun A};	ZD_59: SP_8 {Anchoring & Mooring};	ZD_60: SP_84 {Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Fwd)};
1 st Platform	ZD_67: SP_148 {MMR Gas Turbine (1st Platform)};	ZD_68: SP_154 {AMR (1st Platform)};	ZD_69: SP_7 {Air Conditioning Room}; SP_120 {Sonar Equipment Room}; SP_133 {Electrical Switchboard Room};	ZD_70: SP_79 {Magazine 5" Gun B};	ZD_71: SP_17 {Bosun Storeroom (Fwd Mooring)}; SP_21 {Chain Locker}; SP_108 {POL & Paint Locker (Storage)};	ZD_72:
Hold	ZD_79: SP_147 {MMR Gas Turbine (Hold)};	ZD_80: SP_153 {AMR (Hold)};	ZD_81: SP_10 {Auxiliary Propulsion Room}; SP_66 {Fwd Pump Room};	ZD_82: SP_9 {Armory};	ZD_83: SP_22 {Chain Locker Sump};	ZD_84:

Amidships

Bow

A Mixed-Integer Heuristic for the Structural Optimization of a Cruise Ship

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Abstract

A heuristic approach is proposed to solve the structural optimization problem of a cruise ship. The challenge of optimization is to define the scantling of the structure of a ship in order to minimize the weight or the production cost. The variables are the dimensions and positions of the constitutive elements of the structure: they are discrete by nature. The objective functions are nonlinear functions. The structure is submitted to geometric constraints and to structural constraints. The geometric constraints are linear functions and the structural constraints are implicit functions requiring a high computation cost. The problem belongs to the class of mixed-integer nonlinear problems (MINLP). A local heuristic of the type “dive and fix” is combined with a solver based on approximation methods. The solver is used as a black-box tool to perform the structural analysis and solve the nonlinear optimization problems (NLP) defined by the heuristic. The heuristic is designed to always provide a discrete feasible solution. Experiments on a real-size structure demonstrate that the optimal value of the mixed-integer problem is of the same magnitude as the optimal value of the optimization problem for which all the variables can take continuous values.

1. Introduction

In the domain of naval architecture, structural optimization of a cruise ship occurs at the stage of the proposal, the earliest phase of a project. Preliminary ship sizing and structural design always pose difficult problems to designers. They have to make the most adequate choices within a very short period of time. This happens in numerous industries working with large projects whose characteristics are that the product is unique and has to be custom-designed at the very beginning of the project or even before the client’s order (i.e. naval or spatial structures).

The decisions taken during this preliminary design phase will greatly influence the subsequent steps of the production. Indeed, the preliminary structural design drastically limits the choices of production techniques and fixes the main constitutive elements of the structure. The constraints to take into account are the customer requirements concerning the ship characteristics such as, for example, speed or capacity.

The problem, as we formulate it, is to define the scantling of the constitutive elements of a structure modeled as a transversal cross-section of a cruise ship, composed of stiffened panels. The optimization is performed in order to minimize either the weight, the production cost or a combination of these two objectives. This choice has a great influence on the resulting structure. The design variables are the dimensions and positions of the constitutive elements of the structure: they have discrete values by nature. The structure is subject to geometric constraints and structural constraints. The geometric constraints ensure the feasibility of the structure (e.g. lower bounds on steel thickness) and the structural constraints model the response to solicitations and stresses.

The cost, the weight and the geometric constraints are nonlinear functions. The structural constraints are defined by implicit functions and their evaluation requires a high computation cost. This evaluation can be done thanks to analytical methods or to the use of simulation of mechanical models,

such as finite element methods. The resulting model belongs to the class of mixed-integer nonlinear programming problems (MINLP).

2. Problem formulation

A ship is a large and complex steel structure whose study requires simplifications. The front and the back of the boat have particular shapes that are the object of other specific researches (Mesh models, finite element methods, etc.). We are concerned here with the structure between these two parts. The ship is considered as the repetition of similar structural pieces, Fig.1. Each piece is left-right symmetric such that the basic element to optimize is a half piece, Fig.3. The basic element to optimize is an assembly of stiffened panels, Fig.2. The number, the arrangement, the width and the length of the panels are given data. The problem formulation used in this work is an adaptation of the model presented by *Rigo (2001a,b,c)* for the optimization of stiffened structures.

Fig.1: Decomposition of a ship into simpler elements

Fig.2: A stiffened panel

Fig.3: Cross section of a structure

2.1. Variables

Let P be the collection of panels of the structure. Each panel $p \in P$ of the structure is characterized by the plate thickness, as well as by the spacing and the dimensions of the members. The design variables apply to each stiffened panel p of the structure, Fig.4:

- δ^p is the plate thickness,
- h^p, d^p, w^p are the dimensions of web and flange of the longitudinals/stiffeners fitted along the X direction,
- h^p, d^p, w^p are the dimensions of web and flange of the transverse frames fitted along the Y direction,
- Δ^p_x is the spacing between two longitudinals/stiffeners fitted along the X direction,
- Δ^p_y is the spacing between two transverse frames fitted along Y,

Note that t^p_x and t^p_y are not design variables.

For convenience we use also the notation $(v_1^p, v_2^p, v_3^p, v_4^p, v_5^p, v_6^p, v_7^p, v_8^p, v_9^p)$ to represent the vector of variables $(\delta^p, h_x^p, d_x^p, w_x^p, \Delta_x^p, h_y^p, d_y^p, w_y^p, \Delta_y^p)$ for each panel $p \in P$. We denote by $v_i = v_i^p : p \in P$ the vector of values assumed by variable v_i^p over all the panels, for each $i=1, \dots, 9$. We also use the notation v to denote the vector $(v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8, v_9)$.

Fig.4: Design variables along x and y directions

The thickness and dimensions of the elements $(\delta^p, h_x^p, d_x^p, w_x^p, \Delta_x^p, h_y^p, d_y^p, w_y^p)$ fall within a finite set of standard thicknesses and dimensions, as they are found in a catalog by a manufacturer. Therefore, we define for each variable and for each panel a discrete set of admissible values. The extreme values of a set are fixed by the technological constraints and we use a realistic discretization step. The definition of the admissible sets (one set for each panel and each variable) is of the following type:

$$v_i^p \in D_i^p \text{ with } D_i^p = \{ v_i^p \text{ min}, v_i^p \text{ min} + \text{step}_i, v_i^p \text{ min} + 2 * \text{step}_i, \dots, v_i^p \text{ min} + n_i^{p*} \text{step}_i = v_i^p \text{ max} \}$$

$$i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8\}$$

The number of members that have to be equidistantly fixed on a panel is integer by nature. Therefore, the spacing between two frames along the x direction (Δ_x^p) may take its value in a finite set of values. For each panel we determine the set of admissible spacings using the length of the panels L and the admissible number of members $(n_{\text{min}}^p, \dots, n_{\text{max}}^p)$ for the panel p . The definition of the admissible set (one for each panel) is of the following type:

$$v_5^p \in D_5^p \text{ with } D_5^p = \{ v_5^p \text{ min}, \dots, v_5^p \text{ max} \}, v_5^p \text{ min} = L/n_{\text{max}}^p, \dots, v_5^p \text{ max} = L/n_{\text{min}}^p$$

We can not define such discrete sets of admissible values for the spacing of the members along the y direction : there are some correspondence constraints between the spacings of the longitudinal members of some panels and the widths of these panels are not identical. Thus, it is not possible to have a discrete set for the spacing of the longitudinals that would fit for every panel. It follows that, for each panel p , the spacing of the longitudinals may take its value in a set D_9^p that is a continuous interval: $v_9^p \in [v_9^p \text{ min}, v_9^p \text{ max}]$.

2.2. Objective functions

Two objective functions are modeled: the weight and the production cost of the structure. These are nonlinear functions in terms of the design variables.

- Weight objective function :

$$F = \gamma L \sum_p B^p \left\{ \delta^p + \frac{h_x^p d_x^p + w_x^p t_x^p}{\Delta_x^p} + \frac{h_y^p d_y^p + w_y^p t_y^p}{\Delta_y^p} \right\}$$

where L is the length of the panel according to the X coordinate (m), B^p is the width of panel p

according to the Y co-ordinate (m) and γ is the specific weight (N/m³).

- Cost objective function

The cost is composed of three elements: the cost of raw materials (plates, bars, etc), the cost of manpower used for the construction of the entire structure and the cost of the consumables necessary for the manufacturing process (energy, welding materials, etc.). A complete expression of the cost objective function is given in, *Rigo (2001c)*. It has the generic expression F_c :

$$F_c = \sum_p F_c^p$$

$$F_c^p = a_1 \delta^2 + a_2 \delta + a_3$$

$$+ b_1 \frac{d_x^2 h_x}{\Delta_x} + b_1 \frac{d_x w_x t_x}{\Delta_x} + b_2 \frac{d_x h_x}{\Delta_x} + b_2 \frac{w_x t_x}{\Delta_x} + b_3 \frac{d_x}{\Delta_x} + b_4 \frac{l}{\Delta_x}$$

$$+ c_1 \frac{d_y^2 h_y}{\Delta_y} + c_1 \frac{d_y w_y t_y}{\Delta_y} + c_2 \frac{d_y h_y}{\Delta_y} + c_2 \frac{w_y t_y}{\Delta_y} + c_3 \frac{d_y}{\Delta_y} + c_4 \frac{l}{\Delta_y}$$

$$+ a_4 \frac{l}{\Delta_x \Delta_y}$$

where the specific coefficients depend on the application (efficiency of the shipyard, unitary cost of the materials, etc.). The user may choose to optimize the structure using the weight, the cost or a combination of these two objective functions.

2.3. Constraints

The constraints of the mathematical model are classified into three types: technological, geometrical and structural. We present the generic formulation of each constraint. The set of constraints for any specific application model is a subset of these generic constraints.

- Technological constraints

These constraints set bounds on the design variables. The lower bounds are usually determined by technical limitations (for example a lower bound for a thickness variable to limit the impact of corrosion) and the upper bounds are usually set by to production requirements (for example handling capabilities).

$$v_i^p \min \leq v_i^p \leq v_i^p \max$$

- Geometrical constraints

These constraints limit the values of some ratios between the design variables to ensure that the structure is feasible and reliable, they originate from regulations and norms. An example is to fix a maximum ratio between the dimensions and the thickness of members (frames, stiffeners) or to link the dimensions of two distinct types of members of a panel (frame height, stiffener height). An example is $\delta^p - 2 * d_x^p \leq 0$. These constraints can be expressed by linear inequalities of the type:

$$a_i v_i^p - b_j v_j^p \leq 0$$

- Structural constraints

As external loads and forces are applied to the structure, some resultant effects such as displacements, deformations and internal stress occur. The complexity of the behavior models leads to the impossibility of explicitly drawing the relationships between the parameter studied (deflection, stress, etc...) and the design variables (element dimensions and position). The

evaluation of these resultant effects (and of their derivatives with respect to the design variables) is possible at expensive computational cost using analytical approaches or finite element methods (FEM). Given the values of the design variables, the displacements, deformations and internal stress are computed for several loading scenarios.

The structural constraints define the maximum admissible values of these resultant effects in order to limit the apparition of physical phenomenon such as yielding, buckling, ruin, etc. They are computed at a set of points defined by the user for each panel. The generic mathematical expression of these constraints is :

$$c_j(v) \leq c_{j \max}$$

with v the design variables and $c_j(v)$ the value of the effect (displacement or stress). For any fixed value of the design variable v , a structural analysis is performed to compute the value of the constraints. For this calculation, we utilize the LBR-5 software. LBR5 is based on an analytic method to solve the systems of differential equations of stiffened panels, *Rigo (2005)*.

2.4. Compact mathematical model

The problem to be solved has the following generic formulation :

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Minimize } f(v) \\ &\text{s.t.} \quad g(v) \leq 0 \\ &\quad c(v) \leq c_{\max} \\ &\quad v_i^p \in D_i^p \quad i=1, \dots, 8 \\ &\quad v_9^p \in C_9^p, \end{aligned} \tag{P1}$$

with v the vector of all variables, v_i a sub-vector of variables ($i=1, \dots, 9$), $f(v)$ a nonlinear function, $g(v)$ linear functions and $c(v)$ implicit functions, D_i are discrete sets and C_9^p is a continuous interval.

This structural optimization problem creates several difficulties: it involves mixed (continuous and discrete) variables, a nonlinear objective function and implicit structural constraints with a nonlinear behavior. To solve this problem we will use a relaxation of P1 where the discretization constraints are removed such that each variable may take its value in a continuous interval $C_i^p = [v_i^p_{\min}, v_i^p_{\max}]$, where $v_i^p_{\min}$ and $v_i^p_{\max}$ are the extreme values of D_i^p . We obtain the following formulation :

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Minimize } f(v) \\ &\text{s.t.} \quad g(v) \leq 0 \\ &\quad c(v) \leq c_{\max} \\ &\quad v_i^p \in C_i^p \quad i=1, \dots, 9 \end{aligned} \tag{P2}$$

We first present the resolution method available for the relaxed problem P2. A candidate solution (maybe not feasible) is initially considered and a structural analysis is performed. This analysis requires an important amount of computing time for real-size structures. Then an explicit local approximation of the problem is built using the output values of the structural analysis. This approximate problem is a conservative convex problem (any solution of the approximation is also a solution of the original problem). We apply an optimization algorithm based on a dual method, *Fleury (1993)*, *Schmidt and Fleury (1980)*, to obtain the optimal solution of the approximate problem. This new solution is introduced in the original problem and a new structural analysis is performed to check its feasibility. These successive steps of optimization and structural analysis may

be iterated a number of times fixed by the user: usually about 10 iterations are performed to obtain a solution that is satisfactory for the designer. We use the LBR5 software developed by *Rigo (2001a)* to perform the structural analysis and the optimization of the non linear approximate problems.

We conclude this section with a proposition based upon the experience of the designers. In structural optimization problems each design variable has a direction in which its value can change that tends to satisfy the constraints of the problem. For example an increase of the thickness of an element or a decrease of the spacing between members does not affect the feasibility of a feasible solution and may lead to a feasible solution, starting from an unfeasible one. Let's call a change in this direction a "positive change" then the proposition can be stated as follows :

Any "positive change" of the value of some or all of the design variables of a feasible solution always defines a feasible solution. (Proposition 1)

While not mathematically proven, this proposition always seems to hold in practice.

3. Heuristic Algorithm

3.1 Local search framework

We now turn to the more interesting case where the set D_i^p are discrete. The main challenge is to build a heuristic that always provides a discrete feasible solution of good quality to the problem P1, while requiring a very small number of structural analyses. The quality of the heuristic solution may be evaluated by comparison to the optimal value of the relaxed problem P2, where all the variables may take continuous values. This can also be compared with the value obtained by a single-step rounding procedure applied to the solution of the relaxed problem P2.

We use a local search heuristic inspired by the work of *Fischetti and Lodi (2003)* who experimented with a "relax and fix" heuristic for the solution of large MIP (Mixed Integer Programming Problems). This heuristic uses a generic MIP solver as a black-box "tactical" tool to explore suitable solution subspaces defined and controlled at a "strategic" level by a simple external branching framework. The "relax and fix" heuristic acts as described below. The variables are partitioned into disjoint sets of decreasing importance. A succession of MIPs are defined and solved iteratively. In the first MIP, the integrality requirement is imposed on the variables of the subset of greatest importance and the integrality constraint is relaxed on all the other variables. The resulting sub-problem is solved to optimality and the optimal values of the integer variables are fixed. The integrality constraint is imposed only on the variables of the next group in order of importance to form the MIP problem of the next iteration. The iterations stop when all the values of the variables are fixed. The 'local branching' procedure introduced by *Fischetti and Lodi* consists in adding to the MIP model, at each iteration, a linear constraint that imposes a minimum percentage on the number of variables to fix at this iteration.

Our approach is a similar two-stage approach: an external heuristic framework acts as a "strategic" tool to control at a "tactical" level the definition and the optimization of the sub-problems. At the strategic level the "relax and fix" heuristic is replaced with a "dive and fix" heuristic. This heuristic for mixed integer linear problems is presented in *Pochet and Wolsey (2006)*. Initially the heuristic solves a linear relaxation of the problem. Then a succession of linear relaxations of the problem are solved: at each step a selection of variables are rounded and their values are fixed, this defines the next linear sub-problem. The iterative process ends when all the variables have been rounded to integer values. A main difference between the "relax and fix" heuristic and the "dive-and-fix"

heuristic is the nature of the sub problems solved: the “relax and fix” heuristic adds some constraints and solves a MIP sub-problem while the “dive and fix” heuristic fixes the values of some variables and solves continuous sub-problems.

Applied to the structural optimization problem, the “dive-and-fix” procedure fixes the values of some variables while the discretization constraints are relaxed for the other variables. This defines a nonlinear sub-problem (instead of the linear problems discussed in Pochet and Wolsey: the procedure applied to select the variables and fix their values is described in the sequel of this paper. The LBR5 black box tool performs the structural analysis for the current solution and solves the current approximation to optimality.

We consider the mixed discrete-continuous nonlinear and implicit problem P1. The variables of the problem are grouped according to their physical meaning, they represent the dimensions of the panels and the dimensions and the spacing of the stiffening members. There are 9 variables for each panel p : $(\delta^p, h_x^p, d_x^p, w_x^p, \Delta_x^p, h_y^p, d_y^p, w_y^p, \Delta_y^p)$ as described at Section 2.1, which we symbolize as $(v_1^p, v_2^p, v_3^p, v_4^p, v_5^p, v_6^p, v_7^p, v_8^p, v_9^p)$ for convenience. We first consider the group of variables v_i : this is the vector composed of all the variables with index i , it may represent for example the thickness of all the panels of the structure. The variables in the vectors $v_1...v_8$ take their values in discrete sets as defined earlier and the vector v_9 has real values in a finite interval. We now consider only the eight groups of discrete variables. The groups v_i are sorted by order of decreasing importance: the importance of each group is defined by the designer according to their importance in the production process. This importance is roughly linked to the sensitivity of the objective and the constraints with respect to these variables. For clarity we assume that the order of importance is $v_1...v_8$. Finally we note v the vector of all the variables of the problem.

An initial solution is given by the designer: the values of the variables represent the dimensional characteristics of the structure. This solution may be feasible or not, discrete or not. We consider that the bounds and the linear explicit constraints are always respected. A non-feasible initial solution is allowed as the optimization algorithm used to solve the nonlinear sub-problems may start with any solution to derive a feasible solution to the initial problem. Given an initial solution v^0 the heuristic starts by computing an optimal solution v^{NLP} of the relaxed NLP problem P2, where all the variables are free (no variable has its value rounded and fixed).

At each iteration k , the heuristic starts with the solution of the previous iteration v^{k-1} . The sub-vector v_i^{k-1} of greatest importance among the free variables is selected and the values of these variables are fixed according to a rounding procedure (described below) to form the solution v^k . A structural analysis is performed at v^k by the LBR-5 software, it computes the value of the structural constraints for the solution v^k . These values are used to build an explicit approximated problem NLP^k . The LBR5 optimization module is then applied to solve the NLP^k problem. If the NLP^k problem appears to have no feasible solution, a relax procedure (described below) is applied to free the variables that have been fixed at the previous iteration and the algorithm moves to the next iteration. If a feasible solution for NLP^k is obtained then the algorithm moves to the next iteration (diving). This iterative scheme is repeated until all discretization constraints are satisfied.

The round and the relax procedures are the core of the dive-and-fix heuristic. They act jointly to define which regions of the solution space will be explored. They control the creation of the nonlinear sub problems P^k at each iteration by defining how the values for the variables are rounded and fixed. Three variations have been implemented and tested. The first one is a “closest rounding” procedure, the second one is a “up & down rounding” procedure and the third one, the “intensified closest

rounding” procedure, may be seen as an enhancement of the closest rounding procedure.

3.2. Closest rounding procedure

The dive-and-fix heuristic based on the closest rounding procedure is the following. The algorithm starts by computing an optimal solution v^{NLP} of the NLP problem, i.e. the problem where all discretization constraints have been removed and where all the variables are free. At each iteration the group of free variables of greatest importance is selected and each variable v_i of this group is individually rounded to its closest value. The values of all the variables of this group are fixed. This forms the initial solution v^k of the iteration and the local approximated problem P^k is built from this solution. Three situations may occur at this point: either P^k has a feasible optimal solution and all the discretization constraints are satisfied, in which case the heuristic stops or all the discretization constraints are not satisfied and the algorithm moves to the next iteration (diving). Third, no feasible solution is found for P^k , which implies that the problem is too constrained. A relax step is introduced to free the values of the group of variables v_i . This backtracking step allows the heuristic to consider an alternative rounding procedure to create an alternative solution $v^{k'}$. The alternative rounding procedure chosen here is to round up all the variables of the group selected for rounding. If proposition (1) holds this procedure is guaranteed to always provide a solution $v^{k'}$, for which $P^{k'}$, the approximate problem, has a feasible solution. A complete run of the algorithm generates at least 8 and at most 16 iterations. Each iteration involves a given number (fixed between 10 and 15 by the LBR5 user) of structural analysis : a complete discrete optimization using this procedure thus involves 160 up to 240 structural analysis.

3.3. Up & down rounding procedure

This procedure differs from the previous one in such a way that at each iteration k , the considered nonlinear sub-problem produces exactly two nonlinear sub-problems: P_{Up}^k and P_{Down}^k respectively obtained by rounding up or rounding down all the variables of the currently selected group of variables. A key difference with the closest rounding is that all the variables of a group are always rounded in a common way. A complete execution of the heuristic with this rounding procedure involves the creation and the resolution of exactly 16 sub-problems.

The heuristic using this procedure, as well as the one using the closest rounding procedure, may look similar to a branch and bound method, *Pochet and Wolsey (2006)*, but there are two important aspects that prevent us from using an exact branch and bound method. First, we are dealing with an implicit problem and each step of the local search defines and optimizes only a local approximation of the original structural problem. Therefore, no upper bounds can be obtained and used in a branch and bound tree. Second, as the definition of each local approximation requires a computationally expensive structural analysis, we prefer to operate on groups of variables instead of individual variables. This decision reduces the number of sub-problems but not induce a complete enumeration of the solution space as in a branch and bound approach.

3.4. Intensified closest rounding procedure

We want to enhance the closest rounding procedure to intensify the local search towards more promising regions of the solution space. The heuristic is modified in order to analyze more sub-problems and to use some lower rounding. The improved heuristics act exactly as described with the closest rounding procedure except that when a discrete feasible solution is found the algorithm performs some backtracking instead of stopping.

The backtracking is an iterative procedure that relaxes the fixed values of one or several groups of variables of a current solution to create a new solution on which the diving process is applied. The backtracking considers the solution before the last rounding step on v_i . If this step was a closest rounding, this operation is replaced with a lower rounding and the diving starts again with the new solution. If the last rounding step was an upper rounding (meaning that a closest rounding on this group of variables has previously led to an unfeasible solution) or a lower rounding (meaning that the closest rounding was by chance equivalent to a lower rounding or that backtracking has already been applied to this sub-problem), then the values fixed at this step are relaxed and the procedure backtracks to the sub-problem where the rounding step was applied on the group of variables v_{i-1} .

This enhanced heuristic may create up to 2^8 sub-problems and may be highly time consuming. It can be stopped at any time by the user or can be set to stop when a time limit is reached.

The framework of the three heuristics is presented in Fig.5.

Fig. 5: Flowchart for the heuristic procedure

4. Enhancements of the heuristic

4.1. Sorting the groups of variables

Usually in the dive-and-fix heuristics the choice of the variables to be fixed is value-driven: the variables whose values are close to a discrete admissible value are chosen to be rounded and fixed. In our heuristic the variables are partitioned in groups according to their physical meaning. We have performed several experiments with other orders of the groups of variables and the results obtained using the order of the groups proposed intuitively by the designers outperforms the results with other orders. This observation suggests that the methods usually presented in the literature to select the variables to round (i.e. rounding the variables whose values are close to the discrete admissible value) would not provide good results as some variables of structural importance could be fixed too early. In such situations unfeasible solutions may appear early and the search process may terminate prematurely.

4.2. Balancing the workload between the number of sub-problems created at the strategic level and the number of iterations performed to solve a nonlinear problem at the tactical level

Within the LBR5 black-box, each nonlinear (continuous) sub-problem is optimized thanks to an iterative method, each iteration implies the resolution of a computationally expensive structural analysis. Usually, the number of iterations in LBR5 is fixed by the user to 10 or up to 15 for difficult problems. This number of iterations allows a convergence of the optimization method even starting with unfeasible solutions. In practice, we have observed that after 5 iterations, a solution of good quality is usually found. We add a dynamic control of the iterative process : the number of iterations to solve the nonlinear sub-problems is set to 5 and 10 extra iterations are allowed if no feasible solution is found after the 5 initial iterations.

4.3. Tolerance for the rounding rule

A major characteristic of both heuristics is that the rounding procedure is applied simultaneously on all variables of a group. Although this “group-based” approach is a key to limit the number of sub-problems optimized and the number of structural analyses performed, it may appear too restrictive when using the up- or down-rounding. We may want to independently consider the variables whose values are very close to a discrete admissible value. We define a tolerance parameter so that if the value of a variable selected to be rounded (up or down) falls within a tolerance interval of a discrete admissible value then it is fixed to this value even if this does not comply with the active rounding procedure. The interval for this rule is defined using $(tolarr * step)$ where $tolarr$ is the tolerance parameter and $step$ is the difference between two consecutive values of the admissible domain of the variable. For example, a variable $delta$ is rounded to its closest admissible value if the following condition is true:

$$(\text{modulo}(\delta, \text{step}) \leq \text{tolarr} * \text{step}) \text{ or } (\text{modulo}(\delta, \text{step}) \geq (1 - \text{tolarr}) * \text{step})$$

4.4. Tolerance for the feasibility of the solution

The optimization method applied to solve approximate nonlinear problems is a dual approach that allows some constraint violation and tries to reduce these violations as much as possible. An initial

solution may be unfeasible. The result of the optimization of the approximate problem may not satisfy exactly all the constraints of the original problem: a structural analysis is performed to check that the solution is feasible for the original problem. We use a tolerance factor to accept solutions of the nonlinear problem for which the constraints violation is less than a given percentage of the value of the constraint. Allowing to consider these non feasible solutions of the approximated problem as a starting point for sub-problems allows the diving process to continue and leads to the creation of sub-problems for which feasible solutions of good quality are sometimes found.

5. Computation experiments

The heuristic has been tested to find discrete values for the design variables of the structure of a real ship build by a major European Shipyard. A partial model of the ship structure is composed of 68 panels whose structural characteristics have to be optimized. The problem has 460 discrete variables and 52 continuous variables. The solution space for the discrete variables contains more than $10e^{360}$ solutions. There are 1709 constraints. A nonlinear analysis of the relaxed problem (with all continuous variables) takes about 10 minutes on a workstation with a processor pentium 3GHz and 2GB of RAM. Using the same machine, a run of the “dive-and-fix” heuristic may last from one to thirty hours, depending on the settings and the number of sub-problems generated. One may notice that the computing time is mainly due to the structural analysis.

Solving the relaxed problem (P2) with a cost objective function provides a value of magnitude 904197 (in cost units). When the solution of the nonlinear problem is rounded by a designer, the values of the objective functions increases by about 3%. We implemented a straightforward method to obtain a discrete solution. First a simultaneous rounding of all the variables down to their closest admissible value is performed. The solution produced by this method appears to be unfeasible. Then we try rounding the variables to their closest admissible discrete value. This again leads towards an unfeasible solution. Finally, rounding of all the variables up to their closest discrete value gives a feasible discrete solution with cost value of 942469, that is an increase of 4.2%.

The optimization of the relaxed problem P2 with the weight objective function provides an objective function of magnitude 6244916 (in weight units). A discrete solution is computed thanks to the same procedure as above. Rounding down yields a weight value of 6414353, i.e. a increase of 2.7%.

We ran the heuristic with the three rounding procedures. The results are presented in Table I. We computed the percentage of loss due to the discretization of the problem. Two orders of importance, o1 and o2 provided by the designer, were used to sort the groups of variables. Other orders have been tested and only lead to only unfeasible sub-problems or provide results that are significantly worse. When using the heuristics the increase from 1.4% up to 2.2% for the weight objective function and from 0.3% up to 0.8% for the cost objective function, depending on the method used, Table II.

Table I: Results for dive-and-fix heuristic

Order of the groups	Systematic Rounding		Closest Rounding		Enhanced Closest Rounding		
	Value of the objective	Nb of sub-problems	Value of the objective	Nb of sub-problems	Value of the objective	Nb of sub-problems	Nb of solutions
Weight objective function							
o1	6338793	117	6381804	10	6352028	131	64
o2	6333208	147	6349315	10	6334737	160	52
Cost objective function							
o1	906901	22	908348	11	907375	53	26
o2	911293	24	912187	11	911459	56	26

Table II: Results - percentage of increase due to discretization

Order of the groups	Systematic Rounding	Closest Rounding	Intensified Closest Rounding
	% of increase	% of increase	% of increase
Weight objective function			
o1	1.5	2.2	1.7
o2	1.4	1.7	1.4
Cost objective function			
o1	0.3	0.5	0.4
o2	0.8	0.9	0.8

The basic heuristic using the closest rounding procedure provides results of good quality really fast. The number of sub-problems generated is around 10 and is guaranteed to be less than 16. The basic heuristic provides results of better quality using the up & down rounding procedure but the number of sub-problems generated is much larger and the run may take up to 30 hours. The enhanced heuristic may produce a number of sub-problems as large as the basic heuristic with up & down rounding and produces results of the same quality. Any one of these two methods may be interrupted at any time by the user or a time limit may be imposed. An interesting feature is that 50% of the solutions generated with these two methods are feasible discrete solutions. The designer may choose among those solutions the one that complies with some constraints that are not expressed in the model. He may also use this list of about 60 discrete solutions to choose the one that provides low values for both the weight and the objective function.

6. Conclusion

This paper has presented a basic heuristic and an enhanced heuristic to solve the structural design of a cruise ship. This is a mixed integer nonlinear problems with implicit constraints and discrete variables. To evaluate if a structure complies to the structural constraints a computationally expensive structural analysis has to be performed. The heuristic method proposed is a two-stage local search heuristic. At a strategic level a “dive-and-fix” method controls the definition of nonlinear sub-problems. The generation of the explicit sub-problems and their optimization are performed at a tactical level, using the LBR5 software as a black-box. Other structural analysis and optimization methods could be chosen. Two rounding procedures have been proposed and tested for the basic heuristic and one for the enhanced heuristic. Any heuristic is guaranteed to always provide a solution using a small number of structural analysis and a reasonable amount of time, if proposition (1) holds. The heuristics have been tested on a real ship structure. The solutions of the heuristics shows very similar values for the objective functions and always outperform a “hand-made” rounding or an automatic single step rounding of the solution of the continuous problem. The designer may choose among the proposed heuristics the one that is fast to give a discrete result or the one that generates an important number of discrete feasible solutions in a more important period of time.

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Integration of a Bottom-Up Production Cost Model in LBR-5 Optimization Tool

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Abstract

The LBR-5 software allows the optimization of ship structures following different objectives as the highest inertia, least weight and/or least cost. The interest of European shipyards to optimize the ship structure is basically related to the production cost and mainly to the labor cost. In order to increase the quality of cost estimation, a bottom-up module has been developed by University of Liege in partnership with AKERYARDS France. This module has been validated on different types of ships (LNG, Cruise Vessels, Fast Ferry) and integrated in the LBR-5 optimization process. The bottom-up cost module has two important goals. The first one is to estimate accurately the labor cost of a given ship structure taking into account the production breakdown, the block splitting sequence and all the individual operations required by the fabrication process. The second one is to compute properly the sensitivities of the design objective (construction cost) related to the design variables (scantlings). The paper also presents the results of a validation test on a large passenger vessel. The effect of the bottom-up cost module on the optimal scantling and on the cost gain is highlighted through a comparison with the results obtained using a basic cost module.

1 Introduction

LBR5 is a structural optimization tool that, in the early design stage of the project, allows:

- a 3D structural analysis of a portion of the structure (usually located in the mid-ship region, where the global bending moment is maximal);
- a scantling optimization of the structural elements (plate thickness, size and spacing of the longitudinal and transversal members), based on different objective functions as highest inertia, least weight and/or least cost.

The cost-based optimization can be performed using one of the two available cost modules:

- The basic cost module (BCM) is based on a simplified assessment of labor and material costs. To calibrate the module, the cost of a standard LBR-5 stiffened panel, Fig.1, is assessed using the unitary production costs of the shipyard.
- The advanced cost module (ACM) is a more complex cost assessment tool that takes into account detailed shipyard database. About 60 different fabrication operations are considered, covering the different construction stages.

Fig. 1: Standard LBR-5 stiffened panel

2 Description of the Basic Cost Module of Lbr-5 (Bcm)

The basic cost module of LBR5 is able to compute the material cost (as a function of weight) and the labor cost using a simplified methodology. In order to link the objective function to the design variables, the unitary costs of raw materials, the productivity rates for welding, cutting, assembling must be specified by the user.

These unitary costs vary according to the type and the size of the structure, the manufacturing technology (manual welding, robots, etc.), the experience and facilities of the construction site, the country, etc. It is therefore obvious that the result of this optimization process (scantling optimization) will be valid only for the specified economic and production data. Sensitivity analyses of the economic data on the optimum scantling can also be performed, thus providing the manager with valuable information for improving the yard.

Global construction costs can be classified into three distinctive categories: cost of raw materials, labor costs and overhead costs (Eq. 1).

$$TC = MatC + LabC + OvC \quad (1)$$

The overhead cost is not function of the design variables, so it can be ignored by the analytical cost model. Therefore, the considered cost will be:

$$TC = MatC + LabC \quad (2)$$

The material cost and the labor cost are expressed in Equations 3 and 4:

$$MatC = \sum_{j=1}^k Q_j \times P_j \quad (3)$$

$$LabC = \sum_{i=1}^{NT} T_i \times M_i \times S_i \quad (4)$$

where:

- j = reference number of a given material; k = number of materials;
- Q_j = expected quantity of the j material;
- P_j = unit price of the j material (Euro / unit); i = reference number of a given task; NT number of tasks;
- T_i = required working load for the standard i task (man-hours);
- M_i = number of repetitions for the T_i task;
- S_i = labor cost (Euro / man-hour).

Detailed information about the basic cost module (BCM) is given in *Rigo (2001, 2003)*.

3 Development of the advanced bottom-up cost module (ACM)

The cost assessment performed with the basic cost module (BCM) for large complex ship structures presents rather important differences with respect to the shipyard predictions. A number of significant parameters related to production costs (as preparing, transport, workshop type, ...) cannot be taken into consideration. More than that, the cost related to structural details (as collar plates, flat stiffeners on the web, ...) is not considered by BCM. In some cases, the construction of structural details requires an important labor load and its cost could be related to the basics scantlings variables (spacing, thicknesses). ANAST carried out since 2002 a research with the partnership of AKERYARDS France for the development of a cost module that will better fulfill the shipyard's needs.

The new advanced cost module (ACM) complies with a number of issues that were incompatible with the BCM:

- the specificity of each LBR-5 panel is considered according to the real structure (horizontal - vertical, straight – formed etc.), for a distinctive use of the shipyard’s unitary costs;
- better implementation of the unitary cost variations with the thickness of the structural members, which is not always linear;
- considering the extra costs related to the stiffening of important web height members (ex: flat bar stiffening of the web-frames);
- considering that several workshops are involved in the construction, with different production costs;
- introduction of an exhaustive representation of the fabrication operations in relation with the selected design variables.

The integration of ACM in LBR-5 tool is based of the flow-chart presented in Fig.2.

Fig.2: Integration of ACM in LBR-5

The ACM module includes about 60 basic production operations selected prior to the development following their level of labor cost. The following construction stages are covered by this selection :

- fabrication of pieces : stiffeners, individual plates, collar plates, flat-bars, ...
- pre-pre fabrication : fabrication of web-frames (including cutting and stiffening), girders and longitudinal bulkheads
- panel line : fabrication of plate panels
- pre-assembling of plate panels and frames, girders, bulkheads
- building of blocks from different assembly
- assembling of blocks.

The cost for each operation is calculated with a general analytical expression (Eq. 5).

$$CO_{ik} = Q_{ik} \times CU_{ik} \times K_{ik} \times CA_{ik} \times CAT_{ik} \quad (5)$$

where:

- i = LBR-5 panel index;
- k = operation index;
- CO_{ik} = cost for operation k on panel i;
- Q_{ik} = operation related quantity (welding length, number of brackets etc.);
- CU_{ik} = operation related unitary cost;

- K_{ik} = corrective coefficient used to calibrate the operation related quantity with respect with model particularities;
- CA_{ik} = accessibility coefficient for the operation k on panel i ;
- CAT_{ik} = workshop coefficient for the operation k on panel i.

The total structure cost will be the sum of all CO_{ik} (Eq. 6):

$$CT = \sum_i \sum_k CO_{ik} \quad (6)$$

When the BCM is used, the cost function is continuous and its sensitivities could be calculated analytically. This advantage is lost if the cost function is evaluated by the ACM. Basically, the ACM sensitivities can be written with the Equation 7 for each LBR5 panel, each design variable and each operation.

$$\delta_{ijk} = (T_1 \times CU_{ik} + T_2 \times Q_{ik}) \times K_{ik} \times CA_{ik} \times CAT_{ik} \quad (7)$$

where: T_1 = sensitivity of the quantity by each design variable X_j (Eq. 8), which is calculated analytically; T_2 = sensitivity of the unitary cost by each design variable X_j (Eq. 9), which is usually a discrete function (Fig. 3) and its calculation requires a numerical procedure.

$$T_1 = \frac{\partial Q_{ik}}{\partial X_j} \quad (8)$$

$$T_2 = \frac{\partial CU_{ik}}{\partial X_j} \quad (9)$$

A number of tests were performed on simplified structures - double hull panel, Fig.4, and on real hull structures in order to validate the ACM in terms of design variables sensitivities and total costs.

The cost sensitivity related to some design variables on the selected double hull panel was analysed. Figure 5 shows for instance the total cost variation as a function of the strake 1 thickness. As it can be noticed, the ACM calculation gives a clearly improved slope with respect to the direct calculated cost, compared to the BCM result. The average uncertainty related to the ACM, taking as reference the direct calculation is about 4%.

Fig.3: Unitary cost variation for different welding positions

Fig.4: Double hull panel

Fig.5: Total production time versus plate thickness

Straightening costs can be taken into account with both the BCM and the ACM. The welding of structural elements involves local heating of the steel. This phenomenon causes deformations which have to be reduced to obtain an acceptable surface flatness. The straightening is the process that consists in removing/reducing these distortions in order to improve the structure flatness for esthetical and service reasons. The straightening process involves non negligible labor cost; it is thus required to estimate the straightening impact on the production workload to improve the research of an optimal solution. The cost assessment of the plate straightening is done by using a general formula linking the straightening cost to the scantlings and to other section characteristics, *Caprace et al.(2007)*. This formula was obtained through a data mining method, using statistical data on straightening costs for a number of 12 ships built by AKERYARDS France. Fig.6 illustrates the variation of the straightening costs (in hours/m²), for different regions of the ship, as function of the weight of the defined lots.

Fig. 6: Straightening costs for different regions of the ship

4 Validation test for the advanced cost module (ACM)

4.1 Structural model

The LBR-5 model of the ship's mid-section was imported from an existing Mars2000 (scantling verification software based on Bureau Veritas Rules) model prepared by AKERYARDS France. LBR-5 disposes of an automatic data transfer module allowing the use of Mars2000 geometry and loads, *Richir et al. (2007)*. Fig.7 shows an imported mid-ship section (transversal members and pillars were added manually). A number of 98 LBR-5 panels were used to define the model (77 stiffened plates and 21 pillars).

Based on structure symmetry, only half of the structure was modelled. Five load cases were considered for the calculation:

- sagging wave vertical bending moment with a probability of 10^{-8} ; still water pressures; static deck loads;
- hogging wave vertical bending moment with a probability of 10^{-8} ; still water pressures; static deck loads;
- sagging wave vertical bending moment with a probability of 10^{-5} ; still water and wave pressures; static deck loads;
- hogging wave vertical bending moment with a probability of 10^{-5} ; still water and wave pressures; static deck loads;
- no bending moments; still water and wave pressures; static and inertial deck loads.

Bending efficiency coefficients were considered in order to take into account the participation degree of each deck to the longitudinal bending. These coefficients are directly imported from the Mars2000 model.

Fig.7: LBR-5 model of the ship mid-section

4.2 Optimization model

The design variables used in the optimization are (for each LBR-5 stiffened panel):

- plate thickness;
- web height (longitudinal and transversal members);
- web thickness (longitudinal and transversal members);
- flange width (longitudinal and transversal members);
- spacing (longitudinal and transversal members).

Technological constraints were assigned to the design variables to define the search space of the optimization problem. These constraints are formulated on basis of technological limitations, like minimum plate thickness considering corrosion, or maximum size or thickness of plates and members with respect to welding process.

The structural constraints imposed throughout the model to satisfy the limit states are related to:

- plate buckling based on *Hughes (1988)* formulations;
- ultimate strength of stiffened panels
- yielding in plates and longitudinal stiffeners;
- yielding in transversal members at web-plate and web-flange junctions.

The structural constraints are imposed for each load case, and when needed, at more than one point of each LBR-5 panel.

A number of equality constraints between design variables belonging to different panels were also imposed to reach a rational and exploitable solution. Transversal member spacing is considered equal all over the section. Plate thickness and transversal member web thickness are supposed to be constant on each deck. A global constraint relative to the gravity center vertical position was imposed to limit its variation between fixed lower and upper limits.

The size of the optimization problem is illustrated in Table I.

Table I: Size of the optimization problem

Type of constraints	Number of constraints
Technological	627
Structural	4109
Geometrical	622
Equality	137
Global	1

4.3 Optimization results

Due to the international competition between shipyards, a lot of valuable information will not be mentioned in the present paper. Nevertheless, the authors acknowledge AKERYARDS France for its courtesy for allowing use of their results. In this paper, data are mainly presented in terms of ratios to avoid publishing sensitive confidential quantitative data. The structural optimization was performed with both the BCM and the ACM and a comparative analysis has been carried out on the optimal configurations. These configurations (scantlings) are “feasible” solutions, which mean that all the constraints imposed to optimization are satisfied. The convergence of the cost objective function required only five iterations for both cost modules. The results revealed differences between cost assessments of the two modules, but also in terms of cost savings. This was expectable as the sensitivities of the design variables are less realistic with the BCM, compared to direct cost calculation. Figs.8 and 9 show respectively the BCM and the ACM gains in terms of production costs, considering as reference the initial design cost assessments.

Fig.8: Gain obtained with the BCM

Fig.9: Gain obtained with the ACM

The initial cost assessment shows a difference of 20.4% between the BCM and the ACM calculations. The optimal solutions present a 7.7% gain for the BCM and a 5.5% gain for the ACM, meaning a 2.2% difference in gain. This gap is given by the different cost assessments on one hand and the different sensitivities on the other. A way to evaluate the effect of sensitivities alone is to assess the costs of BCM based optimal scantlings using the ACM approach and then compare it with the ACM optimal solution. This calculation showed a gap of 0.93%. In other words, almost half of the 2.2% difference between gains obtained with the BCM and the ACM is due to the optimization process.

The general tendency for the ACM based optimization was to increase the plate thickness by ~80% on the upper decks and ~31% on the double-bottom. The longitudinal members section modulus also increased up to ~286% on the upper deck and ~260% on the double bottom, while it was reduced with ~32% in the neutral axis region. The plate and longitudinal members general increase is fully compensated by a reduction of the number of stiffeners (~27% for the transversals members respectively 20 to 38% for the longitudinal members), as well as a reduction by ~20% of the transversal member section.

The same trend was observed with the BCM based optimization, the main differences in terms of scantlings are found for the plate thickness and stiffener scantlings. The plate thickness was increased with ~100% on the upper decks and ~30% on the double bottom. The section modulus for the longitudinal stiffeners increased with ~183% on the upper deck and ~262% on the double bottom; in the neutral axis region a 32% reduction is noted. The spacing of the transversal members is the same for both methods, as it reaches each time the maximum limits of the technological constraints. Table II resumes the differences between the two calculations in terms of final scantlings.

Table II: Scantlings comparison

Structural item	Ship region	BCM	ACM
Plate thickness	Upper deck	-100%	-80%
	Double bottom	-30%	-31%
Stiffener modulus	Upper deck	-183%	-286%
	Double bottom	-262%	-260%
	Neutral axis	+32%	+32%
Stiffener spacing	Upper deck	+38%	+38%
	Lower decks	+20%	+20%
	Double bottom	-34%	-34%
Transverse spacing	Overall	+20%	+20%

5 Conclusions

The ACM is a new feature of the LBR5 software. It was developed for and with the support of AKERYARDS France, but can be used for other shipyards as well, if exhaustive specific information about unitary costs and technologies of production is available.

This paper presents an example of scantling optimization performed with the LBR-5 software. The goal was to minimize the production costs for a large passenger vessel using the two available cost assessment tools. Plate straightening was taken into account with both the BCM and the ACM.

A comparison was made between solutions found with the two cost modules. The cost assessment made with the advanced cost model (ACM) based optimization was found to be about 20% less optimistic than the simplified BCM approach. The ACM optimization found a 5.5% gain compared to the initial cost assessment, while the BCM found a 7.7% gain. The difference between these two ratios is the result of a more realistic cost assessment and calculation of sensitivities for the ACM.

Nevertheless, the general optimization trend is similar with the two approaches, as plate thickness and longitudinal stiffeners section modulus grow, while the number of longitudinal and transversal members decreases.

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Market-Mechanisms for Integrated Container Terminal Management

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Abstract

Containers came into the market for international conveyance of sea freight almost five decades ago. Today over 60% of the world's deep-sea general cargo is transported in containers, whereas some routes are even containerized up to 100%. The crucial competitive advantage in this standardized industry is the cheap shipping and turnover of the containers forcing the container terminal operators to continuously increase their productivity and reduce their handling costs. Other than strategic investments in terminal infrastructure, this can be achieved by optimizing and especially integrating the various operations of the different infrastructural components. The difficult planning of the operations and their difficult integration in a hardly predictable environment with incomplete information constitute the complex and distributed resource allocation problem of container terminal management. Based on the holistic objective to minimize the terminal-effected costs of container handling, this paper discusses a market-based approach for automated and integrated container terminal management. We also present concrete market-mechanisms for the integrated allocation of quayside transport vehicles and storage blocks and introduce a prototypical multi-agent based simulator for their validation and comparison. The proposed mechanisms are simple, flexible, efficient and terminating and thus meet the specific domain requirements. Together, market-based control and multi-agent simulation can be considered as a promising approach to handle the complexity of operational container terminal management.

1. Introduction

Reducing costs and time of international conveyance, the introduction of standardized containers in the 1960s can be considered as an important acceleration factor of international trade. The standardization of cargo results in a standardization of service quality, which makes the price of transportation the crucial competitive advantage for all market participants. These economies of scale dictate a continuous increase of container ship capacity as well as container terminal (CT) productivity, and allow the profitable transportation of more and more goods.

This containerization trend with high increasing rates, combined with high competition, evolves a high market pressure on CT operators who are forced to continuously increase their productivity and reduce their handling costs, in order to offer a rapid and low-cost turnover of the containers. This can either be achieved by strategic investments in terminal enlargement and infrastructure or by short-term improvement of the terminal operations. Especially in countries with high labor costs, the purchase of automated handling equipment gains popularity. While strategic investments are only sporadic measures, the terminal operations can be subject to a steady optimization process.

The complexity of operative container terminal management (CTM) is caused by expensive, time-critical and inter-dependent operations with incomplete information in a hardly predictable environment. CT operators are facing various distributed resource allocation problems that are hard to plan in isolation and even harder to integrate, *Gambardella and Rizzoli (2000)*.

While CT operators traditionally controlled their terminals by rules of thumb, today the problem is approached by computational methods of heuristics and simulation. In order to reduce the overall complexity, various sub-problems are optimized in isolation with a central planner integrating the partial solutions. Despite high computational efforts, the solution quality is hardly satisfactory: while the technical performance of quay cranes, e.g., is in the range of 50-60 containers/h, the operational performance yields a range of only 22-30, *Steenken et al. (2004)*.

Newer holistic and integrative approaches to terminal coordination exploit methods of Distributed Artificial Intelligence (DAI) and Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) that examine the interactions of autonomous entities and offer a decentral and flexible view on distributed problems. Some of these methods use market-mechanisms like auctions to handle distributed resource allocation problems. Consequently, first market-based ideas for the coordination of CTs have been presented by *Thurston and Hu (2002)* and *Henesey et al. (2003)*.

The paradigm of *market-based control* for the coordination of complex and distributed problems is based on the theory of supply and demand, describing markets as efficient mechanisms that lead to a globally desirable economic equilibrium with market clearing, stable prices and a fair distribution of resources. Though markets do not guarantee optimality, the solution quality often exceeds the computational and informational efforts, *Clearwater (1996)*.

This paper presents a market-based approach for integrated CTM including specific market-mechanisms as well as a prototypical multi-agent based simulator, as developed by *Franz (2006)*. The simulator is implemented with *Mulan (Multi-Agent Nets)*, a Petri-net based agent framework. In Section 2 we describe the complex problem domain of operative CTM and give a brief overview of related integrative approaches. After short introductions to market-based control (Section 3) and *Mulan* (Section 4), we present our market-based approach to integrative CTM (Section 5). Our prototypical simulator is introduced in Section 6, before providing some conclusions and future prospects (Section 7).

2. Operative Container Terminal Management

2.1. Overview

CTs are responsible for the transfer of containers between ships berthed on a maritime interface, the quay, and trucks and trains dispatched at a landside interface, the gate. This function requires loading and unloading operations of the external transport modalities by special cranes as well as a transport between them by an internal transport system. For a decoupling of quayside and landside operations, containers are temporarily stored in several storage blocks, where they usually are stacked on top of each other either by the internal transport system or by special gantry cranes.

Despite regional and historic differences in layout and infrastructure, CTs generally consist of the sub-systems (1) quay, (2) internal transport, (3) storage yard and (4) gate, which are consecutively passed in either direction by all import and export containers. Since every container is thus required to pass the storage area once, the analysis of the container transfer can often be reduced to the processes (a) quayside storage, (b) quayside retrieval, (c) landside storage and (d) landside retrieval. Fig. 1 illustrates the four sub-systems as well as the four transfer processes.

Today modern CTs reach a very high degree of automation, demanding advanced optimization methods. The Container Terminal Altenwerder (CTA) in the port of Hamburg, e.g., is equipped with dual-trolley quay cranes for the semi-automated loading and unloading of the ships, automated guided vehicles (AGVs) for a wire-guided transport of the containers between the quay and the storage yard and double rail-mounted gantry cranes (DRMG) installed at each storage block for the automated storage and retrieval of containers.

The traditional objective of CTM, as a rule of thumb, is to minimize the average ship turn-around time, in order to reduce the associated high capital and opportunity costs for the ship operators as well as to increase the utilization of the terminal's expensive berths and cranes. Therefore, the average ship turn-around time is a common CT performance indicator for both ship and terminal operators.

Fig.1: Schematic overview of CT sub-systems and transfer processes

A lot of attention is also paid to the utilization of the quay cranes that have direct influence on the ships' berthing times and offer a great potential of optimization, as mentioned above. The productivity of the cranes however depends on a good transport and storage organization, which again depends on the delivery and receipt operations at the gate. Therefore, the requirements for a steady operational improvement are a detailed understanding of the productivity determinants and their interdependencies as well as a systematic coupling of the determinants with the actual costs of container handling, *Dowd and Leschine (1989)*.

2.2. Operational Management Problems

Operational CTM faces various (real-time) optimization problems concerning each of the four sub-systems. Consequently they can be classified in problems of ship planning, transport optimization, storage and stacking logistics and gate operations, following the classification of *Steenken et al. (2004)*, who provide a comprehensive literature overview on CT operations and operations research.

The ship planning process consists of the three partial problems berth planning, crane split and stowage planning. For every arriving ship, a berth has to be allocated, considering possible technical restrictions and possibly the actual container distribution on the yard. The crane split assigns the quay cranes to different ships and sections of ships, depending on the estimated transfer demand. In stowage planning, every container is eventually assigned to a specific position on the ship in respect to the shipping lines' stowage instructions and stability requirements of the ship.

Operational transport optimization is concerned with fleet sizing, vehicle scheduling and vehicle routing, trying to maximize vehicle utilization and minimize tardiness and travel distances. Due to the strong influence on the pivotal quay crane performance, scientific research focuses on quayside transportation. With manned equipment vehicle scheduling is commonly solved by a permanent allocation of vehicles to cranes. According to this simple *single-cycle mode*, vehicles sequentially transport either import containers from the crane to the yard or export containers in the opposite direction, which inevitably leads to empty travels. Automated vehicles, on the contrary, are operated in *dual-cycle mode*. They serve several cranes and are thus able to alternately transport import and export containers. This reduces empty travels at the expense of also increasing the problem's complexity thoroughly. While fleet sizing is important with manned equipment for a timely staff planning, vehicle routing especially poses a problem for automated vehicles.

The main problem of storage and stacking logistics is the allocation of a storage position in the storage yard that is usually divided into several storage blocks. Since the containers are stacked on top of each other, only the top ones are directly accessible by the stacking equipment, which leads to unproductive container reshuffles. Therefore, the main objective is to find a position that minimizes the expected reshuffles, which is complicated by insufficient container data and hardly predictable future storage demands. Other problems can be the assignment of flexible rubber-tired gantry cranes (RTG) to storage blocks or the job allocation for DRMG.

Optimization problems at the gate result from the loading and unloading operations of the external trucks and trains that require the scheduling of special cranes and the allocation of transfer lanes. Like at the quay, objectives are short turn-around times as well as high crane utilization.

While in early CTM the terminals were mainly steered by simple rules of thumb, today optimal solutions or acceptable heuristics have been developed for all the different sub-problems and have been described in countless publications; see *Steenken et al. (2004)* for a comprehensive survey. Most of them concentrate on isolated solutions of the sub-problems though, neglecting the inter-dependence for reasons of complexity. Lately however, more and more researchers focus on integrative solutions, which are briefly introduced in the following section.

2.3. Integrative Approaches

For an integrative and holistic view on CTM researchers have presented analytical approaches with methods of Operations Research (OR), simulation-based approaches and approaches using methods of DAI with few of them describing first market-based ideas. As computational resources grow, more and more detailed simulation models have been developed mostly for supporting conventional methods and already prove their value at many CTs in daily practice. Again research concentrates on the integration of quayside problems, especially on quayside retrieval for its close relation to the stowage planning process.

OR methods for the integrated planning of vehicle routing and storage space allocation are presented, e.g., by *Murty et al. (2005)*. Their integrative decision support system (DSS) could reduce the ship turn-around time by 30% and the container handling costs by 35% at a CT in Hong-Kong. Terminal simulations and terminal simulation concepts for a better understanding of the inter-dependencies of different decisions and their influence on the overall performance are described, e.g., by *Veenstra et al. (2004)* who aim to expand their prototypical simulator in order to integrate advanced operational and financial strategies like dynamic pricing.

Methods of DAI have been proposed by several groups of researchers. Most of them develop MAS for constructing distributed simulation systems and integrate analytic approaches. *Gambardella et al. (1998)*, e.g., integrate an agent-based simulation module, a forecasting module and an analytical resource planning module. *Carrascosa et al. (2001)* present a prototypical MAS, where the terminal resources are controlled by different agents with autonomous goals. *Henesey (2004)* documents the development of a flexible, multi-agent-based CT-simulator both for strategic and operational decision support in order to provide a holistic view for the validation of different strategies.

Henesey et al. (2003) also present ideas of market-based terminal control, where agents represent different terminal functionalities and negotiate the resource allocation. For every arriving ship, a ship agent negotiates with the berth agents to find the cheapest berthing position. The ship agent also negotiates with yard agents to buy the required stowage containers and to sell the discharge containers. The yard agents that represent the different storage blocks equally deal containers with the gate agent. For price quotes, berth and yard agents also consider the costs for transportation and crane operations that they again negotiate with corresponding resource agents. Yard agents are also supposed to consider the estimated selling price of the containers at future retrieval. Being only an initial conceptual approach, it neither specifies market-mechanisms nor evaluation criteria.

Another market-like approach is described by *Thurston and Hu (2002)*, who propose a reverse auction for the allocation and routing of quayside transport vehicles that is based on the vehicle's individual estimated times of arrival (ETA) at the quay cranes and thus tries to integrate quay crane and transport vehicle schedules.

3. Market-Based Control

Market-based control is described as a paradigm for controlling complex systems that consist, in analogy to real markets, of distributed and interacting entities with some kind of resource allocation necessary. In contrast to central, monolithic approaches, markets can achieve a globally satisfying outcome with adequate computational and communicational effort by only considering local information and reducing communication to simple price quotes or costs, *Clearwater (1996)*.

In addition to efficient computation and communication, possible advantages of market-based systems result from flexible structures that are easy to maintain and expand and the high intuitiveness and transparency of market-mechanisms. From a problem-solving perspective market-approaches enable natural problem decomposition, while from a software-engineering standpoint they can provide a natural system decomposition for a straightforward component design and evaluation, *Karlsson and Ygge (2000)*. Moreover, their explicit economic orientation corresponds to the formal management objective of profit maximization. Consequently, market-based approaches, where artificial competition is used for the coordination of naturally cooperative entities, have been proposed for a variety of different problem domains like transportation, production, supply chain management and load balancing in computer networks.

Fundamental for a successful development of market-based systems is the design of efficient and effective mechanisms that maximize the sum of the entities' individual utilities and therefore the social welfare. Concepts for market-based control are inherited from various fields of economic and social research. In particular game theoretic branches like mechanism design and auction theory provide the theoretic foundation for the analysis and design of markets and mechanisms.

Especially widely spread and thoroughly examined auctions provide a rich source for the design of efficient market-mechanisms. The four classic auction types are the popular English auction, where all bidders outbid each other until only one remains, the Dutch auction, where the auctioneer continuously lowers the price until the first bidder accepts, the first-price sealed-bid auction, where all bidders place their sealed bids simultaneously with the highest bid awarded, and the Vickrey auction, where in a sealed-bid auction the highest bid wins at the price of the second-highest bid, and thus stimulates rational bidders to reveal their true evaluation. In addition, plenty of other different auctions and auction-like mechanisms have been described and categorized in literature. While most of the mechanisms are designed for real markets with competitive participants and thus face fraud and manipulation, the challenge for mechanism design in cooperative environments is to carefully balance competitive and cooperative attributes to combine the advantages of both worlds.

Another issue of mechanism design is the consideration of the participants' commitment and disposition flexibility. Since the submission of binding bids can limit a bidder's capability to participate in simultaneous auctions, mechanisms should either reduce the binding period or allow the supplemental re-allocation of resources to overcome local optima. Decommittment from negotiated contracts, e.g., can lead to an iterative improvement of the overall solution, though it is not appropriate in time-critical settings.

Also, market-based systems can have both distributed and hierarchical properties. While on the macro-level the entities coordinate their activities based on distributed market interactions, they can integrate analytical and hierarchical methods on the micro-level. Therefore, market-based control can be seen rather as a complement than a rival to traditional approaches, *Clearwater (1996)*.

Fig.2: Mulan: MAS as “nets within nets“

4. Multi-Agent Nets (Mulan)

The examination of autonomous entities (agents) is subject of DAI and MAS. Whereas traditionally DAI concentrated on cooperative problem solving and MAS focused on interaction and coordination, today both merged to a common field of research. On the agent level research is concerned with agent architectures and internal reasoning, while on the system level coordination, communication and administration are examined, where market-based control is one of many coordination concepts.

For the technical implementation of MAS appropriate software-engineering methods and tools are required that comply with the requirements of distributed systems. The agent framework *Mulan* is based on reference-nets that support the “nets within nets” paradigm for an efficient multi-agent system modeling. Reference nets are higher level Petri-nets that provide a graphical-intuitive model with formal semantics and allow maximum concurrency, *Duvigneau et al. (2002), Rölke (2004)*.

The Mulan architecture provides four levels of abstraction to implement the hierarchical structure of MAS, using the “nets within nets” paradigm as illustrated in Fig. 2. On the top level the multi-agent system is modeled as a network of different system locations (*places*), connected by communication channels (transitions and edges). Every location is administered by an agent platform that is situated as a token on the corresponding place. The platforms, being reference nets as well, again contain multiple agents (as tokens at the central place) and provide them communication channels for internal and external communication means. They also contain transitions for the dynamic addition and deletion of agents, also allowing them to move between platforms.

The encapsulated Mulan agents that are also modeled as reference-nets can interact with their environment by message passing through an incoming and an outgoing transition. They possess a knowledge base for intelligent reasoning and a set of communication protocols that define their behavior. The protocols (reference-nets again) are initiated reactively or proactively with respect to the agent’s internal state and executed at a special conversation place until they are stopped.

Mulan agents and MAS are developed and executed with Renew, a Reference-Net Workshop, which offers a reference-net editor as well as a simulator for executing the modeled nets, see *Kummer et al. (2004)* for an introduction to Renew. When the simulation is started, the user is able to explore the whole system by navigating from one net to every net referenced, following the Mulan architecture. MAS designers are thus provided with an effective development environment for an intuitive and integrated design with a powerful formalism as well as a visual simulation of the running system.

5. A Market-Based Approach for Integrated Container Terminal Management

5.1. Overview

The key concepts of our integrative approach are a holistic objective, an integrative cost estimation and a systematic market design.

Holistic Objective

Predominant terminal management objectives lack either explicit consideration of cost parameters or the explicit integration of the customers' objectives. Minimizing ship turn-around times, e.g., acknowledges both the terminal's and its customers' interests regarding efficient resource utilization, but neglects associated operational costs as well as the landside processes. The goal of minimizing the average costs of container handling, on the other hand, usually concentrates only on the costs of the terminal, neglecting its customer's expenses for their waiting transport modalities.

Our holistic objective, on the contrary, is to minimize the average terminal-affected costs per container, considering not only the terminal's direct costs of container handling, but also the terminal's influence on its customers' costs on both sides of the terminal. Implicitly, this objective leads to an economically balanced optimization of turn-around times, waiting times and resource utilization. Although external costs are unknown, it is possible to work with reasonable estimates.

Integrative Cost Estimation

On the artificial market that represents the CT system every resource allocation is decided on the basis of the actual or the anticipated resource costs. Similar to the integration of external costs for the evaluation of the overall terminal performance, the cost estimation process for the different resources takes into account not only the direct costs for the execution of the job, but also integrates the indirect costs of affected terminal components and affected subsequent orders.

When calculating the expected costs of a transport vehicle for picking up a container from a quay crane, e.g., our approach considers the operational costs for driving to the crane as well as the costs arising from both resources eventually waiting for each other. In addition, possible costs of delaying subsequent jobs of the transport vehicle are also included. This *principle of responsibility* thus explicitly considers the influences between cooperating resources and effectively integrates their different activities.

Systematic Design

In order to find appropriate mechanisms for the market-based CT control, we follow a systematic design process. Based on a functional analysis of the terminal's operations, we transfer the real-world system into a market system, determining the structures of the market. These system statics finally provide the design framework for the market-mechanisms, the system dynamics.

While in the phase of functional analysis the focus lies on the identification of the CT's components, resources and processes, in the market design phase the corresponding market participants, goods, their trade relations and their evaluation functions are determined. For every good or service traded within the market system a different market is distinguished. In order to adjust the system's variety and computational complexity, on this structural level different design alternatives are considered that result from the introduction of market coordinators and the integration of inter-dependent markets. With central coordination and full market integration it is even possible to integrate traditional, centralistic methods of optimization.

Based on the alternative market models adequate negotiation mechanisms are developed by customizing common auction-mechanisms to meet the specific domain requirements. On this communicational level design alternatives can derive from mechanism variations and possible resource re-allocations. In addition to standard auction models, we consider double auctions and combinatorial auctions where bids can be placed on combinations of goods.

Fig.3: A simplified container terminal model

In the remainder of this chapter we will give a brief functional analysis of a limited problem scenario, describe market system structures and design options and finally present our market-mechanisms.

5.2. Scenario

In order to validate and implement our market-based approach, in a first step, we consider a limited problem scenario that is reduced to the two important problems of storage block allocation and quayside transport vehicle scheduling. Therefore, we concentrate on the critical synchronization of quay crane, transport vehicle and storage block operations. Both resource allocation problems are characterized by short planning horizons and require a high degree of flexibility and robustness.

The underlying, simplified CT model, illustrated in Fig.3, is based on the actual layout and configuration of the CTA at the port of Hamburg, considering AGVs and automated cranes. Especially the automated equipment appears to be suitable for methods of DAI like market-based control. It consists of a quay area equipped with fixed quay cranes (QCs), a quayside transport area for AGV operations, a storage yard divided into several storage blocks (SBs) each served by a single RMG, a landside transportation area where external trucks (XTs) deliver and receive containers directly to/from the storage blocks and a gate. In addition, we consider an external transportation area where the XTs transport containers to/from a virtual client representing all the terminal's customers. The client owns the containers, governs the fleet of XTs and also acts as a virtual ship that is considered to be permanently berthed at the quay.

In addition to the negligence of different ships and berthing positions at the quay, our model also disregards particular storage positions inside the storage blocks as well as a detailed transport area layout. Therefore, congestion and other possible vehicle conflicts are also neglected.

The different processes of retrieval and storage on either side implicate the execution and the allocation of different container handling tasks by the appropriate resources. Thereby, we assume the primary allocations of containers to QCs and XTs to be predetermined. Regarding the two retrieval processes, the allocation of SBs is predetermined by the precedent container storage process. While the quayside retrieval process only requires an AGV-allocation and the landside storage process only requires a SB-allocation, the quayside storage process requires an allocation of both AGV and SB. For landside retrieval none of the resources need to be allocated.

The two allocations for quayside storage are inter-dependent, since delivery goal and appointment for container transportation depend on the allocated SB and the delivery appointment for container storage depend on the allocated AGV. These inter-dependencies can only be considered by a complex integrated allocation process, looking for the best AGV-SB combination. For simplification, they could also be allocated in succession, where the first allocation is to be made under insecurity and the second allocation can be based on the allocation result of the first.

Table I: Processes, tasks and resource allocations

	Task	Resource	Allocation	Allocation Order
Quayside Storage	Discharge Transportation Storage	QC AGV SB	predetermined required required	1st 2nd or 3rd 2nd or 3rd
Quayside Retrieval	Retrieval Transportation Stowage	SB AGV QC	predetermined required predetermined	2nd 3rd 1st
Landside Storage	Delivery Storage	XT SB	predetermined required	1st 2nd
Landside Retrieval	Receipt Retrieval	XT SB	predetermined predetermined	1st 2nd

Typical for the problem domain is, that each task not only requires execution, its execution (and therefore also its allocation) is also required within a very short period of time that is defined by the cranes' dynamic loading and unloading schedules. An overview of the required allocations depending on the processes and tasks is given in Table I.

5.3. Market System

The structure of a market system is defined by the traded goods, the market participants, their preferences and their market relations. In accordance to the two examined sub-problems of CTM, the two types of goods in the market system are transportation and storage. Since both types of goods are consumed right when they are produced, and therefore are non-material, they are called services. Every service peculiarity of either type can unambiguously be described by specifying different service attributes like transfer locations and appointments. The market system thus consists of two different markets with heterogeneous, single-unit and non-material goods.

Of course, the two designated terminal resources act as suppliers: AGVs supply container transportation between any two transfer locations and SBs supply container storage for both their quayside and their landside interface. As demanders we regard the particular containers. While containers for quayside storage demand transportation and storage, containers for landside storage only demand storage and containers for quayside retrieval only demand transportation. In contrast to the suppliers that can only offer their services in general, the demanders can express their specific needs by specifying different utility equivalent service peculiarities. Thus, the demanded services are not necessarily specified completely at the time of the occurring demands. For quayside containers the definite specification of one service depends on the specification of the other one. Demanders can deduce the allocation deadline and from there also the bid submission deadline from the cranes' operation schedules.

The suppliers evaluate the services, following the concept of integrative cost estimation, by calculating direct and indirect costs of the service provision. They have direct costs for the actual execution of the task and for waiting on other resources in case of predictable earliness. Indirect costs occur when the service evaluated would influence the costs of their previously allocated tasks or, according to the principle of responsibility, provoke a deferral of dependent resources in case of predictable lateness. For not completely specified services their cost evaluations might be expressed as non-linear functions of the unknown attributes. Since the evaluation of one task may influence the evaluation of another one, suppliers could also evaluate combinations of services.

The demanders, on their part, may evaluate services based on the cost estimations of the suppliers. Import containers can also evaluate combinations of the two required services, since their individual evaluations are inter-dependent. On both markets the relation of suppliers and demanders is many-to-many, so that both constitute bilateral polypolies. Because of inter-dependent evaluations of the two different services by some market participants, the two different markets are considered to be inter-dependent as well.

Table II: Comparison of structurally different market models

	Un-Coordinated	Decentral-Coordinated	Central-Coordinated
Sequential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local optimization - very low variety + simple + flexible + robust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o partial optimization o medium variety o medium computational complexity + flexible + robust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + global optimization + high variety - high computational complexity - inflexible allocation process - error-prone
Integrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local optimization - low variety + fairly simple + fairly flexible + robust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o partial optimization o medium variety o medium computational complexity + fairly flexible + robust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + global optimization + very high variety - very high computational complexity - inflexible - error-prone

Difficulties in finding satisfying allocations can arise on one hand from the computational complexity of combinatorial service evaluation and on the other hand from the inherent locality of the distributed allocation process that reduces the system’s variety and thus a priori limits the problem’s solution space. In order to balance the complexity and variety of the examined problem, we consider structural design options regarding market coordination and market integration.

Market Coordination

By introducing coordinators to the described market system it is possible to raise the system’s variety and overcome local optima. In addition to the un-coordinated market system as described above, we consider decentral coordination for an aggregated allocation of multiple demands and central coordination for global optimization. While un-coordinated allocation is fairly simple and flexible, but bound to local optimization, central-coordinated allocation allows global optimization, but is very complex, inflexible and also requires more communication. With the middle course of multiple decentral coordinators for partial optimization, it could be possible to combine the advantages of the two other coordination models.

Functionally, the central coordinator can be represented by the CT. For the representation of the decentral coordinators we consider different process-related terminal resources to be adequate: the QCs appear to be suited for the coordination of the import containers’ demands that they are bound to discharge, the SBs appeal for the demand coordination of the stowage containers they hold, and the gate could take the role of coordinating the demand of the arriving export containers.

Market Integration

In addition to the three coordination levels, we also distinguish two integration models for the inter-dependent demands of the quayside import containers. In addition to the more complex integrated, combinatorial allocation, we also consider a simpler sequential allocation process that de-integrates the inter-dependent markets.

In combination these two different modification measures lead to six structurally different market models, that are compared in terms of optimization scope, system variety, computational complexity, allocation flexibility and robustness in Table II.

5.4. Market-Mechanisms

The specific requirements for resource allocation in the described problem domain result from the short allocation times, the absolute allocation necessity, the dynamic operation schedules, the inherent distribution of information, the concurrent activities of the market participants, the insecurity about future demands and offers and the inter-dependent allocations. Appropriate market-mechanisms thus have to be flexible, robust, efficient and terminating.

For this market system with bilateral polypolies, where the allocation necessity and the service specification are given by the demanders, we suggest one-sided reverse auctions and double auctions. In order to fulfill the specific requirements, we propose four different market-mechanisms that are based on general auction types: the Extended Reverse Auction (XRA) and the Dutch Reverse Auction

(DRA) for un-coordinated market models and the Continuous Combinatorial Reverse Auction (CCRA) and the Continuous Double Auction (CDA) for the integrated and coordinated market models. Note, that independent mechanisms for un-coordinated market models are functionally equivalent whether they are applied directly by the demanders or by intermediate coordinators.

In the standard reverse auction model that we consider, the demander initiates the allocation process by broadcasting his request for quotes (RFQ) with the required submission deadline to all designated suppliers who try to calculate and submit their binding quotes in due time. With expiration of the deadline the demander evaluates all submitted offers and effectually contracts the cheapest supplier by broadcasting the allocation result.

Since suppliers may be hindered to submit their offers by concurrently submitted offers or workload constraints, the bid submission in due time cannot always be guaranteed. In this case, the standard reverse auction mechanism would terminate without allocation and thus would need to be restarted. Therefore, a main feature of our market-mechanisms is the flexibility of submission deadlines.

Extended Reverse Auction (XRA)

In order to guarantee an allocation in every auction we firstly propose a simple modification of the standard reverse auction: if there are no bids submitted before the deadline, the allocation process is simply extended until the first belated offer arrives, that instantly is rewarded. The demanders thus change their market clearing strategy with expiration of the deadline from the election of the best to the election of the first quote. For minimum bid commitment the best strategy for the suppliers is to wait with the bid submission until just before the deadline. If they cannot submit their quotes in due time they wait either until they can or until the allocation result is broadcasted.

In order to be able to react to possible changes in the operation schedules after the broadcasted RFQ, in a variation of the XRA the demander is allowed to modify the submission deadline during the running auction. While the XRA-mechanism seems to be appropriate for the sequential market model, for the integrated case the binding quotes of duly bidders can be significantly extended since the demanders always have to wait for the first feasible quote combination. Of course, this mechanism is only valid for cooperative market systems, where bidders always bid according to their true evaluation.

Dutch Reverse Auction (DRA)

The following DRA-mechanism is the reversion of the traditional Dutch auction. It is inspired by *Kameshwaran and Narahari (2001)* who propose a “Dutch auction with an English clock” for road transportation marketplaces. Accordingly, the demanders continuously increase the price they are willing to pay for the tendered service until one supplier is willing to provide it for the announced price.

The great advantage of this mechanism is the minimization of bid commitment, since the market is cleared right after the submission of the first bid. The suppliers are able to continuously recalculate their cost estimations without the insecurity of pending quotes and therefore are able to participate in many concurrent auctions. While the evaluation effort is raised for suppliers, demanders do not have to expend any effort at all for the allocation decision. Since the demanders only have imprecise knowledge about the expected costs, they can have difficulties though to define an appropriate price function that determines the speed of the clock.

The increasing price function should presumably exceed the expected costs before reaching the desired allocation deadline that would delay the schedule and without provoking an early allocation that would decrease the suppliers’ disposition flexibility. Therefore, we propose a progressive, exponentially increasing price function, where the price clock increases very slowly at first and faster and faster the longer the auction lasts. In contrast to the standard linear clock, the exponential clock grants the suppliers more time for more precise cost estimations and forces allocation when the deadline approaches.

Since the allocation decision is made by the suppliers and thus the demanders of inter-dependent services do not have the chance to evaluate and reward combinations of services, the DRA-mechanism cannot be applied to integrated market models.

Continuous Combinatorial Reverse Auction (CCRA)

As a mechanism for coordinated market systems we suggest the CCRA-mechanism that allows suppliers to submit bids for combinations of services and also allows a combinatorial and market-integrative allocation.

For decentral coordination demanders are disjunctively assigned to several coordinators that continuously collect their demands and frequently broadcast RFQs with a list of unallocated demands to the designated suppliers. The suppliers, on their part, continuously estimate their costs for possible combinations and submit mutually exclusive bids for every evaluated service combination and for every coordinator. Considering all submitted bids, the coordinators frequently calculate combinatorial allocations minimizing the average handling cost per container and broadcast the allocation results. In central-coordinated market models bids are collected, broadcasted and allocated by the unique coordinator only, allowing a global optimization that is limited though by computational complexity.

The quote and market clearing frequencies are to be determined carefully, in order to allow the timely allocation of every open demand. If a demand remains unsatisfied after the allocation deadline it simply remains in the RFQ-list of unallocated demands and gets re-tendered until it can be allocated. In order to increase the disposition flexibility and to decrease the complexity of cost estimation and market clearing, not every open demand should be tendered and allocated as soon as possible. The frequencies as well as the inclusion criteria are yet to be determined and subject to further research.

Continuous Double Auction (CDA)

For central-coordinated market models we additionally suggest the CDA-mechanism, where both demanders and suppliers continuously and independently submit their general allocation intentions to the central coordinator, who frequently clears the market. Again, the frequency of market clearance is yet to be determined.

The main difference to the CCRA is the bidding behavior of the suppliers who continuously submit their current service evaluation functions without previous RFQs. Since the evaluation functions are complex and hard to describe, the combinatorial market clearance for average handling cost minimization also is a very complex task for the coordinator.

6. MAS Design and Prototypical Implementation

Based on both the functional and the market-based analysis of the limited problem scenario, we designed and prototypically implemented a MAS for simulating the container transfer processes and the market-based allocations. The objective is to construct a modular and flexible MAS that allows to examine the eligibility of different market-mechanisms regarding different terminal configurations and market models by comparing the average terminal-effected costs of container handling. The design and implementation of the MAS should also consider the future subsequent integration of the remaining resource allocation problems of CTM.

The functional requirements thus are the generation of container handling tasks, their allocation according to interchangeable mechanisms and evaluation functions, the distributed simulation of all terminal operations, the logging of the operational costs and the configurability of the terminal and its resources. The interchangeability of the market-mechanisms and the expandability of the market system technically require a modular agent design and a consistent negotiation model.

For a systematic design of a modular and flexible MAS we incrementally specified agent roles, types, functions and interactions, roughly following the Gaia-Methodology, which is a conceptual

framework for MAS design suggested by *Wooldridge et al. (2000)*. Agent roles provide a further level of abstraction to describe and encapsulate agent behavior.

Every entity type of the market system is modeled by an agent type that inherits its capabilities from a set of roles he is assigned to. That way, common capabilities of different agent types (like their skills to communicate and negotiate) only need to be modeled once and allow the flexible adjustment to different market and terminal configurations. To increase modularity, we additionally divided the agents' behavior into activities of planning, allocation and operation, effectively designing a horizontally layered agent architecture. Whereas the allocation layer controls the agents' negotiational behavior, the planning layer schedules the allocated contracts and the operational layer executes and simulates the tasks according to the schedule.

In order to implement a consistent and expandable negotiation model, we designed an auxiliary mechanism for the random determination of the allocations that we assumed to be predetermined (according to Table I). While the CT agent takes the role of the central coordinator, we stipulate the QC, SB and gate agents as decentral coordinators. Since the independent mechanisms for the un-coordinated market models can also be effectively tested in decentral-coordinated markets, the decentral coordinators act as intermediates (without coordinative functions) in un-coordinated market systems as well.

This simplification also allows to consequently implement a simple version of the intuitive and widely applied *contract net protocol (CNP)*, where co-operative agents recursively solve problems by decomposition and distribution. Accordingly, import containers, e.g., (randomly) contract a QC for quayside storage that decomposes the task and again contracts the required AGV and SB.

Based on a detailed specification for agent architecture and agent interaction, we implemented the prototypical simulator with a simple version of the Mulan-framework; for further details see *Franz (2006)*. Therefore, we modeled role-based Mulan protocols for every function specified.

The simulation of the different resource operations is realized with time-based reference-nets that can be accessed by the agents' operational layer. While the simulation nets for AGVs and XTs are based on simple coordinate systems that represent the different transfer locations, the simulation nets for QCs and SBs explicitly simulate their horizontal and vertical movement. Graphically displayed, the simulation nets are also very eligible for user observance of the running system.

A snapshot of a running terminal simulation, configured with four QCs and three SBs, is shown in Fig. 4. It displays the four QC simulation nets at the bottom and the three SB simulation nets in the middle, where the black places represent the cranes' possible positions and the black transitions their possible operations. The three nets, vertically lined up at the left, are the simulation nets for the transport vehicles, showing the vehicles they contain: the lower one is for the AGVs, the middle one for XTs inside the CT and the top one for XTs outside of the CT. The two simple nets at the middle top represent the client and the gate. In addition, at the upper right corner, the Mulan agent platform is displayed, where the user is able to explore the execution of every agent and all active protocols.

The terminal simulation prototype already (rudimentarily) implements all the specified functional requirements. Though, being a first proof of concept for the validation of the market analysis and the system specification, it so far implements only the XRA-mechanism and uses simplified evaluation functions with fictional cost data.

Fig.4: Snapshot of the running prototype of the market-based terminal simulator

7. Conclusion

The complexity of operative CTM is founded by the difficult planning of the sub-problems and their difficult integration in an unpredictable environment with incomplete information. For integrative and holistic solutions of this distributed resource allocation problem, in recent years researchers suggested various MAS-approaches, with some of them describing initial market-based ideas. In this paper we presented a market-based approach to CTM that is based on the holistic objective of minimizing the average terminal-effected costs of container handling, an integrative cost estimation concept and a systematic design process.

In a first step, we applied our approach to a limited problem scenario that contains the two important and inter-dependent management problems of quayside transport vehicle scheduling and storage block allocation. Based on a detailed functional analysis, we discuss structural aspects and design options of an appropriate market system by considering different models of market integration and coordination. In respect to the structural framework, we present specific market-mechanisms that are simple, flexible, efficient and terminating and thus meet the specific domain requirements.

In order to analyze the feasibility and to quantitatively compare our mechanisms for different terminal and market configurations, we designed a modular and expandable multi-agent simulator that we prototypically implemented with Mulan, successfully validating our approach. Together, the presented holistic approach, the market-mechanisms and the market-based multi-agent simulator are a practical contribution to the integrative control of the complex CTM problem domain.

Future steps are the development of a productive multi-agent simulator to effectively analyze and improve our mechanisms and the subsequent integration of the remaining CTM problems.

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Propeller Blade Optimization for Maximum Cavitation Margin Using Viscous-Inviscid Panel Method and a Differential Evolution Algorithm

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Abstract

The paper presents an automatic computer aided design optimization method for the geometry of propeller blade profiles with increased cavitation margins. Cavitation is taken into account using the value of the vaporization pressure as threshold for the minimum pressure predicted over the profile by a viscous/inviscid flow solver. The new integrated system described in detail in the paper features: a parametric geometry generation module using B-Splines for thickness and mean line definition, a coupled viscous-inviscid solver, an optimization algorithm which uses a modern and efficient differential evolution algorithm.

1. Introduction

The modern trend in ship design is leading to an always increasing demand of higher speed on different class of vessels, from small passenger ferries to navy vessel, from mega-yachts to fast supply vessels, from container ships to trawlers. This higher speed requirement coupled with the inherent limitations on the draft of these vessels, typically results in a higher specific load on the propellers. Hence the need to search new methods in the design of marine propellers, which has been made a very delicate problem since it is necessary to ensure a good efficiency while widening the cavitation free region of the propeller. Cavitation results in a loss in the blade lift, an acoustic signature, and possibly blade erosion: all problems to be avoided by an optimized design. In order to have good performances but increased margin to cavitation one possibility is to abandon standard blade profiles geometries, such as NACA 16 and NACA 66 traditional shapes, still commonly used in the majority of modern propellers designs. Actual practice in this direction is primarily based on trial and error procedures. The aim of this work is to devise a “systematic”, computer aided, optimization method which will consider almost every possible geometry, to finally converge on the best non-cavitating profile for a given operating condition, while ensuring a set of dynamic, geometric and strength constraints. Some attempts of this kind have appeared in the literature, for instance in USA the work of *S. Black (1994)* or that of *Yamaguchi (1999)* in Japan and more recently *Ferrando et al. (2004)*. The approach presented in the paper, *Munari (2007)*, couples an optimization algorithm, based on a Differential Evolution strategy developed by *Price and Storn (1994)*, with a 2D panel method, in this case the viscous/inviscid method developed by *Yamaguchi (1999)*.

2. Integrated Optimization System

2.1. Geometry Generation

For the definition of the foil geometry 4th order B-Splines are used, Fig.1. The thickness distribution is generated with a six point control polygon, with two points having the same x value for $x/c=0$. In this way it is possible to control the radius of the leading edge. The trailing edge has finite thickness and it is fixed, as well as the first point which has both coordinates set to zero value. Also the x value of the other points has been blocked, while the y value is free. The only constraint on thickness distribution is the maximum value of t/c , which has to be 9.52% of the chord length. This goal is achieved scaling each thickness distribution in order to have the desired value of t/c .

For what concerns the mean line, a five point B-Spline has been used, again with the first and last control points fixed at the leading edge and at the trailing edge respectively. The internal points have free y value, with the possibility to assume even negative value, and blocked x value except for the

central point which is free to move chord-wise. The geometry thus defined allow us to obtain even very unusual foils, which ensures that the optimization is considering any possible optimum shape, not conditioning a priori the solution. The free coordinates of the control polygon points are also the free parameters of the optimization process. The problem has, therefore in our case, eight free variables in number.

Fig.1: Coordinates of the Control Polygon Vertices to obtain NACA 16 thickness distribution

2.2. Hydrodynamic Analysis

Once the foil geometry is defined his hydrodynamic characteristic are evaluated using a 2D panel method which couples a potential method, based on Hess scheme, and a thin boundary layer solver, based on the displacement body concept, Fig.2.

Fig.2: Displacement Body Concept

This method was realized by *Yamaguchi (1999)* in order to study foils with a delayed cavitation inception, so it has been considered particularly suitable for this kind of optimization. Yamaguchi's method allows to analyze the hydrodynamic characteristics of 2D hydrofoils, under the hypothesis of ideal fluid with viscous corrections due to the thin boundary layer developed, so for sufficiently high Reynolds numbers without large separated regions. The perturbation potential is created with a proper distribution of sources and doublets on the foil surface. Each panel has a specific, constant value of the source intensity, while there is a single value doublet distribution all over the foil surface.

The body-boundary condition is expressed in term of zero normal velocity component, while the Kutta condition is enforced by imposing that that tangential velocity component on the panels adjacent the trailing edge, on the face and on the back, is the same.

The boundary layer is defined by solving the integral momentum equation. For the laminar boundary layer has been used the Thwaites method, modified by Curle. For the natural transition from laminar to turbulent boundary layer Yamaguchi used the Cebeci-Smith criterion. Finally, Head method, modified by Cebeci has been used to solve the turbulent boundary layer equations. The coupling between the potential solution and the boundary layer is achieved iteratively, solving a potential flow on a surface obtained by adding the displacement thickness of the boundary layer to the original surface of the foil. Each profile is analyzed both in terms of cavitation bucket and in terms of given lift. Since all the foils are wanted to give the same lift they are made to work at the same hydrodynamic angle of attack, Fig.9, by assuming the linear relation of lift versus angle of attack with

the usual constant slope taken from thin profile theory (2π). This affect the position of all the operating points which are shifted following the zero lift angle, as described in paragraph 4.1.

Fig.3: Reference System and subdivision of blade profile in segments

2.3. Optimization Algorithm

Differential Evolution (DE) is a modern, *Price and Storn (1994)*, global convergence single objective optimization algorithm. This algorithm has proven its superior speed and global convergence with respect to other optimization algorithms, such as for instance genetic type algorithms, in different test cases. The optimization strategy is based on a parallel direct search method which utilizes NP parameter vectors

$$x_{i,G} \quad i = 1, \dots, NP$$

as a population for each generation G . The number of individuals NP does not change during the minimization process. The initial population (that of the first generation) is chosen randomly if nothing is known about the system. A uniform probability distribution for all random decisions is assumed, unless otherwise stated in the paper.

Fig.4: Generation of Trial Vector in the Differential Evolution Strategy, *Price and Storn (1994)*

The crucial idea behind *DE* is a scheme for generating trial parameters vectors. *DE* generates new parameter vectors by adding a weighted difference vector between two population members and a third member, Fig.4. If the resulting vector yields a lower objective function value than a predetermined population member, such vector will be replaced in the following generation by the newly generated vector. In addition the best parameter vector $x_{best,G}$ is evaluated for every generation G in order to keep track of the progress made during the minimization process.

Extracting distance and direction information from the population to generate random deviations results in an adaptive scheme with excellent convergence properties. To maintain a certain diversity between the individuals of the generations and enhance the global convergence property of the algorithm, a cross-over mutation is performed on the trial vector, very similar to that used in the genetic algorithms, with a random probability distribution governing the number of elements of the vector to be swapped with those of a reference vector.

Fig.5: Flow Chart of the Optimization System

2.4. Optimization System

The flow chart of the automatic computer aided optimization procedure is shown in Fig.5. The designer has to select the constraints of the problem, in this case: the operating points of the blade profile to be compared with the cavitation bucket (sigma.dat), the max thickness of the profile and the lift coefficient C_L of the profile at the design angle of attack. The whole optimization process is run under the evolution algorithm called by *Diffevol.sci* that generates the free variables vectors and controls the converge of the optimization procedure. For every combination of free parameters, the blade profile geometry is defined, in terms of mean line and thickness distribution, using B-Splines by the subroutine *profile.sci*. Once the geometry is defined, the profile is analyzed using *free_prblg.exe*, the 2D panel method coupled with a boundary layer solver devised by Hagime Yamaguchi (1999). The obtained results are interpreted and combined through the objective function by *eff.sci* in order to obtain a single scalar value representative of the efficiency of the foil with respect to the design goal.

For the case presented in this paper the objective function is properly defined in order to be indicative of the cavitation margin achieved by the best profile at the given operating points.

3. Preliminary tests to validate the method

In order to validate this design method, some comparisons were done with symmetric and asymmetric sections designed using different optimization approaches. In followings, the optimum solutions for two cases taken from work of *Black (1998)* are described. Fig.6 represents the optimum profile shape found for a symmetrical strut, working without angle of attack (at $\alpha=0$), for the maximum possible cavitation inception speed. Solutions from this present optimization method are opposed to Black's and Eppler's solution for comparison. The dotted lines in both figures represents a NACA 0012 used as a reference shape, in order to appreciate difference between these new unconventional geometries (Eppler's optimum profile is represented by the continuous line; Black's optimum profiles are drawn with double-dashed lines), with respect to the ones traditionally employed in naval architecture. The comparison evidences the excellent convergence of the optimization procedure on the shape found by previous authors who used different methods. The table on the side of Fig.6 illustrates the value of the minimum pressure coefficient predicted on the profile surface at design condition and the corresponding maximum cavitation inception inflow speed, for all the optimized profiles (current method: Sym_1)

Fig.6: Comparison between present and previous work (Eppler/Black), Symmetrical Profile

Fig.7: Comparison between present and previous work (Eppler/Black); Asymmetric Profile

The second validation case presented is for an asymmetric profile. The aim of this design exercise is to achieve the maximum width of the cavitation bucket at the design cavitation index $\sigma_{des}=0.6$, while

respecting the constraint on the design lift coefficient at the design hydrodynamic angle of attack.

The design maximum thickness of the profile $t/c \approx 0.10$ is taken as a constraint in the procedure. Optimized geometry and relative width of the bucket is presented in Fig.7, bottom plot, against Eppler's and Black's results, top plot. Also in this case, the automated optimization procedure is able to converge on a optimized solution which is actually able to enlarge the operating range at the given cavitation index, with respect to the conventional NACA four digit profile. In this case the shape of the final optimized profile with the proposed method is very similar to that found by Eppler and Black, but the width of the bucket, as presented in the table of Fig.7 is rather smaller, measuring only 3.57° , against the 4.5° achieved by the cited authors. This deviation may be due to the different parameterization of the geometry used in our method and to the different CFD method used to evaluate the minimum pressure coefficient on the foil profile.

These two presented cases are only few with respect to all the test undertaken to validate the method. In general it can be stated that the devised optimization procedure is able to converge to an final profile shape having better characteristics than the standard NACA shapes, almost in every analysed case.

4. Optimization of a Propeller Blade Profile Working in a Non-uniform Wake

All the previous solutions have been achieved imposing simple working conditions, i.e. referring to a single angle of attack or a single value of the cavitation number. As an example of a more sophisticated design, it has been taken into account the same problem presented by *Ferrando et al. (2004)*. A set of operating points is defined corresponding to the different conditions met by the blade section during a revolution in the non-uniform ship wake, in terms of angle of attack and cavitation number. Using the minimum value of the pressure distribution over the foil surface obtained by the flow solver for a set of different angle of attack, a cavitation bucket, *Brockett (1966)* is built. The position of all the given operating points with respect to the boundary of the bucket is then evaluated in order to define the cavitation margin of the section during its revolution.

Fig.8 presents the design working points, in terms of angle of attack and cavitation index, overlaid on the cavitation bucket of a conventional NACA 16 profile having $t/c=9.52\%$ and cambered with a NACA $a=0.8$ line in order to obtain a design lift coefficient $C_L=0.1841$ at an angle of attack $\alpha=0.57^\circ$. With the usual assumption to take incipient cavitation when the minimum pressure on the profile reaches the vapour pressure of the water, the theoretical bucket of the profile can use the cavitation index or the modulus of the minimum pressure $|C_p^{\min}|$.

The automated optimization procedure has been run, with a set of design constraints the same chosen by *Ferrando et al. (2004)*, i.e.:

- the maximum value of the design t/c has been imposed, in order not to change significantly the inertia modulus of the section and hence the strength;
- the operating points of each candidate profile have been shifted of a proper angle of attack in order to obtain the same design lift coefficient at the design angle of attack, as described in detail in the next paragraph. Two design philosophies have been tested for limiting the maximum range of translation of the operating angles of attack:
 1. no limitation is imposed to the variation, hence allowing to have optimum foils working at negative angles of attack even in the design condition. This case leads in general to extreme "S" shaped optimum foils;
 2. any candidate foil is forced to have a positive angle of attack (at least) in the reference design condition, i.e. at the angle at which the foil develop a $C_L=0.1841$. This additional constraint has the effect to actually limit the diversity of each candidate profiles thus converging to more conventionally shaped profiles. This design case has been tested to verify the possibility to obtain an optimized foil with operating points closer to those of the conventional NACA profile, but eventually was as effective as the one obtained with the first approach.

Fig.8: Cavitation Bucket and Operating Points of the conventional cambered NACA 16 foil

The optimization has been conducted taking into account the effects of the boundary layer in both cases, setting the Reynolds number to $Rn_c=Uc/\nu=10^7$ (c = chord length), representative of the average operating condition of the blade profile at full scale.

4.1. Working Points

The operating points are translated along the α -axis, in the cavitation bucket plane, for each foil's geometry analyzed accordingly to the zero lift angle value. Using the subscript k for any candidate foil analysed in the optimization procedure and without subscript any angle measurement which refers to the NACA 16 profile, each operating point of the profile working at the angle of attack α_k is obtained with the following translation:

$$\alpha_k = \alpha + \Delta\alpha \text{ where } \Delta\alpha = \alpha_{0k} - \alpha_0 \quad (1)$$

By this translation we ensure that the foil works at the same hydrodynamic condition, especially for what concerns the generated lift. It must be observed that this is true only if the lift dependence from the angle of attack α can be considered linear in the range of angles of attack studied and its slope can be approximated with that coming from the thin profile theory, i.e. the following relation is true:

$$C_L = 2\pi\alpha_l \quad (2)$$

Fig.9: Definition of velocity angles on the blade profile

4.2. Objective Function

Since the design goal is to include the major possible number of operating points inside the bucket, an objective function has been devised, in a way that its value increases each time an operating point is found inside the bucket. This definition comes out from a series of tests that showed the superior behaviour of this type of definition with respect to other even more elaborated *Ferrando et al. (2004)*. So, the objective function Eff used in the optimization examples presented hereinafter has following formula:

$$Eff = \sum_i \frac{dist_i}{\sigma_i} + P1 \quad \text{with} \quad dist_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sigma_i \geq -C_{Pi} \\ |C_{Pi}| - \sigma_i & \text{if } \sigma_i < -C_{Pi} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where Eff and $P1$ represent respectively the objective function value and the penalty to limit an excessive translation of the operating points according to the equation (1) previously defined.

$\sigma_i = \frac{p - p_v}{\frac{1}{2} \rho V_R^2}$ represents the cavitation index of profile at the considered operating point i .

C_{Pi} is the value read on the cavitation bucket of the profile at the angle of attack corresponding to the operating point i .

Each member of the sum in the objective function defined by (3) is divided by the cavitation index value of the correspondent working point, because the lower is this value the more important is to include this point inside the bucket. The penalty function that appears in (3) is expressed as follows:

$$P1 = \begin{cases} 2 \left[e^{(\Delta\alpha - \Delta\alpha_{lim})^2} - 1 \right] & \text{if } |\Delta\alpha| > \Delta\alpha_{lim} \\ 0 & \text{if } |\Delta\alpha| < \Delta\alpha_{lim} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

4.3. Results

During the optimization the procedure evaluates thousands of different geometric alternatives, in this way assuring a wide investigation over all the possible design solutions. Fig.10 presents an example of the history of the objective function value during the evolution of the optimization procedure. As it can be noted, the value of the function decreases rapidly in the first generation evaluated and reaches an asymptotic value after about 100/120 successive generations, after which the optimization procedure is stopped.

Fig.10: Objective function value vs. successive generations

The best individual found at the end of the differential evolution, is taken as the optimum profile. The two cases presented in this paragraph have been obtained for design problem defined in previous paragraphs following the two different design approaches described in paragraph 4, i.e. accepting (1st approach) or limiting (2nd approach) negative angles of attack at design operating condition of the profile. Obviously, if the definition of the objective function well interprets the meaning of the design goal, the bucket of the final optimum profile should include as many points as possible. Fig.11 compares the three buckets: two corresponding to the optimum profiles obtained with design approach 1 and design approach 2, and the third is that of the reference NACA 16 profile.

Fig.11: Performance of the two optimized solutions and the NACA 16

Fig.12: Optimized blade sections geometries (1st and 2nd design approach) and the NACA-16 profile

The foil obtained with the 2nd approach (*foil-2*) has in general a much wider cavitation bucket (especially for lower cavitation indexes) than the corresponding one of NACA 16. The different zero lift angle between the two profiles has the beneficial effect to improve the bubble cavitation margin, by shifting the operating points of the optimum profile towards lower operating angles of attack (with respect to the original operating points relative to the reference profile). On the other hand, some points result still outside the bucket, and some sheet cavitation is expected on the pressure side of the optimum profile working at these operating points. Overall, the profile obtained with the first approach (*foil-1*) is the best in terms of bucket width, but has a lesser margin for bubble cavitation,

which is the most damaging phenomenon for propeller blades. Incidentally, *foil-1* is also scoring the lowest value of the objective function, but with reference to its lower margin to bubble cavitation, from a design point of view, is not preferable against *foil-2*. In general, both optimized profiles have better performances than the reference NACA 16.

Foil-2 is preferable to *foil-1* also from a geometrical point of view, having a “more conventional” geometry than that of the other, so allowing an easier fairing with the rest of the blade surface. In fact, considering that the optimized section will be used in a portion of a blade geometry (usually already designed with conventional NACA profiles), a more homogeneity in the shape of the optimum profile can avoid dangerous pressure gradients along the radial direction on the blade surface, hence reducing the probability of generation of undesired cross flow effects.

5. Conclusion and Future Perspective

This paper describes the use of Differential Evolution algorithm coupled with a 2D panel method as a design tool for hydrofoil with delayed cavitation inception. The simple parameters used as basis for the optimization code and their immediate geometrical meaning makes this integrated system easy to be used for any particular propeller design problem. The presented approach solves many of the practical application problems encountered with other optimization methods, e.g. *Ferrando et al. (2004)*.

The consistency of the solution in terms of dynamic equivalence of the optimum profile with the design requirement (requested design lift), is granted by the shifting technique of the operating angles, included in the optimization procedure and described in the paper.

Having considered the viscous solution instead of that coming from a potential flow solver allows to reduce the differences which were found by other authors, *Viviani (2000)*, between experimentally measured performance and numerically predicted values. To validate the results of the predicted performance for the optimum foil with the viscous/inviscid method used in the design procedure, not being able to conduct specific model tests, the authors are used to simulate the final profile geometry with a RANSE solver. As an example, Fig.13 compares the lift coefficient – angle of attack curve predicted with the two CFD methods in the case of *foil-2* geometry. Except for the slight deviation noticeable at the higher angles of attack, the results obtained with the panel method corrected with viscous effect is very well correlated with those coming from the “exacter” RANSE solver.

Fig. 13 - Lift computed by panel method and a RANSE code for *foil-2*

The most difficult task for the user remains that of translating the physical design target in a scalar objective function depending on the geometry of the blade section. Different objective functions can be devised and adapted in order to cover a wide range of problems. The large number of foils evaluated by the optimization procedure assures the investigation of a wide range of solution with small calculation time (due to the panel method used as CFD solver). In fact, several hundreds of geometries are analyzed in an hour considering the viscous method, while the whole process, involving some thousands of trial geometries, can be executed in the same time if only the potential flow solver is used.

The aim for future works is to extend the optimization process to the whole blade, including the problem of fairing of the blade surface, which can lead to undesired cross flow phenomena, eventually resulting in a reduction of the propeller performance.

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Study of Scale Effects around Fully-Appended Ships with an Unstructured RANSE Solver

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Abstract

During the EFFORT (European Full-scale FLOW Research and Technology) european research project, two appended hull configurations have been simulated using unstructured grids composed exclusively of hexahedrons with local refinement. Numerical uncertainty is assessed with grid refinement and the influence of turbulence model and wall function approach have been investigated for one ship. Scale effect is also studied for the other configuration characterised by a higher geometric complexity. Numerical results are validated both with measurement data and with alternative computational results based on structured grids when possible.

1 Introduction

In spite of considerable progresses made during the last decade both in hardware and software development, the accurate prediction of turbulent flow around appended hull remains a challenging task. In addition to appropriate turbulence model, the success of a numerical simulation depends on the quality of the body-fitted grid employed for the computation. For a simple geometry, a good quality block-structured grid can be generated with available grid generation software, at least near the solid wall. However, for more complex geometries such as a hull with appendages, the generation of a good quality block-structured grid is not a trivial task and may take weeks of human time. Although unstructured tetrahedral grid can be easily generated for such complex geometry, most of the flow solvers employed in engineering applications such as those based on second order finite volume method are unable to give accurate numerical solution with such grids. Another efficient way to handle complex geometries is to use a Cartesian grid associated with the immersed boundary method. Although reasonable prediction for inviscid flow can be obtained, the accuracy of an immersed boundary method for turbulent flow especially at high Reynolds number remains to be demonstrated. Based on the Cartesian grid approach, recent grid generation softwares such as HARPOON and HEXPRESS offer the possibility to capture the viscous layer with body-fitted grid while maintaining the flexibility of the unstructured grid and the accuracy of hexahedral element. However, compared with conventional block-structured body-fitted grid, the viscous layer near the body surface is usually not well captured. In addition, it contains non-conformal elements in finite element sense. Furthermore, like all unstructured grid generators, the grid density in the computational domain is not well controlled. Hence, the accuracy of a numerical computation using such kind of grid needs to be evaluated. The present study is devoted to this issue. Effect of turbulence modelization will also be addressed. For a bare hull configuration, the most challenging task in turbulence modelization is the modelization of vortical flows due to the bilge vortex developed in the aft-part of the ship. A correct prediction of this phenomenon requires advanced turbulence models such as non-linear model or even Reynolds stress transport model, associated sometimes with empirical corrections. Additional vortical structures may appear when appendages are added, making the task of turbulence modelization even more challenging. The sensitivity to turbulence model as well as to the validation of wall function approach will be investigated.

2 The numerics

Computations are performed with the ISIS-CFD flow solver developed by EMN (Equipe Modlisation Numrique, i.e. CFD Department of the Fluid Mechanics Laboratory). Turbulent flow is simulated by solving the incompressible unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANSE). The solver is based on the finite volume method to build the spatial discretization of the transport equations. The

face-based method is generalized to two-dimensional, rotationally-symmetric, or three-dimensional unstructured meshes for which non-overlapping control volumes are bounded by an arbitrary number of constitutive faces. The velocity field is obtained from the momentum conservation equations and the pressure field is extracted from the mass conservation constraint, or continuity equation, transformed into a pressure-equation. In the case of turbulent flows, additional transport equations for modeled variables are discretized and solved using the same principles. Free-surface flow is simulated with a multi-phase flow approach. Incompressible and non-miscible flow phases are modeled through the use of conservation equations for each volume fraction of phase/fluid. Several turbulence models ranging from one-equation model to Reynolds stress transport model are implemented in ISIS-CFD. Most of the classical linear eddy-viscosity based closures like the Spalart-Allmaras one-equation model *Spalart and Allmaras (1991)*, the two-equation $k-\omega$ SST model by *Menter (1993)*, for instance are implemented. Two more sophisticated turbulence closures are also implemented in the ISIS-CFD solver, an explicit algebraic stress model (EASM) (*Deng et al. (2005)*) and a Reynolds stress transport model (*Duvigneau and Visonneau (2003)*).

3 The hopper-dredger “Uilenspiegel”

3.1 Description

The first test case is a hopper-dredger called Uilenspiegel built by IHC HOLLAND Dredgers BV. The geometry of the dredger Uilenspiegel is more complex than the frigate. In addition to all appendages present in the previous configuration except the sonar bulb, it also contains a nozzle and a triangular base (called headbox) that supports the nozzle and the rudder.

Fig.1: Uilenspiegel- Surface grid around the aftpart

Fig.1 shows the surface grid generated by HEXPRESS. It contains about 6 million nodes, among them about 340 000 are located on the hull. Computations have been performed at full scale ($Re = 1.03 \times 10^9$) and model scale (1:23.5, $Re = 8.27 \times 10^6$) with and without propeller. The free-surface flow is computed with a free-surface capturing strategy and the propeller action is modeled by a classical actuator disk approach. The coupling between the actuator disk and the the wake flow is made by updating at each time step the balance between the thrust of the propeller and the total drag of the ship. An additional computational time of about 20% compared to the duration of a computation without propeller is necessary to get a converged flowfield.

A magnified view is also provided by Fig.1 (right) to evaluate the level of representation of the discretised geometry around appendages and struts. One can underline the high level of refinement automatically achieved by HEXPRESS near the junction between the appendages and the hull.

3.2 Computations

3.2.1 Free-surface

The wave elevations are illustrated with Fig.2 which compares full scale (FS) and the model scale (MS) conditions and no dramatic differences can be qualitatively detected.

Fig.2: Uilenspiegel Normalized wave elevations

The corresponding 3D views are shown with Fig. 3(a). Details about the full scale bow wave region are presented with Fig. 3(b) where the wave breaking is clearly visible.

Fig.3: Uilenspiegel- 3D view of the free-surface

Fig. 4 provides a comparison of measured and computed model scale free-surface elevations at two transversal sections called, for confidentiality reasons, ProbeA and ProbeB. Although the mesh was not specifically refined in the horizontal directions, all the waves are captured by the computations at ProbeA and correctly positioned. The predicted bow-wave elevation is smaller than its measured counterpart but one can question the reliability of measurements in that region because of the occurrence of wave-breaking. At ProbeB, the same waves are present although more damped by the numerical diffusion as expected.

3.2.2 Wall streamlines

Figures 5 show the limiting wall streamlines of model scale free-surface flows with and without propeller. Due to computational resources limitations and for time saving, the air/water volume fraction for the simulation with propeller (WIP) is frozen to the field obtained without propeller (WOP), and, consequently, the influence of the propeller on the free-surface elevation near the stern cannot be analyzed here. However, one can observe the strong upstream influence of the ducted propeller on the near-wall flow and the drastic reduction of separated flow regions when the propeller is working. At model scale and without propeller, one can see the print of a very complex structure made of three longitudinal vortices visible from their focal prints near the intersection between the hull and the propeller shaft. When

Fig.4: **Uilenspiegel**- Model scale - Free-surface elevations at two transversal sections ProbeA and ProbeB (Symbols: experiments; Continuous line: ISIS-CFD computations)

the propeller is activated, one longitudinal vortex disappears and the two remaining ones seem to be partially sucked by the propeller. One can also notice that the wall flow on the propeller shaft is strongly influenced by the propeller, as expected.

Fig.5: **Uilenspiegel**- Model scale - Limiting wall streamlines with and without propeller

Figure 6 shows the limiting wall streamlines of full scale free-surface flows with and without propeller. One can observe again the strong upstream influence of the ducted propeller on the near-wall flow and the drastic reduction of separated flow regions when the propeller is operating. Compared to the computations performed at model scale (Fig. 6), the Reynolds number influence appears to be very significant since, even without propeller, the three focal points related with the strong longitudinal vortices emanating close to the intersection between the propeller shaft and the hull, have totally disappeared. This

Fig.6: **Uilenspiegel**- Full scale - Limiting wall streamlines with and without propeller

noticeable influence of Reynolds number on the flow topology will have a strong impact on the isowake distribution in sections located in front of the ducted propeller, as it will be shown later.

Case	Cp	Cf	Ct
MS:WOP	0.00359	0.00318	0.00677
MS:WIP	0.00391	0.00332	0.00723
FS:WOP	0.00361	0.00169	0.00530
FS:WIP	0.00277	0.00173	0.00449

Table I: Resistance prediction for the Uilenspiegel (MS: model scale, FS: full scale, WOP: without propeller, WIP: with propeller)

3.2.3 Force coefficients

Resistance results are summarized in Table I. A grid dependency study has not been performed for this test case. At model scale, unlike the previous case, the viscous resistance at model scale without propeller agrees well with the ITTC 1957 estimation (0.00318 compared with $C_{f0}=0.00310$). This may be due to the fact that the surface of appendages represents only about 1.2% of the total wetted surface. Hence, the influence of appendages on viscous resistance is limited. At full scale, the predicted viscous resistance for the case without propeller $C_f=0.00169$ is 10% higher than the ITTC 1957 estimation $C_{f0}=0.00153$. This is a usual observation in full scale computations. What is somewhat unexpected is that the pressure resistance is reduced at full scale when the propeller is in action, while it is increased at model scale. This behavior can be explained by the fact that aft-body flow structures are quite different in model scale and in full scale as illustrated in Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 6(b) where the predicted wall streamlines at model and full scale, respectively, are shown with the influence on the vortical structures of the suction related with the propeller effect. A multiple vortex structure is present in model scale simulation which interacts with the nozzle and the rudder, while these vortices disappear or become very weak in full scale. Experimental visualization confirms the existence of the multiple vortex structures predicted at model scale. As indicated in the previous section, the activation of the propeller modifies considerably those structures, resulting in the above-mentioned variation in Cp.

Fig.7: Uilenspiegel- With propeller - Scale influence on the isowakes at station 1

3.2.4 Scale effects

With the following results, it is possible to carry out a study of the scale influence on the isowake distribution in the vicinity of the ducted propeller. Figures 7 to 9 show the isowake contours at model and full scale with propeller. As indicated previously, the scale effect is clearly visible on the respective boundary layer thicknesses. Figure 7 shows again the acceleration of the flow in the region located between

the propeller shaft and the hull, a phenomena which is illustrated by the wall streamlines at full scale. In Fig. 8, one can see that the vortical structure which is convected between the V-brackets at model scale has somewhat disappeared at full scale and the longitudinal velocity component seems to be more homogeneous below the propeller shaft at full scale. The same remark applies to Fig. 9.

Fig.8: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - Scale influence on the isowakes at station 2

Fig.9: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - Scale influence on the isowakes at station 3

Finally, Fig. 10 shows the longitudinal evolution of the isowakes viewed from inside a transparent hull at model and full scale. The scale effect on the isowake distribution is clearly visible on this figure which confirms the previous analysis.

To conclude this brief analysis of scale effects, Fig. 11 and 12 show the secondary streamlines at model and full scale for two sections called WinDE and WinAC for which experimental results described in the next part of the article, are available. At model scale, one can notice the strong longitudinal vortex emanating from the junction between the propeller shaft and the hull which is clearly visible at section WinDE and convected and diffused downwind at section WinAC. The situation is totally different at full scale where Fig.12 does not show any longitudinal vortex near the propeller shaft. However, a small vortex attached to the propeller shaft is captured in the full scale computations and hardly visible at model scale.

Fig.10: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - 3D views of the longitudinal evolution of the isowakes between the propeller shaft and the hull

Fig.11: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - Secondary streamlines at section WinDE

Fig.12: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - Secondary streamlines at section WinAC

3.2.5 Comparisons with model scale experiments

PIV model-scale experiments with operating propellers were carried out by the Polish Ship Design and Research Center (Centrum Techniki Okretowej, Gdansk, Poland) within the EFFORT consortium at

a section called WinDE which is not located precisely for confidentiality reasons but corresponds to the same location used for the full scale measurements. Figures 13 provide global views of computed isowakes and secondary velocities at this measurement section and the rectangular zone indicates precisely the PIV window for which measurements are provided in Figures 14 and 15.

(a) Isowake distribution

(b) Secondary velocities distribution

Fig.13: **Uilenspiegel- WinDE** - Global views of isowake and secondary velocities distribution at model scale with propeller. The rectangular zone indicates the PIV measurement window

In Figures 13, one can observe a region of low longitudinal velocity between the hull and the propeller shaft. The strong distortion of the isowakes between the shaft and the hull is associated with the presence of a clockwise longitudinal vortex.

(a) Model scale experiments with propeller

(b) Model scale SST computations with propeller

Fig.14: **Uilenspiegel- WinDE** - Comparison on the isowake distribution between model scale PIV experiments and ISIS-CFD computations at section WinDE

Figures 14 show a comparison between PIV measurements and computations in the rectangular region indicated above. The white rectangle located in the prolongation of the propeller shaft corresponds to a region where no measurements are available since the PIV setup is located in the right part of this figure. The global agreement between experiments and computations is very satisfactory since the distortion of the isowakes and the shape of the low speed region between the shaft and the hull is well reproduced by this blind simulation.

Figures 15 show the secondary velocity distribution in the same rectangular region. The existence of a clockwise longitudinal vortex is confirmed by the experiments and one can observe that the location and

(a) Model scale experiments

(b) Model scale SST computations

Fig.15: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - WinDE - Comparison on the secondary velocity distribution between model scale PIV experiments and ISIS-CFD computations at section WinDE

the intensity of this vortical structure is well predicted by the computations.

3.2.6 Comparisons with full scale experiments

A major part of the european research project EFFORT was devoted to sea trials to get accurate full-scale measurements at several longitudinal sections. This part is devoted to a comparison of ISIS-CFD computations with the experimental isowake distribution at two different sections for Windows D & E and Windows A & C which will not be explicitly located for confidentiality reasons.

Figures 16 show the mesh density and the flow field at section WinDE. This section is the same as the one shown at model scale. Although not coarse, this unstructured mesh already comprised of about 6 million nodes should be refined in the vicinity of the appendices. A grid dependency study would be welcome but unfortunately impossible to carry out on the available national computational facilities.

(a) Mesh density

(b) Isowakes

Fig.16: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - WinDE - Global view of the mesh density and the computed full scale flow at section WinDE

Figures 17 show a comparison of experimental and computed isowakes at windows D and E, located between the hull and the propeller shaft. Compared to the similar results shown in the previous section at model scale, one can observe that the isowake distortion is less pronounced at full scale, indicating a less intense longitudinal vorticity in that region. Moreover, the mean value of the longitudinal component of

the velocity between the hull and the propeller shaft is around $0.45 U_{ref}$ at full scale when it is about $0.10 U_{ref}$ at model scale. This observation confirms the huge difference between model and full scale flows already observed on the topology of the near-wall flow discussed before. This scale effect is accurately predicted by ISIS-CFD which provides computational isowakes in very good agreement with the sea measurements although computed with a standard $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model.

Fig.17: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - WinDE - Comparison on the isowake distribution between full scale experiments and ISIS-CFD computations at windows D & E

Figures 18 show the mesh density and the flow behavior at another section called WinAC located closer to the propeller nozzle but before the struts supporting the shaft and the nozzle. One can see the upwind influence of the struts illustrated by the distortion of the isowakes which is more pronounced than in the previous examined section.

Fig.18: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - WinAC - Global view of the mesh density and the full scale computed flow at section WinAC

As previously, Figures 19 show a comparison between the full scale experiments and the computations at windows A and C. Window C, located on the right handside of the figure shows the thick boundary layer developing outside of the propeller shaft. The agreement between computations and experiments is very good. Window A shows a more complex flow located between the hull and the shaft. Both experiments and computations reveal a distorted region of decelerated longitudinal flow with a mean value of $0.6 U_{ref}$ for the experiments and a slightly more pronounced deceleration in the computations with a mean value around $0.55 U_{ref}$.

Fig.19: **Uilenspiegel**- With propeller - WinAC - Comparison on the isowake distribution between full scale experiments and ISIS-CFD computations at windows A and C

Case	Loaded(CD1)	Empty(CD2)
Water depth	13.5 m	Infinite
Lpp	111.4 m	111.4 m
Draught at App	8.55 m	6.6 m
Draught at Fpp	9.55 m	1.7 m
Ship speed	6.482 m/s	8.231 m/s
Froude number	0.196	0.2490

Table II: **IHC-co1246**- Summary of ship characteristics

4 Dredger in loaded and empty conditions

4.1 Description

This second test case concerns a new dredger built by IHC HOLLAND Dredgers BV and referenced here as IHC co 1246. For this hull, full scale flow is considered with working propeller and free surface under two conditions: loaded (CD1) configuration with shallow water and an empty (CD2) condition in deep water. For both cases, the hull has a prescribed constant speed and draught as listed with Table II.

4.2 Numerical details

Simulation is conducted so that the predicted wake field must be predicted with sufficient quality to enable the possibility for proper propeller design. Since complexity of the geometry is similar to the the previous one including nozzled propeller whith attached headbox and rudder, the overall methodology for meshing and computing retains the parameters successfully adopted on the Uilenspiegel case in full scale situation.

All geometries have been meshed using the HEXPRESS grid generator. The computational domain concerns only one half portion of the ship: it is a rectangular box of size $[-500\text{m},500\text{m}] \times [0,500\text{m}] \times [-13.5\text{m} \times 8\text{m}]$ for (CD1) and $[-500\text{m},350\text{m}] \times [0,500\text{m}] \times [-200\text{m} \times 8\text{m}]$ for (CD2). For all configurations, the highest vertical resolution for free surface capturing is $dZ=5\text{cm}$. Grid resolution at the walls is such that the normalized y^+ distance is about 300. Details of the grids are summarized in Table III. Nomenclature is such that AH means “Appended Hull”, BH means “Bare Hull”. Details about the surface grid for CD1

Case	Number of CV	Number of wall faces	Number of processors
CD1(AH)	5,863,105	194,197	40
CD1(BH)	4,836,832	133,703	32
CD2(AH)	3,997,407	136,092	26
CD2(BH)	2,738,039	081,044	18

Table III: **IHC-co1246**- Summary of grids for studied configurations

are plotted with Fig. 20(b) for the appendices, and the explicit mesh refinement specified around the mean water level is clearly visible with Fig. 20(a).

Fig.20: **IHC-co1246** (CD1) - Surface grid around the aftpart

4.3 Results

Wave profile along the hull and the symmetry plane are plotted in Figs. 21 for the two conditions. Although not illustrated, it is observed that the propeller influence is highest with empty case (CD2) than with the loaded one (CD1).

Fig.21: **IHC-co1246**- Wave profiles

Flow field results are simply presented from limiting streamlines on the walls and plotted in stern region from a symmetry plane point of view: Figs. 22 for the loaded condition (CD1) and Figs. 22 for the empty condition (CD2), both with comparison for propeller in operation (**WIP**) or not (**WOP**).

For loaded conditions in finite depth (CD1), the separation near the symmetry plane and before the transom appears amplified when propeller is running. From the point of view of dredger builder, due to propeller suction and lack of water in front (in relation to that suction demand), the propeller obtains its needs from behind and trying to avoid this phenomenon in shallow water should be a progress.

Fig.22: IHC-co1246 (CD1) - Wall streamlines

For empty condition in deep water (CD2), the propeller suction cancels the small separation zone observed on the hull, just behind the headbox and no separation is detected from streamlines near the transom with/without propeller.

5 Conclusions

Two complex appended hull configurations have been investigated in the present study. By making most of grid generation steps fully automatic, the unstructured grid generator HEXPRESS leads to a reduction of the mesh generation time from weeks to two or three days compared to more classical block-structured meshers. This evolution makes now possible RANSE computations for industrial configurations of arbitrary geometric complexity on a routine basis. The accuracy of an unstructured finite-volume method on grids made exclusively of hexahedrons with local refinement is now under systematic evaluation in our CFD group (see *Deng et al. (2006)* for our recent studies conducted with manufactured solutions). On one hand, the use of hexahedric control volumes and the fact that the surface discretization is automatically very dense, which reduces the aspect ratio of the cells, are very beneficial for the overall numerical accuracy of the discrete solution since sources of error due to misalignment and non-orthogonality are eliminated in most parts of the mesh. The weak point is the local loss of accuracy near the locally refined faces where misalignment and non-orthogonality are very high and reduce the local accuracy to first order at best with the actual flux reconstruction schemes implemented in ISIS-CFD. The improvement of the gradient reconstruction at such faces is now a high priority task to take advantage of the flexibility provided by such locally refined grids.

As expected, the computation of flows around complex hulls with appendages becomes more challenging for numerical simulation. The performance of the ISIS-CFD code has also been demonstrated in a

Fig.23: **IHC-co1246** (CD2) - Wall streamlines

computation at model and full scale for the hopper-dredger Uilenspiegel which is a fully appended hull configuration including free-surface, ducted propeller, brackets and rudder. The agreement between the blind computations and model and full scale experiments is very satisfactory and seems to indicate that CFD tools may be used with confidence for the design of complex ship hulls in full scale conditions. A complete analysis of the scale effects on free-surface and on the structure of the viscous stern flow reveals that these scale effects are not negligible and depend strongly on the stern geometries, making a computational approach mandatory at full scale. For this second test case, a systematic grid convergence analysis, although probably less critical for these locally refined grids, should be performed in the future to assess the computational results. Moreover, an additional study of the influence of turbulence modelling should be necessary to evaluate the influence of turbulence closures for these fully-appended ship wake flows.

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Workflow Support for Ship Development Projects

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Abstract

Due to the continuously increasing competition in the shipbuilding industry with strong cost pressure, an efficient ship production is required. Especially made-to-order product development projects in shipbuilding are very complex as a result of simultaneous design, fabrication and assembly, which leads to the need of an extensive planning and coordination of processes during the whole project. In contrast to the well planned and structured fabrication and assembly, the design processes at a shipyard can still be improved for a better coordination, process overview and less inconsistencies. In order to achieve this, a new approach for coordination and control of development processes is essential. Workflow management is an approach to coordinate processes that has been used in other industries like the banking sector for many years. This article evaluates possible application areas for workflow management in product development processes in the shipbuilding industry from the project management point of view. For this purpose, tasks and processes of a development project are characterized and categorized to generic process types. Based on this, a model for individual workflow support for each process type is developed. A flexible approach for workflow management in product development based on workflow modules will then be derived. Supported by predefined workflow modules, it is possible to configure and adapt the many different processes and their variants even during project runtime in a flexible way. Furthermore, design and usage of these workflow modules are explained. Finally, the interdependencies between workflow and other development support systems (e.g. project management system) will be displayed.

1. Introduction

In the shipbuilding industry with high cost pressure ships have to be developed and fabricated very efficiently in order to survive in competition. Nevertheless, the shipbuilding's project management is mainly focussed on the fabrication and assembly processes. Design processes are often neither planned nor supported or controlled in detail, so that there exists a risk for delays or errors. For remaining competitive, an active coordination even of design processes is required for a successful project management. In the following, workflow management is introduced as tool for coordinating ship development processes in detail. Based on an analysis of today's project management the workflow management concepts are adapted to the requirements of development.

2. Management of ship development projects

In this chapter ship development projects are analyzed from the project management point of view. First, the current situation of managing development projects in shipyards is presented based on an analysis of several German shipyards. Afterwards existing approaches for process coordination in development projects are introduced.

2.1 Process coordination in shipbuilding industry

The development and fabrication of ships requires strong efforts for coordinating different departments in order to complete the ship on time in the desired quality while not exceeding the planned costs. In this context, an extensive project management is needed for project planning, coordination and control of design and fabrication processes. Due to the fact that European ships are mostly made-to-order products with simultaneous design, fabrication and assembly and that shipyards take increasingly the role as system integrator, coordination of processes in project management is getting more and more a key success factor for an efficient production.

Nevertheless, project management for the shipbuilding project as a whole plays a secondary role in shipbuilding industry. Studies in the most important Germany shipyards had the result that projects are managed by a small project team with no managerial authority in the operational departments. In most cases, the organizational structures and several simultaneously occurring ship building projects allow no identification with a certain project while information about the project's status quo is only rarely provided by the project management team. As consequence, outstanding efforts have to be made to supply the staff with project relevant information like deadlines for work packages and to coordinate processes.

But while planning and process control of the fabrication and assembly can be characterized as well planned and structured, retaining enough flexibility to respond to short-term changes and problems, design processes are not in focus of the project's management. In fabrication and assembly the bandwidth of support systems for detailed work package planning and monitoring range from sophisticated Excel spreadsheets to product planning and control and process simulation systems, *Wagner (2006)*. In contrast, design processes are only regarded on a very rough milestone-level and are mostly not supported by any management software at all. An exception is the monitoring of some important engineering drawings on low level in respect of degree of completion (e.g. steel plan, general arrangement plan) in the product data management system. Besides this, design processes are neither modelled nor monitored and controlled in a management system. Fig.1 shows the use of tools for managing ship building projects. By considering the complex design processes in a very tight project plan and the 2000-3000 design changes per ship that have to be handled additionally to the plan, this approach seems to be incomprehensible.

Fig.1: Tools for managing ship building projects

Thus, the lack of managing design processes on higher levels, e.g. on work package level, makes it difficult to rate dependencies on other processes, to control them regarding deadlines and content and to provide staff with the required information. Design processes with their large quantity of interdependencies and simultaneous tasks can therefore be characterized as mostly unmanaged which leads to higher consumption of development time as well as development costs. A large potential for improving the project in respect of better coordination, process overview and less inconsistencies therefore exists so that new approach for managing and coordinating ship design processes is needed. Such an approach is provided by workflow management.

2.2 Characteristics of Workflow Management

Workflow management has been used in the banking sector for many years and is lately more and more implemented in development processes of the automotive sector. It can be defined as computer supported management and coordination of processes with help of a digital process model. Workflow management systems execute these process models by allocating tasks to users and by evoking software applications and data needed in the current work step, *Hollingsworth (1997)*.

In practice, workflow users use a worklist-client, where all tasks for the user are displayed. For each task script code is programmed, stored in the workflow model and executed by effecting the task. This launches applications and loads data, e.g. into input masks, so that it is possible to use the integrative functions of the workflow management system to provide relevant work information to the user. Time-consuming and error-prone search for information as well as the so called application hopping (switching between different programs while accomplishing a work step) can though be avoided and fast and efficient work processing is possible, *Nedeß (2003)*.

In this classic field of application, it is the intention to improve productivity of staff. By providing data and applications to the user and via the electronic process routing, throughput, handling and search time can be reduced up to 90%, *Erdl and Schönecker (1995)*. Fig.2 shows the functionality and potentials of workflow management.

Fig.2: Functionality and potentials of workflow management

In order to build such a workflow application, workflows have to be modelled and programmed on a very detailed level, so that the exact process and all relevant data and applications have to be defined. As a result, it takes high effort to model and program a workflow application so that workflow management systems are often only used for high-volume processes, where an extensive automation is needed. Workflow management thus provides an approach to manage and control certain processes and to increase their productivity. In product development however, it is more important to coordinate the project as a whole than to improve single processes. Additionally, development processes are considered as creative work, where an exact procedure cannot be defined. Due to this reason, workflow management systems are despite of their advantages considered as not applicable in product development, *Paetzold (2004)*.

A product development project though consists even of other tasks than the creative work, e.g. more formal processes like documentation or structured change processes so that a generalized conclusion about that cannot be derived. Furthermore, workflow management systems' functionality is affected by key users of the banking and insurance sector. By considering the product development's different functional requirements and the different goals in developing a suitable workflow solution, it could be a powerful tool for coordinating processes even in development projects. This is underlined by the many approaches in literature in respect of workflow management in development and in project management.

2.3 Approaches for Workflow management in development

Even though there is a strong demand for active process coordination, project management tools mainly provide functions for planning the project plan, the resources and costs. Project execution is not or only rudimentary supported, *Jäger (2002)*. In order to provide the project staff the right information and to improve communication flows in a project, project platforms are discussed in literature approaches, lately also in domain of ship development with the SHINCOS platform, *Bronsart (2005)*. With help of such web-based platforms, data exchange and errorless information flows can be achieved and is therefore the right basis for project management in shipbuilding. However, the active coordination of processes, that is partly implemented there for basic change management, can still be improved and expanded to other processes.

In order to achieve such an extension, workflow management systems are used to improve the standard project management applications by executing the project plan, *Leymann et. al. (2000)*, *Maurer et. al. (2000)*. Although this coupling can improve process coordination in general due to active assignment of tasks, this is not the right approach for product development. In the practice of very large development projects with thousands of detail processes, project plans or GANTT charts are used as rough planning tools on the level of main components (e.g. assembly of main engine), in shipbuilding mainly for fabrication and assembly operations, and no detailed process sequences are defined. Project plans can therefore from the practical point of view of large shipbuilding projects not be used as planning tool for the execution of workflows. They provide rather a framework for defining due dates and dependencies for work packages that can be used for much more detailed processes.

Approaches that focus more the workflow use in large development projects, e.g. in the automotive industry, rely on improvements of IT-solutions in the subject of workflow and project management. This can for example contain coupling architectures of project management planning tools with workflow execution systems, *Bauer (2004)*, or improvements in the workflow execution model, *Beuter (2002)*. These are definitely very important approaches needed for developing workflow support for development projects, but through isolated optimization of computer systems or the integration into the company environment there cannot be completely verified how workflow management can be used in the domain of product development. A lack in existing approaches is that besides technical solutions, possible fields of application of workflow support are hardly in focus. Therefore an analysis of the project's processes and a deduction how workflow management can be used to support these processes in development projects has to be done before finding deep technical solutions.

3. Concept for Workflow management in product development

3.1 Process and workflow types in development

For developing a specific workflow support for product development projects, all occurring tasks and process types have to be considered. Contrary to common opinion, product development consists not only of creative work but for a big part also of formal processes like approval or report processes. Beside this more formal characteristic of engineering tasks, there exist also project management,

commercial and administrative processes in a development project, that have a direct influence on the projects' success. Caused by that high amount of different processes with different characters, a global statement about application of workflow management systems in development projects is not possible. Before judging about it, there has thus to be analyzed what sort of processes can be found in development projects and how they fit to the workflow managements requirements.

As it is not possible to analyze all processes of development projects, representative process types have to be developed so that they can be tested instead of them. Gilbreth classified human movements into 18 basic elements like pick, drop or hold, *Ferguson (2000)*, which was later enhanced to the MTM (Methods-Time-Measurement) method and can be used to configure all movements and assembly processes. This basic idea has to be transferred to office processes to develop such basic task or process elements for the development.

In order to achieve this, a ship development project can be separated into the process domains

- Engineering processes
- project management processes
- commercial processes
- administrative processes and
- management processes in fabrication

Based on the approach of Blessing, *Blessing (1994)*, who developed process types for engineering in regard to construction tasks, the following more comprehensive basic task elements, so called process types, can be derived and defined from example processes. Those process types can be described with help of process attributes and differ in their characteristics. Fig.3 shows the process types with examples.

Fig.3: Process types in development projects

Process types cover the complete variety from very unstructured tasks to very formal procedures. On the one hand, there occur creative, unstructured development processes like for example the conceptual design with no predefined sequence of activities or responsibilities and as well unknown required data and support tools. On the other hand, the so called execution processes are very structured what means that the particular activity steps, involved persons and needed information and tools for work processing can be defined in advance so that the process just has to be executed. An

example for an execution process is the handling of a test procedure (e.g. accreditation of a product) with defined, standardized steps. Between these two extreme examples numerous nuances of process types occur.

It is clear that such differing process types cannot be supported by the same sort of workflow management so that it has therefore to be adapted to the needs of each process type. For some process types like execution processes, a deeper workflow management support is possible and advantageously. Unstructured processes in contrast need more degrees of freedom in work processing.

In order to meet the process requirements, a model of differentiated levels of workflow management was developed by varying the parameters of workflow applications. This model contains five steps from elementary workflow routing without many additional features to sophisticated workflows with complete automation. With help of these different shades of workflow management, each of the process types can be considered in an individual way.

The different workflow levels differ in the parameters

- level of details of workflow modelling
- depth of integration of applications and data and
- the user's degree of freedom in work processing

On the basic level called 'workflow routing', notifications of begin of work packages are only routed via a process model to the adequate user. The workflow system is not involved in the work processing at all so that applications have to be started and used as usual. Additional to this work package start notification, advices and tips concerning the particular tasks are attached. Through this simplified way of workflow management, a basic coordination on rough level with monitoring of work can be achieved while there is only a little effort needed for modelling the workflows. On the next level, 'workflow processing support', the workflow is modelled on a deeper level and tasks are linked with needed data what leads to higher transparency and lower error rate. The user is still free to work in the way he wants.

The level 'workflow piloting' contains a partly integration of applications and data with the goal to relieve the user of inconvenient but necessary work by providing standard functions and semi-automation of applications. The main task is not affected by this and only additional actions are supported. Through this, the potential of workflow management can be used while the engineering way of working is not too much restricted. An example for this could be an automated check out and lock of product data in the product data management system.

The workflow level 'semi-automation' is equivalent to common workflow applications e.g. in the banking sector. Processes are modeled on the very detailed level of subtasks, needed applications are called and controlled by the workflow system and data is collected automatically from different databases and provided to the user. Here is hence nearly no degree of freedom in work processing left as the workflow system leads the user through his work. By this, a reduction of work processing time and throughput time of the whole process can be achieved, but flexibility is reduced to zero and programming effort for such a workflow is very high. On the highest level of workflow management called 'workflow automation', no user interaction or process flexibility is possible anymore. Workflows are completely processed by the workflow system, e.g. for creating reports or filing data. Fig.4 illustrates the five levels of workflow management for product development.

The different process types can now be assigned to the levels of workflow management for an individual process support. In this manner, workflow management can be used for more kinds of processes, even if they do not fit to the classic process requirements of workflow management (rigid high-volume processes). Of course a basic structure of a process is needed, because otherwise no modeling into a computer based workflow model is possible. In creative development processes, that are often equated with development processes in general, the process cannot be specified in detail in

advance due to the flexible working methods of engineers and frequent changes in product specifications. The process does hence not follow specific rules. Nevertheless, process routing along different work packages with planned due dates and attached information will lead to more transparency and better overview as well as to a more structured proceeding. The characteristic of these creative work matches very well to the workflow level “workflow routing”.

Fig.4: Levels of workflow management

In contrast, execution processes need besides the process routing also support for the detailed work steps themselves for working as efficient and fast as possible in those processes, that are often affecting the whole project. A check and release procedure of an development step and the following information of affected users for example has to be done as fast as possible so that the complex project plan with mutual influencing work packages is not disturbed. An automated supply and preparation of the information and data to be checked and an automated generation of documentation and release would though make the process faster, more efficient and less error-prone. The reduced degree of freedom in work processing is in this case no problem as standardized check routines have to be fulfilled and documented. Fig.4 shows examples for assigning process types to workflow levels.

Thus, basic functions of workflow management like an active process routing, information providing and monitoring possibilities can be used to manage and to support a development project. Additional features can additionally be used for some processes to make work easier and more efficient. The application of workflow management in product development thus requires a totally different concept in comparison to common use.

Even though the adequate functionality of workflow management for different process types has been developed, the technical modeling concept has to be adapted to deal with the high amount of processes in development projects.

3.2 Module based workflow management

In today’s workflow applications, a limited number of processes is modelled and programmed with high effort by process and computer experts as workflow, compiled to the workflow server and can

then be executed by the users. There is thus a division into modelling phase and use phase. This approach is not applicable in development projects as there exists a very big number of processes to coordinate with the workflow management system. In addition, not every process can be specified in advance and therefore not be modelled as workflow. Because of that, a new concept for workflow creation has to be developed.

3.2.1 Module based workflow approach

Due to the many variants of processes in development and the problems to specify all processes in advance, workflows in product development have to be modelled during the project. This approach would cause capacity and time problems if workflows would have to be created by programmers or competence problems when delegating this work to the workflow users, thus the engineers and other project staff. Workflow users usually do not have neither expert knowledge in process modelling or programming nor detailed knowledge of the process as a whole. Therefore a simple solution is needed, that supports on the one hand all variants of processes and requires only rough product and project knowledge to create a workflow.

By using a modular design principle of workflows it is possible to avoid pre-modelling before the start of the project and the need of owning modelling knowledge. The modular system is based on the idea, that small workflow modules are pre-programmed by experts in advance and just have to be combined during runtime of the development project by the users. Key words help them to find the right modules and case-based reasoning algorithms allow them to check which combinations of workflow modules have been used in past projects.

The construction set of workflow modules consists of three different module types:

- process modules (containing sequences of tasks and activities)
- application controlling modules (script code to call and control applications) and
- data object modules (links to needed data and information or attached documents)

These modules can easily be combined by drag and drop and specified by individual information in order to create a new workflow instance for the current situation. This set of workflow modules remains flexible during runtime so that modules can be added or replaced. Fig.5 shows the concept of flexible combination of workflow modules in comparison to common modelling.

Fig.5: Modeling concepts of workflow management

3.2.2 Design and usage of the workflow modules

With help of the workflow modules, it is on the one hand possible to define standard workflows for different situations, that can be adapted in detail for the specific situation and on the other hand to configure completely new workflows from single- or multi-activity-modules. The advantage in comparison to modelling from the scratch is the reduction of the workflow modelling competencies to a minimum as for configuration only knowledge about the product and on a basic level about the project and the process is needed.

The configuration is done in a workflow client with graphical user interface. Users with the adequate rights to instantiate workflows are able to open the configurator where all the workflow modules can be found and composed to new workflows. In order to find the right workflow modules during configuration even without detailed process knowledge, a module classification via attributes is required. The attribution has to follow the competencies of the users what means that they can find matching modules by using their specific knowledge. These are mainly attributes corresponding to product knowledge (e.g. modules matching a specific ship type) or task specific attributes (e.g. modules matching a specific task like designing). For filtering the modules during workflow configuration so that only modules matching to the current situation are available, the module's attributes have to be compared with selections of the user in a mask where the current situation is specified via combo boxes. For the reduced list of suitable workflow modules, additional metadata can be displayed via click so that the right choice will be easier.

By using this sort of configuration in different development projects, experience about how to configure modules in future development projects can be collected. Especially for processes that occur very often like change processes in ship design, it is possible to derive standard processes and often occurring variants and store them in a workflow library. For deriving these standard processes as well as for configuration of workflow modules, case based reasoning is a suitable method. With the principle of transformational reuse, previous combinations of workflow modules are completely or partly reused or adapted to the new case. The adaptation is done by using modified parameters, substitution of one or more modules or by manually changing workflow and programm script.

In practical use, a list of former used combinations is shown with an indicator how similar the two compared situations are. In addition, performance indicators of the workflow like the throughput time or a rating made by a responsible person indicates, if a module was a good choice or not can be stored and analyzed so that experiences of the module use can be included. In this way, repetitive errors in workflow configuration can be avoided and improved step-by-step.

In case of a new configuration of workflow modules, it begins with the definition of the task sequence by joining process modules whereas they can consist of single activities or larger modules with several activities (e.g. a standardized loop for approval) composed to a sequence. The complete sequence has to be complemented with application controlling modules and data object modules to a complete workflow application. With help of compatibility matrices only modules that fit together are displayed. For semi-automated workflows of the level four, it is necessary to test the functionality of application controlling, because parameter passing between modules is difficult. Mechanisms for automatic consistency check still have to be developed. Fig.6 shows the principle of workflow configuration with modules.

Fig.6: Principle of configuring workflows with modules

3.3 Interaction between workflow and project management

After having developed a module-based modelling solution as basis for the application of workflow management in product development projects, it is now necessary to integrate the solutions into a project management tool.

As project management tools in shipbuilding are usually not used to manage the whole project but only fabrication and assembly and information flow to users especially in engineering in design is fragmentary, the implementation of a centralized project and communication platform that integrates data, project and information management seems to be indicated. The SHINCOS-platform, *Bronsart (2005)*, as well as modern integrated product development or PLM platforms are a very good basis for a comprehensive project management in shipbuilding industry. They provide a centralized information basis for all kinds of project staff with the focus on information pull. For an active process management with information push, system-supported monitoring of development processes and work processing support, the basic workflow functionality of these platforms has to be enhanced in respect of the developed workflow management approach.

Due to the use of the workflow management as additional coordination tool to the project management functionality, the interaction between them and responsibility for certain tasks have to be defined for a successful management of the development project as a whole. A parallelized use of workflow and project management functionality without link between them would lead inevitably to inconsistencies.

Project management provides methods and functionality to manage processes on a very rough level while workflow management is able to manage them in detail. It is thus a good idea to plan a project with the project management functionality of the ship development platform and to create by this a framework with due dates and required work results for the detailed execution of processes. The execution and detailed process coordination should be done in the workflow management system because of its numerous functions to coordinate processes and to support and automate work steps.

For executing processes with help of a workflow system, information about the time schedule and

project structure, especially about due dates, are needed, which have to be imported from the project plan. In order to reduce complexity and integration effort, the data exchange is limited to

- start and end dates of work packages
- consistency checks (is a workflow executable in the desired period in respect of due dates and available resources?) and
- completion notification of a workflow or of a process result (e.g. go / no go in an approval process)

Fig.7: Interaction between workflow and project management

From the technical point of view, the workflow system accesses the project management database and queries the required data as well as it writes data in certain data fields. A deeper system integration between project and workflow management functionality in terms of a totally integrated project platform would indeed be a nice feature, but it is not necessary for supporting work coordination and monitoring development processes. It would rather increase the programming effort for the platform solution and reduce flexibility in project execution. This can be made clear on the example of a change process which is the trigger for replanning the project. An automated adaptation of the project plan and the automated start of replanning and controlling actions is not appropriate, because a proper appraisal of the consequences cannot be described by rigid rules. The workflow support is thus an additional feature for managing the development processes in detail, but further interactions should be done manually. Fig.7 shows the architecture of the project platform and the interaction between the components.

4. Coordinating ship development processes with workflows

The concept ideas for workflow management in ship development projects have been prototypical implemented in a workflow solution that is based on the workflow management standard software COSA BPM. It has an open and expandable architecture and was enhanced by means of programming a workflow application in java, which provides the required functionality for workflow use in development projects. In the following, the use of workflow management modules is shown for the example of an engineering change management process.

Project- and product data management platforms like SHINCOS or commercial tools like PTC Windchill provide an integrated web interface with portal technology. The project can here be planned on a low detailed level and has functionality in respect of milestone management and project performance monitoring via “traffic lights”. Here the workflow management tool is intended to support the project’s processes even on a more detailed level. At the moment, the workflow solution is an extra tool but in future it will be provided as a plug-in in order to be integrated in such platforms.

In a development project there can be differentiated between planned and unplanned processes. This example of an engineering change process is an unplanned process, which can occur when either a customer has a principle change request of a system or design solution (about 20-30 times per year during ship development for the example of a marine vessel) or due to internal issues which lead to design changes (about 3000 times during ship development). It is very important to perform the process as fast as possible in order to avoid negative interaction with other work packages or delays as well as to document the whole change process for later audit track. As unplanned process, there has to be worked on this process additionally to the existing very tight project plan, which mostly cannot be adapted to this new situation. In order to process the tasks as efficient as possible, it is important to provide the required information to the user in a concentrated way so that start-up-time for the task and the processing-time itself are reduced.

With help of the workflow configurator, the change process, that consists of different request, operative processing, documentation and approval steps can be configured from predefined modules (here called proclerts). In order to find the right workflow modules the current project has to be specified by the user, in this case a member of the project management team, so that only suitable proclerts for the current situation are offered by filtering the proclert database. This is done by selecting key words to from combo boxes that are linked as attributes to proclerts. Fig.8 shows the workflow composer, where attributes for the project and the product, e.g. ship type and customer have been selected. The matching workflow modules are displayed in a list. As the name of such a workflow module provides not sufficient information for configuration, metadata is displayed when clicking on a module name. The metadata consists besides others of descriptive text of the module content, of attached information and detailed information about the individual activity steps. Here it is possible to change or specify assigned users, to include additional data or to add script modules for invoking applications. In the example, several documents like the change request or a solution description are attached to this proclert and preprogrammed script modules for prompting the approval are included.

Fig.8: Workflow composer

In order to make it easier to compose the right procleets, it is possible to access former workflow compositions, that have been used in similar situations and transform them to the current case. For achieving this, the workflow composer uses case-based reasoning algorithms that are analyzing old projects. In a separate window procleet compositions are displayed with their degree of similarity to the current situation which can be measured by comparison of the process attributes with the project and product specification done before. It is obvious that combinations that have been used successfully in the past can often be reused for the current project by using exactly the same workflow or by adapting it in some cases (transformational reuse). Therefore it is possible to select directly an old case and paste the accordant procleets by click in the case-based reasoning tool to the composer. Fig.9 shows the query window for display of former procleets.

Fig.9: Case-based reasoning for workflow composition

Finally, the different workflow modules, no matter if selected individually or adopted from a former project, have to be composed to a new workflow and to be instantiated. In contrast to conventional workflow design, the modules are only selected in a list, sorted in the right order and then the workflow is initiated. From the technical point of view not a new workflow is compiled but it is announced to the workflow system to execute precompiled, parameterized modules in the defined order. Fig.10 shows the self-explanatory composer for the modules.

In the background the workflow tool analyses, if the composition can be executed in the current project phase by calculating the workflow throughput time and matching this with a query of the project database.

Fig.10: Initiating a new workflow composition

5. Summary

By having adapted workflow management's functionality to the different process types of development projects, workflows can be used for an active coordination of shipbuilding design processes. Even project staff that is not familiar with workflow modeling techniques is able to configure and initiate workflows with help of predefined workflow modules in the workflow composer. With this tool it is possible to define, execute and monitor the design processes in detail that have not been in focus of the project management so far and to achieve therefore a comprehensive management of the project. For the future, the workflow user interface has to be integrated in project platforms in order to have a central project management tool.

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Automatic Piping System Implementation: A Real Case

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Abstract

The topic of developing an automatic system to generate optimum collision-free routes for pipes in ships has been of great interest to researchers. However, most research concentrated on academic systems, with only a few pipes and in a simplified environment. This paper shows how the Automatic Piping System was implemented to overcome a pipe routing problem on a real system. As a test case, a Tug Boat was selected and the Automatic Piping System was used to find the optimum routes for its 8 essential piping systems. The result was compared with the actual pipe routes which were done by the human designer. The comparison aspects dealt with in this paper are the duration to find the solution, and the length of each pipe. Considering only those aspects, the performance comparison shows that the Automatic Piping System has a promising future.

1. Introduction

Pipe routing is the process to develop a collision free route of a pipe between two or more connection points in a 3-D, obstacle-scattered environment, according to the rules and standards. This process consumes a significant part of the total ship design time because the piping systems in a ship typically consist of thousands of pipe elements and are usually routed manually by pipe engineers using Computer Aided Design (CAD) workstations using personal knowledge and experience of how to route pipes through the structure. In addition to that, there are numerous regulatory and functional design rules which must be satisfied.

The routing process is highly repetitive and design outputs can vary significantly between engineers. Piping design often proceeds in parallel with principal structural design. The iterative nature of the total design process is such that structural changes are prone to occur, requiring time-consuming rework for any pipe affected.

Pipe routing has been a research topic for a long time resulting in various approaches, not only in ship production application *Asmara and Nienhuis (2006)*, *Fan et al. (2006)*, *Zuurmond (2004)*, *Storch and Park (2002)*, *Kang et al. (1999)*, and *Kuo et al. (1999)*, but also in process plant *Ito (1999)*, *Newell (1972)*. The research started with 2D workspace *Rubin (1974)*, simple obstacles *Matsui et al. (1979)*, and gradually extends to the stage of 3D workspace with multiple constraints and multiple objectives *Storch and Park (2002)*. In terms of the optimization technique, either deterministic *Zuurmond (2004)*, nondeterministic *Fan et al. (2006)*, or combination of both methods *Asmara and Nienhuis (2006)* have been used to improve the results.

Although pipe-routing algorithms have already been developed, to date most of the algorithms are verified to solve the pipe routing problem on *academic systems*, like on a system with only a few pipes and in a simplified environment, and have paid little or no attention to the scalability of the algorithm to be applied in the real ship design process which consists of much larger number of pipes. Moreover, most of the researches neglect the existence of pipe branches. Finally, a comprehensive pipe routing method must include the knowledge rules originating e.g. from classification constraints.

In our previous work *Asmara and Nienhuis (2005)*, the automatic piping system has been developed and verified in an academic (i.e. simple) system. In this paper, the automatic piping system is used to solve the pipe routing problem on the real ship, and the result is verified by comparing with the actual pipe routes designed by the pipe engineers.

Fig.1: Automatic Piping System

In section 2, the short description of the automatic pipe system is explained. Section 3 describes the optimization criteria that are used in this paper. The test case is described in section 4. Section 5 consists of results and its comparison with the actual routes. This paper is concluded in section 6.

2. The Automatic Piping System: DelftRoute

The Automatic Piping System - DelftRoute is developed as a computer aided technique of generating a collision free and efficient route for pipes in a ship. This section only covers a brief description of the tool Asmara *and Nienhuis (2006)*.

As shown in Fig.1, the main architecture of DelftRoute has 3 main parts:

1. Interface Module,
2. Router Module,
3. Optimizer Module.

DelftRoute needs some information to perform the pipe routing: *construction of the hull, general arrangement, information of equipment, and piping and instrument diagram*. In practice, that information is available in CAD Software. To take advantage of this fact, the *interface module* was built to be a bridge between the system and the CAD software. It receives the data in the particular format of the CAD system and translates it to be useful for the *router module*. Conversely, it also translates the output of the *router module* to the format that can be read by the CAD software. Thus routing results can be visualized and integrated in the CAD environment.

The second part of DelftRoute is the *router module* which uses the data from the *interface module* and calculates the route of all pipes. This is the part of the system that actually performs the routing. This module in essence uses the Dijkstra algorithm to find the shortest path of each pipe, and the way it works is dependent on the parameters that are given by the third part of DelftRoute, the *optimizer module*.

Fig.2: The Multi Purpose Pusher Tug (MPPT33171)

As implied by its name, the *optimizer module* optimizes the performance of the *router module*. After the *router module* finishes its task, the quality of the result is evaluated by the *optimizer module*. Based on that result the new set of parameters are defined by the *optimizer module* and used by the *router module*. This cycle continues until a result with a defined quality is found.

3. Optimization Criteria

There are 2 main criteria to verify the quality of the solution:

1. Standard Criterion,
2. Performance Criterion.

The standard criterion is the criterion that has to be fulfilled; otherwise the solution cannot be used. If the result has passed the first criterion, then it can be evaluated using the second criterion.

3.1. Standard Criterion

Ideally the standard criterion requires that the solution should meet the Marine Classification, e.g. Lloyd's Register's Rules and Regulations. For this paper, the standard criterion that was used is not fully complying with the Marine Classification, which is subject of subsequent work not reported here. However the common rules such as that the pipe should always route to the lower level for grey and black water has been applied.

The standard criterion defines the validity of the solution; if it meets the standard criterion then the solution is categorized as a *valid solution*.

3.2. Performance Criterion

The quality of the valid solution is evaluated using the performance criterion. For the purpose of this paper the performance criterion is limited to minimizing the pipe length and number of bends, while considering the time that is needed to find the solution. In essence this amounts to a (simplified) cost criterion.

4. Test Case: the Multi Purpose Pusher Tug, build number 33171

The tug boat that was selected as a test case is shown in Fig.2. This vessel is a multi purpose pusher tug (MPPT33171) that can be used for a wide range of marine operations in sheltered, shallow waters and open sea, including pushing, pulling, buoy handling, dredging support work, anchor handling, ferrying of goods and personnel, fuel oil and water supply.

Table I: The Multi Purpose Pusher Tug (MPPT33171)

Dimension:		
Length overall	:	31.05 m
Length between perpendiculars	:	29.86 m
Breadth, molded	:	10 m
Depth at half length, molded	:	3.45 m
Draught at half length approx.	:	2.5 m
Propulsion:		
Main diesel engines	:	2 sets
Hydraulic driven bow thruster	:	1 set

Table II: Comparison of pipe length (mm)

System	Pipe Diameter	Pipe Length	
		DelftRoute	Actual
Bilge-Ballast	50	63840	62427
	65	75040	80866
	80	2590	2669
	100	6360	5533
Dirty Oil	32	10880	11099
	40	1480	1713
	50	8200	7633
	80	14560	14447
Exhaust Gas	100	6480	9463
	150	12920	18585
	200	7480	7094
	300	20880	18421
Fresh Cooling Water	25	14120	12582
	50	21840	19142
	80	40960	41990
	125	21440	17510
Raw Cooling Water	25	18390	20382
	32	11200	11779
	40	12400	12406
	50	7880	9056
	65	45520	45585
Fuel Oil Consumer	35	56160	62685
	32	26960	42455
	40	12640	27612
Fuel Oil Transfer	25	1640	4154
	40	560	993
	65	62360	72182
	100	40280	48462
	Hydraulic	10	86200
15		4200	3873
25		21520	21094
32		17360	15539
40		22040	24021

Fig.3: Dirty Oil System

MPPT33171 was designed by Merwede Shipyard and has main dimensions and propulsion particulars that are shown in Table I.

Eight essential systems of the MPPT33171, consisting of 198 pipes, were routed by the automatic piping system.

These systems are:

1. Dirty Oil System,
2. Bilge-Ballast System,
3. Exhaust System,
4. Fresh Cooling Water System,
5. Raw Cooling Water System,
6. Fuel Oil Consumer System,
7. Fuel Oil Transfer System,
8. Hydraulic System.

5. Result and Discussion

The CAD software (in this particular case Nupas/Cadmatic) has the capability to make a list of pipe components, including the length of the pipe and also make a list of elbows, flanges, reducers, sockets, and other parts of the pipe that are used. Because we intend to compare the exact length of the pipe, some adjustments need to be made. To calculate the exact pipe length, the length of the pipe should be added with the length of its pipe parts.

After the adjustment, the pipe length comparison between the result of DelftRoute and the actual pipe designed by the pipe engineers is shown in Table II.

Considering only the length of the pipe, Table II shows that the result of DelftRoute corresponds quite well with the pipe routes designed by the pipe engineers.

Fig.3 to Fig.10 shows the pipe routes for each system. The left side of each figure shows the pipe routes designed by the pipe engineers and on the right side is the result of DelftRoute.

The Dirty Oil System is shown in Fig.3.a) and b). These two figures show that most of the pipes have different paths for both solutions. For example one pipe was routed above the tank by the pipe engineers while DelftRoute routes it below the deck.

Fig.4: Bilge-Ballast System

Fig.5: Exhaust System

Fig.4.a) and b) compare the result of the Bilge-Ballast System. For most pipes in this system, these two figures show the similarity of both results, only for a few pipes the solutions show some difference. The pipes that are routed by the DelftPipe are constrained to be in orthogonal direction as much as possible while in practice deviations from this occur.

Fig.4.c) and d) depict the excerpt of one part of the Bilge-Ballast System that has a quite high complexity. Fig.4.d) proves the ability of DelftRoute to find a solution in such a complex part of the system.

Fig.5 shows the similarity of both solutions for the Exhaust System. The difference only occurs for one pipe. As shown in Fig.5, the pipe engineers chose longer pipes compare to more bending while DelftRoute chose the other way around.

a)

b)

Fig.6: Fresh Cooling Water System

a)

b)

Fig.7: Raw Cooling Water System

For most of the pipes in the Fresh Cooling Water System, the solution from DelftRoute is almost the same with the one that are done by the pipe engineers. As shown in Fig.6, one big difference is only on one pair of pipes that should have been routed in parallel by the algorithm.

In Table II shown that for the Raw Cooling Water System, the solution of DelftRoute has shorter pipe length compare to the pipe engineers, but as is shown in Fig.7 the solution of the pipe engineers still looks better because most of the pipes are routed in parallel. Such aspects, related to aesthetics and ease of maintenance, are not yet included in the optimization scheme.

Fig.8: Fuel Oil Consumer System

Fig.9: Fuel Oil Transfer System

In terms of pipe length, in comparison with the solution from the pipe engineers, the solution by DelftRoute is better for the Fuel Oil Consumer System. As can be seen from Fig.8, this is because for some pipes DelftRoute routed it below the deck, while the pipe engineers chose to go below the engine room and routed it above the tank. Considering only the functional aspect, the solution of DelftRoute is correct, but if aesthetics and ease of installation are also be considered, the solution from the pipe engineers is better.

For the last two systems, the Fuel Oil Transfer System and the Hydraulics System, the results are shown by Fig.9 and Fig.10 respectively, the result from DelftRoute seems to have almost the same tendency as before, which shows a good solution in terms of pipe length but has a lack of the aesthetic value.

The next comparison aspect is the time that is needed to find the solution. According to some pipe engineers, if every data that they need, like the construction hull, general arrangement, information of equipment and piping and instrument diagram, is already available it takes around one month or so to route the systems mentioned above.

If those data is available, thanks to its interface module; DelftRoute only needs a few hours to retrieve those data to be used in DelftRoute. For the routing process itself, it takes around 3-4 hours on the personal computer Pentium Centrino 1.6 MHz, with 512 MB RAM.

Fig.10: Hydraulics System

6. Conclusion

The Automatic Piping System – DelftRoute has been implemented to overcome the pipe routing problem in the real ship. The result shows that in terms of the functionality and the length of the pipes, the solution from DelftRoute is good enough.

One of the most interesting parts is the time that is needed by DelftRoute to find the solution which is very fast compare with the time that is needed by the pipe engineers. This is one of the advantages of DelftRoute, since in practice piping design often proceeds in parallel with principal structural design and each time the structures are changed some of the pipe might be affected, and needs to be re-route.

Further ongoing development focus on the improvement of DelftRoute to fully comply with the Marine Classification, and also to include other important aspects such as the ease of pipe installation and maintenance and the aesthetic aspect.

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Computer Aided Approval – Needs, Problems and Opportunities

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Abstract

The ship approval process is today in large parts dependent on the checking against predefined rule sets, which leads to high efficiency as compared to direct calculations. Computer Aided Approval describes a way to combine flexibility of the simulation based approach with the efficiency of the rule based way of work. The paper describes the needs, problems and opportunities when implementing this new process by using product data from yard and supplier IT systems.

1. Initial Situation

The shipbuilding approval process is characterised by a sector-specific peculiarity. In contrast to the TÜV (German Technical Inspection Authority) or the “Luftfahrtbundesamt” (the German Civil Aviation Authority), where inspections concentrate on the verification of operational safety, the regulations governing shipbuilding consist predominantly of a set of laid down rules which govern construction.

A Design Engineer, who adheres accurately to these regulations, providing evidence/demonstrating it through construction plans, documents and records, subsequently does not have to concern him- or herself over an explicit verification of the safety and function of the actual construction. This procedure is practised up to this day due to the fact that, on the whole, a ship is produced as an “original” or in a small series, making a more explicit approval overly sophisticated, time consuming and expensive. Thus, the approval process in shipbuilding does not, as one might expect, bear a lot of similarities to automotive or aircraft manufacturing but instead more resembles the structural engineering of buildings. In respect to its dynamic load bearing capabilities, its preliminary design boundary conditions and therefore also its certification, a ship resembles comes to totally new constructions has up to now not outweighed this efficiency advantage.

Taking this into account it has proved more efficient to follow rules of construction based on years of research and empirical experience, built up from praxis and then compiled, put into force and controlled by professionally trained specialists, than a verification management solely relying on direct calculation. The lack of flexibility when it comes to totally new constructions has up to know not outweighed this efficiency advantage.

Still, the following two aspects could bring change in the near future. On the one hand, such lack of flexibility could turn out to stand in the way of the efforts of (in particular German and European) dockyards to stay competitive with innovative products. On the other hand, increasing safety and environmental concerns have resulted in a growing pressure from the general public to speedily investigate the causes of ship accidents and promptly introduce safety improvements, leading to ever growing and more complex regulations. The vast number of different requirements, with their complicated and sometimes complex underlying principles and correlations, make it necessary to think about alternative verification processes (e.g. risk assessments, system simulations) and also to lay the groundwork towards changes in the political framework that surrounds them, *Securiu and Sideris (2000)*.

Putting aside the thematic complexity of such approaches, it can be noted that alternative approval processes can only be successful when they are backed up by an efficient management of the relevant data. For such operations, the amount of information, as well as its requirements on consistency, is notably higher than a complete review based on the existing rules of construction. The required information to be collated with these methods increases considerably and can only be handled by

digital means. At the same time, ever-shorter development cycles create pressure to speed up the approval process, including using the possibilities of digital data processing in a more efficient way. In a classic engineering drawing check, however, these possibilities are quite limited, often giving the impression that the use of drawings causes unnecessary delays in the approval process. Unfortunately, the solution is not as easy as it might first appear.

2. Scope of review

Within all of these considerations, it should not be forgotten that the reviewing and approval of constructions is also a juridical problem. From the beginning, the contractor and Plan Approval Engineer have to agree on what is to be reviewed and on what basis the approval will be founded. The accordingly defined scope of review will then have to be documented with great accuracy, allowing a verification of the process even many years later.

The starting point of any review carried out at present is a carefully specified set of documents describing the part of the construction that is to be reviewed, as well as a specification of its function when needed. This limitation of data automatically also defines the scope of the review. Formally, the Plan Approval Engineer only has to take that information into account that can be found in the available documents. In case the sheer number of documents is too high, a selection can be made, marking the chosen papers with a stamp. Furthermore, the Plan Approval Engineer can also quickly and clearly mark where problems might occur, where the given information is not distinct or complete, or where the described technical solution cannot be approved.

A Plan Approval Engineer who views him-/herself solely as a controller can restrict the review to the given data and in some cases ask the contractor to supply further information. Apart from that, he/she can sport an attitude of “What I don’t know cannot do me harm”.

A Plan Approval Engineer, who also sees him-/herself in the role of a service provider aiming to create an efficient reviewing process in the interest of the client, will try to establish a working environment that allows him/her to obtain any missing information him-/herself. After all, he/she knows best what information is missing. A very effective way to enable this to happen, would be the direct access to the original product database, out of which the Plan Approval Engineer could extract the required information first hand. Alas, such a comprehensive database can prove to be a ‘Trojan Horse’, a gift whose destructive effects will only unfold at a later date in that once they have penetrated the review process, slowly but steadily the hitherto taken for granted boundary conditions disappear and suddenly a multitude of new questions arise. How can we then, comprehensively describe the approval framework and who assumes responsibility for it? Is the Plan Approval Engineer, in the role of a responsible service provider, duty-bound to pay regard to faults and anomalies that lie outside of the approval process, and also to communicate them further?

One can assume that performing this at first voluntary extra task, may, with time become a matter of cause and even later a legally enforceable and prosecutable joint responsibility. With the whole of the information at his/her disposal the Plan Approval Engineer could, in theory, be blamed for any unrecognised errors in the database. From the standpoint of the engineer, the reviewing procedure thus increases to an unimaginable size. He/she has to work wonders and master a markedly increased review effort in an ever shorter time. At the same time the information would be no longer prepared with regard to the context of the approval or the need for the Plan Approval Engineer to quickly understand the system’s functions and integrity. As a consequence, this additional task will have to be taken on by the engineer. Anyone who has ever strived to familiarise themselves with a hitherto unknown database knows how time-consuming that can be.

3. What exactly is Computer Aided Approval?

The phrase Computer Aided Approval is used as a synonym for the review and approval of construction on the basis of digital documents and model files as defined below.. As a process it

cannot be considered separately from the management of this data. Digitalised databases can be divided into two categories, in which the used terms are not clearly defined and in which their scope of what we understand by them overlaps at the margins.

The often used wording ‘Electronic Approval’ respectively ‘Digital Approval’ is in any case not a really suitable phrase to exactly communicate its activities and needed changes, in that it places digital data tasks too much at the forefront, and with it implies the downgrading of human technical expertise. From the view of the authors, the term ‘Computer Aided Approval’ (CAA) is a lot more precise and because of its analogous nature with CAD/CAE and CAM, definitely more trusted and able to be understood by the engineers involved, making it easier for them to accept change.

In the following, the term “digital document” is used to represent any kind of document whose contents can be interpreted in the computer with the help of text or image editing standard software without knowledge about its semantics, e.g. DOC-, TIF-, PNG- or PDF-files.

The term “data model file” on the other hand means data files which can directly transport semantic information about the character of the construction – in the sense of geometry, parameters, attributes and/or structure – and therefore the contents of product describing data models. These include for example STEP physical files or specific XML files as well as all system-specific exchange files. Three basic variations can be conceived of as a foundation for Computer Aided Approval:

1. Design drawings, lists, data sheets and/or product specification texts are rendered in the form of digital documents.
2. The data is presented partly in data model files and partly as digital documents. This variant is often seen today. Considering the issue of data consistency, it is the most problematic variant because there are no mechanisms to establish whether the content of a design plan or a data sheet overlap and/or correspond with the information in the data model file. A problem occurs immediately when, for example within the framework of a component approval process, concurrently a construction drawing, a written technical specification, a parameter file and a STEP file with a mass of component group and geometrical information (AP214) are exchanged.
3. The whole product is described in one or more data model files in its entirety.

In the first and the second variant it is the client who produces the digital documents, thereby limiting the nature, place and scope of the review within the framework of the regulations. If necessary, the Inspector can ask for additional and/or more detailed information that will be passed on in the form of a sketch, a modified drawing or a text document.

However, Computer Aided Approval is only secondarily concerned with the examination of digital documents. Firstly, it aims at a general advancement with regard to the information density of the inspection documents through the use of data model files that describe the product or the construction (product information). For this reason, in the third variant, the contractor provides the digital database in data model files. The Plan Approval Engineer generates, on the basis of the existing regulations, the documents in question or directly checks the contents of the data model files.

Usually the handling of digital documents does not create many problems, since the software required is widely used by various consumer groups (in private households as well as in all industrial and administrative areas). Accordingly, it is wide-spread and offers high performance at a reasonable price. However, a drawing formatted for example as a TIF-file, is only a description of how to reproduce an image in a certain part of the monitor. The actual character of a construction is still modelled or transported with the help of the standardised glossary as well as with symbols for engineering drawings and has to be interpreted by the person responsible just as before.

On the other hand, in order to work with data model files, a software must be able to interpret the content and consistency of those files. Thus, it would be a genuinely sector-specific solution which

would have to be able to match the complexity of its field of application. For large and capital intensive sectors such as automotive industry this appears to be a minor problem because huge development costs can still be allocated to a vast number of purchased software licences. This makes it worthwhile, even if the relative increase in productivity is low. However, if the circle of potential users of such a specific solution is too small and/or the realisable productivity growth is not enough to justify its development and maintenance costs – a situation often encountered in the area of shipbuilding classification – the development will not go ahead, even if it was achievable on a technical level.

It is to be feared in the short run that an approval process based on over-comprehensive digital product information would not become faster and cheaper but indeed instead, slower and more expensive. Does that mean that any attempt to integrate digital data into the approval process should be abandoned? That would be a comfortable, but also for clients and a critical public, incomprehensible move. It is better to actively take up the challenge and to assess critically the potential of Computer Aided Approval with regard to improvements within the various sections of the review process and in different reviewing methods.

4. Methods

4.1. Plan approval – Steel Ship Structures

The term Digital Approval is already widely recognised in this field of operation as being very controversial. It is positively impossible to digitally – i.e. with the help of implemented algorithms and regulations – review a technical drawing rendered as a digital document in terms of the correctness of its content. An inspection through a Plan Approval Engineer can always only be done by visual means. A significant change, (always meant to be an improvement), can only be reached with the aid of data model files. The entire inspection of a digital construction model contradicts, however, the nature of the classification, in that the area of responsibility of the Plan Approval Engineer can no longer be clearly defined. An unrestricted inspection of all aspects would lead to such an extensive investment in work and such an assumption of liability that it would be no longer realistically possible for any inspection/classification company. The replacement of the construction drawing through data model files cannot be the right way in the short and mid term. Instead, it is more important to ask the question as to whether digital data can be used in a complementary way to gain relevant and prompt supplementary information. This process must be supported through the fast generation of digital documents (for example, drawings) from the digital models. From the view of the client, these additional drawings can ascertain the review framework. From the viewpoint of the Plan Approval Engineer, they can document what was considered for the review in the data model and on what basis the approval was given.

4.2. Rule based approval of machinery parts

When dealing with a rule based approval of machinery parts, it can be assumed that the size of the database will stay manageable as long as only the data relevant for the approval process is exchanged. However, even here the size of the model can get quickly out of control when no agreement between the process participants exists.

This may happen when, for example within the framework of an engine system certification, washers and screws as components with individual geometrical descriptions are also exchanged. If this is prevented by an exchange of data on an ‘as required’ basis, then the problem of a digitally supported rule based approval becomes not one of the amount of data, but one of the variety of it. The parameters relevant for the approval will be provided and communicated by each manufacturer in various different forms. The scope here extends from a text-based specification supplemented with diagrams, to complex parameter files including geometry. Up to this point, there are only suggestions and guidelines for the designation of such attributes, but no mandatory standards.

In the course of manually carried out approvals, this can only turn out to be a problem if the designation so much departs from the usual, that the technical knowledge of the Plan Approval Engineer is not enough to accomplish the correlation of the data. In contrast, in a computer based approval process, only a small discrepancy from that of the implemented standard could seriously disrupt the working process. Due to the fact that, in a complex supply chain, a ship classification society cannot and does not want to take on a dominant role in terms of the content and form of data exchange, it has to be able to flexibly adapt to the possibilities of the respective supplier. Here mechanisms are needed that accurately inform the Plan Approval Engineer about any eventual problems and subsequently put him/her in the position to quickly and comprehensively react. The advantages of computer based approval systems in terms of time and quality should not be endangered through extensive manual re-inputting from a format that is not appropriate – such as a data model file.

4.3. Approval on the Basis of Direct Calculation

The extent in which the results of FE-calculations are used as a foundation for construction decisions also has an indirect effect on the approval process. The referral to compliance with construction regulations will only be acceptable for customers wanting to save the cost for a FE-calculation. However, in case they already have invested in one, and the results from their viewpoint were successful, they should be considered in the approval procedure. Consequently, the FE-evaluation also has to become part of the review. Such an action is no longer conceivable without the use of computerized technology. Critical points in this respect are the control of the model quality and correctness, as well as the conformity of the load generation to the regulations and the linking of the calculation results with the structure actually being built.

4.4. System Checking

In the SOLAS-I.5 one can find a reference to the effect that variations from the construction regulations can be accepted as long as it can be proved that the alternative material or system is equivalent or better to the material or system already stated as being in conformance to those regulations. In the area of fire prevention, SOLAS-II.2/17 documents the conformance requirements of equivalent safety explicitly, so alternative designs and structural arrangements can be approved. The aim of this evidence is to demonstrate that no reductions in terms of safety and function are to be expected through deviations from the construction regulations as they are laid down.

One possibility to provide such evidence is through a classic system simulation. This is, however, often rather complicated and therefore only used for limited parts of the whole construction. Another solution is using risk-based verification procedures. These can be divided into two basic techniques. The first involves individual reviewing on the basis of risk-assessment methods, called a Safety Case. The other one, the Formal Safety Assessment (FSA), is seen as a tool which makes the development of risk-based regulatory frameworks possible. The EU-backed project “Design, Operation and Regulation for Safety” (SAFEDOR, please see www.safedor.org) is concerned with setting out the groundwork for a risk-based ship development and approval process. With this comes totally new demands on data management. As this concerns itself with the appraisal/assessment of systems, this aspect also has to be considered with regard to data management. The Designer/Constructor and the Plan Approval Engineer have to exchange a great deal of information. In order to, for example assess a fault tree, the inspector absolutely has to know the described system and be able to make an assessment of its failure modes and conditional probability of failure.

Today, it is no longer possible to carry out both classic simulations and also risk-based considerations as component parts of a review and approval process without the massive intervention of computer science. In both cases programming the simulation software requires a high standard of accuracy and quality assurance.

4.5. Automation and Control Systems

A totally different aspect of system certification comes to the fore when a major functional component of a system is itself a control and regulatory system that can only be classified, and with it certified, when the employed hard- and software work together on an error-free basis in all thinkable norms and operating conditions. Typical examples would be engine systems that are controlled via autopilot or positioning systems and also the control of diesel-electric drive mechanisms. The classic proof used for an approval procedure – the conformance of the mechanical components of the power plant and rudder system with modern technology standards – is indeed still important information for the ship owner and perhaps the insurer to have, but it is no longer in itself sufficient. In the sense of Computer Aided Approval, test procedures have to be developed and certified with which the safety testing for complex control mechanisms and regulatory systems can be carried out. “Hardware-in-the-Loop” simulation is a testing procedure that can check control mechanism components within a ‘virtual test bed’, through the use of the simulation and combination of various operational states, with the resulting input and output data tested with regard to their functional safety. For such procedures, alongside the technical description of a component and its embedding within a system, the test-relevant value ranges that have to be run through the “Hardware-in-the-Loop” simulation need to be stored, see e.g. *Gomez (2001)*.

5. Data Management Requirements

The requirements and the possibilities arising from direct calculation and system appraisal, show that Computer Aided Approval as a consequence should no longer only be seen as an aid in a classic approval process. Instead, the Plan Approval will, through the implementation of new procedures and methods, acquire a new quality. As a consequence, from a data-technical viewpoint comes a multitude of new demands that cannot be solved individually, but instead have to be considered in their entirety. The main problem regarding the filing and storage of components lies in the fact that the type-specific parameters of a component that are needed for a review cannot be fully acquired for the database management during the specifications phase of the system. Every new or further development of the underlying build design (type) can lead to new or changed parameters. These then have to be promptly transferred into the data model without having the consequence that, through this, the older data loses its validity and the administrative load becomes too large. This expansion has to be simple, but even so, must happen in a controlled way. That requires a lexicon of characteristics in which the known product characteristics (Power, Outer Diameter, etc.) can be bindingly laid down. Within the database, these characteristics (expandable) can be allocated to the components as properties.

It is a stringent requirement from the standpoint of the modelling of the system structure, to be able to integrate the individual components into various systems through references, as well as to be able to display their relationship to one another. This makes a structured way of storing the component instances, or more specifically their reference points necessary, which can then be displayed optionally in lists, in a branch and/or network structure. In this way the description, meaning the technical data of a type-certified pump, would be located in a component list. More pumps of this type are built into specific places in the system. These must be described as references to the data in the component list in a branch structure (for example *Ship/Piping_system/Mid ship/Bay_1*). Simultaneously, these pumps interact with valves, gate valves, electrical regulators and switches, through which a net structure is created.

From the component level up, a stringent categorization has to be possible in order to guarantee that, even after the approval process, variables can be calculated without losing the data describing the approved status. It must be possible to give the database (the variable) a status that allows the blocking of approved data records. Any changes are then traceable and can, depending on the status, also be reversed. It is also necessary to make sure that data on this level can be linked to geometrical information, drawings, data calculations and certificates. At the same time transparent (neutral) exchange formats have to be employed that can also communicate the approved status to the client, since traditional documents, such as drawings, are no longer sufficient for that purpose. An

implementation example of such a data management system is the GL Technical Information System (TIS), Ehrler et al. (2007).

Consequently, the data models become the primary carrier of information and can be generated by the Plan Approval Engineer in case they are needed. With this, the unavoidable necessity to check and document the quality of such models comes to the fore.

At the same time, not only must the Plan Approval Engineer, as hitherto, be trained and approved, but also the deployed software components and/or systems must be thoroughly tested and certified. Up to this point, the experience for this is still lacking, however it is conceivable, in a way analogous with the 'Hardware-in-the-Loop' simulation, to deploy a 'Software-in-the-Loop' test area which would guarantee that new software and software updates would not be able to carry over errors into the approval process.

6. Summary

If Computer Aided Approval is ever to become more than the reviewing of digital documents, namely the beginning of a wholesale improvement of the information density in reviewing documentation through the use of data model files, then the process of ship-building approval will have to substantially change. These changes do not only consist of the replacement of drawings with digital data models, but also in reorganization of approval procedures and of the legal framework that governs them. At the same time, totally new demands will be placed on the management of digital databases. However, it must be the guideline for all activities to always keep in mind that Computer Aided Approval is of no value in itself, but instead merely an important building block to improve the approval process in the sense of Enhanced Approval. Wisdom has it, that without an accurate analysis of the process to be changed in respect to its crucial effects, its real requirements, as well as its costs and benefits, the chances are high that, in the end, the result may not be the desired one. Not everything that is technologically possible has therefore also to be practical or economical.

The unknown terrain that lays before us holds not only new possibilities but also new dangers in such a way that one cannot initially navigate a true path through the ground laying ahead. Instead one must prepare for careful exploration in small stages. It is the role of research to act as the pathfinder in this undertaking. The leader of the exploration however, should be an experienced Plan Approval Engineer.

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Simulation based Planning of Ferry Terminal Operations

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Abstract

This paper presents the design of a software tool developed for modelling and simulation of the landside vehicular operations in passenger ferry terminals. The tool is an add-on module to the crowd flow simulation tool Helios and is named Helios-PortSim. This tool should be of interest to operations analysts and port facility designers seeking to evaluate the performance of a designed facility or operation with respect to vehicular throughput. This tool addresses the peculiarities of ferry loading/unloading operations that are impossible to model convincingly using the general purpose simulation tools such as discrete event simulators. This work was supported by a major European ferry operator and has been enriched with a wealth of practical knowledge and experience of the said operator. The tool has helped evaluating ferry loading/unloading operations for three busy ports and its results have contributed to some important design decisions regarding the acquisition and renovation of the ports' infrastructure. The paper discusses the requirements of Helios-PortSim and presents the software design that meets such requirements.

1. Introduction

The latest ferry ships are very fast and efficient on the waters but the typically slow port operations bring down the efficiency of the overall operation. Improving the efficiency of the port operations can make an appreciable difference in the revenue of ferry operators. In order to address this need we have investigated on and developed a software tool (named Helios-PortSim or simply PortSim) for planning of port operations through simulation.

This tool is specifically designed for planning of ferry-terminal operations. The general purpose discrete event simulators such as QuestTM, FlexSimTM, AutomodTM etc. are suitable for planning the operations of manufacturing, cargo handling, material handling, warehousing, packaging, etc., but when it comes to modeling the ferry terminal operations they fall short of some important modeling features. PortSim, on the other hand, has built in features for evaluating port-specific aspects such as placement and multiplicity of check-in devices, buffer area size, trailer yard layout, layout of parking areas for different types of vehicles, customs facility, vehicle exit facility, trailer operations, and so on. Three full scale case studies undertaken as a part of this development reveals that the trailer loading/unloading process, which is usually the longest sub-process of a ferry loading/unloading operation, can be improved significantly by proper planning of the operation.

In this paper, we present the design of the PortSim software and describe the modelling elements that are combined to create the wide variety of vehicular operations required in a ferry terminal. The modelling involves creation of a connected structural abstraction representing the port as a multi-layer traffic network comprising the parking lanes, ramps, shipboard lanes in multiple decks, connecting roads and nearby public roads. The behavioural model of the simulated vehicles includes goal-based and rules-constrained automatic planning of routes on the road network. A number of behavioural elements such as manoeuvres, event triggers, mutual exclusion, queuing, deferred action etc. are combined in the task of modelling the simulation scenario. The simulation helps the operator to answer questions such as the following.

1. Can the requisite number of trailers be booked given a required turn-around time and a known number of tugmasters that can be deployed?

2. Can the same be done if the number of tugmasters is increased?
3. What is the maximum number of cars that can be loaded within a given time?
4. Given the arrival rates of an exceptionally busy period, will the incoming traffic spill over to the main road? How many additional check-in personnel (in addition to the usual self check-in devices) would be required to prevent the spill-over?
5. What would be the impact of a broken-down check-in device?

Visualization of the simulation is done using 3D interactive computer graphics. The state of the simulation can be altered dynamically during the simulation using mouse-clicks and keystrokes. The following sections present the requirements and the design of the PortSim system.

2. Operations in a Ferry Terminal

The complete port operation consists of a complex interaction of several cooperating players including the ship operators' staff, the port management, passengers, tug-master operators etc. It is not necessary to model every single aspect of the operations. Only the operational aspects that contribute significantly to the ships' turn-around time and the ship operators' port usage time are of interest. With that limit on the scope there still are quite a few operational processes to model. Following is a list of those processes.

1. Arrival of Passengers: Passengers start arriving a few hours before the vessel's departure time. An exponential distribution of inter-arrival time is normally assumed for steady state arrival processes, but that does not quite hold for passenger arrivals. The arrival processes for the ferry port has its own peculiarity. This is so because a large section of the passengers are aware of the ferry departure schedule, and typically want to arrive at the port as late as possible and yet make it on time for the loading. The last hour before the departure is extremely busy when cars arrive very frequently.

Fig.1: Typical Arrival and Check-in Process (Screenshots from Helios-PortSim)

2. Passengers checking-in: As the passengers arrive at the port they take a diversion from one or more public roads to enter into the port area. Then they reach the check-in devices where they use their magnetically or optically coded travel-pass to grant access to the inner car-park where the checked-in cars are parked. This applies to all types of vehicles except the trailers that arrive much earlier (and are assumed to be already parked in the trailer yard). The time to complete the check-in procedure varies from person to person and is generally assumed to follow a normal distribution. In a busy period during the arrival, there would be queuing of cars at the check-in devices, Fig.1.
3. Parking in the inner car park: There is usually a large parking space in which the cars are parked after the drivers complete the check-in procedure. These cars are ready to be loaded once the ferry finishes unloading. There can be several ways that this space can be filled. Normally the operators choose to fill this space one lane at a time so that this parking order

can be used to ensure that the earlier one comes to the port the earlier she gets to board the ship and hence the earlier she gets to disembark and leave the port on reaching the destination. This incentive helps maintain a good spread of arrival time.

4. Unloading the ship: Once the ship is docked, one or more link spans establish a continuous connection between the ship and the port. By that time all the onboard car passengers are in their respective vehicles and waiting for their turn to disembark. When disembarkation begins one or more lanes are signaled to disembark at a time, and this continues in a sequence until the vessel is empty.

Fig.2: Vehicles disembarking from the ship and leaving the port. (Screenshots from Helios-PortSim)

5. Loading of cars: The loading of cars ensues as soon as the unloading process is complete and continues until all the cars that checked in have embarked on the ship. Ground and onboard crew coordinate to guide the process.
6. Loading and unloading of trailers: Ferries carry a significant amount of cargo on wheeled trailers that don't have their own engine and are driven by the so-called tug-masters. Usually the trailer loading process is the longest sub-process of the loading process, and more is to be gained by optimizing this process. The procedure for loading and unloading of trailers normally consists of the following – The tug masters unload the first several trailers from the ship (typically twelve or so, for a ship with two trailer lanes on each side of the centre casing). This makes enough free space for loading/unloading to be carried out simultaneously in unloading the rest of the trailers. This is quicker than fully emptying the trailer space and then starting the trailer loading process. This method also has the advantage of affording better utilization of the trailer yard space. After a trailer is loaded (i.e. removed from the trailer yard) its space can be used for parking the next unloaded trailer so that no additional space is necessary for the subsequent process.

Two tug masters with trailers can operate independently on either side of the center-casing (the center casing is a structural element comprising lifts and stairwells that lies between the starboard and port side of the vehicle deck) but usually there is not enough space left for a third tug master with a trailer to operate simultaneously on the same deck. Therefore sometimes some tug masters would have to wait for another tug master to come off the ship.

The tug masters are very agile and maneuverable when not attached with a trailer. So after detaching from a trailer on the deck, a tug master can reverse itself on the same side of the center-casing. The tug masters make similar reverse maneuvers, in the trailer yard while making their way to other trailers.

Fig.3: Tug masters deployed to load and unload trailers

7. Customs inspection: The customs inspection is a process carried out near the exit of the port. In some ports there is a separate exit lane going through an inspection zone for vehicles that have some items to declare. Besides some vehicles are chosen from the rest of the vehicles for inspection. The customs check of a vehicle within an exit lane causes its tailing vehicles to pause for the duration of the inspection.

The aforementioned procedures are the most significant elements of the loading/unloading process. There are some more sub-processes such as (i) lowering of the mechanical ramps, (ii) attachment of the link span to the ship's bow/stern door, (iii) opening of the bow/stern door, (iv) lashing of the trailers and trucks, and so on. Some of these operations are done simultaneously with some other processes and the rest must be done sequentially.

The primary requirement of PortSim was to be able to simulate the aforementioned processes and generate data on the performance of a modeled operation.

3. Design of the PortSim Software

The following subsections briefly describe the key elements of the design of Helios-PortSim.

3.1 The PortSim Environment Model

The primary design decision in the development of PortSim was that of the level of abstraction at which the operations were to be modeled. The motions were decided to be modeled purely kinematically (i.e. in terms of the geometry of motion, not in terms of the forces causing the motion). Helios already had visibility based and graph based motion (planning) model for simulation of pedestrians but the kinematics of wheeled vehicles were fundamentally different. The kinematical models of wheeled vehicles are differential equations with a special property called non-holonomy – referring to differential constraint(s) between kinematical parameters that can not be integrated into an algebraic equation. Although wheeled drives have been ubiquitous for a long time, the kinematical planning of wheeled drive has not been studied until recently, *Murray and Sastry (1993)*. The said work and its sequels were studied in the initial phase of PortSim development but the high mathematical sophistication of the method was considered beyond the resources available for this project. If we could incorporate the methods presented in *Murray and Sastry (1993)* into Helios-PortSim, we could have computed kinematically correct maneuvers (motion plans) of wheeled vehicles in the presence of obstacles.

So, instead of trying to compute the motion from scratch, we decided to constrain the motion to a network of pre-defined tracks, and a set of pre-defined maneuvers. The operations could then be modeled using a task-level programming of the vehicles. Thus, the instantaneous motion of the

vehicles would be 1DOF motion along paths in a 3D network. The non-holonomic constraint of the vehicles' motion would then condense into a minimum-curvature constraint on the construction of such paths. It would be tedious to construct such paths interactively, so PortSim provides features to construct a full connection network from a skeletal description of the network. Besides, there are track array creation features to minimize the effort involved in constructing the network model.

Fig.4: Network of vehicular tracks generated in PortSim, shown as black lines in the left image and as white lines in the right image

Fig.5: A partial UML class diagram for PortSim

The aforementioned network model is actually an annotation sketched atop a multi-layer 3D spatial database which forms the core of Helios as reported in *Majumder et al. (2005)*. This database is generated automatically from a 2D map of the port and general arrangement (GA) drawing for the ship.

The path network approach is used in other simulation tools such as Automod and Flexsim, but the path sketching is much more efficient in PortSim due to the facts that (i) node creation is unnecessary, path nodes are inferred from the paths (ii) user only creates a skeletal network and generates the rest of the network using convenient auto-connect and array functionality. The path network so generated may also be tweaked or edited on the popular CAD tools such as Autocad and Intellicad.

Besides the path network, there are a number of other types of annotations that one can do on the Helios spatial database in relation to vehicular simulation. These annotations are sketched on the spatial model of the ship and port environment using simple geometric figures such as circles, polygons, directed lines (arrows), points and rectangles. The sketched figures may be named and used in specifying additional information. For example, one can specify a region using a sketched set of rectangles or polygons and ask PortSim to record the number of vehicles in that region. Such regions are also used in enforcing exclusion zones, sink zones (where vehicles are annihilated once they go beyond the area of interest), and source zones (where vehicles spring into existence during the arrival process). As another example, one-way tracks are specified using arrow annotations.

So the environment model for PortSim is essentially a 2-manifold surface in 3D space (as is the spatial database of Helios), annotated with local information associated using overlaid sketches.

Fig.6: Left: The sketched geometric figures serving as spatial annotations in the environment model
Right: A screenshot of the Helios user interface

3.2 The PortSim Operations Specification Model

It is usually preferable to make the modelling task a declarative activity – i.e. in this context the model is preferred to be described as a set of declarations about the operational model. This was achieved for cases in which one could declare the final destination lanes for the vehicles; however the specification of operation models has a very imperative semantics, i.e. if the operation is specified unambiguously, such a specification would take the form of a simple task-level program for the vehicles.

This need was addressed by introducing imperative semantics for the description of operations. Thus the tasks assigned to vehicles are not just destinations but a sequence of sub-tasks. Most subtasks are road names but they can be other things such as (1) a maneuver (2) instruction to attach or detach a trailer (3) any script that would be executed with the vehicle’s self in context (4) pause for a specified duration, etc.

Among the aforementioned sub-task types, maneuvers are similar to tracks in the sense that they too are represented by curves and lines in 3D space, but they are interpreted differently. A track is fixed in space and has an absolute position in the port/ship layout. But a maneuver is a path that is followed relative to the current position and orientation of the vehicle. Several parametrically defined maneuvers have been provided in the PortSim data library.

Most of these task descriptions get utilized for tug masters whose operation happens to be the most complex of all.

The vehicles carry out the list of tasks assigned to them in sequential order, but user interaction and event handlers can potentially change their task assignment. By event handlers, we do not mean the GUI event handler for mouse click, keystroke and such. There is a rich set of events available in Helios-PortSim to model a variety of operational aspects.

For example, after driving up the link-span the cars enter through the bow door, where there is a crew member directing the incoming cars into the car-deck lanes, using some policy or logic for distribution. This may be modeled by a handler for an event that gets generated when a vehicle comes to the end of a track that leads up the link-span to the bow-door. This handler is a scripting procedure implementing the distribution policy or logic. Speaking of scripting, all the functionality of Helios is scriptable – i.e. available for runtime scripting using the scripting language called TCL (<http://www.tcl.tk>). Thus any event handler can potentially make any change in the state of the simulation. The following are types of events that are detected and handled in the PortSim functionality.

1. A vehicle entering or leaving a road.
2. A vehicle entering or leaving an annotated region.
3. A road becoming occupied, choc-a-bloc full, or empty.
4. A vehicle parking or becoming stagnant.
5. A timer event (scheduled to happen at a certain time or after a certain interval).
6. A periodic timer event (an event that is triggered every so many seconds).
7. Mouse click event at a higher level of abstraction (e.g. with the context of a point in the 3d model space that has been pointed to while clicking, or the object that has been clicked on)

An event handler can do virtually anything that can be done in Helios (e.g. query the current state of the simulation, record information, modify the current state etc.), and it is passed all the specific information relevant to the particular instance of the event (for example, for a road exit event the names of the road in question and the exiting vehicle is provided to the handler). The handling of the aforementioned set of events has so far been sufficient for modeling all the operations mentioned in section 2.

Some features of declarative modeling has been included in PortSim but the aforementioned event handling method has been found to be more flexible in handling all possible idiosyncrasies of the operational specification. Some of the declarative features are as follows:

1. Automatic planning of path to a destination, observing declarative path constraints (one-way etc.) using graph based algorithms. This enables a procedure to be declared only in terms of its initial and final state.
2. Regular expression based specification of actions for cyclic procedures. The planning algorithm for this novel method is very interesting, and is based on deep concepts of computing science. The regular path expression is translated into a finite automaton (which is a labeled graph), and then an automata theoretic product is taken between the path network and the automaton from the path expression. Any path on this product automaton between start and accepting states of the automaton is a path that satisfies the specified regular path expression, *Mendelzon and Wood (1995)*.
3. Predefined parameterized event handlers that hide the imperative semantics. For example, a predefined handler “*checkinFillOneLaneAtATime {lane1 lane2 lane3 lane4}*” may be used as an exit handler for a check-in track, that fills the parking lanes ‘lane1’ first, and then ‘lane2’ and so on as the vehicles check in. Such pre-defined procedures are less flexible than an imperative user-written handler but provide a declarative abstraction which reduces modeling effort.

Thus the current design of the operational model may be seen as a partition of the task between (A) built-in features (such as obstacle avoidance and event triggering services), (B) user defined behavior written in the modeling script (C) model data created using sketching features.

3.3 The Data exchange Interface

Helios requires a number of types of input data towards modelling of a simulation scenario. Firstly it requires the layout of the environment expressed as a drawing. Normally a general arrangement (GA) drawing is directly usable if it is available in the AutoCAD-DXF format. If the drawings are too elaborate, they require some simplification. Some additional annotations need to be made in the drawing file (in specially named layers) to specify the bounding polygons of staircases and ramps. Optionally the initial distribution of vehicles (e.g. pre-parked trailers and other vehicles) and tracks may also be done on the drawing. Such annotations are automatically exported into the Helios data files. So, there are two ways of creating Helios annotations - (1) creating within Helios using the sketching interface (2) annotating on a DXF supporting CAD editor such as AutoCAD, IntelliCAD etc.

The basic layout drawing can NOT be built from scratch in Helios, it must come from a drawing file created on a CAD editor.

One can also import colourful and textured 3D geometry files (e.g. given in 3D Studio, DXF etc. formats) for display in Helios. Such models are loaded for display purposes only (e.g. for superposition of the hull, superstructure and the port geometry with the simulation to create a virtual reality (VR) effect).

As regards output, there is no single format that may be stated as the output format for Helios. There are a number of query commands using which the user can get numerical and textual information about the state of the simulation. These queries can be scheduled to be recorded on files either at fixed intervals or in response to certain events or conditions. For example, one might use the query "numberOfVehiclesInCheckInQueue" to find the number vehicles waiting to check in. This query may be added to a so called *observer* in Helios, to display its graph plot against time and to record it to a CSV data file which can be opened on a spreadsheet program for post-processing. An example of such recorded data is shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Performance data recorded on PortSim: two operational alternatives for the early morning (8:00AM) departure, the first one meets the schedule by checking in all passengers 12 minutes before the departure, in the second one it fails to check everyone in.

It is up to the user to select the information to be recorded. One can also save a playback file to enable replay of a completed simulation without having to re-compute the simulation. It also supports export

of the OpenGL frame-buffer into bitmap files for every screen update. This feature came handy in recording the screen animation on a very old computer without 3d graphics accelerator. The exported images for each frame were later collated to form a smooth animation.

Besides exporting the frame-buffer image, vector graphics diagrams (in the FIG format) may also be saved periodically or in response to events. In the vector graphics export mode, a 2D drawing file is exported with colour coded occupants and vehicles marked within the drawing.

To summarize the data exchange interface of Helios-PortSim, the input data can be created using Helios, a text editor (for scripting), and a CAD editor; and there is a wide variety of output options to choose from.

4 Conclusion and Scope for Future Work

The Helios-PortSim tool as described in sections 2 and 3 has been useful in making decisions about the design of port facilities and processes with respect to vehicular operations. It has been efficacious but there still is significant room for improvement.

There are a number of ways in which the Helios-PortSim model can be improved. Firstly it should be possible to make the modelling task largely declarative by providing a parameterized object library for all procedural elements. This should enable the user to pick and place such objects without having to resort to any scripting.

The simulation functionality may also be extended to include additional dynamic models such as (1) multiple ships in the port waters, and (2) container operations involving cranes.

The kinematical model of vehicles can be improved further by introducing the non-holonomic motion planning as described in *Murray and Sastry (1993)*.

Currently the simulation data for a given simulation project resides in multiple files. It would be more convenient to the user if there is a single database file that contains all the data pertaining to a project.

It would also be useful to improve the 3d content base for the simulation. For example, the current generic vehicles may be replaced by fully textured realistic meshes. We could provide a 3d object gallery to drag and drop to help the users easily make the simulation visuals more convincing.

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The Effect of Synthesis Model Uncertainties in Ship Design Optimization

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Abstract

Multi-disciplinary analysis and design optimization allow designers to break away from the traditional design spiral approach and focus on searching the design space for the best overall design rather than considering best discipline-specific designs. The effects of uncertainty in the disciplinary calculations of complex design simulation models are considered. Uncertainty is quantified using a “confidence of success” calculation that is developed based on the Mean Value method. The confidence of success is the probability that a design will satisfy all constraints and meet performance objectives. Multiple sources of uncertainty are quantified and represented in a ship synthesis model. Optimizations using confidence of success as a third objective, in addition to cost and effectiveness, in a multi-objective genetic algorithm are executed. It is demonstrated that designs lying along constraint boundaries, which are typically identified as optimum designs in deterministic design optimizations, likely have a very low chance of being successful.

1. Introduction

This paper presents an optimization tool that might be used during the concept exploration phase of a ship design process. The concepts illustrated here, however, apply to any optimization utilizing a process simulation that may contain uncertainties. In the case of ship design, the simulation, or ship synthesis model, is the aggregate of several disciplinary calculations made to determine the characteristics of a ship possessing a chosen set of attributes. During early stages of design, it is customary to perform these disciplinary calculations using parametric, perhaps regression, analyses of varying accuracy. Decision makers would benefit from having an understanding of how the uncertainties in these disciplinary calculations either compound or cancel in arriving at the ship design characteristics being calculated by their synthesis models.

Further, it is important for them to consider the impact of these uncertainties on the results of optimization algorithms operating on these synthesis models. By the nature of the optimization process, the optimum solution, more often than not, resides along one or more constraint boundaries. If the characteristics being calculated by a model (simulation) are uncertain, what are the chances that those characteristics will actually fall outside of the constraint, in an infeasible region? In the work described below, we have shown that an optimum solution calculated without regard to model uncertainty often has a fairly small chance of being a successful design, i.e., meeting all criteria.

A traditional way of dealing with uncertainty is to introduce margins or safety factors. This approach penalizes all designs and does not allow the designer to identify regions of the design space that may produce more robust designs. It may even occur that the “penalty” being added is used as a virtue by another aspect of the design. It is suggested here that a more appropriate means of treating these uncertainties is to adopt a probabilistic approach throughout the analysis. This approach, if implemented using a brute-force technique such as a Monte-Carlo simulation would add unacceptable computational loads to an optimization. The key to this approach then, is to identify a much simpler calculation technique which will yield sufficiently accurate results.

In the following, we introduce a confidence of success (CoS), which is defined as the probability that a given design meets all objectives and constraints concurrently. It is insufficient to look at each criterion (objective or constraint) and its distribution independently, since all attribute values are generated by the same design choices and thus are interdependent. We accomplish this by first introducing uncertainties in a number of disciplinary calculations in a multidisciplinary ship synthesis

model through the addition of uncertain variables with assumed probability distributions. We then examine the joint probability distribution, in all uncertain variables, of each appropriate ship characteristic determined by the model employing these, now random, disciplinary calculation results to determine what portion of the uncertain variable space satisfies all criteria. This is done using the approximation of the Mean Value Method. The CoS is calculated as the integration of the joint probability of occurrence of designs over the portion of the uncertain variable space satisfying all criteria. CoS merges reliability and robust based design approaches into an uncertainty calculation.

2. Multi-Objective Optimization and Uncertainty

There is typically no single global optimum when performing multi-objective optimization because of tradeoffs between associated objectives. Multi-objective optimization results in a set of Pareto optimal design solutions having the property that, within the feasible portion of the design space (defined by the constraints applied to the design), there exists no other design solution which can improve upon any single objective without decreasing the desirability of at least one other objective, *Parsons and Scott (2004)*. The set of these Pareto optimal solutions forms what is called a Pareto front or non-dominated frontier (NDF). Fig.1 is an example of a Pareto front in a two-dimensional objective space, assuming the objective is to minimize the cost and maximize the effectiveness in a deterministic optimization process. Fig.1 also introduces the concepts of the design variable space, of dimension three here, in which the possible combinations of design variable values reside versus the objective space, of dimension two here, which represents the range of objective values obtained for all combinations of design variable values. Every design solution, \mathbf{S} , in the objective space is represented by one or possibly more vectors, \mathbf{X} , in the design variable space. The Pareto front is marked by the bold line at the boundary between the feasible and infeasible regions in the objective space of Fig.1. In a problem with three objectives, the Pareto front would form a three dimensional surface.

The decision of which member of the Pareto optimal set to choose needs to be made by a decision maker. Attractive designs include those at the extremes of the front and at “knees” in the curve or surface. Designs located at the “knees”, such as the region circled in Fig.1, are of interest because of their sharp increase in, for example, effectiveness with a relatively small increase in cost.

Fig.1: A design point in the design variable space (left), corresponds to a solution in the objective space (right). The Pareto front is emphasized by the bold curve coinciding with part of the boundary between the infeasible and feasible regions in the objective space.

The deterministic optimization considered above does not consider the possibility that the chosen design will actually perform as predicted regarding cost, effectiveness or any of a number of constraints imposed on the design. Due to uncertainties associated with the problem definition or the synthesis model, there is a risk that the chosen design may under perform in terms of effectiveness, cost more than predicted and/or not meet the constraint requirements. As a result, there is a need to address uncertainty in any design optimization problem to produce both effective and reliable results.

If the chosen design is deemed too risky, it is not sufficient to simply select a more reliable design from the two-dimensional Pareto front. If uncertainty has not been included in the optimization process, there may not even be a more reliable design on the Pareto front. More reliable designs might be located well below the Pareto front in the feasible region of the objective space of Fig.1. Therefore, the optimization process should be performed with a constraint on uncertainty, or uncertainty must be treated as a third objective. Confidence of Success (CoS) is defined here as the probability that a specific design will satisfy all constraints and meet performance objectives, and it is treated as a third objective in this work. With CoS included as a third objective, the designer has the ability to make design decisions that are effective, efficient, and reliable. A sample Pareto front in three objective (effectiveness, cost, and CoS) space is shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2: A hypothetical three objective Pareto front with the objectives to minimize cost and maximize effectiveness and CoS. Encircled is the same knee as in Fig.1, yielding 10% CoS. In this situation, increasing cost or reducing effectiveness raises CoS.

Sources of uncertainty are abundant. They may arise from both qualitative and quantitative sources. This work focuses on the quantitative modeling and simulation uncertainties that occur due to discrepancies in computational predictions. These are the uncertainties associated with, perhaps parametric, disciplinary calculations that may propagate through multi-disciplinary models due to the interdependence of modules. The computational output of one discipline is typically the input of another disciplinary calculation, allowing the initial uncertainty to transform and interact with other uncertainties as it progresses through the model.

There are a number of approaches to handling system uncertainty, *Haldar and Mahadevan (1999)*, *Koch and Cofer (2000)*. Most of these can be classified into three categories: random sampling, design of experiments (DOE), and sensitivity based approaches. Which is the most efficient approach is strongly problem dependent, as there is typically a trade-off between accuracy and computational cost. For the multi-objective design optimization of a multi-disciplinary ship synthesis model, the

system uncertainty approach of choice must have a low computational cost due the computational burden associated with a complex model and genetic optimization algorithm (GA). Therefore, the CoS calculation in this work is based only on the first steps of the Mean Value method (MV), i.e., a first order Taylor series expansion, classifying it as a sensitivity based approach. This method is discussed in greater detail below.

A method familiar to most is the Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) or simple random sampling. MCS is implemented by randomly simulating a design or process, given the stochastic properties of one or more random variables, with focus on characterizing the statistical nature of the responses of interest, *Handscomb and Hammersley (1964)*. This simulation method has long been considered to be the most exact method for calculation of probability distributions of responses from systems dealing with uncertainty. However, MCS typically calls for many thousands of system evaluations; thus for a time consuming analysis, MCS becomes impractical. MCS will be employed to verify the results obtained below from MV.

3. Mean Value Methods

Mean Value methods utilize most probable point (MPP) analysis, and, being based on first order Taylor series expansions, are appropriate for well-behaved response functions that are computationally intensive, *Thacker et al. (2001)*. Mean value methods approximate a cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the response function (here a model output), which can be differentiated to obtain a probability density function (PDF). In the analysis, a response, Z , is defined as a function of the uncertain random variables, \mathbf{X} . Each point in the design space spanned by \mathbf{X} has a specific probability density according to the joint probability density function (JPDF) of the uncertain random variables (RVs). Therefore every response value $Z(\mathbf{X})$ has an associated probability density, *Mavris et al. (1997)*.

The failure surface or the limit state, g , for an arbitrary response function Z is defined as:

$$g = Z(\mathbf{X}) - Z_{ls} = 0$$

where the limit state value Z_{ls} is a particular value of Z . The limit state function (LSF) is defined such that $g(\mathbf{X}) = 0$ is a boundary that divides the random variable space into two regions, failure/infeasible and safe/feasible, see Fig.3. We have now introduced a third space, the random variable space, that spans the range of possible values taken by the quantities we are considering to be uncertain.

The most probable point (MPP) is defined as the point along the LSF where the uncertain variable combination yields the highest probability of occurrence. For a JPDF of two standard normal and independent variables it is obvious that the point of minimum distance from the origin to the LSF represents the most probable combination of the random variables, and is therefore named the most probable point, as seen in Fig.3, *Thacker et al. (2001)*. For nonlinear limit states, identifying the MPP becomes an optimization problem in itself. Non-normally distributed random variables may be transformed into normal form with some distortion of the LSFs. Once the MPP has been identified, it can be used as a basis to develop approximate polynomial LSFs.

Assuming the response function, Z , is “smooth” or can be “smoothed” and that a first order Taylor series expansion of Z exists at the mean, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_x$, of the uncertain variables \mathbf{X} , the response function Z can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} Z(\mathbf{X}) &= Z(\boldsymbol{\mu}_x) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial Z}{\partial X_i} \right)_{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \cdot (X_i - \mu_{xi}) + H(\mathbf{X}) \\ &= a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cdot (X_i - \mu_{xi}) + H(\mathbf{X}) \\ &= Z_{MV}(\mathbf{X}) + H(\mathbf{X}) \end{aligned}$$

where the derivatives are evaluated at the mean of the uncertain variables, μ_{x_i} is the mean of uncertain variable i , and n is the number of uncertain variables. $Z_{MV}(\mathbf{X})$ represents the MV method function and is the sum of the first order terms only; $H(\mathbf{X})$ represents the remaining higher order terms. The coefficient a_0 is simply the expected value of Z at the mean values, and the coefficients a_i are generally computed using numerical differentiation with a minimum of $(n+1)$ Z -function evaluations, *Wu et al. (1990)*. Since the function $Z_{MV}(\mathbf{X})$ is linear and explicit, a CDF can be calculated and differentiated to obtain a PDF. Fig.3 shows the JPDF of two independent standard normal variables. The MPP, the exact LSF of a typical response function Z , and the MV approximated LSF of Z are plotted. The approximate LSF is used to define the infeasible region of the design space, which has been cut away from the JPDF, leaving the feasible region and appropriate probability density only.

Fig.3: JPDF $f(\mathbf{x})$ of two standard normal variables. The MV approximate LSF is used to define the infeasible region of the variable space, from which the JPDF has been cut off. Also plotted are the exact LSF and the MPP, after *Thacker et al. (2001)*.

In the calculation of CoS, this procedure is followed for each design criterion. Each resulting LSF may remove another section of the RV space. The integration of the JPDF over the remaining RV space yields the probability of simultaneously meeting all criteria. The result of this integration is the confidence of success.

4. Ship Synthesis Model and Genetic Algorithm Optimizer

The multi-disciplinary ship synthesis model used in this project has been under development for several years. The history of its development, additions, and modifications can be found in *Brown and Thomas (1998)* and *Stepanchick and Brown (2006)*. This particular ship synthesis model was constructed to represent modern United States Navy (USN) surface combatants (SC) such as Ticonderoga Class Cruisers (CG), Arleigh Burke Class large multi-role Destroyers (DDG), and Oliver Hazard Perry Class Frigates (FFG). The DDG 51 Arleigh Burke was selected as a model evaluation DP and was chosen as the initial design in all optimization efforts. It appears multiple times below.

ModelCenter version 6.1, a commercial process integration and design optimization software package from Phoenix Integration, Inc., was used to build and execute this complex ship synthesis model. ModelCenter (MC) provides a visual environment in which design processes can be assembled as a series of linked applications with a single interface in order to easily perform multi-disciplinary analysis. MC automatically connects design data from one application to the next, producing an automated multi-disciplinary design environment.

A multi-objective genetic optimization algorithm is chosen for this work. A genetic algorithm uses evolutionally processes drawn from Darwin's "survival of the fittest" such as reproduction, crossover, and mutation to improve upon an initial population of designs, *Brown and Thomas (1998)*. Since

genetic algorithms do not need to calculate gradients, they have the ability to treat discrete choice design variables. This work uses Phoenix Integration’s multi-objective genetic optimization plug-in, Darwin version 1.1.3. The results presented below make use of Darwin’s Multiple Elitist selection scheme with a population size of 300 and 100 designs preserved between generations for crossover and mutation.

The complete model is comprised of an input module, primary ship synthesis model modules, a constraint module, three objective modules, a numerical differentiation calculation, and the genetic algorithm optimization module. The primary ship synthesis model is comprised of several interlinked disciplinary modules, each containing considerable detail that will not be discussed here. The primary ship synthesis modules include combat systems, propulsion, hull form, electric power, resistance, weight and stability, space required, space available, tankage, feasibility, cost, and effectiveness.

Table I: Surface Combatant Design Variables

Variable	Description	Type	DDG 51	min	max
LWL	Length at Waterline (m)	Continuous	141.8	125.0	160.0
B	Beam at Waterline (m)	Continuous	17.9	15.0	20.0
D10	Hull Depth at Station 10 (m)	Continuous	12.8	10.0	14.0
T	Design Draft (m)	Continuous	6.1	5.0	7.0
Cp	Prismatic Coefficient	Continuous	0.607	0.550	0.700
Cx	Maximum Section Coefficient	Continuous	0.818	0.700	0.900
Crd	Raised Deck Coefficient	Continuous	0.8	0.7	1.0
VD	Deckhouse Volume (m ³)	Continuous	5400	3000	6000
CDHMAT	Deckhouse Material Type	Discrete	1	1	2
BALtype	Ballast Type	Discrete	1	0	1
PSYS	Propulsion System	Discrete	3	1	17
GSYS	Generator System	Discrete	1	1	8
Ts	Stores Duration (days)	Discrete	60	45	60
Ncps	Collective Protection System	Discrete	1	0	2
CMan	Manning Reduction Factor	Continuous	1	0.5	1.0
AAW	Anti-Air Warfare System	Discrete	3	1	10
ASUW	Anti-Surface Warfare System	Discrete	1	1	4
ASW	Anti-Submarine Warfare System	Discrete	2	1	9
NSFS	Naval Surface Fire Support System	Discrete	1	1	2
CCC	Command, Control, Communications System	Discrete	2	1	5
SEW	Signal & Electronic Warfare System	Discrete	2	1	2
GMLS	Guided Missile Launch System	Discrete	2	1	7
LAMPS	Light Airborne Multi-Purpose System	Discrete	2	1	3
SDS	Self-Defense System	Discrete	2	1	3
Ndegaus	Degaussing System	Discrete	1	0	1
Nfins	Number of Pairs of Fins	Discrete	0	0	1

Table II: Surface Combatant Design Constraints

Parameter	Constraint	Type	Boundary
Ata	Total Available Area	Minimum	Dynamic
Ada	Available Deckhouse Area	Minimum	Dynamic
Vs	Sustained Speed	Minimum	28 knots
Pbpengend	Brake Propulsion Power at Endurance Speed	Minimum	Dynamic
KWg	Generator Electric Power	Minimum	Dynamic
Cgmbmin	Minimum GM to Beam Ratio	Minimum	0.05
Cgmbmax	Maximum GM to Beam Ratio	Maximum	0.15
D10	Hull Depth at Station 10	Minimum	Dynamic
E	Endurance Range	Minimum	3500 nm

Each ship design is defined by 26 design variables (DV), as listed in Table I, and 21 fixed input parameters, which are set as either fixed constants or fixed constraints in accordance with the DDG 51. The nine constraints defined in this ship synthesis model are listed in Table II. There are four static constraints and five dynamic constraints. Static constraints are constant for every ship design, while dynamic constraints move their boundaries based on other DP attributes.

4.1 Objectives

The two original objectives in the ship design optimization are to minimize total ownership cost (CTOC) and to maximize effectiveness. To these, the COS is added as a third objective. The CTOC is weight-based with consideration of inflation and other financial effects, *Good and Brown (2006)*.

Effectiveness is quantified by a parameter called the Overall Measure of Effectiveness (OMOE). OMOE is a quantitative measure of a ship's ability to perform over a range of mission types and mission scenarios, *Good and Brown (2006)*. OMOE ranges from 0.0 to 1.0: an OMOE of 0.0 represents the least effective ship design possible in the given design space; an OMOE of 1.0 represents the most effective ship design possible. In practice, however, there may not be a feasible design with an OMOE close to 1.0. Definition of the OMOE is structured as a multi-attribute decision problem, and a Multi-Attribute Value function approach is used to develop a measure spanning several mission types. Specific measures of performance (MOPs) are developed and values of performance (VOPs) are set to specify the value of a particular MOP to a specific mission area for a particular mission type. USN defense policy and goals, projected operational environment (POE) and threat, mission need, modeling and simulation, war gaming results, and expert opinion are only some of the inputs that must be considered when developing an OMOE metric. MOPs are determined based on DVs and required operational capabilities. Goal and threshold values or options are identified for each MOP, and MOP weights are calculated using pair-wise comparison and expert opinion. The dot product of the MOP weight vector and a specific VOP vector generates an OMOE value for a particular ship design, *Brown and Thomas (1998)*

$$OMOE = \sum_i w_i VOP_i(MOP_i)$$

It should also be noted that 9 of the 20 MOPs used in this work originate directly from combat system selection, and they represent almost 77% of the OMOE metric. A weight-based cost algorithm does not adequately reflect the cost variation of designs with various combat system combinations but is the only cost algorithm available to this study. Consequently, the results shown below should be considered illustrative only. They may not accurately reflect realistic design choices.

The CoS computation is divided into two distinct steps, a numerical differentiation calculation to obtain the required criteria responses and a probability calculation that trims away the infeasible portion of the JPFD. The optimization process is accelerated by setting CoS equal to zero for all deterministically infeasible DPs, eliminating the need for excessive CoS calculations. Although it is possible that a deterministically infeasible DP has a reasonable CoS, it is unlikely that any decision maker would choose a deterministically infeasible design. All nine constraints and both the cost and overall effectiveness objectives are used as criteria for the CoS evaluation. The cost and effectiveness limit state functions are defined such that designs with costs exceeding a specified percentage of the deterministic CTOC are excluded as are designs with effectiveness less than another specified percentage of the deterministic OMOE.

5. Introducing Uncertainty

Randomness is assumed to arise only from the embedded uncertainties in the analysis; all input variables are presumed deterministic for each DP. Uncertainties within the analysis arise mainly from the parametric equations located in the primary ship synthesis model modules. Uncertainties were considered in the resistance, weight, center of gravity (KG), endurance range, required area and electrical load. Each uncertain variable Y is modeled through the use of an extra random variable X :

$$Y = \mu_y \cdot (1 + \delta_x \cdot X)$$

where $X \in N(0,1)$ and is independent of any other RV, μ_y is the mean value (i.e., the deterministically calculated value) of the uncertain variable, and δ_x is the coefficient of variation of the uncertain variable.

The resistance calculation is based on the Holtrop-Mennen regression equation, *Holtrop (1984)*, with a wave resistance correction, *Good (2006)*. This calculation was verified by comparison to match runs of the USN’s tool for early-stage ship design, ASSET. Match run outputs have been previously adjusted to accurately represent the actual characteristics of particular ships. Match runs were obtained for Arleigh Burke Class Flight I and Flight IIa Destroyers, the Oliver Hazard Perry Class Frigate and a Ticonderoga Class Cruiser. The standard deviation of total resistance was found to be 7.98% and thus δ for uncertain resistance was set to 0.0798.

The Weight and Stability Module evaluates SWBS weight groups to calculate ship weight. Each SWBS weight group calculation is the sum of smaller subsystem weights calculated using parametric equations, or a parametric equation itself. This fact combined with weight’s significant impact on the weight-based cost algorithm makes weight a critical uncertainty to analyze. Since each SWBS weight group behaves differently, seven new RVs would be required to model SWBS weight groups 100-700 with complete accuracy. However, similarities between a few of these weight groups allow weight to be analyzed with three RVs as shown below in Table III. These three coefficients of variation were calculated from the same set of ASSET match runs. Also, it should be noted that in the first model execution involving only two RVs, total lightship weight is summarized in one RV with a coefficient of variation of 10%.

Table III: SWBS Weight Group RVs

Random Variable	δ Value	Description
W16	9.94%	SWBS 100 & 600 weight groups
W235	5.74%	SWBS 200, 300, & 500 weight groups
W47	9.65%	SWBS 400 & 700 weight groups

Although the two most significant sources of uncertainty are bare hull resistance and weight, there are still other critical sources of uncertainty embedded within the ship synthesis model. The most important sources of uncertainty are those that have a direct impact on the CTOC and OMOE objectives as well as the nine design constraints. A few of the calculated parameters that directly affect the nine design constraints are identified below in Table IV. Coefficients of variation were calculated based on ASSET match runs where data was available or assumed to be 10%.

Table IV: Other Sources of Uncertainty

Random Variable	δ Value	Description
Atr	10.00%	total required area
E	10.00%	Endurance range
KG	3.65%	KG value
KWmflm	13.20%	maximum functional electric load

6. CoS Validation

Properties of the CoS calculation are examined considering only the two most important sources of uncertainty, resistance and weight. For these calculations, the weight uncertainties are combined into a single RV representing total lightship weight. The MV method used to calculate CoS will work best for responses that vary slowly with the uncertain variations of the RVs locally within the design space. Criteria response behavior was investigated at a selection of feasible DPs and was found to be nearly linear over the range of interest for most of the criteria that depend on the RVs. Exceptions were OMOE, which was discontinuous due to its stepwise definition and two continuous but non-linear responses; sustained speed and endurance range. While the first order series expansion of the MV is expected to have significant problems approximating a response surface to the discontinuous

OMOE, it was found that the OMOE objective has a very low standard deviation and that, within one standard deviation of the deterministic mean, the OMOE response is well behaved for most DPs. It was also found that the LSF for OMOE is rarely in effect, that is, the OMOE LSF rarely eliminates any designs. As a result, the OMOE approximation error was judged to be acceptable.

An evaluation of the variability of CTOC and OMOE at the DDG 51 DP showed that, for CTOC, a one standard deviation departure from the deterministic value represented a 2.74% departure from the deterministic value while a 1.58% departure from the deterministic value of the OMOE represented two standard deviations. These percentage departures are used to set the LSFs for CTOC and OMOE. A full calculation of CoS was performed for the DDG 51 DP and the results are compared to a 100,000 sample Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) in Table V. Percentages represent the probability of feasibility for each specific criterion. As expected, the OMOE error is the largest but the error in the overall CoS calculation is only 0.33%.

Table V: CoS Calculation compared to MCS for DDG 51 DP

Criterion	MCS (%)	CoS (%)	Error (%)
CTOC	84.25	84.40	0.15
OMOE	88.67	84.05	-4.62
Ata	77.83	78.30	0.47
Ada	100.00	99.99	-0.01
Vs	100.00	99.99	-0.01
Pbpend	100.00	99.99	-0.01
KWg	100.00	99.99	-0.01
Cgmbmin	99.89	99.88	-0.01
Cgmbmax	100.00	99.99	-0.01
D10	100.00	99.99	-0.01
E	75.73	75.60	-0.13
CoS	53.56	53.89	0.33

This agreement can be visualized by overlaying the MCS distribution with the MV approximated LSFs, Fig.4. Fig.4 shows the two-dimensional RV subspace spanned by the standard normal RVs. The bare hull resistance and total weight means are located at zero, and each unit away from the mean represents one standard deviation. This design subspace is scattered with the solutions produced from the MCS; the feasible solutions are marked with a black 'x' and the infeasible solutions are marked with a gray '+.' Those approximated constraint and objective LSFs from the CoS calculation that lie in the design subspace domain have been superimposed on the scatter plot. The approximated constraint LSFs follow the edges of the infeasible regions very well, and only the E and Ata LSFs are active. The two approximated objective LSFs can also be superimposed on the scatter plot to show the region used for the actual CoS percentage calculation. The OMOE LSF is slightly active in this regard. The CTOC LSF is also shown but is not a factor in the CoS calculation. These approximated LSFs are determined from only three model evaluations.

6. Multi-Objective Genetic Optimization (MOGO) Calculation

The first example calculation done with the ship synthesis model and optimizer described above uses only the resistance and the single lightship weight uncertainties. The analysis was performed on a PC with a 2.66 GHz CPU and 1.0 GB of RAM. The optimizer terminated after 46.5 hours or 166 generations due to lack of improvement. A total of 49,800 individual design variable combinations were evaluated of which, 43,037 were deterministically infeasible and 6,763 were deterministically feasible. With three model evaluations being required for the feasible DPs, for which the CoS calculation was made, the total number of design evaluations was 63,326. This represents a 27% increase in the number of model evaluations over an optimization considering the same number of DPs without the CoS calculation, however, due to overhead savings in the extra CoS model evaluations, the time increase was only 18%.

Fig.4: Monte Carlo simulation determination of feasibility vs. mean Value approximation of limit state functions. Also shown are the approximations of limit state functions for CTOC and OMOE.

The calculation resulted in a three-dimensional non-dominated frontier made up of 225 Pareto optimal design solutions. While it is difficult to visualize the front in a static two dimensional plot, it is useful to present such a figure. Fig.5 shows the Pareto optimal designs in the three-dimensional objective space along with a designation of a “Best DP”. Of course, the designer’s choice of design from among the Pareto optimal DPs is highly subjective and may be based on a number of unquantifiable preferences. Our designation of a “Best DP” means only that this is the point that yields the highest objective ratios for all possible objective combinations concurrently; OMOE/CTOC, CoS/CTOC, and OMOE·CoS. Combining these yields the definition of a quantity we are calling *Fitness*;

$$Fitness = \left(\frac{OMOE \cdot CoS}{CTOC(\$M)} \right) \cdot 1000$$

Our “Best DP” is thus the point among the Pareto optimal set that has the greatest *Fitness*. Table VI gives the objective values of the best individual objective points, the “Best DP”, and the DDG 51 DP. The DDG 51 DP has a relatively high OMOE due to its emphasis on combat systems. While the DDG 51 DP lies on this particular Pareto front, subsequent optimization runs did find other combinations of DVs that gave performance increases in all three objectives over the DDG 51. Many other discovered designs offer significant cost savings over the DDG 51 as well as an increase in CoS.

Two features of Fig.5 need to be mentioned. First, the Pareto optimal DPs did not spread out well over the Pareto front. Modifications to the optimization have been developed to encourage a more uniform distribution of points across the front however they will not be discussed in this paper. A second, and more important feature of Fig.5 are the points lying along the CoS = 0 plane. These are DPs that are slightly deterministically infeasible, i.e., the deterministic value of one or more of the constraint criteria values falls slightly outside of the constraint boundary. However, because the optimizer adds a 5% tolerance to these boundaries and these DPs do not exceed the constraint values by an amount that is greater than that tolerance, they are treated as feasible by the optimizer and retained in the optimization. On the other hand, the CoS calculation procedure does not employ such a tolerance, identifies the DP as deterministically infeasible, and does not perform the CoS calculation but sets CoS = 0 to accelerate the optimization process. These DPs do not actually have a zero chance of success but the actual CoS values are small. Attention is drawn to these points here but they will be discussed in detail in the next section.

Fig.5: Three-dimensional scatter plot of Pareto optimal design solutions. CoS obtained assuming uncertain bare hull resistance and lightship weight. Choice of “Best DP” is explained in the text. Points lying closer to the foreground are shown larger.

Table VI: Objective values of selected design solutions

Solution	CTOC(\$M)	OMOE	CoS
Lowest CTOC DP	720.7	0.2420	0.3052
Highest OMOE DP	1364.9	0.7921	0.2331
Highest CoS DP	1001.5	0.3525	0.8246
“Best” DP (see text)	1081.2	0.6928	0.6833
DDG 51 DP	1455.8	0.7685	0.4276

Fig.5 is very hard to interpret in printed form, and a surface fitted to the Pareto front may be misleading and hard to translate into specific design solutions. The set of designs on the Pareto front does not form a continuous surface since many of the DVs are discrete. Points along a surface fitted to the Pareto front do not always correspond to a feasible design solution; only the actual design solutions in the objective space have a feasible set of DVs in the design space. Fig.6, a scatter plot of the Pareto optimal design solutions in two-dimensional CTOC and OMOE space, with CoS indicated by marker, may be easier to interpret. All design solutions with a CoS less than 50% were marked as “low” CoS level because it is unlikely that any designer would be interested in a solution that would most likely not meet requirements and/or performance objectives. (Note that this includes the DDG 51 DP in this model.) It is also unlikely that any designer would be interested in a deterministically infeasible solution. For these reasons, “low” CoS level DPs and deterministically infeasible DPs are removed from the scatter plot in Fig.7. The advantage of this two-dimensional scatter plot is that the Pareto fronts at different CoS levels can be better visualized from a plot of the DPs themselves; a surface or contour is not needed. Several possible design solutions have been highlighted. This method of examining alternative design choices presents a number of attractive designs to the designer for further analysis.

Fig.6: Pareto optimal design solutions in two-dimensional CTOC and OMOE space, with CoS level categories indicated by marker. The selected design solutions of Table VI are indicated by labels.

Fig.7: Scatter plot of Fig.6 with deterministically infeasible and low CoS DPs removed. Possibly attractive points at knees are indicated.

7. The CoS = 0 Designs

Perhaps the most important point of this paper is to be made by considering the DPs lying along the CoS = 0 plane in Fig.5. The process of setting CoS = 0 for deterministically infeasible DPs (as discussed in the previous section) in conjunction with the optimization, effectively sorts out those DPs lying along constraint boundaries and having desirable levels of CTOC and OMOE. Because objective values usually improve as constraint boundaries are approached, this is precisely the type of points sought by a deterministic two-objective optimization considering only CTOC and OMOE. This line of points in the CoS = 0 plane of Fig.5 closely approximates the Pareto front that would be generated by a deterministic optimization process with only CTOC and OMOE as objectives. Such a deterministic optimization process was created for this work by simply eliminating the CoS objective from the three-objective optimization. The remainder of the optimization problem formulation was left unchanged. Fig.8 compares the resulting two-dimensional Pareto front with the deterministically infeasible (CoS = 0) DPs of Fig.5.

The difference in the fronts reflects a real difference in the numerical details of the two optimizations. In the two-objective deterministic optimization, the entire population is pushed to the constraint boundaries as they represent the most desirable designs. In the three-objective optimization considering uncertainty through the CoS calculation, those deterministically infeasible designs found which lie close to constraint boundaries are flagged by having CoS set to zero but they are not exceptionally desirable to the optimization process since it is seeking designs of high CoS as well as desirable values of CTOC and OMOE. The optimizer thus does not probe the constraint boundaries to the extent done in the two-dimensional deterministic optimization but rather encourages the population to spread out into regions of higher CoS. Thus the deterministic optimization finds better designs in terms of CTOC and OMOE but it turns out that all but 2 of the 41 Pareto optimal DPs found by the deterministic optimization are actually deterministically infeasible in the sense of the CoS calculation. An evaluation of the CoS of these 41 DPs was carried out and the results are shown in the histogram of Fig.9.

Fig.8: 2-D objective space comparison of the two-objective deterministic Pareto front with the three-objective deterministically infeasible (CoS = 0) front.

Fig.9: CoS values of the two-objective deterministic Pareto optimal DPs in Fig.8

From these results, it can be seen that an optimization performed without consideration of the inherent uncertainty in the associated simulation pushes the resulting optimal design(s) to the extremes of constraint boundaries where there may actually be little chance of successfully meeting the design criteria.

8. Increasing the Number of Uncertain Quantities

The CoS computation described above was extended to accommodate three and four uncertain quantities at a time. Runs were made considering those sources of uncertainty previously identified in various combinations. The extension of the Taylor series expansion to n RVs requires $n+1$ model evaluations at each DP. The extension of the numerical integration of the JPDF over n dimensions quickly becomes the limiting factor as n increases. The limitation of the 1 GB RAM capacity of the PC being used for this effort precluded calculations of more than 4 uncertain quantities at a time. The resolution of this integration needed to be reduced in order to reach four uncertain quantities. The computational times required for the three and four uncertain quantity cases were 31% and 100% greater than that required for a deterministic calculation evaluating the same number of DPs respectively. The exponential increase in both computational time and memory required means that further extensions of n will require significant computational resources.

9. Conclusions

A method of treating uncertainty in a simulation model and its implementation in a multi-disciplinary, multi-objective ship design optimization has been demonstrated. The technique, which is based on the Mean Value method is shown to be well suited to this application, enabling an accurate evaluation of the confidence of meeting all design criteria, for a given design solution, using only $n+1$ model evaluations where n is the number of uncertain quantities being considered. Treating the confidence of success as an additional objective in a design optimization can give a designer significant insight not afforded by deterministic analyses. Further, it was demonstrated that deterministic optimizations drive optimal solutions to the extremes of constraint boundaries where uncertainties in the model calculations will likely mean that these solutions have a small chance of actually meeting the imposed design criteria. While extension of this technique to consider more than five or six uncertain quantities simultaneously will require significant computational resources, those resources are available and the additional information that would be provided to decision makers is well worth the investment for design projects of any significant magnitude. It is the opinion of the authors that optimization of simulations involving uncertainties may actually lead the designer to make less than wise choices if those uncertainties are not quantified and accurately represented in the analysis.

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Evaluation of Different Control Strategies for Teams of Unmanned Marine Vehicles (UMVs) Comparing the Requirements of Underwater Communication and Navigation in MATLAB® Simulations

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Abstract

The paper gives a review of applications in that Multiple Unmanned Marine Vehicles (MUMVs) shall be employed and their relevance to industrial needs, before describing an autonomous supervisor instance that guarantees the team work of the team members. A realistic software simulator is introduced to compare and evaluate different strategies.

1. The European Research Project GREX: An Overview

1.1. Main purposes of the project

Autonomous vehicles applications have been growing very fast over the last few years following the advent of new innovative technologies which provide high levels of autonomy and reliability. The past decade has witnessed the emergence of autonomous behaviours in single mobile systems, with applications to the safe operation of ground, air, and marine vehicles in the presence of changing and unknown environmental conditions. The experience thus acquired is now steadily being brought to bear on the solutions to far more complex problems that arise when multiple systems must work together. This shift of attention was brought about by the introduction of the concept of multiple autonomous vehicles performing missions cooperatively as an attractive alternative to the traditional single vehicle paradigm.

With the increasing feasibility and the decreasing expense of enabling vehicles, sensors and communication technologies, the interest in multiple vehicles is growing even if many problems have to be still solved to implement robust and high performance schemes for groups of cooperating heterogeneous uninhabited systems. This is specially true in the case of systems designed for underwater operations because of the extremely adverse operating conditions, like lack of reliable communications and navigation.

The multiple vehicle approach offers new emerging capabilities to a number of applications including ocean sampling, mapping, surveillance and communication other than advantages such as increased efficiency, performance, re-configurability of a generic mission. So the use of multiple vehicles for defined tasks is currently an important topic within civil and military robotic research even if all attempts are still in their infancy, as described for example in *Spennberg et al. (2005)*.

It is in this context that a group of leading European autonomous robots manufacturers, researchers, and end-users¹ is working together in the scope of the GREX project, a R&D initiative supported by the European Commission, www.grex-project.eu. The project aims to create a conceptual framework and middleware system to coordinate a group of diverse, heterogeneous robotic vehicles working in cooperation to achieve a practical goal. A selected number of methodologies and systems developed

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under the GREX project will be validated through real tests with Unmanned Marine Vehicles, including Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs), Unmanned Surface Vehicles (ASVs).

GREX proposal brings together experts from different areas to integrate and transfer knowledge and competences developed in the field of control, communications, computing, and networks to the underwater robotics. In fact, GREX consortium intends to significantly advance the field of coordination and control of cooperating unmanned systems developing new paradigms for the safe and high performance management of fleet of unmanned vehicles.

GREX will develop solutions for missions that involve the following two key ingredients:

1. the missions require the use of several autonomous vehicles equipped with appropriate instrumentation,
2. inter-vehicle coordination and mission control are dynamic and highly dependent on the type of information obtained as the missions unfold.

In this way, consortium is going to satisfy the following market needs:

- to extend the complexity of a mission facing problems which cannot be solved by a single system alone,
- to improve the efficiency of a mission from the cost/time point of view and at the same time and to secure a better quality of the results obtained,
- to optimize and eventually to enlarge a pre-existing vehicles fleet.

Considering the above mentioned purposes, GREX is facing the major technological challenges of multi-vehicle scenario developing solutions in the field of control system of multiple vehicles and of underwater communications. The main technical outputs expected by project activities are the following:

- A user interface with underlying middleware to plan and distribute a coordinated mission for heterogeneous vehicle – and for post mission analysis.
- A generic control system for coordinated control of multiple vehicle in an uncertain environment including aspects of swarm navigation.
- A communication middleware, which enables heterogeneous vehicles to communicate with each other by LAN, radio and UAC (underwater acoustic communication)
- An open local communication middleware for inter-module and interprocess communication.

Moreover, to validate the results obtained on site trials will be performed at the end of the project. One of the purposes of GREX project is also to promote the cross-fertilization of ideas between system developers and users and to bring operational needs to bear on the formulation of new problems to solve or new products to develop. Namely, it is the project goal to open the “GREX platform development” to a community of world-wide experts, who thanks to their on-field experience can provide us with a significant contribution for the development of “market-driven” products.

1.2. Aimed Scenarios for GREX Multi Vehicle Missions

Right from the beginning of the project there were concrete definitions of the aimed mission scenarios that would be executable in a better way using a team of cooperating marine vehicles. These scenarios were mainly influenced by the marine scientist from the University of the Azores that participate in the project. Two important aspects were kept in mind when the decisions about the scenarios were made:

- The chosen scenarios should have a close combination to similar relevant applications that are enquired by the industry
- In general, the introduction of new scenarios should be easy as the project intern market analyses will maybe show other demands of the industry.

To execute the challenging team missions, a number of autonomous vehicles must work in cooperation, under high level human supervision. This entails the development of advanced systems for coordinated motion control and navigation in the presence of severe underwater communication constraints, together with the respective software and hardware architectures.

Two of the aimed scenarios are displayed in the following:

Fig.1: GREX missions - Marine habitat mapping (left) and search for hydrothermal vents (right)

Marine Scientists have an enormous interest in a deeper understanding of the distribution of marine habitats to establish sensible approaches to the conservation needs and to facilitate a better management of the marine environment. Hence, the use of marine vehicle teams can optimise the execution of a mapping process and minimize the working time of human operators.

The principle of the scenario is shown in Fig.1 (left). The process is deviated from the classical approach for underwater mapping procedures. The main mapping process is performed by an ensemble consisting of an Autonomous Surface Craft (ASC) and an unmanned underwater vehicle. The underwater vehicle is linked to the ASC with a fibre optic cable, and hence it is referred as Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV), independent from the question whether it is really remotely operated by the ASC or uses own autonomous behaviour to stay always directly under the ASC. Both vehicles perform a lawnmower manoeuvre in the area that shall be mapped. The ROV collects pictures of the seabed and transmits them to the surface craft using the cable connection. The ASC uses a strong radio link to transmit the pictures online to a supply ship or a station on land where the pictures are monitored directly by scientific personal. Whenever they detect an interesting area on the seabed and want to have more data in that specific area, they command an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) to perform a fine scan. One or more AUVs are in stand-by close to the ASC/ROV-combination. They get their orders from the ASC via acoustic communication. Immediately they move to the defined coordinates and perform a mapping manoeuvre collecting data in great detail. The ASC/ROV combination continues on their tracks. The approach leads to a relief of the scientific personal. They can concentrate on the online pictures to find new areas of interest, and they do not need to care about the ongoing fine scan.

Many possible mission scenarios with industrial interest could be similar to the approach described above. The search for several minerals at the seabed can be organised in a comparable way, also the inspection of underwater pipelines .

Fig.1 (right) shows another scenario planned to be realised during the GREX project. In the focus of this mission there are hydrothermal vents that are interesting due to their intriguing ecosystems and

chemosynthetic life forms. Both marine scientists and the biotechnological industry are striving to find and evaluate these natural phenomena. A lot of vents in deep water areas are already known, nevertheless there are strong indications that vents also exist in shallow water at depths of 150 m, e.g. in *Cardigos et al. (2005)*. Teams of underwater vehicles can be used to ease the search for the vents.

The aimed mission consists of two parts. At first, a team of mainly ASVs is in charge to make a survey on the main mission area using acoustic sensors to produce a rough map of the seabed. This data will be analysed by marine scientist after the vehicles have finished the mission execution. Possible smaller inspection areas will be defined using the collected data where the possibilities to find a hydrothermal vent are high. Then a team of AUV equipped with methane sensors approaches these areas and tries to find a trace of the vents that usually produce methane gas. Once an unusual high concentration of methane is detected by the vehicles, gradient methods are used to guide the vehicles along the methane field to areas of higher concentration. Thus, the vent can be localised.

This task is closely related to applications in anti terror warfare, where a team of vehicles shall locate under water explosives attached to a ship-hull or detect under water penetration of harbour areas. Also the search for illegal deposited waste in the water is a possible scenario where the knowledge of this mission can be transferred to.

A generic realisation of the missions in the GREX project will be the base for the possible expansions by new scenarios for industrial applications in the future.

2. An Approach for Coordination and Control of Unmanned Vehicle Teams

In the research on mobile robots and systems there are different approaches for the realisation of the control software. *Albus et al. (1989)* proposed a hierarchical concept. *Brooks (1991)* developed a peripheral concept. The Rational Behaviour Model (RBM) is an often used architecture, described in *Kwak, McGhee, Bihari (1992), Byrnes (1993)*. This hierarchical concept, Fig.2, consists of the three levels 'Strategy', 'Tactic' and 'Execution'. Fig.2 shows also the typical tasks assigned to the levels. The Autopilot belongs to the Executive Level and is directly linked with the actuators of the vehicle. The Tactical Level is responsible for the execution and supervision of the single manoeuvres. The monitoring of the mission plan, adjusting and replanning is performed at the Strategical Level. This architecture has proved itself in prior projects concerning single underwater vehicles, e.g. in *Pfützenreuter (2003)*. Autonomous Marine Vehicles usually have a mission plan, consisting of several manoeuvres that are executed sequentially. This process can be described using the RBM.

Fig.2: Rational Behaviour Model (RBM)

2.1. The concept of the Adaptive Autonomy

The classical understanding of the term 'autonomy' leads to some serious problems, *Glotzbach (2004)*. Especially in vehicle teams, there is a discrepancy between the meaning of 'autonomy' of the

single vehicle and ‘cooperation’ in the team. To become a valid team member, a vehicle must be able to subordinate itself and obey general team commands. Nevertheless, each vehicle will still execute autonomous functions that can not be supervised all the time by a central control instance, due to communication constraints, for instance. *Glotzbach (2004)* suggested the notation ‘Adaptive Autonomy’ to solve this problem. The principle is displayed in Fig.3. The unmanned vehicles are called ‘semi-autonomous’, and they are tagged with an individual ‘Level of Autonomy’.

Fig.3: Adaptive autonomy

An important part of their control software is an adapter that is responsible for the determination of the current Level of Autonomy. This adapter can be realised using different ways like state graph or a fuzzy controller. The values of the vehicle own sensors and the mission plan are the inputs of the adapter that then calculates the current Level of Autonomy. This can be in the complete area between (total) autonomous and tele-operated. Going this way, it is possible to integrate a human operator into the mission of autonomous vehicles. But the operator only needs to interact when his special knowledge and cognition is necessary. Beyond he is relieved from dull and tiring tasks that are executed by the vehicles with a high Level of Autonomy. Theoretically it is also possible that the vehicles raise their Level of Autonomy to reach a safe state if the competence of the operator is unclear due to tiredness or something else or if there is the danger that received commands are not from the operator, but from somewhere else (this may be important in military scenarios).

2.2. Adaptive Autonomy in applications with Multiple Unmanned Marine Vehicles (MUMVs)

In the last chapter we described the problem of the construction of vehicle teams under the aspect of a high single autonomy. It is possible to solve this problem using the concept of the Adaptive Autonomy. A first example was given in *Glotzbach and Wernstedt (2006)*. This approach shall now be expanded.

As described in the last chapter, every vehicle gets a Level of Autonomy like it is displayed in Fig.3. The current Level of Autonomy is calculated by the control software that is able to use the vehicle-internal sensors values, the mission plan and the communication data from other team mates. For the vehicle team, we introduce the notation ‘Team Instance’ that also has a Level of Autonomy. The Team Instance is a metaphor for the software that is necessary to realise the cooperation. This software runs at the hardware of a single, leading vehicle or peripheral at several vehicles. The Level of Autonomy of the Team Instance is designed in the same way as shown in Fig.3. The antilogy between ‘Single Autonomy’ and ‘Cooperation’ is now expressed and simultaneously solved with the different Levels of Autonomy of single vehicles and Team Instance. We will show this in some examples for different cases in real mission scenarios of AUVs:

It is important to keep the limited abilities for communication in mind, especially in underwater scenarios. In general, it can be stated that underwater vehicles need to operate with a higher Level of Autonomy than land vehicles in comparable situations. The movement of an underwater vehicle team in a close formation is shown in Fig.4. As it is displayed in the left part of that figure, the vehicles (only three are displayed here), operate with a very high autonomy level. Every vehicle moves according to the predefined movement data, like coordinates or a path. So the Level of Autonomy of the Team Instance is on a very low level. Its only task is to check the formation pattern in regular time intervals.

Fig.4: Perfect Situation: A Team of AUVs in a coordinated formation

After the detection of discrepancies in the formation by the Team Instance, it is responsible for the rebuilding. Therefore it raises its own autonomy level and lowers the ones of the single vehicles. New movement commands are generated and transferred to the single vehicles. (Fig.5) After the rebuilding of the formation, the old state is re-established. According to the RBM as described before, the Executive-/Autopilot- Layer is responsible for the mentioned action.

Fig.5: AUVs in a disturbed formation

Fig.6 shows another situation in which the interaction of the Team Instance is necessary. In this case, there is an obstacle in the predefined paths of the underwater vehicles. The old formation is dissolved and changed into a line formation. Going this way, the autonomy of the single vehicles is lowered more than in the last example. This leads to an enormous rising of the autonomy level of the Team Instance. Now it is possible to move around the obstacle. This process needs to be coordinated by the Tactical Layer / Manoeuvre Management of the Team Instance according to the RBM.

In some cases it can be necessary that the Team Instance performs an enormous interaction into to autonomy of the single vehicles. Fig.7 shows a situation where one vehicle had a serious accident. The whole mission needs to be cancelled and replanned respectively. The Strategical Layer / Mission Management of the Team Instance is responsible to executed the necessary action. The recovery of

the disabled vessel has the highest priority now. Two team mates surface immediately to inform the operator via radio communication. A third vehicle stays close to the disabled vessel to ease the position finding. In this case, the Team Instance takes nearly the complete autonomy away from the single vehicles by cancelling the mission and defining new mission plans.

Fig.6: A team of AUVs is avoiding an obstacle

Fig.7: Accident of a single vehicle – New Mission Plans

An important aspect of the proposed organisation of underwater vehicle teams is the ability of the single systems to operate with a higher Level of Autonomy over a long time period. This level is lowered only if group specific interactions are necessary. The advantage of this approach is the lower amount of communication that is a main problem in underwater areas, but also needs to be taken into account on land if there are long distances / lots of data / no direct view or something else. Besides, this means that a single system needs to be able to operate in a high Level of Autonomy before it is able to become a member in a described team.

2.3. Realisation of the control strategies: Hierarchical vs. Peripheral Approaches

The described Team Instance can be realised using different approaches. As it was described above for single autonomous vehicles, again it is possible to differentiate between the two main concepts ‘hierarchical’ and ‘peripheral’. It must be kept in mind that the realisation of the autonomy of the single vehicles that will be used in the project was performed in a hierarchical way, as it is very common for Unmanned Marine Vehicles. This realisation shall not be changed in the project. This is an important aspect for the later utilisation of the GREX results: It must be easy to implement other vehicles from different providers in a GREX team without complete changing their current control software. So we assume a hierarchical realisation of the single vehicle’s control software, based on the Rational Behaviour Model as displayed in Fig.2.

Starting from the realisation of the single vehicle’s control software, it is possible also to realize the Team Instance in a hierarchical way. Fig.8 shows an accordant design for three vehicles. The RBM-

design of the single vehicle's control software with the three levels is still visible. Additional, there is the Team Control Software that is also realised according to the RBM. This software runs on the hardware of on certain vehicle that can be tagged as leader. The mission execution follows a strict path: Every vehicle executes its own mission plan. The Autopilot of the Team Instance is responsible to align this process whenever discrepancies between the vehicles are detected. An example was given in Fig.4 and Fig.5. A disturbance of the formation was equalised by accelerating and slowing respectively the particular vehicles. The Team Manoeuvre Management supervises the execution of the current manoeuvre of the Team Mission Plan and interacts in cases of problems, like obstacles. The Team Mission Management is able to change both the Team and the Single Vehicle Mission Plans in cases of severe problems.

Fig.8: Hierarchical Realisation of the Team Instance

With the hierarchical realisation of the Team Control Software, only one certain vehicle is responsible for all team- concerning supervising and commanding. According to the concept of Adaptive Autonomy, this leadership function can be transferred to every vehicle, but there is always one vehicle in charge. This avoids double entendres and guarantees a clear control structure. The disadvantage is that every information need to be transferred to that certain vehicle with can lead to serious problems in underwater missions. As it was described above, there will be one or more surface vessels in many GREX missions. Usually, on of these vehicles will be the leader. In this case, it is possible to inform the operator via radio in all cases of severe problems, and the operator can interact whenever this is necessary.

It is also thinkable to realise the Team Instance in a peripheral way, Fig.9. There is no leader in this realisation. Software for team control runs on the hardware of all vehicles all the time. Every vehicle is able to change the Team Mission Plan, whenever accordant cognitions are made by the particular vehicle. Whenever several vehicles are able to communicate with each other, they can coordinate their actions. It is necessary to formulate strict rules to avoid ambiguities. This can be stated as one of the main problems of this approach. The advantage is that the vehicles are able to adapt their behaviour to the current local situation in an optimal way. If several vehicles are far away from the others and communication becomes difficult, there is no need to communicate with the vehicles in great distance. Only the vehicles that are close to each other will communicate to coordinate their actions. When they

go back to the rest of the team, it is possible to perform a team- internal coordination between all vehicles.

Comparing both described approaches it can be stated that they lead to very different kinds of teams with variable behaviour. The hierarchical approach creates clear structures for monitoring and commanding, but it also makes great demands on the communication abilities, as on certain vehicle must always be informed about all current situations in the team. Using a peripheral approach, the vehicles can adapt the communication needs to the current situation. This is a great advantage of this way. On the other hand, the missing of clear structures can cause a lot of problems.

Fig8: Peripheral Realisation of the Team Instance

We propose to differentiate between both approaches by using different names for the particular team. The notation 'Team' is used as an umbrella term, Fig.10. Taken from the biological archetypes, the team with a hierarchical structure is named 'pack'. We propose the name 'swarm' for teams with a peripheral control software. Both principles were used for different applications with teams of mobile systems and vehicles, e.g. *Glotzbach (2004)* for a hierarchical realisation of a team of small mobile robots. Peripheral organised teams can often be found in the simulation of ant swarms, especially for optimisation tasks, like described in *Dorigo et al.(1996)*. These peripheral realisations often contain evolutionary- or stochastic- based control strategies. This may lead to the lost of several systems which is no problem in simulations, for example to solve optimisation tasks. In GREX missions, the most important aspects will be the safe, collision- free execution of the mission and the recovery of all vehicles. Also for juristic reasons in future applications, analytical structure are preferred to stochastic- based ones. All in all it can be stated that both hierarchical and peripheral realisations offers both advantages and disadvantages. The optimal way for realisation may be found somewhere in between those ways to get clear defined structures and guaranteed safety aspects as well as an approach that can deal with the given constraints in the marine environment.

To be able to evaluate different approaches for control software, a high-level software simulator will be developed within the GREX project. This simulator need to consider all the described environmental constraints and the real behaviour of the vehicles. With the use of this simulator, it must be possible to estimate the eligibility of different control structures according to their requirements in the amount of communication and the accuracy of team navigation. The simulator shall be developed according to the future realisation of the vehicle teams so that the original software

can be evaluated prior to the experiments in laboratory and the sea. With the simulator it shall be possible to continue the research in the area of Multiple Unmanned Marine Vehicles within the GREX project (for example online mission replanning) and beyond. We will describe the structure of the simulator in the following chapter.

Fig.9: Different kinds of Teams in the area of unmanned vehicles

3. Description of the High-Level Software Simulator for Team Mission of Heterogeneous Marine Vehicles.

The simulator which is introduced in this section is created for the development and the test of the separate algorithms for control and navigation of cooperating underwater vehicles. Moreover, it should allow investigating possible strategies for an efficient guidance of a team of underwater vehicles. In the following sections the concept of the simulator will be introduced generally. A description in detail of the several algorithms of the simulator would exceed the volume of this paper. Therefore only the model of the controlled vehicle behaviour (marked green in Fig.12), which is a part of the vehicle module, will be described in detail.

3.1. Structure of the simulator

The simulator consists of the several vehicle modules and an environmental module. Through the object oriented programming in C++ the simulator can work either under MATLAB[®]/Simulink[®] or as a stand alone program. In the first case, a simulation system consisting of the separate blocks for the particular vehicles of the team and for the environmental module will be created and linked together in Simulink[®]. In the second case when the simulator works as an independent program, the separate vehicle modules will be created at the program start and will be assigned to the environmental module. The MATLAB[®] environment makes it possible

- to evaluate the tests very easily and to present the results under MATLAB[®],
- to connect to the Virtual Reality Toolbox from Simulink[®] for visual evaluations,
- to create a structure of test scenarios easily with the block construction procedure supported from Simulink[®] and
- to use all libraries available in Simulink[®].

Fig.10 shows that a data transfer exists only between the separate vehicle modules and the environmental module. Hence, only the data telegrams sent from the vehicles will be delivered to the

environmental module. This module stores the incoming data telegrams in a queue together with the position and the attitude of the vehicle as well as the time of the transmission. Furthermore, the environmental module includes the correct navigation data of all vehicles (position, location) in each time step. In each time step the data telegrams waiting in the queue are checked if a transmission to a separate vehicle must be carried out depending on the maximum transmitting range, the position and the attitude of the transmitting and the receiving vehicle. Moreover, the environmental data like sea current, altitude over ground and concentration will be transmitted to the separate vehicles in each time step depending on the position of the vehicle.

Fig.10: Principal structure of the simulator

Fig.11: Components of the vehicle module

3.2. Vehicle Module

The vehicle module contains modules for team control and navigation as well as for communication which are working together with the internal vehicle control over a vehicle specific interface (the four yellow blocks in Fig.12). The internal control of the vehicle simulates the behaviour of the vehicle in dependence to the received guidance data like a manoeuvre list or a target position. In order to realise this actually as a sub module, the simulation of the controlled vehicle behaviour (the green block in Fig.12) is integrated in addition to the error model for the navigation.

A demand on the technical realisation of the vehicle module is the consistent integration of the C++ code for the modules TeamHandler, TeamNavigation, GREX Interface Module and Communication Module (yellow in Fig.12), which are working as independent programs on the computer units of the vehicles. The used interface design of the separate modules makes this easy. Fig.13 shows this in case of the TeamHandler. For this purpose, basic classes are existing, which define public interfaces (TeamHandler_C, InputProcessor_C, OutputProcessor_C). These classes have common references. The derivations of these classes use the interface definitions shown in Fig.13.

Fig.13: Interface design of the team handler

To integrate the TeamHandler into the simulation only the classes of the data interfaces are deviated from their basic classes and their objects are implemented as s-function of the vehicle module block together with the sub-modules of the TeamHandler. During the translation the separate libraries of the module TeamHandler are integrated into this process. This makes it possible to take over changes in the functionality locally within the TeamHandler code very easily just by a renewed translation of the Simulink®-program. (In the programs which are working in the vehicles the classes which are deviated from the basic classes InputProcessor_C, OutputProcessor_C are extended with the socket functionalities to the communication of the independent working modules.)

3.3. Controlled Vehicle Behaviour

The main requirement in the development of the simulator is to maintain low costs of computation, so that scenarios with several vehicles and long mission periods could be carried out in an acceptable time. Moreover, modelling the controlled vehicle as well as the autopilot dynamics would be an elaborate task. Especially in the project GREX different vehicle types should be considered, which would lead to an extensive modelling effort for each vehicle.

For this reason, the behaviour of the vehicles will be reproduced in a simplistic kinematical model. In this case only the control loop behaviour for the vehicle states roll, pitch, heading and surge will be reproduced with a time delay element corresponding to Fig.14. Therefore, only four parameters (the minimum x_{min} and maximum x_{max} of the state, a time constant T and the maximum rate of change of the state dx_{max}) are necessary to describe the control loop behaviour for each state. The set points w

for the autopilot are the inputs of the model. The output x includes the states of the underwater vehicle such as the position, the attitude and the velocity.

Fig.12: Block diagram of the state control loop

Fig.13: Structure of the controlled vehicle behaviour model

In order to model the guidance tasks like depth, track keeping and distance control, controllers work in combination with an algorithm to compensate the sea current influence. This is possible by using the known sea current. The compensation of the sea current convert the desired set point values like course or speed over ground in the effective set points of the vehicle states. Fig.15 shows the hierarchical structure of the controlled vehicle behaviour model.

4. Conclusion

The European research project GREX is one of the first steps towards a commercial realisation of cooperating unmanned marine vehicles. The project will deliver a generic solution for example scenarios with predefined vehicles that will be able to be transferred to other marine vessels and new tasks. In this paper, we provide an overview of the development of the control software that is responsible to guarantee the cooperation between the vehicles that have by now only single autonomous abilities. The understanding of autonomy as an adaptive term allows it to solve the antagonism between 'autonomous' and 'cooperating'. The environmental constraints in marine missions deliver a special challenge for the design of the control structure. Different realisations are thinkable, whereas the question whether the control software has a hierarchical or a peripheral structure is one of the most important issues. First activities seem to advise the usage of a mixture of both structures to meet both the requirements of the existing constraints and the needs of clear structures and safety procedures. To find the optimal way between a hierarchical and a peripheral solution, we will employ a high-level software simulator for the testing of different realisations. This simulator considers all relevant aspects of the marine environment, especially in the areas of communication and navigation. The structure of the simulator follows the original realisation of the vehicle team, and the simulator will also be used to evaluate the control software before it will be tested in laboratory tests and in the sea. Furthermore, the simulator will be a good base for continuative research in the area of Multiple Unmanned Marine Vehicles whose importance in the international domain of both science and economy can be expected to raise strongly in the near future.

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From Basic Design to Strength Assessment – CAD-CAE integration

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Abstract

We consider integration between computer aided design (CAD) and computer aided engineering (CAE). We define and implement an application protocol interface (API) using XML schema and standard XML services embedded in our Microsoft development platforms. In order to perform strength assessment the design model must be simplified. This is a difficult process which we handle by means of a semi-automated system that we call “the idealization toolbox” (IDTB). The IDTB consists of an API derived from the schema, transformations that define idealizations, and a part library that consists of a set of parameterized structural objects that can be defaults for structural details in the vessel. In the current paper we concentrate on the application protocol, and on the idealization strategy we employ.

1. Introduction

In this paper we consider CAD-CAE integration and describe how we currently export from an early design system – NED – to a CAE system based on engineering concepts– SESAM Genie – for strength assessment. NED is short for Nauticus Early Design and is a CAD tool tailor-made for early design. SESAM Genie, a general design application for plates, curved shells and 3d frame structures, has become a leading design tool in several fields of modelling, including 3D frame structures and stiffened plate/shell structures.

2. CAD-CAE integration

2.1. CAD-CAE integration – the problem

It is assumed that the user creates a model in a CAD tool and then exports the model and the associated properties to a CAE system. There are two main problems in this approach: i) to represent the geometry in a practical way and ii) the required simplification of the model when it is transferred to strength assessment.

In addition, there are several data consistency issues and problems, and exceptions due to system failures, which we do not consider in this paper. Robust and efficient solutions to these are, however, essential for a successful system.

2.2. Application protocols and a CAD-CAE integrator concept

In order to obtain a robust and efficient export of structural data we define and implement an API. The API concept is shown in Fig.1. We use XML schema to define the API.

An important issue in the development of an integrator is the transformation from the internal object model to a model that is convenient for exchange of data between applications and thus may serve as an integrator (i.e. API). We call this new integrator model *the exchange model*. Notice that the exchange model does not contain the complete internal object model, but does only contain data of global interest. That is, we assume that the exchange model describes the structure and the format of the data to be exchanged. This means that we so far have an insufficient model if we aim at a common understanding of data that is exchanged between some collaborating applications. Thus, we need another model that, in addition to what does the exchange model, describes how to interpret the data. We call this model *the reference model*, and by means of this model data is converted to information. Thus, the reference model can be viewed as a specialization of the exchange model. In other words,

the reference model inherits the exchange model and adds semantics to enable interpretation of the data that is exchanged between collaborating applications.

Fig.1: The CAD-CAE integrator concept.

We assume further that all entities in the reference model are specializations of at least one entity in the exchange model, and that all attributes present in the reference model are present in the exchange model. That all attributes must be present in the exchange model is obvious since any data item must be represented in the instance. The reference model in turn inherits all entities and attributes from the exchange model and provides a restricted interpretation compared to the exchange model by enforcing constraints on the behaviour.

The main objective of the API development can now be summarised as: For two applications that support the same reference model we expect that the same semantical understanding is present and that they can collaborate in the same manner as old fashioned point-to-point integration according to the rules described in the reference model. This usage of the two models is shown in Fig.1.

2.3. Geometry representation

After some internal DNV Software studies we have, for the time being, concluded that no general standard for exchange of geometry and topology does satisfy our needs. Therefore, we have decided to embed geometrical data into the XML data sets as CDATA sections that contain ACIS¹ representations of the geometry. The embedded geometry data can be referenced, i.e. geometrical entities included in the embedded data may be referenced directly in the application that receives the data.

2.4. Idealization (simplification)

One of the key steps in an engineering analysis is the idealization process. The aim of this process is to transform the intentions, under constraints and rules, to engineering models describing them in the language of structural engineering. The models we use are a structural model and a general constraints, boundary condition and load model which we call a constraints model. The idea is that any business intention, constraint or rule that is known and defined in the design model should be built into the engineering model in terms of structural constraints and requirements. And likewise, that

¹ Copyright 2003-2007 Spatial Corp, see <http://www.spatial.com/>.

any non structural intention, constraint or rule (means that it is not a part of the structure itself but affects and disturbs the structure) is built into the constraints model. These constraints are typically environmental loads, equipment loads, etc. that define and provide disturbances and constraints to the behaviour of the structure. It is assumed that rule loads, gravitational loads and any other physical constraint that may be derived from the product model by default, is transferred to the constraints model. We note that structural boundary conditions often need to be applied to regularize the problem if the analysis method is not able to handle singular problems.

Fig.2: The Idealization ToolBox concept.

What we do is thus an idealization from a design model to an engineering model that has been embedded with engineering knowledge in order to comply with all the intentions, constraints and rules that have been set forth. The design model is assumed to contain the complete domain. We note that we do not foresee that this process will ever be fully automated, but rather be semi-automated with adequate support to ease the logistics for the engineer. The idealization may be viewed as a sequence of transformations where we record each step in order to provide a cycle-back from the engineering model to the design model. Such transformation mechanisms enable us to transfer changes in the design back to the design model in a language understood by the designers.

The Idealization ToolBox is responsible for all adaptations, translations and idealizations that are needed to exchange information between two applications that implement a common API. It is, however, not responsible for the internal interpretation of information as performed in a receiving application. Figure 2 shows a conceptual view of an Idealization ToolBox. The responsibility of the tool box is shaded, while the validation of information and data with respect to a reference model is the responsibility of the applications themselves, i.e. follows the concept shown in Fig.1.

In addition to the Idealization ToolBox, we develop an analysis and modelling framework in order to support the ideas briefly introduced above. In such a framework we need pre-processors, post-processors and general analysis components to do the strength assessment. This leads to the next step in our analysis and modelling framework, the creation of analysis models. In this context an analysis model is a numerical discretization of the engineering problem, for instance by means of finite elements. The creation of numerical models is similar to the process we use to create the engineering model and is done by a sequence of transformations. The main difference is that while the first

sequence is semi-automated, this process is automated and we facilitate means for the engineer to tailor-make the discretization to serve specific purposes. Like the former idealization process we ensure a ‘way back’ from the numerical model to the engineering model. We use the standard SESAM suite of analysis software to perform the basic tasks required in the analysis process, *SESAM (1996)*. Since we have two engineering models we need to do a merge when we create the numerical model. This process is non-trivial but enables us to tailor the discretization to serve specific purposes, see also the short discussion on adaptive finite-element analyses in the next paragraph.

Important methods and concepts in the analysis and modelling framework are model adaptivity and adaptive finite-element analyses. Model adaptivity, *Stein and Ohnimus (1995)*, is a technique we use to ensure that the numerical models are capable of representing complex physical behaviour in an adequate way in order to provide good predictions of the response. We may start in a reduced space, say 2D, and enforce kinematical constraints, for instance from Kirchhoff hypothesis. If this reduced space cannot represent what we want to analyse, we transform the model to full 3D theory in the critical areas. Adaptive finite-element analysis is another technique we use to reduce the actual numerical errors in the computations, *Ladevèze and Oden (1998)*. The main concern here is to tailor the discretization to the constraint situation and enable an adaptive refinement of the discretization until it provides a response prediction with an error estimate that meets the requirements. The procedure is then a standard implementation of adaptive FE analysis. One problem with this strategy is that it works well only with simple elements. There are considerable problems to develop good error estimators for more complex finite-element formulations.

3. Implementations and examples

The integrator system and the idealization process discussed in Sec. 2 have been implemented as part of DNV Software’s general CAD-CAE solutions. In particular, we have implemented a two way data exchange between Nauticus Early Design (NED) and Genie. The NED software suite is developed as an extension to Intergraph’s IntelliShip™ software and is tailor-made for early design.

3.1. API model interface

The model is specified in XML schema and is implemented as a Document Object Model (DOM²).

This sub-section gives an overview of the top level entities in the model.

3.1.1. entity Ship

The “Ship” entity is the root of the DOM. It has a “Name” attribute and aggregates three entities.

² The Document Object Model is a platform- and language-neutral interface that will allow programs and scripts to dynamically access and update the content, structure and style of documents. The document can be further processed and the results of that processing can be incorporated back into the presented page, for further information ref “<http://www.w3.org/>”.

3.1.2. entity Administrative

“Program” gives information about the program that created the data set (NED), and “Session” provides information about date and time.

3.1.3. entity BoundingBox

The bounding box defines the selected set of the CAD model in terms of two points. The bounding box may extend to the whole ship.

3.1.4. entity Plates

The “Plates” entity represents a plate group, has a “Name” attribute and aggregates a “Plate” and a “Stiffeners” entity. Each plate can be considered as part of the plate group. The “Stiffeners” entity so collects the set of stiffeners that are contained in the plate group. Note that we do not represent beams that are not functioning as stiffeners on the plate structure in the current version of the model.

3.1.5. entity Plate

The “Plate” entity has a “Name” attribute and aggregates a set of entities of which “Geometry” impose restrictions to the use of a data set generated according to this model.

Notice that “Plate” does not nest plates. I.e. no recursion is yet implemented. This is defined in the base model we aim at – but currently the matters are as described here.

3.1.6. entity Stiffeners

The “Stiffeners” entity has a structure similar to “Plates” and has the same role for “Stiffener” entities. Thus it has a “Name” attribute and aggregates a “Stiffener” entity.

3.1.7. entity Stiffener

The “Stiffener” entity has a “Name” attribute and aggregates a set of entities of which “Geometry” impose restrictions to the use of a data set generated according to this model.

3.1.8. entity Geometry

The “Geometry” entity aggregates two entities a “sat_embedded” and a “line” entity.

The “sat_embedded” entity contains a base64 decoded CDATA section that represents the geometry. This implies that the receiving application must be equipped with an ACIS sat file interpreter. A “Geometry” entity evaluates to something like the following in a data set:

```
<Geometry>
  <sat_embedded encoding="base64">
    <![CDATA[MTUwMCAwIDEgMCAgIC .....]]>
  </sat_embedded >
</Geometry>
```


The “line” entity is an explicit geometry for a straight segment.

3.2. Idealization ToolBox

This section sketches the process flow of the Idealization ToolBox for inner structural parts, Fig.4, and shows some examples that have been processed by the Idealization ToolBox as a step under export from NED to Genie.

Fig.4: Overview of the part idealization process

Figs.5 and 6 show examples of idealizations to demonstrate the feasibility of the suggested approach. The idealizations include stiffer snapping, hole simplification, offset of structure to eliminate eccentricities, and extrusion line simplification (for corrugated bulkheads).

Fig.5: Mesh quality for production model, detail model and cargo hold model.

Fig.6: Idealization of web frame. To the left the design model, and to the right the idealized model.

Fig.6 shows what we call “aggressive” idealization of a typical web frame in order to reduce the size of the resulting analysis model as much as possible. Such simplifications are used for global analyses and cargo hold analyses.

3.3. Application of rule loads and code check

For completeness we include a brief section on rule loads and code checks as implemented in Genie. As mentioned in Sec. 2.4., loads are applied to a constraints model which is merged with the structural geometry in order to build a complete analysis model. Genie is based on engineering concepts and thus enables loads to be applied directly on the concepts. In a rule based context this means that loads and boundary conditions are applied to the concepts according to the governing rule sets.

After the finite element solution is available post-processing of the results are performed. In a ship classification session this often means code check, for instance fatigue and plate buckling checks. Since the engineering modeller works on engineering concepts it is possible to implement automatic generation of models for code checks. We call these models capacity models. This is implemented in Genie where the capacity models are derived from the engineering concepts, again according to the rules that govern.

4. Conclusions and further work

We have implemented a CAD-CAE system which is promising. There are issues to be solved, such as rule based idealizations where the user will be provided means to decide how specific details shall be idealized. Another issue is scalability of the solution when the model size increases. Yet, we have not met models that are large enough to challenge the system but we foresee larger and more complex models in the future and careful analysis of the scalability is needed.

An issue we omitted in this study is mesh generation. Mesh generation is hard because classification rule systems pose requirements to the mesh structure. Such requirements must sometimes be solved by inspection and we are in process of improving our mesh generation modules in order to handle the requirements.

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Prediction Model for the Outfitting Costs of Technical Spaces

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Abstract

Space allocation for technical equipment is done in an early stage of ship design. The amount of space reserved is based on historical data and rules of thumb using parameters such as total installed propulsion power. During engineering, the engineering department has to make sure that all equipment can actually be positioned in the room, and can work properly. If the space estimations appear to be incorrect, costly alterations are needed, because enlargements have a considerable effect on the design of the ship and its engineering and production process. The main goal of this research is to develop a method that enables ship designers to make a more balanced decision between costs, owner's demands and required space. This paper provides insight in the parameters that define the outfitting costs of technical rooms. Outfitting costs turn out to be strongly dependent of piping length. The method developed in this research makes use of the DelftRoute piping tool to predict piping length for different room configurations. Within a case study the relation between piping length and available space is shown.

1. Introduction

For years and years, ship designers, and especially designers of complex, 'engineered-to-order' (ETO) ships, have been conditioned to focus on optimization of the ship's performance, *Brown (1996)*. This for example results in the 'standard practice' to minimize the structural weight of the ship, at the expense of limited standardization of plate and stiffener properties and an increase in manufacturing costs, *Kriezis (1991)*. Both the decline of ship-owners' construction budgets and the strong competition between shipyards however no longer justifies such an approach. A rational approach to implementing manufacturability enhancements is required, taking into account both the effects on development costs as on performance, *Brown (1996)*, *Andrews (2005)*.

It is vital that manufacturability aspects are taken into account within early stages of the design process, as the influence on the costs of the vessel is the greatest during design, *Storch (2000)*. During preliminary design, designers however often have insufficient knowledge and information to take manufacturability aspects into account, *Vliet (1999)*. For example: Definition of engine room dimensions during preliminary design is done based on limited design data (e.g. an estimate of propulsion power), designer's experience and data of reference vessels. Estimates of room dimensions are commonly aimed at maximizing payload volume and/or area and thus at minimizing engine room length. Evaluation of producibility considerations, such as, increasing engine room length to improve accessibility, facilitate production and reduce production costs is hardly ever done.

Research aimed at producibility enhancements in shipbuilding can be subdivided in:

- Design for production of the ship's hull ('steelwork')
- Design for production of outfitting work (placement of equipment, piping, etc.)

Producibility improvements considering 'steelwork' are not considered in this paper. Ample research concerning this topic has already been done, e.g. *Okumoto (2002)*, *Harwig (2003)*, *Varghese (2006)*. This research is focused at outfitting. Outfitting as well has been subject of

research before. *Altic (2003)* for example states, states that significant reduction of labor can be achieved by making sub assemblies that can be directly installed on a block or on board. A drawback of this approach is the increased space required for a room, as sets of prefabricated components are harder to incorporate within the ship's shape. This can lead to an inefficient usage of space. This is especially a problem for ships with a low block coefficient i.e. fast patrol vessels. Furthermore piping length seems to increase through the application of sub-assemblies. It is thus the question whether the benefits of easy installation and improved fabrication circumstances are not outweighed by an increase in piping length and required space.

Fig.1: Example of a subassembly product breakdown, *Altic (2003)*

Current budgeting and planning techniques as used at a shipyard, are usually not well suited to accurately answer these kinds of questions or to systematically evaluate various configurations. They either take too much time, or do not take sufficient parameters into account to differentiate between alternatives.

The aim of this project is to develop a method and tool that assist designers in making a more accurately evaluation of the consequences for the outfitting costs of changing the configuration of a (technical) room. Changing the configuration of a room can imply: changing dimensions, using a different number of components, variations in filling grade, etc. Research is focused at complex engineered-to-order ships such as corvettes, frigates or large suction hopper dredgers. For this research it is assumed that the content of outfitting work is not affected by changing a room's configuration. For example, different joining techniques for piping than currently in use at the shipyard are not considered.

First of all the distribution of costs in shipbuilding is analyzed to identify the various parts of the outfitting costs. Consequently, relevant parameters for predicting outfitting costs are identified and the effect of parameter changes is investigated with the use of DelftRoute within a case study.

2. Cost distribution in shipbuilding

Purchased goods, labor and knowledge contribute to a significant percentage of the total costs of a ship. For complex ships, purchased inputs can rise to 70 or 80% of the total costs of the ship, *Aalbers (2003)*. This does however not mean that the input of the yard is insignificant. Or

as *Koenig (2002)* states it: ‘Many major material items are relatively undifferentiated and are supplied on a highly competitive market. This implies that it may prove difficult to build a unique competitive advantage based on an especially effective material procurement function’. Although an effective purchase process thus clearly is important for short-term survival, in order to differentiate itself from its competitors, an optimized shipyard production and engineering processes is vital in the long run.

Value directly added by the shipyard employees mainly consists of man-hours. Man-hours are required for activities such as: design and engineering, construction of the hull, installation of piping, management, etc. *Aalbers (2003)* gives the following overview of shipyard man-hours for commercial ships in:

Fig.2: Shipyard man-hour division

If only production hours are considered, i.e. shipyard labor without design and engineering, hull erection would account for $\pm 65\%$ of the required labor.

Shipyard data of a Western-European Naval shipyard shows that the man-hour division for navy ships is slightly different. Design and engineering takes a larger share of the total man-hours, whereas the share of man-hours for hull erection is lower¹. Data presented by *Lamb (2004)* shows the same trend, Table I.

Table I: Shipyard labor division in %

	Tanker	Cruise Ship	Naval Combatant
Structure	29	33	25
Machinery	17	10	7
Electrical	15	37	20
Comm & Cont	7	Sub Contracted	9
Auxiliary MC	22	20	20
Outfit	10	Sub Contracted	18
Weapons	-	-	6

The numbers do not directly match the 65% share in production effort for hull erection as mentioned by *Aalbers*, as most European shipyards nowadays sub-contract electrical, communication and HVAC work (part of Auxiliary MC). Assuming subcontracting of 50%

¹ As long as the plate thickness is not reduced too and welding distortion becomes a major problem, which requires a large rework effort to correct distortion

‘Auxiliary MC’ and all electrical work, structural work for the cruise ship comes down to 62% and for the naval combatant to 40%. Outfitting work, including placement of equipment (machinery) and outfitting of the accommodation, than comes down to about 55% of the total required production effort for a naval combatant.

Baade (1998) reports that for a commercial vessel, such as a container ship, more than 30% of the hours required for hull construction and 40% of the effort required for outfitting are spend on the engine room section. Naval shipyard data shows that even though navy ships are more ‘equally’ filled than most cargo vessels, and thus require outfitting all over the ship, the engine room and diesel-generator rooms still require about 30% of the outfitting effort.

3. Overview of Outfitting Processes in Shipbuilding

Outfitting of technical spaces can be divided as shown in Fig.3. The total outfitting costs are dependent of the amount of work and the costs per hour of the production employees. Implementing manufacturability enhancements is assumed not to change employee’s costs per hour. The work for installation of the electrical system (cabling, converters, UPS) and the Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning system (ducts, AC-units, etc.) is assumed to be subcontracted. For this project, outfitting work executed by the shipyard thus consists of: placing and positioning of the components of mechanical systems and installation of pipelines between the components.

Fig.3: Simplified view of outfitting for technical spaces

In this paper only the costs for fabrication and installation of pipelines is considered. Effort required for piping work takes up the main share of the total outfitting effort, Fig.4. Furthermore shipyard experts expect that ‘piping’ is the part that is most strongly affected by changes in space configurations. The breakdown of the outfitting costs for ‘piping’ fall is shown in Fig.5.

Fig.4: Division of outfitting labor across the various outfitting activities

Fig.5: Breakdown of outfitting costs for piping

Two different types of parameters define the total amount of outfitting work:

- “Size drivers”:
A size driver defines the extent of the work. For example, the total pipeline length to be installed.
- “Effort” drivers:
An effort driver defines how much effort is required to carry out a given amount of work. Effort drivers for example take into account how hard it is to execute a certain activity and include parameters as: filling grade, accessibility, etcetera.

The working of the two parameters types is graphically displayed in Fig.6. The area within the box ‘total effort’ represents the total amount of work, which is a combination of a size driver and an effort driver. In reality there are however multiple size and effort drivers.

Fig.6: Graphical display of effort and size driver

3.1 Effort and Size drivers

To identify the parameters that define the outfitting costs, the outfitting process at a naval shipyard was analyzed, resulting in the size and effort drivers as shown in Table II. Individual worker related parameters as experience or education are not taken into account.

Taking a closer look at these parameters reveals that most of the parameters are not independent and that some parameters affect most, if not all, of the different cost items. For example piping mass is dependent of piping length, diameter, material density and wall thickness. ‘Number of pipe spools’ is dependent of total piping length and maximal allowable spool size, etcetera.

The main size and effort drivers turn out to be total piping length, piping diameter and accessibility. The other parameters can either be expressed by these parameters; are little occurring; or are independent of the configuration of a room. The parameters that are independent of the configuration of a room, such as the distance between the storage location and the place of usage or the material type, are not relevant for this research.

Table II: Size and effort driver for 'piping'

Material cost	
Size driver:	Effort driver:
Length of piping	Number of contractors
Diameter	Type of material
Wall thickness	
Fabrication cost	
Size driver:	Effort driver:
Number of spools (spool= pipe piece)	Complexity of the system
Number of operations	Material type
Number of bends	Piping diameter
	Quality of engineering output (e.g. readability of drawings)
Transport	
Size driver:	Effort driver:
Spool mass	Accessibility
Distance between storage and place of use	Spool length
Number of runs	Piping diameter
Installation on board	
Size driver:	Effort driver:
Number of spools to install	Accessibility
Spool length	Orientation
Piping Diameter	Piping wall thickness
	Quality of engineering output (e.g. readability of drawing)
Preservation and insulation	
Size driver:	Effort driver:
Piping length	Accessibility
	Orientation
	Diameter
	Type of preservation/insulation

The total piping length is dependent of the number of connections to make between components, the distance between the components and the available space for piping. In practice it is often not possible to connect two components with a pipeline with a length equal to the shortest distance between the components, Fig.7. The available space for piping is limited due to other components, walkways or maintenance areas and thus detours are required.

Fig.7: Routing of pipelines between two components

The piping diameter is defined by the required amount of flow through a pipeline and the maximum allowable fluid speed within a pipeline. In theory, the length of a pipeline affects the resistance and thus the diameter required to obtain the desired amount of flow. With piping

distances as encountered within an engine room (the largest technical room) the effect of length on diameter is however negligible.

The accessibility of working areas within a room is defined by the filling grade. Filling grade is defined as:

$$\frac{\text{space required by components and no go areas}}{\text{total available space within a room}}$$

The filling grade can be expressed as both a 2D parameters (based on area) or as a 3D parameter (based on volume). During the outfitting process, the filling grade of a room increases; filling grade is thus dependent of time and building sequence, Fig.8.

Fig.8: Filling grade of a room in time (t=0, t=2, t=4)

Furthermore the filling grade is not constant across a room. Especially for large rooms, it could be useful to divide the room in different segments, and use a filling grade per segment. See for an example Fig.9. It is not hard to imagine that installing a pipeline between component M and N is far more easy than between component F and J.

Fig.9: Variable filling grades across a room

3.2 Space configuration

The configuration of a space is dependent of:

- The dimensions of the room;
- The shape of the room;
- The number of components within the room;
- The relative position of the components within the room.

In the current process, the dimensions of a room and the shape of a room are laid down when the general arrangement plan and the hull form is created. The number of components within a room is defined during system design. The relative position of the components within a room is partly defined by engineering rules and physical laws (e.g.: place of a pump) and partly by the engineer's preferences.

3.3 Outfitting producibility enhancements

The aim of this research is to investigate if outfitting producibility enhancements can be obtained by applying alternative space configurations. The most obvious measure to reduce

outfitting costs is to reduce piping length. Reducing piping length however implies placing components closer together, which reduces the available space for piping, and increases the risk of collisions, detours and hinders installation. To optimise outfitting costs, the optimum between piping length and accessibility thus need to be found.

In the next chapter a method is presented to show the effect of the various configuration parameters on piping length. The next step, to calculate the outfitting costs for a given piping length and a set of configuration parameters is made in subsequent research. To investigate the relation between the configuration parameters and the piping length within a room, DelftRoute is used. DelftRoute is a pipe routing program developed by the TU Delft (Asmara 2006).

4 DelftRoute simulations

Delft route consists of three main parts, the first part is the interface between commercial Cad software as Nupas/Cadmatic and DelftRoute. This interface is needed to be able to load ship structures, equipment etc. in DelftRoute and to be able to export the obtained route to the cad software. The second part is the routing module, it consist of the routing tool, which uses the Dijkstra algorithm to find the shortest route between the connection points of the equipment. In the module there is also an optimizer. Its purpose is to give priority to certain pipes in routing order. This will lead to the shortest route for the selected pipe(s) the other pipes are routed thereafter and must avoid this pipe. This can cause an elongation of the path. The third part is the optimizing part of the program. The used particular swarm optimizer decides the order in which the pipes are routed. In practice priority is given to pipes in order of pipe diameter or used material.

4.1 Validation of program

Asmara validated the program by comparing pipelines for a tug routed in DelftRoute with manual routed pipelines. For the majority of the pipelines the routing found was similar. Only in difficult cases, where an aesthetic or practical solution has to be found; the results found by the program are worse. Although this is not a ‘proof’ that the program will give good results for all rooms, the authors are convinced that the predictions come sufficiently close to manually routed pipelines to be suitable for this research.

Fig 10: Connection diagram simulated engine room.

4.2 DelftRoute Simulations

The piping length is affected by all space configuration parameters. In this paper only the effect of changing the dimensions of a room and the number of components within the room will be shown. The method used to identify the effect of the other parameters is however similar.

The DelftRoute simulation is started with an engine room accommodating only two systems: a freshwater (blue line) and a fuel oil system (brown lines), Fig.10.

The components are placed in the engine room model, obeying the relevant engineering rules that apply for specific components (e.g. vertical position for a centrifugal pump or the orientation of a diesel generator set etc.) and leaving sufficient space for operational ability, maintenance, accessibility and ducting. In the program this is done by defining so called “no go areas”, the shaded areas in Fig.12. Within a no go area piping cannot be routed.

Fig.11: 2 Top view of the simulation with 2 systems

After defining all connections between components, the program routes the pipelines in the engine room and calculates the resulting pipe length and number of bends.

Fig.12: Overview of the engine room, the shaded boxes visualizing the no go areas (5 systems)

Fig 13: Overview of routed pipes. (5 systems)

Hereafter the available space is stepwise reduced, until the components can no longer be placed within the available space, or until DelftRoute is no longer able to find a solution. This procedure was done with 2, 3, 4 and 5 systems. The arrangement of component is done according to a set of engineering rules, which aims at minimising piping length, by grouping components in a logical way. It was not always possible to maintain the same arrangement of components, which affects the purity of the quantitative results as shown here. All arrangement are however based on the same engineering rules, additional research is carried out to identify the effect of the arrangement on piping length.

The display the results, the total piping length as found by DelftRoute is plotted against total filling grade of the room.

Fig 14: Relations between filling grade and piping length.

The graphs show that there actually is an optimal filling grade for the piping length. Decreasing the filling grade with a constant number of components can in first instance be done without any problems (descending part of the lines). At a certain filling grade, there is however a turning point. Further decreasing the filling grade result in blockades of optimal routes, which requires the program to make detours, resulting in an increase in piping length. Further research has to show, if and how this optimum filling grade is affected by the manufacturability aspects.

5 Evaluation, conclusions and further research

Piping length is the main parameter of the outfitting costs that is influenced by the configuration of a space. Simply decreasing the available space, bringing component closer together, will however not always optimise the outfitting costs and may even have an opposite effect. When the relation between piping length and filling grade is quantified as well, DelftRoute can help in the proposal phase to make a quick, more founded decision about the required room dimensions in order to optimise the piping length. This can be done by modelling a number of alternative room configurations and compare the results. This evaluation will not only help to find the solution with the lowest outfitting cost, but can also help to visualize differences between operability, maintainability and accessibility.

In the near future the engine room of an existing patrol vessel will be simulated in DelftRoute, to improve validation of the DelftRoute results. Further research is also required to quantify the relation between piping length, accessibility (filling grade) and outfitting costs.

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Capability Prediction for Weathervaning Dynamic Positioning Systems

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Abstract

To assess weathervaning dynamic positioning (DP) capability, a new type of capability plot is developed, which shows limiting environmental conditions for a weathervaning DP vessel. The weathervaning capability is here based on a static analysis of the DP system.

1. Introduction

Since its first application in 1957, Dynamic Positioning (DP) has developed rapidly and became a widely applied technology within the maritime industry. Nowadays DP finds many different applications on drill ships, pipe laying vessels, FPSOs, dive support vessels and many more.

Essentially a DP system's function is to keep a vessel on a specified position/track and/or heading, by using the vessel's thrusters. Any type of thruster can be used, but most DP systems use a combination of shaft propellers (with or without rudder), tunnel thrusters and azimuthing thrusters. Environmental disturbances due to wind, waves and current and other external loads have to be balanced against the thruster forces by the DP system in order to hold position, Fig.1.

Different modes of operation are generally available in a DP system, such as manual joystick control, automatic tracking, target following and position/heading control. This paper will focus on the position control function of DP systems, as this is the operating mode for which capability plots can be used.

Fig.1: DP vessel, KM (2007)

Fig.2: Traditional capability plot, KM (2006)

2. DP Capability

When a vessel operates in position control mode, the thrusters in the DP system have to counterbalance environmental disturbances, which mainly consist of wind, wave and current loads, and possibly other external loads. For some applications also other external loads have to be

counterbalanced, such as the force of a pipe that is been laid or a hawser force in case of offloading operations.

The wind loads that act on the vessel will be varying due to gusts and wind shifts, the current on the other hand will be very slowly varying. Second order wave drift loads will act on the vessel, mainly due to wind generated waves. Swell imposes very limited second order drift loads, as the wave periods in swell are long. Wave-frequent vessel motions are typically not regarded in DP, because the frequencies are too high for thrusters to react to, so only the low frequent loads of wind-generated waves are taken into consideration.

The position of the vessel can be controlled in the horizontal plane in three directions: surge, sway and yaw. The DP system usually controls the three directions simultaneously to maintain position and heading. Vertical motions (pitch, roll and heave) are generally neglected in DP analyses, as they will have negligible influence on the system.

There are certain maximum external loads above which a DP vessel cannot maintain its position and/or heading. The environmental circumstances under which these maximum loads occur are called 'capability' of the DP system. This capability is an important design parameter, as it is directly coupled to the uptime of the vessel and it shows under what circumstances a vessel should be prepared to loose position and/or heading. For an FPSO the capability shows under what circumstances a disconnect procedure should be initiated to decouple its risers such that the vessel is able to leave the field on which it is producing.

To determine a DP system's capability, first a constant current speed and direction are assumed (as current will be slowly varying). The waves are determined as a function of the wind speed. This wind-wave relation is site-specific and is known for most locations, but if not available a standard relation can be used as proposed by *IMCA (2000)*.

The current, wind and waves have to be translated into forces that act on the vessel, to be able to compare the load on the ship with the available thrust, in the three directions surge, sway and yaw. Estimation methods, such as developed by *Remery and v. Oortmerssen (1973)*, can be used to find load-coefficients for the vessel. These methods are however a bit outdated, as strip theory and diffraction analyses can give more accurate results. The latter require more computational resources, but as capability analyses are mostly done in the design phase of a vessel and not during operation this will not be problematic.

Using the assumptions on the current and waves, a traditional capability plot can be constructed, Fig.2. In this plot the maximum allowable wind speed (with corresponding significant wave height) is shown at which the DP system can maintain the vessel's position and heading, given the chosen wind – wave relation and current. The vessel is shown in the centre of the plot, with its bow pointing upwards. The maximum wind speed is shown for a discrete series of angles at which the wind and waves enter the vessel. The current is (mostly) coming from a fixed direction in the plot or can rotate with the wind. In Fig.2, the radial axis shows the maximum allowable wind speed in knots, with the used series of wind directions shown around the plot. Industry standards for capability plots can be found in *IMCA (2000)*.

3. Weathervaning DP

On most vessels a DP system has to maintain the ship's position in all three degrees of freedom in the horizontal plane: surge, sway and yaw. For some applications however the heading of the vessel is of no influence on the vessels operation, and it can be chosen freely by the DP system. The vessel will then be rotated to the direction in which it encounters the smallest environmental loads, Fig.3, pointing with its bow into the resultant of wind, waves and current. This direction with the smallest loads is called neutral heading. Operation where only the position and not the heading of a vessel is controlled, is called weathervaning DP and is, for instance, applied on FPSOs. Positioning the ship in

the neutral heading will enlarge the ship's capability, because the loads that have to be counterbalanced are smaller than when the environment is entering beam-on.

Fig.3: Full DP (a) vs. Weathervaning DP (b)

Fig.4: Required thrust for (a) Heading control, and (b) weathervaning DP

Until now no FPSOs have been operating in weathervaning mode. Bluewater's FPSO Munin has been operating on DP on the Xijiang field near China, but on a 'manual' weathervaning DP mode, where the operator had to determine the vessel's neutral heading. Because the vessel has been operating on DP only for a short period of six months, no new DP system has been installed and the existing DP system is used in the 'manual' weathervaning mode. However for FPSO DP operations, the development of a new, weathervaning system will be worthwhile.

Most weathervaning DP systems not only have the freedom to choose a heading, they are often allowed to make relatively large excursions from their setpoint. This gives the vessel a large area to recover from a possible position offset, which can be used in the recovery strategy.

A traditional DP system can be used in a weathervaning mode, but this will be far from optimal, as the thruster layout for a weathervaning system should be essentially different from a DP system with heading control. For heading control a large amount of transverse thrust should be available both at the bow and stern of the vessel. This thrust is needed to withstand large sway and yaw loads that will act on the vessel as environment is entering from aside, Fig.4a..

Because a weathervaning system will position itself on the neutral heading, the thrusters do not have to be capable of delivering large yaw moments, Fig.4b. By installing the transverse thrusters as far to the bow as possible, a moment is created due to the thrust and the environmental sway load on the vessel. This moment will turn the vessel into the neutral heading and thus contributes to position keeping. This is essentially the weathervaning behaviour of the system. This way of positioning will only be stable in case the control point is placed forward of midship, as proven by *Pinkster (1987)*.

4. Weathervaning capability

Due to the characteristics of weathervaning DP operations, traditional capability plots are not very useful for these systems. Because a weathervaning vessel will be positioned in the neutral heading, the wind will come from a fixed direction relative to the vessel. Limiting wind speeds for each angle of attack around the vessel will therefore not provide useful information. Weathervaning DP systems of course do have a capability, as there are still limiting loads above which the position keeping cannot be maintained. To find the weathervaning capability a new approach is developed, *Tjallega (2006)*

When a weathervaning DP vessel is operating exactly in the neutral heading, the sway and yaw loads are (theoretically) zero, such that only the surge load has to be counterbalanced by the thrusters. In

this position the capability is the same as for a traditional DP system if it is positioned in the neutral heading. If the vessel however gets an offset from the neutral heading the capability will change. Restoring the heading will be given priority in this situation over maintaining the position, because the vessel is allowed to make some excursion, see Section 3). Once the heading is restored the position will be stable again, but at some distance from the setpoint. The vessel can now restore its position until it is back at the setpoint, while maintaining in the neutral heading.

Fig.5 shows the motion of a vessel after it has got a heading offset. Picture (a) shows the vessel before the offset. In (b) an offset is shown, due to for instance a wind shift or whatever other reason. Pictures (c) and (d) show the vessel adjusting its heading back to the neutral heading, while it is drifting away from the setpoint. In picture (e) it has recovered its heading and is sailing back to the setpoint and in the last picture the vessel is back on position, still in the neutral heading. As can be seen in picture (d), the vessel might slightly ‘overcompensate’ its heading to be able to sail back to the setpoint. In severe environments this overcompensation will be small; otherwise a new unstable situation will be created.

Fig.5: Motion of a vessel after a heading offset

Using the described method, the capability of a weathervaning DP system will represent the maximum environmental loads at which the system is capable to control the surge and sway position of the vessel, and the heading can be restored from an offset while the vessel stays within its excursion limits.

Because restoring the heading is given priority in the method, the vessel will drift a certain distance before the heading is restored. Using this static method, the distance that the vessel will drift cannot be determined directly, so dynamic analysis has to be performed to verify if the vessel is capable of staying within an excursion limit.

5. Weathervaning capability plot

The defined weathervaning capability can be visualized in a polar plot, similar to traditional

capability plots. In the new plot however, the wind, waves and current will be plot on fixed angles, and the angles for which the capability line is drawn for each heading offset of the vessel. In this way the plot shows the limiting wind speed and wave height for each heading offset.

Because the vessel will rotate from a certain heading offset back to the neutral heading, the capability from the neutral heading to a heading offset of 180°, in both clockwise and counter-clockwise direction, can never increase. An increase in capability would mean that the vessel will not be able to turn its bow past the maximum in the capability line.

Fig.6 shows two examples of weathervaning capability plots, one for a collinear environment and one for a non-collinear environment. The markers on the top of the plot show the directions of wind, waves and current. In the pictures traditional capability plots are drawn as well, for comparison with the weathervaning capability. The outer plot represents the weathervaning capability, the narrow plot shows the traditional capability.

Fig.6: Weathervaning capability plots for (a) collinear environment, (b) non-collinear environment

Fig.6 shows that the weathervaning capability is much 'wider' than the traditional capability. In the neutral heading the capabilities are similar, as can be expected: in that direction the maximum surge thrust is governing for the capability and sway and yaw have no influence. The traditional capability plot is somewhat changed to display it in the same plot: instead of rotating wind, the plot now shows a rotating vessel. This means that the relative angles between wind, wave and current direction are constant in the plot, while in most traditional plots these change due to rotating wind and waves and fixed current direction. The weathervaning capability is much smaller in the lower half of the plot. This is due to the fact that the capability cannot increase between 0° and ±180° in the picture. A proper design weathervaning DP vessel will however never reach such large heading offsets: the vessel is supposed to keep its heading in the neutral heading, so offsets larger than 90 degrees will be very unlikely. Fig.6b plot shows an asymmetric capability, due to the non-collinear environment in that situation. The weathervaning capability shows roughly the same asymmetry as the traditional capability.

6. DP System Design

When a vessel is designed for operation on DP, capability plots can be a very useful design aid. In an early design stage the capability can be estimated, based on a relatively limited amount of data. A DP layout can be chosen and if necessary adjusted to provide the vessel with sufficient capability for its

expected operations and environmental circumstances.

When an operational profile for a vessel is known, the analysis can be reversed to find the amount of thrust that is needed under given wind, current and waves. This can be useful to predict the fuel consumption of a vessel that will operate on DP, under a given environment. This method is described in *Brinkman (2006)*, where scatter diagrams are used to estimate a ship's fuel consumption.

When the vessel restores from a heading offset, it will drift from its setpoint for a certain distance, because the heading is given priority in the recovery process. The excursion that the vessel gets in this process is determined by the forces that have to be counteracted to recover from the heading offset, which again depends on the environmental loads. This means that the size of the watch circle (and thus the maximum allowed excursion) determines the maximum environment and thus the capability. To determine the capability as function of the maximum excursion however, a dynamic analysis is needed. This dynamic analysis should give the maximum excursion that is reached in the heading recovery process, so it can be determined whether the maximum allowed excursion is reached.

Although dynamic analyses are not included in the capability prediction method, it can be used in early design phases and for easy visualization of the system's limits, but in a later design stage time-domain simulations should be performed to analyse the system's dynamic behaviour. In most capability analyses a 'dynamic allowance' is incorporated, which is a factor that scales the capability down to account for dynamics in the system. The value of this factor is mostly determined by experience.

Usually one constant factor to scale the complete capability is used, which is not a very sophisticated method because dynamic effects will not be the same at all headings. Scaling the plot with a factor that depends on the heading will already give a better result. Maybe a sinusoidal scaling factor can be used, depending on the heading for which the capability is scaled. For now the dynamics are not included in capability analysis and the designer should thus include this in the design and use his experience when defining dynamic allowances in the capability analyses.

7. Conclusion

Using the described method for determination of weathervaning capability provides the possibility to design a DP system specifically for weathervaning applications. The weathervaning capability plots provide a powerful design aid by quickly showing the impact of design choices in the DP system on the capability of the system.

The weathervaning capability that is determined by the presented method however is based on static analysis of the DP system and therefore does not incorporate dynamic behaviour of the system. As a result, the size of the watch circle cannot directly be determined using the method. In a later design stage a dynamic time- or frequency-domain simulation method should be used to include the dynamics of the system in the analysis. Once some experience is gained with dynamic simulations and full scale weathervaning DP applications, the static capability prediction can be refined by estimation of dynamic allowances, such that the capability better matches the system's dynamic behaviour.

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Integration of Software Packages with Different Programming Paradigms, Exemplified by a Ship Model Generating Tool

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Abstract

The paper describes problems and solutions for integrating old existing software in Fortran with new programming paradigms in the context of a specific tool to simulate a new ship design in a bridge simulator. A system kernel in pure Java application is combined with simulation tools written predominantly in Fortran.

1. Introduction

Many large software products in use today represent continuous development since 10 or 20 years, reflecting accumulated knowledge from many research projects. All this know-how is part of this software and should be used in future without a total new implementation. But information technology (IT) is a young science. The way to develop software has changed over the years. Modern techniques are very different from traditional or historic programming paradigms.

These differences create problems, when an integration of modern and classical software packages is necessary. Especially in engineering, powerful and large simulation tools need to be integrated in a design environment. The simulation tools may come from different environments and philosophies. Apart from that, we have today software at our disposal to handle problems of distributed databases, communication by distributed computation problems and other information technical tasks. However, the integration of large simulation tools from different sources in one system still poses challenges.

Our particular case here is the E4 ship design software, a complex software for different tasks in ship design, *Krüger (1999)*. The system consists at present of a set of 116 different methods, and further simulation and user-interface modules may be added in the future. The flexible approach of E4 allows an engineer with little IT background to write his own application in a short time. The engineer can concentrate on the physical problem, instead of the IT part. Due to historical reasons, E4 is largely based on a procedural way and not event driven, as is practice today. For an engineer, this procedural approach is easy to understand, because the behaviour of a program can be analysed and structured directly and is not based on complex modern design pattern, *Gamma (2004)*, as required by event-driven applications. It is not useful to demand that all engineers, who want to implement software, have to be familiar with complex IT concepts. Instead, it is more practical to use a framework with a clear restricted functionality, which allows implementing software with only a short training period. The task of a software-developing engineer is to build numerical models for a physical problem and not to waste time for computational problems. A naval architect who uses the E4 framework has his know-how in ship design and its physical behaviour. By the use of the above-described framework, this know-how can be used in an easy way.

Since programming E4 started, the technical environment has changed significantly. Computational power has increased and distributed work came with wide availability of computers. Aspects of user authentication and a management of privileges are now very important. The distributed use of data generates problems of informational consistency. Computational networks with high bandwidth worldwide allow now distributed computational power and data. For example, shipyards and suppliers want to have their computational environments to communicate directly. Time consuming calculations may be executed remotely at dedicated computer centres. The new demands require updating of E4. Generally, simulation software frequently does not consider complex IT handling tasks.

This was the motivation to launch the BMBF funded project SESIS, <http://www.sesis.de>. This is an IT project to solve such problems. SESIS combines naval architect with pure IT specialists, Fig.1. The project will design a system kernel for technical applications like the ship-design software E4, which will be called in the following RCE (Reconfigurable Computing Environment). The RCE should handle all the tasks of data handling, user-authentication, management of privileges and network communication. A further important aim is that existing numerical methods can be integrated to the RCE without a new implementation. Therefore, the interfaces between the new RCE and existing methods are vital.

In contrast to the existing numerical methods, normally written in FORTRAN and compiled to system depending executables, the RCE is a pure Java application, which needs a Java-Virtual-Machine for executing the byte-code of a Java program. Java has been chosen because its hardware independence makes it easier to handle different platforms and the communication between them. Moreover there are many free add-on packages available, which can be used without own implementation effort. But these two concepts are based on total different software paradigms. In a classical environment of compiled executables, different computer languages can interact in a relative simple way, because all compilable languages generate object files, which can be connected by a linker to one application. In contrast to this, an interpretative language generates no executables but it needs an interpreter for executing the application. Therefore, object files cannot be connected to the byte-code of a Java application, but such a connection is necessary for integration.

Fig.1: Partners of the SESIS project

E4 is continuously under development and in use by different partners. Taking E4 out of operation for several months to implement major updates is not an option. With several E4 users not participating in SESIS, the danger of developing incompatible versions must be avoided. Therefore the migration path from a stand-alone executable to an integrated version is absolutely important. Without a clear strategy for this task it is impossible to migrate a continuously used software system of similar complexity.

A further task by the migration of such software is to handle the complexity of the total system. Because there are many different technologies, which have to interact homogeneously, they all have to be supported and controlled by the developers. But nobody can be familiar with all these different IT techniques. There are experts for numerical problems of physical FORTRAN methods, experts for designing complex object-oriented software architectures, and experts for databases. Nevertheless a system has to be built, in which all these different people can work, although they can not overview the complete system in all details. This is only possible if there are clear boundaries with simple interfaces. Every section of the global system has to support and to regard the facilities of the different experts. The layout of the system has to reflect these aspects of psychologies.

Not only should existing software be integrated, but the framework should also adapt to future developments. Most of these future developments will come from naval architects and not by computer scientists. Therefore it is also important for new implementations to have a development

framework, which regards the facilities of technical engineers. This group of persons, who are not pure users of the software and who want to implement themselves software for their physical problems, will be called in the following power-user.

Fig.2: Structure of the SESIS platform

One of these sub-projects is to develop an interface from the new SESIS system to the bridge simulator Simflex, <http://www.simflex.dk>, from the company FORCE Technology. The aim is to have an automatic link between a ship-design tool and a bridge simulator. This link allows testing a ship design in a virtual environment before the ship has been built. The classical use of a bridge simulator is training the crew. The numerical models are adjusted mostly by results of model and full-scale tests. Such test results are not available during the design stage of a ship. Therefore numerical simulations have to identify the behaviour of the projected ship. In the past, many methods have been already implemented within the ship design software E4. There are methods for resistance, manoeuvring and seakeeping of the ship. These methods allows a ship designer to estimate the performance of a new design. However, the generated information is hard to understand for people not familiar with engineering. Therefore discussions between project engineers of a shipyard and customers are sometimes a little bit complicated, because a customer does not think in terms like lift coefficients of a rudder. The customer has special missions for the ship he wants to own. For example, he wants to transport a special charge between two ports. Such a mission should be realized with a maximum of benefit for the investor. Therefore, the customer is not interested in technical terms but for example in questions, how often he needs tug support within a port and which technical actions and costs are necessary to avoid this need. For a customer it would be much more useful to let his own captain navigate within a bridge simulator than to discuss about simulation results based on first-principle methods. For the communication between engineer and customer, a bridge simulator could thus be useful. Unfortunately, at present the preparation of a manoeuvring model for a bridge is time consuming, because the physical flow simulation uses completely different data representation from the bridge simulator. The task at hand is to interface the two applications within SESIS, allowing virtually automatic data transfer. This will offer two benefits. The application as such is useful and it demonstrates the feasibility of the SESIS approach.

2. Architecture of the RCE (Reconfigurable Computing Environment)

The new RCE is a platform for other software tools. The aim is that these tools can be connected to the RCE and that they can use its functionality for their own purpose, Fig.2. The level of integration is not constant for every method. It is possible that some tools are connected only over file exchange, whereas other methods are directly part of the RCE in form of a Java package. Between these

extremes all levels of integration are possible. Further there are three different roles of people who want to use the SESIS platform:

1. The Naval Architect as User only wants to use the SESIS platform for the design applications. He does not want to program. If he encounters a bug, he will wait until stable versions are available before he updates his platform.
2. The Power-User primarily wants to use the software. But he also develops new methods (respectively plug-ins) for a technical task. His focus is on the physical effects of his engineering problems. He wants a developing framework, which allows building standard methods basing on the RCE without having to be familiar with all the software techniques, which are working in the background. He is responsible for the technical use of the SESIS system.
3. The Computer Scientist develops and supports the total RCE platform. He is familiar with the software techniques used within the RCE, as they are the data management, the user identification and the network communication. He is not an expert for questions of engineering methods.

Fig.3: Screen-Shot of the new RCE platform

The RCE is based on a flexible OSGI plug-in architecture allowing different developers to build their own functionality without having to build the RCE. It is possible to build only the own plug-in and add it to the already existing RCE. A set of plug-ins is part of the RCE as shown in Fig.3 (data management, update, privileges, service broker, communication). The power-user can use this platform by developing his own plug-in. For example, the wrapper plug-in, which has an interface for external code, would be such a plug-in. The external code could be a classical E4 method.

This plug-in architecture has two main advantages. (1) There is a clear interface definition between the RCE system and the numerical methods and (2) it is possible to distribute the complete SESIS system in different configurations. Not everyone who uses SESIS has to get every functionality. If there are licence problems by some functionality, the corresponding plug-ins can be distributed by their own, directly to authorized partners. This allows an organisation to develop functionality on the RCE platform without having to make this functionality becomes part of the complete SESIS system, with the consequences of an automatic distribution to all SESIS partners by the next update. A system based on a plug-in structure allows a much better protection of own investments.

Fig.4 shows another important feature of the RCE architecture. The system kernel of the RCE is designed for a distributed network. If different computer have installed the RCE kernel, these kernels can build a virtual network by themselves. A user working with his own client is able to use functionality and data from the distributed RCE network if he has the correct permissions. This permission handling will be managed by a system of certifications.

Fig.4 Distributed Network based on the RCE platform

3. Technical problems and solutions of integration

This section explains which technical problems appeared and how they were solved. The main problem at the beginning was the incompatibility between interpreted byte code of a Java application and a classical stand-alone FORTRAN application with object files compiled to a specific hardware. Because the changes to the existing source code should be minimized, it had been discussed, whether it is useful to let the new basic kernel RCE and the existing software E4 as two separated processes on a system. After all, the main task of the SESIS project is not to improve the methods for ship design but to develop a basic framework to support modern IT demands. Therefore principally it is acceptable to keep the classical method. Even if the user-interface is not completely up to date, it has been proven its use in practise. An approach would be to run the naval architect software stand-alone as up to now and to realize the communication with the RCE in the background by a special communication library over inter-process communication. After initial discussions, some performance tests showed that inter-process communication is very expensive and a use of naval architect functionality within the RCE system would be impossible. Thus a closer connection between E4 functionality and the RCE was necessary. The only way to connect compiled object files with a Java application is to use JNI (Java Native Interface). This means to put all needed functionality (compiled object files) to a shared-library, to add interface descriptions and to load this library during runtime directly to the Java-Virtual-Machine. The difficulties of this approach will be discussed now.

3.1 Modifications of the existing methods

It is difficult to modify a software system continuously being in use. However, it was necessary to modify the E4 methods to generate shared libraries for the RCE system without splitting off a separated version of E4 methods. The consequence was to develop a build system for the source code, which automatically allows generating, based on the same source code, stand-alone methods for the E4 system and shared-libraries for the RCE system. An aggravating fact is that parallel to the adjustments for the RCE system a porting of E4 from the UNIX operating system HP-UX to Linux is in process. Although both operating systems are UNIX systems, there are many problems in detail. The existing system was not able to handle all these different demands. Based on the GNU tool Make, it has been implemented. The problem of different target platforms and different types of output

(executables/shared-libraries) will be handled by the build system, which uses the correct compilers and options for the special purpose. Needed differences in behaviour of the programs are handled by a configuring of the source code with a pre-processor. Among other things this approach was used to distinguish between executables, static and shared libraries. Fig.5 shows such a part of starting an E4 method. The original version contains only the section program. The macro variable E4USECPPMAIN triggers now whether the E4 method will be compiled as a stand-alone executable with a “program” statement, or if a “subroutine” statement will be used for generating the start-point. This little switch allows building automatically the different types of software.

```

#ifndef E4USECPPMAIN
program E4StandaloneFortranMain
implicit none
  call E4StandaloneFortranEntry()
end program
#endif

#ifdef E4USECPPMAIN
subroutine E4StandaloneCPPEntry
#else
subroutine E4StandaloneFortranEntry
#endif

  ...

end subroutine

```

Fig.5: Excerpt from E4 code, source: FSG

Fig.6: Static and shared linked processes

Because now a defined starting point is available, a standardized interface to a Java-Virtual-Machine can be implemented. This interface can be developed independent from the actual source code of a method. Even if this interface is in development and not usable for a real purpose, it is continuously possible to generate working methods.

3.2 Coupling a Java Virtual Machine with compiled object code

This section describes the handling of shared libraries in more detail. On a first view, it is only necessary to use the “-shared” option of the compiler to produce shared libraries. Fig.6 shows two examples of linking an executable. “Prog1.exe” is linked static. All functionality is connected to one big binary. Different executables, using the same libraries, have to store all needed object code by their own. Therefore the binaries of executables are relatively big. In contrast “Prog2.exe” is linked shared, i.e. this application only has to store the object code of the main program. All source code of the libraries is stored in the shared libraries. This object code will be loaded by the scheduler of the operating systems (OS) on starting the process. Thus the OS has to solve all dependencies as shown in Fig.6 during runtime and not during compilation time. This approach needs a strict version control system. Otherwise it cannot be guaranteed that a method is useable when needed. One incompatible library is enough to prevent the execution. Apart from that, this approach allows saving memory, because the OS can share such a library to different processes, i.e. the OS has only to load a shared library one time and all different processes can use this one. This approach is possible because different processes have different address spaces by the scheduler of the OS. In combination with the MMU (Memory Management Unit) of the processors chip set, every process has its own set of base addresses, Fig.7. Because all memory references within the object code of a shared library are offsets to these base addresses, there are no memory conflicts if a library often uses static memory as global variables. By activating a sleeping process, the scheduler activates at the same time the corresponding bases addresses for the MMU. Therefore, the activated process has automatically its own memory environment as symbolised by the red arrow. This safe mechanism has proven itself for a long time and is described e.g. in detail in *Tanenbaum (1992)*.

Fig.7: Memory management from shared libraries in multi-process systems

Fig.8: Conflict by using same libraries by two applications

In combination with a Java-Virtual-Machine (JVM), there are the same problems. The concept in the SESIS project is that the RCE is a Java application, which supports the running naval architect applications. These applications are plug-ins, which do not run as stand-alone processes but as threads within the JVM. As a consequence, all applications are part of the same process. I.e. the object code of used shared libraries has a reference to the same base registers as shown in Fig.8. Therefore, two applications using the same library can destroy the memory state of each other. The security mechanism of the operating system in combination with hardware is not available by using threads for different applications instead of processes.

Fig.9: Memory allocation of SESIS application libraries

An E4 method has to be transferred into a shared library. An obvious approach would be to compile all needed libraries of an E4 method not static but shared. Additionally, the source code of the main program can be compiled to a shared library too, as Fig.5 shows by using the pre-processor. In this case the “Lib1” and “Lib3” in Fig.8 are the main programs of two E4 methods and “Lib2” would be e.g. a numerical functionality used by both methods. Resulting from this conflict, a design decision was made to limit one E4 method has to be transferred into exactly one shared library. Thus a shared-library used within SESIS has more analogy with the static link executable of Fig.6 as the shared-library one. Fig.9 explains this mechanism. Because an application library is a container of all object code of an E4 method, the compiler has already allocated memory space relative to the generated library. A second library, using the same object code of a classical E4 library, labelled “Lib2” in Figs.7 and 8, will get an own memory space relative to itself. Although, the memory spaces of the

different application libraries are part of the memory space of the same process (they are still part of the JVM process), they have within this process-memory an own part, because they are two different shared-libraries. This allocation is handled by the dynamic link loader and not by the process scheduler of the operating system.

This approach has the further advantage of easy version handling. Because all object code needed by a method is included in one library, there are no problems in resolving dependencies between needed libraries. This allows an easy distribution of updates in a distributed environment without maintaining a complex dependency database. The application library can be stored as one item within the JAR file of an RCE plug-in. The plug-in concept allows differing between the main RCE system and additional plug-ins. Because one plug-in is only one JAR file, it is easy to handle these plug-ins. These files can be combined with a certification strategy, whereby it is easy to implement different licensing and update strategies. In terms of memory effort, this approach is sub-optimal, but it avoids a total redesign of the existing E4 methods to eliminate all memory access of global or static variables. In a classical FORTRAN environment this is nearly impossible. The approach explained here and shown in Fig.9 allows using the existing source code without radical changes.

To summarize, it should not be asserted that the duplication of object code is the best way of software design, but under practical decisions it is a good choice in view of the constraints in a large integration project as SESIS. Furthermore, there is now a clear interface between the system kernel and the physical/numerical part. Thus software scientists and engineers can concentrate on their own problems with only a small coupling to the problems of the other partners, which allows an efficient workflow. Meetings between all project partners can be focused to design decisions, which are relevant for the global system. Because of the strict partitioning between the different software worlds, problems of one part have normally no side effects on the other part.

3.3 Loading / Unloading of Application Plug-ins

After explaining the mechanism of integration of classical FORTRAN/C/C++ methods in a Java system, we will focus on the handling of the shared libraries. At first glance, there is no problem, because the Java standard has the function “System.loadLibrary(<LibName>)”. However, this function is problematic to use in the SESIS environment. The main problem is that there is no unload function. But such a function is fundamental. The application libraries described in the previous section are big because of the inclusion of all relevant object code in one library. If a user is working with the SESIS system and is starting one method after another, these methods will be not automatically unloaded after use. Thus over runtime the memory of the used computer will be filled continuously. The pure Java functionality does not allow to control which libraries are really necessary during the use of SESIS. A second problem is that some older methods are not properly initialised. Historically, simulation software in FORTRAN was developed without stringently initialising all variables. Compilers often performed the initialisation automatically, but this cannot be guaranteed, particularly not when using optimisation flags during compilation. It can happen that the functionality of a method depends on the random memory state at starting time of the method. Such bad software design has to be fixed in the source code of the method, but because of limitations in man-power these bugs can be fixed only in a long process. As a work around, such methods are often compiled with the debug flag of a compiler, which forces the compiler to include initialisation code within the binary. But this initialisation code is only executed once at starting time. In combination with the shared-library concept of SESIS there is another problem. In a classical environment methods are stand-alone processes. If a user needs different methods in a sequence or in a loop, these methods are started by the operating system as a new process and therefore the compiler included initialization is executed. Within the SESIS system the RCE is responsible for starting the application bundles. This means, the initialization code of the library will be executed only once at loading time. If the user of SESIS starts an application plug-in twice during a session, the shared-library will not be initialised a second time. This can result sometimes in corrupt computational output. The forced compiler included initialization code is only a work around for not fixed software bugs! But a system, which should be designed as a framework for a numerous software, has to be stable enough to handle methods, which

do not satisfy high quality standards. E4 alone consists already of more than 100 methods. SESIS will be an even larger framework, where we do not know yet which software will be integrated in future.

Resulting from these assumptions, an own dynamic library loader and unloader has been implemented in the RCE. By using this loader the RCE has the possibility to control exactly the application libraries. The RCE can guarantee that the start of a plug-in enforces a new load of the corresponding library and that the initialisation code is executed before use by the user. A software design problem was that such functionality needs a direct communication with the operating system. But the main RCE concept is to develop the RCE framework as a pure Java application to guarantee platform independency. The dynamic link loader has to be native code in the same way as the application libraries. Thus a shared-library of this loader is needed for every platform on which a plug-in with an application library is available. At the moment the focus for this loader is on a Linux system, because E4 methods selected for integration, are running on this operating system. But for future purpose a loader for Windows would be useful, too.

4. Link-up of the bridge simulator Simflex

So far only the structure of the SESIS system has been explained. Now we focus on how this framework can be used for naval architectural applications. We want to develop a link to the bridge simulator Simflex. This requires extraction of physical characteristics of a ship design from the ship design tool. In the SESIS project, this means using the functionality of the E4 methods within the new SESIS environment. Therefore a new SESIS application has to be implemented. This application is a new naval architectural application, which is not part of the integration task of the existing E4 methods. It will be a pure SESIS application and should demonstrate how naval architectural software can be developed within the new framework. This issue needs the following tasks:

1. Java plug-ins basing on the RCE have to be designed.
2. Fortran functionality of existing E4 methods has to be used.
3. A useful flow control between the Java and FORTRAN world has to be designed.
4. All necessary information has to be prepared and exported to Simflex.

Fig.10: Screen-shot of the new RCE platform

After solving the second item, as described in Section 3, the actual Simflex application could be designed. This application has been designed as shown in Fig.9. A RCE plug-in controls the user interaction, and a shared-library imports all needed naval architectural functionality. This shared library is a collection of existing E4 libraries and newly developed Simflex relevant functionality. The corresponding Java plug-in controls the communication with the RCE. It loads and unloads the shared

application library and handles the workflows of the application. Especially the last point is a main difference in contrast to the existing E4 methods, which are integrated to the RCE framework. Because these are existing methods, the workflow is already implemented within the main program of the FORTRAN part of the application. These methods are classical procedural programs with a workflow symbolised in Fig.10 (A). The control loop is part of the algorithms and user interaction depends from state of the workflow. Modern applications are normally event driven as shown in Fig.10 (B). This workflow does not have a main-loop, which controls the application. The main-loop in event-driven application is only needed to poll continuously I/O-devices and react to events from them. Such events are for example mouse- or key-events. The task of the software engineer is not to define exactly every sequential step of user-interaction and numerical processing, but the way of handling the user input.

For existing methods it is nearly impossible to redesign the workflow. Moreover the benefit of such a redesign would be less than the effort invested. The disadvantage is that only little functionality of the RCE is available within a method. But because the existing methods are already designed without the new RCE functionality this is no disadvantage at the moment. Just in the moment, when these methods will be adjusted with functionality of the RCE there will be some problems. But such adjustments are at the moment not part of the project. Nevertheless they will be not ignored. Concepts are available to implement an interface for calling RCE functionality from the side of the application-library. The Java-Native-Interface allows such calls from native code to Java, but the problem is to handle objects from a procedural language like FORTRAN. Approaches as described in *Abels (2005)* can be used to handle object-oriented tasks within FORTRAN software, if they are necessary for communication with the Java part of the RCE framework.

But differing from existing methods, which should be integrated in SESIS, new methods are less restricted. Because the Simflex method is totally new, the workflow has to be designed from scratch. Now the Java part of the application will be used not only for loading and starting of the method, but to control the complete application. I.e. the interface is more complex as one of a classical method. Fig.10 (B) shows that there are lot of calls from the GUI plug-in to the FORTRAN library. By implementation of the main control on the Java plug-in part, the software designer can use in an easy way both, the Java RCE functionality and the numerical FORTRAN libraries with all naval architect know-how.

The RCE framework handles the database of ship information. Corresponding to the privileges of the user, it is possible to initialise the FORTRAN application library with the needed data. Due to historic reasons, the E4 library functionality need a set of binary files, which represent the database of all ship information. A long-term target is to map this binary file database to a relational or object-oriented database. In a first step, the binary format will be used further, but the files will not be longer handled by the clients' file systems. Each binary file will be stored as one item within a RCE controlled database. This database does not need to be located on the local client. It can be somewhere in the distributed RCE network. The RCE will handle the communication with the database, while the FORTRAN libraries will only see a temporary local copy of the database files. These files will be locked during use of the library and written back after use to the real location of the database, wherever it will be. These details are no longer relevant for the numerical FORTRAN library. E.g. information about resistance curve, manoeuvring or seakeeping behaviour can be used as before. But in contrast to the existing integrated E4 methods the new one can change the database during runtime of the application. Because the control loop is on the side of RCE, the Simflex method triggers the loading and initialising process not only once at starting of the application, but every time it is needed. This allows to use rudder, propeller or other information not only from the actual project. This is momentary no feature of the classical data model. At present, there are special import/export functions necessary to transfer explicit information from one project to another.

Further the Java plug-in is able to use directly all file input/output and network functionality of the RCE. The FORTRAN part of the application will load and calculate all characteristics of the ship design which have to be passed to the bridge simulator Simflex. This is primary a numerical task

which is already implemented within the existing E4 system. The post-processing and transferring of information to the correct destination is primary an IT task, which will be supported by the RCE. Depending on whether it has to be stored just to a special destination within the file system or perhaps transferring it directly with email to someone, the corresponding output module can be used.

This software design structure allows large flexibility. The power-user can develop functionality as before. But if the classical software environment is not enough, one can use the new features of the RCE. While work on the Simflex method continues, the main structure has been implemented and proven its functionality. Ship design characteristics have been extracted from the classical E4 environment. The new SESIS application has shown that the software set-up is able to handle the task of building a link from the design tool to the bridge simulator within the SESIS framework. Soon it should be possible to create new designs and simulate those in bridge simulations as shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11 Bridge simulator view of the port of Copenhagen

5. Conclusion

Different types of software can be integrated, but there are many detail problems. Especially the combination of interpreted Java byte code and compiled object code is complicated, requiring closer examination of the memory handling. Features, which are normally handled by the operating system, have to be handled within a JVM by the software developer. This requires effort, but is feasible. The integration of a big software system like E4 is possible. Theoretically, there are no principal problems. The Java-Native-Interface between a Java and native code allows implementing all types of interfaces. In practice there are many problems, because the existing source code of such projects imply many constraints. Besides aspects of software design, restrictions in man-power drive solutions in practice. A balance between clear and quality software and required effort in man-power has to be found.

The Simflex link-up allowed to demonstrate that the problem of software integration can be handled. Using shared-libraries as a container for the needed object code of existing FORTRAN methods allowed to solve problems of memory consistence. Further, such a container allows an easy handling of loading and unloading of functionality which is necessary for the JVM, by memory handling.

The project has also shown that a complex system, composed of such many different technologies, needs a close communication between different project partners. Despite an overall coherent structure, the structure must contain a separation between IT parts and engineering parts to allow individual

specialists to work on their fields of expertise. Suitable interfaces require communication between the partners.

Beside the integration of existing FORTRAN based ship design methods, it was investigated, in which way a power-user (i.e. an engineer with average know-how in software techniques) is able to implement a naval architectural application within a complex IT framework. A design structure for using existing numerical functionality was developed. The link-up from SESIS to the Simflex bridge simulator is under development, with the principle functionality being already proven.

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Introducing Damage Structural Assessment to Onboard Decision Support Tools

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Abstract

This paper discusses the introduction of structural assessment technology into onboard tools in response to incidents such as grounding and demonstrates how the tool can be used to assess an emergency scenario. A number of assessment techniques are demonstrated including a progressive collapse method used to analyse the longitudinal strength of the hull girder and fatigue methods are also incorporated to allow the management of any cracks that may occur in the structure as a result of damage or during operation. The information produced by the tool augments the extensive damage control training provided to Royal Navy crew extending the capability to assess scenarios to identify potential recovery plans or whether further failures will result in the loss of the ship.

1. Introduction

The introduction of computerised loading instruments has provided an ideal opportunity for marine software developers to provide additional tools which may assist crew in operating the ship and improving the performance of the vessel. Although extending loading computer software to cover emergency scenarios by incorporating damage stability analysis was a small step technologically, it allows sufficiently trained ship crew to make an accurate assessment of the situation at the site of a collision or grounding incident. Furthermore, shore side emergency response service often work with the same software as installed on the ship and can support crew throughout the incident.

Fig.1: MSC Napoli (left) suffer major cracking during a January storm in 2007 (note the sharp bend in the shear strake. The Prestige (right) suffered cracking during 2002 and sank.

However, incidents where catastrophic structural failure is a more likely danger than capsizing or sinking may leave crew with a major dilemma. Statistics show that collisions and grounding rarely happen in high sea states unlike structural failure which becomes more likely as a result of the increased wave induced loading. Abandoning a perfectly safe ship exposes the crew to additional risks especially in stormy weather but if they decide to stay onboard and ship breaks up the opportunity to leave may have passed. Mariners often face very difficult conditions during storms. Confusion and incorrect or lack of action may allow a minor issue to propagate into a significant incident as demonstrated in the cases of MSC Napoli and Prestige, Fig.1.

Structural analysis plays a significant role in the design of vessels but there are relatively few examples of structural analysis capability in tools that may be used during vessel operation particular in emergencies. There are many reasons for this. Detailed structural analysis is still an emerging technology which means that confidence in the accuracy of results still needs to be improved to the extent that experts are happy for these tools to be used in the live environment of an emergency

incident. By proceeding with sensitivity to the assumptions behind structural analysis techniques and to the users expected to operate these systems, tools can be developed today capable of supplying accurate information in a concise manner allowing crew to make informed decisions when managing structural damage.

2. Background

Although naval vessels are often treated differently to commercial vessels, the problems Naval ship operators face have parallels to any other ship operating company. The ships need to be kept operational for as long as possible maintaining a high level of safety and there is a need to minimise the running and maintenance costs despite the fact that the physical operational requirements may be different to all other vessels. While these ships are designed to operate in hostile circumstances, the reality is that in terms of the life span of the ship these instances may be few. Consequently, most of the time, the vessels are subjected to the same environmental and operational hazards that all other vessels are exposed to.

While naval vessels experience grounding and collisions as much as any other vessels, there is often a higher public profile associated with these incidents especially when images are broadcast worldwide in news reports. The Royal Navy has experienced a number of notable incidents in recent history, Table I.

Table I: Incidents involving damage to Royal Navy vessels.

Ship	Year	Incident	Damage
HMS SOUTHAMPTON	1988	Collision	Extensive damage to the full depth of the hull with penetration to B/4
HMS BRAZEN	1995	Grounding	Significant raking damage from Stem to Echo Section
HMS GRAFTON	2000	Grounding	Slight damage to sonar equipment
HMS NOTTINGHAM	2002	Grounding	Significant raking damage over half ship length
HMS GRIMSBY	2006	Grounding	Damage to GRP hull significant enough for ship to require transportation on a heavy lift ship.

The incident involving HMS NOTTINGHAM forms the basis of the work presented in this paper. The damage experienced by ship was the significant enough that the loss of the ship was a possibility and it was largely due to the efforts of the crew that the ship was saved. Since the incident a lot of material, including photos and reports of the incident, have been collected and this is now being extensively used to improve procedures, training and to develop the tools available to both ship crew and shore support teams.

2.1 The Grounding of HMS NOTTINGHAM

HMS NOTTINGHAM is a Type 42 destroyer built in 1978. Whilst on passage from Australia to New Zealand in July 2002, she grounded on Wolf Rock near Lord Howe Island, 425 miles north east of Sydney. The ship had turned into the wind to recover a helicopter returning from the Island and was travelling at 12 knots. The ships general alarm was sounded at about 22:00 and a broadcast was made to increase the watertight integrity of the vessel. On arrival at the ships main damage control centre, it took the Marine Engineering Officer around 10 minutes to receive damage information around the ship and produce an initial estimate of the extent of the damage. The following relevant points are highlighted in *McCarthy (2006)*.

1. Communications were lost with the outlying parts of the ship very rapidly. Flooding reports were obtained relatively quickly but damage reports were limited as compartments were flooded and subsequently sealed.
2. The forward Engine Room bulkhead was considered a structural priority, principally since its

loss would have resulted in a significant loss in the ship's remaining stability.

3. The priority in the initial response was to deal with the extensive flooding.
4. Communications with shore based authorities (Emergency Response Centres) were complex and had to be made from ashore.
5. Considerable effort and manpower was expended erecting shoring on bulkheads and hatches.
6. The flooding was fully under control and ship assessed as safe after 4½ hours.
7. A full damage assessment was only possible 12 hours after the initial incident at 10:00 the next day, with the assistance of divers who has been dispatched to Lord Howe Island by the Royal Australian Navy when they were informed of the incident.
8. The first teams from the UK MOD Salvage and Mooring Organisation (The Primary Emergency Response Team for Warships) arrived after approximately 3 days.
9. Damage strength calculations were undertaken in UK (by QinetiQ).

Fig.2: HMS NOTTINGHAM near Lord Howe Island. Floating attitude (left), Flooded Forward Machinery spaces (right)

2.2 Post Incident Activities

Once the ship had been stabilised the activity to recover the vessel could begin. The ship was moved to relative shelter near the island and provisions were made to recover the crew, the ship being no longer habitable. During the next month preparations were made to tow the ship to Sydney where the vessel would be placed upon a heavy lift vessel for return to the UK. Since the vessel suffered racking damage to most of the forward portion, extensive structural analysis was required to prove that the vessel could be towed the 425 miles to Sydney without loss. These calculations were made by QinetiQ, (the then privatised government defence research agency), using in-house analysis tools capable of handling damage structure. Manual definition was required to digitise ship structural plans before the tools could be used. The ship was successfully returned to the UK without further incident.

Fig.3: Racking damage to the hull of HMS NOTTINGHAM including the loss of the starboard stabiliser

2.3 Lessons Learned

One of the points identified by reviewing the incident was that the emergency response team on ship and shore had limited access to any structural information that could guide them during activities to stabilise the ship and then recover the vessel. Unlike damage stability, relevant information regarding the residuary strength of the vessel could only be obtained by engaging third party consultants leaving on site experts with only their experience and judgement when making decisions in the short term.

As a result of the lack of readily available structural analysis information which could be used to support decisions relating to damage, a project was put together to develop software tools capable of being used onboard ship which could be used to assist those responding to an incident. The project brought together three methods namely:

- Ultimate strength of the hull girder
- Bulkhead collapse due to hydrostatic loading
- Risk of brittle fracture due to cracking

3. Decision Support Tools for Structural Damage

There are already a range of different decision support tools available which cover the stability aspects of damage. The objective of stability based decision support tools is to warn of the imminent loss of stability and provide a means to allow the user to assess mitigation options which will either prevent or prolong failure allowing all to be evacuated from the vessel. Loss of stability will almost always result in capsizing or sinking leading to loss of the ship.

The loss of structural integrity through damage may not result in such a catastrophic failure as a capsized ship. In fact, a complete failure of the hull girder may separate the vessel into two parts each of which is perfectly stable and structurally sound allowing safe abandonment and some form of recovery. However, unlike stability, the structural failure mode and the amount of time available to evacuate the ship may not be predicted so easily and may lead to indecision.

Furthermore, a scenario consisting of structural damage and flooding of watertight compartment produces a coupling effect between the stability and strength of the vessel. Further flooding increases the load on the vessel which may lead to subsequent structural failure which in turn will lead to further flooding. Consequently, a ship that is ultimately predicted to capsize may fail sooner if the residual strength is exceeded as the ship floods progressively.

4. Naval Ship Structures

The structure of naval vessels is often lighter than their commercial counterpart due to a number of factors. The maintenance of structural integrity in an incident involving damage is considered a most important priority. The operational requirements of naval vessels mean that they should be kept as light as possible to be able to maintain a high cruising speed. They are not required to carry deadweight loads of any significance which means that environmental loads form the largest variable load experienced by the hull girder. However, they will be designed to withstand the shock loads which result from near mine or torpedo explosions. Consequently, the structure must be able to accept a certain level of damage without catastrophic failure.

Historically, these vessels have been developed by large design departments funded by the nation which may extensively research requirements and the capability of design solutions before a final version of the vessel is selected. Naval rules developed for structural design will, over time, incorporate the results of experiments and experience. This is in contrast the approach of classification societies which must use a “one-size fits all” approach to maintain a cost effective service for the entire life cycle of a vessel.

As a result of the significant amount of research available to them, naval ship designers have been better positioned to understand the behaviour of structural arrangements employed on their vessels

allowing them to go beyond the elastic limits and exploit the plastic behaviour of structural materials. This has allowed the use of thinner structural elements and the weight of the vessel becomes lighter. Given that naval ships may experience hostile damage, one of the primary design challenges is to ensure the ship can survive a certain level of damage to structure and systems and still remain operational. A great deal of knowledge is required to develop ships with a high level of robustness and redundancy. This experience has been built up over a significant period of time and has produced a large number of analysis tools during the process. This project has utilised these tools by bringing them together in a software application which allows users to assess structural damage to ships and provide information upon which they may base their subsequently decisions.

5. Factors Affecting the Analysis of Real Ship Structures

Structural analysis performed during the design phase of a vessels life fundamentally assesses an imaginary situation. Fabrication problems may be encountered during the production of the vessel and changes will be made as the ship goes through refit processes which may lead to distortions and discontinuities in the structure. Material quality may differ to those originally specified. Furthermore, corrosion, wear and operation will reduce the size of structural members. Consequently, a considerable number of additional factors must be taken into account when analysing the structure of a ship that may have been in service for a number of years:

Panel Distortion: This is often described as the “staved horse” look often associated with naval vessels. Any distortion will mean that amount of loading (particularly compressive loading) the structure can withstand before fails may be reduced.

Variation in Material Quality: The quality of material specified during in the design process may not be the same as used on the ship. This may be due to variability in the quality of the material produced by the foundry or the yard may have chosen to use alternative specifications.

Poor Detailing: The structure of the ship is different to that shown on the plans. Poor alignment and continuity of structural members may result increased stress around joints resulting in local failure or worse, instigation of a crack.

Poor Treatment: Once the ship is in service there are many factors which may change the effectiveness of the structure. Bad treatment during loading such as the use of Tugs in the wrong place along the hull or the use pneumatic drills to release cargo may damage the ship structure.

Corrosion: Over time corrosion will affect structural materials reducing the thickness of plate and stiffeners profiles.

It is difficult to develop mathematical rules which model the effect of each of these points on the load carrying capacity of the hull structure. However, by measuring the performance of structural materials on vessels in-service and performing practical experiments on similar structural arrangements the effect of these issues can be factored into the analysis models.

6. Modelling Loads Experienced by the Structure

The most important factor when carrying out any structural analysis is the accurate capture of the loads experienced by the ship. Furthermore, certain analysis approaches may be precluded from use because not all the loads experienced by the vessel will be known. Loads experienced by a damaged ship may be broken down into the following groups:

Intact Loading Condition: Weight of structure and equipment plus any fluids and cargo carried by the vessel will all impart a load on the structure when opposed by buoyancy forces generated by the hull. This “still water” load distribution is often accurately captured in the departure loading condition that is generated as part of standard stability management procedures. It can be kept up to date during a

voyage by monitoring the state of tanks and stores so that it is readily available if any emergency situation is encountered.

Flooding: Once the watertight integrity of the hull has been breached, additional loads will be placed on the hull structure as a result of the water entering the vessel. These loads can be predicted by observing the height of floodwater or by using flooding sensors if fitted. These loads can be used to augment the intact loading distribution.

Grounding: Grounding loads may increase loading quite significantly as the load application may be quite localised if the vessel is grounded on a pinnacle for example. Grounding often results in some localised plate deformation, but if the hull is punctured floodwater will enter the hull.

Environmental Loads: The most difficult piece of information required for structural analysis is the accurate capture of the wave loads experienced. The variety of loads known and the associated confidence in the data may have the greatest influence over the types of analysis techniques that can be used confidently to assess the damage structural performance of the hull girder. The hull girder is exposed to several different loading modes. The easiest to understand are the longitudinal loads produced by the peaks and troughs of the waves. However, the ship is also subjected to lateral and torsion loads which are less well understood. It is possible to predict these loads using hydrodynamic software allowing an estimate of what the vessel may actually experience to be obtained. However, without full scale measurement there may be limited confidence in the accuracy of these predictions.

First of class vessels are often instrumented with strain gauges to capture the forces the ship structure experiences during operation. The Royal Navy is no exception and has had several vessels instrumented for a number of years. Historically, instrumentation onboard Royal Navy vessels has focused on longitudinal loading. This information has been combined with hydrodynamics studies performed using the WASIM code developed by DNV to produce loading models which are compatible with mature structural analysis codes. The models are parameterised by sea state, information which can be estimated with a good degree of accuracy by crew and included as part of the initial conditions of any structural analysis.

Current finite element models are capable of accounting for lateral and torsion loads in addition to longitudinal loads. However, as there is not yet enough measured data (experience) relating to lateral and torsion loads within the MOD support network. Experts do not yet have the confidence to employ recent advances in structural analysis tools in situations where robust, accurate results and guidance is required in situations where the safety of the ship and its personnel are involved. Meanwhile, data collection will continue onboard vessels in the fleet and the instrumentation will be improved so that, in the future, more detailed analysis techniques may be used.

7. Limit State Failure Criteria

The final piece of information required is some form of criteria against which the results of any analysis can be compared to indicate a level of severity to the crew. This information can then be used to develop a plan to bring the emergency situation under control and recover the ship. Alternatively, if analysis indicates that the ship is beyond repair and the structure is in danger of catastrophic failure then a decision to abandon ship may be taken. Unlike analysis performed during design which is often levied with a conservative safety factor, decision support tools need to be able to predict outcome of a damage scenario with a high degree of accuracy and confidence. Furthermore, as there may be significant deformation in the structure which may affect the operation of important systems onboard the vessel, the situation may become untenable long before there is catastrophic failure. The failure criteria of a bulkhead, for example, may be based on the maximum level of deformation that can be tolerated before fixtures and fittings fail rather than on the limits of the structure itself. This example illustrates that the exact details of limit state criteria will be dependent on the design of the ship and will require expert knowledge of the ship's operation and emergency procedures to develop. However, limit state criteria used by this study are based entirely on the performance of the structure to allow

operators to build up experience with the tool before more realistic criteria are proposed.

8. Usability

The final point that needs consideration is that the decision support system may be used onboard ship by users who are not structural analysis experts. This means that both the input data and guidance produced by the tools needs to be relevant to them. At the same time, experts on the shore side emergency response team may also be using the same tool to verify the onboard results and suggest alternative recovery plans.

Numerical results produced by the structural analysis tools need to be transformed into illustrative and descriptive guidance. Graphical displays such as traffic lights and information overlaid over general arrangement plans can be used to accurately convey the severity of a particular hazard with a minimum level of interpretation on the part of the crew allowing them to focus on prioritising their actions. Any information provided by the software should follow the same style and terminology to existing practices and training making it easier to adapt any guidance into ship procedures.

Finally, any analysis implemented in a decision support system must be capable of producing results on a rapid basis. If a tool requires a significant amount time to perform calculation any results may be invalid if the damage scenario has suffered further failures as a result of progressive flooding or the environmental effects. The tools need to be able to return results at least as fast as damage control crews can respond to the unfolding scenario so that the team can prioritise the shoring up of sensitive locations as soon as they are identified.

9. Selected Structural Analysis Routines

There are a larger number of tools available for structural assessment. A smaller subset allow enough simplification for onboard use given the availability and accuracy of information that may be obtained in an emergency scenario, time available for analysis and usefulness of results that may be presented to the user. The tools utilised in this project have been selected on the basis of experience. These approaches and tools have been used for a number of years which means that there is a good degree of confidence in the accuracy of input data and applicability of results produced by these tools.

9.1 Assessing the Ultimate Strength of the Hull Girder

Hull girder failure occurs when the loading (bending moment) at a particular longitudinal location (section) exceeds the structural capability of that section. Damage to any longitudinal continuous structure at a particular section reduces the ability of that section to withstand the same loads as if it were intact. Hull girder failure is assessed by a progressive analysis code known as NS94D developed by QinetiQ. The NS94D calculates at the ultimate strength of transverse sections through the hull structure using a load shortening code method that assess the plastic limits of structure. Studies, *Arason* (2002), comparing a number of structural analysis methods have indicated that this method is capable of producing results that are equivalent to 3D finite element analysis and with much less processing time.

At each chosen section, the ship structure is discretised into a stiffener/plate element representation and progressively loaded. Two limit states are identified at each angle of heel. The load required for the first element in the section to yield, i.e. reach the elastic limit of its material properties and the load required for all elements to reach their elastic limit. Structure is not usually designed to go beyond its elastic properties but when it does it will not immediately fail until it reaches the plastic limits of the material. Another failure mode incorporated into the analysis software is plate buckling which happens when compressive loads are applied. The relative distance between the 'first-yield' point and the ultimate strength of the section may be used to indicate if catastrophic failure is imminent once a section begins to fail. Localised yielding can be often beneficial as plastic deformation may allow loads to be shared with surrounding structure.

Stress strain relationships for individual elements are modelled using load shortening curves which take account of geometrical arrangement and material qualities. Realistic material properties and defects can be modelled by modifying load shortening curve data. This has been achieved by performing non-linear finite element analysis using the FABSTRAN code, *Dow* (1986).

Damage structure is simulated by removing elements of the section reducing the load carry capacity of the section. At present damage is defined using a number of cuboids. Any element within a damage cuboid is removed from the analysis. As the analysis is based on a 2D approach, the ends of cuboids are tapered into wedge shapes to reduce the effectiveness of elements in neighbouring sections and allow stress flow to be modelled more representatively.

9.2 Assessing the Bulkhead Failure

The method used to assess the failure of bulkheads is straightforward and does not require a great deal of explanation. Based on an approach described in *Chalmers* (1993), it identifies the maximum hydrostatic head required for panel spans between decks to fail. The failure mechanism is based on a three point plastic hinge. This method assumes that there is little deflection of deck structure due to hydrostatic loading and that these supporting structural members remain effective. In the future it is hoped to upgrade these tools so that it will take account of hydrostatic loading to both bulkheads and decks.

9.3 Analysing the Probability of Brittle Fracture due to Cracking

Brittle fracture can be caused by a number of reasons. Low toughness steels can fail as a result of rapid variations in stress intensity as a result of collision or weapons damage for example. High toughness steels can fail as a result of low temperatures, large crack sizes or high residual stress intensity. Cracks can often provide a good indicator of future brittle fracture. Furthermore, the increased use of high tensile steels with low fatigue tolerance means that brittle failure may occur much earlier after crack initiation. As a result, Classification societies strongly recommend that any cracking should be repaired immediately due to the potentially serious consequences that may occur if a crack propagates potentially leading to brittle fracture of the hull structure. However, there is anecdotal evidence that ships have been able to operate safely with large cracks. Therefore, a method has been developed which allows the future likelihood of brittle fracture, as a result of the formation of a crack, to be assessed.

Brittle fracture will occur when the stress intensity factor, which is a combination of crack length and loading, exceeds the material toughness. However, up to that point, the crack will continue to propagate as a function of material properties, temperature and changing stress intensity. Both material properties and stress loading will experience some degree of variability and can be modelled with probabilistic distributions. Physical measurements are required to determine both sets of information. Charpy tests can be used to determine material toughness by testing a large number of samples with respect to temperature. Statistical models of stress intensity can be obtained experimentally or by instrumenting vessels with monitoring equipment although it may also be estimated using hydro-elastic analysis.

POSF is used to assess the probability of brittle fracture. It uses an iterative method to propagate crack length and calculate the associated risk of failure. Stress loads are based on the position of the crack in the structure and the current loading condition factored by wave induced load distributions based on in service measurements. Wave induced loads are parameterised by sea state which is set by the user who also specifies temperature. Risk of failure is presented to the user in the form of a traffic light display where the limit state criteria, Table II, is representative of threshold levels of fracture over the year within the world wide shipping fleet.

Table II: Limit State Criteria for Brittle Fracture

State	World Wide Fleet Wide Events per Year
Green → Amber	5×10^{-4}
Amber → Red	4×10^{-3}

10. Including Structure in the Ship Model

Fig.4: The stability model (left) and structural model (right) in Paramarine.

A model of ship compartmentation and structure must be developed before the effects of damage to watertight integrity and structure can be assessed. Most UK naval vessels have stability models developed in Paramarine as part of existing onboard installations of Seagoing Paramarine prior this project. Paramarine also provides a structural definition capability for ship design purposes that could with a small amount of extension, be adapted to allow accurate structural detailing. Paramarine's structural modelling tools are, however, primarily aimed at design structural analysis rather than the development of detailed production information. Consequently, they are simpler and more parametric than some of the detailed structural modelling tools found in other integrated ship design systems. The structural model of a ship is broken down into two elements, panels and girders. A panel is a surface that has attributes describing material, thickness and stiffener placement. The location of each stiffener can be customised using end points which lie on the edges of the panel and define the stiffener as a straight line. At no point is any geometry developed which represent plate thickness or extruded stiffener profiles. The rendered image of the structural model shown on screen, Fig.4, is generated from the attribute parametric information associated with each panel. Girders are defined in a similar parametric manner being stiffener profiles associated with the shared edge of two adjacent panels. All structural specifications are associated with tolerances which can be used to introduce corrosion affects and reduce effectiveness of structural members in the hull.

11. Seagoing Paramarine

Paramarine is an integrated ship design tool which allows users to represent or design using solid modelling tools and perform analysis on the ship model geometry. In 2000, an onboard Paramarine based tool called Seagoing was released which could support ships crew and shore side project teams in daily stability check calculations and, in case of emergency, could support damage stability and grounding calculations. Unlike Paramarine, where the user must build the ship model themselves, the ship model in Seagoing is preloaded allowing an alternative user interface to be used which is specifically focused on loading condition and stability calculations. Graphical views are used to show the user which tanks have contents and where solid loads are located. The Seagoing software has been installed on all major Royal Navy vessels over the last 4 years and has been incorporated into both shore side and large scale exercise training.

Fig.5: The Seagoing Paramarine user interface (left) mimics the damage control board (right). The damage control board photo is from the grounding of HMS NOTTINGHAM.

The grounding incident involving HMS NOTTINGHAM showed that there was a need to have readily accessible structural analysis tools alongside the stability assessment tools already in use.. The analysis tools discussed previously were available to experts supporting the recovery of HMS NOTTINGHAM. However, as they were primarily in-house tools, they lacked the user interface and support required for onboard use. Using Paramarine's structural definition model, these tools were integrated into Seagoing by developing user interface tools that would allow non-expert users to define and assess scenarios involving damaged structure.

11.1 Responding to an Emergency Situation

The Seagoing Paramarine user interface is generically windows based so that it can support a wide range of analysis functions that have been integrated into the system. As the software may be used infrequently, it incorporates a simple menu driven wizard system which allows the user to perform any analysis on the basis of answering simple questions. On selecting to look at a damage situation, the user is asked to ensure that the loading condition inside the software is the same as the actual condition of the vessel before being taken to a ship plan view where damage to watertight integrity can be defined. The graphical presentation of the ship arrangement is displayed in exactly the same style as used on the damage control board on the vessel, Fig.5.

Fig.6: The Seagoing Paramarine interface for structural damage. The damage is defined by drawing a red rectangle on the arrangement.

After the stability of the vessel has been assessed, the user is asked if they want to review the effect of structural damage using the Ultimate Strength, Bulkhead failure or Brittle Fracture analysis tools. In all three cases a traffic light approach is used to indicate the severity of the situation.

11.2 Assessing Structural Damage to the Hull Girder

The effect of structural damage to the hull girder is displayed on a graph, Fig 7. The ultimate strength of the hull girder is assessed by comparing the combined still water bending moment and wave induced bending moment, with the first yield and ultimate strength limit states for Hog and Sag respectively. If any of the bending moment curves resulting from the load exceeds the first yield limit state then an amber warning condition is displayed on the traffic light. If the ultimate strength limit state is exceeded then a red condition is displayed, Fig 8. The graphical curves are overlaid on top of the profile to highlight locations where structural capacity is limited.

Fig.7: The structural capability of an intact vessel. Capability is indicated by the upper and lower pair of curves and current loading is illustrated by the middle three curves.

Fig.8: The structural capability of a damaged vessel based on the information illustrated in Fig.6.

11.3 Assessing the Serviceability of Bulkheads

Bulkhead strength is assessed by comparing the pressure head resulting from flooding against the capability of the bulkhead structure. The pressure head on each side of the bulkhead is calculated by evaluating the amount of fluid in neighbouring compartments. A profile of the vessel is displayed with each bulkhead highlighted and an associated circle representing the traffic light state with amber and red colours being used to indicate the proximity of the structure to failure, Fig 9. From the profile, a cross section view of the bulkhead can be displayed allowing experts to look at the analysis results for each structural panel.

Fig.9: The risk of bulkhead failure is illustrated using a traffic light display, the circle below the frame number (left). More detailed information on bulkhead serviceability is displayed by reviewing the transverse structure (right).

11.4 Managing the Growth of Cracks to Prevent Brittle Fracture

The fracture analysis tools, unlike those described in the previous sections can be used independently of physical damage to the hull structure allowing cracks that appear as part of everyday operation to be assessed. Individual cracks are defined using a wizard interface. The user first selects a longitudinal location, Fig 10, and then goes on to identify where in the transverse section the crack has been observed. Next, the user defines some basic parameters such as crack length, sea state and whether it emanates from a physical hole in the hull structure.

Fig.10: Cracks are located by choosing the longitudinal position (left) and then specifying the failed panel (right).

The results of the analysis are displayed as a histogram using traffic light colours to describe the severity of the crack length, Fig 11. The current crack length is displayed as a horizontal line across

the chart. By inspecting the bar with the closest temperature from the bottom axis and comparing the crack length indicated on the left axis with the colour, the user can identify the status. If it is in the green area then the crack can be left until the next practical opportunity for repair. If it is in the amber zone then it should be repaired as soon as possible but the crack does present an immediate risk of failure. If it is in the red zone then the crack should be repaired immediately. Another display provides an estimate of the amount of time that may elapse before the crack enters the amber state. The tool can be used to identify critical crack length allowing monitoring procedures to be introduced where cracks are checked and repairs scheduled. Furthermore, the user may change sea state to assess the effect of adverse weather which may be used to determine whether the ship should seek a shelter port if it cannot be repaired.

Fig. 11: Risk of brittle fracture is illustrated using a histogram of temperature against crack length with the severity being indicated by traffic light colours.

12. Use of Software Onboard Ship in an Emergency Context

The design of the software user interface, particular for onboard tools, can result in passionate debates and for good reason. Decision support tools used for emergency response may only be used in anger when there is a significant risk to the ship and personnel. The user may have limited expertise and will be under a great deal of pressure. Consequently, misuse and misinterpretation of information supplied by the software (or any other complex user driven system for that matter) may further exacerbate an unfolding emergency situation.

The Seagoing software is perhaps in a unique position in that it is deployed onboard naval vessels where training is a frequent activity. Ships crews spend a great deal of time training to respond to flooding and fire so that they can act instinctively if the ship becomes damaged during a hostile situation. Furthermore, the software has been incorporated into the stability courses that engineering crew receive as part of their shore side training. That said, Marine Engineering Officers have stated they would initially follow their normal procedures in the event of damage, but would then consult the software after flooding is under control.

The introduction of structural analysis into software has a particular impact on the design of the user interface that is intended to be used by crew in emergencies and has to be undertaken with some considerate care. Although there are many stability tools which provide support during emergencies no proper precedent has been set for the best way to provide support for structural damage. Furthermore, training of engineering officers in structural matters is limited compared to stability even though many will hold qualifications to master's degree level and have chartered status. Therefore, the software is being gradually introduced a period of years. Firstly to shore side support teams, with trials onboard a single ship so that feedback can be captured before the software is rolled out more widely to other vessels. In the short term, the design of the user interface has been based on experience of the development team, the naval structures group within the UK MOD (TES-SSG) and

the experts who have developed the structural analysis routines (QinetiQ Rosyth).

13. Concluding Remarks

The extensive structural damage experienced during the grounding of HMS Nottingham in 2002 identified a real need for structural analysis software that can be used in a live and evolving emergency situation. In seeking to address this gap in technology, for the UK Royal Navy, a decision support system has been developed which combines both stability and structural analysis in software which can be used onboard ship.

A range of structural analysis routines were selected on the basis of experience taking account of accuracy, availability of compatible long term statistics for environmental loading, the range information that crew are able to provide and above all confidence in the techniques. The analysis routines cover a range of different structural problems that a ship may face, at both global and local levels, and must account for the fact that the real ship structure may differ from the original design.

It is clear that software quality and the design the visual interfaces contribute greatly to the accuracy and effectiveness in which a tool can be used. Moreover, in this particular case, the software is intended for use in emergency situations where the user will be stressed. To evaluate the latter is the purpose of trials on board and a long integration phase with the project teams who operate the ships. During this process feedback will be collected and used to enhance the design of the software and alternative approaches for displaying guidance explored.

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Improvements to a Knowledge-based CAD System for Conceptual Ship Design

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Abstract

This paper presents several improvements for a knowledge-based CAD system. The improvements follow from the experience gained during the first major application of the system: the design of a Joint Logistic Support Ship (a new type of naval auxiliary vessel) at the Netherlands Ministry of Defence. The improvements focus on three areas. First, further increase flexibility to allow the designers to investigate a broader range of designs in a given time frame. Second, reduce the programming effort when developing new geometry scripts. Third, include a solid-based geometry definition to increase the robustness of geometry scripts and performance prediction, e.g. stability and signatures. Together, the improvements greatly enhance the existing capability of the knowledge-based CAD system.

1 Introduction

Van Oers and Van Hees (2006) presented a knowledge-based CAD system based around the knowledge-based shell Quaestor and the commercial NURBS modeller Rhinoceros. Several unique features make it a design environment that is more flexible than conventional CAD software. First, the system utilises VBScripts instead of manual operations to create and analyse all geometry. Second, the system separates geometry and parametric relations to enable their re-use. Third and most importantly, Quaestor's inference engine ensures that geometry is created only when required to solve for the requested goals.

For several years, the system has been used successfully by the Royal Netherlands Navy for the conceptual design of surface vessels, e.g. *Bos et al. (2004)* and *Bons (2006)*. The most elaborate application so far concerns the design of a Joint Logistic Support Ship (JLSS), a new type of naval auxiliary vessel.

This paper discusses and remedies a number of limitations encountered during the JLSS project. More specifically, the current inability of Rhinoceros to generate scripts, parameters and relations inside Quaestor's knowledge-base was found to have two important consequences. First, the scripted generation of geometry forces the user to spend significant effort on developing scripts. Moreover, the user does not have any visual feedback during programming, increasing the scope for errors. Second, the extensive use of relations to position objects, e.g. weapons or accommodation spaces, requires the user to frequently change these relations alpha-numerically in Quaestor, again without any visual reference. This reduces the incentive to make large design changes in the internal arrangement, to the detriment of the resulting design.

Section 2 provides an introduction to Quaestor, Rhinoceros and the data exchange. Section 3 discusses the JLSS design model and suggests improvements. These improvements are introduced in Section 4 to 6. Conclusions and future research are presented in Section 7.

2 Quaestor & Rhinoceros

2.1 Quaestor

Quaestor, *Van Hees (1997)*, is a knowledge-based shell consisting of an inference engine coupled to a numerical solver, operating in a network database. Inside the shell, the user defines relations, parameters and constraints.

Quaestor uses relations to store design knowledge. Relations can be of numerical, nominal (dealing with text) or binary type, e.g. access external applications. Figs.1 to 3 show an example of each. Fig.1 shows

a simple numerical relation which can be used to calculate the width of an arbitrary hull. Fig.2 shows a nominal relation that creates a VBScript (Visual Basic Script) from a document template and input parameters. Fig.3 shows a binary relation. The relation uses the VBScript from the relation in Fig.2 to access an external program and execute the VBScript remotely.

$$B_{\text{hull}} = B_{\text{hold}} + 2 * B_{\text{wingtank}}$$

Fig.1: A numerical relation

$$\text{Macro\$} = \text{TEMPLATE\$}(\text{TEXTITEM\$}(1), \emptyset, \text{length}, \text{width})$$

Fig.2: A nominal relation

$$\text{Result\#} = \text{MACRO}(\text{'Rhino4.Interface'}, \text{'D:\RhinoMacro.ipo'}, \text{Macro\$}, \text{''})$$

Fig.3: A binary relation

Parameters form the building blocks of relations; they contain data. Parameters can be of any of the following types: numerical, characters, binary or object. Numerical parameters contain numerical data. Parameters containing characters can contain for example the VBScript resulting from the relation in Fig.2. Binary parameters differ from binary relations in that they store binary data; for instance images or CAD-files. Object type parameters provide canisters to store other parameters and data. For instance, an object parameter can hold both a numerical parameter with the length of the ship together with a character parameter holding the name of the vessel.

Constraints provide conditions which must be met before a relation can be used in the computational model; therefore, constraints are tied to relations. As an example, a constraint tied to the relation in Fig.1 could require that the right hand side of the relation is larger than zero.

After feeding the knowledgebase with appropriate relations and constraints, the user can select one or more parameters as goals. To be able to solve for these goals, Quaestor's inference engine uses the available relations in the knowledgebase to assemble a coherent computational model. If multiple relations are deemed suitable, Quaestor asks the user to select the appropriate one. Quaestor applies a set of heuristic rules to establish the sequence in which relations are proposed. In addition to retrieving relations, the inference engine also prompts the user to provide input for the requested parameters. The need for user input is reduced by reversing relations, which limits the input to solely independent parameters.

During model assembly, the computational model is solved using a multi-dimensional Newton-Raphson solver. The solving takes place sequentially, i.e. requested parameters are calculated when sufficient input is provided. As a result, the memory requirement of the solver reduces and the speed of calculations improves. The solver can detect and solve closed sub-sets of relations concurrently. Even though the term computational model is used here, it consists of a combination of relations, parameters and constraints and can deal with numerical values, text and binary data in a single design and analysis model.

A key feature of Quaestor is the separation of the computational model and data of individual designs, i.e. knowledge and values. For example, an existing computational model can be re-used with different input values; alternatively, the computational model can be rebuilt to investigate different goals with different input parameters. The latter capability allows the re-use of existing relations, unlike, for example, a spreadsheet.

Van Hees and Van der Blom (2006) present an object-oriented approach, which stores and provides a hierarchical overview of design data, such as the one shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5. In addition, the structure enables the use of dynamic arrays containing the data of multiple parameters of a single type. For

example, instead of defining parameters related to the bulkheads shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5 for each bulkhead individually, the hierarchical structure allows the designer to define them once and re-use them as required.

```

Dataset[Ship]
- Ship
  - Ship
    - Hull
    - Superstructure
      - Part[1]
    - Bulkheads
      - Bulkhead[1]
      - Bulkhead[2]
    - Decks
      - Deck[1]

```

Fig.4: Hierarchical structure containing design data

Bulkhead[1]		
AreaBulkhead	187.21	m ²
AreaBulkhead\$	1	Str
CompMacroDrawBulkhead		Str
ID\$	Ship.Bulkheads.Bulkhead.1	Str
Longitudinal_Position	81	m

Fig.5: Contents of Bulkhead[1]

Ship designs exhibit dependencies between different design aspects, e.g. both hull form and general arrangement influence the initial stability. Therefore, data can be shared between different branches of the hierarchical structure. This allows the designer to take dependencies in the design into account. As a result of this sharing, the hierarchical structure may not reflect all dependencies in a design.

For a more thorough introduction to Quaestor, please refer to *Van Hees (1997)* and *Van Hees (2003)*; *Van Hees and Van der Blom (2006)* discuss the more recent developments.

2.2 Rhinoceros

Rhinoceros, *McNeel (2007)*, is a cheap and powerful general purpose CAD-package. It uses Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines (NURBS) to define curves, surfaces and solids. It also includes a large set of analysis tools, e.g. to establish area, volume and curvature properties. A powerful scripting language, based on Visual Basic script offers automated creation and analysis of geometry. Though no inherent parametric capability exists, the scripting enables the parametric design of geometry. Most importantly, using an ActiveX object, the scripting in Rhinoceros is exposed to other programs, enabling the real-time exchange of scripting commands and data derived from the CAD-model to and from other programs. In addition to the scripting, purpose-built plug-ins, written in Visual C++, enable further expansion of capabilities.

2.3 Data exchange

From the start, Quaestor has had the capabilities to execute external programs, e.g. to use analysis tools. More recently, *Van Oers (2004)* expanded this capability by enabling access to Rhinoceros through an ActiveX control object, allowing the real-time execution of Visual Basic scripts containing operations on and analysis of geometry.

Fig.6: Work flow and data exchange

```
data_from_rhino# = MACRO('Rhino4.Interface', input_file$, Script$,output_file$)
```

Fig.7: Relation to execute the script

Fig.6 shows the data exchange and work flow. The script files are generated using a template, shown in Fig.8. All characters after the '~', i.e. 'length', 'width' and 'output_file\$' are replaced with parameter values from Quaestor. In addition to defining input parameters, the template also contains script commands to create and analyse geometry inside Rhinoceros -in this case to draw a square. Fig.7 and Fig.8 also show the possibility to analyse the geometry, i.e. determine square's area, and write it to an output file to export the data back to Quaestor. This allows results to be processed in the calculation process. The relation shown in Fig.7 writes the script file, executes it in Rhinoceros, reads the resulting output file and stores the data in 'data_from_rhino#'. The inference engine in Quaestor ensures the correct order of execution.

3 Lessons learned: the JLSS design model

The most elaborate test case thus far concerns a design model for a Joint Logistic Support Ship (JLSS), currently under design at the Netherlands Ministry of Defence (*Van der Knaap (2006)*). Such a ship, shown in Fig.9, combines the functionality of an under-way replenishment vessel with a strategic sea-lift capability and support for the operation of up to four Chinook helicopters.

The design model itself was presented in *Bons (2006)* and briefly discussed in *Van Oers and Van Hees (2006)*. An in-depth description of the design model and its role in the materiel procurement process at the Netherlands Ministry of Defence is planned for a future publication. This paper focuses mainly on the geometry capabilities and design work flow employed by the model presented in *Bons (2006)*. The utility of the hierarchical structure, presented in *Van Hees and Van der Blom (2006)* and employed in the JLSS model will not be discussed.

3.1 Geometry definition

The geometry definition used is presented in *Van Oers (2004)*. The envelope consists of a hull form scaled to user-defined dimensions, shown in Fig.9. More advanced hull form deformations were lacking. The superstructure is defined as a set of solids placed on top of the hull. Decks and bulkheads are defined as surfaces, shown in Fig.9, and constructed from the intersection of a parent surface with the hull and superstructure. Tanks were defined using solids and moulded to fit the envelope, again refer to Fig.9.

```

Script$ = TEMPLATES$(TEXTITEM$(1),0, length, width, output_file$)

TEXTITEM1 = | 'Define the dimensions of the rectangle
length = ~length
width = ~width

arrPoint1 = Array(0,0,0) 'Define Arrays with the corner points
arrPoint2 = Array(length,0,0)
arrPoint3 = Array(length,width,0)
arrPoint4 = Array(0,width,0)

'Define an Array consisting of the corner points

arrPoints = Array(arrPoint1,arrPoint2,arrPoint3,arrPoint4)

strRectangle = Rhino.AddSrfPt(arrPoints) 'Add a surface in Rhino

dblArea = Rhino.SurfaceArea(strRectangle)(0) 'Calculate Area

datafile = "~output_file$" 'Define output file

'Open the output file

Set file1 = CreateObject("Scripting.FileSystemObject")
Set file2 = file1.OpenTextFile(datafile,2, True)

file2.WriteLine(Cstr(dblArea)) 'Write area value to file

file2.Close 'Close the output file
|

```

Fig.8: Relation for a VBscript that draws a square and calculates the area

Fig.9: One of the concept designs of the JLSS model showing envelope, decks, bulkheads and tanks

3.2 Internal arrangement

A distinct choice made by *Bons (2006)* in the development of the model was the extensive use of relations to define the internal arrangement. More specifically, the relations were used to describe the topology of the internal arrangement, i.e. the object (items placed onboard) sequence, and to prevent overlap among objects. Fig.10 shows some example relations dealing with the longitudinal configuration of flight deck

and hangar. The capability of Quaestor to select from multiple candidate relations, presented in *Van Oers and Van Hees (2006)*, was not employed.

```
HelicopterSpot.X1 = 0
HelicopterSpot.X2 = HelicopterSpot.X1 + HelicopterSpot.L
Hangar.X1 = HelicopterSpot.X2
Hangar.X2 = Hangar.X1 + Hangar.L
```

Fig.10: Relations defining the longitudinal configuration of the flight deck and hangar

3.3 Design work flow & proposed improvements

The purpose of the relations discussed in Section 3.2: achieve a parametric design model, had limited success. First, a significant amount of effort is spent on parameterizing the design prior to entering all relations in the Quaestor knowledgebase. Second, parametric variations inevitably led to unbalanced designs, e.g. designs with insufficient initial stability or with too little or too much available space. As a result, the relations describing the internal arrangement have to be adapted manually to regain a balanced design. Third, the altered relations are entered alpha-numerically in the Quaestor knowledgebase.

The geometry definition also presented problems. All hull form modifications are carried out in external programs, reducing the interaction between internal arrangement and envelope shape. Furthermore, performance evaluations such as intact and damaged stability prediction and signature predictions are hampered by the lack of a watertight, i.e. a solid, envelope definition.

Both the geometry definition and parametrization clearly limit the flexibility of the designer. The following practical improvements are pursued: a flexible hull form definition and a more flexible internal arrangement. Furthermore, a solid-based geometry definition and improved robustness of scripting will also be pursued. To achieve this, two improvements must be realised. The first improvement enables the generation of relations in the Quaestor knowledgebase from Rhinoceros and is discussed in Section 4. The second improvement, presented in Section 5, enables the real-time generation of parameters from Rhinoceros in the Quaestor knowledgebase.

4 Generating knowledge-base relations from inside Rhinoceros

4.1 Drawbacks of script-based geometry generation

An approach to provide a more flexible hull form definition in Quaestor and Rhinoceros was already presented in *Van Oers and Van Hees (2006)*. Building upon *Goris (2005)*, the hull surface is based on the interpolation of a set of three dimensional parametric NURBS-curves. The approach allows large changes that can be both continuous, by changing the curve parameters, and discrete, by interchanging the curves themselves. The latter enables changes to hull topology, i.e. changes that affect the number of surfaces and control points per surface. Figs.11 and 12 show an example with the parametric curves and the resulting hull surface.

One major drawback hampered the actual implementation; any new set of hull curves required extensive programming to create the required relations and scripts in the knowledgebase. This problem is generic and widespread in the knowledge-based CAD system discussed in this paper; it results from the reliance on script-based geometry definition. Programming scripts had to be carried out without any visual reference of the geometry the script would create. In addition, the parametrization of geometry also has to be developed without visual reference. Two different approaches were taken to reduce the user effort during programming: generic scripts and automated script generation. In the latter case, visual feedback during script generation was also provided.

4.2 Generic scripts

The first approach, applied to geometry that relies on a fixed parametrization, uses generic scripts to create geometry. Examples include the scripts responsible for decks, bulkheads and tanks. As the parametrization itself does not change, a generic script template suffices. Three bulkheads with different input values but a similar parametrization are shown in Fig.13. Though visual feedback during programming is welcome, for these scripts it is not essential, as they are only developed once and re-used many times. A generic routine for decks and bulkheads will be presented in Section 6.2.

Fig.11: Parametric three-dimensional curves used to define the hull surface

Fig.12: Hull surface following from interpolation of the curves in Fig.11

Fig.13: Different bulkheads with similar parametrization

4.3 Automated script generation

The second approach, used for geometry that requires a changing parametrization, is more complicated. It relies on a similar definition of the geometry under consideration. For example, the hull curves in Fig.11 are all NURBS curves with a finite but variable number of control points (each with variable weight) and a varying knot vector (which describes the number and location of kinks). The use of similar definitions can be exploited to develop an approach to generate a custom knowledgebase with the required relations and scripts. The approach consists of four steps and will be discussed below. The example deals with the generation and parametrization of hull curves, such as those shown in Fig.11.

In the first step, an user defines curves by hand, in Rhinoceros. Fig.14 shows an example: a manual deformation of the bulbous bow shape. The curve definition can be done either from scratch or by extracting

and modifying curves from existing hull surfaces. The manual definition of the curves in a graphical environment best provides the flexible and visual interaction required by the user.

Fig.14: Manual deformation of the bow curve

```

CV_x    = [0, 0.8, 7, 7, 2, 5, 8]
CV_y    = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
CV_z    = [0, 0, 1, 5, 3.27, 7, 10]
weights = [1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1]
knots   = [0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 5, 5]
degree  = [3]

```

Fig.15: Properties of the original bow curve in Fig.14

The second step consists of a script, executed manually inside Rhinoceros, that analyses the hull curves. The script retrieves the number of control points, their positions, the corresponding control point weights and the knot vector of each curve. The analysis provides sufficient information to re-create the curves, which, in turn, enables the script-based curve generation. Fig.15 shows the information retrieved by analysing the curve shown in Fig.14. The information will be inserted into a script template that consists of the code that re-creates the curves, which is adapted to the number of curves that were analysed. Prior to creating this script an additional step is required. So far, the capability only allows the conversion of curves from geometry to a script and the execution of the script to re-create the curve. No options are available to the user to modify the curves. Therefore, the script generation is postponed to allow the third step.

The third step concerns the parametrization of the curves. This parametrization can be either fixed, user-defined or a mixture of both. In case of a fixed parametrization, specific parameters such as the longitudinal position of the curve are inserted to allow a systematic variation. For example, the parameter `X_Pos_Curve_number_1` in Fig. 16. Users do not have any influence on this parametrization, apart from manually adapting the script itself. Often, a more flexible approach is required, focussing on an interactive dialog with the user. After all curves are analysed, users can specify their own parameters and relations among control points inside the graphical user-interface provided by Rhinoceros, e.g. the parameter `L_bulb` in Fig.16. Unlike *Harries (1998)*, no capability yet exists to include differential and integral properties of the hull form in the parametrization. Sufficient information, e.g. the parametrization shown in Fig. 17, is now available for the fourth step,

Fig.16: Parametrization of the bow curve

```

CV_x    = [X_Pos_Curve_number_1,
           0.8, 7, 2 + L_bulb, 2, 5, 8]
CV_y    = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
CV_z    = [0, 0, 1, 5, 3.27, 7, 10]
weights = [1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1]
knots   = [0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 5, 5]
degree  = [3]

```

Fig.17: Parametrization of the curve in Fig.16

The fourth step concerns the conversion of the script into a Quaestor knowledgebase. This requires the assembly of a XML-file containing parameters, relations and the script. Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 respectively show the parameter `X_Pos_Curve_number_1` defined in both the XML-file and in the Quaestor

knowledge-base. By sticking to a similar curve definition and a proper naming convention, users can manually import the hull curves into an existing knowledge-base prior to making a calculation. There, they are readily used in existing prediction modules, e.g. stability and powering calculations.

```

- <parameterDef>
  <name>X_Pos_Curve_number_1</name>
  <type>num</type>
  <qclass>Top Goals/Undefined</qclass>
  <adr>4</adr>
  <dim>m</dim>
  <inp />
  - <ref>
    <reftext />
  </ref>
  - <data>
    <![CDATA[ @TOPID: 13]]>
  </data>
  <prop>INI 1.00, COL 9, FF 2, NN, USR,
    OUT, VALUE, CLASS: Top Goals/Undefined</prop>
</parameterDef>

```

Property	Value
(Contents)	X_Pos_Curve_number_1
(Data type)	Value
(Error)	No Relation to derive value or no
(Type)	Parameter
Cell color	
Cell width	9
Data	@TOPID: 13
Decimal places	2
Determined by	USR: User or System/equation
Dimension	m
Document	
Fixed KB value	
Format	FF: Fixed
Illustration	
Initial value	1.00
Maximum value	Undefined
Minimum value	Undefined
Output to	OUT: Report + Screen
Reference	
SmallZero	No
Value range	NN: Non negative

Fig.18: XML-definition of the parameter X_Pos_Curve_number_1

Fig.19: Definition of parameter X_Pos_Curve_number_1 in Quaestor

The approach allows the rapid generation of a library of knowledge bases containing user-defined, parametric hull curves. This, in turn, provides a far more flexible parametric hull form definition. Most importantly, during the definition and parametrization of the curves, the user has graphical feedback. In addition, the effort required to convert geometry into robust VBscripts reduces significantly. Summarised, the approach largely remedies the drawbacks of the script-based geometry generation. As a result, the user can now focus on the design and parametrization of geometry, instead of programming.

5 Generating knowledge-base parameters from inside Rhinoceros

5.1 Codifying object positions

The design model for the JLSS relied extensively on the use of parametric relations in Quaestor to define the internal arrangement, as described in Section 3.2. Two distinct approaches improve the ease of change for the internal arrangement, while still allowing the user full control over the changes. A third, optimisation-based, approach is presented in *Van Oers et al. (2007)*, which differs from the approaches below in that the user does not select the design change, but a range of allowed design changes.

The first approach seems rather similar to the one presented in Section 4. It tries to support defining and redefining the relations through an improved user-interface. The underlying approach remains similar to *Bons (2006)*, i.e. relations still define a large portion of the object positions. Still, changes to the relations are more easily implemented to make alterations more efficient, e.g. to achieve a space and weight balanced design.

The second approach discards a large portion of the relations. Instead, objects are defined by their position in an user-defined coordinate system. This is possible because any information that Quaestor retrieves from Rhinoceros, e.g. the center of gravity or hydrostatic data, depends solely on the object positions, not on relations used to determine those positions. Still, it can be useful to retrieve object positions to Quaestor in order to safeguard specific relations, e.g. those that define the propulsion system.

Two issues determine the suitability of either approach. First, changes to the internal arrangement take place while making a calculation with Quaestor. Therefore, any changes in object positions should be processed real-time. The level of control needed to create and alter relations in the Quaestor knowledge-base from Rhinoceros in real-time is under development, but not yet available. Second, codifying object positions uses, by definition, a fixed parametrization, i.e. the parameter values may change, but the parameters themselves do not. Retrieving object positions, i.e. the parameter values, from Rhinoceros is rather similar to retrieving any other object property and is easily implemented.

A two-tier approach is therefore taken. Relations are solely used to define hard, e.g. mechanical, connections. All other objects are defined by their positions in an user-defined coordinate system. Moreover, to provide visual feedback, Rhinoceros is selected as the software environment to make manual changes to the internal arrangement. The object positions stored in Quaestor are updated by retrieving them from Rhinoceros. The purpose of relations according to *Bons (2006)*: prevent overlap among objects and scaling the envelope to the correct dimensions, will be achieved manually by the user. The work flow of employing manual changes seems rather similar to *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*, with the important distinction that the user enjoys the benefits of the knowledge-based system (*Van Oers and Van Hees (2006)*).

The new approach allows the user to manually change the internal arrangement in Rhinoceros, while safeguarding important relations, e.g. mechanical connections. All geometry operations needed to process changes in object positions are handled by scripts in Rhinoceros executed from Quaestor, retaining the speed advantage. Furthermore, all calculations and data management are still performed by Quaestor.

5.2 Retrieving coordinates from Rhinoceros

Retrieving object coordinates and re-creating the objects at their new position requires a slightly different implementation than when providing input directly from Quaestor. After all, coordinates can now be treated either as *input* in Quaestor, or as *output* in Quaestor, i.e. retrieved from Rhinoceros. To achieve this, the implementation exploits the Quaestor's capability to select from multiple relations to calculate a requested parameter and to switch parameters between input and output during a calculation.

Two scripts are necessary, one that retrieves the coordinates and one that re-creates the object. When the user requests a property of an object, the inference engine assembles the scripts to create the object. Upon requesting the user to provide input for the object coordinates, two options are available. The user either provides the coordinates numerically or the user rejects the numerical input. With the latter, the user indicates that the coordinates should be calculated using one or more relations, i.e. retrieve them from Rhinoceros. To allow this, the old object should already be present in Rhinoceros and meet an user-defined naming convention. To retrieve the position, a second script is assembled. Even though the object has not been re-created in Rhinoceros, it already has a name provided by Quaestor. By selecting the old object by this name in Rhinoceros the object specific ID is retrieved. Using this ID, the script can retrieve the coordinates of the object. After retrieving the coordinates, the old object is deleted (a more efficient updating routine is proposed in Section 5.3). With coordinates known, the first script can now be completed and the object re-created at the new coordinates. Fig.20 shows the pseudo-code used for retrieving the object coordinates.

5.3 Reduction of computational effort

Previous implementations of Quaestor and Rhinoceros did not include versioning capability for geometry operations. As a result, changes in the scripts for Rhinoceros were propagated by regenerating the entire geometric model. This, in turn posed stringent demands on computational power and user patience.

Fortunately, version 4.0 of Rhinoceros allows users to attach user-defined data to objects. This enables the storage of the parameter values used to create an object. When the geometric model is updated, the parameter values of the previous calculation are compared to the current values. If the parameter values

1. Requested: center of gravity of object(q)
2. Provide position for object(q)

User selects from two relations to provide position

```
Relation 1 --> provide numerical input
object (q).x = 1
object (q).y = 25
object (q).z = 14
```

```
Relation 2 --> retrieve positions from Rhinoceros
Assemble script to retrieve positions
Execute script in Rhinoceros
Retrieve positions from output file
```

3. Use positions to assemble geometry script
4. Execute script in Rhinoceros to create and analyse geometry
5. Retrieve center of gravity of object(q) from output file

Fig.20: Pseudo-code for retrieving object positions from Rhinoceros

are unchanged, the previous version of an object can be retained, preventing computationally expensive geometry operations. As a result, the speed of propagation of design changes improves significantly.

6 Other improvements

6.1 Solid envelope definition

The JLSS design model employs the geometry definition presented in *Van Oers (2004)*, as discussed in Section 3.1. Two different approaches together define the envelope. The hull form is defined as an open poly-surface and scaled to dimensions. Fig.9 shows an example hull form. Instead, the superstructure was defined as a solid. The approach reduced robustness, as is discussed using two examples. The generation of bulkheads, decks and tanks crossing the boundary of the hull and superstructure was difficult. Furthermore, changes to the hull form took place outside Quaestor and Rhinoceros, preventing instant feedback on design changes. As a last consequence, large angle stability calculations would fail when the edge of the hull surface submerges.

A solid envelope definition resolves these problems, but introduces several new problems. Most importantly, the solid should remain a solid, which can be cumbersome when trying to construct or modify a solid from a large set of adjacent surfaces. Boolean operations, i.e. addition and subtraction operations of solids on other solids offer a robust solution, but require an initial solid to start with.

A sculpting-like approach is taken to create and modify the solid. Figs.21 to 32 illustrate the process. A set of parametric hull curves is created, shown in Fig.21, using the process described in Section 4. A hull surface is interpolated through the curves using Rhino's proprietary interpolation routine, shown in Fig.22. Two curves, one at the bow, one at the stern, provide the edges of the side shell, Fig.23. Again using one of Rhino's of interpolation commands the upper edge of the hull surface is swept upwards, creating the side shell (Fig.24). The two surfaces are mirrored, Fig.25 and closed Fig.26.

A closed, i.e. solid, envelope definition is now available. To create the required amount of detail, this solid is modified using Boolean subtraction, i.e. subtracting one solid from another and Boolean addition, i.e. merging two solids. Using Boolean subtraction the solid is sculpted to a more ship-like shape, shown in Fig.27 to Fig.29. Further detail is added, using Boolean difference in Fig.30 and Boolean addition in Fig.31 and Fig.32.

Key issue is that the process of closing the solid is robust, even if it comes at the expense of detail. After all, detail can be added later on using Boolean operations. Different options to close the envelope can be developed. For example, the approach shown in Figs.23 to 26 can be replaced by a simple closure of the hull surface by adding a flat deck defined by the upper edges of the hull surface.

6.2 Robust intersection routine

A severe drawback of the scripts used in the JLSS model was the lack of a robust routine for the generation of decks and bulkheads. The surfaces were generated by closing curves resulting from the intersection of a bulkhead parent surface with the hull surface. The implementation was unable to deal with, for example, bulkheads covering both hull and superstructure or bulkheads in multi-hulls.

Rhinoceros' scripting language offers the capability to split NURBS surfaces but the important issue: how to determine which of the resulting surfaces to keep, was unresolved. Fortunately, the shift to a solid based envelope, presented in Section 6.1, enabled the development of a robust intersection routine.

The new routine exploits the solid envelope definition by creating closed intersection curves at the longitudinal position of the bulkhead (Fig.33 and Fig.34). Next, the bulkhead surface itself is created and splitted by the solid envelope (Fig.35). For each of the resulting splitted surface, the boundary curve is retrieved and analysed (Fig.35). If any point on the boundary curve falls outside the closed intersection curves, the surface lies outside the envelope and is deleted (Fig.36). The surfaces remaining after the execution of the routine are all located inside the envelope, e.g. the light grey surface in Fig.36.

The new routine allows the robust generation of decks and bulkheads, even in unconventional hull forms such as multi-hulls and submarines.

Fig.21:

Fig.22:

Fig.23:

Fig.24:

Fig.25:

Fig.26:

Fig.27:

Fig.28:

Fig.29:

Fig.30:

Fig.31:

Fig.32:

Fig.33:

Fig.34:

Fig.35:

Fig.36:

7 Conclusions & Future research

7.1 Conclusions

The following improvements are presented based on the lessons drawn from the first major application of the knowledge-based CAD system presented in *Van Oers and Van Hees (2006)*.

- Improvements related to the generation of relations inside the Quaestor knowledgebase:
 - The design and parametrization of geometry with a changing parametrization, i.e. the hull, can now take place with graphical feedback.
 - The effort required to generate scripts for geometry with a changing parametrization was reduced significantly through the use of automated script generation.
- Improvements related to the generation of parameter values inside the Quaestor knowledgebase:
 - An approach was developed to retrieve object positions from Rhinoceros during a Quaestor calculation. This allows a large reduction of the number of relations used to define internal arrangements. As a result, users can now manually change the arrangement in a visual environment. This replaces the old approach which defined the entire design alpha-numerically in the Quaestor knowledgebase.

- Improvements to the robustness of the geometry definition:
 - The mixed surface / solid-envelope definition was replaced by a more robust solid definition. The new definition is better suited for intact and damaged stability prediction and the evaluation of signatures. Furthermore, the development of generic scripts for geometry definition was also assisted by the solid envelope definition.
 - The scripts used to create geometry with a fixed parametrization were updated to a more generic level, improving their re-usability.

7.2 Future research

Two improvements are proposed to further enhance the capability of the knowledge-based CAD-system presented in this paper.

- A further improvement would be the real-time parametrization of geometry in Quaestor from Rhinoceros. Efforts to develop this capability are underway, but as realising this requires advanced external control of Quaestor, it will take quite some time to develop.
- The ability to retrieve object positions from Quaestor allows the knowledge-based CAD system to be used as a post-processing tool for optimisation applications. For instance, the output from the space allocation approach presented in *Van Oers et al. (2007)* can be imported into an existing knowledgebase enabling further detailing. The integral design approach thus remains ensured, but the magnitude of changes reduces and becomes more oriented towards the fine-tuning of a concept. In the latter case the experience of a designer to decide upon specific design changes is handled better in the knowledge-based CAD system presented in this paper.
- The improvements proposed in this paper will be employed in a design model for small submarines. The development of the model is carried out through an MSc. project in industry.

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Integrated Project Execution and its Influence on an Engineering Portal Solution

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Abstract

The paper explains AVEVA's understanding of Integrated Project Execution (= IPE) as a strategy for different yard departments, design agents, classification societies, suppliers, engineering contractors, and owners to provide them with a sustainable approach for a successful usage of the core of their business – information. After an overview about the different IT integration solutions built in the past and present (EDM, Engineering databases, PDM, Data Warehouse Solutions) the paper describes the main features of the VNET engineering portal as one of the two central modules in the AVEVA's IPE strategy, finishing with an outlook on AVEVA's PLM strategy for the shipbuilding industry.

1. Introduction

Within the commercial and naval shipbuilding sectors, there is a strong need for integrated solutions which address the same spectrum of functional requirements as conventional PLM (= Product Lifecycle Management), including; data and document storage, workflow and process management, product structure management, application and data integration, and visualisation / collaboration. However, in practice, there are only very few shipbuilders using conventional PLM solutions to address their lifecycle information management needs. This failure to penetrate the shipbuilding marketplace has arisen because the industry has a number of defining characteristics which differentiate it from discrete / repetitive manufacturing. These characteristics dominate the business processes and associated product data management requirements of shipbuilding organisations and ensure that conventional PLM software acquisition and deployment is either an unsuitable or sub-optimal lifecycle management solution.

IT solutions designed as part of a PLM strategy are mostly and primarily focused on integration. Hence organisations in the capital project market designing a PLM strategy should firstly develop an over-all strategy for an Integrated Project Execution (= IPE). Thus an integration solution will be an essential component and a foundation for each IPE strategy. For a better understanding of the keyword 'information' in the context of PLM it is very useful to take a closer look at the PLM definition as published by CIMdata, the independent strategic consultancy in the PLM business area. CIMdata defines PLM as:

“A strategic business approach that applies a consistent set of business solutions in support of the collaborative creation, management, dissemination, and use of product definition information across the extended enterprise from concept to end of life—integrating people, processes, business systems, and information.”

2. Integrated Project Execution: the initial situation

2.1 The Project Culture

If we want to find a better way of using project related information and capitalising its value, then we need to understand what the existing limits and constraints are. Especially the project culture is a major constraint that has to be understood in the context of information. So we have a closer look at typical characteristics of the most currently project execution environment:

- Formal project control (quality, schedule, engineering coordination) is achieved through a document paradigm. Most project organisations have dedicated document control groups to manage the approval, issue and "flow" of documents as part of the project work processes.
- Most engineering applications are task-oriented at discipline or at best at departmental level with

ad-hoc data integration based on manually driven data transfer routines. Many applications have the same duplicated data (for example tag id) with more or less inconsistencies.

- Beneath the formal document issues there are many file issues and database issues of similar computer-interpretable data, which is not fully controlled and thus provides the basis for data anarchy, competing with official document issues. Although documents are, in the majority, generated from engineering databases, there is no linkage or connection back to the database once the document has been produced.
- Most of the engineering applications are designed to work in a single LAN environment, which makes sharing work over a WAN or the internet in any sort of workflow process difficult to achieve and requiring a lot of manual intervention.

By their definition projects are short-lived independent activities. This plays against more productive and project-independent use of information. Better use of information means re-use between projects, continual learning and cross-project investment in information. But projects are focused on solving problems immediately and moving on for reaching their goals. Projects have to avoid risks and have to work within fixed boundaries wherever possible. So project culture creates innovation only in localised information systems, but in fact one single project team is not directly interested in their knowledge and innovation being captured by the corporate organisation.

Fig.1: Knowledge leaks in the middle of project and corporate organisation

Projects are executed using different discipline groups. Although they are coordinated through various methods, they are mainly measured and resourced in isolation on how they produce their deliverables, not by the way in which those deliverables can add value to other down-stream processes. The ideal example is the intelligent P&ID. Whilst it does not add great value to the process of creating a P&ID, downstream the fact that this information can be exploited is of great value to the project team.

It is in this environment that project managers have to execute complex, global projects, and consequently plan improvements within these constraints.

2.2 The Life Cycle in Context of Information

In developing an integration strategy, the first thing that must be acknowledged is that there is not a single generic approach that can be applied through a single information management solution. Only too often, we try to solve a very complex problem area with solutions like a “lifecycle information management system” as if this could be provided through a single information system. When we look closer, we will see that although the engineering processes can be described as a continuum, the way in which information is used varies according to the project phase and to the view of the project collaborator; be it the shipyard, the classification society, any supplier, or an engineering contractor.

The information management characteristics change over the life cycle of a shipbuilding project. The life cycle can be divided into several main phases:

- Contract Design
- Basic Design
- Detailed Design
- Parts Manufacturing

- Assembly (Hull and Outfitting)

Let us have first a look at the characteristics of the main project phases in fact from the point of information view.

2.2.1 Contract & Basic Design

Contract & Basic Design is characterised by low volumes of information. Many options may be checked and verified and information associated with non-feasible options will be discarded. In this phase data inconsistency is quite usual while different options are investigated, and the consistency or integrity of the data is primarily required to support bid packages, not procurement. Hence the requirements on change control and quality control is less than in other life cycle phases. There is, however, a wish to re-use captured knowledge through repeated designs and/or standardisation of design through modular concepts. This re-use of knowledge supports optimised cost (80% of the project cost is committed at this point) and accelerated Contract & Basic Design schedules.

The handover of information from Contract / Basic Design to Detail Design is very often through documents that have been unlinked from the application systems that created them. Potentially intelligent schematics and 3D models (Basic Design) may be available but there is no standard industry practice for handling this.

2.2.2 Detail Design

Detail Design is characterised by concurrent engineering, this means a split of work over different departments, business units and locations and a quick increase of information volume. The focus here is on risk management and high information integrity to support the processes for procurement and fabrication. The project is likely to be distributed and involve several contractors with different interface management issues. Particularly change management; workflow and error-free engineering are the key drivers for any information system in this phase.

3 The IT Integration Solutions in the Past and in the Present

Even if our view should go into direction information and not only into information systems, we should have a closer look how different IT approaches handle the integration issue and the smarter use of information. That is not to say that there is a right or wrong way with regard to the selection of IT approach, but we need to understand how the different systems work solving the integration task and the best way to fit them together.

Many attempts have been made to provide integrated systems, but these haven't usually reached the original goals for a number of reasons. Key reasons have been:

- thinking it is primarily a computer application problem, rather than a business process problem, thereby focusing on the software and the IT system and not on the information.
- thinking that information management solutions are generic across the life cycle and between work processes.
- trying to reach a complete integration, rather than partial integration, even though solving 20% of the integration problem will most likely yield 80% of the benefits.
- not acknowledging the benefits that can be accrued from better use of information by its consumers rather than the creators.

These attempts have followed several approaches.

3.1 Electronic Document Management (EDM)

A collaborative workflow environment, based on electronic versions of the documents and files: Electronic Document Management (EDM). Essentially EDM automates an existing process of managing workflow through document issues and flows. EDM has brought about some benefits, but has not reached the productivity and business gains expected of the technology. Why is this? Again comparison with another industry can help us understand the limitations of EDM.

Fig.2: Applications transfer their outputs into an EDM system

If we look at the insurance industry, there are huge volumes of information of simple structure, usually created using word processing documents, with well-defined and repeatable workflows. EDM has made a lot of difference here. Engineering however consists of complex data relationships, semi-defined and changing workflows, but more importantly the information sources that hold the master data are NOT documents, but databases or other applications like 2D CAD systems. The documents are typical reports from the databases or plot from the CAD system. Therefore the concept of checking in the master document and then "checking it out" to work on is a false concept in the world of 3D and engineering databases. Version and workflow control need to be built around the originated application, not around the reports that come from that application. Hence EDM can replicate and add value to the role of the document control department, but not to a world of more granular information sets with which the project team needs to work with.

3.2 Best in breed approach

Best in breed point solutions provide deliverables (documents and drawings) from their database, with point-to-point batch integration based on predefined file formats. Most shipyards and engineering companies use this type of useful but limited integration.

Fig.3: The best in breed approach combines point to point integration with EDM

This approach improves quality and productivity within a single discipline or department. The risk, as we all know is that the result is lots of “islands of information” that struggle to communicate effectively. For a simple business model this type of solution can be very suitable. For engineering with its complex interdependencies this causes problems.

- Firstly the shared data within the islands are duplicated, either by manual re-keying or by point-to-point file transfer. This in itself is not a huge problem, but the issue of managing the data transfer is.
- Version control, quality of data and context of data become big problems, and these tend to be managed manually.
- Very seldom are these information exchanges submitted to formal workflows, because the formal workflow procedures are all document-centric and these exchanges are not controlled documents but data extracts. So there exists a formal way of moving data around the organisation (documents) and a semi-formal way (file based information exchange between applications).

The end results are inconsistencies and duplicates resulting in “data anarchy” if not well managed through manual procedures. Knowing that the intelligent information is locked up in the application architecture and code and only insiders as applications specialists can really exploit it, we recognize that we have very often a two-tier project organisation: those that have access to the document level and those that rely on the databases. How often this situation generates questions like “Which is the valid data set for this object?” or “Can I trust this data?”

3.3 Integrated Engineering Databases

A more comprehensive integrated engineering database, around which sets of logically linked applications are built (such as a 3D modelling system, a material management system, a work preparation and production system) solves some of the problems of the above mentioned point-to-point solution. Based around a single central database data duplication is eliminated; version control and release of granular information sets is improved and it is ensured that documents produced as reports are consistent with the database across the discipline boundaries. What we don’t achieve, of course, is as much flexibility of disciplines/departments to choose their application of choice; this is dismissed against the benefits of integration.

Fig.4: Integrated Engineering Database with all modules in a consolidated environment

One common reason for not adopting this type of approach is the scepticism that a central engineering database will be too unmanageable, slow, unresponsive, and will not be able to support project teams at distributed locations – the arguments against the “mother of all database”. In the 1990s, when many engineering companies tried to build these systems themselves, this may have had an element of truth

about it, but not in the 21st century where distributed database architecture is commonplace and web enablement allows global teams to use this approach effectively. Nowadays the main reason for not following this approach of integration and rationalising many discipline applications lies in the business culture of the corporate organisations and the liking for choice at discipline level, rather than organisational level.

The best example of an integrated engineering database system is the data-centric 3D system, Tribon M3 and its follower Vantage Marine. This represents a large, single, central database, with version control at the object level and between objects and drawings. It also has the ability to distribute the database globally and manage change between distributed teams.

Of course, although this approach is very powerful there is still a lot of information outside of these applications that needs further integration. Furthermore the applications usually require specialist support and training and, as for the best of breed approach, it is not easy for other information consumers to exploit it.

3.4 Product Data Management (PDM)

For many years those involved in engineering IT in the shipbuilding industry have looked with interest and sometimes envy at the PDM approach which has proved quite successful in the discrete manufacturing industry as a means to manage product information. PDM combines the document/file management approach of EDM and overlays it with configuration management. What does this mean? Product configuration is based on the actual component objects in the product, analogous to the objects building a ship, and these are set in a hierarchical tree with parent/child associations modelled along with attached documents/model files that represent the engineering definition of these components. Of course, version control is handled to the extreme so that as the configuration of the product evolves with time, either through new component design or ability to create different products from sub assemblies, the configuration is maintained.

The problem with applying this to the shipbuilding industry is that the investment that has to be made in building and maintaining the ship object/information configurations is large and ships are very much “one off configurations”, rather than evolving product structures. Furthermore, it doesn’t really solve the integration issues and data duplication between applications. This type of system is much more suited to industry sectors where design reuse around standard assemblies is important.

Fig.5: Data Warehouse concept combines central database with best in breed approach

3.5 Data Warehouses

More recently strategies have included the concept of a central engineering data model for shared data with “plug and play” applications that can publish and subscribe data to and from this central model. This looks very similar to the central engineering database concept, but concentrates on only holding the shared data and enabling discipline applications to “talk” to the shared database via publish and subscribe methods. Especially in the field of versioning this concept shares some basic ideas with PDM: it is necessary to hold a versioned object map of the ship objects and their associations, around which data (and sometimes documents) can be organised.

This is a sound concept, but one that must complement the three other approaches, not compete with them. The danger is that this concept can lead to the shared data model being seen as the master owner of the data. When this happens, the pressure builds for it to take on functionality that is also duplicated in the application that originally published the data.

The other major problem using this approach is that very often the applications to be “plugged and played” do not have proper application protocol interfaces (= API’s), version control or change management. This requires a lot of work to be done in the interface or adaptor application. On top of this, of course, is the fact that each application has a different data model and different levels of data granularity, all of which must be mapped into and out of the shared database.

On top of this is the need to maintain the adaptors and mapping at a very detailed level to manage all the flexibility needed in workflow and information changes through the life cycle. This is potentially different for every application and adaptor maintenance is required each time when applications are further developed.

Very often this concept is realised as a proprietary, central-engineering database around a defined set of applications. When both database and applications are developed by the same vendor, most of the above mentioned problems (different data model, API) are eliminated or reduced. But in this case the efforts are enormous for adapting applications from other s/w vendors. It also mirrors or replaces a lot of functionality currently existing in the applications themselves, and should be categorised as a central engineering database approach.

3.6 Federated Systems that utilise web-centric technologies and standards for information classification and workflow

The latest developments comprise a federated approach that combines elements of all the above approaches in a single coherent strategy that can evolve from a work process based on “dumb” documents to a workflow based on intelligent data templates. This approach uses a single-shared, distributed engineering model, which can be used as a hub to share intelligent granular data between applications in a controlled fashion.

The evolutionary approach is essential to get increasing advantage right from the start through integrating disparate applications, without an unsustainable development and support overhead. The strategy must maintain pace with, and rigorously adopt the development of standards for the exchange of information within the shipbuilding industry.

Organisations also need to be aware that the applications that they currently use, by virtue of a lack of data management and version control of their data, are uncontrolled and cannot work effectively in a “plug and play” publish and subscribe paradigm.

What might be most important is that the projects must benefit without undue risk, and this means finding an evolutionary way in which to grow into the information age.

Fig.6: Integration approach based on web technology and XML templates

4. AVEVA's understanding of Integrated Project Execution (= IPE)

4.1 Evolution – not revolution

Any IPE solution must be able to evolve from the current business model and application portfolio. This is needed so that project risk can be managed. For an evolutionary strategy to work there must be a clear vision and goals for the IPE solution, and implementation must be proactively managed. Without this there will be a tendency to drift, progress will be slower, and direction will trend to the course of least resistance, or status quo. It's a realistic assumption that 80% of the benefit can be gained from the core 20% of an IPE solution. This core must be identified early and a plan put in place for its implementation.

4.2 Design Principles

To create an IPE strategy the following principles need to be adhered to.

Firstly IPE is about information, not software applications. This is of crucial importance. Much work has been done to develop flow charts of how applications link together and what data needs to be exchanged between applications. However this is a very application-driven approach and perpetuates the division between information sets by the applications that own or use the data. This is stark contrast to the procedures and processes built around documents that reflect how information flows around the organisation. Documents are simply content, and it is right to look at how content flows. However the emphasis needs to move from documents to more granular intelligent information sets (information objects or information templates) that can be derived from, and linked to the data creation applications.

Secondly, the purpose of applications needs to be understood. There are three types of applications:

- **“Doing” applications**, such as 3D CAD, schematics and engineering databases. These applications are really about the ongoing creation and revision of data as the design develops. Doing applications are very often stand-alone and have some degree of version and revision control, change management, and can produce information sets (generally drawings, data sheets

and reports as deliverables). Usually these applications are well tailored to those that use them to create and maintain data, but are not easy to use for those people who simply want to access and use the information.

- “Informing” applications, such as engineering data warehouses, portals, document management systems and other shared engineering solutions. These are about taking information content in many forms (drawings, indexes, information sets) and making that information available in a structured way that is easy to access normally across an enterprise. Informing applications enable decision-making. As such they can also be thought of as decision-support applications.
- “Integrating” application, where workflow is controlled to move versioned information sets between “doing” applications. Very often this is seen as an extension to an informing application like on engineering database or indeed an engineering data warehouse approach. It is this new area that overlaps both doing and informing processes and where most confusion exists for those planning an IPE strategy. The danger is that doing, informing and integrating can all become the task of some new, central data management application that is going to solve the complete integration problem. This is the “holy grail” approach that has been shown many times to be either a step too far, or a reincarnation of existing systems with all the associated problems of proprietary data models.

4.3 Selecting s/w components for an IPE strategy

An IPE strategy has three main streams of doing applications:

- Engineering – an integrated application suite covering the engineering disciplines.
The core components of the engineering system are the tag registers. Once they are in place they nominate the main “engineering objects” around which information sets can be organised. These tag registers must all be managed consistently. A stated ideal approach is to have single entry of tags from a master application and then have these distributed to other applications in a controlled manner. However in practice this is very difficult and there is no single prescribed workflow that can be applied to this process.
And last but not least, the deliverable documents and drawings such as schematics and datasheets and indexes that come from the engineering databases must be consistent with the data within the databases, and so must be version controlled and change managed as part of the process.
- 3D Design – The use of 3D design tools to create a representative model of the ship from which construction deliverables such as drawings and lists for production and assembly are produced is now commonplace. 3D models have been shown to provide many benefits such as:
 - reducing errors and rework in construction
 - improved efficiency and speed of design
 - improved material take off and material control.Finally, the deliverables from the 3D model must be managed as part of the 3D database system to maintain consistency. There should be change management between the deliverables and the 3D model.
- Project management, material control, and work preparation. At the project managers level the key to project success is twofold:
 - knowing where you are in the project,
 - controlling the supply of resources (documents, drawings and materials)

All these doing applications must work together and are linked through an integration application that forms the backbone for collaboration and extends the integration to other enterprise and third party applications.

Layered over these applications is an informing application, which can be deployed in various levels depending on the detail workflows. This application essentially creates a single view of the information contained in many other systems, and it can be said to create a “federated data warehouse”, with the information presented in a neutral format and accessed and used through an intuitive user interface.

4.4 Integration

Getting the integration strategy right is the cornerstone of a successful IPE strategy. This strategy must fit alongside the doing application strategy. For example, if the business need is for a very granular approach to discipline applications (i.e. very many applications) this will influence the selection of the integration technology and investment profile in a different manner to a strategy in which there is a more rationalised approach to the doing applications, where they handle a lot of integration and version control within themselves.

Integration should be approached in an evolutionary manner. There is no software solution to realise integration “out-of-the-box”! Certainly integration platforms and technology strategies need to be chosen carefully if they are to sustain a viable integration strategy, but the main work is in understanding the work processes and mapping the information flows.

4.5 Information access and decision support

The central repetitive goal in each project execution is: The right information! The right time! The right place! When deciding on this important keystone of an IPE strategy the following should be taken into account:

- Access should be through a web-based portal, and the information served to the portal should be in the form of application neutral XML templates and documents.
- The navigation engine should be built around an object-management concept that holds all the engineering object definitions, associations to other objects, information sources, and key metadata.
- The portal must deliver a consistent set of quality information that encompasses documents, drawings, 2D and 3D models and engineering data templates derived from the doing engineering databases, such as equipment specifications, line lists etc.
- The portal solution must encompass storage and version control; either internally or through a link to a document management system where object data as well as documents can be held and versioned.

Thus the core requirements for the informing application are the same as for the integrating application.

A good example of a decision support application would be one that queried the material database to find out the status of material in fabrication and then displayed in the 3D model the shortages against the proposed construction schedule. This type of application would work with any material status system, any planning system and any 3D model, without having to be modified. This is because all of the data is classified according to the engineering information model, rather than the proprietary internal model of the applications that originally created the data.

5. The Engineering Portal VNET as a typical informing application

Recapitulating the last sections of this paper the implementation of an integration solution as a central component of an IPE strategy should consider the following issues:

- Mainly, the implementation should be done in an evolutionary way. This ensures a faster ROI – preconceiving that solving 20% of the complete problem will reach most likely over 2/3 of the benefits.
- Already providing a shared information portal will bring more transparency into the project execution and as a result this will increase quality of data, documents and deliverables.
- The core requirements for informing and for integrating applications are the same. Hence implementing an engineering information portal is the first step into an overall integrating application.

Considering all these issues AVEVA has developed their Engineering Information Portal VNET

(= Vantage Enterprise NET) as a typical informing application. This solution as a central component of an IPE strategy will be introduced and explained in the next sections.

5.1 Introduction to VNET

AVEVA's Engineering Portal VNET is an engineering information management platform which answers the question 'how can delivered information across the project life cycle all over the distributed project team?' Its implementation delivers control, context, integration and presentation of all ship related data in any form, at any stage of the ship's lifetime. Based on XML and the industry standard ISO15926, VNET provides a flexible solution for informing as well as integrating. It brings disparate applications together, integrates their information in terms of datasets and documents and provides web-based viewing, collaboration and markup using 2D schematics and 3D models for information and navigation.

So, VNET will be of interest to all members of a project team: the design office in the shipyard as well as any engineering contractor who wants to improve their ability to share information and collaborate more effectively across globally distributed project teams.

5.2 Capture and Delivery of Information

As its main task VNET comprises a unique middleware platform enabling many sources of data to be integrated together and then delivering this information through an portal.

Information is published to an Engineering Information Model as XML templates and associated files or documents. This is conform to the industry standard ISO15926 data model and reference data library, providing a single extensible data model for all engineering and document objects and all technical data.

The extensibility enables an evolutionary implementation (see below). Firstly, it is not necessary to design a fully complete data model before starting with the implementation. Far from it! VNET is able to increase the data model along the project execution according to the evolutionary completion of project engineering data.

Fig.7: VNET captures information from disparate sources and delivers it in an integrated way

Gateways are used to bridge between the information sources and VNET. A gateway may publish on demand, in batch or when triggered by events in the information source. In this manner, VNET presents a 'published, revised and approved' information view from its Engineering Information Model. For a number of popular commercial applications gateways can be provided.

An essential functionality of the CAD gateways is converting 2D and 3D CAD models in a neutral format and converting the specific object model coming from the CAD system into VNET's

application independent Engineering Information Model:

- 2D documents will be converted into SVG format. Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG) is a text-based graphics language that describes images with vector shapes, text, and embedded raster graphics. SVG files are compact and provide high-quality graphics on the Web. In addition, SVG supports scripting and animation, so is ideal for interactive, data-driven, personalized graphics. SVG is a royalty-free vendor-neutral open standard developed under the W3C (World Wide Web Consortium) Process so the related viewers are available as freeware.
- 3D models will be converted into ZGL format. ZGL is the zipped version of XGL format. This format is designed to represent 3D information for the purpose of visualization. It uses XML 1.0 syntax, so it is easy to write and can be parsed by standard, freely available code. These features make XGL the ideal format to use when data must be exchanged between two graphics systems for the purposes of visualization.

This conversion ensures that 2D documents and 3D models can be used as navigation vehicles with hotspots, hyperlinks as well as being information in themselves.

Other file formats like XLS, DOC, and PDF will not be converted in any neutral format but presented in their original format.

5.3 VNET Use Cases

The use cases for VNET which can be deployed provide but are not limited to:

- an engineering portal for enhanced decision support. Even in today's highly computerised world, getting fast, consistent, quality information delivered to users desktop in a useful form can still present a considerable problem. VNET provides an intuitive and automated solution to organise, gather and access documents, engineering data, vendor data, and 2D and 3D models from any information source. Information and tasks such as status and consistency checking are automatically correlated and displayed in the context of 2D and 3D graphical views
- a collaboration environment where the same information can be assembled into packages and submitted to a workflow for review, comment and action
- a project handover solution where all project data from any project partner is brought together to create a 'digital ship'. This solves completion and handover problems by assembling and relating information
- an application integration solution into which data is published from existing applications as XML templates to be managed and shared with other engineering applications

5.4 Evolutionary Implementation

As datasheets, documents, schedules and many other types of engineering information may be added to its Engineering Information Model on an ongoing basis, VNET offers both immediate and growing value. Aware this the implementation can be done in an evolutionary fashion: starting with simple document types as 2D schematics, adding step by step more complex documents the digital ship model will grow more and more up to the final and complete engineering information model.

Due to its characteristic as a not invasive product VNET can be implemented in a risk-free fashion: the 'doing applications' and its workflows and processes are not 'disturbed', but an added value will be given to the Information Portal from the very first beginning.

5.5 Navigation and Search in VNET

The VNET User Interface based on the Microsoft Internet Explorer is divided into 3 main sections:

- the Enterprise Explorer (see left)
- the Content Explorer (see left)
- and the Content Viewer for visualisation of any document content

The Enterprise Explorer provides several hierarchical structures, e.g. for

- assets (blocks, equipments, pipes, ventilation ducts, ...)
- functional facilities (Hull blocks, Outfitting Modules)
- document types (3D models, arrangement drawings, datasets, Isometrics, P&I diagrams, purchase orders)
- document folders – comparable to folders on mapped network drives.

For understanding the VNET functionality it is very important to know that these structures are fully flexible configurable and the kind of structures and quantity of parallel built structures are not limited to any presettings.

After selecting a node in the Enterprise Explorer the corresponding object information and the associated document types will be displayed in the Content Explorer. Expanding the document type icon shows all associated documents. Each document node is hyperlinked for opening its content in the Content Viewer.

As all objects linked together as in a network VNET provides several methods for finding the right information. In addition to the above mentioned navigation along predefined breakdown structures a flexible search feature is available: simplest you can use it similar to the Google search engine – just type in the search string, VNET will deliver a list of search results independent of object types. In this case the search result list is as long as in Google, this is only useful for a very first search. Normally you will detail the search string e.g. with an object class like ‘pump’, ‘arrangement drawing’, ‘purchase order’, ‘status’ etc. The elements in the search result list are hyperlinked as in the breakdown structure for further navigation through the engineering information model.

On the one hand linking all engineering related information VNET provides a 360° view for each object but on the other hand you can avoid an information overflow for information consumers by defining role specific views with limited breakdown structures.

Fig.8: VNET GUI
- Enterprise and
Content Explorer

Fig.9: Three clicks from asset to 3D model

Example 1: A very simple navigation starts in the asset breakdown structure and opens the corresponding 3D model in the content explorer, see Fig.9.

Example 2: Starting within the document (e.g. a schematic diagram) or 3D model enables further navigation to other associated documents, see Fig.10 (from 3D model to equipment ‘TTP-XX9005’ in the content explorer) and Fig.11 (shows the arrangement drawing associated to the equipment ‘TTP-XX9005’).

Fig.10: Two clicks from 3D model via Content Explorer to Arrangement Drawing (next fig.)

Fig.11: Outfitting Arrangement drawing in SVG format – with hotspots for further navigation

Example 3: Isometrics are typical associated documents for pipe pieces. All associated documents are shown in the content explorer, e.g. ‘3D models’, ‘Arrangement drawings’, ‘Datasets’ → see Fig.12.

Fig.12: Isometric Drawing as one associated document for a pipe piece (SVG format)

6. Outlook on AVEVA’s PLM strategy

AVEVA always has been working closely together with the thought leaders in its industry. PLM widely is seen as the next big step in the shipbuilding industry and although it has been driven and already adopted by Automotive, Aerospace and consumer goods industries, the specific requirements from the shipbuilding customers make it more complex to offer a solution. This becomes very clear when focussing on the differences between the users of classical PLM solutions and our target industries shipbuilding and plant design and operation.

The “Capital Project” focus means that one ship is planned and then built. Each ship is a project of its own and has a separate profit/loss measurement. Sisterships are similar to a great extent but details will be different. Compare this to car manufacturing: All cars of the series are basically the same, there are configuration capabilities but they are limited to certain components. Consequently a main focus of PLM in shipbuilding is project management and using best in class solutions linked together very closely.

Concurrent design and production is another fundamental difference. The ship is already being built while detailed design still is ongoing. In discrete manufacturing these two phases are clearly sequential and there is also the concept of prototyping. Because of the parallel process it is of

fundamental importance that everyone knows the status and quality of information that is accessed at any time during the project. Wrong information and decisions made on that basis can make a difference between profit and loss. Given this, a PLM solution for shipbuilding needs to be tightly integrated with the 3D design tools and all flow of information has to be controlled very carefully, not only between departments but also across organisational boundaries.

The third big difference is the Lifecycle itself. In the discrete manufacturing the data captured through the design and manufacturing process is used to support post production activities such as spare parts inventory and defects tracking. Normally there is no requirement to track the lifecycle of a specific product instance.

In Shipbuilding not only the products lifecycle spans several decades but also during its life it is likely to undergo several modifications. Each of them is a one-off project on its own and the PLM solutions need to support these activities which will involve many different partners and, of course, special tools which might differ from the original toolset.

Building on top of the actual products like Vantage Marine and VNET AVEVA's PLM strategy will allow the customers to gradually step up to a fully integrated PLM solution at their own pace. Rather than enforcing a 'big bang' implementation the phased implementation will allow the customers to gain maximum benefit from each step they take.

As seen before, VNET and its rapid implementation can already make a huge difference to today's work processes just by making information available in a consolidated, controlled way.

On the other hand the VNET architecture will be the basis for future extensions to cover the different areas of PLM. It already allows capturing data through application specific gateways and presenting this information in a unified way to the users. Yet PLM is more and the following areas need to be covered:

- Secure data and documents Storage
- Data and document management
- Workflow and process management
- Product and configuration management
- Application and data integration
- Visualisation and collaboration
- Project management and control

Fig.13: Business Objects in the PLM context

The above functional areas apply to PLM in all industries. However in shipbuilding there are some very important additional requirements such as coding management, structure management and also change management. AVEVA currently has already applications that cover this functionality but while these applications have a rich feature set within their domain, they are not necessarily linked together and integrated in a way to support the concept of PLM in the best effective way. The experience of having built these applications and the deep knowledge about the business needs and the connected processes allow AVEVA to leverage what already exists and build a solution that will be superior to those offered by the traditional PLM vendors. One of the main concepts for the AVEVA PLM solution is an application agnostic object model and its repository derived from the experience with VNET.

Through a very flexible object and association model the AVEVA approach supports

- any required object data structures
- a variety of product and functional breakdown structures
 - e.g. design, assembly, production etc.
- multiple projects
- multiple organisational breakdowns and responsibilities
- customised access rights and permissions
- user-defined workflow processes and procedures

In addition all objects and associations can be “interrogated” to find / produce reports such as:

- parts lists and BOM’s for any given structure or part of a structure
- list of all instances of where a component is used
- document item lists
- item document lists
- status reports
- change effect analysis
- item quantity lists

This is the basis for a content management, change management, workflow management and BOM Management (Bill of Material) as all these are linked very closely together.

The gateway concept developed for VNET and the complete openness secures investment of the customers at any time.

Given the complexities of the shipbuilding process and the unique lifecycle information management characteristics outlined above, selecting a solution with a dedicated industry focus and corresponding track record is essential. AVEVA’s PLM solution is the only commercial of the shelf (COTS) software solution which has been specifically designed to address the PLM requirements of the shipbuilding industry. Building on the experiences and insight AVEVA has gained as the world’s number one supplier of shipbuilding software solutions, AVEVA’s PLM solution has been developed with two key design objectives in mind:

- to provide an information management infrastructure through which the various organisations involved in shipbuilding projects can optimise their project execution capabilities, thereby allowing them to deliver higher quality products and to do so faster and more cost effectively.
- to reduce the lifetime cost-of-ownership of marine assets by providing a persistent, application-neutral foundation for information integration, evolution and re-use, that supports all phases of the product lifecycle

While not all of the above described functionality is available in the current product set, a constant development and focus on PLM will ensure that the requirements of the market will be matched and a complete, extensible solution will be available within the next months. Implementing VNET and Vantage Marine is the first step of embracing the PLM concept for shipbuilding.

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Site Neutral Design for Site Specific manufacturing in Shipyard Groups

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Abstract

Shipbuilding companies having several shipyards are more and more facing the business situation that, to meet the delivery date and use the available capacities in the most efficient way, the design for a ship is made at one yard whereas the manufacturing has to be carried out at several yards. Because of specific production facilities, different working processes and historical reasons, each shipyard has typically their own standards for design and manufacturing, meaning that an existing design will have to be redesigned when manufacturing is to take place at another site. For obvious reasons, design departments are today often optimized to serve their local production sites. This paper tries to analyze the design work in terms of what can be site independent (standard) and what has to be site dependent, related to manufacturing and processes. An important question is how far a design can be developed before it is affected by the conditions of the manufacturing location and its facilities (block size, panel lengths, welding methods, cutting and assembly equipment etc). To elaborate on the answer to that question it is necessary to make a clear distinction between details and standards for the design itself on one hand and information for parts manufacturing and assembly on the other. Concurrent work on one design and several production models also requires appropriate data management functionality to handle controlled access to both data and system functions. Additionally, functions for synchronization of the design and the connected production models are necessary to ensure consistency at any given moment.

1. Introduction

In the shipbuilding industry there are more and more shipyard groups, where the design is done at one yard, but by designers from different yards and the production of whole ships or blocks of ships is done at different places. Today the original project data are copied to the production site and then more or less reengineered to fit the site-specific production needs. This reengineering typically takes more time than estimated. One of the reasons is, that inside several shipyard groups are no clear defined scenarios and workflows for this kind of distributed production. The capacities of design and production inside the group should be used as good as possible. So there are several requests to reduce the reengineering work as much as possible for these business cases.

2. Typical Scenarios

Inside a ship yard group can be different scenarios of how work is spread among the different yards. E.g. there can be a standard design for a 3000 TEU container ship, where complete ships should be built at each shipyard (scenario 1). Another scenario can be that a ship is designed and built at one shipyard but parts of this ship need to be built at another shipyard (scenario 2) for capacity or time reasons. The decision can be from the beginning to work like scenario 1 or 2, but it is also possible that the decision comes late especially for scenario 2, that some blocks need to be produced at another site inside the group. Also a scenario of a combination of situation 1 and 2 can be realistic. Both shipyards deliver complete ships, but e.g. one shipyard is also delivering some blocks to another shipyard for the same master ship, but also for different ones. Designer may work for the shipyard where they are sitting, but also via Internet on the model of another shipyard. Both, design and production capacities, need to be shared inside a shipyard group.

2.1 Scenario 1, production of complete sisterships is done at yard A and B

In this scenario designers from shipyard A and B are working together on the master ship AV3000, depending on capacity. Each shipyard will have its own sistership, which is derived and synchronized with the master ship. The difference in the 2 sisters is the production related data and information that

need to fit the different production facilities of the 2 shipyards. The physical place of the specific sisterhip is at the shipyard producing the ship. The master ship can be located at one of the shipyards and the other yard can access this model via Internet connection.

Fig.1: Design and production scenario 1

2.2 Scenario 2, design and production of a ship at one shipyard, some blocks produced at another shipyard

In this situation a ship could be designed and produced at one shipyard (A) and also delivered from this shipyard. For capacity or time schedule reasons it happens that one or several blocks should be produced at another shipyard inside the group (B). This can be a planned activity from the beginning or coming late because shipyard A becomes capacity problems and is looking for another yard inside the group to produce some blocks and deliver them to shipyard A. Shipyard B then needs in their sistership only the blocks they should produce. This scenario happens today very often, because one yard inside the group may work on their capacity limits and other yards may have no work at the moment. Then as many blocks as necessary to get back a balance in the workload should be produced outside the original planned working place. It may also be that some blocks are produced at yard B but some others at an additional yard C. There then also a sister ship need to be installed to produce here specific production information.

Fig.2: Design and production scenario 2

3. Analysis what is site dependant and what can be standard

When looking at above scenarios, it is obvious that it is necessary inside a shipyard group to check what kind of standards are used to design and produce ship parts. Mainly the production related points would be site specific. They can be divided in parts production tasks and tasks that have to do with the planning and assembly process. The parts production tasks are mainly the plate and profile nesting, cutting and pipe bending and cutting. Also yard specific are the definition of the assembly structure that represents assembly places and the process chain. Related to this is also the shrinkage and excess handling that have to do with the assembly processes and the workshop conditions. The connection to ERP systems is typically also specific. Welding processes are also site specific and can result in different edge preparation (bevels) and also different shrinkage and excess values.

Some part size issues like plate length and width, profile length and block size can differ between different yards. With the concept of having a common model for both Structural and Detail/Production design the block splitting can be handled dynamically, but there may be some necessary after work in the detail design. To reduce the amount of extra work, it could be useful inside a shipyard group to decide on group wide plate length and width and also profile lengths. The same is with the block size. The assembly planning tools offers the possibility to define the assembly size yard specific, so that at one yard two blocks are a big assembly that can be handled via crane capacities and at another yard only one block is the biggest assembly. The block length resulting from the maximum possible plate and profile length is a limiting parameter that should be standard.

Naming conventions for blocks, panels, modules or systems should be standardized inside a shipyard group. Cut-outs may be different depending on if welding is done via robots or not.

Drawings are a special case. They are typically different at different shipyards. They are normally block based. To make it easier to exchange production between shipyards the drawing rules should be defined as group standards or the approach to create automatically assembly drawings just in time when they are needed should be used.

Fig.3: Assembly instruction Drawing

The production Manager is the tool that can show the model graphically and via a tree view. It is connected to Planning and material systems. The assembly instruction drawing that can be created from this application combines all relevant information for the workshop to produce an assembly.

Fig.4: Connection of Assembly Planning to other systems

Table I: Standard and site specific items

Standard	Standard or specific	Yard specific
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structure (Geometry) • Plate, profile scantlings • Holes, notches • Brackets • Stiffener, flanges • Seams, plates • Pillars • Swedging • End-cuts • Stiffener end connections • Component database • Volume data base • Equipment • Pips systems • Ventilation systems • Cabeling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plate length and width • Profile length • Block size • Position number system • Block, panel, module, system naming conventions • Component naming rules • Cut-outs (robot, non robot) • Drawing rules • List rules • Nesting forms • Bevels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assembly structure, which represents the process chain • Welding methods (bevels) • Profile nesting • Profile cutting • Plate nesting • Plate cutting • Panel line • Connection to ERP systems • Shrinkage • Excess • Plate bending radii • Curved panel assembly: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Jigpillars ○ Plate jigs ○ Bending templates • Pipe bending machine parameters

4. Tools for controlled access and synchronization

The Tribon data management tools and the sistership handling functionality can be used to control the access, workflow and synchronisation of site independent standard projects and site manufacturing related specific projects.

Tribon Data Management is an embedded and adapted data management functionality fully integrated in the Tribon PIM (Product Information Model). Tribon Data Management focuses on:

- Workflow control, based on object status and triggers
- Status on objects
- User-defined attributes
- Access control on data, based on Status
- Access control on functions

This is a solution to control the development, approval and release of design data on a project both within and outside the design department. Status and Access Control on all design data will ensure that only approved data will be used according to the shipyard rules for access and distribution. This is a flexible framework for creating the data management style that suits the need for concurrent engineering and /or distributed manufacturing.

4.1 Status Control

Four independent Status categories exist:

- Design status
- Manufacturing status
- Assembly status
- Material control status

Table II: Customisation of Status, examples

Design status	Manufacturing status	Material status	Assembly status
Basic Design started	Released for production	Not defined	Material requested
Pending classification	Manufacturing planned	Request For Quotation made	Material availability OK
Classification approved	Manufacturing started	Material ordered	Material issued
Detail design started	Manufacturing finished	Material delivered to stock	Material assembled
Pending approval		Material delivered for assembly	
Design approved			
Released for production			

Status is set in Modelling or Viewing applications. The Status is set under the control of a person with the correct authority rights. The Status on an object can be used to control the use of the object via Access Control.

4.2 Workflow control

With the status, access control and trigger functionality, workflows can be created and controlled.

- Trace Status Changes using the Trigger Mechanism available in Tribon through the Developers' Toolkit
- trig_tdm_status_change
- User defined triggers in various Tribon functions

Fig.5: Example of a workflow control via triggers

4.3 User-Defined Attributes

User defined attributes can be used to handle customer specific tasks. They can be customizable categories and names, may include any number of strings, numbers and dates and can be attached to Tribon Objects.

Table III: Examples, Category: AuditTrail:

AttributeName: Assumptions Data: String: Actions String: Justification Date: ActionDate	AttributeName: Decisions Data: String: Decision String: Justification Date: ApprovalDate
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4.4 Access Control

The following access possibilities are implemented: None, Read, Read & Write, Read & Write & Change status. Different roles can be defined like Hull Designer or Pipe Designer. Each user is connected to one or several roles. These can be different also in different projects. The roles are used to control access to functions and objects in a project. The access can depend on the status of an object. This is important for a workflow control.

4.5 Sistership Management

A Tribon Sistership cluster represents a series of ships (a *class*). The Sistership cluster includes one Master project and one or more Slave projects. The Master project is the baseline project of the class, while there is one Slave project for each ship in the class.

The Effectivity specification specifies how the models of the master project should be applied on the slave projects.

The Tribon master project is connected to one or more Tribon slave projects in a Tribon sistership cluster. The projects within the sistership cluster are kept synchronized according to the effectivity specification.

Fig.6: Sister Ship Management

For all modelling in Tribon, it has to be decided if the particular model is valid for the whole class (which means modelling in the master project) or just for one specific ship in the class (which means modelling in the specific slave project). If there are big changes to be made for a certain ship and the following ships in the series, a new sistership cluster can be created. Each cluster is self-contained, i.e. the second cluster will not have any link back to the first cluster. When a new sistership cluster has been created and the effectivity rules are in place, the master project can be initialized by copying the appropriate data from any other project (which could be a master or slave project of another sistership cluster or any other project). Depending on the effectivity rules in the new sistership cluster the data will be automatically propagated to the slave projects. Manual sistership copying is allowed from master project to slave project, as long as it does not conflict with the effectivity specification.

Within a sistership cluster there is one Effectivity specification per slave project. The Effectivity specification defines which models (objects) of the master project that are valid for the slave project. An effectivity specification consists of a set of Effectivity rules. Filtering on Status and other TDM attributes can make the object selection. Once the effectivity specification link is established for an object, the sistership management tool will control that the objects are kept synchronized. Tribon will keep track of the objects, which need to be transferred. The ordinary Data Access control rules apply for the copying operations within sistership management.

5. Concepts to handle concurrent engineering, collaboration and distributed production

The first step to be done inside a shipyard group is to decide what is standard and is therefore modelled in the master ship and what is site dependent and therefore done in the derived sister ships. The border for this may be different at different ship yard groups. When looking at above table for standard and specific things, there is a field in the middle, where points are mentioned that may be standard in one group and site specific in another group. One example is the block size. The Design Panel approach allows doing the block splitting dynamically. That would mean, that the sister shipyard would get the Design Panels and create their own block sizes and therefore different production panels compared to another sister. That means more work at the sistership yard and less flexibility to change the production place.

Every ship inside a shipyard group should be modelled in a standard master ship to be able to decide as late as possible where ships or parts of ships should be produced. From these master ships sisterships then can be derived when necessary. The workflow how this transfer should be done (transfer from master to sister ship only when the block to be transferred has the status “Modelling Ready”, e.g.) need to be defined. There may be other rules as well. The sister ship only contains blocks that are ready from the modelling point of view and where production information should be created in the sister ship. It could make sense to define special users that are responsible for the transfer from master to sisterships. They need to have special rights to do that, so that normal users cannot transfer model data. There are 2 steps in this kind of transfer. The first step is to initially create a sister ship at a certain place where production should be done. Those parts of the master that are needed are transferred to the sister. Inside the sistership management it can be set which blocks of the master are valid for sister A and which ones for sister B etc. This ensures that only relevant blocks are transferred.

Step number 2 is the change management. Also workflows need to be created to update a sister ship model with changes from the master ship. Assemblies and production information that has already been created in the sister ship need to be kept and the transferred (changed) part will get the same assembly than the old part had before. Maybe some additional parts have to be collected in the sister to the proper assemblies. The program creating automatically parts can handle where parts are nested and only stores those parts that are new or that have been changed. The result of this program run also contains the information on which nestings changed parts are. With this information the process of updating the existing production material can be done properly.

In the master project the Basic Design is done in parallel to the detail design. Designers of a shipyard inside the group typically do the basic design. Designers of the same yard locally can carry out the detail design, or designers from other yards via Internet connection or by design agents sitting locally or working in their office offline or connected via Internet to the master ship. The access to the different system functions or models, e.g. blocks is controlled via status and access control from Tribon Data management functions. There are several methods available to handle the directly working on the model and design agents sending material that then is brought into the model at the shipyard. The production blocks delivered by design agents can be synchronised with the Design Blocks existing at the shipyard. When design agents are working directly on the model at the shipyard

via Internet connection (via RDP or Terminal Server or directly), then they should only have read and write access to those blocks that they are working on. For surrounding blocks they need read access but for the rest they may have no rights. When the block a design agent is working on has reached the status ready, then the access may change to none, so they cannot see or modify anything.

Fig.7: Concurrent engineering and collaboration at the mastership

When the master project has reached a level where the preparation of production information can be done, it is propagated to the production yards via Sistership management controlled via the status of the different objects in the master ship and workflow- and access rules.

The first task to be done with a site-specific sister ship derived from a master ship is to define the assembly structure and collect the parts to it. The next site-specific task is to run the automatic parts generation program that will calculate production related issues like shrinkage, excess, bevels and markings. After that parts production and assembly material has to be created. The planning can start as soon as the sistership transfer has been done.

Some time of thinking should also be spent on material handling. When there is a late decision to produce a few blocks at another yard than originally planned, the material like plates, profiles, pipes or equipments need to be transported from the original yard to the production yard or there has to be a minimum set of stock material available at every yard. Equipments and special steel qualities have anyway to be transferred to the production yard. Another possibility is to order the material but the delivery is done when it is decided where the production should be.

The production yards then can prepare their site-specific production information and start to produce the ship. Design modifications are distributed from the master ship to the different production ships on a scheduled time (every day) or when necessary. At the sister ship yard there need to be a setup, that blocks where production has started are updated, but new production material is only produced for those parts that are not yet manufactured. The updated model then can be used to handle a modification management (creating papers what has to be changed e.g.) for those parts that have already been assembled. This synchronisation ensures that the design at the sistership is the same as in the master ship, but the sistership yard can decide how to feed their production also when late changes come.

If it is necessary to update the sister ship model with site-specific information for an optimised production, then it will save time and avoid errors when rules are defined for these updates that can be

handled via scripts inside Tribon. That means that the update can be run automatically with as less extra handwork as possible. The goal is that a production yard should be able to start with the first production part shortly after the first sistership transfer, to make it possible to decide as late as possible where ships or part of ships are produced.

Fig.8: Synchronisation of Mastership and sistership

6. Conclusion

It could be shown, that the tools to handle this business case are available and can be adapted to the different needs of different shipyard groups. The point that divides a design into standard and specific may be different in different companies. But this way of working gives the possibility to decide as late as possible where to produce a ship or parts of it and get the best benefit of existing design and production capacities.

Implementable Efficient Time and Energy Consumption Trajectories Design For an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle

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Abstract

In this paper we consider the implementation of time and energy efficient trajectories onto a test-bed autonomous underwater vehicle. The trajectories are loosely connected to the results of the application of the maximum principle to the controlled mechanical system. We use a numerical algorithm to compute efficient trajectories designed using geometric control theory to optimize a given cost function. Experimental results are shown for the time minimization problem.

1 Introduction

The oceans cover over 75% of the earth's surface and are currently exploited for energy, recreation, transportation, food and much more. However, almost 95% of this vast resource is unexplored. What other resources lie beneath the surface of the water? What else does the ocean have to offer? The answer to these questions among many others can only be answered through extensive ocean research and exploration. Today's maritime industries and research communities employ the use of underwater vehicles as a method to help discover the secrets of the abyss. Whether it is searching for oil deposits in the Gulf of Mexico, monitoring a coral reef in Papahānaumokuākea Marine National Monument (formerly the Northwestern Hawaiian Islands Marine National Monument), or just gathering data in Monterey Bay, underwater vehicles play a large part in understanding the oceans. Due to the extensive role that these vehicles play, their autonomy has become a large research interest. Much research has gone into making autonomous vehicles that travel underwater and perform a multitude of tasks far surpassing the abilities of human divers and small human-driven submarines. This extension of tasks also reduces the risk to humans while still gaining information about the vast ocean. This has motivated the research and development of AUV's and their control systems to have the ability to take over more responsibilities in ocean research. As we give a vehicle more responsibilities, assuming all else is constant, it will require an increase in efficiency. To do this we search for optimal trajectories which minimize some cost, such as time or energy. This is the basis for optimal control theory. We all know of many success stories in the AUV community; Kongsberg's HUGIN and WHOI's REMUS are well known. But, even with such successes in AUV control, optimal control is still a very underdeveloped area. Adaptive control research has contributed to cost minimization problems, but vehicle design has been the driving force for advancement in optimal control research. We look to advance the development of optimal control theory by expanding the motions along which AUV's travel. Traditionally, AUV's have taken the role of performing the long data gathering mission in the open ocean with little to no interaction with their surroundings *MacIver et al. (2004)*. The AUV is used to find the shipwreck, and the remotely operated vehicle (ROV) handles the up close exploration. AUV mission profiles of this sort are best suited through the use of a torpedo shaped AUV, *Bertram and Alvarez (2006)*, such as WHOI's REMUS and MIT's Odyssey, since straight lines and minimal (0° - 30°) angular displacements are all that are necessary to perform the transects and grid lines for these applications. However, the torpedo shape AUV lacks the ability to perform low-speed maneuvers in cluttered environments, such as autonomous exploration close to the seabed and around obstacles *MacIver et al. (2004)*, *Molnar et al. (2005)*. To this end, we approach the problem from a geometric control viewpoint and study optimal trajectories for vehicles with unconstrained movement in six degrees of freedom. From a practical point of view, this increases the difficulty of the control problem. However, without any movement constraints, the tools of geometric control theory are able to exploit the inherent nonlinear structure of the mechanical system and increase the size of the control domain. This

results in a greater understanding of the geometric properties of the AUV as a mechanical system. Expanding our knowledge based on theory alone is insufficient, especially in such a practical field as AUV control. In parallel to the theoretical study, we conduct weekly experiments on a test-bed AUV in order to validate our algorithms. This gives us a benchmark in both theory and application as to the limitations of one on the other. With all of these tools in hand, we are well suited to bridge the gap between geometric control theory and optimal control application onto AUV's.

2 Equations of Motion

The equations of motion for a submerged rigid body have been extensively studied, *Fossen (1996)*. We will not repeat the derivation of these equations but rather add some comments which we consider very important, and which are usually omitted from AUV literature.

First we precisely define the configuration space of a rigid body. We identify the position and the orientation of a rigid body with an element of the matrix group of rigid displacements $SE(3)$: (b, R) , where $b = (b_1, b_2, b_3)^t \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the position vector of the body and $R \in SO(3)$ is a rotation matrix describing the orientation of the body. The translational and angular velocities in the body-fixed frame are denoted by $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)^t$ and $\Omega = (\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \Omega_3)^t$ respectively. It follows that the kinematic equations of a rigid body are given by: $\dot{b} = Rv$, $\dot{R} = R\hat{\Omega}$ where the operator $\hat{\cdot} : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow so(3)$ is defined by $\hat{y}z = y \times z$; $so(3)$ being the space of skew-symmetric matrices. Notice that the linear space of the body-fixed velocities is the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{se}(3)$. We assume for the rest of the paper that the origin of the body-fixed frame is the center of gravity C_G . Moreover, we assume the body to have three planes of symmetry with body axes which coincide with the principal axes of inertia. The kinetic energy of the rigid body is then given by $T_{body} = \frac{1}{2}\xi^t \mathbb{I} \xi$ where \mathbb{I} is the inertia matrix and $\xi = (v, \Omega)$.

We now assume that the body is immersed in a real fluid. By real fluid we mean a viscous ideal fluid. Here a real fluid is assumed to be irrotational, but from a practical point of view a viscous fluid is rotational. Our assumptions on the vehicle imply that the body inertia, the added mass and the moment of inertia matrices are diagonal, and the added cross-terms are zero. It follows that the total kinetic energy of our rigid body in an unbounded real fluid is given by $T = \frac{1}{2}(v^t(mI_3 + M_f)v + \Omega^t(J_b + J_f)\Omega)$ where m is the mass of the rigid body, I_3 is the 3×3 -identity matrix and J_b is the body inertia matrix. Moreover, M_f, J_f are respectively referred to as the added mass and the added moments of inertia. These coefficients depend on the density of the fluid. In the sequel we will use $M = mI_3 + M_f$ and $J = J_b + J_f$. The Coriolis and centripetal effects can be expressed in terms of ∇ ; the Levi-Civita affine-connection for the Riemannian metric induced by the kinetic energy T . Explicitly, if $\gamma(t) = (b(t), R(t))$ is a curve in $SE(3)$, and $\gamma'(t) = (v(t), \Omega(t))$ is its pseudo-velocity, then

$$\nabla_{\gamma'}\gamma' = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{v} + M^{-1}(\Omega \times Mv) \\ \dot{\Omega} + J^{-1}(\Omega \times J\Omega + v \times Mv) \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

. Gravity, buoyancy, drag and lift can be modeled using external forces and torques. The equations of a rigid body submerged in a real fluid can then be modeled using affine differential geometry. They form a first-order affine control system on the tangent bundle $TSE(3)$ that represents the second-order *forced affine-connection control system* on $SE(3)$

$$\nabla_{\gamma'}\gamma' = \begin{pmatrix} M^{-1}(D_v(v)v + R^t \rho g \mathcal{V}k + \varphi_v) \\ J^{-1}(D_\Omega(\Omega)\Omega - r_B \times R^t \rho g \mathcal{V}k + \tau_\Omega) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where ∇ is the Levi-Civita affine-connection for the Riemannian metric induced by the kinetic energy T . The matrices $D_v(v), D_\Omega(\Omega)$ represent the drag force and momentum respectively. Finally, we have a restoring force and a restoring moment. The only moment due to the restoring forces is the torque from the buoyancy force $-r_B \times R^t \rho g \mathcal{V}k$ where r_B is the vector from C_G to the center of buoyancy C_B , where ρ is the fluid density, g the acceleration of gravity, \mathcal{V} the volume of fluid displaced by the rigid body and k the unit vector pointing in the direction of gravity. The forces $\varphi_v = (\varphi_{v_1}, \varphi_{v_2}, \varphi_{v_3})^t$ and $\tau_\Omega = (\tau_{\Omega_1}, \tau_{\Omega_2}, \tau_{\Omega_3})^t$

account for the control. In the absence of restoration, drag forces and momentum the equations of motion (2) represent a *left-invariant affine-connection control system* on the Lie group $\mathcal{SE}(3)$.

System (2) is equivalent to

$$M\dot{v} = Mv \times \Omega + D_v(v)v + R^t \rho g \mathcal{V}k + \varphi_v \quad (3)$$

$$J\dot{\Omega} = J\Omega \times \Omega + Mv \times v + D_\Omega(\Omega)\Omega - r_B \times R^t \rho g \mathcal{V}k + \tau_\Omega \quad (4)$$

which are the form of the equations of motion usually encountered in the literature. We refer interested readers to *Leonard (1996,1997)*, *Chyba et al. (2007)* for an in depth treatment of the geometric features of submerged rigid bodies.

For our computations and experiments we make the following assumptions. We assume a drag force $D_v(v)$ and a drag momentum $D_\Omega(\Omega)$, neglecting the off-diagonal terms. The contribution of these forces is usually assumed to be quadratic in the velocities, more precisely we have $D_v^{ii}(v) = C_D \rho A |v_i| |v_i|$ where C_D for a sphere is taken as 1.2 for laminar flows and 0.2 for turbulent flows, ρ is the density of the fluid and A is the projected surface area of the object. Under these assumptions, the drag force and momentum are then non differentiable functions which causes difficulties for theoretical analysis. To overcome this, some people assume the vehicle to move in a single direction, hence $|v_i| |v_i| = v_i^2$. We do not want to make this assumption, because at least rotations are needed in both directions. Based on our test bed vehicle, our computations for the total drag forces for various velocities are approximated well using a cubic function with no quadratic or constant term. To summarize, the contribution to the translational motions is given by $D_v(v) = \text{diag}(D_v^{i1} v_i^3 + D_v^{i2} v_i)$ and to the rotational motions by $D_\Omega(\Omega) = \text{diag}(D_\Omega^{i1} \Omega_i^3 + D_\Omega^{i2} \Omega_i)$ where D_v^{ij}, D_Ω^{ij} are constant coefficients.

In local coordinates, the equations of motion for a submerged rigid body in a real fluid are as follows. We denote by $\eta = (b_1, b_2, b_3, \phi, \theta, \psi)^t$ the position and orientation of the vehicle with respect to the earth-fixed reference frame. The coordinates ϕ, θ, ψ are the Euler angles for the body frame. The coordinates corresponding to translational and rotational velocities in the body frame are $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3)^t$ and $\Omega = (\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \Omega_3)^t$. We have:

$$\dot{b}_1 = v_1 \cos \psi \cos \theta + v_2 R^{12} + v_3 R^{13} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{b}_2 = v_1 \sin \psi \cos \theta + v_2 R^{22} + v_3 R^{23} \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{b}_3 = -v_1 \sin \theta + v_2 \cos \theta \sin \phi + v_3 \cos \theta \cos \phi \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{\phi} = \Omega_1 + \Omega_2 \sin \phi \tan \theta + \Omega_3 \cos \phi \tan \theta \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \Omega_2 \cos \phi - \Omega_3 \sin \phi \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = \frac{\sin \phi}{\cos \theta} \Omega_2 + \frac{\cos \phi}{\cos \theta} \Omega_3 \quad (10)$$

$$\dot{v}_1 = \frac{1}{m_1} [-(m_3)v_3\Omega_2 + (m_2)v_2\Omega_3 + D_v(v_1) - G \sin \theta + \varphi_{v_1}] \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{v}_2 = \frac{1}{m_2} [(m_3)v_3\Omega_1 - (m_1)v_1\Omega_3 + D_v(v_2) + G \cos \theta \sin \phi + \varphi_{v_2}] \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{v}_3 = \frac{1}{m_3} [-(m_2)v_2\Omega_1 + (m_1)v_1\Omega_2 + D_v(v_3) + G \cos \theta \cos \phi + \varphi_{v_3}] \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Omega}_1 = & \frac{1}{I_{b_1} + J_f^{\Omega_1}} [(I_{b_2} - I_{b_3} + J_f^{\Omega_2} - J_f^{\Omega_3})\Omega_2\Omega_3 + (M_f^{v_2} - M_f^{v_3})v_2v_3 \\ & + D_\Omega(\Omega_1) + \rho g \mathcal{V}(-y_B \cos \theta \cos \phi + z_B \cos \theta \sin \phi) + \tau_{\Omega_1}] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Omega}_2 = & \frac{1}{I_{b_2} + J_f^{\Omega_2}} [(I_{b_3} - I_{b_1} + J_f^{\Omega_3} - J_f^{\Omega_1})\Omega_1\Omega_3 + (M_f^{v_3} - M_f^{v_1})v_1v_3 \\ & + D_\Omega(\Omega_2) + \rho g \mathcal{V}(z_B \sin \theta + x_B \cos \theta \cos \phi) + \tau_{\Omega_2}] \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{\Omega}_3 = \frac{1}{I_{b_3} + J_f^{\Omega_3}} [(I_{b_1} - I_{b_2} + J_f^{\Omega_1} - J_f^{\Omega_2})\Omega_1\Omega_2 + (M_f^{v_1} - M_f^{v_2})v_1v_2 + D_{\Omega}(\Omega_3) + \rho g \mathcal{V}(-x_B \cos \theta \sin \phi - y_B \sin \theta) + \tau_{\Omega_3}] \quad (16)$$

where $G = mg - \rho g \mathcal{V}$, $m_i = m + M_f^{v_i}$, $D_v(v_i) = D_v^{i1}v_i^3 + D_v^{i2}v_i$ and $D_{\Omega}(\Omega_i) = D_{\Omega}^{i1}\Omega_i^3 + D_{\Omega}^{i2}\Omega_i$. $\varphi_v = (\varphi_{v_1}, \varphi_{v_2}, \varphi_{v_3})$ and $\tau_{\Omega} = (\tau_{\Omega_1}, \tau_{\Omega_2}, \tau_{\Omega_3})$ represent the control.

The test-bed AUV which we use for our experiments is the Omni-Directional Intelligent Navigator (ODIN), Fig.1. ODIN is owned and operated by the Autonomous Systems Laboratory (ASL), College of Engineering at the University of Hawaii (UH). The experiments are carried out at the Duke Kahanamoku Swimming Complex at UH.

Fig.1: ODIN operating in the pool.

ODIN has a spherical hull which is 65cm in diameter. This sphere is constructed from an aluminum alloy to prevent corrosion. Eight thrusters are attached to the sphere via four fabricated mounts, each holding two thrusters. The thrusters are evenly distributed around the sphere with four vertical and four horizontal. ODIN is capable of moving in 6 degrees-of-freedom (DOF) from either a remote or autonomous mode. For our experiments, ODIN is tethered, but only to send commands via TCP/IP protocol from a shore based laptop to be run in an autonomous mode. This setup allows for multiple tests to be conducted without removing ODIN from the water to upload mission sorties. ODIN's internal CPU is a 800 MHz Intel based processor running on a PC104+ form factor with two external I/O boards providing A/D and D/A operations. Major internal components include a pressure sensor, internal navigation sensor and 24 batteries. ODIN is capable to compute real time, yaw, pitch, tilt, and depth and can run autonomously for up to 5 hours. However the yaw sensor is not designed to follow fast changes of heading ($\geq 6^\circ/s$). ODIN does not currently have real time sensors to detect horizontal (x, y) position. Instead, experiments are video taped from the 10m diving platform, giving us a near nadir view of ODIN's movements. Videos are saved and horizontal position is post processed for later analysis. A real time system utilizing sonar was available on ODIN, but was abandoned for two main reasons. First, the sonar created too much noise in the diving well and led to inaccuracies. More significantly, in the implementation of our optimal trajectories, ODIN is often required to achieve large ($> 15^\circ$) list angles which render the sonars useless for horizontal position. Many solutions were attempted and video led to the most accurate results.

The numerical values of the various parameters used for the model are given in Table I. These values were derived from experiments performed on ODIN. The added mass and drag terms were estimated from formulas found in *Allmendinger (1990)* and *Imlay (1961)*. Moments of inertia were calculated using experiments outlined in *Bhattacharyya (1978)*. We used inclining experiments to locate and place C_B in the location seen in Table I. The drag and C_B estimates were then adapted to match the experimental behavior of the vehicle.

Unique to ODIN's construction is the control from an eight dimensional thrust to move in six DOF. This construction puts redundancy into the system in case of thruster failure. ODIN is able to operate in an

under-actuated condition if necessary, and research is active in this area as well, *Catone et al. (2007)*. It is important to distinguish between the control for the real vehicle, namely the applied control referring to the action of the eight thrusters, and the six DOF introduced before in the equations of motion (4). Our input trajectories to ODIN take the form of the six DOF controls which are converted onboard ODIN to the eight dimensional actual thrusters using the following Thrust Control Matrices (TCM's):

$$TCM_{horizontal} = \begin{pmatrix} -0.707 & 0.707 & 0.707 & -0.707 \\ 0.707 & 0.707 & -0.707 & -0.707 \\ 0.48160 & -0.48160 & 0.48160 & -0.48160 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (17)$$

$$TCM_{vertical} = \begin{pmatrix} -1.0 & -1.0 & -1.0 & -1.0 \\ -0.26989 & -0.26989 & 0.26989 & 0.26989 \\ 0.26989 & -0.26989 & -0.26989 & 0.26989 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

Table I: Numerical values for hydrodynamic coefficients.

m	126.55 kg	$\rho g \nabla$	1243.19 N	C_B	(0.49, 0.34, -7) mm
M_f^u	70 kg	M_f^v	70 kg	M_f^w	70 kg
I_x	5.46 kg.m ²	I_y	5.29 kg.m ²	I_z	5.72 kg.m ²
J_f^p	0 kg.m ²	J_f^q	0 kg.m ²	J_f^r	0 kg.m ²
D_v^{11}	-27.0273	D_v^{21}	-27.0273	D_v^{31}	-27.0273
D_v^{12}	-897.6553	D_v^{22}	-897.6553	D_v^{32}	-897.6553
D_Ω^{11}	-13.793	D_Ω^{21}	-13.793	D_Ω^{31}	-11.9424
D_Ω^{12}	-6.4594	D_Ω^{22}	-6.4594	D_Ω^{32}	-6.9393

Matrices (17) and (18) are based on the following assumptions. Let us denote by γ_i^h , $i = 1, \dots, 4$ the thrusts induced by the horizontal thrusters and γ_i^v , $i = 1, \dots, 4$ the thrusts induced by the vertical thrusters. We assume that the points of application of the thrusts $\gamma_i^{(h,v)}$ lie in a plane through the center of the vehicle. We also assume that the distance from the center of the body frame (C_G in our case) to the center of the sphere (C_B in our case) is small with respect to the radius of the sphere. As a consequence we can decouple the action of the thrusters as follows. The horizontal thrusters contribute only to the forces φ_{v_1} (surge) and φ_{v_2} (sway) and to the torque τ_{Ω_3} (yaw). The vertical thrusters contribute only to the force φ_{Ω_3} (heave) and to the torques τ_{v_1} (roll) and τ_{v_2} (pitch). We have $(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \tau_3)^t = TCM_{horizontal}(\gamma^h)^t$ and $(\varphi_3, \tau_1, \tau_2)^t = TCM_{vertical}(\gamma^v)^t$. Assuming that the thrusters are independently powered, we can reasonably state that each thrust $\gamma_i^{(h,v)}$ is bounded by fixed values $\gamma^{(h,v)} \in \Upsilon = \{\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^8 | \gamma_i^{(h,v), \min} \leq \gamma_i^{(h,v)} \leq \gamma_i^{(h,v), \max}, i = 1, \dots, 4\}$. The image of Υ through the above linear transformation is composed of two flat ellipsoids. We choose a box included in these ellipsoids as the domain of control for the six DOF control. There are different possible choices for this box depending on the controllability properties we prefer for our vehicle. In the sequel, we assume the control domain for the component φ_v and τ_Ω to be

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F} &= \{\varphi_v \in \mathbb{R}^3 | \alpha_{v_i}^{\min} \leq \varphi_{v_i} \leq \alpha_{v_i}^{\max}, \alpha_{v_i}^{\min} < 0 < \alpha_{v_i}^{\max}, i = 1, 2, 3\} \\ \mathcal{T} &= \{\tau_\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^3 | \alpha_{\Omega_i}^{\min} \leq \tau_{\Omega_i} \leq \alpha_{\Omega_i}^{\max}, \alpha_{\Omega_i}^{\min} < 0 < \alpha_{\Omega_i}^{\max}, i = 1, 2, 3\} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

For our numerical computations, we will take $\alpha_{v_{1,2}}^{\max} = -\alpha_{v_{1,2}}^{\min} = 8$ N, $\alpha_{v_3}^{\max} = 30$ N, $\alpha_{v_3}^{\min} = -5$ N, $\alpha_{\Omega_{1,2}}^{\max} = -\alpha_{\Omega_{1,2}}^{\min} = 3$ N.m and $\alpha_{\Omega_3}^{\max} = -\alpha_{\Omega_3}^{\min} = 1$ N.m. The non symmetry of $\alpha_{v_3}^{\min, \max}$ is due to the fact that the 4 vertical thrusters are all oriented in the same direction which is shown by the 4 negative coefficients in the first row of the matrix (18). Along with the tests to determine the values in Table I, we also tested the thrusters. Each thruster has a unique voltage input to power output relationship. This relationship is highly nonlinear and is approximated using a piecewise linear function which we refer to as our thruster model.

3 Maximum Principle

The maximum principle is a powerful tool of optimal control theory. It was developed in the 1950's and the reader can consult *Pontryagin et al. (1962)* for the original publication of this result. This principle provides necessary conditions for a trajectory to be optimal with respect to a given cost. In this section we state the maximum principle in general. The goal of this paper is not to conduct a theoretical analysis based on the maximum principle, see *Chyba et al. (2007)* for such an approach. Our goal here is to introduce the terminology to describe the trajectories that we will consider for our motion planning problem, namely the notion of bang-bang and singular arcs.

First, we rewrite the equations of motion for the submerged rigid body as an affine control system. Indeed, it is true in general that a forced affine-connection control system on a manifold Q is equivalent to an affine control system on TQ . The equivalence is realized via the *geodesic spray* of an affine-connection and the *vertical lift* of tangent vectors to Q . We introduce $\chi = (\eta, v, \Omega)$, and let $\chi_0 = \chi(0)$ and $\chi_T = \chi(T)$ be the initial and final states for our submerged rigid body. We denote the control $\varphi = (\varphi_v, \tau_\Omega)$. Thus, $\varphi_4 = \tau_1$. Then, Equation (2) is equivalent to the following affine control system:

$$\dot{\chi}(t) = Y_0(\chi(t)) + \sum_{i=1}^6 Y_i(t)\varphi_i(t) \quad (20)$$

where the drift Y_0 accounts for the centripetal, Coriolis, Drag and restoring forces. The input vector fields are given by $Y_i = (0, 0, \mathbb{I}_i^{-1})^t$ with \mathbb{I}_i^{-1} being the column i of the matrix $\mathbb{I}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} M^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & J^{-1} \end{pmatrix}$. In other words, we have that $Y_i = \text{vlft}(\mathbb{I}_i^{-1})$. *Bullo and Lewis (2004)* show that trajectories for the affine-connection control system on Q map bijectively to trajectories for the affine control system on TQ whose initial points lie on the zero-section.

Let us now assume that we want to minimize a cost determined by the following expression: $C = \int_0^T f^0(\chi(t), \varphi(t))dt$. This cost can represent the time or energy consumption.

Assume that there exists an admissible cost-optimal control $\varphi = (\varphi_v, \tau_\Omega) : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathcal{U} = \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{T}$, such that the corresponding trajectory $\chi = (\eta, v, \Omega)$ is a solution of (20) and steers the body from χ_0 to χ_T . The Maximum Principle implies that there exists an absolutely continuous vector $\lambda = (\lambda_\eta, \lambda_v, \lambda_\Omega) : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{12}$, and $\lambda_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, $(\lambda_0, \lambda(t)) \neq 0$ for all t , such that the following conditions hold almost everywhere:

$$\dot{\eta} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial \lambda_\eta}, \dot{v} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial \lambda_v}, \dot{\Omega} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial \lambda_\Omega}, \quad \lambda_\eta = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial \eta}, \lambda_v = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial v}, \lambda_\Omega = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial \Omega} \quad (21)$$

where the Hamiltonian function H is given by:

$$H(\chi, \lambda, \varphi, \tau) = \lambda_\eta^t (Rv, \Theta\Omega)^t + \lambda_v^t M^{-1} [Mv \times \Omega + D_v(v)v + R^t \rho g^t \mathcal{V}k + \varphi_v] + \lambda_\Omega^t J^{-1} [J\Omega \times \Omega + Mv \times v + D_\Omega(\Omega)\Omega - r_B \times R^t \rho g^t \mathcal{V}k + \tau_\Omega] + \lambda_0 f^0(\chi, \varphi) \quad (22)$$

Furthermore, the maximum condition holds: $H(\chi(t), \lambda(t), \varphi_v(t), \tau_\Omega(t)) = \max_\gamma H(\chi(t), \lambda(t), \gamma_1, \gamma_2)$. The maximum of the Hamiltonian is constant along the solutions of (21). A quadruple $(\chi, \lambda, \varphi_v, \tau_\Omega)$ that satisfies the Maximum Principle is called an extremal, and the vector function $\lambda(\cdot)$ is called the adjoint vector.

4 Minimum Time

4.1 Singular and bang-bang arcs

In this case we have $f^0(\chi, \varphi) = 1$. The maximum condition, along with the control domain $\mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{T}$, is equivalent almost everywhere to $(M, J$ diagonal and $> 0)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$:

$$\varphi_{v_i}(t) = \alpha_{v_i}^{\min} \text{ if } \lambda_{v_i}(t) < 0 \text{ and } \varphi_{v_i}(t) = \alpha_{v_i}^{\max} \text{ if } \lambda_{v_i}(t) > 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\tau_{\Omega_i}(t) = \alpha_{\Omega_i}^{\min} \text{ if } \lambda_{\Omega_i}(t) < 0 \text{ and } \tau_{\Omega_i}(t) = \alpha_{\Omega_i}^{\max} \text{ if } \lambda_{\Omega_i}(t) > 0 \quad (24)$$

Clearly, the zeros of the functions λ_{v_i} , λ_{Ω_i} determine the structure of the solutions to the Maximum Principle, and hence of the time-optimal control. We say that a component of the control is bang-bang on a given interval $[t_1, t_2]$ if its corresponding switching functions are nonzero for almost all $t \in [t_1, t_2]$. The bang-bang component of the control only takes values in $\{\alpha_i^{\min}, \alpha_i^{\max}\}$ for almost every $t \in [t_1, t_2]$, $i = 1, \dots, 6$. On the other hand, if there is a nontrivial interval $[t_1, t_2]$ such that a switching function is identically zero, the corresponding component of the control is said to be singular on $[t_1, t_2]$. A singular control is said to be strict if all other controls are bang. We consider two types of switching times in this paper. First, assume a given component of the control to be piecewise constant, in particular this is the case if the component is bang-bang. Then, we say that $t_s \in [t_1, t_2]$ is a switching time for this component if, for each interval of the form $]t_s - \varepsilon, t_s + \varepsilon[\cap [t_1, t_2]$, $\varepsilon > 0$, the component is not constant. Secondly, a time t_s will also be referred to a switching time for a given component if it corresponds to a concatenation between a singular and a bang-bang arc for this component. In addition, when computing the total number of switching times along a trajectory we count only one switching time in the case that several components of the control switch simultaneously.

As a final remark, we would like to point out that indirect methods are numerical methods based on the Maximum Principle. The strategy is to rewrite the optimal control problem into a two point boundary value problem with the differential system being the Hamiltonian. These methods, called shooting methods, are very accurate when they converge, however in our case it would be very hard to achieve the convergence due to the bang-singular structure of the time optimal strategies in the case of the AUV's. This is why we base our strategy on direct methods as explained in the next section.

4.2 Numerical computation

A direct method is used for our numerical computations. It is based on the rewriting of the optimal control problem (*OCP*) into a finite dimensional nonlinear optimization problem (*NLOP*). The variables of the (*NLOP*) are the discretized state and control of the (*OCP*). The constraints of this (*NLOP*) are the dynamic constraints; the upper and lower bounds on the control and the final state constraint.

Methods to solve nonlinear optimization problems are well developed and we choose to use the interior point IpOpt, *Wachter and Biegler (2006)*, in conjunction with the modeling Language AMPL, *Fourer et al. (1993)*.

Due to our experimental setting we choose the initial configuration η_0 to be the origin and the final configuration $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$, both at zero velocity. The limitation on the size of the trajectory is bounded by the size of the field of vision of the camera shooting the experiments ($\sim 5\text{m}$ by 7m).

There exists a trajectory between every pair of configurations at rest. Indeed, by only considering pure motions along or about one body fixed-frame axis at the time, we can realize such a trajectory with at most 6 pure motions. For our pair of configurations we need a pure surge, a pure sway and a pure heave. If we saturate the corresponding translational controls the total duration of the trajectory is $t_{\text{pure}} \approx 72.77\text{ s}$.

Numerically solving the minimum time problem for our pair of configurations provides a trajectory with a final time $t_{\text{NLOP}}^f \approx 23.21\text{ s}$. It is less than half the time for the pure motion strategy. Fig.2 shows the minimum time control strategy and trajectory.

The minimum time strategy displays a large number of switchings. We also have a singular arc for the τ_{Ω_3} control (yaw component). This singular arc emphasizes the need for the AUV to maintain a prescribed orientation in order to maximize translational controls. Such a trajectory is attractive because it is time optimal, however its implementation on a real vehicle is impossible. Indeed, close switching times are potentially damaging to the thrusters, and in fact, thrusters are physically unable to adjust to rapid switches. An additional concern is the singular arc. A control strategy that is continuously changing requires a great amount of data to be stored in the AUV's memory. Numerically, (*NLOP*) is time consuming since we need a fine discretization due to the singular arcs. Since the finer the discretization, the larger the problem, we very rapidly encounter problems with tens of thousands of variables (12 states and 6 controls per discretization step).

Fig.2: Minimum time trajectory, $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$.

Practical considerations show the need for a trajectory to be both time efficient and implementable. A compromise between pure motions trajectories and time optimal trajectories is our goal.

First we consider a translational displacement. We can realize trajectory designs which are time efficient and implementable by considering motions with piecewise constant controls containing only one common switching time. If there are no angular velocities, then the evolutions of v_1 , v_2 and v_3 are completely decoupled. Then, given two configurations, a switching time and final time, one can always find six values of control (two values per translational control) that realize the translational motion. Of course these values of control might be out of the bounds of the thrusters. This is simply solved by increasing the switching time and the final time. Note that this is also true if there are initial or/and final translational velocities, provided they are reachable with the allocated control bounds.

Next, we extend this construction to all dimensions of the configuration space (namely the orientations), except we may be required to use more than one common switching time. Applying this idea we can choose to discretize our *(OCP)*, but only with a restricted number of discretization points; typically not more than 10, versus the 1000 plus for *(NLOP)*. The difference between this rewriting and the previous is that we take the values of the constant control and the switching times as the unknowns of the optimization problem. The new optimization problem, called the Switching Time Parameterization Problem *(STPP)_p* takes the following form:

$$(STPP)_p \begin{cases} \min_{z \in \mathcal{D}} t_{p+1} \\ t_0 = 0 \\ t_{i+1} = t_i + \xi_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, p \\ \chi_{i+1} = \chi_i + \int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} \dot{\chi}(t, \varphi_i, \tau_i) dt \\ \chi_{p+1} = \chi_f \\ z = (\xi_1, \dots, \xi_{p+1}, \varphi_1, \tau_1, \dots, \varphi_{p+1}, \tau_{p+1}) \\ \mathcal{D} = \mathbb{R}_+^{(p+1)} \times \mathcal{U}^{(p+1)} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

An interesting feature of STPP is that with the low number of switching times p , it is possible to use a high order integrator to compute the dynamic constraint. This leads to a very accurate solution with respect

to the theoretical model. For practical purposes we also smooth the switchings with linear functions so they do not occur instantaneously.

Applying the nonlinear solver IpOpt to $(STPP)_p$, we get final times that are surprisingly close to the computed minimum time as shown in Table II. The first column corresponds to a given final configuration (at rest), the second to the minimum time, the third to the pure motion time, the third, fourth and fifth to $(STPP)_p$ times with 1, 2 and 5 switchings respectively. Note that the $(STPP)_p$ solutions all contain linear junctions, 120 *ms* wide, between 2 constant thrust arcs. For all these motions we take the initial configuration to be the origin.

Table II: Comparison between minimum time, pure motion time and selected $(STPP)_p$ times.

η_f	$t_{(NLOP)}^f$ (s)	t_{pure}^f (s)	$t_{(STPP)_1}^f$ (s)	$t_{(STPP)_2}^f$ (s)	$t_{(STPP)_5}^f$ (s)
(5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)	23.21	72.77	35.90	25.29	23.93
(5, 3, 0, 0, 0, 0)	23.04	59.18	35.90	28.89	24.46
(5, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)	21.36	35.84	35.90	26.83	22.60
(2, 1, 0, 0.2, 0.2, 0)	11.77	30.75	16.40	14.46	12.94
(3, 4, 0, 0, 0.2, 1)	20.93	66.91	31.86	24.64	21.87

From Table II we note that the final times of the $(STPP)_p$ method are close to the minimum time even for $p = 1$, especially if we take the pure motion time as a comparison. We should note that if $(NLOP)$ and $(STPP)_p$ have the same number of discretization steps, then $(STPP)_p$ yields a shorter time because its set of admissible control strategies contain the set of $(NLOP)$ (by the variable ξ_i). Thus we clearly have the following inequalities:

$$t_{\min}^f \leq t_{(STPP)_{p+1}}^f \leq t_{(STPP)_p}^f \leq t_{(NLOP)_p}^f \quad (26)$$

Note that the first three entries for $(STPP)_1$ are the same which is not surprising since $(STPP)_1$ will give the smallest switching and final times for which the *straight line* control strategy (without change of orientation) is feasible while keeping the controls within the bounds of the thrusters. And, those times are limited here by the largest of the surge, sway and heave displacements.

Another advantage of STPP is that it is computationally efficient since the number of variables of $(STPP)_p$ is $7(p + 1)$; this is less than 50 for $p = 5$. In the cases in which it converges, $(STPP)_p$ is computationally much faster than $(NLOP)$.

Fig.3 shows the trajectory for $(STPP)_2$ with final position $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$. Here the control strategy is easier to implement on a real vehicle than the time minimum strategy shown in Fig.2. The difference between the time optimal strategy and the STPP one is the fewer changes in the orientation along the $STPP$ strategy. This is directly due to the low number of switchings. Also note that the surge and sway control contain one switching time and that the important gain of time realized when adding a second switching time is due to the possibility of changing the orientation during the transfer, which is impossible when only one switching time is allowed.

For ODIN, a change of control implies a control change for at least 4 thrusters, which means a single switching strategy is easier to implement than the pure motion strategy. This is only true when considering the number of switchings of the actual thrusters, but is false if we consider that a pure motion implementation can be complemented with a feedback stabilization.

If we consider the $(STPP)$ method for the control $\gamma \in \Upsilon \subset \mathbb{R}^8$ rather than $(\varphi, \tau) \in \mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^6$, we are still able to compute time efficient trajectories. Fig.4 shows a $(STPP)_2$ control strategy on the control domain Υ . The minimum time for this case is $t_{(STPP)_2, \Upsilon}^f \approx 19.69$ s. Note that this is faster than the time computed for the $(NLOP)$. This is due to the transformation of Υ through the Thruster Control Matrix (17-18). This transformation forces a restriction of $\mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{T}$ to a smaller control domain than allowed by the eight dimensional control. In order to compare this with Fig.3, we also display the control strategy

given by (φ, τ) . The $(STPP)_2$ trajectory is faster since the bounds on the thrusters are loosened, thus, the switchings are of greater magnitude. There is no yaw control (τ_{Ω_3}) applied along this trajectory since all the horizontal thrust is used for φ_{v_1} and φ_{v_2} . Despite the implementability of this trajectory, the unique and unbalanced thruster behavior in conjunction with the larger magnitude thrusts exaggerates errors here more than in the six dimensional $(STPP)$ strategy. Thus, we restrict ourselves to the control domain $\mathcal{F} \times \mathcal{T}$ to minimize the effect of the thrusters' dynamic differences, over which we have no control.

Fig.3: $(STPP)_2$ trajectory for $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$.

Fig.4: $(STPP)_2$ trajectory for $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$ and control domain Υ .

4.3 Experiments

Fig.5 shows the result of the implementation of a pure motion trajectory onto ODIN. The pure motion open loop control in surge, sway and heave is complemented with a feedback control on pitch, roll and yaw. This feedback on orientation compensates for the physical unbalancing of the thrusters. We represent the surge and sway evolution in the picture. The solid line is the actual trajectory realized by

ODIN. The dotted line represents the trajectory obtained using our theoretical model with the thrusts actually applied to ODIN during the test. In the theoretical model, we impose the yaw evolution to be that of experiment, otherwise the horizontal direction diverges very fast due to the sensitivity of the yaw (no restoring moment in yaw).

Fig.5: Comparison between the pure motion experimental surge, sway evolution and the theoretical evolution (with yaw correction) $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$.

Fig.5 validates our theoretical model. Despite many challenges in experimentation at the pool, we observed excellent behavior by ODIN. The difference in heading is the result of our inertial measurement unit's sensitivity to the surrounding magnetic field generated by pool's metal wall and the recirculation pumps. The small difference in surge and sway magnitude are due to factors such as underestimation of damping, imperfection in thruster modeling, pool current and the drag induced by the umbilical tether. The drag from the tether greatly depends on the tether location at the beginning of an experiment. This drag is difficult to take into account due to its variance. The current in the pool is dependent on location and is currently under investigation.

Fig.6: Comparison between $(STPP)_2$ experimental (plain) and theoretical (dashed) trajectories for $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$.

Fig.6 shows the experimental evolution of the implementation of the $(STPP)_2$ control strategy of Fig.3. For comparison, we display the theoretical behavior of the AUV for which the yaw evolution has been corrected similarly to the pure motion analysis. Note that in this experiment, we do not use any feedback

control. We obtained a very good response from ODIN. Its trajectory closely follows the theoretical one. However, we see the heave evolution is not reliable which comes from the drag and slight positive buoyancy of the tether. ODIN is only positively buoyant by only 3 N, thus any change in buoyancy will have a noticeable impact on the depth evolution. The surge and sway are also influenced by the drag of the tether and pool current which explains the theoretical over estimation of their evolutions. We see an overshooting in the pitch and roll experimental evolution. This is partially due to the un-modeled transient behavior of the thrusters.

5 Minimum Energy Consumption

5.1 Criterion

Since we are able to design practical time efficient trajectories, we now consider an energy criterion. Such a criterion is directly related to the physical model considered. Since AUV's are powered by internal batteries, we consider maximization of the life span of the batteries. The majority of the energy consumption of an AUV is the thrusters, while the on-board computer and sensors only play a marginal role. For ODIN, the thrusters are powered by a constant 24 V. We represent the consumption of one thruster by the current it pulls. Since the life span of a battery is given in Amps.hour, the criterion to consider for one thruster is the integral of the pulled current over the trajectory duration. Since ODIN has eight thrusters, the criterion will have the form

$$J = \min \sum_{i=1}^8 \int_0^{t^f} I(\gamma_i(t)) dt \quad (27)$$

where $\gamma_i(t)$ represents the thrust delivered by the i^{th} thruster and $I(\cdot)$ is a function which gives the pulled current with respect to a given thrust. Note that $I(\cdot)$ may be unique for each thruster. For simplicity, we do not consider such a refinement and assume $I(\cdot)$ equal for all thrusters.

For the criterion J , we have three choices for the final time; we fix it, we introduce it into the criterion as a weighted final time to minimize, or we leave it free. Since our mechanical system is dissipative, the third choice will still yield a finite final time. Also, there exists a finite final time with minimum energy consumption such any increase in time uses more energy to compensate the dissipative forces without gaining efficiency over the trajectory. Let us denote by t_{\min}^J the final time which yields the minimum consumption. Then any solution of the fixed final time minimum energy consumption with $t^f < t_{\min}^J$ will be a solution of the weighted minimum consumption and minimum time (the second choice) for a specific choice of weights.

We fix t^f as a multiple of the minimum time computed using the methods of Section 4: $t^f = c_{t^f} t_{\min}^J$ and $c_{t^f} > 1$. This problem does not have a solution for $c_{t^f} < 1$ and the solution for $c_{t^f} = 1$ is the minimum time solution.

Since criterion (27) explicitly involves the eight thrusters, the proper domain of controllability is the complete eight dimensional domain Υ . Indeed, if we insist on using the simplified six dimensional control φ and τ we will encounter an intricate criterion. Hence, we use the eight dimensional control γ , remembering that φ and τ are obtained from γ through the linear transformations (17-18).

Computing the (OCP) associated to (27) depends on the function $I(\cdot)$. From experimental measurements, we conclude that an accurate approximation of $I(\cdot)$ is a piecewise linear function:

$$I(\gamma) = \begin{cases} -0.192\gamma & = \alpha\gamma, \text{ if } \gamma \leq 0 \\ 0.408\gamma & = \beta\gamma, \text{ if } \gamma \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Notice that C^2 -functions are usually required for a numerical optimizer to converge. Moreover, our criterion is non differentiable at the minimum of the pulled current. This is a critical point which plays an important role in minimization. Applying the maximum principle to J gives a control strategy of bang-bang controls connected by singular arcs. Thus, we first smooth J . For this, we consider two fourth order

polynomials P_α, P_β (covering the negative and positive γ respectively). These polynomials form a C^2 -junction P_α/P_β at zero, I/P_α at a negative thrust (γ_α) and P_β/I at a positive thrust (γ_β). Let $\varepsilon > 0$ and $P_\alpha(0) = P_\beta(0) = \varepsilon$. This gives $P_\alpha(\gamma) = \alpha_4\gamma^4 + \alpha_3\gamma^3 + \varepsilon$ and $P_\beta(\gamma) = \beta_4\gamma^4 + \beta_3\gamma^3 + \varepsilon$ where

$$\begin{cases} \gamma_\alpha = 2\varepsilon/\alpha \\ \alpha_4 = -\alpha^4/(16\varepsilon^3) \\ \alpha_3 = \alpha^3/(4\varepsilon^2) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} \gamma_\beta = 2\varepsilon/\beta \\ \beta_4 = -\beta^4/(16\varepsilon^3) \\ \beta_3 = \beta^3/(4\varepsilon^2) \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

. We see that as ε tends to zero, I approaches the smoothed function. Let us call our smoothed current/force function I_ε and the corresponding smoothed criterion J_ε . Before attempting a numerical solution, we take a look at the extremal of the problem, as given by the Maximum Principle.

5.2 Extremal of Consumption

From the maximum principle, the structure of the eight dimensional extremal control is given by eight functions κ_i , $i = 1, \dots, 8$. These functions are a linear combination of the co-adjoint variables λ_{v_i, Ω_i} with linear coefficients coming from the Thruster Control Matrix (17-18). For example, the function κ_1 , describing the control γ_1 , is given by: $\kappa_1 = -\frac{\sqrt{2}\lambda_{v_1}}{2(m+M_f^1)} + \frac{\sqrt{2}\lambda_{v_2}}{2(m+M_f^2)} + \frac{0.4816\lambda_{v_3}}{I_{b_3}+J_f^{\Omega_3}}$. Note that the κ_i would be the switching functions if we were to consider the minimum time problem with γ as control.

The maximization of the Hamiltonian is similar for all control γ_i . If we denote by $\bar{\gamma}_i$ the control that maximize the Hamiltonian we get:

$$\bar{\gamma}_i = \begin{cases} \gamma_i^{\min} & , \text{ if } \kappa_i < \alpha \\ \in [\alpha_i, \gamma_\alpha] & , \text{ if } \kappa_i = \alpha \\ \text{unique root of } \kappa_i - P'_\alpha \in [\gamma_\alpha, 0] & , \text{ if } \kappa_i \in (\alpha, 0) \\ 0 & , \text{ if } \kappa_i = 0 \\ \text{unique root of } \kappa_i - P'_\beta \in [0, \gamma_\beta] & , \text{ if } \kappa_i \in (0, \beta) \\ \gamma_i^{\max} & , \text{ if } \kappa_i > \beta \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

. From this maximization, we see that if γ_β or γ_α are within the bounds of the control, then it is possible for an extremal to have discontinuity in the control. Since the κ_i are absolutely continuous functions, two constant control phases will be linked by a continuous control. However, if c_{f_i} is large enough, we can always expect the control to be continuous without ever being saturated.

5.3 Numerical results

We use the direct method (*NLOP*) to gain insight to such strategies. Multiple shooting methods are currently under investigation. Fully discretizing the (*OCP*) in state and control, we can again apply the *IpOpt* solver along with the modeling language *AMPL*. Despite the problem being significantly more sensitive, we can compute optimal solutions for a various collection of c_{f_i} . For $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$, we take $t_{\min}^f \approx 23.21$ s, the minimum time of the six dimensional controlled system. Before looking at specific control strategies, we consider the evolution of energy consumption with respect to c_{f_i} shown in Fig.7. In the right diagram of Fig.7, the criterion J is not minimized. So, it is not surprising to have an evolution depending on ε . As expected, J is not decreasing with c_{f_i} , but has a minimum for some final time $t_{\min}^{J_\varepsilon}$ which depends on ε . It is of interest to study the dependency of $t_{\min}^{J_\varepsilon}$ with respect to ε , as well as the dependency of $t_{\min}^{J_\varepsilon}$ with respect to the buoyancy of the vehicle and the position of C_B . However, we will not address these questions here.

For initial configuration at the origin and $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$, there are numerous minimum consumption strategies to consider. Nevertheless, a first choice is one that approximately corresponds to $t_{\min}^{J_\varepsilon}$. Fig.8 shows the thrust evolution and trajectory corresponding to $\varepsilon = 0.5$ and $c_{f_i} = 2$.

In Fig.8, we display the controls φ and τ rather than γ since they are more meaningful, even though they are not used in the optimization process. Compare this trajectory to the minimum time trajectory shown

Fig.7: Smoothed function I_ϵ (left) and evolution of the consumption J w.r.t. c_{t^f} for $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$ and $\epsilon = 0.5, 0.4$ or 0.3 (right)

Fig.8: Minimum consumption control strategy and trajectory for $\eta_f = (5, 4, 1, 0, 0, 0)$, $t^f = 46.42$ s and $\epsilon = 0.5$.

in Fig.2. The first obvious difference is the magnitude of the control. For the minimum consumption control strategy, there is minimal actuator saturation, while for the minimum time strategy actuators are saturated for the entire motion.

As is, the minimum energy consumption strategies will be very hard to implement for two main reasons. First, the continuous evolution of the control strategy is not implementable on a real vehicle, and even a discretization would require the storage of impractical amounts of data. Secondly, considering low magnitude thrusts will exaggerate the ODIN's sensitivity to the unmodeled external forces such a tether drag and pool current. For these reasons it would be interesting to adapt the (STPP) method to the energy consumption problem and consider final times which are closer to the minimum time. This will ensure a greater thrust magnitude while still saving energy.

It is reasonable that an adaptation of (*STPP*) is feasible. Indeed extremal strategies will contain constant thrust arcs of maximum and zero magnitude by the maximum principle applied to J . These strategies, will be easier to implement than continuous evolutions provided we take precautions to smooth the transitions between thrust arcs.

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Mesh Size Influence in a CFD Code on Resistance Evaluation of a Motor Yacht

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Abstract

The commercial CFD solver Fluent is applied to a motor yacht and validated against model basin tests. The focus of the investigation is to obtain knowledge about the influence of mesh size on results to allow trade-offs between engineering effort and quality of results in similar CFD analyses. In taking care with the mesh generation, good results can be obtained at lower expense than with the initial mesh.

1. Introduction

The purpose of the study was to investigate the capability of solving the problems of viscous resistance around a full-scale model of hull using commercial CFD software and common hardware. The goal was to compare the results obtained by the software with the tank test results that had been validated by the sea trial of the complete ship to see if the software could render similar results. From the results of the tank test, we took the resistance prediction for the ship, considering these predicted values as the “target” value for comparison with the various CFD results. The results of the tank test cannot be used for a direct comparison with CFD results because they were obtained with different theories (ITTC '57 and ITTC '78 vs k- ϵ models, RANS etc.). Comparing the results from the CFD simulations of the various mesh densities with each other is of particular interest in order to define the influence of the definition of the mesh on the final results.

2. Modelization of the hull surface

The hull surface was modeled in full scale (42 m) using a software program developed for creating the body plan of ships, Figs.1 and 2. Using NURBS theory and working on the surface to the point that the fairing was good enough to be used for the nesting drawings, the authors obtained the final body plan. This body plan was designed only considering the construction needs and without adopting any simplification related to the future use of CFD. The IGES file obtained by the software was used for:

- CAM machine for the creation of the hull in the Tank test
- CAD drawings for the construction of the ship
- Mesh creation for CFD simulation.

The main data of the hull are: $L_{wl} = 40$ m, $B_{wl} = 8.20$ m, Draft $T = 2.41$ m, displacement = 305 t. The hull surface was cut to a height of 249 cm from the base line in order to realize the various meshes and to simulate the viscous resistance.

2. Organization of the work according to the tank tests available.

According to the tank test it was obvious that the frictional resistance was considerable in a range of speed from 10 to 13 knots. For higher speed (up to the maximum speed 16.5 knots), the frictional resistance decreased in importance due to the rising of the other components of the resistance and the trim of the ship was significantly changing. The change in the trim was effecting the wet surface and the condition of the hull, and this prevented obtaining valid results.

Fig.1: Hull rear view

Fig.2: Hull front view

We performed a first simulation using a mesh of about 1500000 elements, corresponding to a volume of the following dimensions:

Length = 140 m
B = 13.5
Height = 19.5

The volume is symmetric and the calculations have been carried out using only half of the volume in order to save computing time. This first set of calculations showed a difference of about 5% between the data of resistance measured in the tank with the ITTC '78 formula and adapted to the real ship. We then decided to investigate different sizes of meshes with the same dimensions of the volume meshed (140 x 13.5 x 19 m). Three other different meshes have been utilized: 250000 elements, 500000 elements, and 1000000.

Fig.3: Volume meshed for calculation

Fig.4: Detail of mesh of 1.5 million elements

Fig.5: Complete mesh of hull with 1.5 million elements

Fig.6: Complete mesh on hull with 250000 elements

Fig.7: Bow detail 1.5 million elements (left)and 250000 elements (right)

3. Model and mesh creation and setting for calculation

The four different meshes have been created by changing the size of the elements directly on the hull surface. The first mesh, consisting of 1500000 elements, was composed by tetrahedral and esahedral elements of about 90 mm of size on the hull and increasing their size with the distance from the hull. The other meshes (1000000 elements, 500000 elements, and 250000 elements) had the size of the elements tetrahedral on the hull increased to about 130 mm, 200 mm, 400 mm respectively with the same law of growth related to the distance from the hull. The commercial CFD FLUENT was used, employing the k- ϵ turbulence model and single precision.

3.1 The Importance of Mesh Convergence

We focussed on the influence of mesh size on accuracy, i.e. cell spacing rather than influence of mismatches in the mesh. We found that investigations on this influence is rarely documented. The formal method of establishing mesh convergence requires a curve of a critical result parameter in a specific location to be plotted against some measure of mesh density. From a physical point of view then, it should be possible to test the convergence of a model by refining the mesh only in the regions of interest and retain the unrefined (and probably not yet converged) mesh elsewhere.

CFD codes (like Fluent) have been developed for compressible and incompressible Euler and Navier-Stokes equations. Reaching the steady-state solution in each analysis cycle in a reasonable

amount of time is crucial for design optimization. The main goal in such a complicated CFD analysis must be focused on minimizing the time to convergence without compromising scalability by means of appropriate mesh algorithms. The convergence rate will vary with conditioning, as determined by Mach and Reynolds numbers, and the correspondingly induced mesh adaptivity.

Furthermore, robustness becomes more of an issue in problems admitting shocks or using turbulence models. In order to assess the importance in meshing and especially the importance of the number of elements, different models have been developed paying particular attention to maintain the standard minimal value to define a good mesh.

In particular, warpage, aspect ratio and skew have been constrained under respectively: 5, 5, and 70%. The number of iterations to reach the convergence increase proportionally to the number of elements (except for the case of 1000000 elements at 10 knots). In particular, four different meshes have been implemented respectively simulating the model with 1500000, 1000000, 500000 and 250000 elements.

Elements	Elements effectively	N knots	N cells on hull	Size cells on hull [cm]	N° iterations	Speed [knots]
1500000	1466008	260877	27420	9	15556	10
1500000	1466008	260877	27420	9	15234	12
1500000	1466008	260877	27420	9	10300	13
1000000	1110538	198614	19540	13	33000	10
1000000	1110538	198614	19540	13	34659	12
1000000	1110538	198614	19540	13	18088	13
500000	544145	99133	7430	20	18990	10
500000	544145	99133	7430	20	19768	12
500000	544145	99133	7430	20	20704	13
250000	250089	47002	2112	40	8106	10
250000	250089	47002	2112	40	12702	12
250000	250089	47002	2112	40	12327	13

4. Analysis of the results

Each set of calculations has been performed maintaining the same settings while changing only the speed of the fluid and the mesh. The hardware used for the calculations is a PC with a Dual Core Intel processors, 2.8 GhZ , 4 Gb of RAM and Windows XP pro 64 bit. Each set of calculations was run until the residuals of the elements of speed, k and ϵ , were at a statistically significant level of less then 0.00001, even if in some applications the software stated results were statistically significant at the 0.001 level. Additionally, an analysis of the speed and turbulence field around the hull, for an average value of each residual of 0.0001 showed that the situation was not yet applicable to “real world” variables, so it was decided to go ahead with the calculations until the graph of the residual values were stabilized at 10^{-5} , Fig.8.

For the value of the residuals of 10^{-3} (the default value of the software to end calculations), the resistance force is still more than double that of the final value at the end of the calculations. The calculations were considered “concluded” only when the curve of the residuals was basically flat, showing an outcome that is almost constant. Once we solved the problem of the residuals and the convergence of the solutions, a complete set of calculations was constructed.

Fig.8: Residuals for calculation at 12 knots

The total time of computing was as follows:

Speed 10 knots	N of elements	Effective number	Cells on the hull	Time
	1500000	1466008	27420	45.0 h
	1000000	1110538	19540	73.0 h
	500000	544145	7430	21.1 h
	250000	250089	2112	4.5 h
Speed 12 knots	N of elements	Effective number	Cells on the hull	Time
	1500000	1466008	27420	56.0 h
	1000000	1110538	19540	71.5 h
	500000	544145	7430	22.0 h
	250000	250089	2112	5.0 h
Speed 13 knots	N of elements	Effective number	Cells on the hull	Time
	1500000	1466008	27420	53.5 h
	1000000	1110538	19540	72.0 h
	500000	544145	7430	20.7 h
	250000	250089	2112	5.5 h

At the end of each set of calculation it was possible to obtain the data of viscous resistance of the ship.

Ship without appendages, resistance data (frictional resistance only)

Speed (knots)	R theoretical	R CFD 1500000 el.	R CFD 1000000 el.	R CFD 500000 el.	R CFD 250000 el.
10	22.8 kN	24.65 kN	19.840 kN	23.85	21.58 kN
12	27.6 kN	31.5 kN	26.512 kN	34.3	30.51 kN
13	42.7 kN	41 kN	30.263 kN	39.388	36.03 kN

5. Conclusions

The final data calculations yielded interesting conclusions. The results obtained with a largely simplified mesh (250000 elements) do not differ significantly from the optimum results of the densest mesh (1500000 elements). The most significant difference in terms of predicted resistance versus actual resistance was related to the mesh of 1000000 elements at a speed of 13 knots (about 30 kN “CFD” versus 41 “tank test”) even though the total time of computation was about 70 hours instead of 55 hours as was utilized for the 1500000 cell mesh. However, even for meshes with a relatively “poor” density, with a reasonable amount of computational time and processor power, the results are quite similar to the results predicted with the tank test. The difference in the results among CFD, tank tests and mesh density becomes greater at the increasing of the Froude number, but for a slow hull ($F_n < 0.2$ approximately) it seems possible to obtain valid results.

Fig.9: Velocity contours at 10 knots and 1.5 million of cells

Fig.10: Velocity contours at 10 knots and 1 million of cells

Fig.11: Velocity contours at 10 knots and 500000 cells

Fig. 12 - Velocity contours at 10 knots and 250000 cells

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A New Approach to Integration of CAD and CFD for Naval Architects

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Abstract

The paper describes the new integration environment FRIENDSHIP-Framework combining CAD and CFD, allowing rapid hydrodynamic evaluation in ship design. The paper will explain the underlying ideas of the new system and will provide an overview of its functionality.

1. Introduction

Mr. A knows the CAD (computer aided design) system available in his design environment by heart and produces hull forms, appendages, rudders and other functional surfaces with great skill and know-how. Dr. B is a CFD (computational fluid dynamics) expert who sets up and runs the CFD system of choice with aptitude and long-time experience. Ms. C is in charge of the current new building and needs to know if the performance of the design can still be improved by a few per cent to meet the customer's expectations – she might have to win the contract yet or cares to avoid falling short of earlier promises.

Now, Mr. A already is fully involved in another project and hardly finds the time to squeeze in any changes let alone realize hull form modifications of suitable quality in a short period of time. Dr. B just left for a business trip and probably struggles with his jet lag. Dr. D might actually be able to help since she is a CFD expert, too. However, she has not worked with the CFD code needed for the specific investigation. She would certainly be able to interpret the CFD results and use them for comparison with the previous baseline but it would take her quite some time to run the new computations as there are several files to be touched and preparations to be made.

One week later: The other design that Mr. A was busy with when he was asked to assist in the new building project now is ready for detailed studies. It is a complicated situation in which many constraints need to be observed, a few of which require some computational effort while others are rather simple. Nevertheless, taking care of all of them at once is tricky and any change introduced to the neatly balanced baseline might cause havoc. Two alternatives are finally ready for CFD based investigations. Unfortunately, both fall short of the team's ambitious hopes. Well, it has been a rather new hull concept after all. Dr. B has returned from abroad and now proposes two changes to the shape. Mr. A will bring them about but it takes precious time before the next CFD runs can be started.

Ship design is a complicated matter. Not only because ships constitute complex systems but also because there are multi-level relationships and dependencies – between people, tools, organizations etc. The complexity of ships will continue to increase in order to meet market requirements and so will specialization and, hence, division of labor. Therefore, most companies have long invested in team building, appreciating that a team is more than just a group of people. The same holds for tighter integration of CAD and CFD: The outcome of the synthesized effort is more than the sum of its individual parts. Having realized this and knowing the design scenarios described above from both own experience and direct consultancy, FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS has introduced a new CAE (Computer Aided Engineering) environment to allow for better use of CAD and CFD. The system was called FRIENDSHIP-Framework to acknowledge the fact that, firstly, there are established codes in the market which need to be utilized rather than replaced and that, secondly, design teams have their individual preferences and mode of operation. The system provides views on and access to the various aspects of interest and aims at supporting the hydrodynamic design process, Fig. 1.

The new approach to integration of CAD and CFD will be discussed in the sections to come. Light will be cast on (i) closer communication along with direct and non-redundant access to common data,

(ii) geometric modeling as a key functionality to produce any non-virtual product and (iii) management and assessment of variants and constraints. The intention is to explain how these features lead to faster turn-around time, increased security of correct operation and, hence, higher confidence in decision making.

Fig.1: Various data of interest to a design team

2. Basics

2.1 Integration

A typical situation encountered at many shipyards, model basins and consultancies is shown in Fig.2. The systems stand alone but connections are established via files. Geometry is often given as simple offsets, iges files or files in legacy formats. Typically, in order to undertake an investigation, geometry is produced interactively within a CAD system. It is then exported and, often, subsequently converted before pre-processing for CFD. The latter steps differ from tool to tool so that several conversions and preparations might be needed for the same geometry. Finally, the numerical simulations are run and the results get analyzed. Commonly, pre- and post-processing (Pre and Post in Fig.2) require specific tools for grid-generation and scientific visualization, respectively. For any changes the sequence needs to be repeated in part or in total. In the end, spread-sheets and word processing etc. are used to submit an intelligible report.

Integration tries to bring the majority of these steps closer together even though some aspects might best be left to dedicated tools. In other words: Some functionality is provided, some tools are replaced, several systems are plugged-in while others are just launched. Fig.3 shows the integration of CAD, CFD and optimization as adopted for the FRIENDSHIP-Framework. The aim has been to take into account existing codes rather than to supply the maritime community with a new monolithic system.

Fig.3 shows that different geometric modeling approaches have been readily considered within the FRIENDSHIP-Framework, see Section 2.2 for more details. The system also provides optimization tools (Opt.) which are used as design engines to drive investigations in addition to manual work. Data

and objects are managed consistently and are made accessible at all stages. CFD tools are plugged in fully (CFD 1) or partially (CFD 2 with Post 2). For wave resistance simulations, for example, two codes are already supported: *SHIPFLOW* by Flowtech and *v-Shallo* by HSVA.

Fig.3 is also meant to illustrate that integration constitutes an important step toward simultaneous engineering. Subsequent stages are brought closer together in both time and content. This leads to shortened turn-around times per variant and gains in investigative complexity.

Fig.2: Typical as-is state

Fig.3: Integration of CAD, CFD and optimization

2.2 Geometric modeling

Taking a techno-economic perspective engineering rarely is decoupled from the harsh restrictions imposed by money and time. Therefore, when undertaking a design campaign the team not only has to aim at an excellent product but also needs to bare in mind the available resources. The outcome might not necessarily be perfect but it ought to be best under the given circumstances.

Consequently, the practicing engineer needs to have a tool kit that offers the right means for the specific task to perform. In geometric modeling the available techniques are rather diverse but they draw their right to exist from the situations in which they serve their purpose. Possible criteria by which to compare different techniques of geometric modeling are as follows (definitions are extracted from <http://en.wikipedia.org>):

- Flexibility – the ability to adapt to different circumstances, here to cope with any possible shape.
- Know-how – the procedural knowledge of how to perform a specific task, here for instance to change geometry.
- Effectiveness – the capability of producing a desired effect, here quality of the design, i.e., the success in achieving a given goal independent of the resources spent (“doing the right thing”).
- Cost – the value of resources that have been used up to produce something.
- Efficiency – the swiftness with which information, here geometry, is generated and changed (“getting things done”).

Geometric modeling techniques can be classified in many different ways (boundary representation vs. constructive solid geometry, discrete vs. transfinite data, regular vs. irregular topology etc.). Here a rather simple classification is used for which details and examples are presented in *Harries et al. (2004)*:

- Conventional modeling (conv. CAD) – shapes are defined by data items that are independent of each other and do not bear any task specific information, e.g. a polyhedron of vertices that define a B-spline surface.
- Partially parametric modeling (par. par. CAD) – changes to the geometry are defined by means of parameters, i.e., a set of modifiers associated with the design task at hand, while original geometry is utilized as-is from any suitable modeling process.
- Fully parametric modeling (ful. par. CAD) – the entire geometry is defined by parameters, i.e., task specific descriptors which capture the essence of the product to be generated or varied.

Fig.4: Qualitative assessment of available geometric modeling techniques

With regard to this classification efficiency seems to be the most prominent feature and is used as abscissa for comparison while the other criteria appear as ordinates in Fig.4. The assessment is both qualitative and subjective and is meant to serve as a guideline when selecting the appropriate technique for a concrete task to perform. Fully parametric techniques usually are very efficient but they lack flexibility. Furthermore, for complex models they require quite a bit of know-how. They yield high effectiveness and low cost per high-quality variant even though the initial investment to develop a fully parametric model is non-negligible. Conventional techniques provide highest flexibility (it simply does not matter if it is an aircraft or a SWATH you want to model). Nevertheless, they require considerable mathematical insight and even more system specific know-how. High-quality changes with regard to fairness and other constraints usually are expensive. This is because concerted changes of many data items are needed and this usually requires a lot of interactive work. Partially parametric models somewhat fall in-between fully parametric and conventional techniques. Their strong point is that they call for less know-how and, hence, are relatively ease to apply. In addition, their cost per variant is rather competitive.

2.3 Partially parametric modeling

While conventional modeling is well known, an introduction to partially parametric modeling is deemed worthwhile. Examples of fully parametric modeling are reported in *Harries et al. (2006)*, *Harries (2006)*, *Birk and Harries (2000)*, www.FRIENDSHIP-SYSTEMS.com. Established techniques of partially parametric modeling are merging, e.g. *Harries et al. (2004)*, box deformation, e.g. *Hoekstra and Raven (2003)*, and added patch perturbation, e.g. *Peri et al. (2001)*. Another method of partially parametric modeling is a Cartesian shift, i.e., a displacement of all point data by Δx , Δy and/or Δz as functions of their initial positions.

Fig.5 shows a propeller as imported to the FRIENDSHIP-Framework via an iges file. The geometry is represented as a patch work of B-spline surfaces built up with a conventional CAD system. Partially parametric changes to the initial design can be easily introduced via a Cartesian shift as depicted (compare dark-red blade to light-grey blade).

A nice function for Cartesian shift is a *cos*-square function of amplitude A and radius r . The Cartesian shift is placed at some arbitrary point in space. At this point the change to the original geometry is largest and corresponds to A . Points in the surrounding also get shifted, the magnitude of displacement, however, falls off with the Euclidian distance to the source. Beyond radius r no more changes are introduced and the geometry remains as-is. Fig.5 nicely shows the effect of a single Cartesian shift on the tip of a skewed propeller. Another example is found in Fig.12 in which various sources act together on the offsets of a container carrier.

Fig.5: Partially parametric model to modify propeller

Fig.6 depicts the effect of a single *cos*-square function on a plane surface lying at $z = 0$. For simplicity the Cartesian shift is placed in the center of the plane. The series of pictures illustrate the effect of increasing the radius of influence r while keeping the amplitude A constant. The top picture nicely shows the *cos*-square function itself while the other pictures give good impressions on the subtleness with which the original surface might be modified.

Note that another example for a Cartesian shift is the well-known swinging of sections as introduced by *Lackenby (1950)*. Here the shift function is more complex, namely Δx as a function of longitudinal position x , which is traditionally considered to be a quadratic polynomial for fore- and aftbody, respectively. The shift function is computed to introduce changes in volume, center of buoyancy and parallel midship. This means that the actual Cartesian shift is dependent of the original geometry.

Fig.6: Illustration of Cartesian shift in z -direction

3. Software development and architecture

For the development of the FRIENDSHIP-Framework a fully object oriented approach was taken. The many advantages this brings about will be briefly discussed from both an information technology and a practical point of view.

Over the last two decades design methods, development toolkits and utilities have become available that allow even smaller companies to address niche markets with software products comparable to what one would have expected from large companies in the past. The look-and-feel of a state-of-the-art CAD program can nowadays be accomplished economically by utilizing development toolkits for the design of graphical user interfaces (GUI). Since the FRIENDSHIP-Framework targets both Linux and Microsoft Windows it was decided to take full advantage of the cross-platform application development toolkit Qt, e.g. www.Trolltech.com. However, neither the functionality nor the usability of a CAE program depend solely on nice widgets and fancy rendering but, naturally, builds primarily on the objects available to describe the problem at hand along with the handles for control. Response time also is an important issue for geometric modeling which calls for a sophisticated update mechanism.

The specification for the FRIENDSHIP-Framework was established from a thorough analysis and a number of design patterns were finally identified as crucial:

- Commands to facilitate the command line control, ability to script etc.,
- Observers to realize efficient lazy fetching and
- Prototypes to ease cut and paste mechanisms and to cope with unresolved relations.

It was decided to follow the approach of Model-View-Controller (MVC) which separates the modeling of the domain, the presentation and the actions into three separate classes, *Burbeck (1992)*. Fig.7 points out the structural relationship of ‘model’, ‘view’ and ‘controller’:

- Model – it manages the behavior and data of the objects, responds to requests for information about their state (usually from a view), and responds to instructions to change state (usually from the controller).
- View – it manages the display of information, each of its own kind.
- Controller – it interprets the mouse and keyboard inputs from the user, informing the ‘model’ and/or the ‘view’ to change as appropriate.

Fig.7: Relationship of ‘model’, ‘view’ and ‘controller’

A major part of the ‘model’ consists of geometric entities like points, curves and surfaces as known from conventional modeling, see ‘conv. CAD’ in Fig.3. In addition, there are complex features such as foils and motion prediction points so as to further ease the work flow in complex design processes, *Wetterling and Richardt (2006)*.

In order to facilitate parametric modeling and CFD analysis, the FRIENDSHIP-Framework offers configurations for parametric shape definition and CFD computations. Finally, it allows the definition of design variables and constraints as needed for variation studies and optimizations.

While the ‘model’ encapsulates the attributes of the data, every ‘view’ gives a special representation of these data. Fig.8 shows a reduced representation of a B-spline curve and three associated views on the curve. The actual curve data only contains point information – aside from degree and knot vector. The different *views* offer different options to edit and visualize the given information, every ‘view’ being developed with focus on a specific working stage or modeling technique.

Fig.8: One-to-n relation ‘model’-‘view’

The control points of the curve can be interactively moved in the GL window (see upper left part in Fig.8). Some properties of the entire curve, though, can be addressed more comfortably by selecting the curve in the tree view (upper right part in Fig.8). For instance, changing the position of all vertices can be brought about in a single step by translation or mirroring. The object editor (upper middle part in Fig.8), meanwhile, nicely allows editing scopes, colors, rendering options and the like.

Modifications on the model can also be achieved through the ‘controller’, Fig.7. A command controller registers all commands available and offers command and object name completion as well as lists of function arguments. The command controller only accepts input which matches the expected type. While this object oriented approach ensures type safety it also adds comfort of selection when choosing arguments.

Fig.9 shows the object editor view of a design engine during the allocation of design variables to be applied in an optimization. Only those objects are displayed for insertion that, first of all, fit the purpose – here to become the free variables for a deterministic search strategy – and that, secondly, have not been selected yet.

Fig.9: Object editor for design engine to set up an optimization

4. Examples

In order to illustrate a typical application of the FRIENDSHIP-Framework representative steps of a small optimization study are presented. The work flow comprises

- Preparation of geometry
- Selection and set up of a suitable parametric model
- Configuration of the numerical simulation
- Choice of optimization strategy
- Assessment of results

As elaborated above the baseline geometry might stem from another CAD system and may be forwarded as a mathematically closed surface representation, usually in iges format, but may also be available as plain offset data. Naturally, since the FRIENDSHIP-Framework features full CAD functionality the initial shape might as well have been generated directly within the system (no import then).

Let us assume that offset data had already been pre-processed with a certain CFD application in mind, for instance SHIPFLOW as it is a well-known and widely applied system for simulating calm-water hydrodynamics. A common predicament then is to prepare the offset data for the panel generator (XMESH) before actually starting a non-linear potential flow computation. Offset data needs to be given in an offset file of specific syntax and semantics. While the FRIENDSHIP-Framework readily

allows the viewing of the offset data it also supports the user with key functionality to manipulate data sets. Typical operations applicable to points, sections and groups are

- Reordering
- Concatenating
- Thinning out
- Clipping
- Repositioning (repair)
- Deleting and adding

Fig.10: Offset data as imported from a SHIPFLOW offset file

Fig.11: Clipping and thinning out of offset data

Typical interactive work performed is displayed in Figs.10 and 11. The snap-shots show the offset data right after the import and after some preparations, respectively.

The next step in undertaking an optimization is to select a suitable parametric model to evoke changes to the geometry. Since here the baseline has been made available as offset data only – without any underlying parametric definition at this stage – a partially parametric model comes as a natural choice and makes a reasonable starting point. Using the *cos*-square Cartesian shift introduced in Section 2 the design team places several of these modifiers in the forebody of the hull. Due to some (hypothetical) restrictions imposed earlier in the design process, changes shall be acceptable from just aft of the forward perpendicular up to the forward shoulder well ahead of the maximum section. Fig.12 depicts the concerted changes brought about by six Cartesian shifts. Note that the individual shifts are superimposed before actually computing the displacements in *y*-direction.

Fig.12: Partially parametric model to modify selected region in forebody of a container carrier

Next, the numerical simulation has to be configured. The FRIENDSHIP-Framework supports a number of plugged-in CFD codes, *Wetterling and Richardt (2006)*. For SHIPFLOW an import of existing command files is available. Alternatively, a new command file can be easily set up by choosing commands in a context specific manner. Commands are ordered according to the modules they belong to (XMESH, XPAN, XBOUND etc.) and can be interactively introduced or discarded as suitable. Execution of the CFD code is triggered from the FRIENDSHIP-Framework, Fig.13. Moreover, there is the necessary parsing functionality to extract the data computed in the simulation as required for further design assessment.

Optimization strategies comprise many different techniques and algorithms and range from ensemble investigations via Design-of-Experiments to deterministic and stochastic methods, e.g. *Birk and Harries (2003)* for a thorough discussion. A variety of strategies is available in the FRIENDSHIP-Framework and the set up of an optimization study is rather straight-forward, Fig.9. Typically, the hydrodynamic fine tuning of a ship hull form requires that a number of constraints be observed and, ultimately, fulfilled (or relaxed). Many of these constraints are related to geometry and hydrostatics and, consequently, the determination of buoyancy forces has been incorporated in the system, too.

Fig.13: Repeated execution of CFD code as triggered by the integration platform

Fig.14: Monitoring of variants, free variables, objectives and constraints

Quite often the design team has to formulate inequality constraints with respect to initial stability and capacity. The example features two constraints as being representative, one on KM the other on change of displacement volume, see table view in Fig.13. The FRIENDSHIP-Framework monitors constraints and gives intuitive feedback if constraint are fulfilled, violated or within a certain warning zone close to becoming active. Fig.14 is a snap-shot from a deterministic optimization study. When constraints are not fulfilled the design is marked as failed. While an optimization is in progress the history and the intermediate results can be viewed and accessed. Fig.14 presents a table view in which the variants were sorted with respect to wave resistance. Other important views on the optimization data are diagrams, for instance the optimization history, and flow visualizations as depicted in Fig.1.

5. Outlook

The integration of CAD and CFD naturally allows many different scenarios of application. The small example of Section 4 is representative of day-to-day design work. It also serves to underline the ease with which to actually run a design task once the user is relieved from the busy work of writing, placing and interpreting files and their content correctly.

Fig.15: Assessment of selected variant at different operating conditions and comparison to baseline

Further typical use cases of the new CAD-CFD integration environment are ensemble investigations in which several speed and trim-draft situations are studied, possibly for different design alternatives, as illustrated in Fig.15. Variants of a vessel were studied at different operating conditions and confronted to identify the best compromise. More advanced applications are design space exploration and full-fledged optimizations to identify design variants with the best possible hydrodynamic performance, not only for calm-water resistance but also for energy consumption, seakeeping and many other aspects. This then constitutes a multi-objective problem for which Pareto-optimal solutions need to be found.

6. Conclusion

The CAD-CFD integration environment FRIENDSHIP-Framework supports the investigation of functional surfaces such as hull forms, propellers and appendages. The system was developed based on experience gained in parametric modeling, numerical simulation and formal optimization. It is intended to assist design teams at model basins, consultancies and shipyards, as well as research and teaching at universities. Main features of the system are

- Variation of hundreds of shapes via partially parametric modeling on data being imported from offsets, panel meshes and iges files.
- Generation and variation of shapes via fully parametric modeling using type specific definitions.
- Plug-in of CFD tools such as SHIPFLOW and v-Shallo for design assessments such as non-linear potential flow codes for wave resistance simulation.
- Incorporated post-processing, comparison and reporting of project data in tables, figures and 3d-plots.
- Integrated design engines for systematic exploration (Design-of-Experiment) as well as deterministic (search strategies) and stochastic (multi-objective algorithms) exploitation.

The examples given illustrate some of the work that can be smoothly performed by the practicing naval architect at the various design stages.

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Decision Support Systems for Oil Spill Response

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Abstract

A state-of-the-art review reveals that current methodologies for decision support systems for oil spill response are insufficient. Requirements for a future decision support system are outlined, involving fine-scale modelling of local hydrodynamic processes, detailed modelling of weathering processes of the oil, quantitative estimation of in-situ and cumulative eco-toxicological impacts, and assessment of environmental economic and socio-economic costs.

1. Introduction

Assessment tools for estimation of impacts of an oil spill on the local environment and socio-economy constitute a vital element in contingency and oil spill response planning. The development of GIS has spawned the emergence of sophisticated Decision Support Systems (DSS), which are now replacing sensitivity maps to provide national response authorities with quick and effective means of determining marine and coastal areas of environmental, economic and strategic sensitivity that could be impacted in the event of oil pollution incidents, and provide valuable resource and logistical information for combating the pollution. The SPILL RESPONSE EXPERIENCE COORDINATION ACTION (SPREEX 2005-07, <http://www.spreeex.net/>) funded as a Coordinated Action by the European Commission intends to assemble existing experience from oil spill response, and is aiming at identifying research needs to achieve a fast and effective response during future oil spills. The working group dealing with research related to 'Environmental impact of spills and its costs' has been analysing the state-of-the-art in relation to decision support systems for oil spill response and has identified several research gaps.

2. Background

The concept of sensitivity mapping using an Environmental Sensitivity Index (ESI) was developed in the 1970s to provide oil spill response coordinators with a means of evaluating a shoreline's sensitivity to oil spill damage, *Gundlach and Hayes (1978)*, and it is now widely used in different countries. Sensitivity mapping has provided various approaches and spawned computerized versions, of which some have been embedded in oil spill response dedicated GIS since the 1980'es. However, methodologies for the integrated assessment of environmental and socio-economic impacts of oil spills as a means for prioritisation of pollution response actions have only recently developed. This development has been spawned by the development of sophisticated decision support systems (DSS) implemented in GIS, and has provided national response authorities with quick and effective means of determining marine and coastal areas of environmental, economic and strategic sensitivity that could be impacted in the event of oil pollution incidents, and has also provided valuable resource and logistical information for combating the pollution. Today, a number of countries, including US, Australia, Norway, Japan, Norway, Greenland and Ghana have developed integrated risk assessments techniques as a key tool in their national contingency planning. Although the technology available today allows for determination of the environmental and socio-economic impacts of oil spills in a large number of oil pollution scenarios, most techniques available make little use of the ability for DSS technology to converge four highly different operational services:

1. fine-scale modelling of local hydrodynamic processes
2. detailed modelling of weathering processes of the oil
3. quantitative estimation of in-situ and cumulative eco-toxicological impacts
4. assessment of environmental economic and socio-economic costs.

Without exception, all existing contingency planning DSS tools are constrained on one or several of

these main components. As a result, the need for developing specifications for an expert-driven 'all-in-one' DSS response tool has been stressed by e.g. the International Salvage Union, *Timmermans (2004)*. The optimal Casualty Risk Assessment Model should take account of all variables, including ship type and size, cargo type and characteristics, vessel damage, proximity to the coast, the environmental and economic assets under threat, the 'worst case' outcome, tug availability and the weather outlook. It is true that no DSS can accommodate the complex political considerations which will influence decision-making when catastrophic pollutions happen. Yet, this fact of life does nothing to detract from the inherent value of a ready-made template for casualty risk assessment. This report investigates the state-of-the-art of existing contingency planning DSS tools and assesses the gap between these tools and an expert-driven 'all-in-one' DSS response tool.

3. Regulations and standards

No EU regulations or standard methodologies for the integrated assessment of environmental and socio-economic impacts of oil spills are currently in force in Europe. Nevertheless there are several related initiatives, both at EU level and at national level. The most relevant is the proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on enhancing ship and port facility security (Brussels, 2.5.2003 COM (2003) 229 final 2003/0089 (COD)) as well as the CLC 92 and FC 92 conventions for tanker spills as well as the coming Bunkers and HNS Conventions with respect to admissibility of damage from mathematical models.

Several national contingency plans have set standards for environmental risk analysis and oil spill contingency assessment related to governmental oil spill preparedness. As an example, the Norwegian Pollution Control Authority (SFT) has prepared an "Oil Spill Contingency and Risk based Governmental Contingency planning", *Nerland, (2001)*, in which the use of models and tools for contingency planning is described in detail.

Optimisation of some components of a full oil combat DSS system is ongoing within most of the institutes offering oil spill impact assessment software, and digital contingency plans are being developed for several oil transport and production regions in the world. However, no initiatives are currently taken to integrate all components into an expert-driven DSS technology neither at national nor at the European level.

Limitations with respect to the admissibility for environmental (and economical) damage may be foreseen if estimated by advanced modelling tools, under the existing CLC 92 and FC 92 conventions for tanker spills as well as under the coming Bunkers and HNS Conventions. The IOPC Fund 'Claims Manual' provides guidance regarding admissibility of costs, <http://www.iopcfund.org/regs.htm#>, and all claims are subject to the test of 'reasonableness'. 'Reasonableness' is not very precisely defined, yet this could be a restriction of the use of DSS systems for forecasting and evaluating ecological and economical damage following an oil spill.

4. Current Oil Spill Response DSS applications

Operational risk assessment methods are generally developed as existing industry standard or in-house GIS applications with or without links to modelling of oil drift and impact assessments. In cases like BMT's OSIS, SINTEF's OSCAR and ASA's SIMAP the drift and weathering processes of the oil are integrated with information on sensitive environmental and socioeconomic areas and prioritised actions are offered by the DSS system, albeit often at variable degree of accuracy and resolution, and not always on the basis of expert-driven functions.

However, most operational risk assessment tools used are based on non-dynamic and simple visualisations and GIS-overlay techniques. The GIS used provides a consistent view of the information throughout the spill operations and provides a means for managing a wide range of data from a variety of sources. It gives response managers a fast and effective tool for assessing the incidents for answering the specific and changing needs of a response. It also provides a means for

briefing spill response personnel, the media and the public to provide an up-to-date status and history of the response activities logged.

A GIS can be used for managing information related to pre-spill contingency planning, during a spill and post-spill damage assessment. A well-developed GIS can be used for a variety of purposes including:

- Preparing site/regional contingency plan maps
- Helping to determine protection plans for shorelines
- Assessing habitats affected or likely to be affected by the spill
- Determining species likely to be impacted by marine pollution
- Measuring affected shorelines
- Visual presentation of response strategies and clean up operations
- Management of environmental monitoring data
- Calculating area of slicks from GPS reading or remotely sensed data
- Keeping an historic record of equipment locations and deployment

In the US and Canada, GIS-based spill response systems have been successfully linked to Incident Command Systems (ICS) as well as shoreline assessment and treatment databases like SCAT and providing valuable clean up and spill command and control document management.

Fig.1: Key components of operational risk assessment as input to oil spill contingency planning.

Examples of the DSS technology and design and examples of applications of the more advanced DSS with incorporation of dynamic model components as means for prioritising actions at all levels during the early stage of oil spill operations can be found on the following homepages:

NOAA ORR Office software and ESI maps <http://response.restoration.noaa.gov>

BMT's OSIS (www.cordis.lu/esprit/src/results/pages/Energy)

SINTEF's OSCAR (http://www.sintef.no/units/chem/environment/numerical_modelling.htm)

ASA's SIMAP (www.appsci.com/SIMAP/)

The contents and functionality of the current applications will be detailed by using NOAA's ORR Response tools and SINTEF's OSCAR model as examples. OSCAR (SINTEF) has been applied in 19 countries. In the following, a short description of the functionality of OSCAR is provided as an overview of the current level of application of oil response tools. OSCAR is a stand-alone application with a GUI interface, which allows the user to view concentrations, bathymetry, velocity vectors, pollutant spatial distributions, visualization of global mass balances of the mixture of constituents

released (one at a time or as a whole), and time-dependent animations of these fields. Compatibility with ArcGIS allows for easy import/export of standard GIS vector data. Vertical sections in the water column are also available for water column concentrations and Lagrangian particle positions. Both single oil spill scenarios and stochastic scenarios with variable start times can be calculated.

The hydrodynamic basis of OSCAR is both 2D and 3D, and the particle tracking dynamics and weathering processes are modelled using state-of-the-art process descriptions including incorporation of 27 standard oil components, and up to 200 components may be included. Response actions are not defined by the DSS on the basis of the calculated spreading and subsequent impact of the oil, Fig.2. Rather, response actions drive the scenarios for which oil mass balances and spatial statistics regarding the oil are estimated.

Fig.2: Schematic overview of OSCAR inputs, outputs, and internal processes

Fig.3: The relationships among the various components of a Nowcast-Forecast System of OSCAR including oil spill and biological impact models (for Net Environmental Benefit Analysis)

Nowcast-forecast applications of the model in general involve establishing a set of automated or manual linkages among hydrodynamic, atmospheric, and surface wave forecasting models. To strengthen the now-casting capabilities, in-situ meteorological and hydrographical measurements may be incorporated into OSCAR, and biological impact models and sensitivity maps may also be included in the system to support Net Environmental Benefit Analysis (NEBA), Fig.3.

NOAA's ORR Response office uses GNOME (General NOAA Oil Modelling Environment) as the oil spill trajectory model tool, and it is generally applied by HAZMAT responders during an oil spill in the US. Response strategies are designed using Environmental Sensitivity Maps (ESI), i.e. the response manager will have to decide on the response priorities himself on the basis of the location of sensitive resources, Fig.4. ESI maps contain three kinds of information:

- Shorelines are ranked based on their physical and biological character, then color-coded to indicate their sensitivity to oiling.
- Sensitive biological resources, such as seabird colonies and marine mammal hauling grounds, are depicted by shaded polygons and symbol icons to convey their location and extent on the maps.
- ESI maps also show sensitive human-use resources, such as water intakes, marinas, and swimming beaches.

Fig.4: Example of a NOAA ESI maps showing vulnerable coastal locations

In ESI maps shorelines are colour-coded to indicate their sensitivity to oiling (they also are ranked on a scale from 1, least sensitive, to 10, most sensitive). On ESI maps, warm colors like red and orange denote the shorelines that are most sensitive to oiling, such as tide flats, swamps, and marshes (including the marshy stream designated in red on the map segment above). Cool colors like blue and purple indicate the least sensitive shorelines, such as rocky headlands and sand and gravel beaches (on the map above, purple line segments denote locations of eroding bluffs). Shades of green denote shorelines of moderate sensitivity (on the map above, green line segments denote areas of riprap). Large habitat areas, such as tidal flats used by shellfish and wetlands used by shorebirds or waterfowl, are shown as colored polygons (above, orange hatched polygons denote shellfish habitat, used by horseshoe crabs). Sensitive biological resources, such as seabird colonies and marine mammal hauling grounds, are depicted by special symbols on the maps. Important human-use resources, such as water intakes, marinas, and swimming beaches, are also depicted with symbols.

Much of the information on an ESI map is shown in a table on the back of the printed copy of the map. The "back-of-the-map" table lists sensitive plant and animal species that live in the area shown on the map. It shows when each species is present in the area, and what that species is doing during

different seasons (for example, a bird species may be nesting, laying eggs, hatching, or fledging young birds).

5. Overview of best practices

A short-coming of all dynamic oil spills response DSS systems is the lack of modules for quantification of both biological and economic impacts. Existing sensitivity maps do not make use of the existing knowledge of the species-specific responses to oil characteristics and behaviour at the surface and in the water column. As a result, impacts on benthic and pelagic ecosystems are often simply assessed as overlap between the coverage of modelled slicks and the abundance or presence of the sensitive resource.

Semi-quantitative descriptions of impacts are estimated by OSCAR as well as by DHI's Oil Spill Analysis Model (SA) on the basis of PEC/PNEC estimations, while ASA's SIMAP make use of laboratory toxicity tests for estimation of mortality. In OSCAR and the SA model an analysis of the risk to aquatic organisms in the pelagic part of the ecosystem is assessed for each of the model oil constituents by comparing the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PECs) of components dissolved in the water column with the predicted No-effect-Concentration (PNECs). PEC equals the model output and PNEC is the component-specific maximum oil concentration for which toxic effects are not likely.

In general, it is assumed that when the long-time average PEC is higher than PNEC, there may be risks of chronic eco-toxicological effects on the ecosystem and on the organisms constituting it. Moreover, it is assumed that acute eco-toxicological effects can be expected when PEC is more than 10 or 100 times higher than PNEC. However, as more than one component is present at the same time, any species will be exposed to more than one toxic component. Therefore, the risks associated with each of the components will be added, i.e. the total risk is estimated as risk ratios defined as:

$$\text{TRR (Total Risk Ratio)} = \sum_i \frac{\text{PEC}_i}{\text{PNEC}_i}$$

i = number of oil component

The evaluation is then summarised for all identified impacts.

New model development at DHI (TORCH) and ASA's SIMAP allow for more realistic quantitative assessments of species-specific effects. TORCH estimates both direct and indirect effects of chemicals and oil components to species of algae, crayfish, fish laves and juvenile fish in the water around oil discharges. The model setup allows tailor-made impact assessments of single substances as well as mixtures of substances within specific pelagic ecosystems and may be a useful tool in the impact evaluation of discharges in small areas or in sensitive ecosystems with complex impact patterns.

In SIMAP species-specific effects on wildlife are estimated on the basis of encounter probabilities between species and the drifting oil slick. Encounter rates are derived from information on behaviour and field observations of mortality under similar circumstances. Effects on fish eggs and larvae are estimated using laboratory acute toxicity test data (LC50, concentration lethal to 50% of the test individuals corrected for temperature and time of exposure, and assuming a lognormal relationship between percent mortality and dissolved concentration). Organisms killed are integrated over space and time by habitat type to calculate a total kill. Animal distribution is assumed static within each season-habitat scenario. Lost production of fish, shellfish, birds and mammals due to reduction or contamination of food supply is estimated using a simple food web model.

Species-specific effects on seabirds have been described in several models using quantitative and detailed data on the spatio-temporal patterns of vulnerability to seabirds (e.g. *Carter et al. (1993)*,

Williams et al. (1995). The scale of the vulnerability depends not only on numbers present but also on the behavioural and other characteristics of the particular seabird species present. The methodology used for assessment of seabird vulnerability currently used by most countries within the North Sea is based on calculation of OVI and AVS scores. An Offshore Vulnerability Index (OVI) is applied which consists of four factors: the amount of time spent on the water, total bio-geographic population, reliance on the marine environment and potential rate of population recovery (for example following a reduction caused by oil pollution). The specific OVIs are summarised into an Area Vulnerability Score (AVS) using the following formula:

$$AVS(\text{Area Vulnerability Score}) = \sum \text{species} \ln(d + 1) \times OVI$$

d = abundance of each species

The abundance of each species is estimated from literature and available survey data. The results are an interpolated map with smoothed AVS scores highlighting areas of high sensitivity.

Limited development has taken place to allow for quantification of the socio-economic impacts on tourism, fisheries and other human activities in the affected region, rather than just visualising coverage of the areas of interest. Further, no attempts have yet been made to establish standards for transferring impact rates on ecosystem components to cost estimates. Using advances within environmental economics such standards would smooth the necessary integration of ecological and socio-economic impacts of an oil spill to obtain a final impact score, on which to base the key decisions for sound response actions.

6. Assessment of research gaps

A full DSS methodology for the oil contingency planning process related to response action for oil spills needs to be developed as a best practice organisation and system to be applied in Tomorrow's oil spill scenarios.

Compared to the existing oil response DSS models realistic, quantitative descriptions of the impact on both benthic and pelagic aspects (all elements) of affected ecosystems need to be included. Ecological disturbances are generally poorly described due to the lack of pre-spill reference baseline data, and mid- and long-term ecological studies taking into account the relationship between species and habitats.

In order to get realistic estimates of biological impacts descriptions may make more use of existing detailed knowledge of species-specific susceptibilities of marine organisms to various characteristics of the oil, e.g.:

- Susceptibility of bird species to oil as indicated by oil rates of beached birds
- Response of birds to the viscosity/fouling characteristics of different oil types

Realistic estimates of impacts on all biological components of the affected area will also need an evaluation of the cumulative effects over the time period covered by the pollution, in order to accommodate impact scenarios running from few hours to several months or even years. Equally important, the dynamic elements of the sensitivity of marine systems need to be addressed. This is probably best carried out by developing frequency distributions of suitable habitat/sensitive areas. Once more realistic and detailed estimations of the biological impacts can be made tomorrow's oil response DSS models may include modules for estimation of the economic consequences of these ecological impacts using technological advances in environmental economics. Similarly, the existing DSS response models may be improved to attempt to quantify the socio-economic impacts on tourism, fisheries and other human activities in the affected region, rather than just visualising coverage of the areas of interest.

Finally, the existing DSS models need to be expanded to accommodate fully functional DSS systems. This would require as a first step to include matrices for summarising and balancing environmental and socio-economic impacts as a function of oil spill scenario and significance of sensitive resources, as well as harmonisation of sensitivity ranking systems. The major aim of a full oil response DSS development is to build a decision support system for identifying quick response actions. The DSS will ultimately allow for the integration of the components mentioned above into GIS-based area-specific maps and tools in relation to various spill scenarios.

7. Conclusion

To satisfy the overall objectives for future unbiased assessments of oil spill impacts within the European Community a coordinated development of an EU-wide oil response DSS seems to be the optimal solution. The development should take place as an open process involving acknowledged experts within:

1. fine-scale modelling of local hydrodynamic processes
2. detailed modelling of weathering processes of the oil
3. quantitative estimation of in-situ and cumulative eco-toxicological impacts
4. assessment of environmental economic and socio-economic costs.

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E-Learning for Higher Education in Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering

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Abstract

An overview of the Network of German Universities offering a program in Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering (mar-ing), its background, and objectives is given. Special focus is on the advanced learning practices utilized to further enhance the master level programs in Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering, including a shared e-learning infrastructure and many time and location independent e-learning methods and modules.

1. Introduction

Networks enable the collaborating partners to combine their competencies and to capitalize on their collective technological and human capacities, *Moxley (2005)*. Taking into account these opportunities the four German universities offering graduate programs in Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering launched the Network of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering (mar-ing). Major objectives of this network are to raise awareness of the excellent career perspectives offered by this industry and to attractively enhance the German graduate and further education programs by collaborative teaching and by implementing new e-learning methods.

The first section describes shortly the background of this unique network, its partners and objectives. The second section outlines the special characteristics of the education in Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering at a graduate level. On this basis it is discussed how e-learning can help to enhance engineering education whereas a few examples for multimedia-based and interactive e-learning modules developed within the mar-ing network are introduced. Additionally, different e-learning methods are described in which these applications can be implemented. Last but not least the infrastructure needed is shortly outlined and an outlook on student assessment of the developed e-learning modules is given.

2. The Network of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering

Shipbuilding is of strategic importance for the European countries. It develops advanced technologies that offer considerable spin-offs to other sectors, provides essential means of transportation for international trade and supplies the navies with advanced vessels. In high-tech industry sectors such as shipbuilding, success is first of all based on knowledge, *CESA (2005)*. The European as well as the German maritime industry, being a major part thereof, have clearly identified the importance of highly qualified engineers to meet the challenges of the future. At the same time current studies reveal that the number of graduates does not satisfy the needs of the industry. In addition a steadily increasing demand of highly qualified naval architects and ocean engineers is due to the current age profile of engineers working in the German maritime industry, e.g. *Feller and Stahl (2005)*.

Being aware of this challenging situation, the four German Universities offering a Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering study program at master level - Technical University Berlin, University of Duisburg-Essen, Hamburg University of Technology and the University of Rostock - have joint forces in the research and development project "Network of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering" (mar-ing). The research group Instructional Design and Interactive Media of the University of Giessen contributes to the project with their expertise in developing new time and location independent learning scenarios and in securing an ongoing evaluation and optimization process. The network is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)

and advised by designated e-learning experts as well as executives of the German maritime industry and maritime associations.

The different core competencies in general engineering and in particular in the fields of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering proof the four German universities involved to be complementary and internationally accepted educational and research establishments. Their wide ranged expertise is primarily based on their extensive research activities: Whereas the Technical University of Berlin focuses on ocean engineering and transport systems/logistics, the University of Duisburg-Essen is specialized in surveying propulsion, ship machinery systems, and inland water vessels. The research activities of the Hamburg University of Technology focus on ship design, hydromechanics, structural mechanics, and ship automation systems and the University of Rostock concentrates on information and communication technologies in ship design as well as on production engineering and ship maneuvering systems. The differentiated study programs of the partner universities currently provided are an ideal basis for the development of a nationally and internationally recognized network of excellence for high quality graduate and further education.

To meet the demand of the maritime industry as mentioned above, the departments involved in the mar-ing network capitalize on their complementary educational and research capacities to impart the required expert knowledge and the methodological skills on the excellent and well-founded way to a sufficient number of students. Additional goals concern raising awareness of the excellent career perspectives being offered by this industry by ongoing public relations work and enhancing the attractiveness of this course of study as well as decreasing the comparable high drop out quota in engineering education by further improving instructional methods and utilizing advanced learning practices.

The advanced learning practices developed within the mar-ing network include primarily time and location independent e-learning methods for teaching Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering students in blended learning as well as in distance learning scenarios. Whereas distance learning scenarios can be thought of as completely offline a blended learning scenario is a combination of traditional face-to-face lectures and online lectures. For both scenarios comprehensive multimedia-based learning materials are essential.

To reach the goals diverse multimedia-based and interactive e-learning modules are collaboratively developed by the project partners. The developed e-learning modules will be utilized in the graduate programs of the partners. Furthermore, they will be adjusted to the special needs of further education and made available to the maritime industry in order to secure the continuous qualification of the naval architects and ocean engineers. To ensure time and location independent access to the modules an e-learning infrastructure is set up that supports a close collaboration of faculty and students. In a further step complex analysis and simulation software systems will be integrated in the e-learning infrastructure so that they can be used collaboratively from different locations.

3. E-Learning for Higher Education in Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering

Engineering study programs in general and the Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering study programs in particular are on the one hand characterized by somewhat very abstract learning content and on the other hand by special application specific learning contents. To a large extent this is based on complex mathematical calculations, extensive formula derivation and complex simulations in order to lay ground for practical issues in ship design and production methods, *Bronsart and Müsebeck (2005)*.

Due to the abstract nature of the learning contents students must be capable of higher level thinking, conceptual understanding and problem solving to adequately deal with it. Therefore, like mathematics education engineering education requires finding the balance between ensuring that students learn the basics and that they work to develop a broader level of thinking, *Kantor (2003)*. In this context practice is an essential ingredient while it balances with and enables a larger kind of exploration and

understanding of problems due to the deep involvement and the high activity level of the students. At the same time practicing is essential in order to rehearse and master the knowledge required. Another point is that frequent and concrete feedback is required to avoid the development of misleading mental models.

The e-learning modules developed in the mar-ing network are produced in close cooperation and according to the specific expertise of the partners. They are set up modularly, enriched with multimedia-based and interactive elements where reasonable. The mar-ing e-learning modules are configurable and applicable in a flexible way so that they can be used either as integral components of a traditional face-to-face lecture or as stand-alone courses or learning materials.

With respect to the special contents most e-learning methods used in subjects like social science and business administration are not appropriate to adequately support the learning process in engineering education. Nevertheless, the fundamental advantages of e-learning in general and some special e-learning methods in particular are regarded to be appropriate for certain application areas. To give an example, e-learning modules can e.g. provide a wide range and variety of exercises as well as give immediate feedback which supports the practicing, the rehearsal and the mastering. At the same time multimedia-based representations like interactive graphics, animations, and simulations enhance the understanding of the underlying concepts because they reduce the complexity by focusing on one particular phenomenon or on visualizing the overall concept as well as support student's involvement and activity.

3.1 Multimedia-based, interactive Animations and Simulations

A major component in engineering education is the visualization of physical phenomena, principles, procedures, systems or product structures. Traditionally this is done with the help of graphics, potentially large drawings, sketches, and sometimes videos which do not interactively involve the learner.

Computer-based interactive graphics, animations, and simulations can be utilized to overcome this problem. They can serve as models that represent real processes or phenomena in a simplified way and therefore help the learner to build up a mental model of the learning contents presented. Mental models are cognitive patterns that represent either procedural or conceptual knowledge and help to recognize and structure the full range of attributes and coherences of reality. Thus, they are essential means of thinking.

Following *Kattmann (2001)* and *Meyer (1990)*, *Engler (2003)* identifies four requirements for animations and simulations that are supposed to serve as models in the learning process:

- Models should be highly accurate and represent the original as adequately as possible as well as indicate the main attributes of the original.
- Models should focus on the essentials for the learning process.
- Models should be adjusted to the specific developmental state and imagination of the learner.
- Models should be as simple and descriptive as possible but exactly enough to allow realistic predictions on the original (under certain conditions).

While an animation is a simulated movement created by displaying a series of pictures a simulation imitates a real process or phenomenon. Because of their special nature these applications enhance the understanding of complex learning content. Animation, simulation and interactive graphics can be easily integrated into traditional lectures and seminars but also lay ground for distance learning scenarios and e-learning modules described in section 3.2 – 3.4 of this paper.

A wide range of animations and simulations already exists. Whereas the simpler enable the manipulation of a single parameter the more complex integrate a couple of interactive parameters which can be manipulated by the student and/or are affected by other interdependent elements. Therefore, anima-

tions and simulations are capable of visualizing different parts or complex concepts in a detailed and workable way.

Another advantage is that they can serve as a substitute of phenomena and processes that are either not possible to observe in nature e.g. because these phenomena take place within a complex machinery or that are not possible to reproduce within a lecture due to the high costs involved. Working with this kind of learning materials instantly shows their superiority to sketches in traditional text books with can not incorporate any interactive components.

There are many software applications available that enable creating animations and simulations. Very popular within e-learning are the software technologies Flash (<http://www.macromedia.com>), Java (<http://www.java.com>), and MapleNet (www.maplesoft.com) because of their internet based and browser independent technology. One problem when utilizing the software Flash is that the visualization of basic mathematical relationships is possible but comparably time expensive. In addition, the integration of interactive three-dimensional visualizations is not easily possible, yet. With the help of Java Applets and Maple Worksheets more complex calculations with associated graphics as well as three-dimensional visualizations and simulations can be generated. In the following examples screenshots serve to show some interactive elements developed.

Fig.1: Simulation on Damage Stability

Fig.2: Interactive Simulation of the Righting Lever Curve

Figs.1 and 2 show screenshots of two interactive flash animations mainly developed for lectures in Hydrostatic and Hydrodynamic at the University of Rostock. While the in Fig.1 depicted simulation focuses on the damage stability, the factors of subdivision, and bulkhead positions which can be manipulated by the user, the simulation pictured in Fig.2 deals interactively with the righting lever curve in combination with the forces acting on the vessel at the corresponding heeling angle. Different hull form parameter can be manipulated interactively by the user and the effects are shown immediately. These simulations are also included in the lecture-corresponding web-based trainings (see Section 3.3).

Java is very versatile and often used in combination with other software. One example is combining java with OpenGL in order to display three-dimensional geometries that can be manipulated by the user e.g. rotated and zoomed in order to visualize the details and its structural composition. In Fig.3 a java applet based on complex numerical calculations done with help of a program implemented in FORTRAN is depicted. While varying e.g. the angle of attack or the profile shape the effect on the flow is visualized.

Another method conceivable for interactively representing complex mathematical relations, its context and for enabling practicing mathematical calculations is with help Maple Worksheets which are available through the software package Maple. Maple integrates mathematical calculations and at the same time graphical representations can be generated.

Fig.3: Java visualizing Fortran calculations
By courtesy of Thomas Rung and Helmut Weberpals, TUHH

Fig.4: Maple on cylinder motion in waves
By courtesy of Günther Claus, TUB

Maple worksheets can be displayed and worked with in any internet browser based on the MapleNet server component. Fig.4 pictures a maple worksheet on the motion behavior of a cylinder in waves. The parameters wave height, wave period and cylinder radius can be manipulated and depending on the input the cylinder moves in-phase or out of phase to the calculated heave motion.

3.2 Lecture Broadcasting and E-Lectures

Lectures are an indispensable part of higher education at universities. Unlike reading a book they are characterized by a high level of liveliness, authenticity, and interactivity. Within the mar-ing network two approaches to distribute lectures electronically are utilized. They can be delivered online and offline but differ on their degree of interactivity and time independence.

The first method is based on lecture broadcasting: the traditional lecture at one university is broadcasted by special videoconferencing soft- and hardware to one or more other universities in different cities. As in traditional face-to-face setting students can see the lecturer and the presentation slides – either in presence or on a silver screen and listen to him/her live or over loudspeakers, Fig.5. This setting has the advantage that also those lectures are delivered that would normally not be made available at each university because of efficiency considerations e.g. when there is no lecturer on location or not a sufficient number of students taking the course. Another advantage is that the participants can communicate with one another just like in traditional lectures, e.g. discuss further questions on the subject presented. When the broadcasted lecture is recorded and reinforced it can also be provided as an e-lecture.

Fig.5: Procedure of e-lecture broadcasting
By courtesy of Katja Jacobsen, TUB

Fig.6: Example of an e-lecture

The second approach relates to electronic lectures (e-lectures, also called m[obile]-lectures) that are basically “bottled” traditional lectures. They include a video of the lecturer in a traditional lecture

combined with the presentation of slides, a directory, and links to further information e.g. on the internet as well as a comment function, Fig.6. Compared to the production of more complex e-learning applications like web-based trainings (see Section 3.3) the production of e-lectures is resource effective and therefore less expensive. E-lectures enhance the procurement of knowledge and the sustainability of the learning process due to the fact that they can be endlessly repeated and by this feature facilitate the self study and the preparation for examinations in an individual way.

3.3 Web-based Trainings and interactive Tests

Web-based Trainings (WBTs) play a major role in the context of self-directed e-learning and are normally provided via the Internet. They often lean against traditional textbook-contents and are enriched with drawings, videos as well as multimedia-based and interactive elements like the discussed animations, simulations, and interactive graphics, see Fig.7 for an example. Additionally, there can be exercises and tests included in order to enable the student's self monitoring as well as to provide an immediate feedback as shown in Fig.8.

Fig.7: Example of an Web-based Training with an integrated video
By courtesy of Günther Clauss, TUB

Fig.8: Example of a Question within a WBT

3.4 Live Seminar Technology

Live seminar technology enables synchronous but location independent collaborative work in small groups over the internet. The participants of a live seminar interact with one another within a shared virtual classroom that is provided by special software tools and communicate with the help of audio and video devices e.g. a headset and a web-camera. Typically a virtual classroom contains possibilities to upload presentations, to collaboratively work on a shared whiteboard or to work with more than two users with remote desktop connections.

Fig.9: Screenshot of a Live Seminar with Macromedia Breeze

Fig.10: E-Learning Infrastructure of mar-ing

Live seminar technologies are suitable for e.g. online software trainings or for collaborative student project works. Fig.9 shows a screenshot of a mar-ing staff member workshop with the help of Breeze from Macromedia (www.macromedia.com).

4. E-Learning Infrastructure

In order to enable time and location independent student’s access to the developed e-learning modules it was found to be appropriate to implement a central learning management system that also supports communication and collaboration between faculty and students. With regard to the fact that it is not an objective of this project to develop a new learning management system it was found to be appropriate to use the open source system ILIAS (<http://www.ilias.de>). Like other learning management systems ILIAS integrates functions for supporting both blended learning scenarios as well as complete online learning scenarios. At the same time ILIAS is capable of processing metadata and e-learning standards like the Sharable Content Object Referring Metadata (SCORM) and IMS Question & Test Interoperability (IMS QTI) which support the exchange of learning objects and modules between the collaborating partners.

As one can see in Fig.10 a streaming server and an application server complete the mar-ing e-learning infrastructure. They allow for short download times when working with data intensive learning materials like e-lectures and for integrating complex analysis and simulation software in the future.

Since March 2006 the mar-ing learning management system is in operation. At this point over 150 students enrolled in any of the NAOE programs of the participating universities have been granted access to 142 e-learning objects (lecture notes, presentation slides, web-based trainings, e-lectures, tests, animations and simulations).

5. Evaluation Results

In summer term 2006 the first web-based trainings within the lecture “Fundamentals of Ship Structural Design” at TU Hamburg-Harburg were evaluated with special focus on user assessment in quality, utility, usability and curricular integration, *Vogt and Glowalla (2006)*. Some evaluation results are depicted in Figs.11 to 13.

This formative evaluation is essential for future developments in order to enable early adoptions or corrections in module design and in the general direction of implementing new learning methods. The overall evaluation results show a positive feedback and encourage the faculty to continue the development in this direction.

Fig.11: Acceptance of the Web-based Trainings

Fig.12: Function of interactive elements in WBTs

Fig.13: General acceptance of e-learning

By courtesy of Ulrich Glowalla, JLU and Wolfgang Fricke, TUHH

6. Conclusion and Perspectives

The mar-ing Network is a challenging research and development program to develop advanced multilingual, multimedia-based and interactive e-learning modules and methods in diverse fields of graduate education of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering. The developed modules and implemented technologies enable time and location independent learning across the participating universities. Especially animations and simulations promote higher level thinking and ease student's transfer of the gained knowledge into practice and apply it on current practical issues.

Within the scope of this three-year project, a full set of e-learning modules will be developed which in the next step are integrated with complex software analysis tools used in ship design.

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Web-based Application to Evaluate Welding Exposures

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Abstract

Toxic fumes generated in metal welding operations pose public and worker health risk potential. This paper reports current knowledge on exposure potential of various welding processes under varying ventilation conditions and other weld parameters. Progress on a web-based application to predict worker exposures to various pollutants resulting from welding operation is reported.

1. Introduction

Welding is the most common method of joining metal parts by applying heat to fuse the metals. Welding is a ubiquitous process used in many industries. It is used to construct and repair parts of ships, automobiles, spacecraft, and thousands of other manufactured products. It is also used to join beams when constructing buildings, bridges, and other structures, and pipes in nuclear power plants and refineries. U.S. Department of Labor's statistics show that there were 416,000 welders in 1994 (Department of Labor).

There are more than 80 different types of welding processes in use. Welding can be classified into two categories, (1) arc welding and (2) oxyfuel welding. Arc welding, by far, is the most commonly used welding category in the industry which also happens to have the greatest emission potential. Emissions from welding processes include, PM, particulate metals (Cr, Mn, Ni, Cd, Co, As, Pb, and others), and gaseous pollutants such as CO, NO_x, and O₃. Based on electrode consumption in 1991, distribution based on process type is given as below (US EPA, AP-42 Document):

- | | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|-----|
| • Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) | - | 45% |
| • Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) | - | 34% |
| • Flux-Core Arc Welding (FCAW) | - | 17% |
| • Submerged Arc Welding (SAW) | - | 4% |

It has been observed that welding process emissions containing metallic hazardous air pollutants (HAPs) drive the health risk criteria for shipyards. Similarly, other industries practicing welding will be driven by EPA's health risk criteria of 1 in 1 Million for cancer and a hazardous index of 0.2 for non-cancer risks because of particulate metal emissions. High toxicity ratings associated with welding emissions make it very important to understand emission scenarios and the modifications (source design, materials, methods, and process conditions) required to reduce welding emissions and finally cancer and non-cancer health risks.

This paper presents most common welding processes within the maritime industry, pollutant emissions from welding and the toxicity ratings, weld parameters that influence emissions, exposure data generated at UNO, and the important features of the Web-based application being developed.

2. Welding Process Description

All four welding processes, SMAW, GMAW, FCAW, and SAW use consumable electrodes. Fig.1 shows four welding processes, SMAW, GMAW, FCAW, and GTAW that are commonly used in the shipbuilding environment and will be of interest to understand the worker exposures. Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW) is another process that is of interest because it has high potential of heavy metal emissions as this is used in welding stainless steel materials containing chromium and nickel compounds. GTAW uses an electrode that is non-consumable. As the weld pool has to be protected from the atmospheric gases to achieve the desired weld quality, welding processes either use a self-shielded vaporization of the flux core or a supplied shielding gas.

Fig.1: Most common welding processes in the maritime industry

A – GTAW (Also known as TIG); B – GMAW (Also known as MIG) ; C: FCAW; D – SMAW (Also known as stick welding); Sources: [www. weldingengineer.com](http://www.weldingengineer.com) (A, B, and D); Kura (C)

3. Pollutant Emissions from Welding Processes

Emissions include PM, particulate-phase hazardous air pollutants (metals) which are of greater concern. Metals emitted include manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), chromium (Cr) compounds including trivalent (Cr(III)) and hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)), cobalt (Co), lead (Pb), and others. Gaseous pollutants emitted include carbon monoxide (CO), oxides of nitrogen (NO_x), and ozone (O₃).

Heavy metal toxicity and carcinogenicity are highly dependent on the identity and oxidation state of the metal. Furthermore, the behavior of particulates in the lung is dependent upon the particle size, shape, and composition. Consequently, toxicity will also be strongly correlated with these particle characteristics. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the amount of metal particulates produced during welding operations, including the metal speciation and particle size distribution. This evaluation must include determination of the mass of each element, the oxidation state for important species such as chromium, and the mass loading of each of these elements in each particle size fraction. The size fractionation of metal particulates is extremely important since different particle sizes have different abilities to penetrate into and deposit within the respiratory system. In addition, small particles have a much larger surface area, and therefore may be more reactive in biological systems, leading to more severe health effects. To understand the health effects properly, it is important to gain knowledge on complete PM size distribution in addition to specific size ranges of coarse (PM_{2.5-10}), fine (PM_{1-2.5}), and ultra-fine (PM₁) fractions. Simultaneously, metal fractionation in all size ranges will be estimated.

In addition to size effects, particle morphology is a critical, but poorly studied factor in controlling the health effects of airborne particulates. For example, chromium(VI) that is encapsulated in a carbon shell will not exhibit the same behavior as a pure chromium(VI) particle of the same chromium mass. Furthermore, much of the chemical reactivity of particulates is associated with edges, defect sites, and other irregularities in the surfaces of the particles. Consequently, a thorough understanding of the toxicity and carcinogenicity of particulates can only be gained with complete particle characterization, including size distribution, chemical composition, and morphology. While extensive previous research has focused on the health effects of particulates, little work has been done to correlate detailed particle characteristics with health effects. Moreover, the relationships between particle characteristics and weld conditions are poorly understood.

Though the emissions based on quantity are less from welding processes compared to, say, blasting processes, the hazardous air pollutant (HAP) content of PM within welding emissions poses a greater health risk to the public health. Toxicity ratings of some select metals (welding related particulate metal emissions) from the National Air Toxics Assessment (NATA, 1996) are presented as Unit Risk Estimates (UREs) and reference concentrations (RfCs) for select metals emitted from welding processes in Table I. URE indicates the extent of carcinogenic health risk due to inhalation of a specific air toxic. URE is defined as the upper-bound excess lifetime cancer risk estimated to result from continuous exposure to an agent at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in air. A pollutant with a higher URE value is expected to pose a greater cancer risk compared to a pollutant with a lower URE. Chromium compounds have the highest “Unit Risk Estimate (URE)” among all the air pollutants identified by EPA in its 1996 National-Scale Risk Assessment. Chromium compounds URE is 0.012 per “1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.”

Table I: Cancer and non-cancer inhalation toxicity ratings

Air pollutant	Cancer Risk Factor, Unit Risk Estimate (URE), [per $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Non-Cancer Risk Factor, Reference Concentration (RfC), [mg/m^3]	Target Organ for Chronic Critical Effect (Non-Cancer)
	Higher the URE, higher the pollutant carcinogenicity	Lower the RfC, higher the pollutant non-cancerous risk	
Chromium (Cr) compounds	1.2 E-02 (1000 times Pb URE)	1 E-04 (15 times Pb RfC)	Lung injury in rats
Nickel (Ni)	4.8 E-04 (40 times Pb URE)	2 E-04 (7.5 times Pb RfC)	Respiratory track inflammation in rats
Manganese compounds		5 E-05 (30 times Pb RfC)	Central nervous system (CNS)
Lead (Pb) compounds	1.2 E-05	1.5 E-03	Central nervous system (CNS)
Cadmium (Cd) compounds	1.8 E-03 (150 times Pb URE)	2 E-05 (0.075 times Pb RfC)	Kidney

Source: Health Effects Information Used in Cancer and Non-Cancer Risk Characterization for the National Air Toxics Assessment (NATA) 1996 National Scale Assessment (EPA)

Similarly, the reference concentration (RfC) indicates the extent of non-carcinogenic health risk due to inhalation of a specific air toxic. The RfC is an estimate of a concentration in air that is likely to be without appreciable risks of deleterious effects during a lifetime (including in sensitive subpopulations). A pollutant with a lower RfC value is expected to pose a greater risk compared to a pollutant with a higher RfC. The table above identifies Mn to have a high non-cancer risk among the compared air toxics.

4. Welding Parameters that Influence Emissions/Exposures

As mentioned earlier, welding emissions include PM (coarse, fine, and ultra-fine) and particulate metals such as Cr, Mn, Ni, Co, As, Cd, Pb, and others. Emissions, thus exposures, depend on a number of welding process parameters which are briefly described below:

- Type of welding process
- Base metal composition
- Composition of filler rod / consumable electrode / wire
- Amperage and electrode/wire feeding rate
- Voltage
- Arc length
- Shielding gas composition and pressure (if shielding gas is used)
- Travel speed
- Welding electrode angle
- Surface contamination such as paints and coatings (paint; zinc)
- Worker training

Compilation of air pollutant emission factors (AP-42) document of EPA (www.epa.gov/ttn/chief/ap42/ch12/final/c12s19.pdf) and other published information provide some emission factors for these processes. However, the information published does not provide the effects of the above process parameters as the publications so far only compiled the information available from different research projects without any standardization. Different research projects used different process conditions, most of the time those applicable to that particular application.

Though emission/exposure data as a function of the above variables is available, additional data to evaluate the effects of the process variables such as amperage, voltage, travel speed, shielding gas, and others is necessary. Complete understanding of how emissions change with respect to various variables is necessary to make improvements in source design, materials, and process conditions.

5. Exposure Data Generated at UNO

The author has been an active participant in the research conducted by the Navy/Industry Task Group that was lead by NAVSEA since 1995. Because OSHA, <http://www.osha.gov>, identified Cr(VI) and other metal emissions from welding is a major concern for the worker health, the Navy/Industry Task Group was formed to evaluate ways and means of reducing emissions as well as worker exposures. As part of the Navy/Industries Group work, the author investigated a few welding processes within the shipbuilding industry. Under this work, exposure values were measured for workers who are near the welding source. Exposures were measured in a variety of ventilation conditions, viz., open, semi-enclosed, enclosed, and confined with and without external controls/ventilation systems. Fig.2 shows examples of enclosed and confined spaces that were measured during the exposure monitoring. Fig.3 shows the portable pump used in sampling occupational air and the welder wearing two sampling cartridges on his lapel. Exposure values measured were 8-hr time weighted averages (8-hr TWA) as a function of welding process type, base metal, filler rod/electrode, ventilation conditions (open, semi-enclosed, and enclosed) and the arc time. Ranges of values obtained are presented in Table II.

UNO collaborated with a shipyard to conduct Cr(VI) exposure studies for specific welding processes. Tests were conducted under controlled laboratory conditions. Performances of two commercially available local exhaust ventilation (LEV) systems were also evaluated. After the lab studies, additional samples were collected to evaluate Cr(VI) exposures in the field for commonly performed welding processes in a shipyard. The study involved evaluating Cr(VI) exposures during welding operations performed at the shipyard and evaluating the effectiveness of two LEV systems, namely, the Nederman Filterbox and the Binzel fume extractor gun, in reducing Cr(VI) exposures. Four welding processes were evaluated for Cr(VI) exposures during this study: FCAW, GMAW, SMAW,

and GTAW.

Fig.2: Examples of enclosed (left) and confined spaces in a shipyard setting

Fig.3: Sampling pump (left) being calibrated and two filter cartridges on lapels for measuring worker exposure to weld fume

The study found that the Nederman Filterbox was effective in reducing total fume levels but not Cr(VI) levels. It was hypothesized that Cr(VI) was present as fine particles in the welding fumes and, therefore, not captured by the control equipment. To investigate this phenomenon, a particle-size distribution study was also initiated. Particle size distribution of welding fumes for two specific welding processes was conducted and the effectiveness of the Binzel gun in reducing Cr(VI) and Mn levels was evaluated.

Important observations from UNO's research work through the years with the Navy and the shipbuilding industry representatives is summarized in this section. It may be noted that the work focused on Cr(VI) and Mn, and to some extent on particle size distribution. This was evaluated as part of worker exposure determination. Similar concepts, equipment and the procedures are being used to generate additional data. Finally, the objective is to develop predictive emission models (mathematical and computer models) for each welding source category which will not only calculate worker exposure values but also the atmospheric emissions (coarse, fine and ultra-fine PM; and particulate metals such as Cr, Mn, Ni, Co, Cd, As, Pb and others).

Table II: Comparison of worker exposures from welding processes with base metal as criteria

Weld Type	Base Metal	Filler Metal	Total Fume (mg/m ³)	Geometric Mean (Total Fume)	Cr(VI) (µg/ m ³)	Geometric Mean (Cr(VI))
FCAW	AH36	E71T-1	9.5 - 34.3	22.54	0.11 - 0.52	0.219
SMAW		7018/6011	3.5 - 26.9	11.87	0.38 - 0.94	0.787
GTAW	SS	309L/316L	0.1 - 0.9	0.33	0.1 - 0.24	0.147
GMAW		ER347	1.5-4.3	2.74	1.3 - 3.2	2.088
Enclosed/Semi-enclosed Conditions (8-Hour TWA - 50% Arc Time)						
FCAW	AH36	E71T-1	13.9 - 97.2	27.88	<0.14 - 0.61	0.261
SMAW		7018/6011	5.4 - 17.9	14.81	0.86 - 1.26	1.062
GTAW	SS	309L/316L	0.7	0.7	<0.08-<0.13	0.1019
GMAW		ER347	1.6 - 4.3	2.802	2.64-9.57	4.87
WITH CONTROLS						
Open Conditions (8-Hour TWA - 50% Arc Time)						
FCAW	AH36	E71T-1	4.8-24.8	11.67	<0.18-0.24	0.211
SMAW		7018/6011	5.7 - 11.7	0.957	<0.35-0.74	0.53
GTAW	SS	309L/316L	NA	-	NA	-
GMAW		ER347	1.5 - 2.7	1.9	2.08 - 3.58	2.85
Enclosed/Semi-enclosed Conditions (8-Hour TWA - 50% Arc Time)						
FCAW	AH36	E71T-1	5.4-8.2	6.65	<0.12	0.12
SMAW		7018/6011	13.2-16.8	14.89	1.04	1.01
GTAW	SS	309L/316L	NA	-	NA	-
GMAW		ER347	2.7-3.6	3.11	23.2	23.2

Important results from various studies under taken at UNO are summarized below:

- Total PM was found to be high for FCAW followed by SMAW, GMAW and, GTAW in that order.
- Exposure levels due to FCAW and GTAW performed on mild steel and stainless steel, respectively, were less than 0.5 µg/m³ with or without the use of local exhaust ventilation systems.
- The exposure levels due to SMAW and GMAW performed on galvanized and stainless steel, respectively, were mostly above 0.5 µg/m³ without local exhaust ventilation.
- Use of local exhaust ventilation systems could not bring down the Cr(VI) exposure levels below 0.5 µg/m³ in case of GMAW and SMAW performed on stainless steel and galvanized, respectively.
- The Nederman Filterbox (a fume capture and control device) was found to be more effective in controlling the total fume than Cr(VI).
- Total PM concentrations were found to be high for particles exceeding 3.5 microns and for particles less than 0.52 micron in size (aerodynamic size), irrespective of the welding process. This indicates a bi-modal distribution of welding fumes with a mode (maximum) in coarse fraction (>1.55 microns) and a mode in fine fraction (<0.5 micron).
- Cr(VI) concentration for GMAW performed on stainless steel was found to be the highest in the backup filter (corresponding to particles less than 0.52 micron). This accounts for nearly 80% of the total Cr(VI) concentration. This indicates that Cr(VI) exists in the fine particle

size range. The variation of Cr(VI) concentration across the impactor stages for all samples showed an increasing trend suggesting the presence of a maximum in the fine particle size range (<0.52 micron).

- The variation in manganese concentration across the impactor stages for FCAW performed on AH36 was found to be similar to that in total fume. Manganese concentrations were found to be high in the uppermost and the last stages and low in the intermediate stages suggesting a bi-modal distribution of manganese. The Mn concentration on the backup filter (i. e., less than 0.52 micron) accounted for 50% to 65% of the total Mn concentration.
- Overall Cr(VI) concentrations observed during GMAW on stainless steel were found to exceed the proposed OSHA limit (PEL of 0.5 µg/m³) even with use of the Binzel gun.
- The total percentage reduction in Cr(VI) for GMAW performed on stainless steel using the Binzel gun was found to be between 25% and 79%. The percentage reduction in the last stage (<0.52 micron) was found to be lower than that for other stages. This observation is particularly noteworthy since the bulk of Cr(VI) particles were found to be in this stage. Most control systems used may be ineffective in capturing metals that are associated with ultra fine particles.

6. Important Features of the Web-based Application Being Developed

This Web-based application being developed allows the industry owner to achieve compliance by forecasting the potential worker exposure thus preventing non-compliance in advance of the violation. The Web-based application estimates the worker exposure based on type of welding process, base metal, filler metal, arc time, and the ventilation conditions. Architecture of the application is being developed in such a way that it will answer the following questions when fully developed.

- What quantities of PM (size specific: coarse, fine, and ultra-fine) are emitted and what are the corresponding 8-hr TWA exposures under varying source/material/process conditions?
- What are the specific particulate metals and their quantities (size specific: coarse, fine, and ultra-fine) emitted under varying source/material/process conditions and the corresponding 8-hr TWA exposures?
- What source/material/process changes are necessary to reduce PM and metal emissions and the associated exposures?
- What changes at source will change the characteristics (size, shape, size distribution of metals) of PM emissions so that they are less toxic to workers and the public?

Though large amount of data is available in the open literature including the data from the author and the author's associates, additional data will have to be generated before the application can answer all the important questions. Efforts are currently being made to develop integrated set of data, predictive models, funding, and the necessary infrastructure.

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The Benefits of Applying Simulation in Ship Production: Arguments Based on Examples from Industry

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Abstract

Recent developments at German and Dutch shipyards show that control over shipbuilding processes can be significantly improved by (discrete event) simulation. Simulation is the dynamic modelling of production and logistic processes that can not be mathematically described. These models take into account all dependencies and details of the engineering and production data. This simulation technique does not comprise an automatic optimization via an algorithm. However, changing the model parameters through scenario research leads to an “optimal” solution. But despite, experience has shown that it is very hard to convince people, departments or companies to apply it. Besides, in spite of the different discussion partners, similar objections have been raised regarding the application of simulation. Most of these objections can be countered by presenting relevant and successful examples from industry; this paper discusses these cases.

1. Introduction

The European shipbuilding industry is faced with a dynamic and globally competitive market. On top of that, it is particularly challenged by pressure relating to reliable and short delivery times at relatively low prices. These factors are more important than ever and improving shipbuilding process control is needed to achieve this. However, factors such as the number of production steps, the enormous amount of parts and subassemblies, and the far-reaching interaction with suppliers make the shipbuilding process very complex, approaching the limits of conventional planning and control methodology. To meet this challenge, it is important for shipyards and their co-operating partners (i.e., suppliers) to use resources optimally, to make a feasible planning, and to keep to this planning.

Recent developments at German and Dutch shipyards have shown that planning, scheduling and coordinating (control) of internal processes and chained processes can be improved significantly by discrete event simulation of dynamic production and logistic process models. These models take into account all dependencies and details of the complex process and product. This simulation technique does not comprise an automatic optimization, but changing model parameters through scenario research leads to an “optimal” solution.

Current research and simulation applications at shipyards prove that production simulation models can be used for the following, *Kaarsemaker and Nienhuis (2006)*:

- Objective evaluation/decision/discussion/communication of the manufacturing plan enabled by dynamical analysis and transparent production;
- Quick and cost-efficient experimenting with product, process organization, or technical systems;
- Planning reliability and flexibility;
- Bottleneck analysis;
- Application on different levels of production planning (strategic, tactical and operational).

But despite all these advantages, experience has taught the authors that it is very hard to convince people, departments or companies to apply simulation. Besides, similar objections have been raised regarding its application, this in spite of the different discussion partners. The most common

objections are; “our company is too big/small”, “our processes are too complicated/simple”, and “we already plan very accurately”. These and most other objections can be countered by presenting relevant and successful examples from industry. This paper shows the benefits of applying simulation in ship production by discussing these cases, but first is given an introduction of applying simulation in ship production.

2. Simulation in ship production

2.1. Ship production

The shipbuilding process is very complex, every ship taken in production represents a challenging planning and control task. The internal activities of the shipyard require the production of a large number of individual parts and their assembly in meaningful order. Beyond that, a large number of supplied systems must be installed. Therefore, organization and convenient taxonomy plays a very important roll in shipbuilding.

The shipyards have adopted Group Technology, *Storch et al. (1988)*, and use product-oriented work breakdown structures for the description of the ship by written texts (i.e., identity code) and for the systematic order of all production procedures (i.e., activity code). With that, every ship is given a consistent constructive, functional structure and all parts and systems are consistently registered and documented. This enables planning of activities, correct allocation of accumulating costs, coordinating of processes, and controlling the total production process (including engineering).

The production exists of many process steps which are brought in the right temporal and on-site order during planning for production. Therefore, the order of production procedures that follows logically from the available technical facilities is first observed. Further, the capacity of available resources of the shipyard needs to be considered. This means that the utilization of machinery, building sites and the working hours of employees have to be distributed over a timeline that ends with the delivery of the ship. At this, applying resource levelling should be aspired. For this purpose, the total volume of work and suppliers of a ship needs to be partitioned in production sections (work breakdown structure) and (fine-partitioned) in work plans, *VSM (1998)*.

The number of production steps, the enormous amount of parts and subassemblies, and the far-reaching interaction with suppliers¹ make the shipbuilding process very complex, approaching the limits of conventional planning and control methodology. In this context, it is reasonable to run theoretically through the total production process of a ship with taking into account all dependencies and details of the complex process and product in a computer simulation.

2.2. Simulation in ship production

Lamb et al. (2006) stated that “due to the nature of the shipbuilding process, the goal of performing realistic, credible analysis remains elusive”. The authors don’t share this opinion, because simulation to control shipbuilding processes has in recent years been applied with success in the steel building area. Main result of this experience is the universally applicable Simulation Toolkit for Shipbuilding (STS) of the Flensburger Schiffbau-Gesellschaft (FSG), *Steinhauer (2005)*. The shipyard independent STS is a class library developed in eM-Plant of Tecnomatix/UGS, a simulation package based on the discrete event simulation principles. The STS contains a wide variety of simulation functions needed for modeling the production of companies in the maritime industries. The tools can easily be implemented in all kinds of simulation models and they can be adapted to certain tasks and specifics by adjusting their parameters, *Steinhauer (2005)*. The development of the STS is part of FSG’s goal to be able to simulate the total ship production process. This strategic view and the STS have attracted the attention of the German shipyard Nordseewerke (NSWE) in Emden and the Ship Production department of Delft University of Technology (DUT) in Holland.

¹ Approximately 70% of the cost price of a ship consists of supplied materials and services.

In 2002, NSWE started cooperating with FSG with the same aspiration as FSG has. In the same period of time, DUT included the simulation in ship production theme in its research program, *Alphen (2004)*. Since then, several simulation projects at Dutch shipyards have been implemented, e.g. *Kaarsemaker (2006)*. FSG, NSWE and TUD are co-founders of SimCoMar², which was established in spring 2004.

Experiences from all involved shipyards show that the steel building processes, from pre-manufacturing up to and including hull erection, are suitable to be simulated. At this time, there is still a lack of experience among simulation applications in the area of the successive more complex shipbuilding processes (e.g., outfitting and supply chain processes). Therefore, research and development in the area of simulation in ship production will focus in the coming years on simulation of outfitting and processes that cross the company boundaries.

2.3. Strength of simulation

The strength of simulation, especially in shipbuilding, has been proven in various projects. In spite of that, showing its direct advantage is often beyond the bounds of the possible because it's extremely hard to quantify. The gained experience in SimCoMar shows that the main benefit from applying simulation is the possibility to test and evaluate (an unlimited amount of) future scenarios accurately in the computer before they become reality (new production facilities as well as building new ships). The objection that simulation is made redundant by an accurate planning can be countered by this advantage, which is clarified in the following section.

2.4. Simulation versus planning

Planning and simulation of production processes form both a “simulation” of reality and have equal goals. The aim is improving controlling the process in terms of time, quality, information, and the control over risks. When simulation is opposed to planning, the following points can be made:

- Simulation can not be used in substitution for a planning tool; competition is out of the question. Simulation is an extra means to make a better plan. This is because it offers the possibility to go deeply into the processes, to perform the planning in a digital environment (shipyard) before the real production starts, and to use the evaluation of this to improve the planning.
- Planning tools often use a “simulation” possibility, which is nothing more than a calculation of times. Simulation is more than animating or playing the planning, because, all restraints (e.g., details and dependencies) of the processes are enclosed in the simulation model. It is very hard to adopt that with the same level of detail in a planning.

The opinion of the authors is that simulation can be seen as an addiction to planning. This is independent of the followed philosophy concerning the level of detail. In the future, planning and simulation will grow towards each other.

2.5. Requisites for simulation

In theory, it is very easy to state that it is reasonable to run through the total production process of a ship in a computer simulation. It's true that model development and maintenance is speed up by the STS, but a disposal simulation model can be created very quickly. A good simulation tool and

² Different simulation in ship production initiatives were bundled in SimCoMar: Simulation Cooperation in the Maritime Industries. Goals of this cooperation are the further development of the STS, knowledge exchange in applying simulation and joint research. The actual cooperation partners are Delft University of Technology, FSG, Nordseewerke Emden, the TU Hamburg-Harburg, the Center of Maritime Technologies, and the University of Liege – ANAST, www.simcomar.com.

programmer³ are of course main requisites for simulation, but the correctness of input and output data is at least as important.

Important influences on the success of a simulation project are; an extended analysis of the “is”-state, clear objectives and a good preparation. A simulation model is as good as its preparation and its results are in accordance with the quality and form of the input data. A consistent data-infrastructure that is continually kept up-to-date is needed, but unfortunately, data-readiness for simulation is still a rarity.

The main benefit from applying simulation is doing “unlimited” scenario research to reach an “optimal” plan. Therefore, product data needs to be available in an early stadium. This is a problem in current ship production practice, because detail engineering information gets out at a very late stage (concurrent engineering). A product data-generator to assess the missing data to enable simulation at an early stage is therefore a requirement.

Careful model validation takes a lot of time, but this is needed to achieve a valuable simulation model. In spite of a well-validated model, a right interpretation of simulation results is required. The results of a simulation are statistical values of a random check, all constraints and simplifications of the model have to be considered. Thereby, simulation cannot guarantee an optimal solution.

3. Relevant and successful examples from industry

This chapter presents relevant and successful examples from industry. By discussing these cases, the benefits of applying simulation in ship production are shown. To create a better idea about the possibilities of applying simulation in ship production, it is tried to give relevant examples for all areas mentioned in the introduction.

3.1. Objective means for evaluation/decision/discussion/communication

At FSG, the closed section assembly production station was faced with a continuous three-day delay in the middle of 2005. The person in charge tried to counteract this by introducing overtime and Saturday shifts and using alternative building methods and sites. In spite of all these steps, the lost time could not be regained at all. But also the cause for the delay could not be traced. This resulted in a discussion about the reasons. The point of departure for this investigation was to use simulation to reconstruct the past, fed by the planned sequences, durations and site allocation.

After analysing the simulation runs, it became obvious that a pin-jig lot, Fig.1, was double occupied as a result of deviation in the production. By combining the static space allocation with dynamic effects (e.g., lacking material, occupied cranes, unavailability of a welder, or any other disturbances), the simulation is able to produce an updated plan every time when necessary. The detailed output of the simulation showed that the only possibility to keep to the schedule in some degree was to change the plan regarding the allocation of building lots and the section building sequences. And even following the given plan, the result would have been a delay of more than 10 days, Fig.1, with the consequence of influencing the following stations. In this case, it would have been impossible to catch up that delay by introducing overtime or more workers because space is the bottleneck of this station.

There were different ideas for reacting on this situation, but after evaluating by simulation, not all of them could be considered as a solution. This shows that applying simulation results in an objective platform for discussing the problem and adopting the plan. Of course, this is only objective when all parties agree on its objectivity and are aware of the chances and limits of the simulation model.

³ Due to the special skills and high efforts usually needed to develop simulation a model, the practical application of production flow simulation in shipyards is still rather limited (*Krause et al. (2004)*).

Fig.1: The closed section assembly production station with its simulation model

3.2. Planning reliability and flexibility

FSG has been using simulation for tactical and operational (monthly and weekly) production planning in pre-production since the beginning of 2002. The manning level, the sequence and the assembly strategies are verified and improved with respect to low costs and adherence to the schedule every week by the planner. Therefore many examples for successful application of simulation exist within this production area:

- Man hours are minimized, unnecessary overtime is avoided.
- Problems in achieving the schedule are detected early enough to act instead of reacting too late.
- Reasons for upcoming difficulties can be analysed on a high level of detail.
- The acceptance of the plan is increased drastically.

A recent problem concerns the prospect of an enormous delay of the production of the section assembly station (St06). A simulation run made at the 20th of September in 2006 showed the simulation department that when the plan wasn't changed, the production of St06 would be delayed 20 days at the end of February in 2007, Fig.2. Such a scenario would have unwanted, financial consequences as this would also affect the production of the following stations. To give an idea of only the personnel costs, at the station directly fed by the product of St06 work approximately 45 people.

In the simulation two possible scenarios were suggested and evaluated. Firstly, Saturday shifts were introduced. This resulted in a four-day production delay, Fig.3, at the 3rd of February 2007 instead of a 15-day holdup. Besides the introduction of Saturday shifts, the regular 8-hour work shifts were secondly changed to 10-hour work shifts. This resulted in eliminating the total delay of production, Fig.4.

Fig.2: Normal plan with the prediction of a 20-day production delay.

Fig.3: Adjusted normal plan, normal shifts and Saturday shifts.

Fig.4: Adjusted normal plan, shifts of 10-hour work shifts and Saturday shifts.

The last simulation run proved that only the introduction of expensive overtime was a solution to keep the planning. FSG anticipated by changing the plan and allocated the production of a certain amount of sections to a following less-occupied station. Of course, this was also simulated with the result that the most “optimal” plan was followed in reality.

3.3. Development of new production facilities

The latest investment project at FSG concerns the reconstruction of the area of part fabrication. The goal was to substitute the old underwater cutting machine increasing the throughput by 50% and reducing the man hours at the same time.

Fig.5: Evaluation of different scenarios before the part fabrication plant is ordered and built.

The grinding, marking, signing and cutting of plates is now done in a completely new way using new plants. The development process of the new part fabrication layout has intensively been supported by simulation. All scenarios based on different ideas with respect to technology or material flow were modelled and evaluated by the application of simulation, Fig.5. Because of this, a suitable and feasible layout, which fits in the existing fabrication hall, could be found to achieve the different goals in terms of performance, quality, and costs.

In addition to the advantages in evaluating the concepts, the possibility to visualize the simulation models as well in 2D as in 3D was very helpful to discuss the ideas with planners or with the operating staff. The STS modules enable automatic generation of 3D animations of the simulation models, which are normally developed in 2D animation.

3.4. Reconstruction of production facilities

In the end of 2004, the owner of NSW (ThyssenKrupp Technologies) decided to accord the investment costs for extending the panel line with a cutting machine. The duration of the conversion was estimated at eleven weeks. The plan was to execute the reconstruction among and during the three-weeks holiday in the summer of 2005. In teamwork with the experts of the production technology department, the NSW simulation team got the task to evaluate the duration of refitting the panel line and its influence on the production plan for that period. Thereby, the goal was to find a cost efficient solution and to keep the impact on the subsequent production stations at the yard. So, a complex and dynamic challenge was to fulfil.

With the existing simulation model of the preproduction, Fig. 6, the simulation experts analysed the throughput of the panel line with taking into account the off-time during reconstruction. The only parameters to change were rearranging the scheduling of the panel line, the plate and profile cutting machines, and adjusting the shift calendar for the staff in this area. Thereby, the production planning of approximately nine weeks of production had to be reallocated, while the cutting machines for plates and profiles had to continue to deliver subsequent production stations at the yard. So, a complex and dynamic challenge was to fulfil.

In several simulation runs, the team adjusted the amount of workers in the range of reasonable values, the sequence of production orders, and the shift calendar until a configuration was found with a maximum of adherence to delivery dates and a minimum of additional personnel costs. The rearranged panel production schedule is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Simulation of panel line with adjusted schedule to enable a reconstruction

To ensure that the subsequent production areas weren't affected and every delivery date would be met, the new schedule meant for the prefabrication area that 10-hour shifts were scheduled from the beginning of 2005 until the start of the conversion. Further, the conversion was scheduled from the last week before the holidays to seven weeks after them, which is obvious to recognize in Fig. 6. In advance, this schedule was discussed with the staff council. The scheduled overtime was saved as extra holiday days in a so called flexi-time account, which could be taken during the off-time of the panel line.

3.5. Generic data module

In 2006, a project called PSMB (“Process control by means of Simulation – an integral approach for the shipbuilding sector”) was pursued at TUD. In this project, two shipyards and three different kinds of suppliers participated. The objective of the project was to examine the possibilities of simulating and improving process control in the steel building area, from preproduction up to and including hull erection, and to make a start of integrated simulation.

In Section 2.5 can be read that a simulation model is as good as its preparation and its results are in accordance with the quality and form of the input data and data-readiness is a requisite for simulation. But unfortunately, data-readiness for simulation is a rarity, the same goes for the involved companies. To overcome the obligation to prepare extensively all input data for every simulation model, a generic data module for simulation models in the area of ship building was developed. This data module converts shipyard specific data (e.g., identity and activity codes, planning times, part and product dimensions, etc.) to generically specific simulation model data, which serve as direct input for such a model. This is possible because shipyards use in general a similar kind of structure for identity and activity coding.

Fig.7: Application of the generic data module to simulation models of different companies

The data module exists of two parts; the first (shipyard specific) part imports the data of the shipyard and checks its completeness and consistency. Next, the data is converted to a format which can be used by the simulation model. Further, the second (generic) part distributes this data over different tables that are necessary for the simulation model and all its sub models.

The data module's flexibility and exchangeability was tested by applying it to the development of the simulation model of Merwede Shipyard and the model of a section building facility of another company, which is shown in Fig.7. With this test, it was proved that it is fruitful to apply the data module for the development of a simulation model. Because, the preprogrammed codes save time, the programmer knows in an early stage what needs to be programmed, and it makes the input data consistent. Besides, models can be exchanged if the models are developed in a similar environment, which was also successfully tested, see the lower arrow in Fig.7. This enables possible simulation across the company boundaries.

4. Concluding Remarks

Simulation is increasingly used in the shipbuilding industry for developing production facilities or for supporting the production planning. The strength of simulation, especially in the planning of shipbuilding processes, has been proven in various applications at several shipyards. At FSG, simulation is integrated in the planning process. At this moment, It's not embedded in all production areas, but the management of the shipyard is fully persuaded of the benefits of applying simulation and strongly drives further developments.

Based on the experiences in the cooperation community SimCoMar, simulation can be predicted as the main development in the field of production planning in shipbuilding, by which costs can be reduced and a more reliable and accepted plan can be drawn up.

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Simulation-Based Design of a Bulb-Cat Configuration

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Abstract

The paper presents the application of a Simulation-Based Design (SBD) environment to the optimization of a catamaran hull provided by a central bulb. Here, the size and the position of the central bulb are optimized in order to reduce the total resistance of a given catamaran hull.

1 Introduction

Innovation in ship hull design moves through the investigation and development of new design concepts. However, once a new concept is outlined, a strong effort is necessary in order to explore all the possibilities and take the best from the peculiarities of the new idea.

The catamaran concept is certainly not a new one, and catamarans are among the more investigated hulls in the last two decades. A long list of variations on the theme of this old design concept have been recently explored in order to enhance the performances over the basic design: staggered hulls and pentamaran hulls are among these examples.

Recently, some experimental studies have been conducted on an original configuration, *Zotti (2001)*, which includes a streamlined body in between the demi-hulls of the catamaran (the base hull is a fast ferry operating in the Gulf of Naples). The main feature of this option is the reduction of the deep trough in the wave pattern between the demi-hulls and the consequent reduction of the wave-interference factor. In a series of experimental studies, Zotti has analyzed the effect of shape, submergence and longitudinal position of the streamlined body, showing reductions of the residuary resistance and of the interference factor in a wide range of speeds. Another interesting feature of this concept is the possibility of refitting an existing ship, although structural problems may arise in placing the system supporting the streamlined body.

The present paper will discuss the efficiency and robustness of the algorithms and the strategies needed in the Simulation-Based Design (SBD) of this relatively new design concept. SBD is a process in which numerical simulation is the primary means of design evaluation and verification. When coupled with appropriate validation processes, the resulting capabilities of a SBD framework can provide shipyards the ability to design superior products in less time and at lower costs, exploring innovative design concepts.

An advanced SBD, *Campana et al. (2006)*, based on Global Optimization (GO) algorithms and able to deal with multiobjective optimization problems and with complex, realistic geometrical constraints (to avoid meaningless design), is applied to this concept. With GO methods more freedom is given to the optimizer. The price to pay is an increasing number of calls to the analysis tool for collecting enough information about the objective function. Using CFD solvers the price can become prohibitively expensive and might prevent the use of enough design variables. This motivated the use of methods which do not require any derivative knowledge on the problem and the investigation and the development of a number of different algorithmic strategies including surrogate management frameworks, parallel architectures, and variable fidelity approaches, to reduce the computational effort, *Campana et al. (2006)*.

A non-linear BEM solver, including lifting surfaces and able to capture the sinkage and trim of the free model, is applied as analysis tool. The code includes a simplified estimate of the frictional resistance, based on the ITTC formula but adopting a local value of the Reynolds number. After a validation phase against the

experiments, numerical optimization techniques, *Campana et al. (2006)* are applied to provide useful trends in the sizing and positioning of the streamlined body.

2 Hull description

In Fig.1, the sections of the investigated catamaran are shown, while the main hydrodynamic characteristics are reported in Table I.

Fig.1: Sections of the optimizing hull.

Table I: Main dimensions and hydrostatic characteristics of the assigned hull.

Length at the waterline LWL (m):	35.867
Breadth at the waterline BWL (m):	11.334
Breadth of the demihull B (m):	5.740
Design Draught T (m):	1.580
Displacement Δ (t):	137.0
Wetted Surface (m ²):	272.2
Ratio S/LWL:	0.225
LCB (m):	14.300
LCF (m):	11.097
C_B (block coefficient):	0.430
C_P (prismatic coefficient) :	0.768
C_W (waterplane coefficient):	0.772
C_M (midsection coefficient):	0.561

The standard catamaran model was built in 1:7 scale and tested at INSEAN towing tank (450 x 12.5 x 9 m). The same geometry was also built in 1:20 scale and tested in the University of Trieste towing tank (50 x 3.10 x 1.60 m).

For the central bulb, the geometry used were obtained from the Systematic Series 58 of the David Taylor Model Basin, *Gertler (1950)*. The length of the bulb was equal to $LWL/5$, where LWL is the catamaran length at the waterline. In Table II the main dimensions and characteristics are reported.

The volume ratio between the bulb and the hull has been experimentally varied between 1:32 and 1:64 of the hull total volume. The selection has been based on previous experience gained on a fishing vessel tested in the facilities of the University of Trieste, *Zotti (2003)*. Center of flotation is $0.3 L_{PP}$ from the stern, while center of buoyancy is located $0.4 L_{PP}$ from the stern. As a consequence, the center of the hydrostatic action is located astern and the adjoint of the bulb near the bow will probably help in balancing the hull better. The application of a central bulb is not changing the shape of the waterplane, and hence will not deteriorate the

extreme slenderness of the bow form. Furthermore, the presence of a deep blunt body in the front part will probably help in the reduction of the evident bow emergence.

Fig.2: View of the BulbCat model tested at the Trieste University.

3 Optimization techniques and algorithms

The great computational expense needed in solving fluid dynamic problems is a great obstacle in the solution of an optimization problem. In fact, even efficient optimization algorithms, especially when dealing with the solution of complex, global optimization problems, require a huge amount of flow solutions before converging to the optimal design. As a rule of thumb, the minimum number of objective function evaluation needed is 100 times the number of design variables. As a consequence, when dealing with a real industrial object the number of design variables grows immediately, and the total cost of the solution of the optimization problem varies accordingly.

In order to deal this difficulty, surrogate models are commonly applied in numerical optimization. Surrogate models, also called *metamodels* (model of a model), are algebraic models trained to mimic the behavior of the real model, e.g. a fluid dynamic solver. Algebraic models require few seconds to run and expensive optimization algorithms can be used. Once the problem is solved by applying the metamodel, the candidate solution will be added to the training set only after a verification with the expensive CFD solver. The optimization problem is then solved again, adopting the improved metamodel.

This approach contains, as a major uncertainty, the lack of equivalence between the problem formulated in terms of the objective function and the problem solved with the metamodel, and it cannot be completely guaranteed that the two solutions would be the same. First order consistency theorems have been produced for some particular class of problems in *Alexandrov et al. (2005)*. The validity limits of the methodology here adopted are out of the scope of this paper, and will be not further discussed here.

In the following, a brief description of the adopted metamodels and optimization algorithm only will be given.

3.1 Applied MetaModel

For the reconstruction of the objective function in the space of the design variables, a Radial Basis Function Network (RBFN) has been successfully applied. RBFN are a particular class of Neural Networks with a radial basis structures, that is, function whose value depends only from the distance between the computing point and the location of the kernel ρ_i . Typically, the core function is an inverse quadratic function, and the resulting expression for the RBFN is:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\sigma_i}{\rho_i^2}$$

Once some numerical values of the objective functions are known, a number of neurons are placed in the design variable space. The unknown strengths of the i^{th} neuron is computed by solving a least square problem casted from equation 1. Subsequently, the position of the neurons is moved through the design variable space and the optimal position of the neurons is found by solving an optimization problem in which the objective function is the residual between the known values of the objective function in the training points and the prediction given by the actual RBFN. Solution of this sub-problem is performed by using pattern search algorithms, *Torczon (1997)*.

Distribution of the initial set of points, usually called training set, is performed by using uniformly spaced sequences, like the LP_τ networks, *Statnikov and Matusov (1995)*.

3.2 Optimization Algorithms

Two different optimization algorithms are applied in sequence for the solution of the following problem. As a consequence, the new point to be verified with the real model will be provided by one of the two selected algorithms, alternatively.

The first algorithm is called DRAGO (Diagonal-Rectangular Analysis for Global Optimization) and belongs to the class of the direct search algorithms. In this algorithm, the investigated space is assumed to be a hypercube in the N-dimensional space of the design variables. This set is iteratively partitioned into smaller and smaller intervals. The choice of which interval has to be subdivided at the step k is made by looking at the possible minimum value the objective function can assume in an interior point of the interval. If we assume the Lipschitz constant of our objective functions (i.e. their maximum slope in that interval), and once we know the values of the objective functions at the extreme points of the interval F_a and F_b , the minimum value will be

$$F_{min} = \frac{F_a + F_b}{2} - \frac{L_k * \|x_b - x_a\|}{2}$$

The selection of the intervals to be subdivided in the current iteration is obtained by building a Pareto front using the objective function values and the corresponding intervals dimension. In this way, at each iteration, small and large intervals will be further subdivided at the same time, with simultaneous local and global exploration. The selection of the Lipschitz constant may arise from physical consideration about the particular problem to be solved (i.e. the flat plate resistance is the lower limit for the total resistance of the ship). The single objective version of the algorithm is described in *Pinto et al. (2004)*.

The second algorithm belongs to a special class of the evolutionary algorithms - Particles Swarm Optimization (PSO) and it is also described in *Pinto et al. (2004)*. The idea of the algorithms is to try to simulate the behavior of a traveling swarm. A number of individuals is moving inside the design space with variable speed. For each particle, the velocity is updated depending onto the distance from two different points: (i) the best position P_i he has visited personally, and (ii) the best position P_b the swarm has visited (this last information is obtained by letting all the elements communicate with each other). The velocity of each particle is hence updated according to the following:

$$v_i^{k+1} = w^k v_i^k + c_1(p_i^n - x_i^n) + c_2(p_b^n - x_i^n)$$

The first term is the so called *inertia* term, coming from the previous iteration. The second is called is the *individual* contribution, while the last term is the *social* contribution. The balance of the different terms is obtained through the coefficients w , c_1 and c_2 .

The DRAGO algorithm starts from a box-bounded interval, and the investigated region do not extend outside this initial limit. On the contrary, PSO can explore all the R^2 design space without limitations. Once the algorithms are applied in sequence, the limits of the DRAGO algorithm are extended to the actual investigated region, so they expand while the optimization problem proceeds. Around a few promising points, a further exploration is performed by adding other trial points.

Both the algorithms are implemented on a parallel machine with 24 CPUs (20 dedicated to this work).

4 Validation of Numerical Tools

A non-linear potential flow solver has been applied to the original catamaran geometry without the central bulb. Around 5000 panels are used to describe the hull and the free surface. The latter extends $1.0 L_{PP}$ fore, $1.5 L_{PP}$ aside and $2.5 L_{PP}$ aft, with a stretching of the panels toward the hull surface. At each iteration, the sinkage and trim of the hull are verified and updated, and the final solution is convergent for the exact (potential) free surface shape and the real sinkage and trim values. Experimental results were available, since that model has been tested at INSEAN. Model scale was 1:7 (5 m. long).

Fig.3: Comparison between the numerical (lines) and experimental (dots) value of the total resistance of the catamaran hull model.

Results are reported in Fig.3. Here the numerical results are reported using dots and line, while the experimental data are the dots alone. Percentage differences between the experimental data and the numerical prediction is in between $2 \div 6 \%$. This result is absolutely aligned with the standard uncertainty of this class of solvers, and they are encouraging under the perspective of the high Froude number involved. As a consequence, the results offered to the optimized are reasonably reliable, and the optimization process can be trusted in principle.

5 Optimization problem definition

In order to investigate the optimal position of the bulb, two parameters control the vertical and longitudinal position of the bulb respectively. Two more parameters control the diameter and the length of the bulb. The geometry of the bulb is here simply stretched: the lacking of a boundary layer model into the flow solver do not allow to produce fully reliable shape modifications for the bulb. The hull lines will be not changed,

in order to verify the possibility offered by a simple refitting an existing hull. During the initial exploration, the scaling factors of the length and the diameter of the bulb are limited to 10%: the optimizer is allowed to remove these limitations. For the longitudinal and vertical displacement, limits are ± 5 meters with respect to the initial position for the longitudinal position and 1 meter inside the water for the vertical position.

The variation of the bulb volume may lead to two different strategies for the optimization problem: one may maintain unvaried the total volume by changing the draught or one can consider indirectly the volume variation by optimizing the ratio R_T/Δ instead of R_T .

As a first numerical test, a single objective function problem is here solved for $Fr = 0.826$, that corresponds to a true speed of 30 knots. The objective function is the total resistance R_T . The draught of the hull is keep fixed, as in the experimental tests.

The base configuration is the intermediate bulb immersed up to the keel line and with the bow aligned with the hull fore perpendicular.

6 Optimization results

As a preliminary test, 440 iterations have been allowed to the optimizer. After this run, a total resistance reduction of about 7% with respect to the initial configuration has been obtained. The course of the optimization process is reported in Fig.4.

Fig.4: The design variables and objective function as a function of the optimization course. All the variables are in between 0 and 1 with respect to the minimum and maximum values.

The different features of the two algorithms are evident from Fig. 4. The algorithms are easily tailored for the parallel cluster: since the optimizer runs on a parallel machine with 20 CPUs, 20 different configurations are suggested by the algorithm at each step. These must be further verified with the CFD solver. As a consequence, the different block of solutions are easily identified. The first 40 runs are related to the training phase of the metamodel: here an uniform exploration of the design space is evident. DRAGO solutions are much more dispersed in the design variable space with respect to those of the PSO, since a chance is sometime given to large intervals too, and the convergence to numerous local minima is obtained this way. As a consequence, deeper investigations are performed in regions not necessarily close each other. Sometime, these exploration are not improving the actual minimum, but they are useful because in this way the wrong predictions of the metamodel are corrected, and the metamodel gains reliability after these runs. On the contrary, PSO concentrates on a single region where the global optimum is supposed to be, and all the best solution are then clustered.

The quality of the metamodel is reported in Fig.5 where, for each computed point, the two values - real and predicted - are reported. If this graph produces a straight line inclined by 45°, this means that for all the points the prediction of the metamodel is correct. Elsewhere, some points do not align. In this case, a perfect alignment has been obtained, that is, the prediction on the available points is correct. Even if this do not guarantee a complete reliability of the metamodel (there are a suite of different way to perfectly fit an assigned data set) this method is a kind of zero-order verification of the qualities of the produced metamodel.

Fig.5: Comparison between the predicted and real values of the objective function. Alignment on a straight line indicates a precise prediction of the real values by the metamodel.

Information from the metamodels may be added to the other information coming from the simulation. As an example, the sensitivity of the objective function to the variation of each design parameters is reported in Fig.6. This is an expensive quantity to derive, since it requires the computation of the objective function gradient on each computed point, but it is also an important indication of the sensitivity of the bulb to its effective position. Designer may be interested in a solution that do not change dramatically the performances of the hull if the bulb is not correctly mounted, or if it moves when travelling at sea. For this reason, a second merit function has been computed, in order to find the best compromise between the objective function and the stability of the objective function to the parameters. The new merit function is defined as

$$f' = f \cdot (1 + \|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}\| + \|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2}\| + \|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_3}\| + \|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_4}\|)$$

The so-called 'robust solution' obtains an enhancement of the objective function of about 2%. The geometries of the original configuration plus the optimal and the robust configurations are reported in Fig.7. Here a side view of the three hulls is reported. This viewpoint allows to get all the variations of the design variables. In both the optimal and robust design the bulb is smaller than the original one and the position is moved backward in both the configurations, if we refer to the extreme longitudinal position. The optimal and robust bulbs are shorter, but aspect ratio L/D is not uniform. In fact, for the robust design the diameter is nearly the same as the original one, but the length is 30% shorter, while for the optimal solution a scale factor around 0.5 is suggested for both length and diameter.

The reduction of the volume and surface of the bulbs seems to indicate an attempt in reducing the frictional resistance of the configuration by reducing the wetted surface area. This type of results is not completely verifiable by using a the present potential flow solver, since the frictional component is approximated: the hull surface is discretized by flat panels and the predicted velocity on each panel is applied for estimating

Table II: Main dimensions and volume of the tested bulbs.

Model	L (m)	D (m)	C_P	Volume (m ³)	Volume ratio
4155	7.1734	1.4347	0.65	4.203	1:32.6
4156	7.1734	1.1956	0.65	2.919	1:46.9
4157	7.1734	1.0248	0.65	2.145	1:63.9

Fig.6: Sensitivity of the objective function to the variation of the four adopted design parameters. Two big circles indicate the position of the optimal solution (1) and of the robust solution (2).

Fig.7: Comparison between the predicted and real values of the objective function. Alignment on a straight line indicates a precise prediction of the real values by the metamodel.

the local contribution to the total frictional resistance. This approach is a little bit more sophisticated than the simple ITTC '57 approach, whose validity is doubtful for catamarans with small demihull spacing, due to interference effects of the boundary layers. Anyhow, the boundary layer is not described by this model and also the prediction of the local velocity is not fully reliable. Being the bulb inserted in between the demi-hulls, its wake will influence the boundary layers on the demi-hull, and the use of a RANS solver is much more appropriate. An experimental test with measurements of the local flow field is also necessary.

Table III: Main dimensions and volume of the tested bulbs.

Model	$\Delta \% R_W$	$\Delta \% R_F$	$\Delta \% R_T$
Optimal	6.10	6.55	6.42
Robust	0.44	2.67	2.05

The improvements are detailed in Table III. For the optimal bulb, the same reduction is obtained on both wave and frictional resistance, whereas for the robust design most of the improvement comes from the frictional resistance.

The single CFD simulation requires about one hour to run. This means that the complete optimization problem have required 440 CPU hours, that is, more than 18 days to complete. The use of a cluster of processors made possible to have the results in only one day. The great advantage of this type of optimization algorithm is that the parallelization of the CFD solver is not required, because each simulation runs in serial way. Load-balancing problems between the processors are also eliminated. Furthermore, inconsistencies of the problem definition are evident in few hours, at least after the first training of the metamodel, and adjustments are made without losing days of computations.

7 Conclusions

An optimization problem on an innovative hull appendage have been performed. Reduction of about 7% for the total resistance have been obtained whereas a 2% of reduction is obtained if robustness is taken into account. The adopted optimization environment take evidently advantage of the parallel architecture. Further investigations are currently planned, both on the CFD and on the EFD side, to use a more accurate solver and more detailed experiments for validation.

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Automatic CFD Optimizing of Hull Forms Using Strategy-Driven Transformation Functions

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Abstract

In contrast of generating hull forms more or less from scratch, the present method uses existing hull forms. This approach allows to improve manually optimised hull forms as they are available on ship yards. To reduce the search domain of possible changes to a starting hull, a set of transformation functions is used. These functions allow a systematic variation of hull characteristics. Generated hull forms are evaluated by CFD tools like the wave-resistance code KELVIN. Spline approximations in the optimization search space allow to reduce the number of actual CFD evaluations, accelerating the optimization process. The modular procedure allows exchanging individually optimization algorithm, different CFD solver, or target function.

1 Introduction

Setting up a new vessel is a complex work flow. Most time is consumed for designing and optimising the ship's hull form to get best performance. As this progress is quite at the start of the design process, this must be very quick and as exact as possible.

Designing ships by starting from scratch is a long, time spending procedure that is necessary if complete new types of vessels are developed. Due to the fact that a lot of reference vessels are normally available on a shipyard, new vessels typically will be based on existing vessels. For that case, it is not required to start from the scratch creating complete new lines, but it will be quite more efficient to further develop existing hull forms to solve the given problem.

1.1 Using a computer aided optimisation tool for hull forms

Because every ship is a tailor-made object, there is a need for individual optimisation of hull forms. In the design process, some data like main dimensions or the size of cargo holds are given and cannot be changed easily. But mostly there will be enough design topics being customised for every special problem. In the early design process, a lot of parameters can be changed, so that it takes most time to find a good solution or even the best. To increase the speed of this design process, it is useful to perform a systematic variation of some global parameters concerning the vessel's performance.

Nowadays this optimisation process is done manually, but this represents a time-consuming, monotonous work flow to the developer. Consequently, the developer is satisfied if the solution is quite better than the vessel of comparison, mostly limited by the given timetable in the design process. At the moment, only 10% of the given time is used for thinking about what kind of variation has to be done because 90% of the time is needed to modify the lines concerning the problem given before. This shows that now this design process is not effective and it would be quite more useful if the developer spent 90% of the time thinking about useful modifications and only 10% of the time for optimising the lines plan. This could be realized by using computer aid for hull-optimisation. So the basic idea with respect to this problem is that human's decide how the problem has to be solved instead of saying what has to be done to solve the problem.

Implementing this idea leads to the main problems of the desired method: it has to be faster than human work. Unlike human beings, computers have no intellectual power to make predictions for desired transformations. This results in the fact, that for optimising hull forms more variations have to be calculated, particularly at the beginning of the optimisation process. The main focus while developing an optimisation algorithm has to be on the efficiency. In this context efficiency means that the algorithm needs not even to be the fastest in finding calculation points, it has to be efficient in case of using as few

calculation points as possible because the calculation time of every point is significantly higher than the optimisation time itself. For example, to perform an optimisation in every day's work, the optimisation process should not take more than half an hour, so that in the moment 15 iterations can be calculated. For a long calculation taking time over a night, some more iterations are possible.

The main intention of this project is that the developer's focus while designing vessels is shifted from making variations of hull forms, to thinking about what kind of variations are necessary to reach an optimal design.

2 Strategy-driven transformation functions

During early design, the developer performs handmade hull form optimisation. After modifying the hull form, CFD-calculations have to be performed to check if the chosen strategy fulfills the prediction.

For numerical representation of the hull designer's daily work, strategy-driven transformation functions can be suggested. The interaction between most methods used in the early design process can be automated without any problems. Setting up free variables describing the different transformation strategies do not result in a too big search area if variables are set to be independent to each other. This can be easily done, due to the fact that in normal work the design topics are treated sequentially, e.g. first optimising bulbous bow and after that finding the best bilge radius or lines.

In the early design stage, absolute values e.g. resistance given by the modified hull form are quite not of interest. The main focus is on the trend of results in working with free variables because only after the last step absolute values are necessary to make a resistance prediction. Manually it is no problem to find good values, but for finding the optimum, mostly not enough time is given in the short early design phase.

For automatic optimisation, policy-functions are more useful than fixed parameters. The main idea in using strategy-driven transformation functions is, that the hull form itself gives all necessary values to the optimising tool, the designer only decides what kind of transformation has to be performed. Because of just defining the chosen transformation function, the designer only has to set up the upper and lower boundaries of the free variable of the function. The functions used are free in definition, so that for every problem individual strategies can be defined. Due to the fact that an optimisation tool has to work with these functions, they have to be controllable by the selected optimisation tool. The value given back to the optimisation tool can also be a combination of results given by different tools, e.g. a transformation of hull form without following CFD-calculation is mostly not useful.

The program ARGO is used for hull form transformations. Originally implemented in the early 80's, the algorithms allow hull form transformations in very short time.

Starting from an existing mesh, ARGO uses transformation functions depending on the local coordinate system to develop the new hull form. The transformations can be additive, the new value results in the old value adding the result of the transformation function in this point, or multiplicative where the new value is given by the old value multiplied with the transformations functions result of the point. Having the definition that frames are always a plane with the x-axis as normal vector, the functions f_2 and f_3 are always set to one.

$$\begin{aligned}x &= x + f_1(x) \\y &= y + f_4(x)f_5(y)f_6(z) \\z &= z + f_7(x)f_8(y)f_9(z)\end{aligned}$$

Such kind of hull form transformation are given in Fig.1. On the left side, a change of the bilge radius is done and the difference is shown in the plot of the two hull grids. On the right side, a transformation of transom immersion is shown and the different behaviour can well be seen.

Fig.1: Examples for hull form transformation, left: change in bilge radius, right: change of transom immersion

Not every transformation leads to a fairing hull form, particularly if the input data results in transformation functions which can not be handled by the program. Because of that, transformation steps may have to be splitted into smaller ones and performed in sequence.

3 Optimisation Process

In the optimisation process theoretically a global minimum can be found, but this would be very time consuming. A lot of calculations have to be done and manually it is quite impossible. Due to the fact that many values to be found are some kind of integers, like main engine scaled in available cylinders and vessel's breadth scaled in container breadths, the result only has to be better than a given limit. In consideration of performing calculations in an acceptable time limit, it is more effective to reduce the number of used calculation points than to get the best possible solution.

The use of independent free variables leads to the possibility of separating the policy-functions into sub-optimisation processes and solve them separately. Only the results of these local optimisations will be used for the following global optimisation step (Fig.2).

Fig.2: Optimising process depending on independent policy-functions

3.1 Optimising with independent variables using convex functions

Searching the whole area to find the optimum is almost impossible because setting up a global mesh of calculation points is not practical.

$$n_{\text{calculation points}} = k^{n_{\text{variables}}}$$

Setting the free variables independent to each other reduces the needed calculation points to

$$n_{\text{calculation points}} = (k - 1) * n_{\text{variables}} + 1$$

for each iteration.

Using convex optimisation methods, only three knots are needed to set up a convex spline for each variable. This indicates a compact and fast system for optimisations:

$$n_{\text{calculation points}} = 2 * n_{\text{variables}} + 1$$

The optimisation tool now runs on an interpolated spline considering an increase of the local error between the interpolated spline and the calculated value in the target point. According to the fact that the results given by the free variables are not really independent, a new calculation or iteration step has to be done, starting in the found point or, if an optimum was found, a calculation has to be done to verify the values given by the optimiser.

The calculation of the knot's values can be done parallel on a cluster. Having the possibility of getting access to a cluster with about 17 processors, 8 variables can be optimised in one iteration step. This is quite faster than calculating all knots what would take 6561 calculations under the same conditions.

3.2 Implementation of optimisation

To optimise a vessels hull form, an objective-function is needed, at least the trivial one, minimize resistance, and one or more constrains.

$$\min_{x \in R^n} f(t) \text{ subject to } g(t) \geq g_{\min}$$

Where $f : R^n \rightarrow R$ and $g : R^n \rightarrow R^m$. The objective-function f and the constrain g indicates the results given by policy-functions t . The policy-functions $t(v)$ are the strategy-driven transformation functions used by ARGO with the free variable v .

For implementation, the objective-function is set to be the ratio of vessel's resistance and displacement. This resistance to weight ratio is similar to the power to weight ratio often used in comparison of different motor vehicles. The main advantage in using resistance to power ratios is the possibility of comparing different variations having not the same weight. Having two variations concerning the same resistance, the larger variation is the more efficient one. This extra displacement can be used for other variations in further transformations.

$$f(t) = \frac{RT(t)}{\Delta(t)}$$

The constraint displacement has to be above limiting displacement. It can be solved easily with the calculations done for the objective-function before .

$$g(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta(t_i) \geq n\Delta_{\min}$$

The free variables of the transformation functions $t(x)$ have to be kept in a realistic limit of giving calculatable results. In this case they have to be configurated during the optimisation process.

$$x_{\min} \leq x_i \leq x_{\max}$$

3.3 Presentation of results

Two transformation functions are chosen for testing the optimisation process. Changing bilge radius will come to a high variation in displacement and variations in transom immersion lead to changes in wave resistance of the longitudinal waves. For the first runs, no constraint is chosen. Upper and lower boundaries of the free variables were set in performing feasible results in calculations. The variation in

Type of transformation	initial	minimum	maximum	result
Bilge radius	5.750m	2.0m	7.0m	5.000m
Transom immersion	1.135m	-1.000m	1.135m	-0.25m

Table I: Boundaries of the chosen free variables

Iteration	Bilge Radius	Transom Immersion	RT/DISPL pred	RT/DISPL calc
1	4.9m	-0.01m	0.0404	0.0391
2	4.1m	-0.50m	0.0381	0.0377
3	5.0m	-0.25m	0.0375	0.0374

Table II: Iteration steps using bilge radius and transom immersion transformations

bilge radius is set to be in the limits between 2.00 m and 7.00 m, the transom immersion varies between 1.0 m below CWL and 1.135 m above.

At first, only three iterations were chosen to show the calculation system's functionality and a calculation system with three calculation points was chosen in development process.

In Fig.3 the results are shown. The first iteration in bilge radius is approximately satisfying, but increases with the following iterations in interaction to the transom immersion. The plots of transom immersion show no major change in the iteration's result, only the optimum position varies. To find the optimum, a decrease in the step size of the search interval was implemented.

Fig.3: Optimisation process of bilge radius(left) and transom immersion (right)

Comparing the initial hull form and the variation after three iterations, the advantage in reducing the vessels resistance is only about 11%, table III. On the other hand, the vessel's displacement increase by about 600t. This extra displacement can be treated as an indirect resistance reduction, due to the fact that the displacement can be used in next optimisation step, for example to reduce the vessel's draft.

The graphical presentation of initial and final hull form shown in fig. 4, shows the reduction of the wave heights. In the stern wave system, the decrease in wave can be clearly seen and the result is plausible with

Vessel	Displ.[t]	RT[kN]	RT/DISPL [kN/m^3]
Initial hull form	15774.4	692.772	0.0439
Final hull form	16378.6	612.409	0.0374

Table III: Results given by the optimisation after 3 iterations.

respect to the transom modification.

Fig.4: Presentation of CFD-Results, left: Initial calculation, right: final result

3.4 Evaluation of needed calculation points

For the evaluation in need of calculation points, the bilge radius calculation was done with an increasing number of calculation points. The plot in fig. 5 shows that the use of only three calculation gives a result more or less besides the graph with 16 points. Using only one more calculation point will increase the calculation quality and by use of eight points, the graphs plot shows a good correlation to the graph with 16 points used.

Fig.5: Influence in calculating with different numbers of calculation points, 3, 4, 8 and 16 points

Using 16 or more calculation points seems not do be useful because to many local extrema are generated. Setting up optimisation systems under use of four to eight calculation points smoothes the original function in a useful way. An other advantage of using more than three calculation points leads to the fact that the whole variable interval can be kept and no decrease in step size has to be done in the iteration steps. Also the number of used iteration steps can be kept on a low level contrary to the three point calculations.

4 Conclusions

The system's functionality allows a good practical optimisation with the first implemented transformation functions. Further tests have to be done to evaluate the necessary number of calculation points and

iterations.

Further more useful transformation functions need to be implemented to increase the existing library. Preconfigured combination of functions should be available and new combinations have to be saved to be used again.

A debug system has to be implemented for use while the optimisation process is running. This is important if calculations lead to results obviously not correct. In this case new calculation points or boundaries have to be set up manually without the need to restart the whole optimising process.

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Quality Enhancement by using Standardized Parts and Methods in Steel Structural Design

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Abstract

The design process in steel structural design is a very complex process based on the knowledge of the engineers. By using the advantages of standardization, this paper outlines a solution for handling both standards and workflows. Hereby the quality in design process is enhanced; productivity is increased.

1 Introduction

The design process in the maritime industry is a complex phenomenon where several partners like yards, subcontractors, and design offices work together in a heterogeneous network. Thus, a significant amount of time is needed for information exchange and the coordination of design activities. Often, the partners simultaneously perform similar design tasks by utilizing their own specific knowledge and design methods which therefore leads to different solutions to identical problems.

This paper outlines a flexible solution for handling standards. The application described is a result of the collaborative research project 'Context Sensual Structural Components' (KonSenS) and relies on a service oriented architecture approach. Based on specific IT-based methods for the management and application of standards for steel structural design an improved standardization is developed that leads to quality enhancements of design tasks.

One major advantage of the application described is that all partners involved in the design process have access to an electronic catalog via network connection. By following a single-source approach there is only one catalog of standards needed for several design projects because a per-project configuration allows tailoring the standards to different problems. Furthermore, it is possible to select a subset of information for several design tasks or contexts which helps to avoid incorrect decisions. Additionally, for common design tasks there are already workflow selections defined. Based on standardized workflow management formats these workflows include both strength, manufacturing, and cost aspects.

2 Standardization at Steel Structural Design

Fig.1 shows the cost effect during the design process. As seen the design phase influences the total cost of delivery significantly. To reduce costs the shipyard, building the vessel, defines a set of regulations and best practice recommendations, so called standards. These standards are highly optimized to increase productivity during manufacturing.

2.1 The Role of Standardization

By using these standards the number of solutions used in a vessel or even in a series of vessels can be reduced, with these series effects the manufacturing costs can be reduced. Design agents are more familiar with the reduced solution, leading to a decrease in labor time needed and to an improvement in manufacturing quality.

To reduce design time similar tasks concerning independent aspects of the vessel design are deployed to different partners. For example the design of all steel structural parts of the bow section is done by one design office, the design of the aft section is done by another design office or directly on the shipyard. Independent design offices are often working on many projects at the same time. This requires that the employee of a design office

- must work in different design contexts at the same time,

Fig. 1: Effect of design time on cost

- must be familiar with the recommendations and requirements of the contractor for each project.

These issues put a high load on the employees of the design office. For new projects the engineer must get familiar and productive within the standards and regulations by the contractor in a limited timeframe. Working on different projects also requires a change of used standards; the probability of using incorrect regulations or misinterpretation is increasing, leading to a decrease of the quality of the solutions.

So, standards offer a means to define solutions to common problems. These standards used by engineers on the shipyard and in design offices to design a vessel in a way that is best for manufacturing capabilities at the construction site. A result, manufacturing costs are reduced and the build quality is improved. If common standard parts are delivered or produced in large quantities, they do not need to be manufactured individually. The material flow is improved, storage requirements are reduced.

2.2 A Definition for Standards

For a given problem, even if limited to feasible solutions only, the number of solutions is large. Based on these solutions, standards impose certain constraints with the objective to limit the solution domain. Constraints can

- either be placed on certain aspects,
- can exclude some solutions completely
- or can allow certain solutions only.

Generally, aspects can be anything that concerns the problem at hand and that influences the result. Constraints limit the parameter space for aspects. This limitation is based on mathematical operations. For example the class rules define certain requirements regarding stiffener dimensions in relation to plate thickness. Description logic allows the definition of relationships between different aspects hence forming a network of rules for a given standard.

Fig.2: Relevant aspects for a standardized object

Here, a distinction between constraints that only affect aspects of the standardized object and relations that also encompass information from the surroundings of the object need to be distinguished.

Fig.2 shows as example a bracket used for a stiffener–stiffener connection. This bracket has two parameters: l – the length of the flange and its thickness t . For the selection of the bracket another parameter is used: H – the height of one of the connected stiffeners, i. e. information from another object used for the dimensioning of the bracket.

In practice, the number of aspects applied for a given standard is limited by issues like maintenance and complexity. From an economic point of view, standardization is only used if the effect of the standardization gives benefits regarding cost or quality compared to the effort needed to define, distribute and apply these standards.

In ship design standardization is mostly applied in the area of steel structural design. Here, high numbers of identical solutions like parts or features are used.

2.3 A system for Managing Standards

Today, the definition and management of standards is mostly performed using standard office applications. In most cases distribution and deployment are done on paper. For each project the shipyard needs to create a new document describing all relevant standards. Changes in the standard require that all related documents need to be updated and distributed to all partners involved. Due to the delay in the distribution process design decisions might occur based on deprecated standards.

An electronic system for the management of standards eases the handling of standards. With a centralized database for the storage and distribution of parts and methods, the deployment of up-to-date informations is improved. Using knowledge-based engineering methods tools are provided to support the application of a set of standards by the engineer. Intelligent functions allow to search for solutions for a given problem.

As part of the collaborative research project “KonSenS” *Bronsart et al. (2006)* an electronic database for

- the creation of a set of standards,
- the management of standards,
- the distribution of standards to all partners involved for a project,

- the application of these standards by the engineers,

is developed.

This system is based on an information server to provide information about design procedures, standards and documentation. Using a platform- and system-independent design, a Client/Server solution offers both flexibility and a centralized infrastructure. With the help of adapter interfaces to CAE-systems or other applications present in shipyards it is possible to consolidate and centralize the management and configuration of different applications in the system. A stand-alone client can be used to access the data stored in the information server directly. Communication to the clients and adapters is done via SOAP and XML-RPC calls, interfaces for search and retrieval of applicable solutions or informations are offered.

Such a system offers the following advantages:

- Standards can be accessed by all partners
- Information retrieval is eased
- All partners work with up-to-date informations
- Deployment of updated standards is no longer required
- Consolidation, i.e. central management of information used within a shipyard and by the partners
- If needed partner only sees the standards they have to see

3 Quality enhancement in design process

First of all the meaning of quality enhancement in the design process must be defined. Therefore some criteria for a later measurement of the quality will be declared. As the main goal, reducing costs in the design process, the following criteria are able to show the quality enhancement.

Simplicity Decisions and calculations should be done by an electronic system as much as possible. Engineers have access to the electronic standard catalog and can use both standardized parts and methods for the design process. So these process will be simplified, the quality of the results is increased.

Reproducibility Based on workflow definitions and standardized parts as base, every step through the design process is reproduceable. Engineers can execute the workflows step-by-step guided by a “wizard”, backtracking and undo functionality are supported. All solutions for a given problem are identical, so the quality increased.

Usability Tools for supporting the design process should have an easy understandable user interface.

For the tests of quality enhancement a suitable testbed is needed. Based on the system architecture of the application KonSenS the Tribon-integrated client solution used, Fig.3. So, there are two machines, the KonSenS Server with a standard installation and the CAD Workstation with Tribon M3 and the KonSenS client software installed. Both machines are connected via network (intranet).

The placement of brackets as one step of the detail design will be exemplary used for further analysis of the quality enhancement. Going this way, a standardized description of all brackets available is needed.

Fig.3: Infrastructure for testing quality enhancement

Fig.4: Some parameters for bracket description

Table I: Parameters for bracket description

name	description	needed for	remarks
A	length of leg A	description	mandatory
B	length of leg B	description	mandatory
C	length of leg C	description	mandatory
MAT	the thickness	description	mandatory
FL	is bracket flanged?	description	calculated by rule
NOA	notch on leg A	description	association to feature
NOB	notch on leg B	description	association to feature
NOT	notch on leg C	description	association to feature
FP	connectable to flatbar	placement	
HP	connectable to bulb profiles	placement	

3.1 Standardization of brackets

Brackets are parts, that means they are solid objects used as main structures in steel structural design. For standardization purposes all brackets used by the shipyard must be describeable in a unique manner. A parametric description is used to achieve this requirement *Hoffmann (2005)*. Fig.4 shows some of the used parameters. The denotation of these parameters is derived from the syntax used by the Tribon system. Table I shows all parameters needed for the description of a bracket. More parameters, acting as constraints for example to assign the bracket to a single project, are associated to the bracket in the same manner.

By this way, all parts and features used on a shipyard can be added to the standard catalog used for all projects on this yard.

3.2 Standardization of bracket placement

Based on the electronic standard catalog, all suitable brackets are well defined. The placement procedure is based on several workflows, executed by the workflow engine of the KonSenS Server.

Such workflows can be described as activity diagrams. Fig.5 shows the activities needed for the placement of brackets. Activities can be either actions like user input or computing processes like the calculation of the bracket dimensions. The whole process is divided into five single steps:

1. **Selection of bracket buildform** First of all the user must select the place of installation for bracket to place for. This can be:
Profile/Profile: The bracket is connected to two profiles.
Profile/Panel: The bracket is connected to a panel and a profile.
Panel/Panel: The bracket is connected to two panels.
2. **Selection of the objects** Based on the installation location the user selects the objects, which will be connected with the bracket, usually in the CAD–System.
3. **Dimensioning** Based on the dimension of the panels/profiles the system KonSenS calculates the correct dimensions for the bracket. Furthermore, the decision, if the bracket will be flanged, is done in this step. All matching results from the standard catalog are presented to the user.
4. **Selection of results and integration of founded bracket into the 3D–model** If more than one bracket will match all requirements, the user can select the adequate bracket from a list with all founded brackets. Based on this selection a statement for the creation of the bracket is generated and executed in the CAD–System.

For other parts or features like stiffeners placement workflows can be defined in the same manner.

3.3 Bracket placement in Tribon M3

To place a bracket the engineer must select the objects which should be connected with the bracket. Now the user selects the buildform (syntax) of the bracket. In Tribon there are seven buildforms available, the right choice is based on the users knowledge. After this selection, a dialog is shown, asking for the parameters of the bracket. As shown in Fig.6 this dialog is very complex. The engineer must calculate the right dimensions for the parameters A, B and C. Other parameters like notches are found at the tab “Notch Stiff”. So switching between tabs is necessary; usability is poor. After setting all needed data, the bracket is created in the 3D–model. There is no support for engineers, they only have their knowledge and documents describing the yard standard.

Fig.5: Activity diagram for bracket placement

Fig.6: Property dialog for brackets in Tribon

3.4 Bracket placement using the system KonSenS

As seen in Fig.3 the KonSenS–client is partially integrated in the system Tribon. All user input is done via the Tribon user interface.

For bracket placement the user select the accordant workflow from the menu, Fig.7. Now the workflow

Fig.7: Selection of workflow for bracket placement

shown in Fig.5 is executed. The engineer will ask for the bracket buildform by a dialog which shows all possible buildforms as pictures, as seen in Fig.8. Next, the user selects the two objects for bracket

Fig.8: Selection of bracket buildform

placement in the 3D–model. The system KonSenS calculates the dimensions for the brackets by rules. The result is shown in a dialog, Fig.9. Advanced users can edit the resulting statement here. Also variable data, which need user interaction and system specifics (for example Tribon) can be edited in this dialog. Last, the generated statement is executed, the bracket is generated.

3.5 Comparison of variants for bracket placement

Table II shows a comparison of interaction for both variants of bracket generation. As seen, the generation of a bracket is done in eleven steps. By using Tribon only, all these steps are triggered by user interaction.

Fig.9: Presentation of matching brackets

With KonSenS only five user interactions are needed, the other, mostly complex steps are done by system. The process of bracket placement is drastically simplified. Using the automatically dimensioning of brackets the amount of possible errors can be minimized, engineers will be comfortably guided through the design process. Usability is improved by minimizing decisions per dialog; the dialogs are clearly arranged. Looking at the further defined quality criteria quality in design process is enhanced.

4 Summary

The design process in steel structural design is very complex, standardized parts and methods can be used to simplify it. Giving all engineers access to up-to-date informations about both standards and workflows design time can be reduced. User interaction are minimized, selection and dimensioning of used parts are mostly done by the system.

Accumulating all these advantages quality in design process can be enhanced.

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Table II: Comparison of interaction

#	interaction name	by	Tribon	KonSenS	
			possible errors	by	possible errors
1	activate panel	user	-	user	-
2	menu selection	user	-	user	-
3	selection - buildform	user	-	user	-
4	selection - profiles	user	-	user	-
5	selection - bracket type	user	-	system	-
6	selection - bracket	user	-		
7	selection - bracket parameters	user	parameters not allowed for	system	-
8	selection - parameter values from catalog	user	wrong dimensions selected	system	-
9	input parameter A, B, MAT	user	input errors parameters not set	system	-
10	change to tab "Notch Stiff"	user	input error	system	-
11	input parameter NOTCH, H	user	input error parameters not set	system	-

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